

Supporting Information for

Policy Brief on Analyzing the Information Requirements and Regulatory Use of Safety Data in National and Regional Chemical Inventories:

Implications for the Global Sound Management of Chemicals and Waste Beyond 2020

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Note: The quotations in this document are highlighted using *italic* font.

S0 Common Definitions by OECD

S0.1 Definitions of Polymers

In *Second Meeting of the OECD Expert Group on Polymer Definition: Chairman's Report* [ENV/MC/CHEM(91)18], it is stated in paragraph 5:

A 'POLYMER' means a substance consisting of molecules characterized by the sequence of one or more types of monomer units and comprising a simple weight majority of molecules containing at least three monomer units which are covalently bound to at least one other monomer unit or other reactant and consists of less than a simple weight majority of molecules of the same molecular weight. Such molecules must be distributed over a range of molecular weights wherein differences in the molecular weight are primarily attributable to differences in the number of monomer units. In the context of this definition a 'MONOMER UNIT' means the reacted form of a monomer in a polymer."

In *Third Meeting of the OECD Experts on Polymers: Chairman's Report* [ENV/MC/CHEM/RD(93)4], it is stated in paragraph 8:

The Working Group recommended the following addition to the polymer definition.

Sequence: means that the monomer units under consideration are covalently bound to one another and form a continuous string within the molecule, uninterrupted by units other than monomer units.

Monomer: means a molecule which is capable of forming covalent bonds with two or more like or unlike molecules under the conditions of the relevant polymer-forming reaction used for the particular process.

Other reactant: means a molecule linked to one or more sequences of monomer units but which, under the relevant reaction conditions used for the particular process, cannot become a repeating unit in the polymer structure.

S0.2 Definition of Polymers of Low Concern (PLC)

In *Third Meeting of the OECD Experts on Polymers: Chairman's Report* [ENV/MC/CHEM/RD(93)4], it is stated in paragraph 8:

The Working Group, as asked, discussed criteria.

(1) Concerning MW: the range of 1,000–10,000 Mn was agreed as a range within which the concern value was likely to lie.

(2) Concerning MW of low MW compounds giving rise to concern: the agreement was MW below 1,000.

(3) Concerning percentage of low MW compounds of concern: no agreement

(4) Concerning functional groups: only one value, applicable to epoxy and anhydride groups was mentioned (it was 1 reactive group in 20 monomer units); no general conclusion was reached.

(5) Metal content: no value agreed.

(6) Extractivity in water: 10mg/l was seen as acceptable, provided that test conditions were standardized

(7) Cationic charge density: the 5,000 equivalent weight value was accepted (as defined by EPA: not more than one cationic charge in 5000 monomer units).

S0.3 Other Definitions from *Guidance on Definitions of Key Terms*

[https://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=env/jm/mono\(2007\)13&doclanguage=en](https://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=env/jm/mono(2007)13&doclanguage=en)

Articles:

Article means a manufactured object formed to a specific shape or design relevant to its function. An article undergoes no change of chemical composition or form during its use, other than that which is

incidental to its use, that which is an intrinsic part of its use, or that which has no commercial purpose separate from that of the article.

Intermediates:

***Intermediate** is a substance produced and consumed in the course of the manufacture of another substance.*

***Consumed** means the substance has chemically reacted to form a different chemical substance, although some of the substance may remain as an impurity in the final product.*

***Non-isolated intermediate** is an intermediate that is not intentionally removed (other than sampling or disposal), from the equipment in which it is produced. The equipment includes the reaction vessel in which it is manufactured, equipment which is ancillary to the reaction vessel, any equipment through which the chemical substance passes during a continuous flow or batch process, and vessels in which the substance is transiently held.*

***Site-limited Intermediate** is an intermediate that is manufactured and consumed at the site of manufacture.*

***Transported Intermediate** is an intermediate that is manufactured at one site and transported to a second site where it is consumed.*

***Imported Intermediate** is an intermediate that is imported and transported directly to the site where it is consumed.*

Substances occurring in nature:

***Substances occurring in nature** are substances that are unprocessed, processed only by manual, gravitational, or mechanical means, or by dissolution in water, or by flotation, or by heating solely to remove water, or are extracted from air by any means, without chemical change in the substance.*

Incidental reaction products:

***Incidental reaction products** are substances produced when a substance undergoes a chemical reaction that is consequent to the use to which the substance is put or that results from storage or from environmental factors.*

Impurity:

***An impurity** is an unintended constituent present in a substance as produced. It may originate from the starting materials or be the result of secondary or incomplete reactions during the production process. While it is present along with the final substance it was not intentionally added, nor does it enhance the commercial value of that substance.*

Mixtures:

***Mixture** means a mixture or a solution composed of two or more substances in which they do not react.*

S1. Supporting Information on Individual Inventories and Their Underlying Frameworks

S1.1 Australian Inventory of Industry Chemicals (AIIC; former Australian Inventory of Chemical Substances, AICS)

Last update: 30 November 2021

1. Sources and Links

- A. Industrial Chemicals Act 2019 (latest version from 6 November 2021):
<https://www.legislation.gov.au/Series/C2019A00012>
- B. Industrial Chemicals (General) Rules 2019 (latest amendments from 23 November 2021):
<https://www.legislation.gov.au/Series/F2019L01543>
- C. Industrial Chemicals Categorisation Guidelines (latest version from 24 June 2020):
<https://www.industrialchemicals.gov.au/sites/default/files/2020-06/Industrial%20Chemicals%20Categorisation%20Guidelines%20%5BWord%20169%20KB%5D.DOCX>; <https://www.industrialchemicals.gov.au/about-us/industrial-chemicals-law-australia>
Including environment categorisation volume (based on total introduction volume or end use scenarios); human health categorisation volume (based on total introduction volume or end use scenarios); known hazard classification (GHS7 + Guidance by Safe Work Australia); persistence (criteria + OECD test guideline); definition of high molecular weight polymer that has lung overloading potential; definition of terms in determining indicative risk; definition of terms in record keeping for reported introductions; definitions of terms and concepts relating to exposure bands and hazard bands; lists of chemicals with high hazards for categorisation; in silico information; suitable read across information; acceptable test guidelines
- D. Step-by-step plain language guide: <https://www.industrialchemicals.gov.au/help-and-guides/guide-categorising-your-chemical-importation-and-manufacture>
- E. Self-guided decision tools: <https://www.industrialchemicals.gov.au/help-and-guides/decision-tools-help-you-categorise-your-chemical-importation-or-manufacture>
- F. Industrial Chemicals (Consequential Amendments and Transitional Provisions) Act 2019:
<https://www.legislation.gov.au/Series/C2019A00013>
- G. Industrial Chemicals (Consequential Amendments and Transitional Provisions) Rules 2019:
<https://www.legislation.gov.au/Series/F2019L01548>
- H. The inventory and guidance: <https://www.industrialchemicals.gov.au/>

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

- Section 10 [A]: *To avoid doubt, this Act only applies in relation to an industrial chemical to the extent that the industrial chemical is used, or proposed to be used, for an industrial use.*
- Sections 39 and 40 [A]: an industrial chemical was included in the old inventory is taken, on and after 1 July 2020, to have been listed on the Inventory under the new law (with the same terms)
- Existing vs. new chemicals: The Inventory is a database of chemicals available for industrial use in Australia. It contains chemical identity details (example chemical name and molecular formula) and regulatory obligations or conditions relating to the importation and manufacture of chemicals in Australia. Industrial chemicals that are listed on the inventory can be introduced by any registered introducer. Industrial chemicals for which an assessment certificate has been in force for 5 years are generally listed on the Inventory (however, applications can be made for early listing and industrial chemicals can be listed in certain other circumstances). If a chemical is not listed on the inventory - or if the intended use is different to the condition of use - it is a new industrial chemical to Australia. Substances in AICS which are not in industrial use have been identified and consulted upon, and will be removed from the AIIC as part of the migration from AICS to AIIC. [H]

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligations

Registration of industrial chemical introducers

- Section 13 [A]: A person contravenes this subsection if (a) the person introduces¹ an industrial chemical² in a registration year; and (b) at the time the industrial chemical was introduced the person was not registered for the registration year.

Introductions must be authorized

- Section 24 [A]: A person contravenes this subsection if (a) the person introduces an industrial chemical; and (b) the introduction is not authorised by any of the following³
 - Section 25 (which deals with listed introductions)
 - The industrial chemical is listed on the inventory; and
 - The introduction is in accordance with the terms of the Inventory listing

¹ import, or manufacture in Australia, the industrial chemical [A]

- Manufacture = any of the following: produce the industrial chemical in the course of a chemical reaction; extract the industrial chemical from a natural environment, with or without chemical change; extract the industrial chemical from a UVCB substance; produce or extract the industrial chemical in circumstances prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph but does not include producing or extracting the industrial chemical as described in paragraphs (a), (b) or (c) in circumstances prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this definition.

² For the purposes of this Act, industrial chemical means any of the following [A]:

- a chemical element that has an industrial use
- a compound or complex of a chemical element that has an industrial use
- a UVCB substance that has an industrial use
- a chemical released from an article where the article has an industrial use
- a naturally-occurring chemical that has an industrial use
- any other chemical or substance prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph that has an industrial use

³ Section 25 [B]: Circumstances in which introductions are NOT exempted or reported

- Industrial chemical subject to an international agreement or arrangement
 - The industrial chemical is listed in (i) Annex III to the Rotterdam Convention; or (ii) Part 1 of Annex A, B or C to the Stockholm Convention; unless
 - The industrial chemical is to be introduced solely for use in research or analysis; and the total volume of the industrial chemical introduced by the person in a registration year does not exceed 100 kg
- Industrial chemical listed on Inventory
 - the industrial chemical is listed on the Inventory; and
 - the terms of the Inventory listing include one or more conditions relating to the introduction or use of the industrial chemical; and
 - the introduction or use is not in accordance with those conditions.
- Industrial chemical where request for information is not complied with
 - The [ED] has, by written notice under section 102 or 104 of the Act: (i) requested the person to provide information relating to the introduction of the industrial chemical; and (ii) to do so within the period specified in the notice; and
 - the information is not given to the [ED] within the period specified in the notice.
 - This subsection ceases to have effect in relation to the introduction if (a) the information requested is given to the [ED]; or the [ED] agrees, in writing, that the information requested is no longer required

- *Section 26 (which deals with exempted introductions)*
 - *Note: An exempted introduction is an industrial chemical introduction that poses a very low risk⁴ to human health and the environment*
 - *+ industrial chemicals listed in 3.2 Exemptions below*
 - *A one-off post-introduction declaration is needed*
- *Section 27 (which deals with reported introductions)⁵*
 - *A pre-introduction report for the industrial chemical has been given to the Executive Director [ED] in accordance with section 97; and*
 - *The introduction is in accordance with the terms of the pre-introduction report*
 - *Note: A reported introduction is an industrial chemical introduction that poses a low risk⁶ to human health or the environment*

⁴ Section 28 / Section 29 [B]: indicative very low human health (HH) / environmental (E) risk for an introduction, if

- *(a) the human health / environmental exposure band for the introduction is 1; and (b) the industrial chemical does not have any of the human health / environmental hazard characteristics in human health / environmental hazard band C / C or D; and (c) none of table items 1 to 3 / 1 to 5 [medium to high risk], 7 or 8 / 10 or 11 [low risk] apply to the introduction*
- *(a) the human health / environmental exposure band for the introduction is 2; and (b) the industrial chemical does not have any of the human health / environmental hazard characteristics in human health / environmental hazard band C / B, C or D; and (c) none of table items 1 to 3 / 1 to 5 [medium to high risk], 7 or 8 / 10 or 11 [low risk] apply to the introduction*
- *(a) the human health / environmental exposure band for the introduction is 3 or 4; and (b) the industrial chemical does not have any of the human health / environmental hazard characteristics in human health / environmental hazard band A, B or C / A, B, C or D; and (c) none of table items 1 to 3 / 1 to 5 [medium to high risk], 7 or 8 / 10 or 11 [low risk] apply to the introduction*

For details on human health and environmental exposure bands, and human health and environment hazard bands, see Schedule 1 in the Rules [B]

⁵ Section 33 [F]: The industrial chemical was introduced in the registration year beginning on 1 September 2019 under the old law; and the introduction was under paragraph 21(3)(b), subsection (4) or paragraph (6)(c) (the authorising provisions) of the old law, is taken, on and after 1 July 2020, to be authorised under section 27 of the new law

⁶ Section 28 / Section 29 [B]: indicative low human health (HH) / environmental (E) risk for an introduction, if

- *(a) the industrial chemical is internationally assessed for human health / the environment; and (b) the international assessment or evaluation was (i) for the same end use for which the industrial chemical is to be introduced in Australia by the person; and (ii) for a maximum concentration of the industrial chemical at end use / for a volume of the industrial chemical that is the same or higher than the maximum concentration of the industrial chemical at the end use / the volume of the industrial chemical for which the industrial chemical is to be introduced in Australia by the person; and (c) the risks to human health / the environment from the introduction and use of the industrial chemical are no higher in Australia than in the overseas jurisdiction, as determined in accordance with the Guidelines; and (d) the complete international assessment report for the industrial chemical is available and will be provided to the [ED] if requested; and (e) either of the following applies: (i) if the international assessment or evaluation is of a kind mentioned in item 6 of the table in subsection 6(3)—the restrictions (if any) set out in Annex XVII of the REACH Regulation relating to the industrial chemical are able to be complied with in Australia; (ii) otherwise—the conditions (if any) that the international assessment body determines must be complied with in order to manage any risks to human health / the environment from the industrial chemical are able to be complied with in Australia; and (f) no further information becomes available to the person after the international assessment or evaluation is completed about: (i) a hazard to human health / the environment from the industrial chemical that is not identified in the international assessment or evaluation; or (ii) a hazard to human health / the environment from the industrial chemical that is identified in the international assessment or evaluation and indicates an increase in the severity of the hazard; and (g) none of table items 1 to 3 / 1 to 5 [medium to high risk] or 12 to 14 / 15 to 17 [very low*

- + *Low volume introductions of industrial chemicals that are solely for use in research and development* [B]
 - *the introduction of the industrial chemical is: (i) solely for the industrial chemical to be used in research and development by the person; or (ii) solely for the purposes of making the industrial chemical available to another person for that other person to use solely in research and development; and*
 - *the industrial chemical is an industrial chemical that: either (i) the industrial chemical is a solid, or is in a dispersion, at the time of introduction and it consists of particles, in an unbound state or as an aggregate or agglomerate, where at least 50% (by number size distribution) of the particles have at least one external dimension in the nanoscale; or (ii) it had not been determined, at the time of introduction, whether the industrial chemical meets the description in subparagraph (i); and*
 - *the industrial chemical is not made available to the general public: (i) on its own; or (ii) in combination with one or more other industrial chemicals; or (iii) as part of an article, including where the industrial chemical undergoes a physical or chemical change to produce the article; and*
 - *control measures are used to eliminate or minimise the risks from the introduction and use of the industrial chemical to: (i) persons involved in the research and development for which the industrial chemical is introduced; and (ii) the environment; and*
 - *the total volume of the industrial chemical introduced in a registration year by the person is greater than 10 kg and less than or equal to 100 kg.*

risk] apply to the introduction; and (h) introduction of the industrial chemical is not prohibited (however described) in the overseas jurisdiction

- *(a) the industrial chemical is an industrial chemical that: (i) is a solid, or is in a dispersion, at the time of introduction; and (ii) consists of particles, in an unbound state or as an aggregate or agglomerate, where at least 50% (by number size distribution) of the particles have at least one external dimension in the nanoscale; and (b) the industrial chemical is not soluble (within the meaning given by the Guidelines); and (c) none of table items 1 to 5 / 1 to 8 [medium to high risk] apply to the introduction*
- *(a) the industrial chemical is a UV filter; and (b) none of table items 1 to 5 [medium to high risk] apply to the introduction [HH risk only]*
- *(a) one of the following applies: (i) the industrial chemical is an organotin chemical; (ii) the industrial chemical is a polyhalogenated organic chemical; (iii) the introduction of the industrial chemical is for an end use as a biocidal active; and (b) none of table items 1 to 5 [medium to high risk] apply to the introduction [E risk only]*
- *(a) the human health / environmental exposure band for the introduction is 1 / 1 or 2; and (b) the industrial chemical has one or more of the human health / environmental hazard characteristics in human health / environmental hazard band C / D; and none of table items 1 to 3 / 1 to 5 [medium to high risk], - / 15 or 16 [very low risk] apply to the introduction*
- *(a) the human health / environmental exposure band for the introduction is 3; and (b) the industrial chemical does not have any of the human health / environmental hazard characteristics in human health / environmental hazard band C / C or D; and (c) none of table items 1 to 3 / 1 to 5 [medium to high risk] or 14 / 17 [very low risk] apply to the introduction*
- *(a) the human health / environmental exposure band for the introduction is 4; and (b) the industrial chemical does not have any of the human health / environmental hazard characteristics in human health / environmental hazard band B or C / B, C or D; and (c) none of table items 1 to 3 / 1 to 5 [medium to high risk] or 14 / 17 [very low risk] apply to the introduction*

- + *Other introductions of industrial chemicals that are solely for use in research and development*
 - *the introduction of the industrial chemical is solely for the industrial chemical to be used in research and development by the person (the **introducer**); and*
 - *the industrial chemical is not an industrial chemical that: (i) is a solid, or is in a dispersion, at the time of introduction; and (ii) consists of particles, in an unbound state or as an aggregate or agglomerate, where at least 50% (by number size distribution) of the particles have at least one external dimension in the nanoscale; and*
 - *the industrial chemical is not made available to the general public: (i) on its own; or (ii) in combination with one or more other industrial chemicals; or (iii) as part of an article, including where the industrial chemical undergoes a physical or chemical change to produce the article; and*
 - *control measures are used to eliminate or minimise the risks from the introduction and use of the industrial chemical to: (i) persons involved in the research and development for which the industrial chemical is introduced; and (ii) the environment; and*
 - *the total volume of the industrial chemical introduced in a registration year by the introducer is greater than 250 kg, and no amount of the industrial chemical that meets the description in subparagraph (2)(b)(i) has been introduced by the person in the registration year; and*
 - *the use of the industrial chemical is subject to the control of the introducer.*
- + *Low-risk flavour or fragrance blend introductions*
 - *the introduction of the industrial chemical is either: (i) a flavour blend introduction; or (ii) a fragrance blend introduction; and*
 - *the concentration of the industrial chemical at introduction and at end use is 1% or less; and*
 - *the introduction is not for an end use in a personal vapouriser; and*
 - *the industrial chemical does not have: (i) any of the human health hazard characteristics in human health hazard band C; or (ii) any of the environment hazard characteristics in environment hazard band D; and*
 - *either: (i) when the pre-introduction report for the industrial chemical is given to the [ED] by the person, the industrial chemical is included on the IFRA Transparency List; or (ii) before the industrial chemical is first introduced by the person, the [ED] is given written notice of the information specified in subsection (5).*
 - *the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name) and the CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical*
 - *any hazard characteristics of the industrial chemical that are known to the person giving the notice*
 - *the maximum concentration of the industrial chemical in the flavour blend or fragrance blend (as the case requires) at introduction and at end use*
 - *the name by which the flavour blend or fragrance blend (as the case requires) is known to the person introducing the industrial chemical.*

- Section 28 (which deals with assessed introductions)⁷
 - The person is the holder of an assessment certificate, or is covered by an assessment certificate, for the industrial chemical; and
 - The introduction is in accordance with the terms of the assessment certificate
 - Note 1: An assessed introduction is generally an industrial chemical introduction that poses a medium to high risk⁸ to human health or the environment. If an introduction of an industrial chemical does not fall within the definition of an exempted or reported introduction and is not listed on the Inventory, it is generally an assessed introduction.
 - Note 2: A person can choose to apply for an assessment certificate for an introduction that would otherwise be authorised under another section
- Section 29 (which deals with commercial evaluation introductions)
 - The person is the holder of a commercial evaluation authorisation for the industrial chemical; and

⁷ Section 19 / Section 26 [F]: A low volume permit / a controlled use permit in respect of an industrial chemical that is in force under the old law immediately before 1 July 2020 is taken, on and after 1 July 2020, to be an assessment certificate issued for the industrial chemical under the new law.

⁸ Section 28 / Section 29 [B]: indicative medium to high human health (HH) / environmental (E) risk for an introduction, if

- The industrial chemical contains a sequence of greater than or equal to 4, but no more than 20, fully fluorinated carbon atoms
- (a) the industrial chemical is a polyhalogenated organic chemical (other than an organic chemical that is covered by item 1); and (b) the industrial chemical, or one or more of its known environmental degradation products, is persistent; and (c) the total volume of the industrial chemical to be introduced by the person in a registration year is greater than 100 kg
- (a) the industrial chemical is an industrial chemical that (i) is a solid, or is in a dispersion, at the time of introduction; and (ii) consists of particles, in an unbound state or as an aggregate or agglomerate, where at least 50% (by number size distribution) of the particles have at least one external dimension in the nanoscale; and (b) the industrial chemical is not soluble (within the meaning given by the Guidelines); and (c) the introduction of the nanoscale portion of the industrial chemical is not incidental to the introduction of the non-nanoscale portion of the industrial chemical
 - The manufacture (whether in Australia or otherwise) of the industrial chemical at the nanoscale is the result of a deliberate manufacturing, or is necessary for the manufacture (whether in Australia or otherwise) of the non-nanoscale portion of the industrial chemical; or the industrial chemical at the nanoscale has specific technical characteristics that are the intended result of changes in the manufacturing process
- (a) the human health exposure band for the introduction is 2 or 3; and (b) the industrial chemical has one or more of the human health hazard characteristics in human health hazard band C [HH risk only]
- (a) the human health exposure band for the introduction is 4; and (b) the industrial chemical has one or more of the human health hazard characteristics in human health hazard band B or C [HH risk only]
- (a) the industrial chemical is a gas; and (b) the industrial chemical is persistent; and (c) the total volume of the industrial chemical to be introduced by the person in a registration year is greater than 100 kg [E risk only]
- (a) the industrial chemical is an organotin chemical; and (b) the total volume of the industrial chemical to be introduced by the person in a registration year is greater than 10 kg [E risk only]
- (a) the environment exposure band for the introduction is 1 or 2; and (b) the industrial chemical has one or more of the environment hazard characteristics in environment hazard band D [E risk only]
- (a) the environment exposure band for the introduction is 3; and (b) the industrial chemical has one or more of the environment hazard characteristics in environment hazard band C or D [E risk only]
- (a) the environment exposure band for the introduction is 4; and (b) the industrial chemical has one or more of the environment hazard characteristics in environment hazard band B, C or D [E risk only]

- *the introduction is in accordance with the terms of the commercial evaluation authorisation*
 - *Section 30 (which deals with exceptional circumstances introductions)*
 - *the person is the holder of an exceptional circumstances authorisation for the industrial chemical; and*
 - *the introduction is in accordance with the terms of the exceptional circumstances authorisation.*

Applying for an assessment certificate (Section 31 [A])

- *A person may apply to the [ED] for an assessment certificate for the introduction of an industrial chemical.*
 - *An application ... cannot be made for an industrial chemical that is listed on the Inventory.*
 - *The [ED] must consider the application in accordance with this Subdivision.*

Applying for a commercial evaluation authorisation (Section 53 [A])

- *A person may apply to the [ED] for a commercial evaluation authorisation for the introduction of an industrial chemical if*
 - *the introduction is for the purpose of ascertaining the industrial chemical's potential for commercial application; and*
 - *the introduction or use of the industrial chemical will not involve any of the following:*
 - *making the industrial chemical available to the general public in circumstances prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this subparagraph*
 - *making the industrial chemical available to the general public on its own*
 - *making the industrial chemical available to the general public in combination with one or more other industrial chemicals*
 - *making the industrial chemical available to the general public as part of an article if [any of the followings, B]*
 - *the article was designed to release the industrial chemical*
 - *the industrial chemical is for an end use in an article with food contact*
 - *the article is a children's toy or a children's care product [products that are intended to facilitate children's sleep, relaxation or hygiene; the feeding of children; or sucking by children]*
 - *release of the industrial chemical into the environment without prior treatment*
 - *uncontrolled use in any workplace*
 - *introduction of a volume of the industrial chemical that exceeds [10 tonnes over the period for which the authorisation is to be in force; B]; and*
 - *the person does not hold, or has not previously held, an authorisation under this section for the industrial chemical and the end use for the industrial chemical; and*
 - *the person has not made another application under this section for the industrial chemical and end use that is yet to be decided or withdrawn.*

Exceptional circumstances authorisations

- *Section 67 [A]: The Minister may issue an exceptional circumstances authorisation for the introduction of an industrial chemical*
 - *Before deciding to issue the authorisation, the Minister must*
 - *Consult with the [ED]; and*

- *Be satisfied that the introduction of the industrial chemical is in the public interest to address*
 - *Significant risks to human health or the environment; or*
 - *If a national emergency declaration (within the meaning of the National Emergency Declaration Act 2020) is in force – an emergency to which the declaration relates.*

Listing on Inventory after 5 years

- Section 82 [A]: *the [ED] must list an industrial chemical on the Inventory if:*
 - *the industrial chemical is not listed on the Inventory; and*
 - *an assessment certificate has been issued for the industrial chemical; and*
 - *the assessment certificate remains in force; and*
 - *5 years have passed since the assessment certificate was issued*
 - *Note: If the industrial chemical has previously been listed on the Inventory, the Inventory listing must be varied in relation to any other assessment certificate for the industrial chemical that meets the requirements in paragraphs (b), (c) and (d).*

Listing on Inventory before 5 years

- Section 83 [A]: *The holder of an assessment certificate for an industrial chemical may apply to the [ED] for the industrial chemical to be listed on the Inventory, if:*
 - *the industrial chemical is not listed on the Inventory; and*
 - *the assessment certificate remains in force; and*
 - *the assessment certificate does not include a condition of a kind mentioned in paragraph 38(2)(c) (which deals with the period for which an industrial chemical is permitted to be introduced); and*
 - *5 years have not yet passed since the assessment certificate was issued*

Listing on Inventory in other circumstances (Section 84 [A])

- *the [ED] may list an industrial chemical on the Inventory if:*
 - *the industrial chemical was previously regulated under another law of the Commonwealth; and*
 - *the [ED] has:*
 - *completed an evaluation under Part 4 relating to the introduction of the industrial chemical; and*
 - *concluded, as part of that evaluation, that the risks to human health and the environment from the introduction and use of the industrial chemical can be managed;*
 - *there is no assessment certificate in force for the industrial chemical; and*
 - *the industrial chemical is currently in use in Australia.*
- *the [ED] may list an industrial chemical on the Inventory if:*
 - *all of the following apply:*
 - *the [ED] has completed an evaluation under Part 4 relating to the introduction of the industrial chemical*
 - *public consultation was conducted as part of that evaluation;*
 - *the [ED] concluded, as part of that evaluation, that the industrial chemical should have been listed on the Inventory instead of a listed industrial chemical that was misidentified; and*
 - *there is no assessment certificate in force for the industrial chemical.*

Varying the Inventory

- Section 85 [A]: *The [ED] may vary a term of the Inventory listing for an industrial chemical if the [ED] is satisfied, whether on application under this subsection or otherwise:*
 - *That there is an error or defect in the listing; or the listing is incomplete, or additional information should be included in the listing; and*
 - *the variation has no regulatory impact.*
- Section 86 [A]: *The [ED] may vary a term of the Inventory listing for an industrial chemical if*
 - *The [ED] has completed an evaluation under Part 4 relating to the introduction of the industrial chemical; and*
 - *public consultation was conducted as part of that evaluation; and*
 - *The [ED] concluded as part of that evaluation that a variation to the listing is necessary to manage the risks to human health or the environment from the introduction or use of the industrial chemical.*
- Section 87 [A]: *The [ED] may vary a term of the Inventory listing for the industrial chemical to incorporate the terms of the other assessment certificate [if]*
 - *an industrial chemical was listed on the Inventory under section 82 or 83 in relation to an assessment certificate; and*
 - *another assessment certificate is in force for the industrial chemical; and*
 - *either: 5 years have passed since the other assessment certificate was issued; or a holder of the other assessment certificate has applied under this subparagraph to the Executive Director for a variation to the listing.*
- Section 88 [A]: *A person may apply to the [ED] to vary a term of the Inventory listing for an industrial chemical.*
- Section 94 [A]: *The [ED] may vary a term of the Inventory listing for an industrial chemical if:*
 - *there is an approval for the proper name or end use for an industrial chemical to be treated as confidential business information under section 108 that relates to the listing; and*
 - *the [ED] decides to revoke the approval under paragraph 111(8)(a)*
- Section 95 [A]: *The [ED] may remove the Inventory listing for an industrial chemical if:*
 - *the [ED] has completed an evaluation under Part 4 in relation to the introduction of the industrial chemical; and*
 - *public consultation was conducted as part of that evaluation; and*
 - *the [ED] has concluded, as part of that evaluation, that:*
 - *the [ED] is not satisfied that the risks to human health or the environment from the introduction or use of the industrial chemical can be managed; or*
 - *the industrial chemical has been wrongly listed on the Inventory.*
 - *Note: The [ED] may add another industrial chemical to the Inventory instead of an industrial chemical that has been wrongly listed*

Post-introduction declarations for exempted introductions

- Section 95 [A]: *A person contravenes this subsection if:*
 - *the person first introduces an industrial chemical during a registration year; and*
 - *the introduction is an exempted introduction; and*
 - *the person does not make the declaration mentioned in subsection (2) within 4 months after the start of the last month of that registration year.*

Pre-introduction reports for reported introductions

- Section 96 [A]: *A person must give the Executive Director a report in accordance with subsection (2) if:*
 - *the person proposes to introduce an industrial chemical; and*
 - *the proposed introduction would be a reported introduction.*

- Section 98 [A]: *A person who gives a pre-introduction report to the [ED] under section 97 may notify the [ED], in writing, of any variations to the pre-introduction report.*
 - *The [ED] must make any changes to the pre-introduction report that are notified under subsection (1).*

Annual declaration for all introduction categories

- Section 99 [A]: *A person contravenes this subsection if*
 - *the person introduces an industrial chemical during a registration year; and*
 - *the person does not make the declaration mentioned in subsection (2) within 4 months after the start of the last month of that registration year.*

Obligation to report information about hazards

- Section 100 [A]: *The person⁹ contravenes this subsection if:*
 - *information becomes available to the person after the most recent assessment statement or evaluation statement for the introduction of the industrial chemical has been published; and*
 - *the information is about:*
 - *a hazard to human health or the environment from the introduction or use of the industrial chemical that is not identified in the most recent assessment statement or evaluation statement for the industrial chemical; or*
 - *a hazard to human health or the environment that is identified in the most recent assessment statement or evaluation statement for the industrial chemical and indicates an increase in the severity of the hazard; and*
 - *the person does not make the information available to the [ED] within 20 working days after the day the information becomes available to the person.*

Prohibited or restricted introductions or exports

- Section 163 [A]: *If an industrial chemical is the subject of a prescribed international agreement or a prescribed international arrangement, the rules may: (a) prohibit the introduction or export of the industrial chemical; or (b) impose conditions or restrictions to which the introduction or export of the industrial chemical are subject.*
 - *A person may apply to the [ED] for the approval; detailed procedures see Section 74 [B] (applying for approval to introduce or export restricted industrial chemicals), Section 75 [B] (decision on application)*
 - *Detailed chemical lists and conditions, see Section 71 [B] (introduction of certain industrial chemicals subject to conditions; selected industrial chemicals subject to the Rotterdam Convention); Section 72 [B] (introduction of tetraethyl lead subject to conditions); Section 73 [B] (export of certain industrial chemicals subject to conditions; selected industrial chemicals subject to the Rotterdam Convention)*

3.2 Exemptions

Exclusion / uses other than industrial uses (Section 9 [A])

- *use as an agricultural chemical product (within the meaning of the Agvet Code) or in the preparation of such a product*

⁹ a person who holds, or is covered by, an assessment certificate for the introduction of an industrial chemical; or a person who has introduced an industrial chemical within the previous 12 months (for which there is an Inventory listing; and for which there is an assessment statement or evaluation statement). [A]

- *use as a veterinary chemical product (within the meaning of the Agvet Code) or in the preparation of such a product*
- *use as a substance or mixture of substances mentioned in paragraph 5(4)(a) of the Agvet Code (which deals with substances or mixtures of substances prepared by a pharmacist or veterinary surgeon) or in the preparation of such a substance or mixture of substances*
- *use as a therapeutic good (within the meaning of the Therapeutic Goods Act 1989) or in the preparation of such a good*
- *use as food intended for consumption by humans or in the preparation of such food*
- *use as feed intended for consumption by animals or in the preparation of such feed*
- *any use prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph – radioactive chemicals [B]*

Excluded introductions (Section 11 [A])

- *This Act (other than Parts 1 [Preliminary], 4 [Evaluations initiated by the ED, ED], 7 [Enforcement], 9 [International agreements and arrangements] and 10 [Miscellaneous] and Division 4 of Part 6 [Confidentiality and disclosure]) does not apply in relation to an excluded introduction.*
- *An introduction of an industrial chemical is an excluded introduction if the introduction is of any of the following:*
 - *a naturally occurring chemical*
 - *a non-isolated intermediate*
 - *an incidentally introduced chemical*
 - *that is introduced, either with or subsequent to the introduction of another industrial chemical, as a result of any of the following:*
 - *the incomplete reaction of starting materials or reaction intermediates used in the manufacture of the other industrial chemical*
 - *an unintended constituent present in the starting materials used in the manufacture of the other industrial chemical*
 - *the exposure of the other industrial chemical to light, heat or other environmental conditions in the course of handling or storage*
 - *the occurrence of a chemical reaction during the manufacture or use of the other industrial chemical; and*
 - *the introduction of which has no commercial value separate from the other industrial chemical.*
 - *an industrial chemical that was released from an article that was not designed to release it*
 - *an industrial chemical of a kind prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph*
- *An introduction of an industrial chemical is an excluded introduction if*
 - *the industrial chemical is introduced at a port or airport in Australia; and*
 - *the industrial chemical remains subject to customs control under the Customs Act 1901 at all times before leaving Australia; and*
 - *the industrial chemical leaves Australia within 25 working days beginning the day the industrial chemical is introduced*
- *An introduction of an industrial chemical is an excluded introduction if*
 - *the industrial chemical is introduced incidentally to the carriage of passengers, or the importation of other products, on an aircraft or a ship that leaves Australia within 25 working days beginning the day the industrial chemical is introduced; and*
 - *the industrial chemical is used to support the operation of the aircraft or ship; and*
 - *the industrial chemical is not freight. [B]*
- *An introduction of an industrial chemical by an individual is an excluded introduction if the industrial chemical is introduced solely for the individual's personal use.*

- *Introductions that are taken not to be for personal use: for the purposes of carrying on an enterprise (within the meaning of the A New Tax System (Goods and Services Tax) Act 1999) is prescribed. [B]*

Exempted introductions

- *industrial chemicals that are imported and subsequently exported (only apply where the chemical is subject to customs control for longer than 25 working days) [B]*
- *industrial chemicals that are solely for use in research and development [B]*
 - *the introduction of the industrial chemical is: (i) solely for the industrial chemical to be used in research and development by the person; or (ii) solely for the purposes of making the industrial chemical available to another person for that other person to use solely in research and development*
 - *the industrial chemical is not made available to the general public: (i) on its own; or (ii) in combination with one or more other industrial chemicals; or (iii) as part of an article, including where the industrial chemical undergoes a physical or chemical change to produce the article*
 - *control measures are used to eliminate or minimise the risks from the introduction and use of the industrial chemical to: (i) persons involved in the research and development for which the industrial chemical is introduced; and (ii) the environment; and*
 - *the total volume of the industrial chemical introduced in a registration year by the person does not exceed: (i) if subsection (3A) applies to the industrial chemical—10 kg; or (ii) otherwise, and subject to subsection (3B)—250 kg.*
 - *3A: This section applies to an industrial chemical if: (a) the industrial chemical is a solid, or is in a dispersion, at the time of introduction and it consists of particles, in an unbound state or as an aggregate or agglomerate, where at least 50% (by number size distribution) of the particles have at least one external dimension in the nanoscale; or (b) it had not been determined, at the time of introduction, whether the industrial chemical meets the description in paragraph (a).*
 - *3B: Subparagraph (3)(d)(ii) does not apply to the introduction of an industrial chemical by a person in a registration year if an amount of the industrial chemical to which paragraph (3A)(a) applies has been introduced by the person in the registration year.*
- *Polymers that are comparable to listed polymers [B]*
 - *the industrial chemical is a polymer; and*
 - *the polymer contains each of the reactants that another polymer that is listed on the Inventory (the **listed polymer**) does; and*
 - *the polymer contains one or more other reactants (the **additional reactants**) that the listed polymer does not; and*
 - *each additional reactant does not constitute more than 2% by weight of the polymer; and*
 - *the introduction complies with the following terms of the Inventory listing for the listed polymer: (i) any defined scope of assessment for the industrial chemical; (ii) any conditions relating to the introduction or use of the industrial chemical; (iii) any specific requirements to provide information to the [ED] in relation to the introduction of the industrial chemical; and (iv) any other information relating to the industrial chemical that is prescribed by this instrument for the purposes of paragraph 81(1)(f) of the Act.*
- *Industrial chemicals that are comparable to listed industrial chemicals [B]*
 - *Aloe barbadensis, extract; brassica oleracea botrytis, extract; brassica oleracea, extract; brassica oleracea gemmifera, extract; fatty acids, palm-oil, sodium salts; jojoba, extract; 3,6,9,12,15,18,21,21,24,27-nonaioxanonatriacontan-1-ol; matricaria recutita, extract; orange,*

extract; pelargonium roseum, extract; soya lecithins; soya phospholipids; spiro[isobenzofuran-1(3H),9'-[9H]xanthen]-3-one, 2',4',5',7'-tetrabromo-4,5,6,7-tetrachloro-3',6'-dihydroxy-, aluminum salt (3:2); tridymite (SiO₂); wheat germ oil

- *the introduction complies with the following terms of the Inventory listing for the industrial chemical mentioned in column 3 of that item:*
 - *any defined scope of assessment for the industrial chemical*
 - *any conditions relating to the introduction or use of the industrial chemical*
 - *any specific requirements to provide information to the Executive Director in relation to the introduction of the industrial chemical;*
 - *any other information relating to the industrial chemical that is prescribed by this instrument for the purposes of paragraph 81(1)(f) of the Act.*

- *Polymers of low concern*¹⁰ [B]

¹⁰ Polymer = (a) are characterised by the sequence of one or more types of monomer units; and (b) are distributed over a range of molecular weights where the difference in molecular weights is primarily attributable to differences in the number of monomer units; and (c) greater than 50% by weight of which have a sequence of at least 3 monomer units covalently bound to at least one other: (i) monomer unit; or (ii) molecule that is linked to one or more sequences of monomer units but cannot, under the conditions of the relevant reaction used for the particular process of polymer formation, become a repeating unit in the polymer structure

Schedule 2 [B]: *A polymer*

- *one of the following applies:*
 - *(i) the polymer has a number average molecular weight that is greater than or equal to 1,000 g/mol, but less than 10,000 g/mol, and has such other characteristics relating to weight as are set out in clause 2;*
 - *The polymer must have (a) less than 10% (by mass) of molecules with a molecular weight that is less than 500 g/mol; and (b) have less than 25% (by mass) of molecules with a molecular weight that is less than 1,000 g/mol.*
 - *If the polymer: (a) includes moderate concern reactive functional groups; and (b) does not include high concern reactive functional groups; the polymer must have a combined functional group equivalent weight of 1,000 g/mol or more (taking into account all moderate concern reactive functional groups included in the polymer).*
 - *If the polymer includes high concern reactive functional groups, the polymer must have a combined functional group equivalent weight of 5,000 g/mol or more (taking into account any moderate concern reactive functional groups, and all high concern reactive functional groups, included in the polymer).*
 - *Moderate concern reactive functional groups: (a) acid anhydrides; (b) acid halides; (c) aldehydes; (d) aldimines; (e) alkoxy silanes (with alkoxy greater than C2-alkoxy silane); (f) allyl ethers; (g) conjugated olefinic groups not contained in naturally occurring fats, oils and carboxylic acids; (h) cyanates; (i) epoxides; (j) hemiacetals; (k) ketimines; (l) methylol-amides; (m) methylol-amines; (n) methylol-ureas; (o) unsubstituted positions ortho or para to phenolic hydroxyl.*
 - *High concern reactive functional groups: (a) alkoxy silanes (with alkoxy of C1- or C2-alkoxy silane); (b) alpha lactones; (c) amines; (d) aziridines; (e) azo groups; (f) beta lactones; (g) carbodi-imides; (h) disulfides; (i) halosilanes; (j) hydrazines; (k) hydrosilanes; (l) isocyanates; (m) isothiocyanates; (n) pendant acrylates; (o) pendant methacrylates; (p) trithiocarbonates; (q) vinyl sulfones; (r) any other reactive functional group that is not a low concern reactive functional group or a moderate concern reactive functional group.*
 - *Low concern reactive functional groups: (a) aliphatic hydroxyls; (b) blocked isocyanates (including ketoxime-blocked isocyanates); (c) butenedioic acid groups; (d) carboxylic acids; (e) conjugated olefinic groups contained in naturally occurring fats, oils and carboxylic acids; (f) halogens (other than reactive halogen-containing groups such as benzylic or allylic halides); (g) imidazolidinone groups; (h) imides; (i) organic*

- phosphate esters; (j) thiols; (k) unconjugated nitriles; (l) unconjugated olefinic groups that are not specifically activated by being part of a larger functional group or by other activating influences.
- (ii) the polymer has a number average molecular weight that is greater than or equal to 10,000 g/mol and has such other characteristics relating to weight as are set out in clause 3;
 - the polymer must: (a) have less than 2% (by mass) of molecules with a molecular weight that is less than 500 g/mol; and (b) have less than 5% (by mass) of molecules with a molecular weight that is less than 1,000 g/mol.
 - (iii) the polymer is made solely from prescribed reactants and has molecules that contain 2 or more carboxylic acid ester linkages, one or more of which links internal monomer units together; and
 - a dibasic or tribasic acid mentioned in the table in clause 7: 1,2/1,3/1,4-Benzenedicarboxylic acid (and some esters); 1,2,4-Benzenetricarboxylic acid; butanedioic acid (and dimethyl and diethyl esters); 2-butenedioic acid (E)-; 1,4-cyclohexanedicarboxylic acid; decanedioic acid (and dimethyl and diethyl esters); dodecanedioic acid; fatty acids, C18-unsatd., dimers; 2,5-furandione, dihydro-; heptanedioic acid (and dimethyl ester); hexanedioic acid (and dimethyl and diethyl esters); 5-isobenzofurancarboxylic acid, 1,3-dihydro-1,3-dioxo; 1,3-isobenzofurandione; nonanedioic acid (and diethyl and dimethyl esters); octanedioic acid (and dimethyl ester); nonanedioic acid (and dimethyl and diethyl esters); octanedioic acid (and dimethyl ester); pentanedioic acid (and dimethyl and diethyl esters); undecanedioic acid; unsaturated fatty acids, C₁₈, dimers, hydrogenated
 - a modifier mentioned in the table in clause 8: Acetic acid, 2,2'-oxybis; 1-butanol; cyclohexanol; cyclohexanol, 4,4'-(1-methylethylidene)bis-; ethanol; ethanol, 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)-; 1-hexanol; methanol; methanol, hydrolysis products with trichlorohexylsilane and trichlorophenylsilane; 1-Phenanthrenemethanol, tetradecahydro-1,4a-dimethyl-7-(1-methylethyl)-; Phenol, 4,4'-(1-methylethylidene)bis-, polymer with 2,2'-[(1-methylethylidene)bis(4,1-phenyleneoxymethylene)] bis[oxirane]; 1-propanol, 2-methyl-; Siloxanes and Silicones, di-Me, di-Ph, polymers with Ph silsesquioxanes, methoxy-terminated; Siloxanes and Silicones, di-Me, methoxy Ph, polymers with Ph silsesquioxanes, methoxy-terminated; Siloxanes and Silicones, Me Ph, methoxy Ph, polymers with Ph silsesquioxanes, methoxy- and Ph-terminated; Silsesquioxanes, Ph Pr
 - a monobasic acid or natural oil mentioned in clause 9: Benzoic acid; canola oil; castor oil; castor oil, dehydrated; castor oil, dehydrated, polymerised; coconut oil; coconut oil, hydrogenated; corn oil; cottonseed oil; dodecanoic acid; fats and glyceridic oils, anchovy/babassu/herring/menhaden/sardine/oiticica; fatty acids, C₈₋₁₀/C₁₄₋₁₈ and C₁₆₋₁₈-unsaturated/C₁₆₋₁₈ and C₁₈-unsatd./castor-oil/coco/corn-oil/dehydrated castor-oil/linseed oil/olive-oil/safflower-oil/soya/sunflower oil/sunflower-oil, conjugated/tall-oil/tall-oil, conjugated/vegetable oil; fish oil; glycerides, C₁₆₋₁₈ and C₁₈-unsatd.; heptanoic acid; hexadecanoic acid; 9-hexadecenoic acid, (9Z)-; hexanoic acid; hexanoic acid, 3,3,5-trimethyl-; hexanoic acid, 3,5,5-trimethyl-; linseed oil; linseed oil, oxidized; linseed oil, polymerised; nonanoic acid; octadecanoic acid; 9-octadecenoic acid (9Z)-; 9,12-octadecadienoic acid (9Z,12Z)-; oils cannabis/palm kernel/perilla/walnut; olive oil; safflower oil; soybean oil; sunflower oil; tung oil
 - a polyol mentioned in clause 10: 1,3-butanediol; 1,4-butanediol; 1,4-cyclohexanedimethanol; 1,2-ethanediol; ethanol, 2,2'-oxybis-; 1,6-hexanediol; 1,3-pentanediol, 2,2,4-trimethyl-; 1,2-propanediol; 1,3-propanediol, -/2,2-bis(hydroxymethyl)-/2,2-dimethyl-/2-ethyl-2-(hydroxymethyl)-/2-(hydroxymethyl)-2-methyl/2-methyl; 1,2,3-propanetriol; 1,2,3-propanetriol, homopolymer; 2-propen-1-ol, polymer with ethenylbenzene;
 - a derivative substance mentioned in clause 11: a diethyl or triethyl ester of a substance listed in clause 7; a dimethyl or trimethyl ester of a substance listed in clause 7; a methyl ester of a substance listed in clause 7 or 9; an anhydride of a substance listed in clause 7 or 9; an ethyl ester of a substance listed in clause 7 or 9
 - the polymer has a low cationic density; and

- *the industrial chemical is a polymer of low concern; and*
- *the industrial chemical is not a high molecular weight polymer [i.e. a polymer that has a number average molecular weight that is greater than or equal to 1000 g/mol] that has lung overloading potential (within the meaning given by the Guidelines).*
- *Low concern biological polymers [B]*
 - *The industrial chemical is a biological chemical; and*
 - *The industrial chemical is a polymer; and*
 - *The industrial chemical would be a polymer of low concern if the definition of polymer of low concern in Schedule 2 did not include a requirement that the polymer is stable (within the meaning given by the Guidelines)*
- *Industrial chemicals resulting from non-functionalised surface treatment of listed industrial chemicals [B]*
 - *the industrial chemical is the result of a reaction between 2 or more chemicals where the reaction occurs at the surface of one of the chemicals (the **substrate chemical**); and*
 - *the substrate chemical and each of the other chemicals that reacts with the substrate chemical is listed on the Inventory; and*
 - *the industrial chemical is not an industrial chemical that: (i) is a solid, or is in a dispersion, at the time of introduction; and (ii) consists of particles, in an unbound state or as an aggregate*

 - *it is not cationic or potentially cationic [if the chemical is likely to become cationic in an aquatic environment that has a pH value greater than 4 and less than 9]; or*
 - *the chemical contains one or more cationic, or potentially cationic, groups and at least one of the following applies: (i) the total combined functional group equivalent weight of any cationic or potentially cationic groups is at least 5,000 g/mol; (ii) the chemical has a solubility in water of less than 0.1 mg/L and will only be used in its solid phase; (iii) the chemical is not dispersible in water and will only be used in its solid phase.*
- *the polymer does not have any known hazard classification; and*
- *the polymer is stable (within the meaning given by the Guidelines); and*
 - *the polymer does not substantially degrade, decompose or depolymerise during use; that is, the polymer is not considerably, meaningfully or to a significantly large extent, changed into simpler, smaller molecular weight chemicals as the result of processes including, but not limited to: oxidation, hydrolysis, heat, sunlight, attack by solvents, microbial action*
- *the polymer contains, as an integral part of its composition, at least 2 of the chemical elements set out in clause 5; and*
 - *carbon; hydrogen; nitrogen; oxygen; silicon; sulfur*
- *the polymer does not contain, as an integral part of its composition (other than as an impurity), an element other than a chemical element set out in clause 6; and*
 - *(a) aluminium as the monatomic counterion Al³⁺; (b) bromine as the monatomic counterion Br⁻; (c) bromine covalently bound to carbon; (d) calcium as the monatomic counterion Ca²⁺; (e) carbon; (f) chlorine as the monatomic counterion Cl⁻; (g) chlorine covalently bound to carbon; (h) fluorine covalently bound to carbon; (i) hydrogen; (j) iodine as the monatomic counterion I⁻; (k) iodine covalently bound to carbon; (l) magnesium as the monatomic counterion Mg²⁺; (m) nitrogen; (n) oxygen; (o) potassium as the monatomic counterion K⁺; (p) silicon; (q) sodium as the monatomic counterion Na⁺; (r) sulfur; (s) boron; (t) copper; (u) iron; (v) lithium; (w) manganese; (x) nickel; (y) phosphorus; (z) tin; (za) titanium; (zb) zinc; (zc) zirconium.*
- *the polymer does not contain, as an integral part of its composition (other than as an impurity), 0.2% or more (by weight) of any combination of the chemical elements set out in paragraphs 6(s) to (zc); and*
- *the polymer does not contain any difluoromethylene or trifluoromethyl groups; and*
- *if the polymer is capable of absorbing its own weight in water—the number average molecular weight for the polymer is less than 10,000 g/mol.*

or agglomerate, where at least 50% (by number size distribution) of the particles have at least one external dimension in the nanoscale; and

- the industrial chemical does not have any reactive functional groups that were not present on the substrate chemical.

Post-introduction declarations for exempted introductions (Section 37; [B])

- industrial chemicals that are imported and subsequently exported
- industrial chemicals that are solely for use in research and development
- polymers that are comparable to listed polymers
- industrial chemicals that are comparable to listed industrial chemicals
- industrial chemicals resulting from non-functionalised surface treatment of listed industrial chemicals

4. Initial data requirements¹¹

¹¹ Section 103 [A]: Without limiting paragraph 102(1)(b), if an industrial chemical is to be introduced for an end use solely in cosmetics, rules made for the purposes of that paragraph may include the requirement mentioned in subsection (2).

- The requirement is that, when determining the category of introduction for such an industrial chemical, a person must not use animal test data obtained from tests conducted on or after 1 July 2020 in circumstances prescribed by the rules.
- Section 22 [B]: all circumstances are prescribed, other than circumstances where
 - The animal test data demonstrates that the industrial chemical has a hazard characteristic; and conflicts with other information contained in the application regarding whether the industrial chemical has that hazard characteristic; or
 - The animal test data is the only information that can demonstrate whether the industrial chemical has a particular environment hazard characteristic; or
 - Both the animal test data has been derived from tests conducted on animals involving a chemical other than the industrial chemical to which the application by the person relates; and the other chemical is not an industrial chemical introduced by the person solely for an end use in cosmetics.

Section 19 [B] – Restriction on animal test data for applications for industrial chemicals with multiple end uses including an end use in cosmetics: ... an application by a person under the Act in relation to the introduction of the industrial chemical must not contain any animal test data obtained from tests conducted on or after 1 July 2020 other than:

- animal test data that: demonstrates that the industrial chemical has a hazard characteristic; and conflicts with other information contained in the application regarding whether the industrial chemical has that hazard characteristic; or
- animal test data that is the only information that can demonstrate whether the industrial chemical has a particular environment hazard characteristic; or
- animal test data that is derived from tests conducted on animals involving a chemical that: is not the industrial chemical to which the application relates; and is not an industrial chemical introduced by the person for an end use in cosmetics.
- Note: This restriction does not apply if the inclusion of the animal test data is approved by the [ED]

Section 20 [B]

- A person may apply, in writing, to the [ED] for approval to include the animal test data in an application (the original application)
- The [ED] may, by written notice given to an applicant, request further information to be provided for the purposes of considering the application. The requested information must be provided within the period specified in the notice ... If the requested information is not provided within the period mentioned ..., the [ED] may take the application to be withdrawn.

Section 21 [B]

- In considering the application, the [ED] must have regard to the following:
 - if the animal test data is for the purpose of identifying a human health hazard characteristic of the industrial chemical—whether the non-cosmetic end use of the industrial chemical to which

Information required to demonstrate exempted or reported introduction (Section 30; [B])

- ... the person must, in determining the category of the introduction, have regard to the following:
 - such introduction and use information as is necessary to determine whether the introduction is to be covered by section 26 [exempted] or 27 [reported] of this instrument;
 - if the introduction is to be covered by subsection 27(4) of this instrument [low-risk flavour or fragrance blend introductions]—the information detailed in the Guidelines to demonstrate the absence of the hazard characteristics;
 - if the introduction is not to be covered by section 26 or 27 of this instrument: (i) such introduction and use information as is necessary to determine the highest indicative risk for the introduction; and (ii) such information as is necessary to determine whether the introduction is covered by any of items 1 to 3 of the table in subsection 28(1) [medium to high human health risk], or any of items 1 to 5 of the table in subsection 29(1) [medium to high environmental risk], of this instrument; and (iii) such information as is known to the person that demonstrates that the industrial chemical has hazard characteristics that are relevant for determining the highest indicative risk for the introduction; and (iv) if the highest indicative risk for the introduction is determined, in whole or in part, on the basis of the absence of certain hazard characteristics—the information detailed in the Guidelines to demonstrate the absence of the hazard characteristics

Post-introduction declarations for exempted introductions (Section 36; [B])

- *Introductions where highest indicative risk is very low risk*
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name) is known to the person: (a) the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name); and (b) the CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical*
 - *If: (a) the proper name for the industrial chemical is not known to the person; and (b) the total volume of the industrial chemical introduced by the person during the registration year is 10 kg or less; then: (c) the names by which the industrial chemical is known to the person; and (d) the name of the chemical identity holder*
 - *If: (a) the proper name for the industrial chemical is not known to the person; and (b) the total volume of the industrial chemical introduced by the person during the registration year is greater than 10 kg; then: (c) the names by which the industrial chemical is known to the person; and (d) the name of the chemical identity holder who has provided to the [ED]: (i) the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name); and (ii) the CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical*
 - *The total volume of the industrial chemical introduced by the person during the registration year*
 - *The end use for the industrial chemical*
 - *The maximum concentration of the industrial chemical at end use*

the original application relates involves, or potentially involves, exposure of humans to the industrial chemical

- *if the animal test data is for the purpose of identifying an environment hazard characteristic of the industrial chemical—whether the non-cosmetic end use of the industrial chemical to which the original application relates involves, or potentially involves, exposure of the environment to the industrial chemical*
- *any further information provided by the applicant under subsection 20(5)*
- *any other information the [ED] considers relevant*

- *If the industrial chemical was introduced for an end use in cosmetics—a statement as to which of the circumstances specified in subsection (3) applies to the introduction*
 - *animal test data obtained from tests conducted on or after 1 July 2020 was not used to determine the highest indicative risk for the introduction*
 - *both: (i) the industrial chemical was introduced for an end use solely in cosmetics; and (ii) animal test data obtained from tests conducted on or after 1 July 2020 was used to determine the highest indicative risk for the introduction in the circumstances mentioned in paragraph 34(a), (b) or (c);*
 - *all of the following apply: (i) the industrial chemical was introduced for multiple end uses, including an end use in cosmetics; (ii) animal test data obtained from tests conducted on or after 1 July 2020 was used to determine the highest indicative risk for the introduction; (iii) the animal test data is of a kind mentioned in paragraph 31(2)(a), (b), (c) or (d).*
- *Introduction of polymers of low concern or low concern biological polymers*
 - *The number of different polymers*
- *If the introduction is covered by another subsection in Section 26, a post-introduction declaration is not required*

Pre-introduction reports for reported introductions

- **Section 38 [B]:** *Introduction of industrial chemicals that are internationally assessed¹² for human health and the environment*
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name) is known to the person: (a) the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name); and (b) any other names by which the industrial chemical is known to the person; and (c) the CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical*
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical is not known to the person: (b) the names by which the industrial chemical is known to the person; and (d) the name of the chemical identity holder who has provided to the [ED]: (i) the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name); and (b) the CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical*
 - *Whether the industrial chemical is (a) imported; or (b) manufactured in Australia*
 - *The maximum total volume of the industrial chemical the person intends to introduce in a registration year*
 - *The end use for the industrial chemical*
 - *The maximum concentration of the industrial chemical at end use*
 - *Any known hazard classification for the industrial chemical*
 - *The name of the international assessment body that assessed or evaluated the industrial chemical for (a) human health; and (b) the environment*
 - *Both: (a) the reference number (however described) for the international assessment or evaluation; and (b) the name by which the industrial chemical is identified in the international assessment or evaluation*
 - *The year the international assessment or evaluation was completed*
 - *If the international assessment or evaluation included any parameters relating to end use, introduction volume or the maximum concentration of the industrial chemical at the end use—those parameters*

¹² By regulators in Canada, the European Union, and the USA. For details, see Section 6 in the Rules [B].

- *If: (a) the international assessment or evaluation is of a kind mentioned in item 6 of the table in subsection 6(3); and (b) there are restrictions set out in Annex XVII of the REACH Regulation relating to the industrial chemical; what those restrictions are and how those restrictions will be complied with by the person in Australia*
- *If: (a) the international assessment or evaluation is not of a kind mentioned in item 6 of the table in subsection 6(3); and (b) the international assessment body determined conditions that must be complied with in order to manage any risks to human health or the environment from the industrial chemical in the overseas jurisdiction; what those conditions are and how those conditions will be complied with by the person in Australia*
- *A declaration that: (a) the complete international assessment report for the industrial chemical is available and will be provided to the Executive Director if requested; and (b) the person has permission to use the report*
- *A declaration that introduction of the industrial chemical is not prohibited (however described) in the overseas jurisdiction*
- *A declaration that the risk to human health and the environment from the introduction and use of the industrial chemical in Australia is no higher than in the overseas jurisdiction, as determined in accordance with the Guidelines*
- *A declaration that no information has become available to the person after the international assessment or evaluation was completed about: (a) a hazard to human health or the environment from the industrial chemical that is not identified in the international assessment or evaluation; or (b) an increase in the severity of a hazard to human health or the environment from the industrial chemical that is identified in the international assessment or evaluation*
- **Section 39 [B]: Introduction of industrial chemicals that are internationally assessed for human health but not internationally assessed for the environment**
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name) is known to the person: (a) the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name); and (b) any other names by which the industrial chemical is known to the person; and (c) the CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical*
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical is not known to the person: (b) the names by which the industrial chemical is known to the person; and (d) the name of the chemical identity holder who has provided to the [ED]: (i) the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name); and (b) the CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical*
 - *Whether the industrial chemical is (a) imported; or (b) manufactured in Australia*
 - *The maximum total volume of the industrial chemical the person intends to introduce in a registration year*
 - *The end use for the industrial chemical*
 - *The maximum concentration of the industrial chemical at end use*
 - *Whether the introduction of the industrial chemical involves a designated kind of release into the environment and, if so, which kind*
 - *The environment exposure band for the introduction, and the exposure band criteria on which the exposure band is based*
 - *Any known hazard classification for the industrial chemical*
 - *Any environment hazard characteristics of the industrial chemical that are known to the person*
 - *A declaration that the person has had regard to the information mentioned in subparagraphs 30(2)(c)(iii) and (iv)*
 - *If the industrial chemical is to be introduced for an end use in cosmetics—a statement as to which of the circumstances specified in subsection (3) applies to the introduction*

- *Whether the introduction is a specified class of introduction to which subsection 7(2) or (3) applies, and, if so, which such class*
- *The name of the international assessment body that assessed or evaluated the industrial chemical for (a) human health; and (b) the environment*
- *Both: (a) the reference number (however described) for the international assessment or evaluation; and (b) the name by which the industrial chemical is identified in the international assessment or evaluation*
- *The year the international assessment or evaluation was completed*
- *If the international assessment or evaluation included any parameters relating to end use, introduction volume or the maximum concentration of the industrial chemical at the end use—those parameters*
- *If: (a) the international assessment or evaluation is of a kind mentioned in item 6 of the table in subsection 6(3); and (b) there are restrictions set out in Annex XVII of the REACH Regulation relating to the industrial chemical; what those restrictions are and how those restrictions will be complied with by the person in Australia*
- *If: (a) the international assessment or evaluation is not of a kind mentioned in item 6 of the table in subsection 6(3); and (b) the international assessment body determined conditions that must be complied with in order to manage any risks to human health from the industrial chemical in the overseas jurisdiction; what those conditions are and how those conditions will be complied with by the person in Australia*
- *A declaration that: (a) the complete international assessment report for the industrial chemical is available and will be provided to the Executive Director if requested; and (b) the person has permission to use the report*
- *A declaration that introduction of the industrial chemical is not prohibited (however described) in the overseas jurisdiction*
- *A declaration that the risk to human health from the introduction and use of the industrial chemical in Australia is no higher than in the overseas jurisdiction, as determined in accordance with the Guidelines*
- *A declaration that no information has become available to the person after the international assessment or evaluation was completed about: (a) a hazard to human health from the industrial chemical that is not identified in the international assessment or evaluation; or (b) an increase in the severity of a hazard to human health from the industrial chemical that is identified in the international assessment or evaluation*
- **Section 40 [B]: Introduction of industrial chemicals that are internationally assessed for the environment but not internationally assessed for human health**
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name) is known to the person: (a) the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name); and (b) any other names by which the industrial chemical is known to the person; and (c) the CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical*
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical is not known to the person: (b) the names by which the industrial chemical is known to the person; and (d) the name of the chemical identity holder who has provided to the [ED]: (i) the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name); and (b) the CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical*

- *If: (a) the industrial chemical is a high molecular weight polymer; and (b) the human health exposure band for the introduction is 4; the polymer molecular weight details¹³ of the industrial chemical*
- *Whether the industrial chemical is (a) imported; or (b) manufactured in Australia*
- *The maximum total volume of the industrial chemical the person intends to introduce in a registration year*
- *The end use for the industrial chemical*
- *The human health exposure band for the introduction, and the exposure band criteria on which the exposure band is based*
- *Any known hazard classification for the industrial chemical*
- *Any human health hazard characteristics of the industrial chemical that are known to the person*
- *A declaration that the person has had regard to the information mentioned in subparagraphs 30(2)(c)(iii) and (iv)*
- *If the industrial chemical is to be introduced for an end use in cosmetics—a statement as to which of the circumstances specified in subsection (3) applies to the introduction*
- *Whether the introduction is a specified class of introduction to which subsection 7(3) or (4) applies, and, if so, which such class*
- *The name of the international assessment body that assessed or evaluated the industrial chemical for (a) human health; and (b) the environment*
- *Both: (a) the reference number (however described) for the international assessment or evaluation; and (b) the name by which the industrial chemical is identified in the international assessment or evaluation*
- *The year the international assessment or evaluation was completed*
- *If the international assessment or evaluation included any parameters relating to end use, introduction volume or the maximum concentration of the industrial chemical at the end use—those parameters*
- *If: (a) the international assessment or evaluation is of a kind mentioned in item 6 of the table in subsection 6(3); and (b) there are restrictions set out in Annex XVII of the REACH Regulation relating to the industrial chemical; what those restrictions are and how those restrictions will be complied with by the person in Australia*
- *If: (a) the international assessment or evaluation is not of a kind mentioned in item 6 of the table in subsection 6(3); and (b) the international assessment body determined conditions that must be complied with in order to manage any risks to human health from the industrial chemical in the overseas jurisdiction; what those conditions are and how those conditions will be complied with by the person in Australia*
- *A declaration that: (a) the complete international assessment report for the industrial chemical is available and will be provided to the [ED] if requested; and (b) the person has permission to use the report*
- *A declaration that introduction of the industrial chemical is not prohibited (however described) in the overseas jurisdiction*

¹³ means the following

- *the number average molecular weight of the industrial chemical*
- *the weight average molecular weight of the industrial chemical*
- *the polydispersity index for the industrial chemical*
- *the percentage (by mass) of molecules with a molecular weight that is less than 1,000 g/mol*
- *the percentage (by mass) of molecules with a molecular weight that is less than 500 g/mol [B]*

- *A declaration that the risk to the environment from the introduction and use of the industrial chemical in Australia is no higher than in the overseas jurisdiction, as determined in accordance with the Guidelines*
- *A declaration that no information has become available to the person after the international assessment or evaluation was completed about: (a) a hazard to the environment from the industrial chemical that is not identified in the international assessment or evaluation; or (b) an increase in the severity of a hazard to the environment from the industrial chemical that is identified in the international assessment or evaluation*
- Section 41 [B]: *Introduction of industrial chemicals that solely for use in research and development*
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name) is known to the person: (a) the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name); and (b) any other names by which the industrial chemical is known to the person; and (c) the CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical*
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical is not known to the person: (b) the names by which the industrial chemical is known to the person; and (d) the name of the chemical identity holder who has provided to the [ED]: (i) the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name); and (b) the CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical*
 - *Whether the industrial chemical is (a) imported; or (b) manufactured in Australia*
 - *The maximum total volume of the industrial chemical the person intends to introduce in a registration year*
 - *Whether the industrial chemical is to be introduced as a solid, in a dispersion or neither. If the industrial chemical is introduced by the person as a solid or in a dispersion—whether the industrial chemical is known to the person to consist of particles, in an unbound state or as an aggregate or agglomerate, where at least 50% (by number size distribution) of the particles have at least one external dimension in the nanoscale*
 - *A declaration that the requirements of subsection 27(2) or (3) (as the case requires) have been met for the introduction*
- Section 42 [B]: *Low-risk flavour or fragrance blend introductions*
 - *The name of the flavour blend or fragrance blend that the industrial chemical is to be introduced as part of*
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name) is known to the person: (a) the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name); and (b) any other names by which the industrial chemical is known to the person; and (c) the CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical*
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical is not known to the person—the name of the chemical identity holder for the flavour blend or fragrance blend that the industrial chemical is to be introduced as part of*
 - *The number of industrial chemicals in the flavour blend or fragrance blend that are to be introduced by the person in accordance with subsection 27(4)*
 - *If the industrial chemical is to be introduced for an end use in cosmetics – a statement as to which of the circumstances specified in subsection (3) applies to the introduction*
- Section 43 [B]: *Other introductions where the highest indicative risk is low risk*
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name) is known to the person: (a) the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name); and (b) any other names by which the industrial chemical is known to the person; and (c) the CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical*

- *If the proper name for the industrial chemical is not known to the person: (b) the names by which the industrial chemical is known to the person; and (d) the name of the chemical identity holder who has provided to the [ED]: (i) the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name); and (b) the CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical*
- *If: (a) the proper name for the industrial chemical (including the CAS name or the IUPAC name) is known to the person; and (b) the industrial chemical is a UVCB substance; and (c) either: (i) the human health exposure band for the introduction is 4; or (ii) the environment exposure band for the introduction is 3 or 4; the UVCB substance description¹⁴ of the industrial chemical*
- *If: (a) the proper name for the industrial chemical is not known to the person; and (b) the industrial chemical is a UVCB substance; and (c) either: (i) the human health exposure band for the introduction is 4; or (ii) the environment exposure band for the introduction is 3 or 4; the name of the chemical identity holder who has provided to the [ED] the UVCB substance description of the industrial chemical*
- *If: (a) the industrial chemical is a high molecular weight polymer; and (b) the human health exposure band for the introduction is 4; the polymer molecular weight details of the industrial chemical*
- *Whether the industrial chemical is (a) imported; or (b) manufactured in Australia*
- *The maximum total volume of the industrial chemical the person intends to introduce in a registration year*
- *The end use for the industrial chemical*
- *Both: (a) the human health exposure band for the introduction; and (b) the exposure band criteria on which the exposure band is based*
- *Whether the introduction of the industrial chemical involves a designated kind of release into the environment and, if so, which kind*
- *Both: (a) the environmental exposure band for the introduction; and (b) the exposure band criteria on which the exposure band is based*
- *Any human health hazard characteristics of the industrial chemical that are known to the person*
- *Any environmental hazard characteristics of the industrial chemical that are known to the person*
- *A declaration that the person has had regard to the information mentioned in subparagraphs 30(2)(c)(iii) and (iv)*
- *If the industrial chemical is to be introduced for an end use in cosmetics—a statement as to which of the circumstances specified in subsection (3) applies to the introduction*
- *Whether the introduction is a specified class of introduction to which subsection 7(3) or (4) applies, and, if so, which such class*

Apply for an assessment certificate¹⁵

- There are 5 types of assessment certificates one can apply for. Each type has different information requirements.
 - Health and environment focus: if introduction's indicative risk to both human health and the environment is medium to high.

¹⁴ = a description of a UVCB substance that provide specific identity information about the UVCB substance, including one or more of the following: the manufacturing process, raw material sources, carbon number ranges, physical property ranges, and/or biological sources [B]

¹⁵ <https://www.industrialchemicals.gov.au/business/apply-assessment-certificate>

- Health focus: if introduction's indicative risk to human health is medium to high and the risk to the environment is low or very low.
- Environment focus: if introduction's indicative risk to the environment is medium to high and the risk to human health is low or very low.
- Very low to low risk: If the highest indicative risk of the introduction to human health and the environment is low or very low, one is not required to apply for a certificate. However, if one wishes to obtain a certificate, choose this application type.
- Comparable hazard assessment: Choose this application if your introduction meets the [requirement for a comparable hazard assessment](#) for human health or the environment.
- Information requirements
 - General information: identification, composition, analytical information
 - Classification and labelling: GHS
 - Manufacture: estimated quantities, site, manufacture, formulation or re-packing, uses at industrial sites, widespread uses by professional workers, consumers uses, article service life
 - Physical and chemical properties (with varied detailed requirements)
 - Environmental fate and pathways (with varied detailed requirements)
 - Ecotoxicological information (with varied detailed requirements)
 - Toxicological information (with varied detailed requirements)
 - Residues in food and feeding stuff, if available
 - Guidance on safe use
 - Assessment report
- If introduction is a specified class of introduction,¹⁶ there will be additional information requirements: gas, certain chemicals at the nanoscale, biochemical, for end use in a personal vaporizer, for end use in an article with food contact, for end use in tattoo ink, for end use as a biocidal active, designated kind of release into the environment, GM product, highly branched organic chemical, polyhalogenated organic chemical, organic chemicals containing a C4–C20 sequence of fully fluorinated carbon atoms, UV filter
- There may be circumstances where one cannot provide test data, or it is infeasible to provide test data for certain physical and chemical properties, environment and human health-related end points. In these situations, one can apply data waivers, including study technically not feasible, study scientifically not necessary / other information available, exposure considerations, study waived due to provisions of other regulation, and other justification. .¹⁷

5. Information updates by companies

Applying for a variation of the terms of an assessment certificate / Applying to cancel a certificate

- Section 43 / Section 51 [A]: *The holder of an assessment certificate may apply to the [ED] to vary a term of the assessment certificate / to cancel the certificate.*

Applying for a variation of the terms of an authorization / Applying to cancel an authorisation

- Section 62 / Section 65 [A]: *The holder of a commercial evaluation authorisation may apply to the [ED] to vary a term of the authorization / to cancel the authorisation.*

Record keeping for all categories (Section 104 [A])

- *The person must keep records relating to the introduction of industrial chemicals in that registration year by the person*

¹⁶ <https://www.industrialchemicals.gov.au/glossary/specified-class-introduction>

¹⁷ <https://www.industrialchemicals.gov.au/help-and-guides/data-waivers-available-iclid>

- *that are necessary to demonstrate the following*
 - *each industrial chemical that the person introduced during the year*
 - *the category of each of those introductions*
 - *the basis on which the person determined the category of the introduction*
- Section 46 [B]: *Listed introductions*
 - *If the CAS number for the industrial chemical is known to the person: (a) the CAS number for the industrial chemical; and (b) either the CAS name or the INCI name for the industrial chemical*
 - *If a CAS number for the industrial chemical is not assigned, or the CAS number for the industrial chemical is not known to the person: (a) the CAS name for the industrial chemical; or (b) both: (i) the names by which the industrial chemical is known to the person, or the names of all products containing the industrial chemical that are imported into Australia by the person; and (ii) a written undertaking from the chemical identity holder that the CAS name and CAS number (if assigned) for the industrial chemical will be provided to the [ED], if requested, within 40 working days after the day the request is made*
 - *If the terms of the Inventory listing for the industrial chemical include a defined scope of assessment for the industrial chemical: records to demonstrate that the industrial chemical is being introduced or used in accordance with that defined scope*
 - *If the terms of the Inventory listing for the industrial chemical include conditions relating to the introduction or use of the industrial chemical: records to demonstrate that the conditions are being complied with*
 - *If the terms of the Inventory listing for the industrial chemical include specific requirements to provide information to the Executive Director in relation to the introduction of the industrial chemical: records to demonstrate that those requirements are being met*
- Section 47 [B]: *industrial chemicals that are imported and subsequently exported (26(2)); that are comparable to listed industrial chemicals (26(5)); polymers of low concern (26(6)); low concern biological polymers (26(7))*
 - *See in the Rules*
- Section 48 [B]: *Introductions of industrial chemicals that are solely for use in research and development*
 - *See in the Rules*
- Section 49 [B]: *Introductions of polymers that are comparable to listed polymers*
 - *See in the Rules*
- Section 50 [B]: *Introductions of industrial chemicals resulting from non-functionalised surface treatment of listed industrial chemicals*
 - *See in the Rules*
- Section 51 [B]: *Other introductions where the highest indicative risk is very low risk*
 - *Including additional record keeping requirements for the introduction involves a designated kind of release into the environment, biochemical, GM product, end use in an article with food contact, end use in an article that is a children's toy or a children's care product*
 - *See in the Rules*
- Section 52 [B]: *Introductions of industrial chemicals that are internationally assessed for human health and the environment*
 - *See in the Rules*

- Section 53 [B]: Introductions of industrial chemicals that are internationally assessed for human health but not internationally assessed for the environment
 - Including additional record keeping requirements for the introduction involves a designated kind of release into the environment, biochemical, GM product
 - See in the Rules
- Section 54 [B]: Introductions of industrial chemicals that are internationally assessed for the environment but not internationally assessed for human health
 - Including additional record keeping requirements for the introduction biochemical, GM product, a UV filter and the human health exposure band for the introduction is 4, end use in an article with food contact, end use in an article that is a children's toy or a children's care product
 - See in the Rules
- Section 55 [B]: Introduction of industrial chemicals that are solely for use in research and development
 - See in the Rules
- Section 56 [B]: Low-risk flavour or fragrance blend introductions
 - See in the Rules
- Section 57 [B]: Other introductions where highest indicative risk is low risk
 - Including additional record keeping requirements for the introduction involves a designated kind of release into the environment, biochemical, GM product, a UV filter and the human health exposure band for the introduction is 4, end use in an article with food contact, end use in an article that is a children's toy or a children's care product
 - See in the Rules
- Section 58 [B]: Assessed introductions
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical is known to the person: the proper name for the industrial chemical*
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical is NOT known to the person: the AACN for the industrial chemical*
 - *If the terms of the assessment certificate include a defined scope of assessment for the industrial chemical: records to demonstrate that the industrial chemical is being introduced or used in accordance with that defined scope*
 - *If the terms of the assessment certificate include conditions relating to the introduction or use of the industrial chemical: records to demonstrate that the conditions are being complied with*
 - *If the terms of the assessment certificate include any specific requirements to provide information to the [ED] in relation to the introduction of the industrial chemical: records to demonstrate that those requirements are being met*
- Section 59 [B]: Commercial evaluation introductions
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical is known to the person: the proper name for the industrial chemical*
 - *If the proper name for the industrial chemical is NOT known to the person: the AACN for the industrial chemical*
 - *If the terms of the commercial evaluation include any conditions relating to the introduction or use of the industrial chemical: records to demonstrate that the conditions are being complied with*
 - *If the terms of the commercial evaluation include any specific requirements to provide information to the [ED] in relation to the introduction of the industrial chemical: records to demonstrate that those requirements are being met*

- Section 60 [B]: Exceptional circumstances introductions – *If the terms of the exceptional circumstances authorization include*
 - *the proper name for the industrial chemical: the proper name for the industrial chemical*
 - *any conditions relating to the introduction or use of the industrial chemical: records to demonstrate that the conditions are being complied with*
 - *any specific requirements to provide information to the [ED] in relation to the introduction of the industrial chemical: records to demonstrate that those requirements are being met*
 - *a scope for the authorisation: records to demonstrate that the industrial chemical is being introduced or used in accordance with that scope*
- Section 61 [B]: Introductions under section 163 of the Act [movements of industrial chemicals into or out of Australia – prohibited or restricted introductions or exports]
- *The person must retain the records for 5 years beginning immediately after the end of the registration year*
- *If the [ED] requires, by written notice, the person to provide information required to be kept for the purposes of subsection (2), the person must provide the information to the [ED] within 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*

Annual declaration for all introduction categories (Section 44 [B])

- *the registration number for the person*
- *the categories of introduction for the industrial chemicals introduced by the person*
- *a declaration that all introductions made by the person during the registration year were authorised by one of sections 25 to 30 of the Act.*
- *The declaration is not required for excluded introductions*

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

Applying for an assessment certificate / Applying for a variation of the terms of an assessment certificate / Applying for a commercial evaluation authorisation

- Section 33 / Section 45 / Section 55 [A]: *The [ED] may, by written notice given to an applicant, request further information to be provided for the purposes of considering the application.*
 - *The information must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 / 20 / 10 working days after the day the notice is given.*
 - *If the requested information is not provided within the period mentioned in subsection (2), the [ED] may take the application to be withdrawn.*
- Section 34 / Section 46 / Section 56 [A]: *The [ED] must, by written notice, seek the advice of a body¹⁸ prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this subsection if the [ED] is considering doing either of the following:*
 - *not issuing an assessment certificate under paragraph 37(1)(b) on the basis that the Executive Director is not satisfied that the risks to human health or the environment can be managed; or including conditions of a kind mentioned in subsection 38(2) on the assessment certificate on the basis that the conditions are necessary to manage risks to human health or the environment / including, removing or varying a condition of a kind mentioned in subsection 38(2) on the basis that the inclusion, removal or variation is necessary to manage risks to human health or*

¹⁸ See Sections 16 (bodies from which the ED must seek advice) and 17 (bodies from which the ED may seek advice) in the Rules [B]

the environment; or not varying a term of the assessment certificate under paragraph 49(1)(b) on the basis that the [ED] is not satisfied that the risks to human health or the environment can be managed / -

- *In considering an application, the [ED] may, by written notice, seek the advice of a body prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this subsection.*
- *The response must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*
- **Section 35 / Section 47 / Section 57 [A]:** *The [ED] must, by written notice, seek the advice of the Gene Technology Regulator if the application relates to an industrial chemical that is a GM product or contains a GM product*
 - *The response must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 / 20 / 10 working days after the day the notice is given.*
- **Section 36 / Section 48 [A]:** *The [ED] must, by written notice, provide each applicant with a draft assessment statement.*
 - *An applicant may make a written submission to the [ED] about the draft statement.*
 - *A submission must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*

Evaluations of introductions authorised by an assessment certificate

- **Section 70 [A]:** *The [ED] may, by written notice given to a holder of, or a person covered by, the assessment certificate, require further information to be provided for the purposes of considering the evaluation.*
 - *The information must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 / 20 / 10 working days after the day the notice is given.*
- **Section 71 [A]:** *The [ED] must, by written notice, seek the advice of a body prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this subsection if the [ED] is considering doing either of the following:*
 - *Including removing or varying a condition relating to the introduction or use of the industrial chemical on the assessment certificate on the basis that the inclusion, removal or variation is necessary to manage risks to human health or the environment; or cancelling the certificate on the basis that the [ED] is not satisfied that the risks to human health or the environment can be managed.*
 - *As part of the evaluation, the [ED] may, by written notice, seek the advice of a body prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this subsection.*
 - *The response must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*
- **Section 72 [A]:** *The [ED] must, by written notice, provide the draft evaluation statement to each holder of the certificate.*
 - *A holder of the certificate may make a written submission to the [ED] about the draft statement.*
 - *A submission must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*

Evaluation of other introductions or matters

- **Section 75 [A]:** *The [ED], when conducting an evaluation, may do any of the following*
 - *consult with a body prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph*
 - *conduct a public consultation process*
 - *request a person to provide information relevant to the evaluation.*
- **Section 76 [A]:** *The [ED] may, by written notice, require a person mentioned in subsection (2) to provide information specified in the notice if any of the following circumstances apply:*

- *the [ED] has been unable to obtain the information by other means*
- *the information is necessary to confirm whether or not a particular industrial chemical or class of industrial chemicals is being introduced, or is in use, in Australia*
- *the information is necessary in order to establish whether there are any risks to human health or the environment associated with an industrial chemical*
- *the information is necessary in order for Australia to meet its obligations under international agreements or arrangements*
- *any other circumstances prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph.*
- *For the purposes of subsection (1), the persons are*
 - *if the evaluation relates to a particular industrial chemical*
 - *all persons who introduce the industrial chemical during the period beginning 12 months before the day the notice is given and ending 12 months after that day; or*
 - *all persons who introduce the industrial chemical during the period mentioned in subparagraph (i) in circumstances specified in the notice; or*
 - *specified persons who introduce the industrial chemical during the period mentioned in subparagraph (i); or*
 - *in any case—a person whom the [ED] is satisfied has information relevant to the evaluation.*
- *The [ED] must give the notice to each person who the [ED] is satisfied is a person mentioned in subsection (2)*
 - *The notice must specify the period within which the information must be provided, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*

Listing on Inventory after 5 years

- Section 82 [A]: *Before listing the industrial chemical on the Inventory, the [ED] must*
 - *give each holder of the assessment certificate written notice of the proposed listing; and*
 - *give notice as mentioned in subsection 110(2) to any confidence holders for an approval for the proper name or end use for the industrial chemical to be treated as confidential business information; and*
 - *if an application is made under subsection 111(1) by any of those confidence holders—ensure that either:*
 - *a decision has been made on that application and, if the decision is to revoke the approval, that the requirements of subsection 111(10) have been met; or*
 - *the approval has been taken to be revoked under subsection 111(11); and*
 - *if no application is made under subsection 111(1) by any of those confidence holders—ensure that the approval has been taken to be revoked under subsection 111(11).*

Listing on Inventory before 5 years

- Section 83 [A]: *Before listing the industrial chemical on the Inventory, the [ED] must give a written notice in accordance with subsection (4) to if there are any other assessment certificates in force for the industrial chemical—each holder of the other certificate; and if there are any confidence holders for an approval for the proper name or end use for the industrial chemical to be treated as confidential business information—each such confidence holder. The written notice must contain the following information:*
 - *that an application has been made to list the industrial chemical on the Inventory;*
 - *that the person may object, in writing, to the Executive Director listing the industrial chemical;*
 - *that any objection must be given to the Executive Director within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*

Varying the Inventory

- Section 87 [A]: *Before varying a term of the Inventory listing for the industrial chemical, the [ED] must give written notice of the proposed variation to each holder of the other assessment certificate; and any other person prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph.*
 - *A notice under subsection (3) must contain the following:*
 - *the terms of the listing as varied*
 - *the reason why the listing is to be varied*
 - *the day the listing is proposed to be varied.*
- Section 90 (following Section 88) [A]: *The [ED] may, by written notice given to an applicant, request further information to be provided for the purposes of considering the application.*
 - *The information must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*
 - *If the requested information is not provided within the period mentioned in subsection (2), the [ED] may take the application to be withdrawn.*
- Section 91 (following Section 88) [A]: *The [ED] must, by written notice, seek the advice of a body prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this subsection if the [ED] is considering doing any of the following:*
 - *including, removing or varying a condition of a kind mentioned in subsection 81(2) on the basis that the inclusion, removal or variation is necessary to manage risks to human health or the environment; or not varying a term of the Inventory listing under paragraph 93(1)(b) on the basis that the Executive Director is not satisfied that the risks to human health or the environment associated with the variation can be managed.*
 - *In considering an application, the [ED] may, by written notice, seek the advice of a body prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this subsection.*
 - *The response must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*
- Section 92 (following Section 88) [A]: *The [ED] must, by written notice, seek the advice of the Gene Technology Regulator if the application relates to an industrial chemical that is a GM product or contains a GM product*
 - *The response must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*

Monitoring and investigation

- Section 128(2) [A]: *Information given in compliance or purported compliance with a provision of this Act is subject to monitoring under Part 2 of the Regulatory Powers Act.*
- Section 128(4) [A]: *For the purposes of Part 2 of the Regulatory Powers Act, the additional powers mentioned in subsection (5) are also taken to be monitoring powers for the purposes of determining: (a) whether a provision mentioned in subsection (1) has been, or is being, complied with; or (b) the correctness of information mentioned in subsection (2).*
 - *The additional monitoring powers are the powers to take and keep samples of any substance at any premises entered under section 18 of the Regulatory Powers Act, as that section applies in relation to the provisions mentioned in subsection (1) or the information mentioned in subsection (2).*

Prohibited or restricted introductions or exports

- Section 163 [A]: *At least 20 working days before rules are made for the purposes of subsection (1), the [ED] must publish on the AICIS website a notice:*
 - *identifying the prescribed international agreement or prescribed international arrangement*

- *listing the name or names by which the industrial chemical is known to the public*
- *requiring all persons who introduce the industrial chemical into, or export the industrial chemical from, Australia to give to the Executive Director information in the approved form about movements of the industrial chemical into or out of Australia.*

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

Applying for an assessment certificate / Applying for a variation of the terms of an assessment certificate

- Section 32 / Section 44 [A]: *In considering the application, the [ED] must have regard to the following*
 - *any risks to human health or the environment associated with the proposed introduction or use of the industrial chemical*
 - *whether any conditions of a kind mentioned in subsection 38(2) are necessary to manage any such risks [not needs for applying for a variation of the terms of an assessment certificate]*
 - *any further information provided in accordance with section 33 / section 45, or subsection 167(4)*
 - *any advice given by a prescribed body in accordance with section 34 / section 46*
 - *any advice given by the Gene Technology Regulator in accordance with section 35 / section 47*
 - *any submissions made by an applicant in accordance with section 36 / section 48*
- Section 37 / Section 49 [A]: *After considering the application, the Executive Director must decide to: (a) issue an assessment certificate; or (b) not issue an assessment certificate / (a) vary the term of the assessment certificate; or (b) not vary the term of the assessment certificate*
 - *The [ED] must be satisfied that any risks to human health or the environment can be managed before deciding to issue an assessment certificate / to vary the term of the assessment certificate*
- - / Section 50 [A]: *The [ED] may vary a term of an assessment certificate for the introduction of an industrial chemical if the [ED] has completed an evaluation under Part 4 relating to the introduction of the industrial chemical; and the [ED] has concluded as part of that evaluation that the terms of the assessment certificate may require variation to manage the risks to human health or the environment from the introduction and use of the industrial chemical; and the [ED] has published the evaluation statement for the evaluation*
 - *The [ED] must give written notice of the proposed variation, and the reasons for the variation, to each holder of the assessment certificate.*
 - *The holder of the assessment certificate may make a written submission to the [ED] about the proposed variation.*
 - *A submission must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*
 - *After considering any submissions made during that period the [ED] must decide to: (a) vary ...; or (b) not vary the term of the assessment certificate.*
 - *The [ED] must give written notice of the decision and the assessment statement to each holder of the certificate.*
- Section 38 [A]: *An assessment certificate must be in writing and include the following (the **terms** of the assessment certificate):*
 - *the proper name for the industrial chemical*
 - *the defined scope of assessment*
 - *any conditions relating to the introduction or use of the industrial chemical*
 - *a condition on the volume of industrial chemical permitted to be introduced*
 - *a condition on where the industrial chemical is permitted to be introduced or used, or*
 - *a condition on the period for which the industrial chemical is permitted to be introduced*

- any specific requirements to provide information to the Executive Director in relation to the introduction
- any other information prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph.

Applying to cancel a certificate

- Section 52 [A]: *The [ED] must grant the application if the [ED] is satisfied that the application complies with section 167; and each holder of the certificate consents to the application*
 - *The [ED] must give written notice of the decision to the following: (a) the applicant; (b) each holder of the certificate.*
- Section 52 [A]: *The [ED] may cancel an assessment certificate for the introduction of an industrial chemical if the [ED] has completed an evaluation under Part 4 relating to the introduction of the industrial chemical; and the [ED] has concluded as part of that evaluation that the [ED] is not satisfied that the risks to human health or the environment from the introduction and use of the industrial chemical can be managed; and the [ED] has published the evaluation statement for the evaluation*
 - *The [ED] must give written notice of the proposed cancellation, and the reasons for the cancellation, to each holder of the assessment certificate.*
 - *The holder of the assessment certificate may make a written submission to the [ED] about the proposed cancellation.*
 - *A submission must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*
 - *After considering any submissions made during that period the [ED] must decide to: (a) cancel ...; or (b) not cancel the term of the assessment certificate.*
 - *The [ED] must give written notice of the decision and the assessment statement to each holder of the certificate.*

Applying for a commercial evaluation authorization / Applying for a variation of the terms of an authorisation

- Section 54 / Section 63 [A]: *In considering the application, the Executive Director must have regard to the following:*
 - *whether the volume of the industrial chemical proposed to be introduced has been justified by the applicant for effective commercial evaluation of the industrial chemical [not needed for applying for a variation of the terms of an authorisation]*
 - *whether the time period to be covered by the authorisation has been justified by the applicant for effective commercial evaluation of the industrial chemical [not needed for applying for a variation of the terms of an authorisation]*
 - *whether any conditions relating to the introduction or use of the industrial chemical are necessary to manage any risks, or potential risks, to human health or the environment associated with the proposed introduction and use of the industrial chemical / any risks, or potential risks, to human health or the environment associated with the proposed variation*
 - *whether the requirements mentioned in paragraphs 53(1)(a) and (b) will be met [not needed for applying for a variation of the terms of an authorisation]*
 - *any further information provided in accordance with section 55 or subsection 167(4)*
 - *any advice given by a prescribed body in accordance with section 56 [not needed for applying for a variation of the terms of an authorisation]*
 - *any advice given by the Gene Technology Regulator in accordance with section 57 [not needed for applying for a variation of the terms of an authorisation]*

- Section 58 / Section 63 [A]: *After considering the application, the [ED] must decide to: (a) issue a commercial evaluation authorisation; or (b) not issue a commercial evaluation authorisation. / (a) vary ... or (b) not vary the term of the authorisation*
 - *The [ED] must not issue the authorisation if the [ED] is not satisfied that any risks to human health or the environment can be managed.*
 - *The [ED] must give written notice of the decision to each applicant / each holder of the authorization*
- - / Section 64 [A]: *The [ED] may vary a term of a commercial evaluation authorisation*
 - *Before making the variation, the [ED] must give written notice of the proposed variation, and the reasons for the variation, to each holder of the authorisation.*
 - *The holder of the authorisation may make a written submission to the [ED] about the proposed variation.*
 - *A submission must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*
 - *After considering any submissions made during that period the [ED] must decide to: (a) vary ...; or (b) not vary the term of the authorisation.*
 - *The [ED] must give written notice of the decision and the assessment statement to each holder of the authorisation.*
- Section 59 [A]: *A commercial evaluation authorisation must be in writing and include the following (the terms of the authorisation):*
 - *the proper name for the industrial chemical*
 - *the period for which the authorisation is in force (which must not be more than 4 years)*
 - *the end use for the industrial chemical*
 - *that any introduction of an industrial chemical under the authorisation must be for the purpose of commercial evaluation*
 - *any conditions relating to the introduction or use of the industrial chemical that are necessary to manage risks to human health or the environment from the introduction or use of the industrial chemical*
 - *any specific requirements to provide information to the Executive Director in relation to the introduction*
 - *any other information prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph.*

Applying to cancel an authorisation

- Section 65 [A]: *The [ED] must grant the application if the [ED] is satisfied that the application complies with section 167; and each holder of the authorisation consents to the application*
 - *The [ED] must give written notice of the decision to each authorisation holder.*
- Section 66 [A]: *The [ED] may cancel a commercial evaluation authorisation for the introduction of an industrial chemical if the [ED] is not satisfied that the risks to human health or the environment from the introduction and use of the industrial chemical can be managed.*
 - *The [ED] must give written notice of the proposed cancellation, and the reasons for the cancellation, to each holder of the assessment certificate.*
 - *The holder of the authorisation may make a written submission to the [ED] about the proposed cancellation.*
 - *A submission must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*
 - *After considering any submissions made during that period the [ED] must decide to: (a) cancel ...; or (b) not cancel the term of the assessment certificate.*

- *The [ED] must give written notice of the decision and the assessment statement to each holder of the authorisation.*

Exceptional circumstances authorisations

- Section 67(3) [A]: *The authorisation must be in writing and include the following (the terms of the authorisation):*
 - *the proper name for the industrial chemical*
 - *the period for which the authorisation is in force*
 - *the scope of the authorisation*
 - *any condition relating to the introduction or use of the industrial chemical that the Minister is satisfied is necessary to manage any risks to human health or the environment from the introduction or use of the industrial chemical*
 - *any specific requirements to provide information to the Executive Director in relation to the authorisation*
 - *any other information prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph*
- Section 67(4) [A]: *The Minister must determine each holder of the authorisation and give each such person written notice of the authorisation and the authorization*

Evaluations of introductions authorised by an assessment certificate

- Section 69 [A]: *The [ED] may initiate an evaluation of the introduction of an industrial chemical that is authorised by an assessment certificate.*
 - *The [ED] must give written notice of the proposed evaluation, and the reasons for the evaluation, to each holder of the assessment certificate.*
 - *The notice must specify the time period within which the evaluation will be conducted.*
 - *In conducting the evaluation, the [ED] must have regard to the following*
 - *any risks to human health or the environment associated with the introduction and use of the chemical*
 - *any further information provided in accordance with section 70*
 - *any advice given by a prescribed body in accordance with Section 71*
 - *any submissions made by a certificate holder in accordance with section 72*
- Section 73 [A]: *The [ED] must issue an evaluation statement within the period mentioned in subsection 69(3). An evaluation statement must be in writing and containing the following*
 - *the subject of the evaluation*
 - *the defined scope of the evaluation*
 - *a summary of the evaluation and any risks to human health or the environment identified during the evaluation*
 - *if risks have been identified -- the proposed means for managing these risks including*
 - *any recommendations relating to the introduction or use of the industrial chemical*
 - *any conditions of a kind mentioned in subsection 38(2)*
 - *any specific requirements to provide information to the [ED] as mentioned in 38(1)(d)*
 - *any other information relating to the safe introduction and use of the industrial chemical that the [ED] considers relevant.*
 - *The [ED] must give each holder of the certificate the evaluation statement.*

Evaluation of other introductions or matters

- Section 74 [A]: *The [ED] may initiate an evaluation of matters relating to industrial chemicals (other than the introduction of an industrial chemical that is authorised by an assessment certificate) ... An evaluation may relate to*
 - *an industrial chemical*

- *a class of industrial chemicals*
- *hazards to human health or the environment associated with an industrial chemical or class of industrial chemicals*
- *exposure of humans or the environment to an industrial chemical or class of industrial chemicals*
- *a use for an industrial chemical or class of industrial chemicals*
- *the circumstances in which an industrial chemical or class of industrial chemicals is introduced*
- Section 78 [A]: *The [ED] must issue an evaluation statement within the period mentioned in paragraph 74(3)(c). An evaluation statement must be in writing and contain the following:*
 - *the subject of the evaluation*
 - *the parameters of the evaluation*
 - *a summary of the evaluation and any risks to human health or the environment identified during the evaluation*
 - *the proposed means for managing any risks*
 - *any other information that the Executive Director considers relevant relating to the safe introduction and use of an industrial chemical that was considered as part of the evaluation*
 - *the conclusions of the evaluation.*

Listing on Inventory before 5 years

- Section 83 [A]: *... if an objection is made within the period specified in the notice mentioned in subsection (3), the [ED]:*
 - *must not list the industrial chemical on the Inventory under subsection*
 - *must notify the applicant that an objection has been made and the industrial chemical will not be listed on the Inventory.*

Varying the Inventory

- Section 89 [A]: *In considering the application, the [ED] must have regard to the following*
 - *any risks to human health or the environment associated with the proposed variation to the terms of the listing*
 - *any further information provided in accordance with section 90 or subsection 167(4)*
 - *any advice given by a prescribed body in accordance with section 91*
 - *any advice given by the Gene Technology Regulator in accordance with section 92*
- Section 93 [A]: *After considering the application, the [ED] must decide to: vary ...; or not vary the term of the Inventory listing.*
 - *The [ED] must be satisfied that any risks to human health or the environment can be managed before deciding to vary the term of the Inventory listing.*

8. Data submission format

IUCLID; Apply online for an assessment certificate, pre-introduction report, through AICIS Business Services.

9. Data confidentiality

Applying for data protection (Section 105 [A])

- *A person may apply to the [ED], in the following circumstances, for the proper name for an industrial chemical to be treated as confidential business information*
 - *in relation to an application under section 31 for an assessment certificate for the industrial chemical*
 - *in relation to an application under section 53 for a commercial evaluation authorisation for the industrial chemical*

- *in relation to a pre-introduction report for the industrial chemical under section 97 that contains information that may be published as mentioned in subsection 97(5)*
- *any other circumstances prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph. [B]*
 - *that the person gives notice under subsection 112(1) of the Act for information relating to the industrial chemical to be subject to Subdivision B of Division 4 of Part 6 of the Act;*
 - *that the [ED] gives notice, under subsection 113(1) of the Act, to the person nominated in the notice mentioned in paragraph (a) of this subsection of a proposal to publish the proper name for the industrial chemical.*
- *A person may apply to the [ED], in the following circumstances, for an end use of an industrial chemical to be treated as confidential business information*
 - *in relation to an application under section 31 for an assessment certificate for the industrial chemical*
 - *in relation to an application under section 43 to vary the end use specified in an assessment certificate for the industrial chemical*
 - *in relation to an application under section 53 for a commercial evaluation authorisation for the industrial chemical*
 - *in relation to an application under section 88 to vary the end use specified in the Inventory listing for the industrial chemical*
 - *in relation to a pre-introduction report for the industrial chemical under section 97 that contains information that may be published as mentioned in subsection 97(5)*
 - *any other circumstances prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph. [B]*
 - *that the person gives notice under subsection 112(1) of the Act for information relating to the industrial chemical to be subject to Subdivision B of Division 4 of Part 6 of the Act; the [ED] gives notice, under subsection 113(1) of the Act, to the person nominated in the notice mentioned in paragraph (a) of this subsection of a proposal to publish the end use for the industrial chemical.*
 - *that the person makes an application under section 62 of the Act to vary the end use specified in a commercial evaluation authorisation.*

Decision on application / continued protection / notice of intention to apply for protection

- **Section 105 / Section 111 / Section 114 [A]:** *In considering an application / the application / ditto, the [ED] must have regard to:*
 - *whether publication or disclosure of the proper name or end use (as the case requires) for the industrial chemical / ditto / the information could reasonably be expected to substantially prejudice the commercial interests of an applicant; and*
 - *whether the prejudice outweighs the public interest in the publication of the proper name or end use (as the case requires) for the industrial chemical; and*
 - *any further information provided in accordance with section 106 / subsection (7) of this section, or subsection 167(4) [not needed for notice of intention to apply for protection]; and*
 - *any advice given by a prescribed body in accordance with section 107 / subsection (7) of this section [not needed for notice of intention to apply for protection]*
- **Section 106 / Section 111 / Section 113A [A]:** *The [ED] may, by written notice given to an applicant, request further information to be provided for the purposes of considering the application.*
 - *The information must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*
 - *If the requested information is not provided within the period mentioned in subsection (2), the [ED] may take the application to be withdrawn.*

- Section 107 / Section 111 / - [A]: *In considering an application, the [ED] may, by written notice, seek the advice of a body prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this subsection.*
 - *The response must be given within the period specified in the notice, which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given.*
- Section 108 / Section 111 / Section 114 [A]: *After considering the application, the [ED] must decide to approve ... or not approve the application / revoke ... or not revoke the application / approve ... or not approve the application*
 - *The [ED] must give written notice of the decision to each applicant / the applicant and each confidence holder mentioned in subsection 110(2) / each applicant*
 - Section 108: *If the decision is to approve an application to treat the proper name for an industrial chemical as confidential business information, the notice must include the following:*
 - *the AACN [AICIS approved chemical name] determined by the [ED] for the industrial chemical*
 - *the circumstances in which the AACN will be published in lieu of the proper name (including the CAS name, CAS number or molecular formula for the industrial chemical).*
 - Section 108: *If the decision is to approve an application to treat the end use for an industrial chemical as confidential business information, the notice must include the following:*
 - *the generalised end use determined by the [ED] for the industrial chemical*
 - *the circumstances in which the generalised end use will be published in lieu of the end use for the industrial chemical.*
 - Section 114: *The [ED] must NOT approve an application to protect any of the following information:*
 - *information for which a person could apply for protection under section 105*
 - *physical and chemical data about an industrial chemical that does not reveal the industrial chemical's composition*
 - *summaries of data relating to risks to human health or the environment from the introduction or use of the industrial chemical.*

Notice of review of protection

- Section 110 [A]: *This section applies if the [ED] has approved an application under subsection 108(1) for the proper name or end use for an industrial chemical to be treated as confidential business information and any of the following circumstances apply:*
 - *5 years have passed since notice of the approval was given under subsection 108(2) and either:*
 - *the [ED] is proposing to list the industrial chemical on the Inventory under section 82*
 - *or the industrial chemical has been listed on the Inventory under section 83*
 - *5 years have passed since the Executive Director has reviewed the approval under this section and given notice not to revoke the approval under subsection 111(9)*
 - *circumstances prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph. The approval will be revoked unless a confidence holder makes an application under section 111. [B]*
 - *Protection of proper name or end use: the [ED] has concluded, as part of an evaluation under Part 4 of the Act in relation to the introduction of an industrial chemical, that a review of the approval to treat the proper name or end use for the industrial chemical as confidential business information is in the public interest.*
 - *Protection of proper name only: (a) an application for the proper name for an industrial chemical to be treated as confidential business information has been approved (other than an application made under paragraph 105(1)(a) of the Act); and (b) after that application has been approved, an application is made under subsection*

31(1) of the Act for an assessment certificate for the introduction of the industrial chemical.

- *Protection of end use only*
 - (a) an application for the end use for an industrial chemical to be treated as confidential business information has been approved (other than an application made under paragraph 105(2)(a) of the Act); and (b) after that application has been approved, an application is made under subsection 31(1) of the Act for an assessment certificate for the introduction of the industrial chemical for that end use.
 - an application for the end use for an industrial chemical to be treated as confidential business information has been approved; and 5 years have passed since notice of the decision to approve that application was given under subsection 108(2) of the Act; and the [ED]: (i) is proposing to vary a term of the Inventory listing for the industrial chemical in the circumstances mentioned in subparagraph 87(1)(c)(i) of the Act; or (ii) has varied a term of the Inventory listing for the industrial chemical following an application under subparagraph 87(1)(c)(ii) of the Act.

Applying for continued protection

- Section 111 [A]: A confidence holder mentioned in subsection 110(2) may make an application to the [ED] to continue the approval.

Providing notice of intention to apply for protection

- Section 112 [A]: A person who gives information to the [ED] (whether under a requirement under this Act or otherwise) in relation to an industrial chemical may give notice, in the approved form, to the [ED]
 - that the information is to be subject to this Subdivision; and
 - nominating the person to whom the Executive Director must give any notice under section 113 in relation to the information.
 - The notice must be given at the same time as the information is given to the [ED]
 - The [ED] must not publish information for which notice has been given under this section other than in accordance with section 113 or 114.
- Section 113 [A]: If the [ED] proposes to publish the information, the [ED] must give written notice to the person nominated in the notice under subsection 112(1).
 - The person may apply to the Executive Director for the information to be treated as confidential business information.
 - An application must be made within the period specified in the notice ..., which must not be less than 20 working days after the day the notice is given
 - If no application is made within the period specified in the notice ..., the [ED] may publish the information

Disclosure of information

- Section 116 [A]: An entrusted person may disclose protected information if the information is disclosed in the course of exercising powers, or performing functions or duties, under this Act.
- Section 117 [A]: The [ED] may disclose protected information to any of the entities mentioned in subsection (2) if the [ED] is satisfied that the protected information will assist the entity to exercise its powers, or perform its functions or duties.
 - a Commonwealth entity (within the meaning of the Public Governance, Performance and Accountability Act 2013)

- *a State or Territory government, agency or authority prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph*
- *an international government, agency or authority prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph.*
- Section 118 [A]: *An entrusted person may disclose protected information that relates to the affairs of a person if*
 - *the person has consented to the disclosure; and*
 - *the disclosure is in accordance with that consent.*
- Section 119 [A]: *An entrusted person may disclose protected information if the information has already been lawfully made available to the public.*
- Section 120 [A]: *An entrusted person may disclose protected information to a person ... if the person requests the [ED], in writing, to disclose protected information relating to an industrial chemical to the person in circumstances where:*
 - *the industrial chemical is listed on the Inventory; and*
 - *the [ED] is satisfied that: (i) the person intends to introduce the industrial chemical; and (ii) the disclosure is necessary for the safe introduction and use of the industrial chemical.*
- Section 121 [A]: *An entrusted person may disclose protected information to the person to whom the protected information relates.*
- Section 122 [A]: *An entrusted person may disclose protected information to the person from whom the information was obtained.*
- Section 123 [A]: *An entrusted person may disclose protected information, or a document containing protected information:*
 - *for the purposes of proceedings before: a court; or a tribunal, authority or person that has the power to require the answering of questions or the production of documents; or*
 - *in accordance with an order of: a court; or a tribunal, authority or person that has the power to require the answering of questions or the production of documents*
- Section 124 [A]: *The [ED] may disclose protected information to an agency ... if the [ED] reasonably believes that the disclosure of the information is necessary for the enforcement of the criminal law, the enforcement of a law imposing a pecuniary penalty, or the protection of the public revenue; and the protected information is disclosed for the purposes of that enforcement or protection*
 - *a Department, agency or authority of the Commonwealth, a State or a Territory; or*
 - *the Australian Federal Police; or*
 - *the police force or police service of a State or Territory; whose functions include that enforcement or protection.*
- Section 125 / Section 126 [A]: *The [ED] may disclose protected information if:*
 - *the [ED] reasonably believes that the disclosure is necessary to prevent or lessen a serious risk to public health / the environment; and*
 - *the disclosure is for the purposes of preventing or lessening that risk*

10. Data that are published publicly

Applying for an assessment certificate / Applying for a variation of the terms of an assessment certificate / Applying to cancel a certificate

- Section 37 / Section 49 / Section 52 [A]: *The [ED] must publish the assessment statement on the AICIS website.*

Applying for a commercial evaluation authorisation

- Section 59 [A]: *The [ED] must publish the following on the AICIS website in relation to a commercial evaluation authorization for an industrial chemical*

- *the proper name for the industrial chemical*
- *that a commercial evaluation authorisation is in force for the industrial chemical*
- *the end use for the industrial chemical*
- *the period for which the authorisation is in force*

Exceptional circumstances authorisations

- Section 67 [A]: *The [ED] must publish the following on the AICIS website in relation to an exceptional circumstances authorisation for an industrial chemical:*
 - *the commonly known name for the industrial chemical*
 - *that an exceptional circumstances authorisation is in force for the industrial chemical*
 - *the reasons why an exceptional circumstances authorisation is necessary*
 - *the period for which the authorisation is in force*

Evaluations of introductions authorised by an assessment certificate

- Section 73 [A]: *The [ED] must ... publish the evaluation statement on the AICIS website.*

Evaluation of other introductions or matters

- Section 74 [A]: *If the [ED] initiates an evaluation, the [ED] must publish the following on the AICIS website*
 - *the subject of the evaluation*
 - *the reason for the evaluation*
 - *the period within which the evaluation will be conducted*

Evaluation of other introductions or matters

- Section 75 [A]: *Before giving a notice, the [ED] must publish on the AICIS website a statement describing the information that the [ED] proposes to require under this section.*
- Section 78 [A]: *The [ED] must publish the evaluation statement on the AICIS website*

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- Section 81 [A]: *The Inventory must include the following (the terms of the Inventory listing) for each industrial chemical that is included on the Inventory*
 - *the CAS name and CAS number for the industrial chemical*
 - *the molecular formula for the industrial chemical (if defined)*
 - *any defined scope of assessment for the industrial chemical*
 - *any conditions relating to the introduction or use of the industrial chemical*
 - *a condition on the volume of industrial chemical permitted to be introduced*
 - *a condition on where the industrial chemical is permitted to be introduced or used*
 - *a condition of a kind prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph.*
 - *any specific requirements to provide information to the [ED] in relation to the introduction of the industrial chemical*
 - *any other information relating to the industrial chemical that is prescribed by the rules for the purposes of this paragraph*
 - *The Inventory listing for an industrial chemical must also include the website address where each assessment statement (if any) or evaluation statement (if any) that has been published for the industrial chemical can be accessed.*

Listing on Inventory after 5 years / Listing on Inventory before 5 years / Varying the Inventory

- Section 82 / Section 83 / Section 85 / Section 86 / Section 87 / Section 93 / Section 94 [A]: *If the [ED] lists an industrial chemical on the Inventory / ditto / varies a term of the Inventory listing for an industrial chemical / ditto / ditto / ditto / ditto ..., the [ED] must:*
 - *publish on the AICIS website a notice containing the following [before varying a term of the Inventory listing for the industrial chemical in Section 86]:*
 - *the terms of the listing / ditto / as varied / ditto / ditto / ditto / ditto*
 - *the reason why the industrial chemical was listed / listed / varied / to be varied / varied / ditto / ditto*
 - *the day the industrial chemical was listed / listed / varied / is proposed to be varied / varied / ditto / ditto*
 - *do so within 20 working days after the day the industrial chemical is listed / listed / varied / before the day mentioned in subparagraph (a)(iii) / varied / ditto / ditto*

Listing on Inventory in other circumstances (Section 84 [A])

- *Before listing an industrial chemical under subsection (1) [previously regulated chemical] or (2) [misidentified chemicals], the [ED] must:*
 - *publish on the AICIS website a notice containing the following:*
 - *the proposed terms of the listing*
 - *the reasons why the industrial chemical is proposed to be listed*
 - *the day the industrial chemical is proposed to be listed; and*
 - *do so at least 20 working days before the day mentioned in subparagraph (a)(iii).*

Removing listed industrial chemicals (Section 95 [A])

- *Before removing the Inventory listing, the [ED] must:*
 - *publish on the AICIS website a notice containing the following:*
 - *the reasons why the listing is to be removed*
 - *the day the listing is proposed to be removed; and*
 - *do so at least 20 working days before the day mentioned in subparagraph (a)(ii).*

Pre-introduction reports for reported introductions

- Section 97 [A]: *The [ED] may publish information related to reported introductions on the AICIS website*
 - Section 63 [B]: *industrial chemicals that are internationally assessed for human health and/or for the environment*
 - *The proper name for the industrial chemical*
 - *The end use for the industrial chemical*
 - *The name of the international assessment body that assessed or evaluated the industrial chemical*
 - *Note: If an application to treat the proper name or end use for the industrial chemical as confidential business information has been approved, an AACN or a generalised end use must be included in the information published instead of the proper name or end use if prescribed circumstances apply*

11. International information exchange and sharing

- See Section 117 above in **9. Data confidentiality**
 - *each Canadian government authority with responsibility for matters relating to the environment in relation to industrial chemicals*
 - *each Canadian government authority with responsibility for matters relating to health in relation to industrial chemicals*
 - *the European Chemicals Agency*

- *each New Zealand government authority with responsibility for matters relating to the environment in relation to industrial chemicals*
- *each New Zealand government authority with responsibility for matters relating to health in relation to industrial chemicals*
- *each United States of America government authority with responsibility for matters relating to the environment in relation to industrial chemicals*
- *each United States of America government authority with responsibility for matters relating to health in relation to industrial chemicals*
- Section 163 [A]: *The [ED] may inform any of the following persons or bodies regarding movements into or out of Australia of an industrial chemical mentioned in subsection (1): a country; the appropriate authority of a country; a relevant international organisation.*
 - *If an industrial chemical is the subject of a prescribed international agreement [Rotterdam and Stockholm Conventions; B]*
 - *The [ED] may give information under subsection (3) in such terms and on such conditions as the [ED] thinks fit, having regard to: (a) the requirements of the relevant international agreement or arrangement; and (b) the interest of any person in maintaining confidentiality in relation to movements of the industrial chemical.*

S1.2 Domestic Substances List (DSL), Canada

Last update: 16 July 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Substances Search: <https://pollution-waste.canada.ca/substances-search/Substance?lang=en>
- B. Canadian Environmental Protection Act, 1995: Part 5 Controlling Toxic Substances: <https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/canadian-environmental-protection-act-registry/publications/canadian-environmental-protection-act-1999>
- C. New Substances Notification Regulations (Chemicals and Polymers) (SOR/2005-247) (2021): <https://laws-lois.justice.gc.ca/eng/regulations/SOR-2005-247/index.html>
- D. *Draft* Guidance Document for the notification and testing of new substances: chemicals and polymers. <https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/managing-pollution/evaluating-new-substances/chemicals-polymers/guidance-documents/guidelines-notification-testing.html> [Note: As of 30 June, 2021, this draft guidance document is undergoing public comment. When finalized, this new guidance document will replace the 2005 Guidelines for the Notification and Testing of New Substances: Chemicals and Polymers: <https://publications.gc.ca/collections/Collection/En84-25-2005E.pdf>]
- E. Non-domestic substances list – homepage: <https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/canadian-environmental-protection-act-registry/substances-list/non-domestic.html>

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory [B]

- **DSL:** *The List shall specify all substances that the Minister is satisfied were, between January 1, 1984 and December 31, 1986 manufactured in or imported into Canada by any person in a quantity of not less than 100 kg in any one calendar year, or in Canadian commerce or used for commercial manufacturing purposes in Canada*
 - Section 87: *the Minister shall add a substance to the [DSL] and, if it appears on the [NDSL], delete it from that List, within 120 days after the following conditions are met*
 - *The Ministers has been provided with information ... under section 81 or 82 and any additional information or test results required under subsection 84(1),*
 - *The Ministers are satisfied that the substance has been manufactured in or imported into Canada by the person who provided the information in excess of (i) 1000 kg in any calendar year, (ii) an accumulated total of 5000 kg, or (iii) the quantity prescribed for the purposes of this section, and*
 - *The period for assessing the information under section 83 has expired, and*
 - *No conditions specified under paragraph 84(1)(a) in respect of the substance remain in effect*
 - *Where the minister adds a substance to the [DSL] and subsequently learns that the substance was not manufactured or imported as described [above], the Minister shall delete the substance from the [DSL], and if it has been deleted from the [NDSL], the Minister shall add it to [NDSL].*
 - *Where a substance is on the [DSL] or is to be added to the [DSL], the Minister may amend the [DSL] ... to indicate that subsection 81(3) [notification of significant new activity] applies with respect to the substance or that it no longer applies or by varying the significant new activities in relation to the substance in respect of which subsection 81(3) is to apply.*
 - *Despite [above], the Minister shall add a substance to the [DSL] and, if it appears on the [NDSL], delete it from that List, within 120 days after the following conditions are met*
 - *The minister has been provided with any information in respect of the substance under subsection 81(1) to (13) or section 82, any additional information or test results required under subsection 84(1), and any other prescribed information*
 - *The period for assessing the information under section 83 has expired, and*

- *No conditions specified under paragraph 84(1)(a) in respect of the substance remain in effect.*
- **NDSL:** *for the purpose of section 81.*
 - *This second publication is based on the United States Environmental Protection Agency's (U.S. EPA) Toxic Substances Control Act (TSCA) chemical substances inventory for 1985, and contains more than 58 000 entries. Substances that are not on the [DSL] but are list on the NDSL are subject to lesser information requirements. [E]*
 - *Beginning in 1995, the NDSL has undergone annual revisions that have added or deleted all substances incorporated into, or removed from, the TSCA inventory five or more years before the date of the NDSL revision. The first NDSL update therefore included substances in the 1990 supplement of the TSCA inventory. Substances on the TSCA inventory that have restrictions imposed on their manufacture or import as a result of a risk assessment by the U.S. EPA are not being added to the NDSL. [E]*

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligations

Manufacture or import of substances [B]

- *Section 81: Where a substance is not specified on the [DSL] and subsection (2) does not apply, no person shall manufacture or import the substance unless*
 - *The prescribed information with respect to the substance has been provided by the person to the Minister ...; and*
 - *The period for assessing the information under section 83 has expired.*

Notification of significant new activity¹⁹ in respect of substance on DSL / NOT on DSL [B]

- *Section 81: Where a substance is specified on the [DSL] with an indication that this subsection applies with respect to the substance / not specified on the [DSL] and the Minister publishes a notice ... indicating that this subsection applies with respect to the substance, no person shall use, manufacture or import the substance for a significant new activity that is indicated on the List with respect to the substance / indicated in the notice unless*
 - *The person has provided the Minister with the prescribed information, on or before the date that is specified by the Minister or prescribed ...; and*
 - *The period for assessing the information specified by the Minister or provided under Section 83 has expired.*

Substances subject to notification [C]

- Chemicals and biochemicals
- Polymers and biopolymers²⁰

¹⁹ *It includes, in respect of a substance, any activity that results in or may result in (a) the entry or release of the substance into the environment in a quantity or concentration that, in the Minister's opinion, is significantly greater than the quantity or concentration of the substance that previously entered or was released into the environment; or (b) the entry or release of the substance into the environment or the exposure or potential exposure of the environment to the substance in a manner and circumstances that, in the Minister's opinion, are significantly different from the manner and circumstances in which the substance previously entered or was released into the environment or of any previous exposure or potential exposure of the environment to the substance. [B]*

²⁰ *Substances that consist of a) molecules characterized by the sequence of one or more types of monomer units; b) greater than 50% by weight of molecules having three or more monomer units that are covalently bound to one or more other monomer units or reactants; c) less than 50% by weight of molecules of the same molecular*

- Unknown or variable composition, complex reaction products or biological materials (UVCB substances)
- Nano-scale substances²¹
- Reduced regulatory requirement (RRR) polymers²² (they are subject to the notification requirements set out in the Regulations; however, they are subject to fewer information requirements in comparison to

weight; and d) molecules distributed over a range of molecular weights whose differences in molecular weights are primarily attributable to differences in the number of monomer units. [C]

²¹ Using the Health Canada Working Definition of Nanomaterials: if it is a manufactured substance and a) it is at or within the nanoscale in at least one external dimension, or has internal or surface structure at the nanoscale (1 to 100 nm), or; b) it is smaller or larger than the nanoscale in all dimensions and exhibits one or more nanoscale properties/phenomena. [C]

²² As one of the following: [C, D]

- a) A polymer that is not one of the types listed in items 1 to 4 of Schedule 7 of the Regulations (see the following) and that has a number average molecular weight greater than 10000 daltons, with less than 2% of its components having molecular weights less than 500 daltons and less than 5% of its components having molecular weights less than 1000 daltons
- A cationic polymer or a polymer that is reasonably expected to become cationic in a natural aquatic environment, except (a) a polymer whose cationic group has a combined equivalent weight greater than 5000 daltons; or (b) a polymer that is a solid material, that is not soluble or dispersible in water and that will be used only in the solid phase, such as polymers that can be used as ion exchange beads.
 - A polymer that is designed, or can be expected, to substantially degrade, decompose or depolymerize, including polymers that could stantially degrade, decompose or depolymerize after manufacture and use, even though they are not intended to do so. Degradation, decomposition and depolymerization refer to the types of changes that convert a polymeric substance into simpler, smaller substances, through processes including but not limited to oxidation, hydrolysis, attack by solvents, heat, light and microbial action (the NS program will consider both the extent of degradation, decomposition or depolymerization and the hazard of the transformation products).
 - A polymer that has, as an integral part o fits composition, only one or none of the following atomic elements: carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, oxygen, silicon and sulphur
 - A polymer that has (a) an atomic elements other than carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, oxygen, silicon, sulphur, fluorine, chlorine, bromine or iodine covalently bound to carbon; (b) any monoatomic counterions other than chlorine ion, bromine ion, iodine ion, sodium ion, divalent magnesium, trivalent alumnium, potassium ion or divalent calcium; or (c) 0.2% or more by weight of any atomic element or combination of the following atomic elements: lithuium, boron, phosphorus, titanium, manganese, iron, nickel, copper, zinc, tin or zirconium.
- b) A polymer that is not one of the types listed in Schedule 7 of the Regulations and that has a number average molecular weight greater than 1000 daltons and equal to or less than 10000 daltons, with less than 10% o fits components having molecular weights less than 500 daltons and less than 25% o fits components having molecular weights less than 1000 daltons; or
- The four in the previous item
 - A polymer (a) that has reactive functional groups other than carboxylic acid groups, aliphatic hydroxyl groups, unconjugated olefinic groups that are considered "ordinary" (not specially activated either by being part of a larger functional group, such as a vinyl ether, or by other activating influences, for example, strongly electron-withdrawing sulfone group with which the olefinic groups interact), butenedioic acid groups, blocked isocyanates including ketoxime-blocked isocyanates, thiols, unconjugated olefinic groups present in naturally occurring fats, oils and carboxylic acids, in combined equivalent weights of less than 5000 daltons; or (b) in which the only reactive functional groups present are part of acid halides, acid anhydrides, aldehydes, hemiacetals, methylol-amides, methylol-amines, methylol-ureas, alkoxysilanes with alkoxy greater than C2-alkoxysilanes, allyl ethers, conjugated olefins, cyanates, epoxides, imines, unsubstituted positions ortho or para to phenolic hydroxyl, in combined equivalent weights of less than 1000 daltons.
- c) A polymer that is a polyester manufactured solely from reactants listed in Schedule 8 of the Regulations (including pre-defined monobasic acids and natural oils, dibasic and tribasic acids and esters, polyols, and

Non-reduced Regulatory Requirement polymers. The letter “P” after identifier of a substance on the DSL indicates that the substance was assessed and added on the basis that it met the RRR polymer criteria)

- Non-RRR polymers (they are added to the DSL once all criteria for addition are met).

3.2 Exemptions

- Section 81 *does not apply to* [B]
 - *A substance that is manufactured or imported for a use that is regulated under any other Act of Parliament that provides for notice to be given before the manufacture, import or sale of the substance and for an assessment of whether it is toxic or capable of becoming toxic.*
 - *Transient reaction intermediates that are not isolated and are not likely to be released into the environment.*
 - *Impurities, contaminants and partially unreacted materials, the formation of which is related to the preparation of a substance.*
 - *Substances produced when a substance undergoes a chemical reaction that is incidental to the use to which the substance is put or that results from storage or from environmental factors.*
 - *A substance that is manufactured or imported in a quantity that does not exceed the maximum quantity prescribed as exempt from this section.*
- Substances described by the following circumstances do not require notification [C]
 - Mixtures, hydrates, homogeneous and heterogeneous alloys
 - Manufactured items
 - Wastes
 - Other Acts of Parliament – Pest Control Products Act and Pest Control Products Regulations, Fertilizers Act and Fertilizers Regulations, Feeds Act and Feeds Regulations, 1983 (substances excluded from the scope of the other Acts of Parliament or regulations listed in Schedule 2 of the Act may be subject to notification under the Regulations. This includes isolated reaction intermediates, feedstocks and other starting materials used in the manufacture of any new substance.
 - Transient reaction intermediates (that are not isolated and are not likely to be released into the environment)
 - Impurities, contaminants and partially unreacted materials
 - Incidental reaction products (incidental to the use to which the substance is put or that results from storage or from environmental factors)
 - Low-quantity exemptions
 - Substances carried through Canada (a substance that is loaded on a carrier outside Canada and moved through Canada to a location outside Canada, whether or not there is a change of carrier during transit; if a substance is brought into Canada and stored for subsequent distribution, the substance may be subject to notification)
 - Polymers on the DSL that is modified by adding reactants, none of which constitutes more than 2% by weight of the polymer (as does not require the specific substance name to be changed)
 - Substances occurring in nature (must be unprocessed; processed only by manual, mechanical or gravitational means, by dissolution in water, by flotation, or by heating solely to remove water; or extracted from air by any means).

4. Initial data requirements [C]

modifiers) or an anhydrous form of those reactants, other than the reactants of their anhydrous forms that include both 1-butanol and fumaric or maleic acid. (irrespective of stability and molecular weight)

- Schedule 1 [2(2), 5(1) to (4)] Information respecting chemicals and biochemicals that are research and development substances, contained site-limited intermediate substances or contained export-only substances, including
 - 1. the type of substance
 - 2. IUPAC or CAS name²³
 - 3. trade names and synonyms
 - 4. CASRN, if such a number can be assigned
 - 5. Chemical identity information:²⁴ molecular formula, structural formula, gram molecular weight, the degree of purity in its technical grade composition, known impurities and their concentration by weight, and any additives, stabilizers and solvents present when the chemical is tested and their concentration by weight
 - 6. A safety data sheet, if available
 - 7. Exposure information, the anticipated annual quantity to be manufactured/imported, the anticipated uses²⁵, its anticipated concentration in products and in end-use products (if known), the expected modes and the size and type of container for its transportation and storage, identification of anticipated environmental release media, recommended destruction or disposal methods; public exposure potential (taking into account factors including its concentration, duration, frequency and circumstances of exposure, factors that may limit exposure, etc.), the location of use (for site-limited intermediate substances)
 - 8. A summary of all other information and test data that are in the possession of the manufacturer or importer or to which they may reasonably be expected to have access and that permit the identification of hazards to the environment and human health and the degree of environmental and public exposure
 - 9. The identification of the other government agencies, either outside or within Canada, that the person has notified of the manufacture or importation of the chemical and, if known, the outcome of the assessment and the risk management actions imposed by those agencies

²³ If the substance is an UVCB substance, the substance name of immediate precursors and/or major constituents as anticipated, the CAS registry number and the range of possible composition expressed in percentages (%) must be provided. [D]

Polymer and biopolymer nomenclature, including pre-polymers, incorporates the identity of monomers and reactants used in the manufacture of the polymer or biopolymer. The name of the polymer may or may not include monomers or other reactants that are either incorporated into the polymer or charged to the reaction vessel at 2% or less by weight. However, these substances must be included in the description of the polymer composition. Commercial dye names should not be used unless they are cross-referred to Colour Index Names in Volume 5 of the Colour Index. The Colour Index is a reference publication for manufacturers and users of dyes. It is published by the Society of Dyers and Colourists with assistance from the American Association of Textile Chemists and Colorists. [D]

²⁴ For polymers, the number or range of repeating units should be indicated and be correct relative to the number average molecular weight (M_n) (e.g., $x = 7-15$, $y = 10-50$). Where applicable, proportions of isomers or tautomeric forms must be indicated ... In addition, a reaction scheme showing a detailed description of the process for which the notified substance is made is required for polymers that are considered RRR ... The reaction scheme must include monomer and reactant information, as well as a sequence description ...

For UVCB substances, an estimate or range of molecular weights must be provided, if known.

Additives are substances that are deliberately introduced into a final product containing the notified substance (e.g., stabilizers, emulsifiers, solvents and anti-oxidants) that are present when the chemical is tested. [D]

²⁵ If known, the functional use code and application code specified in Appendices II and III of the NSN Form should be provided (<https://www.canada.ca/content/dam/eccc/documents/pdf/pded/forms/New-Substances-Notification-Appendix-II.pdf>; <https://www.canada.ca/content/dam/eccc/documents/pdf/pded/forms/New-Substances-Notification-Appendix-III.pdf>). If known, the North American Industry Classification System Code (NAICS), <https://www23.statcan.gc.ca/imdb/p3VD.pl?Function=getVD&TVD=307532>. [D]

- Schedule 2 [2(2), 5(2) to (4) and 6(2) to (4), subpara 7(1)(a)(ii) and (b)(ii) and 8(1)(a)(ii), (b)(ii) and (c)(ii) and paragraphs 10(b), 11(1)(b), 12(1)(b) and 18(2)(b) and (c)] Information respecting biochemicals and biopolymers
 - 1. The identification of the production organisms and the organ from which the biochemical and biopolymer is isolated (if applicable)
 - 2. Any known adverse environmental or human health effects associated with exposure to the production organism
 - 3. The concentration of the viable production organism in the biochemical or biopolymer and in end-use products (if known)
 - 4. The method to separate the production organism from the biochemical or biopolymer
 - 5. The identification of the encoded products, if known
 - 6. A description of any known biological activity or adverse environmental or human health effects associated with nucleic acid or with the encoded products specified under item 5
 - 7. All known catalytic functions, their known substrate specificity and the optimum pH and temperature for the substrates
 - 8. The Enzyme Commission (EC) number as designated by the International Union of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology (IUBMB), if available
 - 9. The catalytic constants K_m and K_{cat} and the conditions under which they were measured
 - 10. The known cofactors necessary for enzymatic activity
 - 11. The enzymatic activity per unit of weight of products and of end-use products (if known)
- Schedule 3 [2(2) and 6]: Information respecting polymers and biopolymers that are research and development substances, contained site-limited intermediate substances or contained export-only substances
 - Schedule 1: 1–4, 6, 8, 9
 - 5. Chemical identity information: molecular formula, structural formula (if possible) or else a partial structural formula, number average molecular weight (M_n) and the maximum concentrations expressed as a percentage of all residual constituents having molecular weights of less than 500 daltons and of all residual constituents having molecular weights of less than 1000 daltons (for contained site-limited intermediate substances and contained export-only substances), target number average molecular weight (for research and development substances), known impurities present and their concentration by weight, the composition of the polymer including constituents – such as monomers and other reactants, additives, stabilizers and solvents – which constituents are present when the polymer is tested, and their concentration by weight
 - The physical state of the polymer and whether the polymer is formulated for dispersal in water
 - Schedule 1: 7 + anticipated releases into municipal wastewater systems
- Schedule 4 [2(2), 7(1)(a)(i), 8(1)(a)(i), 17(2)(c)(i), 17(2)(d)]: Information respecting other chemicals and biochemicals NOT on the NDSL (100 kg) or on the NDSL (1000 kg)
 - Whether the chemical is on the NDSL
 - Schedule 1: 2–4, 6, 8, 9
 - Exposure information: anticipated annual quantity to be manufactured/imported, anticipated uses within Canada, anticipated concentration in products and in end-use products (if known)
- Schedule 5 [2(2), 7(1)(b)(i), 8(1)(b)(i), 8(2) and 16(3)]: Information respecting other chemicals and biochemicals NOT on the DSL (1000 kg) or on the NDSL (10000 kg)
 - The information specified in Schedule 4 or, if that information has been previously provided, the date (year, month, day) of the submission of that information
 - Schedule 1: 5, 8

- Physical and chemical data: melting point, boiling point, density, vapour pressure, water solubility, octanol/water partition coefficient, ready biodegradation test data (and identification of degradation products if known), data from one acute fish, daphnia or algae toxicity test, data from an oral, dermal or inhalation type of acute mammalian toxicity test selected on the basis of the most significant route of potential human exposure, mutagenicity data
- Exposure information: the expected modes and the size and type of container for its transportation and storage, identification of anticipated environmental release media, anticipated releases into municipal wastewater systems, recommended destruction or disposal methods, whether it is anticipated to be used in products intended for use by or for children, the anticipated degree of direct human exposure (including concentration, duration, frequency and circumstances of exposure and factors that may limit direct human exposure), the three Canadian sites where the greatest quantity of the chemical manufactured or imported by the person is anticipated to be used or processed and the estimated quantity by site.
- If the chemical is on the NDSL, the following additional exposure information respecting the chemical: its historical and other likely uses, any factors that may limit environmental exposure, whether it is released to the aquatic environment in a quantity exceeding 3 kg per day per site (averaged monthly and after wastewater treatment), whether public is anticipated to be significantly exposed in a product (including taking into account factors that may limit exposure)
- Schedule 6 [2(2), 8(1)(c)(i) and 17(2)(d)]: Information respecting other chemicals and biochemicals NOT on the NDSL (10000 kg)
 - 1. The information specified in Schedule 4 and 5 or, if that information has been previously provided, the date (year, month, day) of the submission of that information
 - 2. Physical and chemical data: one of an infra-red, ultra-violet, mass or nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum suitable for characterization of the chemical, adsorption-desorption screening test data (when a water solubility $\geq 200 \mu\text{g/L}$), hydrolysis rate as a function of pH and products if known (when a water solubility $\geq 200 \mu\text{g/L}$)
 - 3. The remaining two out of the following three tests: acute fish, daphnia and algae toxicity tests.
 - 4. Unless the chemical boils below 0 °C and has been tested for acute inhalation toxicity under item 6 of Schedule 5, data from one of the remaining types of acute mammalian toxicity test of the chemical that was not completed for the submission of item 6 of Schedule 5 and that is selected on the basis of the most significant route of potential human exposure
 - 5. Information sufficient to assess skin irritation
 - 6. Data from a skin sensitization test
 - 7. Data from one repeated-dose mammalian toxicity test, of at least 28 days duration, selected on the basis of the most significant route of potential human exposure
 - 8. Mutagenicity data obtained from one *in vitro* test, with and without metabolic activation, for chromosomal aberrations in mammalian cells
 - 9. Mutagenicity data obtained from one *in vivo* mammalian test for chromosomal aberrations or gene mutations or another indicator of mutagenicity that, together with data substantiating that the tissue investigated was exposed to the chemical or its metabolites, permits an assessment of *in vivo* mutagenicity
 - 10. Exposure information: its historical and other likely uses; and any factors that may limit environmental exposure.
- Schedule 9 [2(2), 10(a), 18(2)(b), 18(2)(d)(i), 18(2)(e)]: Information respecting reduced regulatory requirement polymers and other polymers and biopolymers (1000 kg)
 - The type of polymer: (a) a reduced regulatory requirement polymer, (b) a polymer on the NDSL, (c) a polymer with all of its reactants on the DSL or the NDSL, or (d) a polymer with one or more reactants not on either the DSL or NDSL.

- Schedule 1: 2–4, 6, 8, 9
- The structural formula of the polymer, if possible, or else a partial structural formula
- The reaction scheme if the polymer is a reduced regulatory requirement polymer, unless it is a polymer referred in paragraph 9(c) of these regulations [a polyester manufactured solely from reactants listed in Schedule 8, or an anhydrous form of those reactants, other than the reactants or their anhydrous forms that include both 1-butanol and fumaric or maleic acid].
- Physical and chemical data: (a) its number average molecular weight, and (b) the maximum concentrations, expressed as a percentage, of all residual constituents having molecular weights of less than 500 daltons and of all residual constituents having molecular weights of less than 1000 daltons.
- The known impurities present and their concentration by weight
- The composition of the polymer including constituents – such as monomers and other reactants, additives, stabilizers and solvents – which constituents are present when the polymer is tested, and their concentration by weight
- Exposure information: the anticipated annual quantity to be manufactured / imported, the anticipated uses within Canada, and if the polymer is not a reduced regulatory requirement polymer, the anticipated concentration of the polymer in products and in end-use products (if known), the anticipated degree of direct human exposure including factors that may limit exposure, whether the polymer is anticipated to be used in products intended for use by or for children, and if known, the three sites in Canada where the greatest quantity of the polymer, manufactured or imported by the person, is anticipated to be used or processed and the estimated quantity by site.
- Schedule 10 [2(2), 11(1)(a), 11(5), 18(2)(d)(i)]: Information respecting other polymers and biopolymers on the NDSL or all of whose reactants are on the DSL or NDSL (10000 kg)
 - 1. The information specified in Schedule 9 or, if that information has been previously provided, the date (year, month, day) of the submission of that information
 - 2. Physical and chemical data: (a) its physical state; (b) whether it is formulated for dispersal in water, (c) its water extractability, (d) its octanol-water partition coefficient, and (e) its hydrolysis rate and products (if known) if water extractability is determined to be greater than 2%.
 - 3. Unless the polymer has a water extractability at pH 7 of less than or equal to 2%, an acute toxicity for the most sensitive species (fish, daphnia or algae), or, if the sensitivity of these three species is unknown, an acute algae toxicity test
 - 4. Data from one acute mammalian oral toxicity test
 - 5. Exposure information: expected modes for its transportation and storage, the size and type of container used for its transportation and storage, anticipated releases into municipal wastewater systems, recommended destruction or disposal methods, its historical and other likely uses, factors that may limit environmental exposure, whether it is released to the aquatic environment in a quantity exceeding 3 kg per day, per site, averaged monthly and after wastewater treatment and, if the release is less than or equal to 3 kg per day, per site, the data substantiating the quantity released, whether the public is anticipated to be significantly exposed to the polymer in a product taking into factors such as that may limit direct human exposure
 - 6. Schedule 1: 7
- Schedule 11 [2(2), 12(1)(a), 12(3), 18(2)(e)]: Information respecting other polymers and biopolymers NOT on the NDSL
 - Schedule 10: 1, 2, 8
 - Data from a ready biodegradation test on the water-soluble portion of the polymer, unless the polymer has a water extractability at pH 7 of less than or equal to 2% or is a branched silicone or siloxane polymer

- Unless the polymer has a water extractability at pH 7 of less than or equal to 2%, (a) if the sensitivity of the three species is known, an acute toxicity test for each other two most sensitivity species: fish, daphnia or algae, (b) if the sensitivity of only one species is known and that species is not algae, an acute algae toxicity test and either a fish or daphnia acute toxicity selected on the basis of the most sensitive of these species, (c) if the sensitivity of only one species is known and that species is algae or if the sensitivity of the three species is unknown, an acute algae toxicity test and either a fish or daphnia acute toxicity test
- Data from one acute mammalian oral toxicity test
- Schedule 6: 5–7
- Mutagenicity data obtained from: (a) one *in vitro* test, with and without metabolic activation, for gene mutations, (b) one *in vitro* test, with and without metabolic activation, for chromosomal aberrations in mammalian cells, and (c) one *in vivo* mammalian test, for chromosomal aberrations or gene mutations or another indicator of mutagenicity that, together with data substantiating that the issue investigated was exposed to the polymer or its metabolites, permits an assessment of *in vivo* mutagenicity
- Exposure information: expected modes for its transportation and storage, the size and type of container used for its transportation and storage, anticipated environmental release media, anticipated releases into municipal wastewater systems, recommended destruction or disposal methods, its historical and other likely uses, factors that may limit environmental exposure
- Section 81(8) [B]: *On the request of any person to whom subsection (1), (3) or (4) applies, the Minister may waive any of the requirements to provide information under that subsection if*
 - *In the opinion of the Ministers, the information is not needed in order to determine whether the substance is toxic or capable of becoming toxic*
 - *The substance is to be used for a prescribed purpose or manufactured at a location where, in the opinion of the Ministers, the person requesting the waiver is able to contain the substance so as to satisfactorily protect the environment and human health, or*
 - *It is not, in the opinion of the Ministers, practicable or feasible to obtain the test data necessary to generate the information.*

Test requirements

- *The conditions to be met and test procedures to be followed in developing test data for a substance in order to comply with the information requirements of Section 81 of the Act – or requests for information under paragraph 84(1)(c) of the Act – must be consistent with the conditions and procedures set out in the “OECD Test Guidelines” that are current at the time the test data are developed. [C]*
- *The laboratory practices to be followed in developing data for the following tests must comply with the practices set out in the “Principles of Good Laboratory Practice” that are current at the time the test data are developed: (a) acute mammalian toxicity tests; (b) repeated-dose mammalian toxicity tests; (c) genotoxicity tests; (d) tests to assess skin irritation; (e) skin sensitization tests; (f) acute fish, daphnia or algae toxicity tests; and (g) biodegradation tests. [C]*
- *If the test was commenced or completed before the day on which these Regulations come into force, the laboratory practices must be consistent with those referred [above]. [C]*
- *Full test reports must be provided for all prescribed test data; summaries will not be accepted. [D]*
- *If literature papers are referenced, a copy of each paper must be provided. If software estimates/models are being used, information about the model (e.g., version of software), the input data and model output must be provided to allow for an assessment of the data by the NS program. [D]*

Record-keeping requirements

- Pursuant to section 13 of the New Substances Notification Regulations (Chemicals and Polymers) (the Regulations), a notifier who is required to provide information to the Minister of the Environment or the NS program under the Regulations must keep a copy of that information and any supporting data at the notifier's principal place of business in Canada or at the principal place of business in Canada of a representative of that notifier. The information and the supporting data must be kept for a period of five years after the year in which the information is provided. [D]

5. Data updates by companies

Notification of a new substance / new significant activity

- Where a person manufactures or imports a substance in accordance with this section in excess of any quantity referred to in paragraph 87(a)(b), the person shall, within 30 days after the quantity is exceeded, notify the Minister that it has been exceeded. [B]
- A person that is required to provide information to the Minister under these Regulations must keep a copy of that information and any supporting data ... The information and the supporting data must be kept for a period of five years after the year in which the information is provided. [C]

Notice to the Minister

- Section 70: Where a person (a) imports, manufactures, transports, processes or distributes a substance of commercial purposes, or (b) uses a substance in a commercial manufacturing or processing activity, and obtains information that reasonably supports the conclusion that the substance is toxic²⁶ or is capable of becoming toxic, the person shall without delay provide the information unless the person has actual knowledge that either Minister already has the information. [B]

Content of virtual elimination plan

- Section 79 [B]: Every person who is required to prepare and submit a plan
 - Shall include in it a description of the proposed actions in respect of the implementation of virtual elimination under subsection 65(3) of the substance in relation to the work, undertaking or activity of the person and the period within which the proposed actions are to be completed; and
 - May include in it relevant information respecting measurable quantities or concentrations of the substance, environmental or health risks and social, economic or technical matters.

Correction of information

- Section 81(11) [B]: A person who has provided information under this section, including for the purposes of a request for a waiver under subsection (8), or under section 82 or 84 shall notify the Minister of any corrections to the information as soon as possible after learning of them

Notification of excess quantity

- Section 81(14): Where a person manufactures or imports a substance in accordance with this section in excess of any quantity referred to in paragraph 87(1)(b), the person shall, within 30 days after the quantity is exceeded, notify the Minister that it has been exceeded.

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators [B]

²⁶ If it is entering or may enter the environment in a quantity or concentration or under conditions that (a) have or may have an immediate or long-term harmful effect on the environment or its biological diversity; (b) constitute or may constitute a danger to the environment on which life depends; or (c) constitute or may constitute a danger in Canada to human life or health. [B]

Notice requiring information, samples or testing

- Section 71: *The Minister may, for the purpose of assessing whether a substance is toxic or is capable of becoming toxic, or for the purpose of assessing whether to control, or the manner in which to control, a substance, including a substance specified on the List of Toxic Substances in Schedule 1*
 - *Publish ... a notice requiring any person who is described in the notice and who is or was within the period specified in the notice engaged in any activity involving the substance to notify the Minister that the person is or was during that period engaged in that activity;*
 - *Publish ... a notice requiring any person who is described in the notice to provide the Minister with any information and samples ... that may be in the person's possession or to which the person may reasonably be expected to have access; and*
 - *Including: (a) in respect of a substance, available toxicological information, available monitoring information, samples of the substance and information on the quantities, composition, uses and distribution of the substance and products containing the substances; and (b) in respect of a work, undertaking or activity, plans, specifications, studies and information on procedures.*
 - *Subject to section 72, send a written notice to any person who is described in the notice and who is or was within the period specified in the notice engaged in any activity involving the importation or manufacturing of the substance or any product containing the substance requiring the person to conduct toxicological and other tests that the Minister may specify in the notice and submit the results of the tests to the Minister.*
 - *The Minister may not exercise the power ... unless the Ministers have reason to suspect that the substance is toxic or capable of becoming toxic or it has been determined under this Act that the substance is toxic or capable of becoming toxic.*

Notice of suspension of five-year period – Priority Substances

- Section 78: *Where a substance is specified on the Priority Substances List and the Ministers are satisfied that new or additional information is required to assess whether the substance is toxic or capable of becoming toxic, the Minister shall publish a notice ... indicating ... (b) the new or additional information that is required to assess whether the substance is toxic or capable of becoming toxic, unless another provision of this Part requires the submission of the new or additional information*

Plans required for virtual elimination

- Section 79: *Where the Minister publishes ... a statement indicating that the proposed measure, as confirmed or amended, is the implementation of virtual elimination under subsection 65(3) in respect of a substance, the Minister shall in that statement require any person who is described in it to prepare and submit to the Minister a plan in respect of the substance in relation to the work, undertaking or activity of the person.*

Request for information previously waived

- Section 81(12): *Where the Minister is notified of any corrections to information that was provided for the purposes of a request for a waiver under subsection (8), the Minister may, after consideration by the Ministers of the corrections, require the person to whom the waiver was granted to provide the Minister with the information to which the waiver related within the time specified by the Minister*

Prohibition of activity

- Section 82(1): *Where the Minister has reasonable grounds to believe that a person has used, manufactured or imported a substance in contravention of subsection 81(1), (3) or (4) [new substance/activity registration], the Minister may, in writing, require the person to provide the*

information referred to in that subsection and prohibit any activity involving the substance until the expiry of the period for assessing the information under section 83.

- On the request of any person required ... to provide information, the Minister may waive any of the requirements for prescribed information if one of the conditions specified in paragraph 81(8) is met and, in that case, subsections 81(9) to (13) apply with respect to the waiver.

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

Categorization of substances on DSL (Section 73) [B]

- *The Ministers shall, within seven years from the giving of Royal Assent to this Act, categorize the substances that are on the Domestic Substances List by virtue of section 66, for the purpose of identifying the substances on the List that, in their opinion and on the basis of available information, (a) may present, to individuals in Canada, the greatest potential for exposure; or (b) are persistent or bioaccumulative in accordance with the regulations, and inherently toxic to human beings or to non-human organisms, as determined by laboratory or other studies.*
 - *Where available information is insufficient to identify substances as referred to in that subsection, the Ministers may, to the extent possible, cooperate with other governments in Canada, governments of foreign states or any interested persons to acquire the information required for the identification.*
 - *(3) When categorizing substances under subsection (1), the Ministers shall examine the substances that are on the Domestic Substances List to determine whether an amendment should be made to the List to indicate that subsection 81(3) [notification of significant new activity] applies with respect to those substances.*

Screening level risk assessment (Section 74) [B]

- *The Ministers shall conduct a screening assessment of a substance in order to determine whether the substance is toxic or capable of becoming toxic and shall propose one of the measures described in subsection 77(2) if (a) the Ministers identify a substance on the Domestic Substances List to be a substance described in paragraph 73(1)(a) or (b); or (b) the substance has been added to the Domestic Substances List under section 105 [adding living organisms to DSL].*

Priority Substances List (Section 76) [B]

- *The Ministers shall compile and may amend from time to time in accordance with subsection (5) a list, to be known as the Priority Substances List, and the List shall specify substances in respect of which the Ministers are satisfied priority should be given in assessing whether they are toxic or capable of becoming toxic.*
 - *Any person may file in writing with the Minister a request that a substance be added to the Priority Substances List and the request shall state the reasons for adding the substance to the List.*
 - *The Ministers may amend the Priority Substances List*
 - *(a) by adding a substance to the List where the Ministers are satisfied on the basis of a determination made as a result of a screening assessment conducted under section 74, the review of a decision of another jurisdiction under subsection 75(3), consultation under subsection (2) or a request made under subsection (3) or for any other reason that priority should be given in assessing whether the substance is toxic or capable of becoming toxic; and*
 - *(b) by deleting a substance from the List where the Ministers have determined whether the substance is toxic or capable of becoming toxic.*

Weight of evidence and precautionary principle (Section 76.1) [B]

- *When the Ministers are conducting and interpreting the results of (a) a screening assessment under Section 74, (b) a review of a decision of another jurisdiction under subsection 75(3) that, in their opinion, is based on scientific considerations and is relevant to Canada, or (c) an assessment whether a substance specified on the Priority Substances List is toxic or capable of becoming toxic, the Ministers shall apply a weight of evidence and the precautionary principle.*

After assessment (Section 77) [B]

- *Where the Ministers have conducted (a) a screening assessment under section 74, (b) a review of a decision of another jurisdiction under subsection 75(3) that, in their opinion, is based on scientific considerations and is relevant to Canada, or (c) an assessment whether a substance specified on the Priority Substances List is toxic or capable of becoming toxic, the Minister shall publish ... a statement indicating one of the measures [below] that the Ministers propose to take and a summary of the scientific considerations on the basis of which the measure is proposed.*
 - *Taking no further action in respect of the substance*
 - *Unless the substance is already on the Priority Substances List, adding the substance to the Priority Substances List, or*
 - *recommending that the substance be added to the List of Toxic Substances in Schedule 1 and, where applicable under subsection (4), the implementation of virtual elimination under subsection 65(3)²⁷.*
- *Where, based on a screening assessment conducted under section 74, the substance is determined to be toxic or capable of becoming toxic, and the Ministers are satisfied that [the following situation], the Ministers shall propose to take the measure referred to in paragraph (2)(c).*
 - *(a) the substance may have a long-term harmful effect on the environment and is*
 - *persistent and bioaccumulative in accordance with the regulations, and*
 - *inherently toxic to human beings or non-human organisms, as determined by laboratory or other studies, and*
 - *(b) the presence of the substance in the environment results primarily from human activity,*
 - *recommending that the substance be added to the List of Toxic Substances in Schedule 1 and, where applicable under subsection (4) [PB, the presence in the environment results primarily from human activity, the substance is not a naturally occurring radionuclide or a naturally occurring inorganic substance], the implementation of virtual elimination under subsection 65(3).*
- *Where the Ministers propose to take the measure referred to in paragraph (2)(c) in respect of a substance and the Ministers are satisfied [one of the following situations], the Ministers shall propose the implementation of virtual elimination under subsection 65(3).*
 - *The substance is persistent and bioaccumulative in accordance with the regulations,*
 - *The presence of the substance in the environment results primarily from human activity, and*

²⁷ Section 65(3) when the level of quantification for a substance has been specified on the [Virtual Elimination List], the Ministers shall prescribe the quantity or concentration of the substance that may be released into the environment either alone or in combination with any other substance from any source or type of source, and, in doing so, shall take into account any factor or information provided for in section 91, including, but not limited to, environmental or health risks and any other relevant social, economic or technical matters. [B]

In establishing the quantity or concentration that is measurable in relation to a substance for the purposes of a proposed regulation or instrument referred to in subsection (2) [virtual elimination], the Ministers shall take into consideration information concerning sensitive and readily available analytical methods and any relevant information contained in plans referred to in subsection 79(2) [virtual elimination plan]. [B]

- *The substance is not a naturally occurring radionuclide or a naturally occurring inorganic substance*

Application of Section 84 (after information correction) [B]

- Section 81(13): *Where the Ministers suspect, after considering (a) any corrections received under subsection (11), or (b) the information provided under subsection (12), that a substance is toxic or capable of becoming toxic, the Minister may exercise any of the powers referred to in paragraphs 84(1)(a) to (c).*

Assessment of information (new substance/activity registration) [B]

- Section 83: *The Ministers shall, within the prescribed assessment period, assess information provided ... or otherwise available to them in respect of a substance in order to determine whether it is toxic or capable of becoming toxic*
 - *Where the Ministers are of the opinion that further time is necessary to assess any information, the Minister may, before the expiry of the assessment period, extend the period for assessing the information, but the extension shall not exceed the number of days in the prescribed assessment period*
- The assessment period ranges from 5 to 75 days. [D]

Action to be taken after assessment [B]

- Section 84: *Where the Ministers have assessed any information under section 83 and they suspect that a substance is toxic or capable of becoming toxic, the Minister may, before the expiry of the period for assessing the information*
 - *Permit any person to manufacture or import the substance, subject to any conditions that the Ministers may specify*
 - *Prohibit any person from manufacturing or importing the substance, or*
 - *Request any person to provide any additional information or submit the results of any testing that the Ministers considers necessary for the purpose of assessing whether the substance is toxic or capable of becoming toxic*
 - *The person to whom the request is directed shall not manufacture or import the substance unless (a) the person provides the additional information or submits the test results; and (b) the period for assessing information under section 83 has expired or a period of 90 days after the additional information or test results were provided has expired, whichever is later.*
 - *The Minister may vary or rescind a condition or prohibition specified or imposed.*
 - *Any prohibition on the manufacture or importation of a substance imposed ... expires two years after it is imposed unless, before the expiry of the two years, the Governor in Council publishes ... a notice of proposed regulations under section 93 in respect of the substance, in which case the prohibition expires on the day the regulations come into force.*
- Section 85: *Where the Ministers have assessed any information under section 83 in respect of a substance that is not on the [DSL] and they suspect that a significant new activity in relation to the substance may result in the substance becoming toxic, the Minister may, within 90 days after the expiry of the period for assessing the information, publish ... a notice indicating that subsection 81(4) [notification of significant new activity in respect of substance not on DSL] applies with respect to the substance.*
 - *The Minister may, by notice ... vary the significant new activities in relation to a substance for which a notice has been given under subsection (1) or indicate that subsection 81(4) no longer applies with respect to that substance.*
 - *A notice ... shall indicate, by inclusion or exclusion, the significant new activities in relation to the substance in respect of which subsection 81(4) is to apply, and if regulations in respect of*

those significant new activities are not made under paragraph 89(1)(c), (d) and (g), specify the information to be provided to the Minister under that subsection, the date within which it is to be provided and the period within which it is to be assessed under section 83

Addition to List of Toxic Substances [B]

- Section 90: *The Governor in Council may, if satisfied that a substance is toxic, on the recommendation of the Ministers, make an order adding the substance to the List of Toxic Substances in Schedule 1.*
 - *In developing proposed regulations or instruments respecting preventive or control actions in relation to substances specified on the List of Toxic Substances in Schedule 1, the Ministers shall give priority to pollution prevention actions.*
 - *The Governor in Council may, if satisfied that the inclusion of a substance specified on the List of Toxic Substance in Schedule 1 is no longer necessary, on the recommendation of the Ministers, make an order (a) deleting the substance from the List and deleting the type of regulations specified in the List as being applicable with respect to the substance; and (b) repealing the regulations made under section 93 with respect to the substance*
 - *Where a board of review is established ... no order may be made under subsection (1) or (2) in relation to the substance until the board's report is received by the Ministers.*
- Section 91: *A proposed regulation or instrument respecting preventative or control actions in relation to a substances shall be published by the Minister ... within two years after the publication of the Ministers' statement under paragraph 77(6)(b) indicating that the measure that they propose to take, as confirmed or amended, is a recommendation that the substance be added to the List of Toxic Substance in Schedule 1.*
 - *The Minister shall, where applicable, publish ... a statement accompanying the proposed regulation or instrument for a substance referred to in subsection (2) describing any additional measures that the Ministers intend to recommend with respect to the implementation of virtual elimination under subsection 65(3) and summarizing their reasons for so intending*
 - *In determining the preventive or control actions in relation to a substance and the dates of which those actions are to take effect that are to be set out in a proposed regulation or instrument ... and in determining any additional measures ... the Ministers shall take into consideration any factor or information that, in the opinion of the Ministers, is relevant, including (a) information contained in [virtual elimination plan]; and (b) environmental or health risks identified in the summary published under subsection 77(6) and any other relevant social, economic or technical matters*
- Section 93: *The Governor in Council may, on the recommendation of the Ministers, make regulations with respect to a substance specified on the List of Toxic Substances in Schedule 1, including regulations providing for, or imposing requirements respecting,*
 - *(a) the quantity or concentration of the substance that may be released into the environment either alone or in combination with any other substance from any source or type of source;*
 - *(b) the places or areas where the substance may be released;*
 - *(c) the commercial, manufacturing or processing activity in the course of which the substance may be released;*
 - *(d) the manner in which and conditions under which the substance may be released into the environment, either alone or in combination with any other substance;*
 - *(e) the quantity of the substance that may be manufactured, processed, used, offered for sale or sold in Canada;*
 - *(f) the purposes for which the substance or a product containing it may be imported, manufactured, processed, used, offered for sale or sold;*

- (g) the manner in which and conditions under which the substance or a product containing it may be imported, manufactured, processed or used;
- (h) the quantities or concentrations in which the substance may be used;
- (i) the quantities or concentrations of the substance that may be imported;
- (j) the countries from or to which the substance may be imported or exported;
- (k) the conditions under which, the manner in which and the purposes for which the substance may be imported or exported;
- (l) the total, partial or conditional prohibition of the manufacture, use, processing, sale, offering for sale, import or export of the substance or a product containing it;
- (m) the total, partial or conditional prohibition of the import or export of a product that is intended to contain the substance;
- (n) the quantity or concentration of the substance that may be contained in any product manufactured, imported, exported, offered for sale or sold in Canada;
- (o) the manner in which, conditions under which and the purposes for which the substance or a product containing it may be advertised or offered for sale;
- (p) the manner in which and conditions under which the substance or a product containing it may be stored, displayed, handled, transported or offered for transport;
- (q) the packaging and labelling of the substance or a product containing it;
- (r) the manner, conditions, places and method of disposal of the substance or a product containing it, including standards for the construction, maintenance and inspection of disposal sites;
- (s) the submission to the Minister, on request or at any prescribed times, of information relating to the substance;
- (t) the maintenance of books and records for the administration of any regulation made under this section;
- (u) the conduct of sampling, analyses, tests, measurements or monitoring of the substance and the submission of the results to the Minister;
- (v) the submission of samples of the substance to the Minister;
- (w) the conditions, test procedures and laboratory practices to be followed for conducting sampling, analyses, tests, measurements or monitoring of the substance;
- (x) the circumstances or conditions under which the Minister may, for the proper administration of this Act, modify (i) any requirement for sampling, analyses, tests, measurements or monitoring, or (ii) the conditions, test procedures and laboratory practices for conducting any required sampling, analyses, tests, measurements or monitoring; and
- (y) any other matter that by this Part is to be defined or prescribed or that is necessary to carry out the purposes of this Part.

8. Data submission format

pdf via e-mail, by storage device or via the NSN online form

9. Data confidentiality

Publication of masked name / Scope

- Section 88 [B]: Where the publication under this Part of the explicit chemical or biological name of a substance would result in the release of confidential business information in contravention of section 314, the substance shall be identified by a name determined in the prescribed manner.
 - A notifier may request that the substance they notify be added confidentially to the DSL using a masked name that complies with the Masked Name Regulations. A Third Party Information Supplier who requests that substance information be kept confidential from the notifier may

also request that a substance be added confidentially to the DSL. A substance eligible for addition to the DSL under a masked name will be assigned a Confidential Substance Identity Number even when a [CASRN] is available. [D]

- The NS program conducts a search for all substances that have been notified as confidential to verify whether these substances are on any public chemical inventory, such as the [NDSL], the United States Environmental Protection Agency's (USEPA) Toxic Substances Control Act (TSCA) Chemical Substances Inventory, the Australian Inventory of Chemical Substances (AICS), the Korean Existing Chemicals List (ECL) and the European Inventory of Existing Commercial Substances (EINECS). If the substance is listed on any one of these public inventories, the notifier will be informed of this fact and will be required to provide, within 20 calendar days, further justification for his or her request for confidentiality ... If the supporting documentation is deemed to be inadequate, the notifier will be informed that the NS program intends to publish the appropriate [CASRN] on the DSL. [D]
- Any information submitted to the NS program may be claimed as confidential. In cases where notifier is not given access to information that is considered confidential by a Third Party Information Supplier, the information to support the [new substance notification] must be supplied directly to the NS program by the Third Party Information Supplier. [D]

Exclusions

- Although submitters may claim any information they submit as confidential, certain types of information of value for risk assessment of substances and for other purposes related to the protection of human health and the environment are generally not expected to be confidential. [D]
 - There is consensus within [OECD] member states that no restriction needs to be put on the exchange of information described below between governments or on the disclosure of such information to the public.²⁸
 - Trade name(s) or name(s) commonly used;
 - General information about uses (the uses need to be described only broadly: closed or open system, agriculture, domestic use, etc.)
 - Safe handling precautions to be observed in the manufacture, storage, transport and use of the substance;
 - Recommended methods for disposal and elimination;
 - Safety measures in case of an accident;
 - Physical and chemical information, with the exception of data revealing the substance identity (e.g., spectra). If the physical and chemical information make it possible to deduce the substance identity, non-confidential ranges of values can be identified; and
 - Summaries of health, safety, and environmental data including precise figures and interpretations. In cases where the study is claimed confidential, the submitter of the health, safety, and environmental study has the option of preparing a non-confidential summary.

Exceptions

- Subsection 315(1) of the Act states that the Minister of the Environment (the Minister) may, however, disclose information where
 - The disclosure is in the interest of public health, public safety or the protection of the environment; and

²⁸ Recommendation of the Council concerning the OECD List of Non-Confidential Data on Chemicals 26 July 1983 - C(83)98/FINAL. <https://legalinstruments.oecd.org/en/instruments/32>

- *The public interest in the disclosure clearly outweighs in importance:*
 - *Any material financial loss or prejudice to the competitive position of the person who provided the information or on whose behalf it was provided, and*
 - *Any damage to the privacy, reputation or human dignity of any individual that may result from the disclosure [D]*
- *Under Section 316 of the Act, information may be disclosed*
 - *With the written consent of the person who provided it or on whose behalf it was provided*
 - *As may be necessary for the purposes of the administration or enforcement of [CEPA]*
 - *Under an agreement or arrangement between the Government of Canada or any of its institutions and any other government in Canada, the government of a foreign state or an international organization or any of its institutions, or between the Minister and any other minister of the Crown in right of Canada, where*
 - *The purpose of the agreement or arrangement is the administration or enforcement of a law, and*
 - *The government, international organization, institution or other minister undertakes to keep the information confidential*
 - *Under an agreement under an agreement or arrangement between the Government of Canada and the government of a foreign state or an international organization, where the government or organization undertakes to keep the information confidential; or*
 - *to a physician or prescribed medical professional who requests the information for the purpose of making a medical diagnosis of, or rendering medical treatment to, a person in an emergency*

Renewal

- *Confidentiality claims for substance identity will be reviewed after a period of 10 years. A minimum of 30 days' notice before the expiry date will be provided to the notifier to update their claim if they wish the substance identity to remain confidential for an additional period of 10 years.*

10. Data that are published publicly

- **DSL:** CASRN (or enzyme commission numbers for biochemicals that are enzymes), substance name, additional information, recent publications, date published

11. International information exchange and sharing

- *Section 75: The Minister shall, to the extent possible, cooperate and develop procedures with jurisdictions, other than the Government of Canada, to exchange information respecting substances that are specifically prohibited or substantially restricted by or under the legislation of those jurisdictions for environmental or health reasons. [B]*
 - *Where the Minister is notified in accordance with procedures developed under subsection (2) of a decision to specifically prohibit or substantially restrict any substance by or under the legislation of another jurisdiction for environmental or health reasons, the Ministers shall review the decision in order to determine whether the substance is toxic or capable of becoming toxic, unless the decision relates to a substance the only use of which in Canada is regulated under another Act of Parliament that provides for environmental and health protection.*
- Information sharing with the US EPA, ECHA and AICIS [D]

S1.3 Regulation on Classification, Labeling and Notification of Hazardous Chemicals and Mixtures, Chile

Last update: 11 November 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Decreto 57 (09 Feb, 2021): <https://www.bcn.cl/leychile/navegar?idNorma=1155752>
- B. Resolution 777 of August 23, 2021: <https://www.bcn.cl/leychile/navegar?idNorma=1164063>
- C. Official List of Substance Classification: <https://dipol.minsal.cl/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/Lista-de-sustancias-clasificadas-Chile-05072021.pdf>

Note: The texts below are based on informal translation using Google Translate.

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory²⁹

- Distinction between new vs. existing chemicals: once the notification has been made, the Ministry of the Environment will issue a Resolution with all the notified substances, until December 31 of that same year. Substances that are not contemplated in said resolution will be considered “new substances”.
- Pool for risk assessment

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligations

- Article 6: The Ministry of Health will approve, by resolution, an official list of classification of substances, hereinafter “the List” [C], which will contain their classes and categories of hazard. Said list will be reviewed at least every two years, which must be recorded ... When manufacturers or importers wish to apply other less restrictive classifications to those indicated in the List, they must present prior to commercialization, the technical background, tests and/or trials, in accordance with the methodologies referred to in this regulation, before the Ministry of Health, who will evaluate and pronounce on the matter, within a period not exceeding 90 business days. Said tests must be carried out by laboratories certified under the ISO 17025 standard that establishes the general requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories.
 - In the event that the manufacturer or importer applies more restrictive or additional classes or categories to those indicated in the List, the pronouncement of the Ministry of Health will not be necessary, without prejudice to the control powers of the Health Authority.
 - Article 7: In the event that the substances are not on the List, manufacturers or importers must evaluate whether the substance or mixture carries any physical, health or environmental hazard.³⁰

²⁹ Polymer = a substance consisting of molecules characterized by the sequence of one or more types of monomeric units and comprising a simple weight majority of molecules containing at least three monomeric units that are covalently linked to at least one other monomeric unit or other reagent and consists of less than a simple majority by weight of molecules of the same molecular weight. Such molecules must be distributed over a range of molecular weights where the differences in molecular weight are primarily attributable to differences in the number of monomer units. In the context of this definition, a "monomeric unit" means the reacted form of a monomer in a polymer.

³⁰ Information to be considered: 1) existing data from the application of trials or tests with internationally validated methods; b) epidemiological data and experience on the effects on humans, such as employment data, data from accident databases, historical data on humans from epidemiological studies in exposed populations, and clinical studies that meet the criteria corresponding to the different classes and dangers; c) information generated within the framework of internationally recognized chemical programs; d) information from the scientific literature; e) new data generated from the application of trials or tests with internationally validated methods (provided all other means of generating information have been exhausted).

- Article 291: Every manufacturer or importer of a substance as such and every importer of a substance contained in a mixture, hereinafter the notifier, that classifies as hazardous according to Title III of this regulation,³¹ in quantities equal to or greater than 1 metric ton annually, must notify in the system. In the case of substances contained in mixtures, only those that represent a hazard to health and the environment, and whose concentrations are higher than the cut-off values reported in paragraph II of Title II³², should be notified.³³
- Article 296: New substances must be notified prior to their commercialization, importation or manufacture. In the case of importation of new substances, the Health Authority will grant the respective import authorization only if the notification process of those has been previously verified.

3.2 Exemptions

The following are excluded from the application of these regulations [A]

- Nuclear substances (defined in Law No. 18, 302, on nuclear safety)
- Pharmaceutical products (defined in the Health Code), except for the raw materials used for their manufacture or preparation
- Pharmaceutical products for veterinary use (defined in Supreme Decree No.25, of 2005, of the Ministry of Agriculture, which approves regulations for pharmaceutical products for exclusively veterinary use), with the exception of additives and raw materials used for their manufacture or preparation
- Food products for human consumption (regulated in the Sanitary Code and in Supreme Decree No. 977, of 1996, of the Ministry of Health, which approves the Sanitary Regulation of Food), except for food additives and raw materials used for the manufacture or preparation of food products
- Food products for animal consumption (defined in Supreme Decree No. 4, of 2016, of the Ministry of Agriculture, which approves the Animal Feed Regulations), with the exception of additives and raw materials used for their manufacture or preparation

In the new data generated, they must consider the application of tests according to internationally validated methods, preferably according to the guidelines of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). In evaluating the information available for classification purposes, the manufacturer or importer of substances or mixtures must consider the forms or physical states in which they are marketed or used.

When tests are carried out to determine the hazardous characteristics of substances and mixtures, and there are no other alternatives that offer sufficient reliability and quality of the data, animal experimentation may be used, under the conditions established in Law No. 20,380 of the Ministry of Health on animal protection.

Where there are no data from trials or tests on mixtures, available information on similar substances and mixtures tested that may be considered relevant may be used, in accordance with the extrapolation principles, as appropriate, to determine if the mixture is hazardous. [A]

³¹ Overall, the decree tends to follow GHS rev. 6, but does contain references to other revisions of the GHS.

³² The cut-off values are those thresholds from which the presence of a substance in a mixture or in another substance, when found as an impurity, additive or individual component, must be considered to classify the substance or mixture as hazardous. Generic concentration limits are those that are assigned to a substance to indicate the threshold from which the presence of this substance in a mixture (or in another substance) when found as an impurity, additive or individual component, makes the substance or mixture classified as hazardous. Specific concentration limits: acute toxicity (≥ 1.0 wt%), corrosion/skin irritation (≥ 1.0 wt%), serious eye damage/irritation of the eyes (≥ 1.0 wt%), respiratory/cutaneous sensitization (≥ 0.1 wt%), germ cell mutagenicity: category 1 (≥ 0.1 wt%), germ cell mutagenicity: category 2 (≥ 1.0 wt%), carcinogenicity (≥ 0.1 wt%), reproductive toxicity (≥ 0.1 wt%), specific target organ toxicity (single exposure/repeated exposure) (≥ 1.0 wt%), aspiration hazard: category 1&2 (≥ 1.0 wt%), toxicity to the aquatic environment (≥ 1.0 wt%)

³³ For substances and mixtures for industrial use, this regulation will take effect one and four years, respectively, after its publication in the Official Gazette. For substances and mixtures of non-industrial use, this regulation will take effect two and six years, respectively, after its publication in the Official Gazette. The process of notification of substances and substances contained in mixtures will take effect after two years from the effective date indicated in the preceding articles.

- Cosmetic products (defined in Supreme Decree No. 239, of 2002, of the Ministry of Health, which approves the Regulations of the National Cosmetics Control System)
- Pesticide residues in food (defined in Exempt Resolution No. 762 of 2011 of the Ministry of Health, which sets maximum tolerances for pesticide residues in food)
- Hazardous waste (defined in Supreme Decree No. 148, of 2003, of the Ministry of Health, which approves Sanitary Regulations on Hazardous Waste Management)
- Articles containing hazardous chemicals or mixtures, except for explosive articles, in accordance with what is defined in Title III of this regulation
- Substances and mixtures subject to customs supervision, in accordance with the relevant regulations, provided that they are not subject to any type of treatment or transformation, and that they are kept in temporary storage for the purpose of being exported or in transit
- Substances and mixtures intended for scientific research and development, not marketed, provided they are used under controlled conditions in accordance with current regulations
- Non-isolated intermediate substances, in accordance with what is established in this regulation
- Medical devices (defined in Supreme Decree No. 825, of 1998, of the Ministry of Health, which approves regulations for the control of products and items for medical use)
- Minerals of natural origin, whose composition has not undergone chemical modifications, extracted mechanically and which are transported directly to where they will be processed, provided that their extraction does not exceed 5,000 dry metric tons of mineral per month
- Fertilizers regulated by Decree Law No. 3,557, of 1981, issued by the Ministry of Agriculture.

Exemptions from notification and risk assessment

- New substances used as explosives or as an active ingredient for pesticides for agricultural use and for sanitary and domestic use

4. Initial data requirements

Notification

- Identity of the notifier, including the address of the manufacturing premises, in the case of manufacturers
- Identity of the substance(s): must be sufficient to be able to identify it
 - IUPAC name or other internationally recognized chemical name or names
 - Other names (common name, trade name, abbreviation)
 - CASRN
 - The hazard classification of the substance, indicating the class and category of hazard
 - Quantity of the substance manufactured or imported per year, expressed in mass ranges
 - Intended uses. In the case of substances contained in mixtures, the corresponding use of the mixture must be indicated
 - Attach the substance safety data sheet in case of substances as such
- The first notification must be made in 2024 (third year from the date of publication of this regulation) for substances for industrial use and in 2025 (fourth year) for substances for non-industrial use

New Substance Notification

- The quantity to be notified will be determined according to the projections of what will be manufactured or imported in a period of one year
- Additionally, and when appropriate, the following minimum information must be provided: acute oral toxicity, acute dermal toxicity, dermal corrosivity, ocular corrosivity and acute ecotoxicity.

5. Data updates by companies

Classification

- Article 15: The manufacturer or importer must be aware of the new scientific or technical information that may affect the classification of substances or mixtures, so that when the information is available and is considered adequate and reliable ... must carry out a new evaluation in accordance with these regulations.
- Article 16: When the manufacturer or importer introduces a change in the composition of a substance or mixture, he must carry out a new classification evaluation and adapt the classification to the results of the new evaluation, when the changes involves: modification in the composition of the initial concentration of one or more of the hazardous components; modification in the composition that entails the substitution or addition of one or more components, in concentrations equal to or greater than the cut-off values or generic or specific concentration limits as appropriate.

Notification

- Article 294: The notification must be made every two years, with a deadline until August 30, with respect to what is manufactured and/or imported in the previous two calendar years.

New substance notification

- Article 297: Once the first notification has been made, new substances must continue with their notification process every two years, as established in the first paragraph of Article 24.

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators**Classification**

- Article 14: The Sanitary or Environmental Authority may request from manufacturers or importers the information used to determine the classification of the hazards of substances or mixtures, in accordance with this regulation.

Notification and new substance notification

- Once the information has been received in the notification platform, the Ministry of the Environment may require additional or clarifying information.

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

- Article 299: The Ministry of Health and the Ministry of the Environment, based on the information collected via notification, will select some substances of interest with respect to which they will request a risk assessment from their manufacturers and importers.
- Article 300: The Ministry of Health, within a period of 18 months from the publication of this regulation (August 2022), will issue, jointly with the Ministry of the Environment, a resolution that determines the modalities and technical criteria of the risk assessment, as well as the criteria for defining the substances of interest that must be subjected to the risk assessment process.

8. Data submission format

- Article 292: Manufacturers and importers subject to the substance notification process, must do so in the Substance Notification System (notification platform), through the portal of the single window of the Environmental Authority.

9. Data confidentiality**Notification and new substance notification**

- Article 298: The treatment of the information provided by virtue of this Title will be governed by the rules contained in Law No. 20,285 on access to public information.

10. Data that are published publicly

Notification and new substance notification

- Once the notification has been made, the Ministry of the Environment will issue a Resolution with all the notified substances, until December 31 of that same year.

Official list for the classification of substances [B]

- Chemical name: they are mostly designated by their IUPAC name, in some cases by their ISO name or common name. Some entries in the list refer to groups of substances. In these cases, the classification and labelling requirements will apply to all substances covered by the description. In some cases, an individual substance may be covered by more than one collective entry; in such cases, the classification of the substance reflects the classification of the two collective entries. If different classifications are given for the same hazard, the most severe hazard classification will apply. For salts (under any denomination) they cover the anhydrous and hydrated forms, unless otherwise stated.
- CAS number
- Classification, class codes and hazard category: the classification for each substance is based on the classification criteria established in Title III, on the characteristics and hazard criteria for the classification of substances and mixtures of DS 57/19. These codes and categories are presented in abbreviated form and are defined in Table No.1
- Classification, hazard indication codes: these codes are indicated as established in paragraph III, of the warning phrases and hazard indications, of Title IV, of the safety labelling of substances and mixtures, of DS 57/2019. In some cases, a letter has been added to make complementary distinctions. These additional codes are presented in Table No. 2
- Specific concentration limits, M factors and ETA
 - The specific concentration limits – LCE – are indicated for some substances and must be used as indicated in paragraph III, of the cut-off values or concentration limits for the classification of substances and mixtures, of Title II, of the classification of dangers of DS 57/19
 - The harmonized ETAs are also indicated. The manufacturer, importer or downstream user must use the LCEs and harmonized ETAs for the classification of mixtures containing this substance
 - The M factors that have been harmonized are also indicated. If not on the list, use those indicated in Table 49 of DS 57/2019 or the one indicated by the manufacturer based on the available data of the substance

11. International information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.4 Regulation to the organic code of the environment, Ecuador

Last update: 12 October 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Reglamento al código orgánico del ambiente (Decreto Ejecutivo 752, Registro Oficial Suplemento 507 de 12-jun.2019; in Spanish)³⁴ <https://www.ambiente.gob.ec/wp-content/uploads/downloads/2021/06/REGLAMENTO-AL-CODIGO-ORGANICO-DEL-AMBIENTE.pdf>

Note: The texts below are based on informal translation using DeepL.

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

- Article 522: The National Environmental Authority shall carry out the national inventory of chemical substances in coordination with the competent authorities. Based on the inventory information, the list of chemical substances imported, manufactured, or produced and marketed in the national territory will be published and updated.
- Article 527: The registration of chemical substances is the environmental administrative authorization that enables the operator to carry out the management phases³⁵ of chemical substances and allows the National Environmental Authority to regulate and control the traceability of such substances.

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligations

- Article 527: Natural or legal persons involved in any of the phases of the management of chemical substances must obtain the Registration of Chemical Substances of those substances determined by the National Environmental Authority.
- Article 528: Chemical substances that are not in the national list of chemical substances and that due to their characteristics represent a risk to health or the environment shall be reported to the National Environment Authority under the procedures established by the same.

3.2 Exemptions³⁶

- Article 527: Operators who obtain other administrative authorizations equivalent to the Registration of Chemical Substances, issued by competent authorities, shall not be required to obtain this Registration before the National Environmental Authority.

4. Initial data requirements

- General information about the applicant
- Chemical information

³⁴ The National Environmental Authority shall issue the secondary regulations and other instruments of public policy and planning necessary for the enforcement of the Organic Code of the Environment and the present Regulation, according to the prioritization made for such purpose. Until said regulations are issued, for all processes, administration authorizations and other procedures in charge of the Competent Environment Authorities, the environmental regulations in force shall apply in all that does not contradict the Organic Code of the Environment.

³⁵ Supply, including import, manufacture or production and formulation; storage; transport; use; and export

³⁶ Article 538: The National Environmental Authority shall establish the requirements and mechanisms to authorize the importation or introduction of reference materials, analytical standards, products for instrument calibration and interlaboratory test materials containing chemical substances whose use has been prohibited, for their use in laboratories for accreditation, research, quality control or service rendering purposes

- Management phase(s) in which the applicant is involved
- Environmental administrative authorization
- Others determined by the National Environmental Authority

5. Data updates by companies

- Article 530: Once the registration of chemical substances has been obtained, the operator shall comply with the following obligations³⁷
 - Declare monthly the movements of chemical substances according to the format, mechanisms, tools, procedures and guidelines determined by the National Environmental Authority
 - Present the program for the integrated management of chemical waste, within the framework of the extended producer responsibility, as applicable, under procedures and guidelines established by the National Environmental Authority
 - The National Environmental Authority may establish exemptions to the registration obligations
- Article 532: The updating of the registration of chemical substances shall be carried out in the following circumstances
 - Changes in general information of the applicant or responsible personnel
 - Aggregation or elimination of a chemical management phase
 - Expansion of quota allocated for the approved management phase(s)
 - Addition or removal of chemicals,
 - Addition, modification or elimination of chemical use
- Article 55:4: The operators of use must make a monthly declaration of the chemicals used according to the format, mechanisms, tools, procedures and guidelines established by the National Environment Authority under secondary regulations. Domestic use is excluded from this chapter. The National Environmental Authority shall establish policies and regulations exclusively for the environmentally sound management of chemicals for such uses

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

N.A.

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

- Article 529: The National Environmental Authority, in coordination with the competent authorities on health, occupational risk and industries, will evaluate the information submitted by the applicants regarding the identification of hazards and risk assessment of each chemical substance, in order to verify the risk to human health or the environment.
- Article 533: The National Environmental Authority may suspend the Registration of Chemical Substances
 - In order to lift the suspension, the operator shall submit to the National Environmental Authority a report of the activity carried out with the evidence showing that the non-compliances have been remedied, without prejudice to the other requirements established in the applicable regulations. The factual statements made in the report shall be subject to inspection, analysis and approval, if applicable, to lift the suspension.

³⁷ Other obligations include: respect the allocated quota and type of use approved in each phase of registration management; apply the risk prevention measures for manifestation of hazards in the chemical safety data sheets of each substance, mixture or product; conduct the transfer of chemicals with persons who hold the chemical registration; maintain in force the environmental administrative authorization; and, comply with the obligations established in the Register of Chemical Substances

- Article 534: The National Environmental Authority may revoke the Registration of Chemical Substances, in case the Registration of Chemical Substances has been suspended for more than two occasions. The revocation of the Registration of Chemical Substances shall cause the suspension of the activities of the project, work or regulated activity, if so determined in the corresponding administrative resolution
- Article 535: The National Environmental Authority may extinguish the Register of Chemical Substances ex officio or at the request of the operator, after a duly motivated report. The extinction will proceed in case of definitive closure of the activity or relocation of the establishment according to the corresponding technical standard. Prior to the termination of the registration, the operator must safely transfer or eliminate the stock of the remaining substance(s) that were available before the definitive closure.

8. Data submission format

- Such registration shall be obtained through the Unified Environmental Information System.

9. Data confidentiality

N.A.

10. Data that are published publicly

N.A.

11. International information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.5 REACH Registration, European Union

Last update: 1 November 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Consolidated version of the REACH Regulation (latest update: 15.02.2021):
<https://echa.europa.eu/regulations/reach/legislation>; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:02006R1907-20210215>
- B. Commission implementing regulation (EU) 2020/1435 of 9 October 2020 on the duties placed on registrants to update their registrations: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32020R1435>
- C. Commission implementing regulation (EU) 2019/1692 of 9 October 2019 on the application of certain registration and data-sharing provisions of Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council after the expiry of the final registration deadline for phase-in substances: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32019R1692>
- D. Commission implementing regulation (EU) 2016/9 of 5 January 2016 on joint submission of data and data-sharing in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0009&qid=1453380621080&from=EN>
- E. Commission regulation (EC) No 440/2008 of 30 May 2008 laying down test methods pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 ... (latest update: 18.05.2017): <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02008R0440-20170518&from=EN>
- F. Guidance on REACH: <https://echa.europa.eu/guidance-documents/guidance-on-reach>
- G. Information on Chemicals, including registered substances, dossier evaluation status, testing proposal public consultation, substance evaluation – CoRAP list, registry of SVHC intentions until outcome, candidate list of SVHC for authorisation, authorisation list, register of downstream user notifications of authorised uses, registry of restriction intentions until outcome, restriction list:
<https://echa.europa.eu/information-on-chemicals>

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

- ECHA is publishing information included in the registration dossiers on its website.

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligations [A]

- Article 1: *This Regulation lays down provisions on substances and mixtures within the meaning of Article 3. These provisions shall apply to the manufacture, placing on the market or use of such substances on their own, in mixtures or in articles and to the placing on the market of mixtures.*

General registration³⁸

³⁸ *Guidance on registration, version 4.0, August 2021*, including registration obligations, the sharing of data, the registration process, preparation of the registration dossier, duty of communication in the supply chain, when and how to update a registration, when is a registration no longer valid, appeal procedures, fees, duties of ECHA: https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/registration_en.pdf/de54853d-e19e-4528-9b34-8680944372f2?t=1629205524601

Guidance on requirements for substances in articles, Version 4.0, June 2017, including deciding what is an article under REACH, requirements for candidate list substances in articles, requirements for substances intended to be released from articles, obtaining information on substances in articles:
https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/articles_en.pdf

- Article 5: *Subject to Articles 6, 7, 21 and 23, substances on their own, in mixtures or in articles shall not be manufactured in the Community or placed on the market unless they have been registered ...*
 - Article 6(1): *Save there this Regulation provides otherwise, any manufacturer or importer of a substance, either on its own or in one or more mixture(s), in quantities of one tonne or more per year shall submit a registration ...*
 - Article 6(2): *For monomers that are used as on-site isolated intermediates or transported isolated intermediates, Articles 17 [registration of on-site isolated intermediates] and 18 [registration of transported isolated intermediates] shall not apply.*
 - Article 6(3): *Any manufacturer or importer of a polymer shall submit a registration ... for the monomer substance(s) or any other substance(s), that have not already been registered by an actor up the supply chain, if both the following conditions are met: (a) the polymer consists of 2% weight by weight (w/w) or more of such monomer substance(s) or other substance(s) in the form of monomeric units and chemically bound substance(s), and (b) the total quantity of such monomer substance(s) or other substance(s) makes up one tonne or more per year.*
 - Article 7(1): *Any producer or importer of articles shall submit a registration ... for any substance contained in those articles, if both the following conditions are met: (a) the substance is present in those articles in quantities totalling over one tonne per producer or importer per year; and (b) the substance is intended to be released under normal or reasonably foreseeable conditions of use.*
 - Article 7(5): *The Agency may take decisions requiring producers or importers of articles to submit a registration ... for any substance in those articles, if all the following conditions are met: (a) the substance is present in those articles in quantities totalling over one tonne per producer or importer per year; (b) the Agency has grounds for suspecting that (i) the substance is released from the articles, and (ii) the release of the substance from the articles presents a risk to human health or the environment*

Notification of substances of very high concern (SVHC) in articles

- Article 7(2): *Any producer or importer of articles shall notify ... if a substance meets the criteria in Article 57 and is identified in accordance with Article 59(1), if both the following conditions are met: (a) the substance is present in those articles in quantities totalling over one tonne per producer or importer per year and (b) the substance is present in those articles above a concentration of 0.1% weight by weight (w/w).*
 - ... shall apply six months after is identified in accordance with Article 59(1).

Registration of on-site isolated intermediates

- Article 17(1): *Any manufacturer of an on-site isolated intermediate in quantities of one tonne or more per year shall submit a registration to the Agency for the on-site isolated intermediate.*

Registration of transported isolated intermediates

- Article 18(1): *Any manufacturer or importer of a transported isolated intermediate in quantities of one tonne or more per year shall submit a registration to the Agency for the transported isolated intermediate.*

Obligation for downstream users to report information

- Article 38(1): *Before commencing or continuing with a particular use of a substance that has been registered by an actor up the supply chain in accordance with Articles 6 or 18, the downstream user shall report to the Agency ... in the following cases:*
 - *The downstream user has to prepare a chemical safety report*

- Article 37(4): ... for any use outside the conditions described in an exposure scenario or if appropriate a use and exposure category communicated to him in a safety data sheet or for any use his supplier advises against
- A downstream user need not to prepare such a chemical safety report ...
 - a safety data sheet is not required to be communicated with the substance or mixture in accordance with Article 31
 - a chemical safety report is not required to be completed by his supplier in accordance with Article 14
 - the downstream user uses the substance or mixture in a total quantity of less than one tonne per year
 - the downstream user implements or recommends an exposure scenario which includes as a minimum the conditions described in the exposure scenario communicated to him in the safety data sheet;
 - the substance is present in a mixture in a concentration lower than any of the concentrations set out in Article 14(2);
 - the downstream user is using the substance for the purposes of product and process oriented research and development, provided that the risks to human health and the environment are adequately controlled in accordance with the requirements of legislation for the protection of workers and the environment.
- The downstream user is relying on the exemptions in Article 37(4)(c) or (f)
 - the downstream user uses the substance or mixture in a total quantity of less than one tonne per year
 - the downstream user is using the substance for the purposes of product and process oriented research and development, provided that the risks to human health and the environment are adequately controlled in accordance with the requirements of legislation for the protection of workers and the environment.
- Except where a downstream user is relying on the exemption in Article 37(4)(c), reporting ... shall not be required in respect of a substance, on its own or in a mixture, used by the downstream user in quantities of less than one tonne per year for that particular use.

Authorisation (Article 56)

- A manufacturer, importer or downstream user shall not place a substance on the market for a use or use it himself if that substance is included in Annex XIV, unless
 - The use(s) of that substance on its own or in a mixture or the incorporation of the substance into an article for which the substance is placed on the market or for which he uses the substance himself has been authorised in accordance with Articles 60 to 64
 - The use(s) of that substance on its own or in a mixture or the incorporation of the substance into an article for which the substance is placed on the market or for which he uses the substance himself has been exempted from the authorisation requirement in Annex XIV itself in accordance with Article 58(2)
 - The date referred to in Article 58(1)(c)(i) has not been reached
 - The date referred to in Article 58(1)(c)(i) has been reached and he made an application 18 months before that date but a decision on the application for authorisation has not yet been taken, or
 - In cases where the substance is placed on the market, authorisation for that use has been granted to his immediate downstream user.
- A downstream user may use a substance meeting the criteria [above] provided that the use is in accordance with the conditions of an authorisation granted to an actor up his supply chain for that use

Restrictions (Article 67)

- *A substance on its own, in a mixture or in an article, for which Annex XVII contains a restriction shall not be manufactured, placed on the market or used unless it complies with the conditions of that restriction.*

3.2 Exemptions [A]**General exemptions**

- Article 2(1): *This Regulation shall not apply to*
 - *Radioactive substances within the scope of Council Directive 96/29/Euratom of 13 May 1996 ...*
 - *Substances, on their own, in a mixture or in an article, which are subject to customs supervision, provided that they do not undergo any treatment or processing, and which are in temporary storage, or in a free zone or free warehouse with a view to re-exportation, or in transit*
 - *Non-isolated intermediates*
 - *The carriage of dangerous substances and dangerous substances in dangerous mixtures by rail, road, inland waterway, sea or air*
- Article 2(2): *Waste as defined in Directive 2006/12/EC ... is not a substance, mixture or article within the meaning of Article 3 of this Regulation.*
- Article 2(3): *Member States may allow for exemptions from this Regulation in specific cases for certain substances, on their own, in a mixture or in an article, where necessary in the interests of defense*
- Article 2(5): *The provisions of Titles II [registration of substances], V [downstream users], VI [evaluation] and VII [authorisation] shall not apply to the extent that a substance is used*
 - *In medicinal products for human or veterinary use within the scope of Regulation (EC) No 726/2004, Directive 2001/82/EC... and Directive 2001/83/EC*
 - *In food or feeding stuffs in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 including use:*
 - *As a food additive in foodstuffs within the scope of Council Directive 89/107/EEC ...*
 - *As a flavouring in foodstuffs within the scope of Council Directive 88/388/EEC ... and Commission Decision 1999/217/EC ...*
 - *As an additive in feeding stuffs within the scope of Regulation (EC) No 1832/2003 ...*
 - *In animal nutrition within the scope of Council Directive 82/471/EEC*
- Article 2(7): *The following shall be exempted from Titles II [registration of substances], V [downstream users], VI [evaluation]:*
 - *Substances included in Annex IV,³⁹ as sufficient information is known about these substances that they are considered to cause minimum risk because of their intrinsic properties*
 - *Substances covered by Annex V,⁴⁰ as registration is deemed inappropriate or unnecessary for these substances and their exemption from these Titles does not prejudice the objectives of this Regulation*

³⁹ D-glucitol; ascorbic acid; glucose; fructose; L-lysine; sucrose; α -tocopheryl acetate; galactose; DL-methionine; lactose; D-mannitol; L-sorbose; glycerol stearate; carbon dioxide; D-form calcium pantothenate; DL-phenylalanine; sodium gluconate; sorbitan oleate; krypton; neon; argon; helium; xenon; nitrogen; water; lecithins; syrups, hydrolyzed starch; tallow, hydrogenated; dextrin; starch; maltodextrin; sodium D-gluconate; D-glucitol monostearate; fatty acids, coco, Me esters; cellulose pulp; glycerides, C₁₆₋₁₈ and C₁₈-unsaturated; syrups, corn, dehydrated; glycerides, tallow mono-, di- and tri-, hydrogenated; glycerides, C₁₆₋₁₈ and C₁₈-unsaturated, mono- and di-; glycerides, C₁₀₋₁₈ [A]

⁴⁰ *Guidance for Annex V Exemptions from the obligation to register, Version 1.1, November 2012:*

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/annex_v_en.pdf/8db56598-f7b7-41ba-91df-c55f9f626545

- *Substances which result from a chemical reaction that occurs incidental to exposure of another substance or article to environmental factors such as air, moisture, microbial organisms or sunlight.*
- *Substances which result from a chemical reaction that occurs incidental to storage of another substance, mixture or article.*
- *Substances which result from a chemical reaction occurring upon end use of other substances, mixtures or articles and which are not themselves manufactured, imported or placed on the market.*
- *Substances which are not themselves manufactured, imported or placed on the market and which result from a chemical reaction that occurs when: (a) a stabiliser, colorant, flavouring agent, antioxidant, filler, solvent, carrier, surfactant, plasticiser, corrosion inhibitor, antifoamer or defoamer, dispersant, precipitation inhibitor, desiccant, binder, emulsifier, de-emulsifier, dewatering agent, agglomerating agent, adhesion promoter, flow modifier, pH neutraliser, sequesterant, coagulant, flocculant, fire retardant, lubricant, chelating agent, or quality control reagent functions as intended; or (b) a substance solely intended to provide a specific physicochemical characteristic functions as intended.*
- *By-products, unless they are imported or placed on the market themselves.*
- *Hydrates of a substance or hydrated ions, formed by association of a substance with water, provided that the substance has been registered by the manufacturer or importer using this exemption.*
- *The following substances which occur in nature, if they are not chemically modified: Minerals, ores, ore concentrates, raw and processed natural gas, crude oil, coal.*
- *Substances which occur in nature other than those listed under paragraph 7, if they are not chemically modified, unless they meet the criteria for classification as dangerous according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 or unless they are persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic or very persistent and very bioaccumulative in accordance with the criteria set out in Annex XIII or unless they were identified in accordance with Article 59(1) at least two years previously as substances giving rise to an equivalent level of concern as set out in Article 57(f).*
- *The following substances obtained from natural sources, if they are not chemically modified, unless they meet the criteria for classification as dangerous according to Directive 67/548/EEC with the exception of those only classified as flammable [R10], as a skin irritant [R38] or as an eye irritant [R36] or unless they are persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic or very persistent and very bioaccumulative in accordance with the criteria set out in Annex XIII or unless they were identified in accordance with Article 59(1) at least two years previously as substances giving rise to an equivalent level of concern as set out in Article 57(f):*
- *Vegetable fats, vegetable oils, vegetable waxes; animal fats, animal oils, animal waxes; fatty acids from C₆ to C₂₄ and their potassium, sodium, calcium and magnesium salts; glycerol.*
- *The following substances if they are not chemically modified: Liquefied petroleum gas, natural gas condensate, process gases and components thereof, coke, cement clinker, magnesia.*
- *The following substances unless they meet the criteria for classification as dangerous according to Directive 67/548/EEC and provided that they do not contain constituents meeting the criteria as dangerous in accordance with Directive 67/548/EEC present in concentrations above the lowest of the applicable concentration limits set out in*

- Directive 1999/45/EC or concentration limits set out in Annex I to Directive 67/548/EEC, unless conclusive scientific experimental data show that these constituents are not available throughout the lifecycle of the substance and those data have been ascertained to be adequate and reliable: Glass, ceramic frits.*
- *Compost, biogas and digestate.*
 - *Hydrogen and oxygen.*
 - *Substances on their own or in mixtures, registered in accordance with Title II, exported from the Community by an actor in the supply chain and re-imported into the Community by the same or another actor in the same supply chain who shows that*
 - *The substance being re-imported is the same as the exported substance*
 - *He has been provided with the information in accordance with Articles 31 [requirements for safety data sheets] or 32 [duty to communicate information down the supply chain for substances on their own in mixtures for which a safety data sheet is not required] relating to the exported substance*
 - *Substances, on their own, in mixtures or in articles, which have been registered in accordance with Title II and which are recovered⁴¹ in the Community if*
 - *The substance that results from the recovery process is the same as the substance that has been registered in accordance with Title II; and*
 - *The information required by Articles 31 or 32 relating to the substance that has been registered in accordance with Title II is available to the establishment undertaking the recovery.*
 - *Article 2(8): On-site isolated intermediates and transported isolated intermediates⁴² shall be exempted from*
 - *Chapter 1 of Title II [general obligation to register and information requirements], with the exception of Articles 8 [only representative of a non-community manufacturer]⁴³ and 9 [exemption from the general obligation to register for product and process orientated research and development (PPORD)]; and*
 - *Title VII [authorisation]*
 - *Article 2(9): The provisions of Titles II [registration of substances] and VI [evaluation] shall not apply to polymers⁴⁴.*

⁴¹ *Guidance on waste and recovered substances, Version 2, May 2010, including requirements for recovered substances under REACH:*

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/waste_recovered_en.pdf/657a2803-710c-472b-8922-f5c94642f836

⁴² *Guidance on intermediates, Version 2, December 2010, including registration of definition, tasks and obligations, isolated intermediates:*

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/intermediates_en.pdf/0386199a-bdc5-4bbc-9548-0d27ac222641

⁴³ *A natural or legal person established outside the Community who manufactures a substance on its own, in mixtures or in articles, formulates a mixture or produces an article that is imported into the Community may by mutual agreement appoint a natural or legal person established in the Community to fulfil, as his only representative, the obligations on importers under this Title. [A]*

⁴⁴ *A substance consisting of molecules characterised by the sequence of one or more types of monomer units. Such molecules must be distributed over a range of molecular weights wherein differences in the molecular weight are primarily attributable to differences in the number of monomer units. A polymer comprises the following: (a) a simple weight majority of molecules containing at least three monomer units which are covalently bound to at least one other monomer unit or other reactant; (b) less than a simple weight majority of molecules of the same molecular weight. [A]*

Substances regarded as being registered⁴⁵

- Article 15(1): *Active substances and co-formulants manufactured or imported for use in plant protection products only and included either in Annex I to Council Directive 91/414/EEC (15) or in Commission Regulation (EEC) No 3600/92 (16), Commission Regulation (EC) No 703/2001 (17), Commission Regulation (EC) No 1490/2002 (18), or Commission Decision 2003/565/EC (19) and for any substance for which a Commission Decision on the completeness of the dossier has been taken pursuant to Article 6 of Directive 91/414/EEC shall be regarded as being registered and the registration as completed for manufacture or import for the use as a plant protection product and therefore as fulfilling the requirements of [general obligation to register and information requirements] and [transitional provisions applicable to phase-in substances and notified substances].*
- Article 15(2): *Active substances manufactured or imported for use in biocidal products only and included either in Annexes I, IA or IB to Directive 98/8/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 February 1998 concerning the placing of biocidal products on the market (20) or in Commission Regulation (EC) No 2032/2003 (21) on the second phase of the 10-year work programme referred to in Article 16(2) of Directive 98/8/EC, until the date of the decision referred to in the second subparagraph of Article 16(2) of Directive 98/8/EC, shall be regarded as being registered and the registration as completed for manufacture or import for the use in a biocidal product and therefore as fulfilling the requirements of [general obligation to register and information requirements] and [transitional provisions applicable to phase-in substances and notified substances].*
- Article 24: *A notification in accordance with Directive 67/548/EEC [the Dangerous Substances Directive – the predecessor of the CLP regulation] shall be regarded as a registration ... and the Agency shall assign a registration number by 1 December 2008.*

Exemption from the general obligation to register for product and process orientated research and development (PPORD)⁴⁶

- Article 9(1): *Articles 5, 6, 7, 17, 18 and 21 shall not apply for a period of five years [since the receipt of the notification at the Agency] to a substance manufactured in the Community or imported for the purposes of product and process orientated research and development by a manufacturer or importer or producer of articles, by himself or in cooperation with listed customers and in a quantity which is limited to the purpose of product and process orientated research and development.*
- Article 9(7): *The Agency may decide to extend the five-year exemption period by a further maximum of five years or, in the case of substances to be used exclusively in the development of medicinal products for human or veterinary use, or for substances that are not placed on the market, for a further maximum of ten years, upon request if the manufacturer or importer or producer of articles can demonstrate that such an extension is justified by the research and development programme.*

Guidance for monomers and polymers, Version 2.0, April 2012, including definitions, tasks and obligations, analytical methods: https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/polymers_en.pdf/9a74545f-05be-4e10-8555-4d7cf051bbed

⁴⁵ Articles 21, 22 and 25 to 28 shall not apply to uses of substances regarded as registered. [A]

⁴⁶ Any scientific development related to product development or the further development of a substance, on its own, in mixtures or in articles in the course of which pilot plant or production trials are used to develop the production process and/or to test the fields of application to the substance. [A]

Guidance on scientific research and development (SR&D) and product and process orientated research and development (PPORD), Version 2.1, October 2017, including definitions, tasks and obligations, PPORD notification dossier, PPORD notification update for new information, extension of the exemption from the obligation to register, request for information and conditions that may be imposed by ECHA, confidentiality: https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/ppord_en.pdf/22a12900-ad27-454c-aedd-82972ef2f675

Notification of substances of very high concern (SVHC) in articles

- Article 7(3): *The producer or importer can exclude exposure to humans or the environment during normal or reasonably foreseeable conditions of use including disposal. In such cases, the producer or importer shall supply appropriate instructions to the recipient of the article.*

Chemical safety report

- *A chemical safety assessment ... need not be performed for a substance which is present in a mixture if the concentration of the substance in the mixture is less than: (a) the cut-off value referred to in Article 11, paragraph 3 of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008; (b) 0.1% weight by weight (w/w), if the substance meets the criteria in Annex XIII to this Regulation.*

Authorisation (Article 56)

- *... shall not apply to the use of substances in scientific research and development. Annex XIV shall specify if [authorisation] apply to product and process orientated research and development as well as the maximum quantity exempted*
- *... shall not apply to the following uses of substances*
 - *Uses in plant protection products within the scope of Directive 91/414/EEC*
 - *Uses in biocidal products within the scope of Directive 98/8/EC*
 - *Use as motor fuels covered by Directive 98/70/EC ...*
 - *Uses as fuel in mobile or fixed combustion plants of mineral oil products and use as fuels in closed systems*
- *In the case of substances that are subject to authorisation only because they meet the criteria in Article 57(a), (b) or (c) [C, M or R, 1A or 1B, and adverse effects on sexual function and fertility or on development for R] or because they are identified in accordance with Article 57(f) only because of hazards to human health, [authorisation] shall not apply to the following uses*
 - *Uses in cosmetic products within the scope of Directive 76/768/EEC*
 - *Uses in food contact materials within the scope of Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004*
- *... shall not apply to the use of substances when they are present in mixtures*
 - *For substances referred to in Article 57(d) [PBT], (e) [vPvB] and (f)⁴⁷, below a concentration limit of 0.1% weight by weight*
 - *For all other substances, below the values specified in Article 11(3) of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 which result in the classification of the mixture as hazardous*
- *Article 58(2): Uses or categories of uses may be exempted from the authorisation requirement provided that, on the basis of the existing specific Community legislation imposing minimum requirements relating to the protection of human health or the environment for the use of the substance, the risk is properly controlled. In the establishment of such exemptions, account shall be taken, in particular, of the proportionality of risk to human health and the environment related to the nature of the substance, such as where the risk is modified by the physical form.*

Restrictions (Article 67)

⁴⁷ *substances — such as those having endocrine disrupting properties or those having persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic properties or very persistent and very bioaccumulative properties, which do not fulfil the criteria of points (d) or (e) — for which there is scientific evidence of probable serious effects to human health or the environment which give rise to an equivalent level of concern to those of other substances listed in points (a) to (e) and which are identified on a case-by-case basis in accordance with the procedure set out in Article 59. [A]*

- *This shall not apply to the manufacture, placing on the market or use of a substance in scientific research and development. Annex XVII shall specify if the restriction shall not apply to product and process orientated research and development, as well as the maximum quantity exempted.*
- *... shall not apply to the use of substances in cosmetic products, as defined by Directive 76/768/EEC, with regard to restrictions addressing the risks to human health within the scope of that Directive.*

4. Initial data requirements

General registration (Article 10, [A])⁴⁸

- *A technical dossier including*
 - *the identity of the manufacturer(s) or importer(s) as specified in section 1 of Annex VI;*
 - *the identity of the substance as specified in section 2 of Annex VI;*⁴⁹

⁴⁸ *Guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment:* <https://echa.europa.eu/guidance-documents/guidance-on-information-requirements-and-chemical-safety-assessment>

Practical guide for SME managers and REACH coordinators – how to fulfil your information requirements at tonnages 1–10 and 10–100 tonnes per year, Version 1, July 2016:

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/17250/pg_sme_managers_reach_coordinators_en.pdf/1253d9f9-d1f0-4ca8-9e7a-c81e337e3a7d

Practical guide – how to use alternatives to animal testing to fulfil your information requirements for REACH registration, Version 2.0, July 2016, including your general obligations, fulfil your information requirements – four-step process, alternatives to avoid animal testing (weight of evidence, (Q)SAR, in vitro data, read-across and categories):

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/17250/practical_guide_how_to_use_alternatives_en.pdf/148b30c7-c186-463c-a898-522a888a4404

Practical guide – how to use and report (Q)SARs, Version 3.1, July 2016, including how to get started with (Q)SARs, how to check a QSAR prediction, practical examples:

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/17250/pg_report_qsars_en.pdf/407dff11-aa4a-4eef-a1ce-9300f8460099

How to report robust study summaries – practical guide 3, Version 2.0, November 2012, including general aspects related to the preparation of a robust study summary, endpoint specific information for physicochemical endpoints, endpoint specific information for environmental endpoints, endpoint specific information for human health endpoints, general aspects related to the preparation of study summary:

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/17235/pg_report_robust_study_summaries_en.pdf/1e8302c3-98b7-4a50-aa22-f6f02ca54352

How downstream users can handle exposure scenarios – practical guide 13:

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/17250/du_practical_guide_13_en.pdf/2c3bc624-fb3c-4515-a581-87b79d460d38

How to prepare toxicological summaries in IUCLID and how to derive DNELs – practical guide 14:

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/17250/pg_14_on_hazard_endpoint_en.pdf/8a85bb85-f4da-49b1-a28a-bfdf269c68b4

How to undertake a qualitative human health assessment and document it in a chemical safety report – practical guidance 15:

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/17250/pg_15_qualitative-human_health_assessment_documenting_en.pdf/26a645d4-a81e-4223-8ca9-20162ae74e72

How to assess whether a substance is used as an intermediate under strictly controlled conditions and how to report the information for the intermediate registration in IUCLID – practical guide 16:

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/pg16_intermediate_registration_en.pdf/291b6e50-5598-42d3-8a2b-d63d50a68104

How to prepare a downstream user chemical safety report – practical guide 17:

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/17250/pg17_du_csr_final_en.pdf/03aeab25-405a-45a4-9a66-5fa5c2dbfcb2

⁴⁹ *Guidance for identification and naming of substances under REACH and CLP, Version 2.1, May 2017, including definitions and abbreviations, framework for substance identification in REACH and CLP, guidance for substance identification and naming in REACH and CLP, criteria for checking if substances are the same,*

- *Name or other identifier of each substance:* including IUPAC name(s), other names such as usual name, trade name, abbreviation, EINECS or ELINCS number (if available and appropriate), CAS name and CASRN (if available)
- *Information related to molecular and structural formula of each substance*
 - *Molecular and structural formula (including SMILES notation, if available)*
 - *Information on optical activity and typical ratio of (stereo) isomers (if applicable and appropriate)*
 - *Molecular weight or molecular weight range*
- *Composition of each substance ...*
 - *Degree of purity (%)*
 - *Nature of impurities, including isomers and by-products*
 - *Percentage of (significant) main impurities*
 - *Nature and order of magnitude (... ppm, ... %) of any additives (e.g. stabilising agents or inhibitors)*
 - *Spectral data (e.g. ultra-violet, infra-red, nuclear magnetic resonance or mass spectrum)*
 - *High-pressure liquid chromatogram, gas chromatogram*
 - *Description of the analytical methods or the appropriate bibliographical references for the identification of the substance and, where appropriate, for the identification of impurities and additives. This information shall be sufficient to allow the methods to be reproduced*
- *Characterisation of nanoforms of a substance: for each of the characterisation parameters, the information provided may be applicable to either an individual nanoform or a set of similar nanoforms provided that the boundaries of the set are clearly specified*
 - *Names or other identifiers of the nanoforms or sets of similar nanoforms of the substance*
 - *Number based particle size distribution with indication of the number fraction of constituent particles in the size range within 1 nm – 100 nm*
 - *Description of surface functionalisation or treatment and identification of each agent including IUPAC name and CAS or EC number*
 - *Shape, aspect ratio and other morphological characterisation: crystallinity, information on assembly structure including e.g. shell like structures or hollow structures, if appropriate*
 - *Surface area (specific surface area by volume, specific surface area by mass or both)*
 - *Description of the analytical methods or the appropriate bibliographical references for the information elements in this sub-section. This information shall be sufficient to allow the methods to be reproduced.*
- *information on the manufacture and use(s) of the substance as specified in section 3 of Annex VI; this information shall represent all the registrant's identified use(s). This information may include, if the registrant deems appropriate, the relevant use and exposure categories*

substance identity within (late) pre-registration and inquiry, examples:

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/substance_id_en.pdf/ee696bad-49f6-4fec-b8b7-2c3706113c7d

- Overall manufacture, quantities used for production of an article that is subject to registration, and/or imports in tonnes per registrant per year in: the calendar year of the registration (estimated quantity)
- In the case of a manufacturer or producer of articles: brief description of the technological process used in manufacture or production of articles. Precise details of the process, particularly those of a commercially sensitive nature, are not required.
- An indication of the tonnage used for his own use(s)
- Form (substance, mixture or article) and/or physical state under which the substance is made available to downstream users. Concentration or concentration range of the substance in mixtures made available to downstream users and quantities of the substance in articles made available to downstream users
- Brief general description of the identified use(s)
- Information on waste quantities and composition of waste resulting from manufacture of the substance, the use in articles and identified uses
- Uses advised against (see section 1 of the safety data sheet). Where applicable, an indication of the uses which the registrant advises against and why (i.e. non-statutory recommendations by supplier). This need not to be an exhaustive list.
- the classification and labelling of the substance as specified in section 4 of Annex VI
 - the hazard classification of the substance(s) ... for each entry, the reasons why no classification is given for a hazard class or differentiation of a hazard class should be provided (i.e. if data are lacking, inconclusive, or conclusive but not sufficient for classification)
 - the resulting hazard label ...
 - specific concentration limits, where applicable ...
- guidance on safe use of the substance as specified in Section 5 of Annex VI;
- study summaries⁵⁰ of the information derived from the application of Annexes VII to XI;
 - Annex VII: standard information requirements for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of one tonne or more
 - Annex VIII: standard information requirements for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 10 tonnes or more
 - Annex IX: standard information requirements for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 100 tonnes or more
 - Annex X: standard information requirements for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 1000 tonnes or more
 - Annex XI: general rules for adaptation of the standard testing regime set out in Annexes VII to X
 - Use of existing data not carried out according to GLP or the test methods referred to in Article 13(3) and historical human data
 - Weight of evidence
 - Qualitative or quantitative structure-activity relationship
 - In vitro methods
 - Grouping of substances and read-across approach
 - Testing is technically not possible
 - Substance-tailor exposure-driven testing

⁵⁰ A summary of the objectives, methods, results and conclusions of a full study report providing sufficient information to make an assessment of the relevance of the study [A]

- *robust study summaries*⁵¹ of the information derived from the application of Annexes VII to XI, if required under Annex I
 - Annex I: general provisions for assessing substances and preparing chemical safety reports
 - 1.1.4. Human health hazard assessment / 3.1.5. environmental hazard assessment: *If one study is available then a robust study summary should be prepared for that study. If there are several studies addressing the same effect, then, having taken into account possible variables (e.g. conduct, adequacy, relevance of test species, quality of results, etc.), normally the study or studies giving rise to the highest concern shall be used to establish the DNELs and a robust study summary shall be prepared for that study or studies and included as part of the technical dossier. Robust summaries will be required of all key data used in the hazard assessment. If the study or studies giving rise to the highest concern are not used, then this shall be fully justified and included as part of the technical dossier, not only for the study being used but also for all studies demonstrating a higher concern than the study being used. It is important irrespective of whether hazards have been identified or not that the validity of the study be considered.*
- *an indication as to which of the information submitted under (iii) [manufacture and use(s)], (iv) [classification and labelling], (vi) [study summaries], (vii) [robust study summaries] or subparagraph (b) [chemical safety report] has been reviewed by an assessor chosen by the manufacturer or importer and having appropriate experience;*
- *proposals for testing where listed in Annexes IX and X;*
- *for substances in quantities of 1 to 10 tonnes, exposure information as specified in section 6 of Annex VI;*
 - *main use category:* industrial use (used in closed system, use resulting in inclusion into or onto matrix, non-dispersive use, and/or dispersive use), professional use, and/or consumer use
 - *significant route(s) of exposure:* human exposure (oral, dermal, and/or inhalatory), environmental exposure (water, air, solid waste, and/or soil), pattern of exposure (accidental/infrequent, occasional, and/or continuous/frequent)
- *a request as to which of the information in Article 119(2) the manufacturer or importer considers should not be made available on the Internet in accordance with Article 77(2)(e), including a justification as to why publication could be harmful for his or any other concerned party's commercial interests.*
- *Except in cases covered under Article 25(3), Article 27(6) or Article 30(3), the registrant shall be in legitimate possession of or have permission to refer to the full study report summarised under (vi) and (vii) for the purpose of registration;*
- *a chemical safety report when required under Article 14, in the format specified in Annex I. The relevant sections of this report may include, if the registrant considers appropriate, the relevant use and exposure categories.*
 - *Article 14: Without prejudice to Article 4 of Directive 98/24/EC, a chemical safety assessment shall be performed and a chemical safety report completed for all substances subject to*

⁵¹ A detailed summary of the objectives, methods, results and conclusions of a full study report providing sufficient information to make an independent assessment of the study minimising the need to consult the full study report [A]

registration in accordance with this Chapter in quantities of 10 tonnes or more per year per registrant.

- A chemical safety assessment of a substance shall include the following steps: human health hazard assessment, physicochemical hazard assessment, environmental hazard assessment, PBT and vPvB assessment
- If ... the registrant concludes that the substance fulfils the criteria for any of the following hazard class or categories set out in Annex I to Regulation (EC) No/2008: (a) hazard classes 2.1 to 2.4, 2.6 and 2.7, 2.8 types A and B, 2.9, 2.10, 2.12, 2.13 categories 1 and 2, 2.14 categories 1 and 2, 2.15 types A to F; (b) hazard classes 3.1 to 3.6, 3.7 adverse effects on sexual function and fertility or on development, 3.8 effects other than narcotic effects, 3.9 and 3.10; (c) hazard class 4.1; (d) hazard class 5.1, or is assessed to be a PBT or vPvB, the chemical safety assessment shall include the following additional steps: (a) exposure assessment including the generation of exposure scenario(s) (or the identification of relevant use and exposure categories if appropriate) and exposure estimation; (b) risk characterisation.
- The chemical safety report need not include consideration of the risks to human health from the following end uses: (a) in food contact materials within the scope of Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 2004 on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food; (b) in cosmetic products within the scope of Directive 76/768/EEC.
- Article 12: The technical dossier ... shall include under points (vi) [study summaries] and (vii) [robust study summaries] ... all physicochemical, toxicological and ecotoxicological information that is relevant and available to the registrant and as a minimum the following
 - the information specified in Annex VII for non-phase-in substances, and for phase-in substances⁵² meeting one or both of the criteria specified in Annex III, manufactured or imported in quantities of one tonne or more per year per manufacturer or importer
 - Annex III criteria for substances registered in quantities between 1 and 10 tonnes
 - Substances for which it is predicted (i.e. by the application of (Q)SAR or other evidence) that they are likely to meet the criteria for category 1A or 1B classification in the hazard classes carcinogenicity, germ cell mutagenicity or reproductive toxicity or the criteria in Annex XIII [criteria for the identification of persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic substances, and very persistent and very bioaccumulative substances]
 - Substances (i) with dispersive or diffuse use(s) particularly where such substances are used in consumer mixtures or incorporated into consumer

⁵² A substance which meets at least one of the following criteria [A]

- It is listed in the European Inventory of Existing Commercial Chemical Substances (EINECS)
- It was manufactured in the Community, or in the countries acceding to the European Union on 1 January 1995, on 1 May 2004, on 1 January 2007 or on 1 July 2013, but not placed on the market by the manufacturer or importer, at least once in the 15 years before the entry into force of this Regulation, provided the manufacturer or importer has documentary evidence of this
- it was placed on the market in the Community, or in the countries acceding to the European Union on 1 January 1995, on 1 May 2004, on 1 January 2007 or on 1 July 2013, by the manufacturer or importer before the entry into force of this Regulation and it was considered as having been notified in accordance with the first indent of Article 8(1) of Directive 67/548/EEC in the version of Article 8(1) resulting from the amendment effected by Directive 79/831/EEC, but it does not meet the definition of a polymer as set out in this Regulation, provided the manufacturer or importer has documentary evidence of this, including proof that the substance was placed on the market by any manufacturer or importer between 18 September 1981 and 31 October 1993 inclusive

articles; and (ii) for which it is predicted (i.e. by the application of (Q)SAR or other evidence) that they are likely to meet the criteria for any health or environmental hazard classes or differentiations under Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 or for substances with nanoforms, unless those nanoforms are soluble in biological and environmental media

- the information on physicochemical properties specified in Annex VII, section 7 for phase-in substances manufactured or imported in quantities of one tonne or more per year per manufacturer or importer which do not meet either of the criteria specified in Annex III;
 - the information specified in Annexes VII and VIII for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 10 tonnes or more per year per manufacturer or importer;
 - the information specified in Annexes VII and VIII and testing proposals for the provision of the information specified in Annex IX for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 100 tonnes or more per year per manufacturer or importer;
 - the information specified in Annexes VII and VIII and testing proposals for the provision of the information specified in Annexes IX and X for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 1 000 tonnes or more per year per manufacturer or importer.
- Article 13⁵³: Information on intrinsic properties of substances may be generated by means other than tests, provided that the conditions set out in Annex XI are met. In particular for human toxicity, information shall be generated whenever possible by means other than vertebrate animal tests, through the use of alternative methods, for example, in vitro methods or qualitative or quantitative structure-activity relationship models or from information from structurally related substances (grouping or read-across). Testing in accordance with Annex VIII, Sections 8.6 and 8.7, Annex IX and Annex X may be omitted where justified by information on exposure and implemented risk management measures as specified in Annex XI, section 3.
 - These methods shall be regularly reviewed and improved with a view to reducing testing on vertebrate animals and the number of animals involved. The Commission, following consultation with relevant stakeholders, shall, as soon as possible, make a proposal, if appropriate, to amend the Commission Regulation on test methods adopted in accordance with the procedure referred to in Article 133(4), and the Annexes of this Regulation, if relevant, so as to replace, reduce or refine animal testing. Amendments to that Commission Regulation shall be adopted in accordance with the procedure specified in paragraph 3 and amendments to the

⁵³ Article 25 - Objectives and general rules [A]:

- In order to avoid animal testing, testing on vertebrate animals for the purposes of this Regulation shall be undertaken only as a last resort. It is also necessary to take measures limiting duplication of other tests.
- The sharing and joint submission of information in accordance with this Regulation shall concern technical data and in particular information related to the intrinsic properties of substances. Registrants shall refrain from exchanging information concerning their market behaviour, in particular as regards production capacities, production or sales volumes, import volumes or market shares.
- Any study summaries or robust study summaries of studies submitted in the framework of a registration under this Regulation at least 12 years previously can be used for the purposes of registration by another manufacturer or importer.

Other relevant articles are: Article 11 – joint submission of data by multiple registrants, Article 19 – joint submission of data on isolated intermediates by multiple registrants, Article 26 – duty to inquire prior to registration, Article 27 – sharing of existing data in the case of registered substances, Article 28 – duty to pre-register for phase-in substances, Article 29 – substance information exchange forums, Article 30 – sharing of data involving tests.

Annexes of this Regulation shall be adopted in accordance with the procedure referred to in Article 131.

- *Where tests on substances are required to generate information on intrinsic properties of substances, they shall be conducted in accordance with the test methods laid down in a Commission Regulation or in accordance with other international test methods recognised by the Commission or the Agency as being appropriate. The Commission shall adopt that Regulation, designed to amend the non-essential elements of this Regulation by supplementing it, in accordance with the procedure referred to in Article 133(4).*
- *Ecotoxicological and toxicological tests and analyses shall be carried out in compliance with the principles of good laboratory practice provided for in Directive 2004/10/EC or other international standards recognised as being equivalent by the Commission or the Agency and with the provisions of Directive 86/609/EEC, if applicable.*
- *If a substance has already been registered, a new registrant shall be entitled to refer to the study summaries or robust study summaries, for the same substance submitted earlier, provided that he can show that the substance that he is now registering is the same as the one previously registered, including the degree of purity and the nature of impurities, and that the previous registrant(s) have given permission to refer to the full study reports for the purpose of registration.*

Registration of on-site isolated intermediates (Article 17)

- *A registration for an on-site isolated intermediate shall include all the following information, to the extent that the manufacturer is able to submit it without any additional testing:*
 - *the identity of the manufacturer as specified in Section 1 of Annex VI;*
 - *the identity of the intermediate as specified in Sections 2.1 to 2.3.4 of Annex VI;*
 - *the classification of the intermediate as specified in Section 4 of Annex VI;*
 - *any available existing information on physicochemical, human health or environmental properties of the intermediate. Where a full study report is available, a study summary shall be submitted;*
 - *Except in cases covered under Article 25(3) [the 12-year rule], Article 27(6) or Article 30(3), the registrant shall be in legitimate possession of or have permission to refer to the full study report*
 - *a brief general description of the use, as specified in Section 3.5 of Annex VI;*
 - *details of the risk management measures applied.*
- *... shall apply only to on-site isolated intermediates if the manufacturer confirms that the substance is only manufactured and used under strictly controlled conditions in that it is rigorously contained by technical means during its whole lifecycle. Control and procedural technologies shall be used to minimise emission and any resulting exposure. If these conditions are not fulfilled, the registration shall include the information specified in [general registration above].*

Registration of transported isolated intermediates (Article 18)

- *A registration for a transported isolated intermediate shall include all the following information:*
 - *the identity of the manufacturer or importer as specified in Section 1 of Annex VI;*
 - *the identity of the intermediate as specified in Sections 2.1 to 2.3.4 of Annex VI;*
 - *the classification of the intermediate as specified in Section 4 of Annex VI;*
 - *any available existing information on physicochemical, human health or environmental properties of the intermediate. Where a full study report is available, a study summary shall be submitted;*

- *Except in cases covered under Article 25(3), Article 27(6) or Article 30(3), the registrant shall be in legitimate possession of or have permission to refer to the full study report summarised under (d) for the purpose of registration.*
 - *a brief general description of the use, as specified in Section 3.5 of Annex VI;*
 - *information on risk management measures applied and recommended to the user in accordance with paragraph 4.*
- *A registration for a transported isolated intermediate in quantities of more than 1000 tonnes per year per manufacturer or importer shall include the information specified in Annex VII in addition to the information required [above]*
- *... shall apply only to transported isolated intermediates if the manufacturer or importer confirms himself or states that he has received confirmation from the user that the synthesis of (an)other substance(s) from that intermediate takes place on other sites under the following strictly controlled conditions*
 - *The substance is rigorously contained by technical means during its whole lifecycle including manufacture, purification, cleaning and maintenance of equipment, sampling, analysis, loading and unloading of equipment or vessels, waste disposal or purification and storage*
 - *Procedural and control technologies shall be used that minimise emission and any resulting exposure*
 - *Only properly trained and authorised personnel handle the substance*
 - *In the case of cleaning and maintenance works, special procedures such as purging and washing are applied before the system is opened and entered*
 - *In cases of accident and where waste is generated, procedural and/or control technologies are used to minimise emissions and the resulting exposure during purification or cleaning and maintenance procedures*
 - *Substance-handling procedures are well documented and strictly supervised by the site operator*
 - *If the conditions listed ... are not fulfilled, the registration shall include the information specified in [general registration above].*

Exemption from the general obligation to register for product and process orientated research and development (PPORD)

- *Article 9(2): ... the manufacturer or importer or producer of articles shall notify the Agency of the following information*
 - *the identity of the manufacturer or importer or producer of articles as specified in section 1 of Annex VI*
 - *the identity of the substance, as specified in section 2 of Annex VI*
 - *the classification of the substance as specified in section 4 of Annex VI, if any*
 - *the estimated quantity as specified in section 3.1 of Annex VI*
 - *the list of customers referred to in paragraph 1, including their names and addresses.*

Notification of substances of very high concern (SVHC) in articles (Article 7(4))

- *The identity and contact details of the producer or importer as specified in section 1 of Annex VI, with the exception of their own use sites*
- *The registration number(s) referred to in Article 20(1), if available*
- *The identity of the substance as specified in sections 2.1 to 2.3.4 of Annex VI*
- *The classification of the substance(s) as specified in sections 4.1 and 4.2 of Annex VI*
- *A brief description of the use(s) of the substance(s) in the article as specified in section 3.5 of Annex VI and of the uses of the article(s)*
- *The tonnage range of the substance(s), such as 1 to 10 tonnes, 10 to 100 tonnes and so on*

Obligation for downstream users to report information (Article 38(2))

- *His identity and contact details as specified in Section 1.1 of Annex VI*
- *The registration number(s) referred to in Article 20(3), if available*
- *The identity of the substance(s) as specified in Section 2.1 to 2.3.4 of Annex VI*
- *The identity of the manufacturer(s) or the importer(s) or other supplier as specified in Section 1.1 of Annex VI*
- *A brief general description of the use(s), as specified in Section 3.5 of Annex VI, and of the conditions of use(s)*
- *Except where the downstream user is relying on the exemption in Article 37(4)(c), a proposal for additional testing on vertebrate animals, where this is considered necessary by the downstream user to complete his chemical safety assessment*

Authorisation (Article 62)

- *Applications for authorisation may be made by the manufacturer(s), importer(s) and/or downstream user(s) of the substance. Applications may be made by one or several persons. ... Applications may be made for the applicant's own use(s) and/or for uses for which he intends to place the substance on the market.*
- *An application for authorisation shall include the following information*
 - *The identity of the substance(s), as referred to in Section 2 of Annex VI*
 - *The name and contact details of the person or persons making the application*
 - *A request for authorisation, specifying for which use(s) the authorisation is sought and covering the use of the substance in mixtures and/or the incorporation of the substance in articles, where this is relevant*
 - *Unless already submitted as part of the registration, a chemical safety report in accordance with Annex I covering the risks to human health and/or the environment from the use of the substance(s) arising from the intrinsic properties specified in Annex XIV*
 - *An analysis of the alternatives considering their risks and the technical and economic feasibility of substitution and including, if appropriate information about any relevant research and development activities by the applicant*
 - *Where the analysis referred to in point (e) shows that suitable alternatives are available, taking into account the elements in Article 60(5), a substitution plan including a timetable for proposed actions by the applicant*
- *The application may include*
 - *A socio-economic analysis conducted in accordance with Annex XVI⁵⁴*

⁵⁴ An SEA may include the following elements:

- *impact of a granted or refused authorisation on the applicant(s), or, in the case of a proposed restriction, the impact on industry (e.g. manufacturers and importers). The impact on all other actors in the supply chain, downstream users and associated businesses in terms of commercial consequences such as impact on investment, research and development, innovation, one-off and operating costs (e.g. compliance, transitional arrangements, changes to existing processes, reporting and monitoring systems, installation of new technology, etc.) taking into account general trends in the market and technology*
- *impacts of a granted or refused authorisation, or a proposed restriction, on consumers. For example, product prices, changes in composition or quality or performance of products, availability of products, consumer choice, as well as effects on human health and the environment to the extent that these affect consumers*
- *social implications of a granted or refused authorisation, or a proposed restriction. For example job security and employment*

- *A justification for not considering risks to human health and the environment arising either from*
 - *Emissions of a substance from an installation for which a permit was granted in accordance with Directive 96/61/EC, or*
 - *Discharges of a substance from a point source governed by the requirement for prior regulation referred to in Article 11(3)(g) of Directive 2000/60/EC and legislation adopted under Article 16 of that Directive*
- *The applicant shall not include the risks to human health arising from the use of a substance in a medical device regulated by Directives 90/385/EEC, 93/42/EEC or 98/79/EC*

5. Data updates by companies

General registration [A]

- *Article 12: As soon as the quantity of a substance per manufacturer or importer that has already been registered reaches the next tonnage threshold, the manufacturer or importer shall inform the Agency immediately of the additional information he would require under paragraph 1. Article 26(3) and (4) shall apply adapted as necessary.*
- *Article 14: Any registrant required to conduct a chemical safety assessment shall keep his chemical safety report available and up to date.*
- *Article 22(1): Following registration, a registrant shall be responsible on his own initiative for updating his registration without undue delay with relevant new information and submitting it to the Agency in the following cases*
 - *Any change in his status ...*
 - *... the registration shall be updated and submitted to the Agency by no later than 3 months from the date when that change takes effect [B]*
 - *Any change in the composition of the substance as given in Section 2 of Annex VI*

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- *availability, suitability, and technical feasibility of alternative substances and/or technologies, and economic consequences thereof, and information on the rates of, and potential for, technological change in the sector(s) concerned. In the case of an application for authorisation, the social and/or economic impacts of using any available alternatives*
 - *wider implications on trade, competition and economic development (in particular for SMEs and in relation to third countries) of a granted or refused authorisation, or a proposed restriction. This may include consideration of local, regional, national or international aspects*
 - *in the case of a proposed restriction, proposals for other regulatory or non-regulatory measures that could meet the aim of the proposed restriction (this shall take account of existing legislation). This should include an assessment of the effectiveness and the costs linked to alternative risk management measures*
 - *in the case of a proposed restriction or refused authorisation, the benefits for human health and the environment as well as the social and economic benefits of the proposed restriction. For example, worker health, environmental performance and the distribution of these benefits, for example, geographically, population groups*
 - *an SEA may also address any other issue that is considered to be relevant by the applicant(s) or interested party.*

Guidance on the preparation of socio-economic analysis as part of an application for authorisation, Version 1, January 2011, including the SEA process – stage 2: scoping phase, the SEA process – stage 3: assessing impacts, the SEA process – stage 4: interpretation and drawing conclusions, the SEA process – stage 5: presenting the results: https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/sea_authorisation_en.pdf/aadf96ec-fbfa-4bc7-9740-a3f6ceb68e6e

- ... the registration shall be updated and submitted to the Agency by no later than 3 months from the date when manufacture or import begins with that change in substance composition [B]
- Changes in the annual or total quantities manufactured or imported by him or in the quantities of substances present in articles produced or imported by him if these result in a change of tonnage band, including cessation of manufacture or import
 - In the case of a change ... that results in a higher tonnage band, the registration shall be updated and submitted to the Agency by no later than 3 months from the following date [B]
 - In a case where new data is generated for an update derived from the application of Annex VII or Annex VIII ..., the date when all the final test reports needed for the update have been received
 - A contract negotiation with a testing laboratory shall be initiated for all the relevant tests by no later than 3 months from the date when the higher tonnage band is reached
 - In a case not falling with point [above], the date when the higher tonnage band is reached
 - In the case of a change ... that involves cessation of manufacture or import, the registration shall be updated and submitted to the Agency by no later than 3 months from the date when manufacture or import ceased [B]
 - In the case of a change that involves restarting manufacture or import, the registration shall be updated and submitted to the Agency before manufacture or import is restarted [B]
- New identified uses and new uses advised against as in Section 3.7 of Annex VI for which the substance is manufactured or imported
 - ... the registration shall be updated and submitted to the Agency by no later than 3 months from [B]
 - In the case of a new identified use, the date when the registrant receives all the information needed to carry out the risk assessment for this new use
 - In the case of a new use advised against, the date when the information on the risks associated with that use is available to the registrant
- New knowledge of the risks of the substance to human health and/or the environment of which he may reasonably be expected to have become aware which leads to changes in the safety data sheet or the chemical safety report
 - ... the registration shall be updated and submitted to the Agency by no later than 6 months from the date when the registrant becomes aware or may reasonably be expected to have become aware of the new knowledge in question. [B]
- Any change in the classification and labelling of the substance
 - In the case of a change ... that is due to the addition, modification or deletion of a harmonised classification in Annex VI to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 ..., the registration shall be updated and submitted to the Agency by no later than the date as of which that change is to apply. [B]
 - In the case of a change ... that is due to an adaptation in the classification of a substance as a result of a new evaluation ..., the registration shall be updated and submitted to the Agency by no later than 6 months from the date when the decision to change the classification and labelling of the substance has been taken. [B]
- Any update or amendment of the chemical safety report or Section 5 of Annex VI

- ... the registration shall be updated and submitted to the Agency by no later than 12 months from the date when the need to update or amend the chemical safety report or the guidance on safe use ... was identified. [B]
 - The registrant identifies the need to perform a test listed in Annex IX or Annex X, in which cases a testing proposal shall be developed
 - ... the registration shall be updated to include the testing proposal and submitted to the Agency by no later than 6 months from the date when the registrant identifies the need to perform one or more of the tests listed in Annex IX or X ... [B]
 - The deadline ... shall not apply in the case of a testing proposal developed as part of a testing strategy addressing a group of substances. Instead, in that situation the relevant registrations shall be updated and submitted to the Agency by no later than 12 months from the date when the registrant or registrants identify the need to perform one or more of the test listed in Annex IX or X.
 - Any change in the access granted to information in the registration
 - ... the registration shall be updated and submitted to the Agency by no later than 3 months from the date when the change occurred. [B]
- Article 22(1): A registrant shall submit to the Agency an update of the registration containing the information required by the decision made in accordance with Articles 40, 41 or 46 or take into account a decision made in accordance with Articles 60 and 73, within the deadline specified in that decision.

Obligation to keep information (Article 36)

- Each manufacturer, importer, downstream user and distributor shall assemble and keep available all the information he requires to carry out his duties under this Regulation for a period of at least 10 years after he last manufactured, imported, supplied or used the substance or mixture. That manufacturer, importer, downstream user or distributor shall submit this information or make it available without delay upon request to any competent authority of the Member State in which he is established or to the Agency, without prejudice to Titles II and VI.
- In the event of a registrant, downstream user or distributor ceasing activity, or transferring part or all of his operations to a third party, the party responsible for liquidating the registrant, downstream user or distributor's undertaking or assuming responsibility for the placing on the market of the substance or mixture concerned shall be bound by the obligation in paragraph 1 in place of the registrant, downstream user or distributor.

Obligation for downstream users to report information (Article 38(3))

- The downstream user shall update this information without delay in the event of a change in the information reported ...

Authorisations for downstream users (Article 66)

- Downstream users using a substance in accordance with Article 56(2) [i.e. a substance that requires authorisation] shall notify the Agency within three months of the first supply of the substance.
- The Agency shall establish and keep up to date a register of downstream users who have made a notification.

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

Exemption from the general obligation to register for product and process orientated research and development (PPORD)

- Article 9(4): In such cases, the Agency may ask the notifier to provide additional necessary information.

Examination of testing proposals (Article 40)

- *The Agency shall examine any testing proposal set out in a registration or a downstream user report for provision of the information specified in Annexes IX and X for a substance. Priority shall be given to registration of substances which have or may have PBT, vPvB, sensitising and/or carcinogenic, mutagenic or toxic for reproduction (CMR) properties, or substances above 100 tonnes per year with uses resulting in widespread and diffuse exposure, provided they fulfil the criteria for any of the following hazard classes or categories set out in Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008*
 - *Hazard classes 2.1 to 2.4, 2.6 and 2.7, 2.8 types A and B, 2.9, 2.10, 2.12, 2.13 categories 1 and 2, 2.14 categories 1 and 2, 2.15 types A to F*
 - *Hazard classes 3.1 to 3.6, 3.7 adverse effects on sexual function and fertility or on development, 3.8 effects other than narcotic effects, 3.9 and 3.10*
 - *Hazard class 4.1*
 - *Hazard class 5.1*
- *Information relating to testing proposals involving tests on vertebrate animals shall be published on the Agency website. The Agency shall publish on its website the name of the substance, the hazard end-point for which vertebrate testing is proposed, and the date by which any third party information is required. It shall invite third parties to submit, using the format provided by the Agency, scientifically valid information and studies that address the relevant substance and hazard end-point, addressed by the testing proposal, within 45 days of the date of publication. All such scientifically valid information and studies received shall be taken into account by the Agency in preparing its decision ...*
- *On the basis of the examination [above], the Agency shall draft one of the following decisions ...*
 - *A decision requiring the registrant(s) or downstream user(s) concerned to carry out the proposed test and setting a deadline for submission of the study summary, or the robust study summary if required by Annex I*
 - *A decision in accordance with point (a), but modifying the conditions under which the test is to be carried out*
 - *A decision rejecting the testing proposal*
 - *A decision in accordance with points [above] but requiring registrant(s) or downstream user(s) to carry out one or more additional tests in cases of non-compliance of the testing proposal with Annexes IX, X and XI*
- *Article 43(1): In the case of non phase-in substances, the Agency shall prepare a draft decision ... within 180 days of receiving a registration or downstream user report containing a testing proposal.*

Compliance check of registrations (Article 41)

- *The Agency may examine any registration in order to verify any of the following*
 - *That the information in the technical dossier(s) ... complies with the requirements of Articles 10, 12 and 13 and with Annex III and VI to X*
 - *That the adaptations of the standard information requirements and the related justifications submitted in the technical dossier(s) comply with the rules governing such adaptations set out in Annexes VII to X and with the general rules set out in Annex XI*
 - *That any required chemical safety assessment and chemical safety report comply with the requirements of Annex I and that the proposed risk management measures are adequate*
 - *That any explanation(s) submitted in accordance with Article 11(3) or Article 19(2) have an objective basis*
- *On the basis of an examination ... the Agency may, within 12 months of the start of the compliance check, prepare a draft decision requiring the registrant(s) to submit any information needed to bring the registration(s) into compliance with the relevant information requirements and specifying adequate time limits for the submission of further information. ...*

- *To check compliance of registration dossiers with this Regulation, the Agency shall select, until 31 December 2023, a percentage of those dossiers no lower than 20% of the total received by the Agency for registrations in tonnage bands of 100 tonnes or more per year. The Agency shall, until 31 December 2027, also select a percentage no lower than 20% of the total received by the Agency for registrations in tonnage bands of less than 100 tonnes per year. When selecting dossiers for compliance checking, the Agency shall give priority, but not exclusively, to dossiers meeting at least one of the following criteria*
 - *The dossier contains information in Article 10(a)(iv) [the classification and labelling], (vi) [study summaries] and/or (vii) [robust study summaries] submitted separately as per Article 11(3)*
 - *The dossier is for a substance manufactured or imported in quantities of one tonne or more per year and does not meet the requirements of Annex VII applying under either Article 12(1)(a) or (b), as the case may be*
 - *The dossier is for a substance listed in the Community rolling action plan referred to in Article 44(2)*
- *Any third party may electronically submit information to the Agency relating to substances that appear on the list referred to in Article 28(4) [pre-registered substances]. The Agency shall consider this information together with the information submitted according to Article 124 when checking and selecting dossiers.*

Requests for further information and check of information submitted (Article 46)

- *If the competent authority considers that further information is required, including, if appropriate, information not required in Annexes VII to X, it shall prepare a draft decision, stating reasons, requiring the registrant(s) to submit the further information and setting a deadline for its submission. A draft decision shall be prepared within 12 months of the publication of the Community rolling action plan on the Agency's website for substances to be evaluated that year.*
- *The competent authority shall examine any information submitted, and shall draft any appropriate decisions in accordance with this Article, if necessary, within 12 months of the information being submitted.*
- *The competent authority shall finish its evaluation activities within 12 months of the start of the evaluation of the substance or within 12 months of the information being submitted ..., and notify the Agency accordingly. If this deadline is exceeded, the evaluation shall be deemed to be finished.*

Authorisation

- *Article 58(4): Before the Agency sends its recommendation to the Commission it shall make it publicly available on its website, clearly indicating the date of publication ... The Agency shall invite all interested parties to submit comments within three months of the date of publication, in particular on uses which should be exempted from the authorisation requirement. The Agency shall update its recommendation, taking into account the comments received.*
- *Article 64(3): In preparing its opinion, each Committee ... shall first check that the application includes all the information specified ... that is relevant to its remit. If necessary, the Committees shall, in consultation with each other, make a joint request to the applicant for additional information to bring the application into conformity with the requirements. The Committee for Socio-economic Analysis may, if it deems it necessary, require the applicant or request third parties to submit, within a specified time period, additional information on possible alternative substances or technologies. Each Committee shall also take into account any information submitted by third parties.*

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)**All registrations**

- Article 20(2): *The Agency shall undertake a completeness check of each registration in order to ascertain that all the elements required ... have been provided. The completeness check shall not include an assessment of the quality or the adequacy of any data or justifications submitted. The Agency shall undertake the completeness check within three weeks of the submission date, or within three months of the relevant deadline of Article 24, as regards registrations of phase-in substances submitted in the course of the two-month period immediately preceding that deadline. If a registration is incomplete, the Agency shall inform the registrant, before expiry of the three-week or three-month period referred to [above], as to what further information is required in order for the registration to be complete, while setting a reasonable deadline for this. The registrant shall complete his registration and submit it to the Agency within the deadline set. The Agency shall confirm the submission date of the further information to the registrant. The Agency shall perform a further completeness check, considering the further information submitted. The Agency shall reject the registration if the registrant fails to complete his registration within the deadline set.*
 - Article 21: *A registrant may start or continue the manufacture or import of a substance or production or import of an article, if there is no indication to the contrary from the Agency ... within the three weeks after the submission date, without prejudice to Article 27(8).*
- Article 22(3): *The Agency shall undertake a completeness check ... of each updated registration. In cases where the update is [change of tonnage], then the Agency shall check the completeness of the information supplied by the registrant and Article 20(2) shall apply adapted as necessary.*
- Article 124: *Competent authorities shall submit electronically to the Agency any available information that they hold on substances registered ... whose dossiers do not contain the full information referred to in Annex VII, in particular whether enforcement or monitoring activities have identified suspicions of risk. The competent authority shall update this information as appropriate.*

Exemption from the general obligation to register for product and process orientated research and development (PPORD)

- Article 9(3): *The Agency shall check the completeness of the information supplied by the notifier and Article 20(2) shall apply adapted as necessary. The Agency shall assign a number to the notification and a notification date, which shall be the date of receipt of the notification at the Agency, and shall forthwith communicate that number and date to the manufacturer, or importer, or producer of articles concerned. The Agency shall also communicate this information to the competent authority of the Member State(s) concerned.*
- Article 9(4): *The Agency may decide to impose conditions with the aim of ensuring that the substance or the mixture or article in which the substance is incorporated will be handled only by staff of listed customers as referred to in paragraph 2(e) in reasonably controlled conditions, in accordance with the requirements of legislation for the protection of workers and the environment, and will not be made available to the general public at any time either on its own or in a mixture or article and that remaining quantities will be re-collected for disposal after the exemption period.*

Substance Evaluation⁵⁵

- Article 44(1): *In order to ensure a harmonised approach, the Agency shall in cooperation with the Member States develop criteria for prioritising substances with a view to further evaluation. Prioritisation shall be on a risk-based approach. The criteria shall consider*
 - *Hazard information, for instance structural similarity of the substance with known substances of concern or with substances which are persistent and liable to bio-accumulate, suggesting*

⁵⁵ <https://echa.europa.eu/regulations/reach/evaluation>

that the substance or one or more of its transformation products has properties of concern or is persistent and liable to bio-accumulate

- *Exposure information*
- *Tonnage, including aggregated tonnage from the registrations submitted by several registrations*
- *Article 44(2): The Agency shall use the criteria in paragraph 1 for the purpose of compiling a draft Community rolling action plan which shall cover a period of three years and shall specify substances to be evaluated each year. Substances shall be included if there are grounds for considering (either on the basis of a dossier evaluation carried out by the Agency or on the basis of any other appropriate source, including information in the registration dossier) that a given substance constitutes a risk to human health or the environment ... The Agency shall submit draft annual updates to the rolling action plan to the Member States by 28 February each year.*
- *Article 46(4): The competent authority shall finish its evaluation activities within 12 months of the start of the evaluation of the substance or within 12 months of the information being submitted under [Article 46(2)], and notify the Agency accordingly. If this deadline is exceeded, the evaluation shall be deemed to be finished.*
- *Article 47: An evaluation of a substance shall be based on all relevant information submitted on that particular substance and on any previous evaluation ... Where information on intrinsic properties of a substance has been generated by reference to structurally related substance(s), the evaluation may also cover these related substances. In cases where a decision on an evaluation has been previously taken in accordance with Article 51 or Article 52, any draft decision requiring further information ... may be justified only by a change of circumstances or acquired knowledge.*
- *Article 48: Once the substance evaluation has been completed, the competent authority shall consider how to use the information obtained from this evaluation for the purposes of Article 59(3), Article 69(4) and Article 115(1). The competent authority shall inform the Agency of its conclusions as to whether or how to use the information obtained. The Agency shall in turn inform the Commission, the registrant and the competent authorities of the other Member States.*
- *Article 49: For on-site isolated intermediates that are used in strictly controlled conditions, neither dossier nor substance evaluation shall apply. However, where the competent authority of the Member States in whose territory the site is located considers that a risk to human health or the environment, equivalent to the level of concern arising from the use of substances meeting the criteria in Article 57, arises from the use of an on-site isolated intermediate and that risk is not properly controlled, it may*
 - *Require the registrant to submit further information directly related to the risk identified. This request shall be accompanied by a written justification*
 - *Examine any information submitted and, if necessary, recommend any appropriate risk reduction measures to address the risks identified in relation to the site in question*

Identification of substances of very high concern (Article 59)⁵⁶

- *The Commission may ask the Agency to prepare a dossier in accordance with relevant Sections of Annex XV for substances which in its opinion meet the criteria set out in Article 57. The dossier may be limited, if appropriate, to a reference to an entry in Part 3 of Annex VI to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008.*

⁵⁶ *Guidance on the preparation of an Annex XV dossier for the identification of substances of very high concern, Version 2.1, October 2018, including legal framework, and preparation of an Annex XV dossier for the identification of substances of very high concern (Article 57 of REACH):*
https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/svhc_en.pdf/8faef33c-b46e-4186-8b7c-8cfbeccd0812

- *Any Member State may prepare a dossier in accordance with Annex XV for substances which in its opinion meet the criteria set out in Article 57 and forward it to the Agency. The dossier may be limited, if appropriate, to a reference to an entry in Part 3 of Annex VI to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008.*
- *The Agency shall publish on its website a notice that an Annex XV dossier has been prepared for a substance. The Agency shall invite all interested parties to submit comments within a specified deadline to the Agency.*
- *If the Agency does not receive or make any comments, it shall include this substance on the [Candidate list]. The Agency may include this substance in its recommendations [as priority for inclusion].*
- *When comments are made or received, the Agency shall refer the dossier to the Member State Committee ...*
- *If, within 30 days of the referral, the Member State Committee reaches a unanimous agreement on the identification, the Agency shall include the substance in the [Candidate list]. The Agency may include this substance in its recommendations [as priority for inclusion].*
- *If the Member State Committee fails to reach a unanimous agreement, the Commission shall prepare a draft proposal on the identification of the substance within three months of receipt of the opinion of the Member State Committee. A final decision on the identification of the substance shall be taken in accordance with the procedure referred to in Article 133(3).*

Authorisation

- *Article 55: The aim ... is to ensure the good functioning of the internal market while assuring that the risks from substances of very high concern are properly controlled and that these substances are progressively replaced by suitable alternative substances or technologies where these are economically and technically viable. To this end all manufacturers, importers and downstream users applying for authorisation shall analyse the availability of alternatives and consider their risks, and the technical and economic feasibility of substitution.*
- *Article 58(1): Whenever a decision is taken to include in Annex XIV substances referred to in Article 57, such a decision shall be taken in accordance with the procedure ... It shall specify for each substance*
 - *the identity of the substance as specified in Section 2 of Annex VI*
 - *the intrinsic property (properties) of the substance referred to in Article 57*
 - *transitional arrangements:*
 - *the date(s) from which the placing on the market and the use of the substance shall be prohibited unless an authorisation is granted (hereinafter referred to as the sunset date) which should take into account, where appropriate, the production cycle specified for that use;*
 - *a date or dates at least 18 months before the sunset date(s) by which applications must be received if the applicant wishes to continue to use the substance or place it on the market for certain uses after the sunset date(s); these continued uses shall be allowed after the sunset date until a decision on the application for authorisation is taken;*
 - *review periods for certain uses, if appropriate;*
 - *uses or categories of uses exempted from the authorisation requirement, if any, and conditions for such exemptions, if any.*
- *Article 58(3): Prior to a decision to include substances in Annex XIV, the Agency shall, taking into account the opinion of the Member State Committee, recommend priority substances to be included specifying for each substance the items set out [above]. Priority shall normally be given to substances with PBT or vPvB properties, wide dispersive use, or high volumes. The number of substances included in Annex XIV and the dates specified [above] shall also take account of the Agency's capacity to handle applications in the time provided for ... The Agency shall make further recommendations at least every second year with a view to including further substances in Annex XIV.*

- Article 58(5): ... after inclusion of a substance in Annex XIV, this substance shall not be subjected to new restrictions ... covering the risks to human health or the environment from the use of the substance on its own, in a mixture or incorporation of a substance in an article arising from the intrinsic properties specified in Annex XIV
- Article 58(6): A substance listed in Annex XIV may be subjected to new restrictions ... covering the risks to human health or the environment from the presence of the substance in (an) article(s).
- Article 58(7): Substances for which all uses have been prohibited ... or by other Community legislation shall not be included in Annex XIV or shall be removed from it.
- Article 58(8): Substances which as a result of new information no longer meet the criteria of Article 57 shall be removed from Annex XIV ...

Granting of authorizations (Article 60)

- The Commission shall be responsible for taking decisions on applications for authorisation ...
- Without prejudice to paragraph 3, an authorisation shall be granted if the risk to human health or the environment from the use of a substance arising from the intrinsic properties specified in Annex XIV is adequately controlled in accordance with Section 6.4 of Annex I⁵⁷ and as documented in the applicant's chemical safety report, taking into account the opinion of the Committee for Risk Assessment ... When granting the authorisation, and in any conditions imposed therein, the Commission shall take into account all discharges, emissions and losses, including risks arising from diffuse or dispersive uses, known at the time of the decision.
 - The Commission shall not consider the risks to human health arising from the use of a substance in a medical device regulated by Council Directive 90/385/EEC ... Council Directive 93/42/EEC ... or Directive 98/79/EC.
 - [This paragraph] shall not apply to
 - Substances meeting the criteria in Article 57(a), (b), (c) [CMR] or (f) for which it is not possible to determine a threshold in accordance with Section 6.4 of Annex I
 - Substances meeting the criteria in Article 57(d) or (e) [PBT or vPvB]
 - Substances identified under Article 57(f) having persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic properties or very persistent and very bioaccumulative properties
 - If an authorisation cannot be granted under [this paragraph] or for substances listed [right above], an authorisation may only be granted if it is shown that socio-economic benefits outweigh the risk to human health or the environment arising from the use of the substance and if there are no suitable alternative substances or technologies. This decision shall be taken after consideration of all of the following elements and taking account the opinions of the Committee for Risk Assessment and the Committee for Socio-economic Analysis ...
 - The risk posed by the uses of the substance, including the appropriateness and effectiveness of the risk management measures proposed
 - The socio-economic benefits arising from its use and the socio-economic implications of a refusal to authorise as demonstrated by the applicant or the interested parties
 - The analysis of the alternatives submitted by the applicant ... or any substitution plan submitted by the applicant ..., and any third party contributions submitted ...

⁵⁷ For any exposure scenario, the risk to humans and the environment can be considered to be adequately controlled, throughout the lifecycle of the substance that results from manufacture or identified uses, if:

- the exposure levels estimated in Section 6.2 do not exceed the appropriate DNEL or the PNEC, as determined in Sections 1 and 3, respectively, and,
- the likelihood and severity of an event occurring due to the physicochemical properties of the substance as determined in Section 2 is negligible. [A]

- *When assessing whether suitable alternative substances or technologies are available, all relevant aspects shall be taken into account by the Commission, including*
 - *Whether the transfer to alternatives would result in reduced overall risks to human health and the environment, taking into account the appropriateness and effectiveness of risk management measures*
 - *The technical and economic feasibility of alternatives for the applicant*
- *Available information on the risks to human health or the environment of any alternative substances or technologies*
- *Article 64(4): The draft opinions shall include the following elements*
 - *Committee for Risk Assessment: an assessment of the risk to human health and/or the environment arising from the use(s) of the substance, including the appropriateness and effectiveness of the risk management measures as described in the application and, if relevant, an assessment of the risks arising from possible alternatives*
 - *Committee for Socio-economic Analysis: an assessment of the socio-economic factors and the availability, suitability and technical feasibility of alternatives associated with the use(s) of the substance as described in the application, when an application is made ... and of any third party contributions submitted ...*
- *A use shall not be authorised if this would constitute a relaxation of a restriction set out in Annex XVII*
- *Authorisation shall be subject to a time-limited review without prejudice to any decision on a future review period and shall normally be subject to conditions, including monitoring. The duration of the time-limited review for any authorisation shall be determined on a case-by-case basis taking into account all relevant information ...*
- *The authorisation shall specify*
 - *The person(s) to whom the authorisation is granted*
 - *The identity of the substance(s)*
 - *The use(s) for which the authorisation is granted*
 - *Any conditions under which the authorisation is granted*
 - *The time-limited review period*
 - *Any monitoring arrangement*
- *Notwithstanding any conditions of an authorisation, the holder shall ensure that the exposure is reduced to as low a level as is technically and practically possible*

Restrictions

- *Article 68: When there is an unacceptable risk to human health or the environment, arising from the manufacture, use or placing on the market of substances, which needs to be addressed on a Community-wide basis, Annex XVII shall be amended ... by adopting new restrictions, or amending current restrictions in Annex XVII, for the manufacture, use or placing on the market of substances on their own, in mixtures or in articles ... Any such decision shall take into account the socio-economic impact of the restriction, including the availability of alternatives.*
 - *... shall not apply to the use of a substance as an on-site isolated intermediate*
 - *For a substance on its own, in a mixture or in an article which meets the criteria for classification in the hazard classes carcinogenicity, germ cell mutagenicity or reproductive toxicity, category 1A or 1B, and could be used by consumers and for which restrictions to*

consumer use are proposed by the Commission, Annex XVII shall be amended ... Articles 69 to 73 shall not apply.

- Article 69: preparation of a proposal
 - *If the Commission considers that the manufacture, placing on the market or use of a substance on its own, in a mixture or in an article poses a risk to human health or the environment that is not adequately controlled and needs to be addressed, it shall ask the Agency to prepare a dossier which conforms to the requirements of Annex XV.⁵⁸*
 - *Within 12 months of the receipt of the request from the Commission ... and if this dossier demonstrates that action on a Community-wide basis is necessary, beyond any measures already in place, the Agency shall suggest restrictions, in order to initiate the restrictions process.*
 - *After the date referred to in Article 58(1)(c)(i) for a substance listed in Annex XIV, the Agency shall consider whether the use of that substance in articles poses a risk to human health or the environment that is not adequately controlled. If the Agency considers that the risk is not adequately controlled, it shall prepare a dossier which conforms to the requirements of Annex XV.*
 - *If a Member State considers that the manufacture, placing on the market or use of a substance on its own, in a mixture or in an article poses a risk to human health or the environment that is not adequately controlled and needs to be addressed it shall notify the Agency that it proposes to prepare a dossier which conforms to the requirements of the relevant sections of Annex XV. If the substance is not on the list maintained by the Agency referred to in paragraph 5 of this Article, the Member State shall prepare a dossier which conforms to the requirements of Annex XV within 12 months of the notification to the Agency. If this dossier demonstrates that action on a Community-wide basis is necessary, beyond any measures already in place, the Member State shall submit it to the Agency in the format outlined in Annex XV, in order to initiate the restrictions process.*
 - *The Agency shall maintain a list of substances for which a dossier conforming to the requirements of Annex XV is planned or underway by either the Agency or a Member State for the purposes of a proposed restriction. If a substance is on the list, no other such dossier shall be prepared. If it is proposed by either a Member State or the Agency that an existing restriction listed in Annex XVII should be re-examined a decision on whether to do so shall be taken in accordance with the procedure referred to in Article 133(2) based on evidence presented by the Member State or the Agency.*
 - *The Agency or Member States shall refer to any dossier, chemical safety report or risk assessment submitted to the Agency or Member State under this Regulation. The Agency or Member States shall also refer to any relevant risk assessment submitted for the purposes of other Community Regulations or Directives. To this end other bodies, such as agencies, established under Community law and carrying out a similar task shall provide information to the Agency or Member State concerned on request.*

⁵⁸ *Guidance for the preparation of an Annex XV dossier for restrictions, June 2007, including legal framework, what prompts a restriction dossier, information for the preparation of a restriction dossier, preparation of an Annex XV restrictions dossier:* https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/restriction_en.pdf/d48a00bf-cd8d-4575-8acc-c1bbe9f9c3f6

Guidance on socio-economic analysis – restrictions, May 2008, including the SEA process – stage 2: scoping phase, the SEA process – stage 3: identifying and assessing impacts, the SEA process – stage 4: interpretation and conclusion drawing, the SEA process – stage 5: presenting the results: https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/sea_restrictions_en.pdf/2d7c8e06-b5dd-40fc-b646-3467b5082a9d

- *The Committee for Risk Assessment and the Committee for Socio-economic Analysis shall check whether the dossier submitted conforms to the requirements of Annex XV. Within 30 days of receipt, the respective Committee shall inform the Agency or the Member State suggesting restrictions, as to whether the dossier conforms. If the dossier does not conform, the reasons shall be given to the Agency or the Member State in writing within 45 days of receipt. The Agency or the Member State shall bring the dossier into conformity within 60 days of the date of receipt of the reasons from the Committees, otherwise the procedure under this Chapter shall be terminated. The Agency shall publish without delay the intention of the Commission or of a Member State to instigate a restriction procedure for a substance and shall inform those who submitted a registration for that substance.*
- *Article 69(6): Without prejudice to Articles 118 and 119, the Agency shall make publicly available on its website all dossiers conforming with Annex XV including the restrictions suggested pursuant to paragraphs 3 and 4 of this Article without delay, clearly indicating the date of publication. The Agency shall invite all interested parties to submit individually or jointly within six months of the date of publication:*
 - *(a) comments on dossiers and the suggested restrictions;*
 - *(b) a socio-economic analysis, or information which can contribute to one, of the suggested restrictions, examining the advantages and drawbacks of the proposed restrictions. It shall conform to the requirements in Annex XVI.*
- *Article 70: Within nine months of the date of publication referred to in Article 69(6), the Committee for Risk Assessment shall formulate an opinion as to whether the suggested restrictions are appropriate in reducing the risk to human health and/or the environment, based on its consideration of the relevant parts of the dossier. This opinion shall take account of the Member State dossier or of the dossier prepared by the Agency at the request of the Commission, and the views of interested parties referred to in Article 69(6)(a).*
- *Article 71: Within 12 months of the date of publication [list of intended restriction], the Committee for Socio-economic Analysis shall formulate an opinion on the suggested restrictions, based on its consideration of the relevant parts of the dossier and the socio-economic impact. It shall prepare a draft opinion on the suggested restrictions and on the related socio-economic impact, taking account of the analyses or information according to Article 69(6)(b), if there are any. The Agency shall publish the draft opinion on its website without delay. The Agency shall invite interested parties to give their comments on the draft opinion no later than 60 days from the publication of that draft opinion.*
 - *The Committee for Socio-economic Analysis shall without delay adopt its opinion, taking into account where appropriate further comments received by the deadline set ...*
 - *Where the opinion of the Committee for Risk Assessment diverges significantly from the restrictions suggested, the Agency may postpone the deadline for the opinion of the Committee for Socio-economic Analysis by a maximum of 90 days.*
- *Article 73: If the conditions laid down in Article 68 are fulfilled, the Commission shall prepare a draft amendment to Annex XVII, within three months of receipt of the opinion of the Committee for Socio-economic Analysis or by the end of the deadline established under Article 71 if that Committee does not form an opinion, whichever is the earlier.*
 - *Where the draft amendment diverges from the original proposal or if it does not take the opinions from the Agency into account, the Commission shall annex a detailed explanation of the reasons for the differences.*

Safeguard clause (Article 129)

- *Where a Member State has justifiable grounds for believing that urgent action is essential to protect human health or the environment in respect of a substance, on its own, in a mixture or in an article, even*

if satisfying the requirements of this Regulation, it may take appropriate provisional measures. The Member State shall immediately inform the Commission, the Agency and the other Member States thereof, giving reasons for its decision and submitting the scientific or technical information on which the provisional measure is based.

- *The Commission shall take a decision in accordance with the procedure referred to in Article 133(3) within 60 days of receipt of the information from the Member State. This decision shall either:*
 - *authorise the provisional measure for a time period defined in the decision; or*
 - *require the Member State to revoke the provisional measure.*
 - *If, in the case of a decision ..., the provisional measure taken by the Member State consists in a restriction on the placing on the market or use of a substance, the Member State concerned shall initiate a Community restrictions procedure by submitting to the Agency a dossier, in accordance with Annex XV, within three months of the date of the Commission decision.*
 - *In the case of a decision ..., the Commission shall consider whether this Regulation needs to be adapted.*

8. Data submission format

IUCLID

9. Data confidentiality

Exemption from the general obligation to register for product and process orientated research and development (PPORD)

- *Article 9(9): The Agency and the competent authorities of the Member States concerned shall always keep confidential the information submitted.*

Access to information (Articles 118 and 119)

- *Regulation (EC) No 1049/2001 shall apply to documents held by the Agency.*
- *Disclosure of the following information shall normally be deemed to undermine the protection of the commercial interests of the concern person*
 - *Details of the full composition of a mixture*
 - *Without prejudice to Article 7(6) and Article 64(2) [application for authorisation], the precise use, function or application of a substance or mixture, including information about its precise use as an intermediate*
 - *The precise tonnage of the substance or mixture manufactured or placed on the market*
 - *Links between a manufacturer or importer and his distributors or downstream users*
- *When urgent action is essential to protect human health, safety or the environment, such as emergency situations, the Agency may disclose the information referred to [above]*
- *Article 119(2): The following information on substances whether on their own, in mixtures or in articles, shall be made publicly available, free of charge, over the Internet ... except where a party submitting the information submits a justification ..., accepted as valid by the Agency, as to why such publication is potentially harmful for the commercial interests of the registrant or any other party concerned:*
 - *if essential to classification and labelling, the degree of purity of the substance and the identity of impurities and/or additives which are known to be dangerous*
 - *the total tonnage band (i.e. 1 to 10 tonnes, 10 to 100 tonnes, 100 to 1 000 tonnes or over 1 000 tonnes) within which a particular substance has been registered*
 - *the study summaries or robust study summaries of [physicochemical data and toxicological and ecotoxicological study]*
 - *information, other than that listed in paragraph 1, contained in the safety data sheet*
 - *the trade name(s) of the substance*

- *subject to Article 24 of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008, the name in the IUPAC nomenclature for non-phase-in substances referred to in paragraph 1(a) of this Article for a period of six years*
- *subject to Article 24 of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008, the name in the IUPAC nomenclature for substances referred to in paragraph 1(a) of this Article that are only used as one or more of the following*
 - *as an intermediate*
 - *in scientific research and development*
 - *in product and process orientated research and development*

10. Data that are published publicly (Article 119)

- *The following information held by the Agency on substances whether on their own, in mixtures or in articles, shall be made publicly available, free of charge, over the Internet ...*
 - *without prejudice to paragraph 2(f) and (g) of this Article, the name in the IUPAC nomenclature for substances fulfilling the criteria for any of the following hazard classes or categories set out in Annex I to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008:*
 - *hazard classes 2.1 to 2.4, 2.6 and 2.7, 2.8 types A and B, 2.9, 2.10, 2.12, 2.13 categories 1 and 2, 2.14 categories 1 and 2, 2.15 types A to F*
 - *hazard classes 3.1 to 3.6, 3.7 adverse effects on sexual function and fertility or on development, 3.8 effects other than narcotic effects, 3.9 and 3.10*
 - *hazard class 4.1*
 - *hazard class 5.1*
 - *if applicable, the name of the substance as given in EINECS*
 - *the classification and labelling of the substance*
 - *physicochemical data concerning the substance and on pathways and environmental fate*
 - *the result of each toxicological and ecotoxicological study*
 - *any derived no-effect level (DNEL) or predicted no-effect concentration (PNEC) established in accordance with Annex I*
 - *the guidance on safe use provided in accordance with Sections 4 and 5 of Annex VI*
 - *analytical methods if requested in accordance with Annexes IX or X which make it possible to detect a dangerous substance when discharged into the environment as well as to determine the direct exposure of humans.*
- *Article 123: The competent authorities of the Member States shall inform the general public about the risks arising from substances where this is considered necessary for the protection of human health or the environment. The Agency, in consultation with competent authorities and stakeholders and drawing as appropriate on relevant best practice, shall provide guidance for the communication of information on the risks and safe use of chemical substances, on their own, in mixtures or in articles, with a view to coordinating Member States in these activities.⁵⁹*

11. International information exchange and sharing (Article 120)

- *Notwithstanding Articles 118 and 119, information received by the Agency under this Regulation may be disclosed to any government or national authority of a third country or an international organisation*

⁵⁹ *Guidance on the communication of information on the risks and safe use of chemicals, Version 1, December 2010, including when is risk communication needed, understanding the issue, determining communication needs, implementing risk communications, evaluation and review, applying the approach in different situations: https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/risk_communications_en.pdf/8c0cbe98-bdae-476a-8c6c-1821f71aff9d*

in accordance with an agreement concluded between the Community and the third party concerned under Regulation (EC) No 304/2003 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2003 concerning the export and import of dangerous chemicals or under Article 181a(3) of the Treaty, provided that both the following conditions are met:

- the purpose of the agreement is cooperation on the implementation or management of legislation concerning chemicals covered by this Regulation;*
- the third party protects the confidential information as mutually agreed.*

S1.6 Inventory of Existing Chemical Substances Produced or Imported in China (IECSC)

Last update: 9 June 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. 新化学物质环境管理登记办法 / **Measures** for the Environmental Management Registration of New Chemical Substances (2020; in Chinese):
https://www.mee.gov.cn/xxgk2018/xxgk/xxgk02/202005/t20200507_777913.html;
<http://www.lawinfochina.com/display.aspx?id=32814&lib=law> (informal translation)
- B. 新化学物质环境管理登记指南 / Guidance for the Environmental Management Registration of New Chemicals Substances (2020; in Chinese):
http://www.mee.gov.cn/xxgk2018/xxgk/xxgk01/202011/t20201119_808843.html
- C. IECSC (latest update in April 2021): <https://www.mee.gov.cn/ywgz/gtfwyhxpjgl/hxphjgl/wzml/>

Note: The texts below are based on informal translation.

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory [A]

- Distinction between **new vs. existing** chemical substances
- The initial inventory was published in 2013, consisting of chemical substances that were produced, sold, processed, used or imported in the People's Republic of China between 1 January 1992 and 15 Oct. 2003⁶⁰. Since 2016, it has been updated several times to include newly registered chemical substances.

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligation to register [A]

- the environmental management registration of the activities in relation to the research, production, import, and processing or use⁶¹ of new chemical substances⁶² (those that are not listed in IECSC) within the territory of the People's Republic of China.
- The new chemical substances contained in the articles which are designed to intentionally release such new chemical substances during their normal use shall be governed by these Measures (e.g. pen, ink box, fire extinguisher, rubber with parfum).
- Where the chemical substances shall be subject to new-use environmental management⁶³ according to the IECSC are used for industrial purposes other than allowed ones, they shall be subject to environmental management as new chemicals substances.
 - For highly hazardous chemical substances, if the registration certificate holder changes their use, or others other than the registration certificate holders use them in industrial uses, they shall

⁶⁰ The applicant may still apply for listing of existing chemical substances with relevant proofs. [B]

⁶¹ Processing or use refers to business activities such as packaging, formulating, or manufacture. It does not include business activities such as trade, storage and transport, nor activities of using articles containing new chemical substances. [A]

⁶² Including both pure substances and mixtures, also including UVCBs and polymers. Polymers are defined as: (1) the same as OECD definition of polymers; (2) *is a substance composed of more than 50% of molecules containing a sequence of at least three monomer units covalently bound to at least one other monomer unit or other reactant*; (3) *has molecules distributed over a range of MW; and (4) has no single MW molecule reaching 50% (w/w) of total molecules.* [B]

⁶³ 新用途管理要求 in Chinese, it is the name of management of dangerous substance in these measures, including highly hazardous chemical substances (persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic substances, very persistent and very bioaccumulative substances or other substances of equivalent environmental or health concern) and substances that are persistent and bioaccumulative, persistent and toxic, or bioaccumulative and toxic. [A]

apply for new-use environmental management registration before production, import, or processing or use (Article 31).

- For substances that are persistent and bioaccumulative, persistent and toxic, or bioaccumulative and toxic, if it is used in areas other than those granted, the applicant shall for new-use environmental management registration before production, import, or processing or use (Article 31).

3.2 Excluded from the Measures [A]

- New chemical substances that are stored in the areas under special customs supervision after import and are completely exported without any processing.
- Pharmaceuticals, pesticides, veterinary medicines, cosmetics, food, food additive, feed, feed additive, fertiliser, and other products, **except** for the new chemical substances that change to be used for other industrial purposes and the new chemical substances used as the raw materials and intermediates of the aforementioned products.
- Radioactive material.

2.3 Exemptions from new chemical substances environmental management registration [B]

- Naturally occurring substances
 - Non-processed or only physically processed via hand-craft, mechanics, gravity, water dissolution, water suspension, and heat dehydration
 - Extracted from air
 - Natural polymers without chemical processing
 - Bio-materials without chemical processing that changes chemical structures, such as DNA, RNA and proteins
- Non-commercial or non-intentional production
 - Impurities, have no contribution to product function, possibly originated from raw materials, reaction by-products or unreacted residuals, non-desired but present in the final products; each impurity should not be more than 10 wt%, and total should not be more than 20 wt%
 - Chemical reaction products, particularly from reaction by coincidence, with environmental factors (e.g. air, water vapor, microbials or sunlight, etc.), during storage and during final use
 - Exhaust, wastewater, solid waste and by-products from reaction
- Other special types
 - Materials: glasses, glass raw materials, ceramic raw materials and items, steel and steel products, concrete products, etc.
 - Alloys: homogenous or heterogenous solids or liquid made from two or more metals or one metal and other non-metals, **except** intermetallic compounds with precise definition
 - Non-isolated intermediates (other types of intermediates are covered by the Measures)
 - Articles
 - Products that are themselves not human-made, -imported or -sold, but have specific functions, or chemical substances that are resulted from reactions when the preparations perform specific functions, e.g. surface treatment agents, chelating agent, flocculant, adhesion promoters
 - Mixtures that are intentionally mixed without generating new chemical substances
 - Anhydrous and hydrates need to be registered only once

4. Initial data requirements [A]

The environmental management registration of new chemical substances shall be classified into regular registration, simplified registration and recordation. The producers or importers of new chemical substances shall obtain registration certificates or undergo the recordation formalities before production or import. (Article 10)

- **Regular registration:** Where a new chemical substance produced or imported is more than 10 metric tons per year. An applicant shall submit the following materials (Article 15):
 - Application form
 - Test reports (preferred, with signature and stamp from the testing institution) or data on the physicochemical properties, health toxicology and ecotoxicology characteristics⁶⁴ of the new chemical substance. The relevant test report and materials shall meet the needs of the environmental risk assessment⁶⁵ of the new chemical substance, and the ecotoxicology test report shall include the data on the test completed on the test organisms of the People's Republic of China⁶⁶ in accordance with the relevant standards. Details on test requirements see [B].
 - Environmental risk assessment report of the new chemical substance,⁶⁷ including the assessment of possible environmental risks, analysis of the environmental risk control measures to be adopted and their suitability, and the assessment conclusion of whether there are unreasonable environmental risks.
 - A letter of commitment to implementing or transmitting environmental risk control measures and environmental management requirements, which shall be signed by the legal representative of the enterprise or institution or its authorized person and affixed with an official seal.
 - For **highly hazardous chemical substances**⁶⁸, the applicant shall also submit the analysis materials of the social and economic benefits of the activities in relation to the new chemical substance,⁶⁹ including explanations of whether the new chemical substance has equivalent or obvious advantages over the chemical substances in use for the same purpose in terms of performance and environmental friendliness, among others. The analysis shall fully demonstrate the necessity of the application.
 - Other information on the environmental and health hazard characteristics and environmental risks that of the new chemical substance the applicant has obtained.⁷⁰
 - Documentation on the testing institutions [B]
 - For polymers, the applicant must provide polymer characterization information (see recordation below), residual levels of monomers, levels of metals or cations. When meeting all of the following conditions, the applicants are exempted from providing health toxicological and ecotoxicological data and environmental risk assessment report: (1) not containing metals other than potassium, magnesium, kalium and calcium; (2) not soluble in water, lipophilic solvents (n-hexanol, n-heptane) and common solvents (tetrahydrofuran, dimethylformamide); (3) stability under acidic or basic conditions [pH = 4.0, 7.0, 9.0 and 1.2 (when important for biological uses) [B]

⁶⁴ E.g. in accordance with the GB/T 24782, GB 30000 series (2–29 based on GHS version 4) and other guidelines published by the ecological and environmental department of the State Council; for more details, see [B].

⁶⁵ It does not include risks from accidents. [A]

⁶⁶ This refers to organisms that are bred in China, match standardized test methods or technical requirements, and are used for specific tests, including *Gobiocypris rarus* and active sludge from China. [B]

⁶⁷ Detailed requirements can be found in [B].

⁶⁸ The applicant should based on the minimum data requirements and all known information and conduct PBT/vPvB/substance of equivalent environmental or health concern assessment, and make conclusive determination and provide complete assessment description. Detailed criteria can be found in [B].

⁶⁹ For details including the report template, see [B].

⁷⁰ Including testing data, estimation results (QSAR, read-across), authoritative database literature, theses and environmental risk assessment data. If analogs to the applied new chemical substances are known to have persistence, bioaccumulation and high hazards to the environment or health, or last long in the environment and can pose rather significant risks to the environment and health, the applicant shall provide such analog information as well. When estimation results are provided, justification, methods or data sources need to be provided. [B]

- **Simplified registration:** Where a new chemical substance produced or imported is more than 1 and less than 10 metric tons per year. An applicant shall submit the following materials (Article 16)
 - Application form
 - Test reports (preferred with signature and stamp from the testing institution) or materials on the physicochemical properties of the new chemical substance, as well as persistence, bioaccumulation, aquatic environmental toxicity and other ecotoxicology. The ecotoxicology test reports shall include the data on the test conducted on the test organisms of the People's Republic of China according to the relevant standards. Details on test requirements see [B].
 - A letter of commitment to implement or transmitting environmental risk control measures, which shall be signed by the legal representative or authorized person of the enterprise or institution and affixed with an official seal.
 - Other information about the environmental and health hazard characteristics and environmental risks of the new chemical substance that the applicant has obtained.
 - Documentation on the testing institutions [B]
 - For polymers, the same requirements as for regular registration, see above.
- **Recordation:** Where a new chemical substance produced or imported is less than 1 metric ton per year, or the new chemical substance is a polymer with the monomer or reactant content of less than 2%⁷¹ or a polymer of low concern.⁷² An applicant shall submit the following materials (Article 36)
 - Application form and proofing documents that the chemical substances meet the requirements
 - the environmental and health hazard characteristics, and environmental risks of the new chemical substances that the applicant has obtained.
 - Once submitted the recordation files, the applicant may conduct the relevant activities.
 - When applying for recordation of polymers, the applicants shall provide the following information: (1) a list of monomers and reactants, including chemical names, CASRN, content ratio (usage/total polymer weight) and listing status in IECSC; (2) molecular weight distribution graphs (must have), including gel permeation chromatography or other characterization results of the polymer molecular weight and distribution such as number average molecular weight; (3)

⁷¹ Either polymers themselves are not in IECSC, but new chemical substance monomers/reactants are equal to or below 2%; or polymers themselves are not in IECSC, but all monomers/reactants are listed in IECSC. [B]

⁷² When meeting one of the following conditions: (1) Number average molecular weight (NAWM) is between 1000–10000 Da, oligomers of less than 500 Da <10%, oligomers of less than 1000 Da <25%, no reactive functional group of high concern [e.g. heavy metals, Cyano (except non-conjugated), acrylates, aziridine, isocyanates (except capped isocyanates), thioisocyanates, vinyl sulfone, alkoxy silanes (alkyl is methyl or ethyl), amines, spiroalkylamines, halo-silanes, hydrazines, alpha/beta lactones, methacrylates, etc.]; (2) NAWM ≥ 10000 Da, oligomers of less than 500 Da <2%, oligomers of less than 1000 Da <5; or (3) belonging to polyesters.

When meeting one of the following conditions, polymers must undergo either regular or simplified registration: (1) cationic polymers (e.g., containing ions with phosphonium, sulfonium, ammonium ions, etc.) or that are expected to become cationic in a natural aqueous environment (e.g. polymers containing amine groups, isocyanates, etc.); (2) degradable or unstable polymers, including polymers that are susceptible to degradation, decomposition or depolymerisation, as well as polymers that decompose after production or use; (3) absorbent polymers (that are capable of absorbing water of their own weight) with a NAWM ≥ 10,000; (4) fluoropolymers containing a perfluoroalkanesulfonic acid group, a perfluoroalkylcarboxylic acid group, or a fluorotelomer moiety in the structure; and fluoropolymers containing a perfluoroalkyl moiety covalently bonded to a carbon or sulfur atom in the polymer molecule; (5) containing, in addition to impurities, elements other than those permitted below: the polymer components must contain at least two elements of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, oxygen, sulphur or silicon (C, H, N, O, S or Si), additional elements: fluorine, chlorine, bromine and iodine (F, Cl, Br and I) covalently bound to carbon, as well as chlorides, bromides and iodides (Cl⁻, Br⁻ and I⁻) in mono-ionic form, other permitted mono-ionic elements are sodium, magnesium, aluminium, potassium and calcium (Na⁺, Mg²⁺, Al³⁺, K⁺ and Ca²⁺), as well as lithium, boron, phosphorus, titanium, manganese, iron, nickel, copper, zinc, tin and zirconium (Li, B, P, Ti, Mn, Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn, Sn and Zr) in less than 0.20% by weight.

polymerization reaction mechanisms, including using figures or text to describe the monomers, conditions, process and mechanisms of the polymerization; and (4) justification why it does not need to undergo regular or simplified registration (see footnote below). [B]

- An applicant may file applications for the environmental management registration of **several new chemical substances with similar molecular structures, identical or similar uses, and similar test data**. The registered quantity applied for shall be determined based on the total of the registered quantities of all substances that the applicant has applied for.
- If two or more applicants apply for the environmental management registration of the same new chemical substance at the same time, they may jointly submit application materials.

To apply for new-use environmental management registration, the applicant shall provide

- Application form
- Accompany materials such as assessment reports of environmental exposure for the applied new use and environmental risk control measures. For highly hazardous chemical substances, also materials that analyse socio-economic benefits, fully demonstrating the necessity of the new use

The **testing institutions** within the territory of the People's Republic of China that provide test data for the environmental management registration of new chemical substances shall be **accredited** as inspection and testing institutions according to the law, and conduct testing in strict accordance with the relevant **standards** for chemical substance testing; and health toxicology and ecotoxicology testing institutions shall also conform to **good laboratory management practices**. Testing institutions shall be responsible for the authenticity and reliability of the testing results issued by them and shall assume responsibilities according to the law. More details can be found in [B].

- The ecology and environment department of the State Council shall organize the supervision and random inspections of the testing conducted by and conditions for chemical substance ecotoxicology testing institutions.
- The overseas testing institutions of the People's Republic of China that issue health toxicology or ecotoxicology test data shall meet the internationally accepted good laboratory management requirements.
- The testing should preferably follow *Chemical Substances Test Guidelines* and relevant national standards. When OECD test guidelines are updated, and national test methods or relevant national standards are not updated, the testing may follow the latest OECD test guidelines. The testing done abroad may also follow other testing methods that are commonly recognized. For specific testing items without standardized methods, exploratory research methods are allowed, with the requirements of thorough description of method selection, test design and complete test reports.
- The testing should use pure substances (total impurities not more than 20% and each impurity not more than 10%). Test reports must note the purity and provide reasons why it can be further purified. When evidence shows specific impurity may have rather high health toxicological or ecotoxicological hazards, and its content varies (<10%), the test samples should be the one with the highest level of this particular impurity and note the content in the test reports.

5. Data updates by companies

For a new chemical substance that has obtained a regular registration certificate, before it is included in IECSC, the registration certificate holder shall apply for

- a new registration in any of the following circumstances (Article 29). To re-apply for registration, the applicant shall submit the re-registration application materials, explain the reasons for the changes in related matters, re-compile and submit the environmental risk assessment report, focusing on the

environmental risk control measures to be taken after the change, their suitability, and whether unreasonable environmental risks exist.

- The quantity of production or import intends to exceed the quantity applied for registration
- The type of activity is to be changed from import to production
- The use of the chemical substances is to be changed
- The environmental risk control measures are to be changed
- Other situations that lead to increased environmental risks
- a modification of the notification certificate, if the information, except for the aforementioned circumstances in Article 29, of the registration certificate changes
- the registration certificate holder may also apply for cancelling of the registration certificate (Article 33).

For a new chemical substance that has obtained a simple registration certificate, the registration certificate holder shall apply for

- a modification of the certificate if the information contained in the registration certificate changes (Article 30).

When applying for a modification of the registration certificate, the applicant must provide modification reasoning and relevant proofing documents. Among them, when modifying the chemical identity information such as the Chinese and English name or CASRN, the proofing documents must thoroughly elaborate that the chemical substance remains the same after modification (Article 30).

For a new chemical substance that has obtained a recordation archive,

- when changing the filling items or related information of the environmental management of the new chemical substances, the applicant shall make timely modification to the recordation information.

Record keeping

The researcher, producer, importer and processors and users of the new chemical substances shall establish new chemical substance activity record system, recording information such as time, quantity, uses, and implementation status of environmental risk control measures and environmental management requirements.

- For regular and simplified registrations, the records shall be kept for at least 10 years.
- For recordation, the records shall be kept for at least 3 years.

After initial production/import,

- The registration certificate holder shall report Notice of Commencement within sixty days
- If the environmental management requirements in regular registration certificate include annual reporting, the registration certificate holder shall from the second year on, report the actual production or import in the previous year, environmental releases, and implementation status of environmental control measures and environmental management requirements.

When discovering new environmental or health hazard characteristics or environmental risks, researchers, producers, importers, and processing users of new chemical substances shall promptly report to the ecological and environmental department of the State Council; if they may lead to increased environmental risks, measures should be taken in time to eliminate or reduce environmental risks.

After receiving the relevant information, the ecological and environmental department of the State Council shall organize its affiliated chemical substance environmental management technical institution and expert committee to conduct a technical review; if necessary, it may change or withdraw the corresponding notification certificate according to the review results.

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

- After accepting the application for registration, the ecological and environmental department of the State Council shall organize an expert committee and its affiliated chemical substance environmental management technical institution to conduct technical reviews. [A]
 - If the technical review finds that the application materials submitted by the applicant do not meet the requirements or are insufficient to make a comprehensive assessment of the environmental risks of the new chemical substance, the ecological and environmental department of the State Council may require the applicant to provide additional relevant test reports or materials. (Article 19)
 - If the technical review finds that the application materials submitted by the applicant do not meet the requirements, the ecological and environmental department of the State Council may require the applicant to provide additional relevant test reports or materials. (Article 20)
 - If the applicant reject or do not provide supplementary test reports or materials within six months, the ecological and environmental department of the State Council will reject the registration with written notice.
- According to national registration status, actual production/import, environmental releases and newly discovered environmental or health hazard characteristics, for new chemical substances with possible increase in environmental risks, the ecological and environmental department of the State Council may request relevant **researchers**, producers, importers and processing users to further submit relevant environmental or health hazards and environmental exposure information. (Article 42)

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom) [A]

After accepting the application for **regular registration** (Article 19)

- the ecological and environmental department of the State Council shall organize **an expert committee**⁷³ and its affiliated chemical substance environmental management technical institution to conduct a technical review. The technical review should mainly focus on the following contents. The technical review opinions shall include the review conclusions on the following content, as well as recommendations on whether to approve registration and recommendations on environmental management requirements.
 - The name and identification of the new chemical substance
 - The quality of the test report or data of the new chemical substance
 - Environmental and health hazards of new chemical substances
 - Environmental exposure and environmental risks of new chemical substances;
 - Whether subject to new-use environmental management when listed in the IECSC
 - Whether the environmental risk control measures are appropriate;
 - For highly hazardous chemical substances, the necessity of the application
 - The necessity of trade secrets protection.
- If no unreasonable environmental risk is found, the registration shall be granted and shall provide the applicant Regular Registration Certificate. For highly hazardous chemical substances, application activity must also meet the necessity requirement.
- If an unreasonable environmental risk is found, or if it does not meet the necessity requirements for highly hazardous chemical substance application activities, the registration shall not be granted, and the applicant shall be notified in writing and the reasons shall be explained.

After accepting the application for **simple registration** (Article 20),

⁷³ Experts from chemistry, chemical engineering, health, environment, economics and other areas (Article 6) [A]

- the ecological and environmental department of the State Council shall organize its affiliated chemical substance environmental management technical institution to conduct a technical review. The technical review should mainly focus on the following contents. The technical review opinions shall include the review conclusions on the following content, and recommendations on whether to approve registration.
 - The name and identification of the new chemical substance
 - The quality of the test report or data of the new chemical substance
 - Persistence, bioaccumulation and toxicity of the new chemical substances
 - Cumulative environmental risks of new chemical substances
 - The necessity of trade secrets protection.
- If not having persistence, bioaccumulation and toxicity as well as cumulative environmental risks, the registration shall be granted and shall provide the applicant Regular Registration Certificate. If opposite, the registration shall not be granted, and the applicant shall be notified in writing and the reasons shall be explained

After accepting the registration application (Article 25),

- The ecological and environmental department of the State Council shall decide whether to grant the registration within twenty working days. It may be extended for another ten working days by approval of the responsible authority, with a written notice of reasoning to the applicant. The technical review time period does not take into account in the time period for decision.
- The technical review time period for regular registration shall not exceed 60 days, and the technical review time period for simple registration shall not exceed 30 days. When the ecological and environmental department of the State Council requires supplementary provision of relevant test reports or materials, the time period required for the applicant to supplement the relevant materials shall not be included in the technical review time limit.

The registration certificate shall include the following items:

- the type of registration certificate; the name of the applicant and its representative; the labelling information of the new chemical substances such as Chinese and English names; uses; quantity; type of activities; environmental risk control measures (Article 26)
- For highly hazardous chemical substances, or new chemical substances that are persistent and bioaccumulative, persistent and toxic, or bioaccumulative and toxic, the regular registration certificate shall include one or more of the following environmental management requirements: permissible release quantity or concentration; new-use environmental management requirements when listing in IECSC; requirements of providing annual reports; and/or other environmental management requirements.

After receiving a modification application,

- The ecological and environmental department of the State Council accept the modification, organize the technical review and make decision on the registration certificate modification in accordance with the procedures and time frame of simplified registrations. Among them, the Department can organize the expert committee to conduct the technical review when it is to modify the chemical identity information such as Chinese and English names and CASRN; the modification application will be denied when it is not possible to judge whether the chemical substance remains the same after modification.

After receiving a new-use environmental management registration, the ecological and environmental department of the State Council shall

- follow the regular registration procedure, organise a technical review and make a decision.
- publicize within twenty working days the name of the applicant and its agent, chemical name, registered new use, and corresponding environmental risk control measures and environmental management

requirements, when a decision is made. For chemical substances other than highly hazardous ones, add the granted new use in IECSC, whereas for highly hazardous chemical substances, the new-use environmental management is not changed.

In one of the following situation, for the need of public interest, the ecological and environmental department of the State Council in accordance with the relevant laws can modify and revoke the registration certificate:

- if environmental risks increase
- if the registration content does not match the national industrial sector policy
- if relevant laws, regulations or mandatory standards change
- if it contradicts relevant international agreements
- and other legally permitted situation.

After receiving a recordation,

- The ecological and environmental department of the State Council shall archive the complete recordation files and send back an archive receipt.
- The ecological and environmental department of the State Council and its subsidiary technical institution will randomly select records for compliance check.

New information

When receive new information such as hazard environmental or health risks and environmental exposure, the department shall organise a technical review by the subsidiary technical institution and expert committee, and modify or revoke the registration certificate according to the review conclusion, if necessary.

Inspection

Every year, the relevant department shall select producers, importers, and processors or users for inspections, with regard to they have made registration according to these Measures, authenticity of registration information, and implementation status of the items in the registration certificate and other requirements of these Measures.

8. Data submission format

Online registration system [B]

9. Data confidentiality [A]

- The state encourages applicants to share environmental management registration data for new chemical substances. (Article 12)
- If applicants consider that the registration application or recordation materials that they submit involve trade secrets and require information protection, the applicant shall apply for trade secret protection when applying for registration or recordation, and submit the materials explaining the necessity of the application of trade secret protection.⁷⁴
- For the information that may pose a major impact on the environment, health and public interests, the ecological and environmental department of the State Council may **not** grant trade secret protection in accordance with the law.
- The protection period for the name and other labelling information of new chemical substances shall not exceed five years from the date of initial registration or recordation.
- When a new chemical substance is listed in IECSC, the applicant can apply for a up-to-five-year **extension** of trade secret protection of the chemical identity. [B]

⁷⁴ For detailed requirements, see [B].

10. Data that are published publicly [A]

IECSC: Chinese and English names, synonyms, CASRN (or register number for trade secret protection), molecular formulas, granted uses (for some), environmental management types (for some)

The ecological and environmental department of the State Council shall

- before making a registration decision, publicize information such as the name or category name of the new chemical substance to be notified, name of the applicant and its agent, type of activity, and new-use environmental management requirements. The publication period shall not be less than three working days. (Article 24)
- after making a registration decision, publicize the status of the new chemical substance environmental management registration within twenty working days, including the name or category name of the new chemical substance to be notified, name of the applicant and its agent, type of activity, and new-use environmental management requirements.
- regular update on new chemical substances environmental management recordation.
- list the new chemical substances that have obtained the regular registration certificate in IECSC **five years after the initial registration** (including those whose registration certificates were cancelled by the certificate holders according to Article 33) and publicize that. For those new substances that are persistent and bioaccumulative, persistent and toxic, or bioaccumulative and toxic, the listing in IECSC shall also include granted use. For highly hazardous chemical substances, and substances that are persistent and bioaccumulative, persistent and toxic, or bioaccumulative and toxic, the listing in IECSC shall also set environmental management requirements other than annual reporting. Chemicals with simplified registration or recordation and those whose regular registration are revoked by the ecological and environmental department of the State Council are not listed in IECSC (Article 45 notes the procedure for the transitioning period).

The producer, importer, and processor or users of the new chemical substances shall

- provide the following information to downstream users: registration certificate number or recordation archive receipt number, applied uses, environmental and health hazardous properties and environmental risk control measures of the new chemical substance, and environmental management requirements of the new chemical substances (Note that the processor or users have the right to demand such information from the supplier)
- publicize implementation status of environmental risk control measures and environmental management requirements via its official website or other means for the public

11. International information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.7 Taiwan Chemical Substance Inventory (TCSI)

Last update: 16 June 2021

1. Links

- A. Toxic and Concerned Chemical Substances Control Act (2019):
<https://law.moj.gov.tw/ENG/LawClass/LawAll.aspx?pcode=O0060012>
- B. Regulations of New and Existing Chemical Substances Registration (2019):
<https://law.moj.gov.tw/ENG/LawClass/LawAll.aspx?pcode=O0060043>
- C. Guidance on Existing Chemical Substances Standard Registration (2020):
<https://resource.chemlinked.com.cn/chemical/File/既有化學物質標準登錄資料撰寫指引第一版20200608.pdf>
- D. New substance registration and TCSI search website:
<https://csnn.osha.gov.tw/content/home/Index.aspx>;
<https://tcscachemreg.epa.gov.tw/Epareg/content/masterpage/index.aspx>
- E. Existing substances list:
https://gazette.nat.gov.tw/EG_FileManager/eguploadpub/eg021002/ch08/type3/gov82/num32/images/Eg01.pdf (2015); newly added substances
<https://gazette.nat.gov.tw/egFront/detail.do?metaid=78617&log=detailLog> (2015)
- F. Draft amendment of “Regulations for New and Existing Chemical Substances Registration” (May 27 2021) for public comments:
<https://gazette.nat.gov.tw/egFront/detail.do?metaid=124226&log=detailLog> (no changes made in the text below, as the draft has not been adopted yet. Future updates may first consider modifications here).

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

- Distinction between new vs. existing chemicals [A], the initial inventory contains more than 100,000 substances that were manufactured in or imported into Taiwan between 1 Jan 1993 and 31 Dec 2014.
- *A new chemical substance registered and approved in any one of following circumstances may be included in the inventory of existing chemical substances by the central competent authority: [B]*
 - *I. It shall be at least five years after the standard registration is filed and completed.*
 - *II. It shall be at least five years after the PLC registration process is filed and completed in accordance with the small quantity registration.*
 - *III. Toxic chemical substances announced by the central competent authority.*
- *A registrant may apply for inclusion in the inventory of existing chemical substances, when a new chemical substance, registered and approved, meets any of the following situations: [B]*
 - *I. Standard registration that has been filed and completed through submission of information on hazard assessment and exposure assessment.*
 - *II. PLC registration in accordance with the small quantity registration that has been filed and completed.*
- *A new chemical substance registered and approved, which has been included in the inventory of existing chemical substances ... is subject to the related rules of registered and approved existing chemical substances. [B]*

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligation to notify

- Those that manufacture or import certain quantities of **existed chemical substances** each year shall apply to register chemical substance data from the competent authority before the specified deadline. Those enterprises of manufacturing or importing **new chemical substances** shall apply to register chemical

substance data from the competent authority 90 days prior to the aforementioned activities. Both abovementioned existed and new chemical substances (it is called registered chemical substance thereafter) shall be allowed to manufacture or import after approval of their registration. (Article 30, paragraph 1; [A]).

- *For an existing chemical substance first manufactured or imported in annual volume of 100 kilograms or more, a registrant shall, within 6 months from the date of occurrence of the fact, apply for the phase 1 registration and attach chemical information ... No existing chemical substance shall be manufactured or imported, unless the registration approval is obtained within the specified time period. The same may be applied to those manufactured or imported in annual volumes less than 100 kilograms; after the registration application is approved, the above mentioned existing chemical substances are subject to the Regulations. [B]*

3.2 Exemptions

- *The Regulations shall not apply to any of the following substances or articles [B]:*
 - *Substances which occur in nature⁷⁵*
 - *Chemical substances in machines or equipment for test run purposes*
 - *Inseparable intermediates from chemical reactions in the reaction vessel or production process*
 - *Chemical substances for national security or national defense purposes*
 - *Chemical substances under customs supervision*
 - *Chemical wastes produced or released from industrial process*
 - *By-products or impurities⁷⁶ that are of no commercial application.*
 - *Mixtures;⁷⁷ but individual constituents of mixtures shall not be applied to the Article.*
 - *Articles (成品).*
 - *Polymers that the 2% Rule is Applicable⁷⁸ and listed on the inventory of existing chemical substances.*
- *The Regulations shall not apply to the substances or articles regulated under the following Acts promulgated by the government authorities [B]:*
 - *Agro-pesticides, as defined by the Agro-pesticides Management Act.*
 - *Feeds and feed additives, as defined by the Feed Control Act.*
 - *Fertilizers, as defined by the Fertilizer Management Act.*
 - *Veterinary drugs, as defined by the Veterinary Drugs Control Act.*
 - *Medicaments, as defined by the Pharmaceutical Affairs Act.*
 - *Controlled drugs, as defined by the Controlled Drugs Act.*
 - *Cosmetic(s), as defined by the Statute for Control of Cosmetic Hygiene.*

⁷⁵ *a substance that is: unprocessed; processed only by manual, gravitational, or mechanical means; by dissolution in water; by water extraction; by vapor distillation; by flotation; by heating solely to remove water; by extraction from air by any means, without chemical change in the substance; or, large molecules from organisms, or polymers occurring in nature and not chemically processed. [B]*

⁷⁶ *an unintended constituent present in a substance as produced. It originates from the starting materials or is the result of secondary or incomplete reactions during the production process. While it is present along with the final substance, it was not intentionally added, nor does it enhance the commercial value of that substance. The concentration of an individual impurity is no more than 10% (w/w). All impurities presented are no more than 20% (w/w). [B]*

⁷⁷ *a mixture or a solution composed of two or more substances in which they do not react. [B]*

⁷⁸ *A polymer when its monomers or reactants may not be regarded as part of the polymer when the weight percentage of the monomers or reactants is less than two percent; if the naming of the polymer is a monomer-based representation, it may or may not include monomers and other reactants used at two weight percent or less. [B]*

- Foods, food additives, food utensils, food containers or packaging, and food cleansers, as defined by the Act Governing Food Safety and Sanitation.
- Tobacco products, as defined by the Tobacco Hazards Prevention Act.
- Tobacco and alcohol, as defined by the Tobacco and Alcohol Administration Act.
- Radioactive materials, as defined by the Atomic Energy Act and the Ionizing Radiation Protection Act.
- Industrial use explosive materials, as defined by the Industrial Explosives Administrative Act.
- Chemicals regulated by the Montreal Protocol under the Air Pollution Control Act.
- Environmental agents, as defined by the Environmental Agents Control Act.
- Toxic chemical substances,⁷⁹ as defined by the Act.
- For a chemical substance manufactured or imported as a raw material of the preceding Paragraph, the chemical substance shall be subject to the provisions of the Regulations.
- New chemical registration is additionally exempted for [B]
 - Scientific Research and Development at manufactured or imported volume less than 1 ton[ne]⁸⁰
 - Polymer of Low Concern⁸¹ at manufactured or imported volume less than 1 ton[ne]

⁷⁹ Those chemical substances that are intentionally produced by human activity or unintentionally derived from production processes and that have been officially announced by the central competent authority as having toxicity subject to the following classification regulations. Toxic chemical substances shall be classified as follows.

A. Class 1 toxic chemical substances: those chemical substances that are not prone to decompose in the environment or that pollute the environment or endanger human health due to bioaccumulation, bioconcentration or biotransformation.

B. Class 2 toxic chemical substances: those chemical substances that cause tumors, infertility, teratogenesis, genetic mutations or other chronic diseases.

C. Class 3 toxic chemical substances: those chemical substances that endanger human health or the lives of biological organisms immediately upon exposure.

D. Class 4 toxic chemical substances: those chemical substances that have endocrine disruptor properties, environmental pollutants or chemicals which endanger human health.

Art. 8. The central competent authority shall officially announce toxic chemical substances ... may restrict or prohibit the handling of Class 1, Class 2 and Class 3 toxic chemical substances ... Prior to handling of Class 4 toxic chemical substances, toxicity and relevant information of the toxic chemical substances shall be reported to special municipality, county or city competent authorities. Such handling shall be performed upon permission of the competent authorities in compliance with authorized items.

The handler shall produce reports and regularly report records concerning the handling of toxic chemical substances and their release quantities; such records shall be preserved properly for future reference.

The central competent authority may control the handling of Class 1 and Class 2 toxic chemical substances by means of total release quantity control methods.

A manufacturer, importer or seller of Class 1, 2 or 3 toxic chemical substances shall apply to the special municipality, county or municipal competent authority for a permit, and shall operate in compliance with the content of the permit.

An enterprise using or storing Class 1, 2 or 3 toxic chemical substances shall apply to the special municipal, county, or city competent authority for registration, and shall operate in compliance with the content of the registration document.

An enterprise disposing of or exporting Class 1, 2 or 3 toxic chemical substances shall apply by the batch or shipment to the special municipality, county or city competent authority for registration, and may only begin handling after doing so. [A]

⁸⁰ As a chemical used in business premises, for the purpose of research and development, (including for research, analysis, sampling, or testing, etc.), submission of documentation to the central competent authority must be made for record and reference. [B]

⁸¹ A substance that is evaluated by the central competent authority, and fulfills any one of the following conditions:
A. A polymer with an average molecular weight in a range of 1000 to 10000 Daltons, contains oligomers of molecular weights below 500 Daltons in an amount of less than 10%; oligomers below 1000 Daltons in an amount

4. Initial data requirements

New Chemicals:

- *Manufacturers or importers shall refer to the following registration types based on estimated annual manufactured or imported quantity [B]:*
 - *Standard registration: at 1 ton[ne] or more.*
 - *Information of registrant and basic identification of the substance⁸²*
 - *Information on manufacture, use⁸³ and exposure of the substance*
 - *Hazards classification and labelling⁸⁴*
 - *Safe use information*
 - *Physical and chemical properties*
 - *Toxicological information*
 - *Ecotoxicological information*
 - *Hazard assessment (may be exempted for non-CMR substances of ≥ 1 and < 10 tonnes, and on-site isolated intermediates, polymers, SRD, PPORD)*
 - *Exposure assessment [may be exempted for non-CMR substances of ≥ 1 and < 10 tonnes, and for substances of ≥ 10 tonnes and not meeting any of the following conditions – physicochemical properties hazardous to human health; health hazard; environmental hazard; persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (PBT); very persistent and very bioaccumulative (vPvB), and on-site isolated intermediates, polymers, SRD, PPORD]*
 - *Submission requirements for physical and chemical properties, toxicological, ecotoxicological, hazard assessment and exposure assessment vary depending on tonnage bands (≥ 1 and < 10 , ≥ 10 and < 100 , ≥ 100 and < 1000 , and ≥ 1000 tonnes), types of chemicals (on-site isolated intermediates, polymers, SRD, PPORD) and whether having CMR properties.*
 - *Simplified registration: at 100 kilograms or more, but less than 1 ton[ne].*
 - *Information of registrant and basic identification of the substance*
 - *Information on manufacture, use and exposure of the substance*
 - *Hazards classification and labelling*
 - *Safe use information*
 - *Physical and chemical properties*
 - *Small quantity registration: less than 100 kilograms.*
 - *Information of registrant and basic identification of the substance*
 - *Information on manufacture, use and exposure of the substance*

of less than 25%. B. A polymer with an average molecular weight over 10000 Daltons, contains oligomers of molecular weights below 500 Daltons in an amount of less than 2%; oligomers below 1000 Daltons in [an] amount of less than 5%. C. Polyester polymers. D. Insoluble polymers. [B]

⁸² Including purity level and impurities [C]

⁸³ Following a six-stage life cycle (production, formulation, industrial uses, uses by professional workers, uses by consumers and article use), may also include uses that should not be applied. [C]

⁸⁴ In accordance with national standards CNS 15030 (latest version from Jan 2015, based on GHS version 4), with many tests following OECD test guidelines. It is also recommended that registrants may follow the following subsequence in preparing their dossier: 1. international databases, 2. QSAR estimation, read across, systematic review, or testing proposal, 3. Study reports (including both test reports or peer-reviewed literature). Test facility should meet the requirements. Detailed requirements for individual items can be found in [C].

- If a new chemical substance to be manufactured or imported meets any of the following circumstances, its registration type shall be selected by referring to the estimated annual manufactured or imported quantity [B]:
 - A substance used for the purpose of Scientific Research and Development (SRD): simplified registration (≥ 1 and < 10 tonnes), standard registration (≥ 10 tonnes)
 - A substance used for the purpose of Process Orientated Research and Development (PPORD), on-site Isolated Intermediates, polymers: small quantity registration (< 1 tonne); simplified registration (≥ 1 and < 10 tonnes), standard registration (≥ 10 tonnes)
 - Polymer of Low Concern (PLC): small quantity registration (≥ 1 tonnes)
- *For a new chemical substance meeting the criteria of [SRD], or [PPORD]; or having other special forms, in addition to registering the new chemical substance in accordance with the required information items of the Regulations, the registrant shall submit the following documents to the central competent authority:*
 1. Registration form for SRD and PPORD.
 2. Nanoscale chemical substances registration form⁸⁵. [B]

Existing Chemicals Registration – consisting of two phases

- Phase 1 registration: obtain phase one registration number [B]
 - *Basic information of the registrant.*
 - *Basic identification of the substance:* CAS No. or serial numbers (serial numbers are established by Ministry of Labor, where information confidentiality request has been approved, or the chemical substance has no CAS number.).
 - *Information on manufacture and use of the substance.*
- Standard registration: *Registrants manufacturing or importing any existing chemical substances listed in Appendix 6, shall, starting from January 1st, 2020, apply for the standard registration of such existing chemical substances and attach information.* [B]
 - *Information of registrant and basic identification of the substance*
 - *Information on manufacture, use and exposure of the substance*
 - *Hazards classification and labelling*
 - *Safe use information*
 - *Physical and chemical properties*
 - *Toxicological information*
 - *Ecotoxicological information*
 - *Hazard assessment* (may be exempted for non-CMR substances of ≥ 1 and < 10 tonnes, and on-site isolated intermediates, polymers, SRD, PPORD)
 - *Exposure assessment* [may be exempted for non-CMR substances of ≥ 1 and < 10 tonnes, and for substances of ≥ 10 tonnes and not meeting any of the following conditions – physicochemical properties hazardous to human health; health hazard; environmental hazard; persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (PBT); very persistent and very bioaccumulative (vPvB)]
 - Submission requirements for physical and chemical properties, toxicological, ecotoxicological, hazard assessment and exposure assessment vary depending on tonnage bands (≥ 1 and < 10 , ≥ 10 and < 100 , ≥ 100 and < 1000 , and ≥ 1000 tonnes) and whether having CMR properties.

⁸⁵ A substance is considered a nanomaterial if more than 50% of the substance has at least one dimension in the range of 1 to 100 nanometers. The registration should include information on particle size, aggregation/agglomeration status, appearance, specific surface area, crystall structure, surface charge, surface characteristics, porosity, etc. Such requirements may be exempted when it cannot be supplied due to challenges in analytical techniques. [C]

- Registrants manufacturing or importing existing chemical substances, which are not any of the chemical substances listed or do not meet the quantity thresholds in Appendix 6 [106 substances as of June 2021], may apply for the standard registration of the chemical substances. [B]
- A detailed timeline is provided in [B] and [C].

5. Data updates by companies

- The manufacturer or importer shall proactively maintain and update the data in Paragraph 1 of approved and registered chemical substances. (Article 30, [A])
- For registered new and existing chemical substances, the registrant shall, starting from April 1st 2020, during the period from April 1st to September 30th of each year, submit a report on the **manufactured or imported quantity in the previous year** for the new chemical substance, or the existing chemical substance. [B]

New chemical registration

- A registrant, to extend the valid period of the registration approval, shall make an application to the central competent authority three to six months prior to its expiration. Information on estimated quantity of new chemical substances manufactured or imported for the following year shall be submitted to the central competent authority at the same time.
 - If the central competent authority is unable to make the rejection/approval decision for the extensions before the original approval registration expires, those who file the extension application pursuant to the preceding Paragraph may continue to manufacture or import the new chemical substance, in compliance with the situation specified in the originally approved registration, until the review is completed.
 - If the registration type intended for extension is inconsistent with the originally approved registration, a new application of registration shall be made. [B]

Modification [B]

- A registrant shall apply for modification when changing the application information for chemical substance registration within 30 working days since changes to the information have been made.
 - If the modification pursuant to the previous Paragraph involves the basic information related to a registrant, a modification application shall be made within 30 working days of changes upon receipt of documentary proof of company registration, business registration, factory registration, as well as other documentary proof issued by government authorities in charge of the subject industry. The modification of owner information shall be made within 60 working days since changes to the information have been made.
- If the registration type for which modification is applied differs from the original registration type that has been approved, a new registration application shall be submitted.

Cancellation [B]

- Under any of the following circumstances, the registrant may file an application to the central competent authority for withdrawal of an approval registration and cancel the corresponding registration number:
 - A new registration has been submitted and approved, pursuant to the preceding Paragraph.
 - A chemical substance with registration approval is no longer being manufactured or imported.

Updates [B]

- For chemical substances registered and approved with any of the following circumstances, the registrant shall provide supplementary information proactively or as prescribed by the central competent authority by an appointed due date:
 - New scientific evidence on chemical substances.

- *New information on the uses of chemical substances.*
- *New information on toxicology and ecotoxicology of chemical substances.*
- *New information on hazard assessment of chemical substances.*
- *Other information designated by the central competent authority.*

Record keeping [B]

- *Registrants shall keep copies of all the submitted information and relevant verification documents in written or electronic form for 5 years, for recordkeeping and reference. Information, where business secrets are involved and information protection is applied for and approved by the central competent authority, shall be kept in written or electronic form for 15 years, for record and reference.*

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

New Chemical Registration

- *If the central competent authority judges that the characteristics of a new chemical substance in compliant with the definition of a toxic chemical substance or chemical substance of very concern⁸⁶, an additional clause shall be appended at the time of registration requiring the submission of chemical substance hazard information, updated registered report data or regular reporting of handling conditions and, when necessary, prohibit or restrict the chemical substance's handling. [A]*
- *For a manufactured or imported new chemical substance that applies for simplified registration or small quantity registration ... the central competent authority may demand the registrant to register data in accordance with the requirements of standard registration if the new chemical substance is identified as a substance of CMR. [B]*
- *By taking into account the overall manufactured or imported quantity of the new chemical substances registered and approved, the central competent authority may require registrants to apply for the new registration under the designated registration type, or apply for the joint registration. [B]*

Existing chemical registration

- *The central competent authority may, by stages, designate the lists of existing chemical substances subject to standard registration, including the names of the chemical substances, quantity thresholds and the deadlines for registration, based on the circumstances of the phase 1 registration of existing chemical substances (see Appendix 6 of the Regulation) [B]*
- *The central competent authority may designate registration information to be submitted based on information collected from Phase 1 registration of existing chemical substances and international information on chemical substances. [B]*

Audit and inspection

- *The competent authority may send personnel bearing documents verifying their implementation of relevant duties or markings sufficient to provide identification to enter public or private premises, and examine the handling of toxic chemical substances, chemical substances of high concern, and other chemical substances that must be registered, relevant goods or premises, or order the provision of relevant information. Such personnel may order the provision of stocking, production, sales, and inventory documents, account books, relevant statements, and other production/marketing or import/export data needed to audit said substance flows. When necessary, such personnel may request*

⁸⁶ Chemical substances aside from toxic chemical substances, that have been officially announced by the central competent authority to pollute the environment or are a suspected threat to human health based on substance characteristics or public consumer issues of domestic or foreign concern and are controlled by the central competent authority. [A]

the presentation of receipts, take samples of relevant chemical substances or goods, implement inspection, and provisionally seal the premises, which shall be left under the safekeeping of the statutory responsible person. [A]

- *Any samples taken as specified in Paragraph 1 shall be promptly tested, and an environmental analysis and testing organization that has received a permit from the central competent authority may be conditioned to perform testing.*
- *The central competent authority shall establish a fund to collect handling fees from handlers on the basis of the handling, release, quantities, state of dispersion, accident hazard or risk of substances for the purpose of management, screening, assessment, and control of announced chemical substances.*

Review by regulators for both new and existing chemical registration

- *Should the review procedure find documents inadequate, mistaken, or unspecific, the central competent authority shall require the registrant to provide supplementation or correction within 30 working days of receiving the notification from the central competent authority. The said notification of supplementation and correction shall be given only twice. However, if the failure to provide supplementation or correction within this limited period is caused by scientific or technical factors, this requirement shall not apply to registrants who report to the central competent authority and obtain its consent ... The application shall be rejected if the registrant fails to make supplementation or correction within the limited time, or fails to make the supplementation or correction within a given time period more than two times. [B]*

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

New chemical registration

- *Upon reviewing new chemical substance information submitted by a registrant, the central competent authority shall approve the registration [B]*
 - *by attaching conditions to prohibit or restrict handling, and require submission of periodic reports of handling status, updates of relevant registration reports, or hazard communication, if the central competent authority determines that there is a concern over the toxicological characteristics of new chemical substances conforming to definitions of Class 1, Class 2, or Class 3 of toxic chemical substances.*
 - *along with conditions to restrict its handling, and require submission of information on exposure assessment and risk assessment, updates of relevant registration reports, or hazard communication, if the central competent authority determines that there is a concern of environmental pollution or endangerment to human health.*
- *The central competent authority issues the registration number for a new chemical substance that is registered and approved. [B]*
- *The valid periods of the new chemical substance registration approval are as follows: [B]*
 - *I. The standard registration is valid for 5 years.*
 - *II. The simplified registration and small quantity registration are valid for 2 years.*
 - *III. The PLC small quantity registration in accordance with Article 5 Paragraph 2 is valid for 5 years.*
- *When discovered after approval and registration, the central competent authority may also modify or add required or prohibited or restricted items. [A]*
- *The approved chemical substance data for registration should be used to manage chemical substances those are utilized by the industry competent authority. Moreover, the data should be provided as the basis for assessment, screening and announcement of toxic chemical substances and chemical substances of high concern. The same applies in the case of data reported for future reference. [A]*

Existing chemical registration

- *The central competent authority issues a completion number for the standard registration of an existing chemical substance to those who apply and complete chemical substance information registration. [B]*

Review periods

- *The review periods of all the applications accepted by the central competent authority in the Regulations are as follows: [B]*
 - *I. New chemical substances small quantity registration, PCL prior verification, PCL small quantity registration, existing chemical substance phase 1 registration, chemical information protection and corresponding extension: 7 working days from the date of receipt of the application.*
 - *II. New chemical substances simplified registration and the inclusion in the inventory of existing chemical substances: 14 working days from the date of receipt of the application.*
 - *III. New chemical substances standard registration: 45 working days from the date of receipt of the application.*
 - *IV. Existing chemical substances standard registration: 90 working days from the date of receipt of the application.*
 - *The review periods for small quantity registration and simplified registration may be extended to 45 working days when the registration applications satisfy the conditions in Article 9. The central competent authority shall notify the registrant if the review period of the previous two Paragraphs is extended. The number of extensions is limited to one time.*

8. Data submission format

- *Annual reporting: The report shall be submitted via the Internet transmission system designated by the central competent authority. However, a report in writing may be submitted with the consent of the central competent authority. [B]*

9. Data confidentiality

- *Chemical information registered, which concerns confidential matters on national defense or business secrets, shall be kept confidential. The aforementioned information business secrets shall conform to the following conditions. [B]*
 - *It is not known to persons generally involved in information of this type.*
 - *It has actual or potential economic value, due to its secretive nature.*
 - *Its owner has taken reasonable measures to maintain its confidentiality.*
- *For registered information determined to be business secrets, the following shall be protected and kept confidential: [B]*
 - *Identification of registrant.*
 - *Identification of chemical substance.*
 - *Information on manufacture or import.*
 - *Use of chemical substance.*
- *A registrant may apply for confidential information protection with proof documents, in any of the following occasions: [B]*
 - *Application for the registration of a new chemical substance.*
 - *Application for the phase 1 registration of an existing chemical substance.*
 - *Application for the standard registration of an existing chemical substance.*
 - *Three to six months prior to the inclusion in the inventory of existing chemical substances pursuant to Article 14.*

- *The confidentiality periods of the chemical substance information approved by the central competent authority are specified as follows:*
 - *Standard registration of a new chemical substance or PLC small quantity registration: confidentiality is to be valid for 5 years.*
 - *Simplified registration or small quantity registration of a new chemical substance: confidentiality is to be valid for 2 years.*
 - *Registration of an existing chemical substance: confidentiality is to be valid for 5 years.*

Except for the existing chemical substance registered pursuant to the Subparagraph 3 of the above Paragraph, the confidentiality period pursuant to Paragraph 5 of the previous Article expires as the valid period for the corresponding registration expires.

A registrant may apply for the extension of the confidentiality periods specified in Paragraph 1 three to six months prior to the expiry of the confidentiality period.

The maximum confidentiality period for a new chemical substance is 15 years; for an existing chemical substance, the maximum confidentiality period is 10 years. [B]

- *When one of the following circumstances occurs, information confidentiality ... shall not be subjected to this restriction pursuant to the authority of the central competent authority. [A]*
 - *It is necessary for benefitting the public.*
 - *It is necessary for protecting people's lives, bodies, health.*
 - *Consent is obtained from the manufacturer or importer.*
- *The Freedom of Government Information Act shall apply to application to the central or special municipality, county and city competent authorities for provision of government information. [A]*

10. Data that are published publicly

- *Chemical substance information registered and approved by the central competent authority shall be made public. The information items which shall be disclosed are as follows: [B]*
 - *Identification of Registrant.*
 - *Chemical substance name.*
 - *Manufacture or import conditions.*
 - *Hazard classification and labelling.*
 - *Safe use information.*
 - *Physical and chemical properties.*
 - *Toxicological and ecotoxicological information.*
 - *Hazard assessment.*
 - *Exposure assessment.*
- *The content pursuant to the previous Paragraph shall be publicly disclosed through the Internet by the central competent authority. [B]*

11. International information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.8 Inventory of Hazardous Chemicals Import in India (ICHCI)

Last update: 10 June 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Manufacture, storage and import of hazardous chemical rules, 1989: <http://moef.gov.in/manufacture-storage-and-import-of-hazardous-chemical-rules-1989/> (including the Schedules)
- B. ICHCI (2008):
<https://www.cpcb.nic.in/openpdffile.php?id=UmVwb3J0RmlsZXMvTmV3SXRIbV8xMjhfcGFja2FnZS5wZGY=>
- C. ICHCI (2010):
<https://cpcb.nic.in/openpdffile.php?id=UmVwb3J0RmlsZXMvTmV3SXRIbV8xNThfTVNJSEMtUkVQT1JULnBkZg==>

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory [B]

To study the inventory of hazardous chemicals being imported by various categories of industrial units in India

3. Scope of the inventory [A]

3.1 Obligation to notify

Rules 7 to 15⁸⁷ shall apply to,

- an industrial activity in which there is involved a quantity of hazardous chemical listed in Column 2 of Schedule 3⁸⁸ which is equal to or more than the quantity specified in the entry for that chemical in Columns 3 & 4 (Rules 10–12 only for Column 4) and
- isolated storage in which there is involved a quantity of a hazardous chemical listed in Column 2 of Schedule 2 which is equal to or more than the quantity specified in the entry for that chemical in Column 1 [11 chemicals]
- for the purposes of rules 7 to 15, “new industrial activity” means an industrial activity which
 - (i) commences after the date of coming into operation of these rules; or
 - (ii) if commenced before that date is an industrial activity in which a modification has been made which is likely to cover major accident hazards and that activity shall be deemed to have commenced on the date on which the modification was made;
- an “existing industrial activity” means an industrial activity which is not a new industrial activity”

4. Initial data requirements [A]

7. Notification of sites.

- An occupier shall not undertake any industrial activity unless he has submitted a written report to the concerned authority containing the particulars specified in Schedule 7 at least 3 months before commencing that activity or before such shorter time as the concerned authority may agree and for the purpose of this paragraph an activity in which subsequently there is or is liable to be a threshold quantity

⁸⁷ 7 = notification of sites; 8 = updating the site notification following changes in the threshold quantity; 9 = transitional provisions; 10 = safety reports; 11 = updating of reports under rule 10; 12 = requirements for further information to be sent to the authority; 13 = preparation of on-site emergency plan by the occupier; 14 = preparation of off-site emergency plan by the authority; 15 = information to be given to persons liable to be affected by a major accident [A]

⁸⁸ Including 179 chemicals with different thresholds, and flammable gases (<http://moef.gov.in/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/SCHEDULE-3.html>)

or more of an additional hazardous chemical shall be deemed to be a different activity and shall be notified accordingly

- No report under sub-rule (I) need to be submitted by the occupier if he submits a report under rule 10(1)

10. Safety reports

- *Subjects to the following paragraphs of this rule, an occupier shall not undertake any industrial activity to which this rule applies, unless he has prepared a safety report on that industrial activity containing the information specified in Schedule 8 and has sent a copy of that report to the concerned authority at least ninety days before commencing that activity.*
- *In the case of a new industrial activity which an occupier commences, or by virtue of sub-rule (2) (a) (ii) of rule 6 [see “obligation to notify” above] is deemed to commence, within 6 months after coming into operation of these rules, it shall be sufficient compliance with sub-rule (I) of this rule if the occupier sends to the concerned authority a copy of the report required in accordance with that sub-rule within ninety days after the date of coming into operation of these rules.*
- *In the case of an existing industrial activity, until five years from the date of coming into operation of these rules, it shall be a sufficient compliance with sub-rule (I) of this rule in the occupier on or before ninety days from the date of the coming into operation of these rules sends to the concerned authority in information specified in Schedule 7 relating to that activity.*

18. Import of hazardous chemicals

- *This rule shall apply to a chemical which satisfies any of the criteria laid down in Part I of Schedule I⁸⁹ and is listed in Column 2 of Part II of this Schedule.*
- *Any person responsible for importing hazardous chemicals in India shall provide at the time of import or within thirty days from the date of import to the concerned authorities as identified in Column 2 of Schedule 5 the information pertaining to*
 - *the name and address of the person receiving the consignment in India;*
 - *the port of entry in India;*
 - *mode of transport from the exporting country to India*
 - *the quantity of chemical(s) being imported; and*
 - *complete product safety information.*

5. Data updates by companies [A]

- **8. Updating of the site notification following changes in the threshold quantity:** *Where an activity has been reported in accordance with rule 7(1) and the occupier makes a change in it (including an increase or decrease in the maximum threshold quantity of a hazardous chemical to which this rule applies which is or is liable to be at the site or in the pipeline or at the cessation of the activity, which affects the particulars specified in that report or any subsequent report made under this rule the occupier shall forthwith furnish a further report to the concerned authority.*
- **11. Updating of [safety] reports under rule 10.**
 - *(1) Where an occupier has made a safety report in accordance with sub-rule (I) of rule 10 he shall not make any modification to The industrial activity to which that safety report relates which could materially affect the particulars in that report, unless the has made a further report to take account of those modifications and has sent a copy of that report to The concerned authority at least 90 days before making those modifications.*

⁸⁹ Including toxic chemicals (extremely toxic and highly toxic via oral, dermal and inhalation routes), flammable chemicals and explosives. Part 2 consists of 429 chemicals (<http://moef.gov.in/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/SCHEDULE-I.html>)

- (2) Where an occupier has made a report in accordance with rule 10 and sub-rule (1) of this rule and that industrial activity is continuing the occupier shall within three years of the date of the last such report, make a further report which shall have regard in particular to new technical knowledge which has affected the particulars in the previous report relating to safety and hazard assessment and shall within 30 days or in such longer time as the concerned authority may agree in writing, send a copy of the report to the concerned authority.
- 17. Collection, development and dissemination of information
 - This rule shall apply to an industrial activity in which a hazardous chemical which satisfies any of the criteria laid down in part I of Schedule 1 and is listed in Column 2 of Part II of this Schedule is or may be involved.
 - An occupier, who has control of an industrial activity in terms of sub-rule 1 of this rule, shall arrange to obtain or develop information in the form of safety data sheet as specified in Schedule 9. This information shall be accessible upon request for reference.
 - The occupier while obtaining or developing a safety data sheet as specified in Schedule 9 in respect of a hazardous chemical handled by him shall ensure that the information is recorded accurately and reflects the scientific evidence used in making the hazard determination. In case, any significant information regarding hazard of a chemical is available, it shall be added to the material safety data sheet as specified in Schedule 9 as soon as practicable.

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators [A]

Where, in accordance with rule 10, an occupier has sent a safety report relating to an industrial activity to the concerned authority, the concerned authority may, by a notice served on the occupier, require him to provide such additional information as is specified in the notice and the occupier shall send that information to the concerned authority within such time as is specified in the notice or within such extended time as the authority may subsequently specify.

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom) [A]

- If the concerned authority at the State is satisfied that the chemical being imported is likely to cause a major accident, it may direct the importer to take such steps including stoppage of such imports as the concerned authority at the State may deem it appropriate.
- The concerned authority at the State shall simultaneously inform the concerned Port Authority to take appropriate steps regarding safe handling and storage of hazardous chemicals while off-loading the consignment with the port premises.
- Any person importing hazardous chemicals shall maintain the records of the hazardous chemicals imported as specified in Schedule 10 and the records so maintained shall be open for inspection by the concerned authority at the State or the Ministry of Environment and Forests or any officer appointed by them in this behalf.

8. Data submission format – N.A.

9. Data confidentiality [A]

Where for the purpose of evaluating information notified under rule 5 [Notification of major accident] or 7 to 15, the concerned authority discloses that information to some other person that other person shall not use that information for any purpose except for the purpose of the concerned authority disclosing it, and before disclosing the information the concerned authority shall inform that other person of his obligations under this paragraph.

10. Data that are published publicly [B, C]

Two reports are available online, among others, including chemical name and import quantities

11. International information exchange and sharing – N.A.

S1.9 Indian REACH Inventory

Last update: 17 August 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Draft Chemicals (Management and Safety) Rules, 20xx (5th draft from Aug 2020, the final version is expected to be adopted in 2021): <https://resource.chemlinked.com.cn/chemical/File/fifth-draft-of-india-reach.pdf>

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

- **Distinction of new vs. existing substance**
 - New substance: *all substances and intermediates that are placed in Indian Territory after the expiry of the Initial Notification Period, and are therefore not existing substances.*
 - Existing substance: *a substance or an intermediate which is already being manufactured, imported, supplied or used in India or has already been placed in Indian territory prior to the expiry of the initial notification period.*

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligations

- Art. 3: *These Rules apply to all substances, substances in mixtures and intermediates that are manufactured, imported, placed or intended to be placed in Indian Territory. These rules do not apply to substances in articles except as otherwise set out in Rule 10 and Rule 12 hereinafter.*
- Art. 6: *No person shall place in Indian territory any substance, mixture or Article unless they comply with these Rules.⁹⁰*
- Art. 7: *Every downstream user who use of a notified substance is not included in its notification, shall notify the Division of such use and submit a Safety Data Sheet in relation to such use in accordance with Rule 12.*

Notification (Rules 8 and 11)⁹¹

- *All manufacturers or importers (or authorised representatives acting on behalf of foreign entities) shall notify ... that they have placed in Indian Territory in **quantities greater than 1 tonne per annum** ... within the Initial Notification Period.*
- *A manufacturer or importer (or authorised representative in the case of a Foreign Manufacturer) shall notify ... that they intend to place in Indian Territory, after the expiry of the Initial Notification Period.*
- *All new substances have to be notified at least 60 days prior to the date on which they are Placed in Indian Territory in quantities more than 1 tonne per annum. Any person intending to Place an Existing Substance in quantities greater than 1 tonne per annum in Indian Territory after the Initial Notification Period shall also Notify the Division in the same manner.*

⁹⁰ Art. 6: *A foreign entity who wishes to place a substance, mixture or article in Indian territory may appoint an authorised representatives, who shall be an Indian national or an entity registered in India with sufficient background in practical handling of substances and with minimum average net worth of ten times the average value of substances dealt by him during the last calendar/financial year. Such authorised representative shall be responsible to act on behalf of the foreign entity to ensure compliance with these Rules and shall be liable for the discharge of all obligations under these Rules.*

⁹¹ Art. 8: *The Initial Notification Period shall commence on the date that is one year from the date of coming into force of these Rules. The Initial Notification Period shall terminate on the date which is 180 days from the date of the commencement of the Initial Notification Period.*

- *Intermediates not included in Schedule II, are required to be notified, but are exempted from registration requirements under these Rules.*

Registration (Rules 10 and 11)

- *All manufacturers, importers and authorised representatives that have placed or are intending to place in Indian territory a substance listed in **Schedule II** [list of priority substances⁹² required to be registered] in quantities **greater than 1 tonne per annum** must register such substance within one and half years from the date of inclusion of the substance in Schedule II.*
- *A requirement for registration of substances that are placed in Indian territory in quantities lower than 1 tonne per annum, may also be published in Schedule II, based on the recommendations of the Scientific Committee and the Division.*
- *If substances set out in Schedule II are present in Articles such that (a) such substances are intended to be or likely to be released from the Article under normal or foreseeable conditions of use, and (b) such substance is present in the article in quantities totalling over 1 tonne per producer or importer per year, then the manufacturer or importer of such article shall be required to register such substance.*
- *All intermediates, which are also substances included in Schedule II, and are stored in a facility (either for consumption in-situ or otherwise) shall be registered in accordance with Rule 10.*
- *Transported intermediates that are substances included in Schedule II, shall be registered as under (a) registration of intermediates transported or to be transported in quantities up to 1000 tonnes per annum shall only contain details regarding the physical and chemical properties in the technical dossier, and (b) registration of intermediates transported or to be transported in quantities greater than 1000 tonnes per annum shall contain all information as required in the technical dossier and the chemical safety report.*

Chemical Safety Assessment (Rule 13)

- *Manufacturers or importers (or authorised representatives ...) that place substances listed in **Schedule II** in Indian territory in **quantities greater than 10 tonnes per annum** shall perform a chemical safety assessment and submit a chemical safety report⁹³ ... at the time of notification or registration.*

⁹² i. Any substance which falls under any of the following hazard classifications of the GHS Rev. 8: a carcinogenicity and/or germ cell mutagenicity and/or reproductive toxicity and categorised as Category 1 or 2, or b. Specific target organ toxicity (repeated exposure or single exposure) Category 1 or 2; or
 ii. any substance which fulfils the criteria of PBT or vPvB, as set out in Schedule I of these Rules; or
 iii. any substance listed in Schedule II

⁹³ Part 1: Summary of risk management measures, declaration that risk management measures are implemented, declaration that risk management measures are communicated.

Part 2: Identity of the substance and physical and chemical properties, manufacture and uses (manufacture, identified uses, uses advised against), classification and labelling, environmental fate properties (degradation, environmental distribution, bioaccumulation, secondary poisoning), human health hazard assessment (toxicokinetics – AMDE, acute toxicity, irritation (skin, eye, respiratory tract), corrosivity, sensitisation (skin, respiratory system), repeated dose toxicity, mutagenicity, carcinogenicity, toxicity for reproduction (effects on fertility, developmental toxicity), other effects, derivation of derived no-effect levels (DNELs), human health hazard assessment of physicochemical properties (explosivity, flammability, oxidising potential), environmental hazard assessment (aquatic compartment including sediment, terrestrial compartment, atmospheric compartment, microbiological activity in sewage treatment systems, derivation of predicted no-effect concentration (PNEC), PBT and vPvB assessment, exposure assessment, risk characterisation (if desired, exposure assessment and risk characterisation may be combined into one section without loss of information).

- *Manufacturers or importers (or authorised representatives ...) that place substances listed in Schedule II in Indian territory in quantities less than or equal to 10 tonnes but more than 1 tonne per annum shall submit an exposure scenario at the time of registration.*

Submission of Information relating to Industrial Activity and Site Safety Report (Rule 22) [a follow-up of the ICHCI and its underlying framework above]

- *An occupier who has control of an industrial activity in which a hazardous chemical⁹⁴ is handled and such industrial activity is not covered by sub-rule (2) below or Rule 24, shall provide evidence to the Concerned Authority to show that he has (a) identified the chemical accident hazards, and (b) taken adequate steps to (i) prevent chemical accidents and to limit their consequences in terms of impact on persons and the environment, and (ii) provide persons working on the site information, training and equipment including antidotes necessary to ensure their safety. This evidence shall be provided within 30 days of commencement of the activity or within 30 days of coming into force of these Rules, whichever is later. The occupier shall obtain the acknowledgement from the Concerned Authority within 60 days of submission, failing which he shall not continue the activity.*
 - *The following industrial activities will have to be notified by the occupier and approved in accordance with this rule: (a) an industrial activity in which there is involved a quantity of hazardous chemical as listed in column 2 of Schedule XII which is equal to or more than the threshold quantity specified in the entry for that hazardous chemical in column 3 of Schedule XII; (b) isolated storage in which there is involved a quantity of a hazardous chemical listed in column 2 of Schedule XI which is equal to or more than the threshold quantity specified in the entry for that hazardous chemical in column 3 of Schedule XI.*
 - *An occupier shall not undertake any new industrial activity unless he has been granted an approval from the Concerned Authority for undertaking such activity and has submitted a report for notification ... and site safety report ... at least 90 days before commencing that activity or before such shorter time as the Concerned Authority may agree.*

3.2 Exemptions (as defined in Article 2, (ss))

- *Radioactive substances*
- *Substances under customs supervision, not being placed in Indian Territory*
- *Substances stored in customs free zones with aim of re-exporting*
- *Wastes, as defined in Hazardous Waste Management Rules 2016*
- *Substances used for the purposes of defence*
- *Substances used as food or feeding stuff for human beings or animals, including human and animal nutrition*
- *Substances set out in Schedule IV:*

⁹⁴ Any substance which satisfies any of the criteria laid down in Part I of Schedule X or any substance listed in Part II of Schedule X, or any substance listed in column 2 of Schedule XI, or any substance listed in column 2 of Schedule XII.

Schedule X – Hazardous chemicals, include Part I: major accident hazard criteria – (a) toxic chemicals, flammable chemicals, explosives, and Part II: list of 669 hazardous chemicals, as of August 2020.

Schedule XI – Isolated storage at installations other than those covered by schedule XIII, including 30 chemicals listed as of August 2020

Schedule XII – List of hazardous chemicals for application of Chapter IV, including Part 1 of 179 chemicals (2 groups of toxic substances, 1 group of highly reactive substances, 1 group of explosive substances) and Part II – classes of substances as defined in Part I, Schedule X and not specifically named in Part I of this Schedule: flammable substances

- *water, distilled, conductivity or of similar purity*
- *starch*
- *fatty acids, coco, Me esters*
- *cellulose pulp*
- *syrops, corn, dehydrated*
- *substances which result from a chemical reaction that occurs incidental to exposure of another substance or article to environmental factors such as air, moisture, microbial organisms or sunlight*
- *substances which result from a chemical reaction that occurs incidental to storage of another substance, mixture or article*
- *substances which result from a chemical reaction occurring upon end use of other substances, mixtures or articles, and which are not themselves manufactured, imported, or placed on the market*
- *substances which occur in nature, if they are not chemically modified. For example, minerals, ores, ore concentrates, raw and processed natural gas, crude oil, coal*
- *compost and biogas, charcoal*
- *hydrogen and atmospheric oxygen, nitrogen and noble gases*
- *by-products, unless they are imported or placed in the Indian market*
- *glass, ceramic fritz*
- *following substances if not modified chemically: liquified petroleum gas, natural gas condensates, cement clinker, magnesium, coke*
- *the following substances when not chemically modified and obtained from natural sources, unless they fall within the definition of priority substances: vegetable fats, oils and waxes, animal fats, oils and waxes, fatty acids from C₆ to C₂₄ and their potassium, sodium, calcium and magnesium salts and glycerol*
- *Note: where a substance used for a specific purpose is exempted, only such quantities of the substances as are being used for the said purpose, are exempted from the application of these Rules. Any manufacturer, importer or downstream user using any quantities of the same substance for any other purpose will not be exempt from the application of these Rules.*
- *Rule 8: All manufacturers and importers who have registered a substance under any other Indian Act, Rule or Regulation currently in force, shall also notify the division in accordance with Rule 8 except sub-rule 12 and 13. Such Substances are exempted from registration, chemical safety assessment and evaluation and restriction and Rules 10, 13 and 16 will not apply in such cases.*
- *Rule 10: Intermediates produced in-situ which are not isolated but consumed in the same process are exempted from notification and registration.*

4. Initial data requirements

Notification (Rule 9)

- *A Notification by a Manufacturer or Importer or Authorised Representative shall include information relating to the Notifier, identity of the Substance, its Uses, the quantity of the Substance that is or will be Placed in Indian Territory, current classification and such other information as set out in Schedule V.*
 - *Details of notifier*
 - *List main constituents of the substance with 10% (w/w) or more concentration: substance no. IUPAC name, common name, CASRN, molecular structure, isomer, % average concentration*
 - *List all impurities with more than 1.0% but less than 10% (w/w) concentration*
 - *For UVCBs, structural representation of the constituents, reaction scheme (including the identity of the reactants and the reaction type), process output (including identity of the precursors, the technology, method of preparation, process terms and they typical compositions)*

- Chemical structural details: molecular weight, SMILES, information on optical activity and typical ratio of (stereo) isomers (if applicable and appropriate), spectral data (including HPLC, GC, GC-MS or LC-MS, infra red spectra, UV-vis spectrophotometer spectra, NMR)
- Hazard classification of the substance (according to GHS Rev. 8)
- Chemical uses
- Name of known downstream users (at least top 3; will be kept confidential)
- Actual quantity per annum in TPA (will be kept confidential under all circumstances)
- Maximum storage capacity / maximum quantity stored
- Note: The information contained in the notification must be based on test reports from NABL accredited labs or GLP labs or any other published authentic study report.
- *All Notifiers are also required to submit a Safety Data Sheet as required under Rule 12.*

Registration⁹⁵

- Registrant details
- Chemical identifiers: chemical name (IUPAC name or common/trade name or CAS name), chemical numbers (CASRN, IN number/notification number), purity, details of all impurities contained in concentrations of greater than 0.1% (w/w), nature of impurities (including isomers and by-products), nature and order of magnitude (ppm, %) of any additives (e.g. stabilising agents or inhibitors)
- Chemical structural details: molecular weight, SMILES, molecular and structural formula, information on optical activity and typical ratio of (stereo) isomers (if applicable and appropriate), spectral data (including HPLC, GC, GC-MS or LC-MS, infra red spectra, UV-vis spectrophotometer spectra, NMR, mass spectrum), type of substance (mono, multi, UVCBs), description of the analytical methods or the appropriate bibliographical references for the identification of the substance and, where appropriate, for the identification of impurities and additives. This information shall be sufficient to allow the methods to be reproduced.
- Identified chemical uses: the calendar year of the registration, an indication of the tonnage used for his own use(s), form (substance, preparation or article) and/or physical state under which the substance is made available to downstream users, concentration or concentration range of the substance in preparations made available to downstream users and quantities, brief general description of the identified use(s), information on waste quantities and composition of waste resulting from manufacture of the substance, the use in articles and identified uses, description of the manufacturing process, and all identified uses that the registrant wants to cover in accordance with use descriptors (these uses shall be included in the Exposure Scenario (1–10 TPA) and chemical safety report as the case may be)
- Classification and labelling information: the hazard classification of the substance(s), the resulting hazard label for the substance(s), specific concentration limits, where applicable
- Robust study summaries
- Main use category: industrial use and/or professional use and/or consumer use
- Specification for industrial and professional use: used in closed system and/or use resulting in inclusion into or onto matrix and/or non-dispersive use and/or dispersive use

⁹⁵ *When tests are required to be carried out by registrants for the purpose of registration, the registrants shall comply with the testing methodology/protocol laid down in the [OECD] guidelines for the testing of chemicals. If the guidelines provide different options for any test, any of the options may be adopted with concurrence of the Risk Assessment Committee. The tests must be carried out in NABL accredited or GLP certified laboratories.*

To avoid repeated testing, the existing test data must be considered prior to requiring a new testing. All efforts should be made to derive the required data using alternative methods recommended by OECD. The registrant must propose a testing strategy and get it approved by the Division before conducting any new test. Tests on vertebrate animals shall be undertaken only as a last resort.

- Significant routes of human exposure: oral and/or dermal and/or inhalatory
- Significant routes of environmental exposure: water and/or air and/or solid waste and/or soil
- Pattern of exposure: accidental/infrequent and/or occasional and/or continuous/frequent

5. Data updates by companies after the initial step

Notification (Rules 8 and 12)

- *All manufacturers and importers who have notified a substance under this Rule shall update the information submitted annually, no later than 60 days after the end of each calendar year. Such update shall ... include information regarding the actual quantities of substances placed in Indian Territory in the previous calendar year. Additionally, any changes or additions to the information submitted at the time of notification must be updated.*

Registration (Rule 10)

- *All manufacturers, importers or authorised representatives who have registered a substance shall update the technical dossier and other data submitted with the registration (if any) to reflect any change or revision in the information submitted that affects hazard and risk management, not later than 60 days after the manufacturer, importer or authorised representatives has become aware of such change or revision.*

Safety Data Sheet⁹⁶

- *All notifiers of a substance or an intermediate listed in Schedule II or a hazardous chemical are required to maintain and submit an up-to-date safety data sheet ... and share such safety data sheet with the downstream user of the substance.*
- *All importers or manufacturers of an article, where a substance or an intermediate listed in Schedule II is present in such article above a concentration of 1.0% weight by weight (w/w), shall maintain and submit an up-to-date Safety Data Sheet ... and share such safety data sheet with the user of the article.*
- *Any registrant who is required under Rule 13 to carry out a Chemical Safety Assessment for a substance included in Schedule II shall ensure that the information in the Safety Data Sheet is consistent with the information in the Chemical Safety Report.*
- *All downstream users of a substance shall recommend additions to the safety data sheet, if any, on the basis of their use of the substance.*
- *All notifiers and downstream users shall update the safety data sheet when new information on hazards or which may affect risk management becomes available.*

Import of priority substances or hazardous chemicals (Rule 27)

- *Upon completion of the relevant registration and notification requirements, an importer of substances listed in Schedule II or hazardous chemicals in India shall submit to the concerned authority, at least 15 days before importation of such substances in quantities greater than the lowest of 1 tonne, the quantity specified in column 3 of Schedule XII and column 3 of Schedule XI, information pertaining to (a) the name and address of the person receiving the consignment in India, the port of entry in India, mode of*

⁹⁶ The safety data sheet shall include the following 16 headings: 1) identification of the substance/mixture and of the company/undertaking, 2) hazards identification, 3) composition/information on ingredients, 4) first aid measures, 5) fire fighting measures, 6) accidental release measures, 7) handling, 8) exposure controls/personal protection, 9) physical and chemical properties, 10) stability and reactivity, 11) toxicological information, 12) ecological information, 13) disposal considerations, 14) transport information, 15) regulatory information, 16) legal status of substance, 17) other information

transport from the exporting country to India, name and the quantity of priority substances or hazardous chemicals being imported, and all relevant product safety information, including safety data sheet.

- *All person importing priority substances or hazardous chemicals shall maintain records of the priority substances or hazardous chemicals imported. The records so maintained shall be open for inspection by the concerned authority or any competent person.*

Safety Audit Reports (Rule 24)

- *The occupier of a major accident hazard installation involving quantities of hazardous chemicals exceeding the threshold quantity of column 4 of Schedules XI of XII shall carry out an independent safety audit of the industrial activity by an accredited expert agency expanelled by the Steering Committee, at least once every 2 years. The occupier shall submit at least one safety audit report within 180 days from the date of coming into force of these Rules.*

Update of site safety report or safety audit report (Rule 25)

- *The occupier shall send a copy of the auditor's report along with his comments to the Concerned Authority within 30 days after the completion of such audit. The concerned authority will forward a copy of such auditor's report to the Division.*
- *When an occupier makes any modification to an industrial activity which could materially affect the particulars in the reports submitted as per Part I of Schedule XIV, or the site safety report or the safety audit report, he shall make a fresh report taking into account these modifications and submit such revised report to the concerned authority, no later than 30 days from the making of these modifications.*
- *Where the occupier has made a site safety report ... and such industrial activity is continuing, the occupier shall within three years of the date of the last such report, make a further report which shall have regard in particular to new technical knowledge which has affected the particulars in the previous report relating to safety and hazard assessment and shall submit the updated site safety report to the concerned authority.*

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

Notification

- *Art. 8: Upon receipt of a notification, the Chemistry Unit of the Division shall conduct a preliminary check to ensure that the notification is complete ... If the notification is incomplete, the Division may require the Notifier to submit additional information. The notifier must comply with such request within a maximum period of 30 days [this may be extended for a maximum of 30 days].*

Registration

- *Art. 9: Upon the receipt of a registration, the Toxicology Unit of the Division shall conduct a preliminary check to ensure that the registration is complete ... If the registration is incomplete, the Division may require the registrant to submit additional information for completing the dossier within 60 days. For substances already registered with any foreign regulator in other jurisdictions, the data submitted on the same substance to that regulator for the purpose of registration shall be acceptable to the extent possible.*

Evaluation

- *The Chemistry and Toxicology Units of the Division shall evaluate the technical dossier within one year of its submission.*
- *If the Chemistry and Toxicology Units find that the technical dossier has incomplete information, they shall require the registrant to furnish the same, including any additional test data within 120 days of being informed [which can be extended for a maximum of 90 days].*

- *If the registrant is unable to supply the required information within the deadline, the registration of the substance shall be suspended. If the registration of the substance remains suspended, the registrant shall not place the substance in Indian territory.*

Safety Audit Reports (Rule 24)

- *Steering Committee may direct safety audit of any industry, at random, or on receipt of any specific complaint.*

Update of site safety report or safety audit report (Rule 25)

- *Where an occupier has sent a site safety report and the safety audit report relating to an industrial activity to the concerned authority, such authority may require the occupier to provide additional information and the occupier shall send such additional information within 90 days.*

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

Notification (Rule 8)

- *If the notification passes such preliminary check, the Techno-Legal Unit shall take a decision on an application for confidentiality, if any.*
- *Once all required information regarding a notification has been submitted to the satisfaction of the Chemistry Unit, the notification shall be deemed accepted and the substance shall be entered into the Register of Notified Substances. A notification number shall be assigned to the notifier for such substance and notification certificate ... shall be granted to the notifier.*

Priority Substance Evaluation After Notification (Rule 8)

- *Art. 8: Upon notification of a substance, the Priority Substance Unit shall check with the Division and notifier for availability of data regarding the substance to find out whether it falls within the definition of priority substance. All data submitted by the notifier to any foreign regulator in other jurisdictions for the purpose of registration of the same substance shall be acceptable to the extent possible. The Priority Substance Unit shall evaluate all notified substances, in concurrence with the Scientific Committee⁹⁷ and the Risk Assessment Committee,⁹⁸ and identify substances that fall within the definition of priority substance. Scientific weight of evidence data, if made available by the notifier, shall also be taken into account before making final determination about any substance. Based on such evaluation, or based on*

⁹⁷ Shall be composed of the following members: a chairperson, one expert in chemistry or chemical regulations, one toxicology expert, one packaging and labeling expert, one environmental expert, two experts in socio-economic analysis (including for instance experts with background in ecological economics, economic sciences, social sciences, etc.), one expert each in analytical chemistry, environmental impact studies, packaging & labeling from industry associations with equivalent experience, and any senior staff member of the Chemistry Unit. Expert members shall have a minimum of 20 years of experience as scientists in relevant areas in any institutes of Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR), Council of Scientific & Industrial Research (CSIR), Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR), National Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research (NIPER) or in any GLP certified lab. Serving or retired professors/ asst. professors with a minimum of 20 years of experience in the relevant areas in any Central University or any institute of national repute may also be nominated. All expert members shall be below 65 years of age on the date of nomination and shall, unless their seats become vacant earlier by resignation, death or otherwise, hold office for 3 years from the date of their appointment, and shall be eligible for re-appointment to either committee only once.

⁹⁸ Shall be composed of: a chairperson, one expert in chemistry or chemical regulations, one medical toxicology expert, one veterinary toxicology expert, one phyto-toxicology expert, one marine toxicology expert, one environmental expert, one expert each in environmental impact studies, medical toxicology, veterinary toxicology and environmental toxicology nominated [by] industry associations with equivalent experience, and any senior staff member of the Toxicology unit.

non-availability of data, the Priority Substance Unit may recommend to the Steering Committee for addition to or deletion from Schedule II [List of priority substances required to be registered, containing 750 substances, as of August 2020]. The Steering Committee shall hold public consultations within 90 days of receipt of recommendations, prior to forwarding such recommendations to the Central Government.

Registration (Rule 8)

- *The Techno-Legal Unit shall take a decision on any applications regarding confidentiality.*
- *Once all required information regarding a registration has been submitted to the satisfaction of the Toxicology Unit, the registration shall be deemed accepted and a registration number shall be assigned to the registrant of such substance and registration certificate ... shall also be granted to the registrant.*

Evaluation (Rule 16)

- *The Priority Substance Unit of the Division shall evaluate the available data to assess if the registered substance poses an unacceptable risk to human safety or the environment during various uses in India. Risk-based approaches including hazard identification, hazard characterization, exposure assessment, and risk characterization (probability of occurrence of known and potential adverse effects) shall be adopted for such overall risk assessment to the extent possible.*
- *If the Priority Substance Unit is of the opinion that the risk posed by the use of the registered substance is substantial, it may propose to restrict the use of such substance or prohibit such substance. Such proposal shall be submitted to the risk assessment committee for its concurrence based on socio-economic impact assessment and availability of suitable alternatives. The Priority Substance Unit may, based on its evaluation, also recommend to the Risk Assessment Committee that an entry be added to or deleted from Schedules X, XI or XII.*
- *Upon carrying out changes, if any, suggested by the Risk Assessment Committee, a substance may be recommended for restrictions or prohibition to the Steering Committee. The Steering Committee shall hold public consultations within 90 days of receipt of the recommendations, prior to forwarding such recommendations to the Central Government.*
- *Once a restriction on a priority substance has been notified, a request for authorization for use of a restricted substance may be submitted by a manufacturer, importer or authorized representative to the Division ... Such request shall be analysed by the Priority Substance Unit, to determine if such restricted substance is essential for the operation of an industrial process or for scientific research and development and a recommendation on such authorization shall be submitted to the Risk Assessment Committee. With the concurrence of the Risk Assessment Committee, such authorization may be granted.*
- *The Division may grant permission for authorised use of substances restricted under sub-rule (4) for an initial period of no more than 4 years. The Division may further extend such permission for a maximum additional period of 4 years on re-application by the registrant.*
- *These Rules are without prejudice to any restrictions, prohibitions or regulations on the use of any substances provided under any other enactment, for the time being in force.*

Import of priority substances or hazardous chemicals (Rule 27)

- *If the concerned authority is of an apprehension that the substance being imported is likely to cause a major chemical accident, it may direct the importer to take such safety measures as it may, deem appropriate.*
- *If the concerned authority, is of the opinion that the substance should not be imported on safety or on environmental considerations, the concerned authority may stop such imports and inform the chairman, central board of indirect taxes and customs or a competent person under him to stop such import. The*

concerned authority shall in such a case provide relevant information relating to such stopped imports to the Division.

Submission of Information relating to Industrial Activity and Site Safety Report (Rule 22)

- *The Concerned Authority shall, (a) within 90 days from the date of receipt of the report, approve the report submitted or on consideration of the report if concerned authority is of the opinion that there is or has been a contravention of the provisions of the Act or the Rules, issue an improvement notice to the occupier, and (b) forward copies of all such reports and approvals, as well as any improvement notices to the Division, immediately. ...*
- *The Division may provide recommendations to the Concerned Authority in relation to any report, approval or improvement notice after reviewing the report forwarded to it.*

Safety Audit Reports (Rule 24)

- *The Concerned Authority may, if he deems fit, issue an improvement notice within 45 days of the submission of the Safety Audit Report submitted under this Rule.*

8. Data submission format

Under development

9. Data confidentiality

- *A notifier or registrant may request that trade secrets, proprietary business information and other intellectual property related data and information shared by the notifier or the registrant be kept confidential and not be disseminated publicly.*
- *A request for confidentiality should be accompanied by ... a statement of reasons clearly identifying (a) what information is to be kept confidential; and (b) the reasons why such information should be kept confidential.*
- *The request for confidentiality will be submitted to the Division and it shall make the final determination of whether such request for confidentiality may be granted. The Division may require the notifier or the registrant to furnish documents or information to determine the validity of the request for confidentiality if it deems appropriate.*
- *The information or data with respect to which the request for confidentiality has been filed will be kept confidential and not disseminated publicly until such time as the Techno-legal Unit makes a final decision on the validity of such request.*
- *If a request for confidentiality has been granted with respect to certain information, then the Members of the Division, Scientific Committee, Risk Assessment Committee and the Steering Committee who have access to such information shall keep such information confidential even after the expiry of their term.*
- *A request for confidentiality may **not** be submitted for the classification of substances and “endpoint” summaries submitted during notification or registration.*
- *Where for the purpose of evaluating notification and registrations, the Division discloses that information to some other person, such person shall not use or disclose such information.*

10. Data that are published publicly (Rule 14)

- *The interactive digital platform ... shall include, subject to Rule 17, an information portal to disseminate, inter alia, the following information to the general public:*
 - *Information relating to notified and registered substances, their uses and classification*
 - *Information relating to deadlines*
 - *Standard operating procedures and technical guidance on notification, registration, chemical safety assessment and evaluation*

- *Templates for providing information for notification and registration*
- *The portal shall also, subject to Rule 17*
 - *Contain notices and other communication from the Division to notifiers and registrants, subject to the confidentiality obligations in Rule 17*
 - *Have provisions for e-filing of appeals.*

11. Information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.10 Chemical Substances Control Law (CSCL) Inventory, Japan

Last update: 25 October 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Act on the Regulation of Manufacture and Evaluation of Chemical Substances (Last Version: Amendment of Act No. 53 of 2017):
<http://www.japaneselawtranslation.go.jp/law/detail/?id=3350&vm=02&re=01>
- B. Order for Enforcement of the Act on the Regulation of Manufacture and Evaluation of Chemical Substances (Last version: Amendment of Cabinet Order No. 35 of 2018):
<http://www.japaneselawtranslation.go.jp/law/detail/?printID=&ft=1&re=02&dn=1&x=37&y=16&co=01&ia=03&ja=04&ky=manufacture+and+evaluation+of+chemical+substances&page=7&vm=02>
- C. Ministerial Order on Notification Concerning the Manufacture or Import of New Chemical Substances (Last Version: Amendment ... No. 5 of 2018):
<http://www.japaneselawtranslation.go.jp/law/detail/?ft=1&re=02&dn=1&x=36&y=11&co=01&ia=03&ja=04&ky=c.%09ministerial+order+on+notification+concerning+the+manufacture+or+import+of+new+chemical+substances&page=4>
- D. Ordinance for Enforcement of the Act on the Evaluation of Chemical Substances and Regulation of Their Manufacture, etc. as the Act Relates to the Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry (Last Version: Amendment of Ordinance of the Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry No. 7 of 2010):
<http://www.japaneselawtranslation.go.jp/law/detail/?printID=&ft=1&re=02&dn=1&x=37&y=16&co=01&ia=03&ja=04&ky=manufacture+and+evaluation+of+chemical+substances&page=16&vm=02>
- E. The guidance of special procedure to submit the annual notification of imported quantity of the previous fiscal year under CSCL (June 2011):
https://www.meti.go.jp/policy/chemical_management/english/cscl/files/publications/forimporters/guidance_eng.pdf
- F. Outline of the Chemical Substances Control Law (CSCL; April 2016):
https://www.meti.go.jp/policy/chemical_management/english/cscl/files/about/01CSCL.pdf
- G. Procedure for new chemicals under Chemical Substances Control Law (CSCL; December 2015):
https://www.meti.go.jp/policy/chemical_management/english/cscl/files/about/03CSCLnewchem.pdf
- H. Standards regarding new chemical substances which are polymers and which do not thought to pose a risk of causing damage to human health or the habitat and/or growth of flora and fauna in the human living environment by causing environmental pollution (September 2021):
<https://www.nite.go.jp/data/000128218.pdf>
- I. Implementation of the Act on the Regulation of Manufacture and Evaluation of Chemical Substances. (September 2021): <https://www.nite.go.jp/data/000128219.pdf>
- J. Testing methods for new chemical substances etc. (March 2011):
https://www.meti.go.jp/policy/chemical_management/english/cscl/files/laws/laws_testingmethods_110331.pdf
- K. Determination criteria for specified new chemical substances set forth in Article 4-4 of the Act on the Regulation of Manufacture and Evaluation of Chemical Substances (September 2021):
<https://www.nite.go.jp/data/000128224.pdf>
- L. Types of notification and data requirements:
https://www.nite.go.jp/chem/kasinn/basic_information.html
- M. CSCL – Laws, by METI: https://www.meti.go.jp/policy/chemical_management/english/cscl/laws.html; by NITE: <https://www.nite.go.jp/en/chem/kasinn/kaiseikasinhou.html>
- N. Chemical Lists under the CSCL: https://www.nite.go.jp/en/chem/chrip/chrip_search/sltLst

Note: These are unofficial translations provided by the Japanese Government.

- O. Polymer under Kashinho (Japanese Chemical Substances Control Law, CSCL):
<https://www.scas.co.jp/en/services/regulatoryscience/application-japan/chemical-substances-japan/polymer-kashinho.html>
- P. Application service for the Chemical Substances Control Law:
<https://www.scas.co.jp/en/services/regulatoryscience/application-japan/chemical-substances-japan/kashinho.html>
- Q. Polymer flow scheme (PFS) under Japan's Chemical Substance Control Law (CSCL):
https://www.cerij.or.jp/ceri_en/gyoumu/PFS.pdf

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

- Art. 1: *The purpose of this Act is to establish a system for evaluating the properties of **new chemical substances** before their manufacture or import and to implement necessary regulations with respect to the manufacture, import, use, etc. of chemical substances, depending on their properties, etc., in order to prevent environmental pollution caused by chemical substances that pose a risk of harming human health or interfering with the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna.* [A]
- List of existing chemical substances of the names of chemical substances that were manufactured or imported as a business at the time of the promulgation of this Act [1973] (excluding those that were manufactured or imported for testing and research purposes and those that were manufactured or imported as reagents)

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligations

Notification of Manufacture/Import

- Art. 3 [A]: *A person who intends to manufacture or import a new chemical substance shall notify the Minister of Health, Labour and Welfare [MHLW], the Minister of Economy, Trade and Industry [METI], and the Minister of the Environment [MOE], in advance, of the name of the relevant new chemical substance and other matters specified ...*
 - A new chemical substance = Art.2, a chemical substance other than the chemical substances listed in the following items:
 - a chemical substance for which public notice has been given by [MHLW], [METI] and [MOE] pursuant to the provisions of paragraph (5) of Article 4 (including cases where it is applied *mutatis mutandis* pursuant to paragraph (9) of Article 5 by replacing the terms, and the cases in which it is applied *mutatis mutandis* pursuant to paragraph (2) of Article 7)
 - a class I specified chemical substance⁹⁹

⁹⁹ (i) a chemical substance that is not likely to undergo a chemical transformation through natural processes and is bioaccumulative, and a chemical substance that falls under either of the following: a chemical substance that poses a risk of harming human health if taken in continuously, or a chemical substance that, if taken in continuously, poses a risk of interfering with the inhabitation and/or growth of predatory animals at higher trophic level (meaning animals that fall under the category of flora and fauna in the human living environment (meaning flora and fauna for which interference with their inhabitation and/or growth would pose a risk of interfering with the conservation of the living environment; the same applies hereinafter) for which chemical substances falling under (a) are most likely to bioaccumulate through the food chain; the same applies hereinafter) (ii) in the case of a chemical substance that is likely to undergo a chemical transformation through natural processes, one where the chemical substance (including an element) generated by the chemical transformation through natural processes falls under the preceding item [A]. As of 25 Oct 2021, it includes 33 substances, many of which have been listed under the Stockholm Convention [B].

- a class II specified chemical substance¹⁰⁰
- a priority assessment chemical substance¹⁰¹ (including one for which the designation has been rescinded pursuant to the provisions of Article 11 [limited to the part pertaining to (d) of item (ii)])
- a chemical substance (excluding any of those set forth in the preceding items) listed in the list of existing chemical substances prescribed in paragraph (1) of Article 2 of the Supplementary Provisions of this Act that has been made public by the Minister of International Trade and Industry pursuant to the provisions of paragraph (4) of the relevant Article
- a chemical substance (excluding any of those set forth in the preceding items) listed in the list [of type II and type III monitoring chemical substances]¹⁰² prescribed in Article 4 of the Supplementary Provisions of this Act that is made public by [MHLW], [METI] and [MOE].

Permission¹⁰³ to manufacture class I specified chemical substance

- Article 17 [A]: A person who intends to operate a business of manufacturing a class I specified chemical substance shall obtain permission from [METI] for each class I specified chemical substance and for each place of business.

Permission to import class I specified chemical substance

- Article 17 [A]: A person who intends to import a class I specified chemical substance shall obtain permission from [METI]; provided, however, that does not apply to the case when a person intends to import a class I specified chemical substance for testing and research purposes.

¹⁰⁰ A chemical substance that is thought to pose a risk of causing damage to human health or damage to the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna in the living environment, [itself or transformation products,] due to a considerable amount of the chemical substance remaining in the environment over a substantially extensive area or because it is likely that such a situation will arise in the near future in view of its properties and manufacture, import, use, etc. [A]. As of 25 Oct 2021, it includes trichloroethylene, tetrachloroethylene, carbon tetrachloride, 7 triphenyltin substances, and 13 tributyltin substances [B].

¹⁰¹ Chemical substances for which it is not clear whether they do not fall under any of the items of paragraph (3) from the perspective of currently available knowledge on the chemical substances, which are found to remain in the environment in considerable amounts or are expected to remain in such a situation in view of the knowledge and the state of manufacture, import, etc., and which are not found to be likely neither to harm human health nor to damage the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna in the human living environment through environmental pollution by the chemical substance; they are therefore designated by [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] as chemical substances that are found to require priority assessment of the likelihood of the chemical substances having the above risks through the collection of information on their properties and through the clarification of the status of their use, etc. [A]

¹⁰² A chemical substance (excluding a new chemical substance) that falls under either of the following items and has been designated by MHLW, METI and MOE: (i) a chemical substance that is not likely to undergo a chemical transformation through natural processes and is bioaccumulative, and where it is unclear whether or not the chemical poses a risk of harming human health if taken in continuously or if taken in continuously, poses a risk of interfering with the inhabitation and/or growth of predatory animals at higher tropic level; (ii) in the case of a chemical substance that is likely to undergo a chemical transformation through natural processes, one where the chemical substance (including an element) generated by the chemical transformation through natural processes falls under the preceding item. [A]

¹⁰³ Conditions may be attached to any permission, and the conditions attached may be changed. The conditions ... are limited to the minimum required for ensuring the secure implementation of the matters to which the permission pertains, and shall not impose undue obligations on the person who obtains the permission. (Art. 40 [A])

Books of class I specified chemical substance (Art. 31 [A])

- A permitted manufacturer/users shall keep books and enter therein the items specified by [METI] with respect to the manufacture/use of the class I specified chemical substance. The books ... shall be achieved in accordance with the provisions by [METI]/competent minister.

Notification of the Planned Quantity to Be Manufactured of class II specified chemicals (Art. 35 [A])

- *A person who manufactures or imports a Class II specified chemical substance, or a person who imports a product that is specified by Cabinet Order and in which a class II specified chemical substance is used ..., for each class II specified chemical substance or each product using a class II specified chemical substance, shall notify [METI], each fiscal year, of the planned quantity to be manufactured or planned quantity to be imported of the relevant class II specified chemical substance or the planned quantity to be imported of the relevant product using a class II specified chemical substance, and other matters specified by Order of [METI] ... ; provided, however, that this does not apply to the case where a person manufactures or imports a class II specified chemical substance or imports a product using a class II specified chemical substance for testing and research purposes.*
- *A person who has given a notification ... shall not manufacture or import in excess of the planned quantity to be manufactured or the planned quantity to be imported to which the relevant notification pertains (when approval has been granted for changes ..., in accordance with the plan after the changes).*

3.2 Exemptions**The term “chemical substance” as used in this Act ... excluding**

- *a radioactive substance*
- *specified poisonous substances prescribed in paragraph (3) of Article 2 of the Poisonous and Deleterious Substances Control Act (Act No. 303 of 1950)*
- *stimulants prescribed in paragraph (1) of Article 2 of the Stimulants Control Act (Act No. 252 of 1951) and stimulants’ raw materials prescribed in paragraph (5) of the relevant Article*
- *narcotics prescribed in item (i) of Article 2 of the Narcotics and Psychotropics Control Act (Act No. 14 of 1953). [A]*
- *... there are items not set forth under Order for Enforcement, and when such are applicable to the following item[s], they are regarded as “Products” and handled in accordance with relevant laws and regulations not stated herein. [I]*
 - *Products which possess unique product shape and which do not change in composition or shape during use (e.g. synthetic resin storage container, plates, tubes, sticks, film). However, in the event that during its use those products undergo changes within the scope of not losing their original function (deformation during use, change in size not affecting its function), undergo change in shape to serve their function (e.g. wear of an eraser), undergo change which cause them to accidentally lose their function as products (damage during use), these will not be handled as change in composition or shape.*
 - *Mixtures that are subdivided as needed and are in a state of being sold at stores, etc. by minimum changes to their labeling, etc. (e.g. synthetic resin paint with pigment, household detergent, etc.)*

Other Acts

The provisions of Article 3 [notification of manufacture], paragraph (1) of Article 7 [evaluation of a new chemical substance pertaining to a manufacturer in a foreign country], paragraph (1) of Article 8 [notification of quantity of manufacture of general chemical substances] (including in cases as applied mutatis mutandis pursuant to paragraph (2) of the same Article), Article 8-2 [provision of information of general chemical substances], paragraph (1) of Article 9 [notification of quantity of manufacture of priority assessment chemical substances],

paragraphs (1) and (2) of Article 10 [study of hazardous properties of priority assessment chemical substances], Article 12 [provision of information of priority assessment chemical substances], paragraph (1) of Article 13 [notification of the manufactured quantity of class I specified chemical substances], paragraph (1) of Article 14 [study on hazardous properties of monitoring chemical substances], Article 16 [provision of information of monitoring chemical substances], paragraph (1) of Article 17 [permission of manufacture of class I specified chemical substances], Article 18 [permission of manufacture of class I specified chemical substances], paragraphs (1) of Article 22 [permission to import of class I specified chemical substances], Article 25 [restrictions on use of class I specified chemical substances], paragraph (1) of Article 26 [notification of use of class I specified chemical substances], paragraph (2) of Article 28 [obligation of conformity to standards of class I specified chemical substances], paragraph (1) of Article 29 [labelling of class I specified chemical substances], paragraphs (1) and (3) of Article 34 [order to take measures in connection with designation of class I specified chemical substances], paragraph (1) of Article 35 [notification of the planned quantity to be manufactured of class II specified chemical substances], paragraph (1) of Article 36 [publication of technical guidelines of class II specified chemical substances], paragraph (1) of Article 37 [labelling of class II specified chemical substances], Article 38 [recommendations], Article 39 [guidance and advice], paragraphs (1) (including in cases as applied mutatis mutandis pursuant to paragraph (2) of Article 40) and (3) of Article 40 [conditions for permission] and Article 42 [reporting on the status of handling] do not apply to the chemical substances which constitute the articles listed in the following items;

the provisions of paragraph (1) of Article 24 [restrictions on import of products of class I specified chemical substances], paragraph (2) of Article 28, paragraph (1) of Article 29 and Article 34 do not apply to the products listed in the following items in which class I specified chemical substances are used;

the provisions of paragraph (1) of Article 35, paragraph (1) of Article 36, paragraph (1) of Article 37, Article 39 and Article 42 do not apply to the articles listed in the following items in which class II specified chemical substances are used; and

the provisions of Article 8-2, Article 12, Article 16, Article 25, paragraph (1) of Article 26, paragraph (2) of Article 28, paragraph (1) of Article 29, paragraph (3) of Article 34, paragraph (1) of Article 36, paragraph (1) of Article 37, Article 38, Article 39 and Article 42 do not apply to the use of chemical substances as raw materials for the articles listed in the following items, but the Acts set forth in the following items apply to them respectively:

- *food prescribed in paragraph (1) of Article 4 of the Food Sanitation Act (Act No. 233 of 1947), additives prescribed in paragraph (2) of the Article, containers and packaging prescribed in paragraph (5) of the relevant Article, toys prescribed in paragraph (1) of Article 62 of the relevant Act, and detergents prescribed in paragraph (2) of the relevant Article*
- *agricultural chemicals prescribed in paragraph (1) of Article 1-2 of the Agricultural Chemicals Regulation Act (Act No. 82 of 1948)*
- *ordinary fertilizers prescribed in paragraph (2) of Article 2 of the Fertilizers Regulation Act (Act No. 127 of 1950)*
- *feeds prescribed in paragraph (2) of Article 2 of the Act on Safety Assurance and Quality Improvement of Feeds (Act No. 35 of 1953) and feed additives prescribed in paragraph (3) of the relevant Article*
- *pharmaceuticals prescribed in paragraph (1) of Article 2 of the Act on Securing Quality, Efficacy and Safety of Products Including Pharmaceuticals and Medical devices (Act No. 145 of 1960), quasi-drugs prescribed in paragraph (2) of the same Article, cosmetics prescribed in paragraph (3) of the same Article, medical devices prescribed in paragraph (4) of the same Article, and regenerative medicine products prescribed in paragraph (9) of the same Article.*

Notification of Manufacture/Import [\[A\]](#)

- *if a person intends to import from a person who has **submitted a notification** ... and has received notice*

- if a person intends to manufacture or import a new substance for **testing and research purposes**
- if a person intends to manufacture or import a new chemical substance as a **reagent**¹⁰⁴
- if a person has received a confirmation from [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] ... to the effect that the manufacture or import falls under a case specified by Cabinet Order as one where the new chemical substance **does not pose a risk of causing environmental pollution** in consideration of the intended method of handling the relevant new chemical substance and other matters, and the relevant new chemical substance will be manufactured or imported in accordance with the particulars for which the relevant confirmation has been received;
 - when a person intends to manufacture or import a new chemical substance as the intermediate to another chemical substance, and has taken the necessary measures to prevent environmental pollution from the new chemical substance during the period until the new chemical substance is transformed into the other chemical substance [B]
 - when a person intends to manufacture or import a new chemical substance for use in a way that does not discharge the emissions outside the facility or equipment, and has taken the necessary measures to prevent environmental pollution from the new chemical substance during the period until the new chemical substance is disposed of [B]
 - Even if a new chemical product is used only in a specified closed system device, if it is used by unspecified and great number of users, it does not fall under this [item]. [I]
 - when a person intends to manufacture or import a new chemical substance for the purpose of export (limited to when the export is to a region that has been designated by [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] as a region where the necessary measures have been taken to prevent environmental pollution from the new chemical substance), and the person has taken the necessary measures to prevent environmental pollution from the new chemical substance during the period until the new chemical substance is exported [B]
 - [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] should rescind the confirmation
 - If the person who has received the confirmation ... had received the relevant confirmation by wrongful means
 - If the person who has received the confirmation ... is found to be manufacturing or importing the new chemical substance to which the relevant confirmation pertains in excess of the quantity to which the relevant confirmation pertains
 - ... if it is found that the new chemical substance ... poses a risk of harming human health or damage to the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna in the living environment by causing environmental pollution
- if the planned quantity to be manufactured or planned quantity to be imported ... in one fiscal year is not more than [1 tonne; B], and where a person has received a confirmation from [METI], [MHLW], and [MOE] ... to the effect that, as determined by already available knowledge, etc., the relevant new chemical substance **is not one that poses a risk** in harming human health or causing damage to the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna in the living environment by causing environmental pollution, and that person is to manufacture or import the relevant new chemical substance in a quantity of no more than that to which the relevant confirmation pertains during the relevant fiscal year;
 - If the total quantity of a single new chemical substance calculated¹⁰⁵ ..., as having an impact on the environment, based on the planned quantity to be manufactured and planned quantity to

¹⁰⁴ A reagent = a chemical substance used for the detection or quantification of a substance by a chemical process, or for the experimental synthesis of a substance, or for the measurement of the physical characteristics of a substance; the same applies hereinafter [A]

¹⁰⁵ multiplying the planned quantity to be manufactured or planned quantity to be imported ... by a coefficient specified by [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] according to the usage of the new chemical substance. [C]

be imported ... relating to the single new chemical substance exceeds [1 tonne; B] ..., [MHLW], [METI] and [MOE] shall not issue the confirmation under the relevant item.

- if the new chemical substance is a **polymer**¹⁰⁶ and if a person has received confirmation from [METI], [MHLW], and [MOE] ... to the effect that the new chemical substance **does not pose a risk** of harming human health or damage to the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna in the living environment by causing environmental pollution;¹⁰⁷ and the relevant new chemical substance is manufactured or imported.
 - The terms used in the test methods¹⁰⁸ are in accordance with the Japan Industrial Standards (JIS K 0211 (Technical terms for analytical chemistry (General part)), JIS K 0215 (Technical terms for analytical chemistry (analytical instrument part)), JIS K 7252 (Plastics -

¹⁰⁶ a chemical substance consisting of molecules characterized by the sequence of one or more types of monomer units, comprising 50 weight % and more of the molecules containing at least three monomer units, and comprising less than 50 weight % of the molecules of the same molecular weight, and the number average molecular weight is 1,000 or more. [H] Polymers are not distinguished by manner of polymerization, degree of crystallinity, tacticity or degree of polymerization (incl. degree of condensation) when the polymers do not have differences from the repeating unites (monomers and other reactants for polycondensation) and manner of polymerization. With regard to a compound that is an organic polymer which includes an initiator or chain transfer agent in the structure and the weight percentage of the initiator or chain transfer agent is less than 1% (if there are multiple initiators or chain transfer agents, weight percentage of each should be less than 1%), if the name of the aforementioned is not included in an organic polymer that is an existing chemical substance, it is handled as the same existing chemical substance. [I]

¹⁰⁷ A polymer that meets all the requirements listed below:

- (1) A polymer that meets the following stability criteria based on the physicochemical stability tests:
 - There is no change in the dissolved organic carbon (hereafter referred to as “DOC”) concentration exceeding 1 % (or change in the weight of test substances exceeding 2% when the decision based on the change in DOC is not appropriate) under any pH conditions of test solutions before and after the test.
 - There is no change in the IR spectrum under any pH conditions of test solutions before and after the test; and
 - There is no change in the molecular weight of test substance under any pH conditions of test solutions before and after the test.
 - (2) Based on solubility test in acid/alkali, there is no change in the DOC exceeding 1 % (or change in the weight of test substances exceeding 2% when the decision based on the change in DOC is not appropriate) before and after the test, or no cationic properties is indicated in the main structure of the test substance.
 - (3) Based on solubility test in water and organic solvents, there is no change in the DOC exceeding 1 % (or change in the weight of test substances exceeding 2% when the decision based on the change in DOC is not appropriate) in water test solution and no change in the weight of test substances exceeding 2% in organic solvent test solution before and after the test.
 - (4) No metal except for sodium, magnesium, potassium or calcium is contained in the chemical structure
- Or a polymer that meets all the requirements of (1), (2) and (4) of item 1, as well as the following (1) to (3):
- A polymer that does not fall under (3) of item 1 and has equal to or less than 1% of components with molecular weight less than 1,000, and is not known to be highly bioaccumulative.
 - The chemical structure contains neither arsenic nor selenium.
 - A polymer that falls ...: a. the number average molecular weight is 10,000 or more; or b. a polymer that does not fall under A and consists of monomers that are existing chemical substances, etc. and does not contain carbon-carbon double bonds, carbon-carbon triple bonds, carbon-nitrogen double bonds, carbon-nitrogen triple bonds, aziridinyl groups, amino groups, epoxy groups, sulfonate groups, hydrazino groups, phenolic hydroxyl groups, and fluoro groups in its chemical structure.. [H]

¹⁰⁸ [H] details test methods for the physicochemical stability and the solubility with respect to acid and alkali, for solubility with respect to water and organic solvents, and for measuring the molecular weight distribution.

Determination of average molecular mass and molecular mass distribution of polymers using size-exclusion chromatography), and JIS Z 8801 (Test sieves, etc.), [H]

- *A chemical substance with the smallest average molecular weight is selected as a test substance. However, if it is dissolved or dispersed in a solvent during polymer synthesis, the polymer isolated from the solvent without changing the properties of the chemical substance shall be used as the test substance. [H]*
- *[MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] should rescind the confirmation*
 - *If the person who has received the confirmation ... had received the relevant confirmation by wrongful means*
 - *If it is found that the new chemical substance ... poses a risk of harming human health or damage to the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna in the living environment by causing environmental pollution*
- *With regard to chemical compounds contained as impurities¹⁰⁹, if the content thereof is less than 1 wt.%, those chemical compounds shall not be handled as a new chemical substance. [I]*
- *With regard to intermolecular compounds, inclusion compounds, hydrates (including water of crystallization), etc. when individual chemical substances constituting the compound are all existing chemical substances, such compound shall not be considered as a new chemical substance. [I]*
- *Regarding “addition salts of organic compounds” (excluding metallic salt), when the acid and base constituting the salts are all existing chemical substances, those addition salts shall not be regarded as a new chemical substance. [I]*
- *In the case of onium salt, if the counter ion is a constituent of an existing chemical substance, that onium salt shall not be handled as a new chemical substance. [I]*
- *In the case of “acid or base”, when “the anion in the acid” or “cation in the base” are constituents of addition salts (excluding metallic salt) or onium salt which are existing chemical substances, that “acid or base” shall not be handled as a new chemical substance. [I]*

Permission to manufacture class I specified chemical substance (Art. 18 [A])

- *No person other than the one who has obtained permission ... shall manufacture a class I specified chemical substance; provided, however, that this does not apply to the case if a person manufactures a class I specified chemical substance for testing and research purposes.*

Notification of quantity of manufacture [E]

- *No need to notify general chemical substances and “Priority Assessment Chemical Substances” (PACs) whose annual manufactured and imported volume is less than 1 ton.*
- *No need to notify chemical substances manufactured or imported for testing and research purposes*
- *No need to notify chemical substances which is listed as low concern chemicals.*
- *No need to notify “products” defined in the implementation of CSCL import.*
- *In case of general chemical substances, no need to notify intentional additives and unintentional contaminations if the concentration rate is less than 10% weight.*
- *In case of mixtures, notifications are submitted by making a deduction for each Class Reference number or CAS number in accordance with appropriate reasoning such as the percentage of components. If the reasoning is unclear, it is acceptable to submit notifications by assuming the quantity of each chemical substance is same as that of total amount of mixture.*

¹⁰⁹ An “impurity” refers unintended substances such as unreacted raw materials, reaction catalysts, indicators or by-products (substances generated through unintended reaction), etc. [I]

- *In case the intended use of chemical substance is unknown, fill out the use category which is normally anticipated or “98(-z) other” as intended use.*

4. Initial data requirements

Notification of Manufacture/Import¹¹⁰ [C]

- *A method of submitting a written notification using Form. 1 setting forth the following particulars*
 - *Name of the new chemical substance*
 - *The structural or rational formula of the new chemical substance (if both are unclear, an outline of the manufacturing method)*
 - *Physical and chemical properties and ingredient composition of the new chemical substance*
 - *Usage of the new chemical substance¹¹¹*
 - *The planned quantity that will be manufactured or imported every year in the three years following the commencement of the manufacture or import of the new chemical substance*
 - *If a new chemical substance is to be manufactured, the name and location of the place of business that is to manufacture such new chemical substance; if the new chemical substance is to be imported, the name of the country or region where such new chemical substance is manufactured*
 - *Biodegradation study, bioaccumulation study, human-toxicity study, eco-toxicity study, polymer flow scheme [L]*
- *A method of using the electronic data processing system prescribed in Article 11*

Notification Concerning the Manufacture of a New Chemical Substance by Manufacturers in a Foreign State [C]

- *... using Form. 1-2 setting forth the following particulars*
 - *Name of the new chemical substance*
 - *The structural or rational formula of the new chemical substance (if both are unclear, an outline of the manufacturing method)*
 - *Physical and chemical properties and ingredient composition of the new chemical substance*
 - *Usage of the new chemical substance*
 - *The planned quantity that will be manufactured or imported every year in the three years following the commencement of the manufacture or import of the new chemical substance*

¹¹⁰ *Among the tests ... , whose purpose meet the purposes in the “combined repeated dose toxicity study with reproduction/development toxicity screening test conducted with mammals” ..., those which have been performed in accordance with OECD Test Guidelines shall be able to be handled as a test that meets the purpose of this joint notification.*

Among tests whose purpose meets the purposes of chronic toxicity study, studies for effects on reproductive ability and subsequent generations, teratogenesis study, mutagenicity study, carcinogenicity study, study on metabolic fate, or pharmacological studies, those which have been performed in accordance with OECD Test Guidelines shall, in principle, be able to be handled as a test that meets the purpose of this joint notification. [J]

Biodegradation test methods can be found at: <https://www.nite.go.jp/data/000128243.pdf> (September 2021); Bioconcentration test of substances in fish shellfish can be found at: <https://www.nite.go.jp/data/000128242.pdf> (September 2021); Concerning the assessment of bioaccumulation of new chemical substances by analog approach, etc. (September 2013):

https://www.meti.go.jp/policy/chemical_management/english/files/laws/bioaccumulation_analog_approach.pdf

¹¹¹ Japanese use category under amended CSCL:

https://www.meti.go.jp/policy/chemical_management/english/cscl/files/publications/forimporters/use_category.pdf

- *If a new chemical substance is to be manufactured, the name and location of the place of business that is to manufacture such new chemical substance; if the new chemical substance is to be imported, the name of the country or region where such new chemical substance is manufactured*

Request pertaining to Confirmation of Small Production Volume New Chemical Substances [C]

- *a method of submitting a written request using Form No. 9 or a copy thereof*
- *a method of submitting the optical disc prescribed in Article 12 (meaning an optical disc with a diameter of 120 mm that conforms to Japanese Industrial Standards X0606 and X6281 or X6241, or X6245; the same applies hereinafter)*
- *a method of using the electronic data processing system prescribed in Article 13*
- ≤ 1 tonne/year, no test data required [L]

Requests for Exceptions in Cases of Evaluations of Low Production Volume New Chemical Substances [C]

- *a method of submitting a written request using Form No. 11 attached to a written notification using Form No. 1*
- *a method of using the electronic data processing system prescribed in Article 11*
- ≤ 10 tonnes/year, biodegradation study, bioaccumulation study [L]

Permission to manufacture class I specified chemical substance (Article 17 [A], [D])

- *A person who intends to obtain permission ... shall submit a written application stating the following matters to [METI]*
 - *A drawing describing the location of the manufacturing equipment (including the relative position to other equipment) and the state of the vicinity of the place of business*
 - *A document explaining state of the employment and arrangement of employees and the technical capacity of employees*
 - *A document explaining a summary of the manufacturing process*
 - *A document stating the production plan and planned quantity of sales for each main customer*
 - *A document explaining means of storage and means of transportation*
 - *When the applicant is a juridical person, the articles of incorporation or articles of endowment and certificate of registered matters of that juridical person*
 - *A document explaining that the applicant (when the applicant is a juridical person, that juridical person and any officer who performs the business of that juridical person) does not fall under any of the items of Article 19 of the Act*
 - *The business report, balance sheet and profit and loss statement or equivalent documents pertaining to recent business years*
 - *In addition to what is listed in the preceding items, a document explaining that the person has a sufficient fiscal foundation to properly conduct that business.*

Permission to import class I specified chemical substance (Article 22 [A], [D])

- *A person who intends to obtain permission ... shall submit a written application stating the following matters to [METI]*
 - *A document stating the name of the manufacturer and name of the country or region it belongs to, the planned date of landing, the name of the import harbor and the planned quantity of sales for each main customer*
 - *A document explaining means of storage and means of transportation*
 - *When the applicant is a juridical person, the articles of incorporation or articles of endowment and certificate of registered matters of that juridical person*

- *A document explaining that the applicant (when the applicant is a juridical person, that juridical person and any officer who performs the business of that juridical person) does not fall under any of the items of Article 19 of the Act*

Notification of use of class I specified chemical substance (Art. 26 [A])

- *A person who intends to use a class I specified chemical substance as their business shall notify the competent minister of the following matters, in advance, for each place of business; provided, however, that this does not apply to the case when a person intends to use a class I specified chemical substance as their business for testing and research purposes*
 - *The name and domicile, and in the case of a corporation the name of the representative person*
 - *The location of the place of business*
 - *The name of the class I specified chemical substance and the usage*
 - *Form 5 [D]*

5. Updates by companies after initial steps

Notification of quantity of manufacture [A]

- *Article 8: A person who manufactures or imports **general chemical substances** shall in every fiscal year ... notify [METI] of the quantity of manufacture, quantity of import or other matters specified ... for each general chemical substance in the preceding fiscal year; provided, however, that this does not apply if the person falls under any of the following items*
 - *i. If a person manufactures or imports a general chemical substance for testing and research purposes*
 - *ii. with regard to a general chemical substance, if the quantity of manufacture or quantity of import of the general chemical substance by the person (in the case of a person who manufactures and imports the relevant general chemical substance, the sum of these quantities) is less than [1 tonne; B] ...*
 - *iii. if a person manufactures or imports a chemical substance that is found not to fall under [class I specified chemical substance, itself or its transformation products] or [class II specific chemical substance, itself or its transformation products] and other chemical substances that are specified by [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] as chemical substances for which it is not found necessary to conduct an assessment as prescribed in paragraph (5) of the relevant Article.*
 - *The provisions here (excluding item (iii)) apply mutatis mutandis to a person who manufactures or imports a new chemical substance pertaining to the notice prescribed in paragraph (5) of Article 4 (including when it is applied mutatis mutandis pursuant to paragraph (9) of Article 5 by replacing the terms) (this person is to be limited to a person who has received the relevant notification) and to a person who imports a new chemical substance pertaining to notification as prescribed in paragraph (5) of Article 4 as applied mutatis mutandis pursuant to paragraph (2) of the preceding Article from a person who has received the relevant notification.*
 - *Form 11 – name of general chemical substances, shipping quantity of the preceding fiscal year of general chemical substance [D]*
- *Article 9: A person who manufacture or imports a **priority assessment chemical substance** (excluding one that is designated as a Class II specified chemical substance ...) shall in every fiscal year, ... , shall notify [METI] of the manufactured quantity, import quantity or other matters specified ... for each priority assessment chemical substance in the preceding fiscal year; provided, however, that this does not apply if the person falls under any of the following items:*
 - *if a person manufactures or imports a priority assessment chemical substance for testing and research purposes;*

- ... when the manufactured quantity or import quantity of the priority assessment chemical substance pertaining to the person (in the case of a person who manufactures and imports the relevant priority assessment chemical substance, the sum of these quantities) is less than [1 tonne; B].
- Form 12 – name of priority assessment chemical substances, shipping quantity of the preceding fiscal year of priority assessment chemical substance, In the case where priority assessment chemical substances were manufactured, the name of the place of business that manufactured those priority assessment chemical substances and its location, and in the case where priority assessment chemical substances were imported, the name of the country or region where those priority assessment chemical substances were manufactured [D]
- Article 13: *A person who has manufactured or imported any **monitoring chemical substance**, each fiscal year, must notify [METI] of the manufactured quantity or the import quantity in the preceding fiscal year and other matters specified by [METI] for each monitoring chemical substance ... ; provided, however, that this does not apply to the case where the person has manufactured or imported a monitoring chemical substance for testing and research purposes.*
 - Form 13 – name of monitoring chemical substances, shipping quantity of the preceding fiscal year of monitoring chemical substance, In the case where monitoring chemical substances were manufactured, the name of the place of business that manufactured those monitoring chemical substances and its location, and in the case where monitoring chemical substances were imported, the name of the country or region where those monitoring chemical substances were manufactured [D]

Permission to manufacture class I specified chemical substance (Art. 21 [A])

- *A person who has obtained permission under paragraph (1) of Article 17 ... shall receive the permission of [METI] if the person intends to make changes to [the structure and capacity of the manufacturing equipment]; provided, however, that does not apply to the case when a person intends to make minor changes specified ...*
 - *The permitted manufacturer shall submit to [METI] a written report stating the monthly quantity of manufacture, the monthly quantity of inventory and the monthly quantity of goods sold for each customer of class I specified chemical substances pertaining to the permission under Article 17, paragraph (1) of the Act in that business year within three months from the end of each business year. [D]*
- *If a permitted manufacturer has made changes to [the name and domicile, and in the case of a corporation the name of the representative person, and the location of the place of business] or has made minor changes specified by [METI], the manufacturer shall notify [METI] to that effect without delay.*

Notification of use of class I specified chemical substance (Art. 26 [A])

- *If a person who has given a notification ... has made any changes to the matters ..., the person shall notify the competent minister to that effect without delay.*

Books (Art. 31 [A], [D])

- *A permitted manufacturer [or a notifying user] shall keep books and enter therein the items specified by [METI] with respect to the manufacture of the class I specified chemical substance*
 - *...for each place of business, the manufactured quantity of class I specified chemical substances, the inventory quantity thereof and the sales quantity thereof for each customer shall be recorded the quantity of goods sold shall be stated for each class I specified chemical substance and place of business, and each quantity of manufacture, quantity of inventory and customer of class I specified chemical substance.*

- *The books of the preceding paragraph shall be arranged by each place of business, and end stating the matters prescribed in the preceding paragraph in the preceding month by the end of every month.*
- *The books in paragraph (1) shall be retained for five years calculated from the date of closure.*
- *The provisions of the preceding three paragraphs shall apply mutatis mutandis to the notifying user. In this case the term "quantity of manufacture" in paragraph (1) shall be deemed to be replaced with "quantity of use", and "quantity of inventory" shall be deemed to be replaced with "quantity of storage".*

Notification of abolition of class I specified chemical substance (Art. 32 [A])

- *When a permitted manufacturer or a notifying user has closed their business, the relevant person shall notify [METI], in the case of a permitted manufacturer, and notify the competent minister, in the case of a notifying user, to that effect without delay.*
- *When a permitted manufacturer has closed their business, the relevant permission is to lose its effect.*

Notification of the Planned Quantity to Be Manufactured of class II specified chemicals (Art. 35 [A])

- *If a person who has given a notification under the provisions of the preceding paragraph has made changes ..., the person shall notify [METI] to that effect without delay.*
 - *Form 14 – Name of class II specified chemical substances or product using class II specified chemical substances, planned shipping quantity of class II specified chemical substances or product using class II specified chemical substances, In the case where class II specified chemical substances are to be manufactured, the name of the place of business that manufactures those class II specified chemical substances and its location, and in the case where class II specified chemical substances or products using class II specified chemical substances are to be imported, the name of the country or region where those class II specified chemical substances or products using class II specified chemical substances are manufactured [D]*
- *A person who has given a notification ..., each fiscal year, shall notify [METI] of the quantity of manufacture or the quantity of import in the preceding fiscal year and other matters specified by [METI] for each class II specified chemical substance or each product using a class II specified chemical substance ...*
 - *Form 13 – Name of class II specified chemical substances or product using class II specified chemical substances, planned shipping quantity of class II specified chemical substances or product using class II specified chemical substances, In the case where class II specified chemical substances are to be manufactured, the name of the place of business that manufactures those class II specified chemical substances and its location, and in the case where class II specified chemical substances or products using class II specified chemical substances are to be imported, the name of the country or region where those class II specified chemical substances or products using class II specified chemical substances are manufactured [D]*

Reporting of Hazardous Properties (Art. 41 [A])

- *When a person operating the business of manufacturing or importing any priority assessment chemical substance, any monitoring chemical substance, any class II specified chemical substance or any general chemical substance ... has conducted tests for the items to be tested prescribed in paragraph (7) of Article 4 or for the studies of hazardous properties prescribed in paragraph (2) of Article 10 [study of hazardous properties of priority assessment chemical substances] or paragraph (1) of Article 14 [study on hazardous properties of monitoring chemical substances] (including those cases in which knowledge equivalent to that which would be obtained from the relevant tests [limited to knowledge that is not publicly known] has been obtained) with regard to the substance to be reported that the person has manufactured or imported and if the person has obtained, as a result thereof, knowledge specified by*

[MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] that indicates that that the substance to be reported possesses the following properties, the person shall report to [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] to that effect and provide the details of the relevant knowledge, ...; provided, however, that this does not apply to cases when the relevant person has obtained the relevant knowledge as a result of a study of hazardous properties to which an instruction under the provisions of paragraph (2) of Article 10 or paragraph (1) of Article 14 pertains and is reporting the details of the relevant knowledge pursuant to these provisions:

- the substance reported is not likely to undergo a chemical transformation through natural processes;
 - the substance reported is bioaccumulative;
 - the substance reported poses a risk of impairing human health if taken in continuously;
 - the substance reported poses a risk of interfering with the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna;
 - in the case that the substance to be reported is likely to undergo a chemical transformation through natural processes, it is one where the chemical substance (including an element) generated by the chemical transformation through natural processes falls under any of the preceding items.
- When a person who engages in the business of manufacturing or importing a priority assessment chemical substance, a monitoring chemical substance or a class II specified chemical substance has knowledge of the composition, properties, etc. of the priority assessment chemical substance, the monitoring chemical substance or the class II specified chemical substance that the person has manufactured or imported as specified by [MHLW], [METI] and [MOE] (the knowledge is limited to that which is not publicly known, and excluding that which is to be reported pursuant to the provisions of paragraph (2) of Article 10, paragraph (1) of Article 14 or paragraph (1) of this Article), the person must endeavor to report to that effect and the details of the relevant knowledge to [MHLW], [METI] and [MOE] ...

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

Evaluation of notification of manufacture/import (Art. 4 [A])

- If [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] find it necessary in order to make a determination [as to which item the new chemical substance falls under], they may request the person who has given the notification ... to submit materials stating the results of tests prescribed¹¹² ... relating to the properties of the new chemical substance ... and any other documents specified ...

Study of Hazardous Properties of Priority Assessment Chemical Substances (Art. 10 [A])

- If [MHLW], [METI] and [MOE] find it necessary to conduct the assessment ... for a priority assessment chemical substance, they may request that a person who engages in the business of manufacturing or importing the relevant priority assessment chemical substance ... submit materials in which results of the tests that are prescribed in paragraph (7) of Article 4 on the properties of the relevant priority assessment chemical substance and that are specified by [MHLW], [METI] and [MOE].
 - Persons = who were operating the business of the manufacture or import of priority assessment chemical substances ... within three years prior to the day of the request for the submission of materials stating test results [D]

¹¹² Test methods and Determination Criteria for New Chemical Substances and the Applicability as Monitoring Chemical Substances (April 13, 2018): <https://www.nite.go.jp/data/000128225.pdf>

Notice of the Good Laboratory Practice for test facilities conducting tests of New Chemical Substances: <https://www.nite.go.jp/data/000009018.pdf>

- *With regard to a priority assessment chemical substance, if it is found that there are reasons to suspect that it falls under [Class II specified chemical substance] from the perspective of the results of tests set forth in the preceding paragraph and other already available knowledge on the relevant priority assessment chemical substance and if the relevant priority assessment chemical substance falls under any of the items of the relevant paragraph based on its properties and the status of its manufacture, import, use, etc., it is expected that the relevant priority assessment chemical substance is likely to harm human health or damage the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna in the living environment by causing environmental pollution; so in case [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] find it necessary to judge whether or not the relevant priority assessment chemical substance falls under any of the items of the relevant paragraph, they may instruct a person who engages in the manufacture or import of the relevant priority assessment chemical substance to conduct a study of ... the effects of the relevant chemical substance on human health and its effects on the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna in the living environment if continuously taken in, and report the results.*

Study on Hazardous Properties of Monitoring Chemical Substances (Art. 14 [A])

- *In the case where [MHLW], [METI] and [MOE] find sufficient reason to suspect that any single monitoring chemical substance falls under [class I specified chemicals], if they have found it necessary to make a determination as to whether or not the relevant monitoring chemical substance falls under [class I specified chemicals] since the relevant monitoring chemical substance is expected to pose a risk of causing environmental pollution if the relevant monitoring chemical substance falls under [class I specified chemicals], in view of the state of its manufacture, import, use, etc., they may instruct ... a person engaged in the business of manufacturing or importing of the relevant monitoring chemical substance (including a person who engaged in such business and who is specified by Order of [METI]) to conduct a study ... on the effects of the relevant chemical substance on human health or on the life and/or growth of predatory animals at higher trophic levels if taken in continuously; ... and to report the results thereof.*

Reporting on the status of handling (Art. 42 [A])

- *The competent ministers may request that a business operator handling a priority assessment chemical substance, a business operator handling a monitoring chemical substance, a business operator handling a class II specified chemical substance, etc., a business operator handling a specified general chemical substance or a business operator handling a specified new chemical substance report the status of their handling of a priority assessment chemical substance, a monitoring chemical substance, a class II chemical substance, etc., a specified general chemical substance or a specified new chemical substance.*

Collection of reports (Art. 43 [A])

- *[MHLW], [METI] and [MOE], to the extent necessary for enforcing this Act, may have a person who has received a confirmation under [notification of manufacture] or under [exception on an evaluation when the planned quantity to be manufactured is below a certain quantity] make a report concerning their operations.*
- *[MHLW], [METI] and [MOE], to the extent necessary for enforcing this Act, may have, respectively, a permitted manufacturer, a permitted importer, a business operator handling class I specified chemical substance, etc. or a person who has given a notification under [notification of the planned quantity to be manufactured of class II specified chemical substance] make a report concerning their operations.*
- *The competent ministers, to the extent necessary for enforcing this Act, may have a person prescribed in Article 34 [order to take measures in connection with designation of class I specified chemical substances] or Article 38 [recommendations] make a report concerning their operations.*

On-site inspections (Art. 44 [A])

- [MHLW], [METI] and [MOE], to the extent necessary for enforcing this Act, may have their officials enter the offices or any other places of business of a person who has received a confirmation under [notification of manufacture] or under [exception on an evaluation when the planned quantity to be manufactured is below a certain quantity], inspect the books, documents, and any other articles, ask questions of the relevant persons, or sample the smallest quantity of chemical substances necessary for testing.
- [MHLW], [METI] and [MOE], to the extent necessary for enforcing this Act, may have their officials enter the offices or any other places of business of a permitted manufacturer, a permitted importer, a business operator handling a class I specified chemical substance, etc. or a person who has given a notification under ... Article 35 [notification of the planned quantity to be manufactured of class II specified chemical substances], inspect the books, documents, and any other articles, ask questions of the relevant persons, or sample the smallest quantity of chemical substances necessary for testing.
- The competent ministers, to the extent necessary for enforcing this Act, may have their officials enter the offices or any other places of business of a person prescribed in Article 34 [order to take measures in connection with designation of class I specified chemical substances], inspect the books, documents, and any other articles, ask questions of the relevant persons, or sample the smallest quantity of chemical substances necessary for testing.

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

Evaluation of notification of manufacture/import¹¹³ (Art. 4 [A])

- If [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] have received a notification ..., they should make a determination as to which of the following items the new chemical substance falls under, within three months¹¹⁴ from the date of receipt of the notification, based on the available knowledge on the composition, properties, etc., of the new chemical substance to which the relevant notification pertains, and should notify the results thereof to the person who has given the notification
 - A chemical substance that falls under **class I specified chemical substance**
 - A chemical substance that is suspected to pose a risk of harming human health if taken in continuously, itself or one of its transformation products, and/or is likely to pose a risk of interfering with the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna, itself or one of its transformation products
 - A chemical substance that does NOT fall under the previous items
 - A chemical substance where it is unclear as to whether or not it falls under the previous items
 - [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] should promptly make a determination as to which one of the items ... the new chemical substances under, based on the results of tests conducted on the new chemical substance, and should notify the result thereof to the person who has given the notification

¹¹³ The Chemical Management Center (CMC) of the National Institute of Technology and Evaluation (NITE) has been developing scientific and objective risk assessment method for Priority Assessment Chemical Substances (PACs) and other chemical substances under the CSCL. CMC has published following documents and a tool (in Japanese): Report summarizing the study results of the method to determine candidate PACs (The screening assessment); Technical guidance documents for risk assessment of PACs (NITE draft; Risk assessment tool based on the method that was proposed in the technical guidance documents (PRAS-NITE). https://www.nite.go.jp/en/chem/risk/risk_index.html

¹¹⁴ It is changed to four months, when a person who intends to manufacture in a foreign country a new chemical substance to be exported to Japan or a person who intends to export a new chemical substance to Japan, in advance, may notify MHLW, METI, and MOE of the name of the relevant new chemical substance and any other matters specified ... [A]

- *A person who intends to give a notification ... and for whom the planned quantity to be manufactured or planned quantity to be imported of the new chemical substance to which the notification pertains during one fiscal year will be not more than the quantity specified ..., when giving the notification, may make a request to [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] ... to make a determination as to whether or not the relevant new chemical substance falls under either of the following items...: a chemical substance where it is unclear as to whether or not it falls under items [as a chemical substance that is suspected to pose a risk of harming human health if taken in continuously, itself or one of its transformation products, and/or is likely to pose a risk of interfering with the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna, itself or one of its transformation products, itself or one of its transformation products]*
- *If [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] have received a request under the preceding paragraph, ..., they should, notwithstanding the provisions of the relevant paragraph, make a determination as to which of the following items the relevant new chemical substance fall under, ..., based on already available knowledge on the composition, properties, etc. of the new chemical substance ... within three months from the date of receipt of a notification ... and should notify the result thereof to the person who has made the request ...; in this case, the provisions of paragraph (2) of the relevant Article do not apply*
 - *A substance that falls under any of the items of the preceding paragraph*
 - *A substance that does not fall under any of the items of the preceding paragraph*
 - *A chemical substance where it is unclear as to whether or not it falls under any of the items of the preceding paragraph*
 - *They should promptly make a determination as to which one of the items ... the relevant new chemical substance falls under, based on the results of tests conducted on the relevant new chemical substance, and should notify the result thereof to the person who has made the request*
- *A person who has received notice ... may make a request in advance, each fiscal year, to [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] and receive a confirmation to the effect that the manufacture or import of the new chemical substance ... falls under the following items*
 - *the planned quantity to be manufactured or planned quantity to be imported of the relevant new chemical substance during the fiscal year to which the request pertains is not more than [10 tonnes; B];*
 - *determined by already available knowledge, etc., the new chemical substance is not one that poses a risk of harming human health or damage to the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna in the living environment by causing environmental pollution.*
- *If [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] have made a determination, if they determine that the new chemical substance ... falls under [A chemical substance that is suspected to pose a risk of harming human health if taken in continuously, itself or one of its transformation products, and/or is likely to pose a risk of interfering with the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna, itself or one of its transformation products] and also falls under [specified general chemical substance],¹¹⁵ they should notify the result*

¹¹⁵ A chemical substance that

thereof to the person who has given the notification; provided, however, that this does not apply to a specified new chemical substance that has been designated [as priority assessment chemical substance].

- When [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] have given notice ..., they should give public notice of the result of the determination ... upon giving public notice pursuant to the provisions [right below]
- One of the hazard assessment values derived according to II.(3-1) of the “Determination Criteria and Test methods for New Chemical Substances and Monitoring Chemical Substances (April 13, 2018, Chemical Safety Office, MHLW; Chemical Safety Bureau, METI; Chemical Evaluation Office, MOE)”¹¹⁶ (hereafter referred to as “Determination Criteria”) is equal to or less than 0.0005 mg/kg/day [K]
- One of (i) the bacterial reverse mutation test and (ii) in vitro mammalian chromosome aberration test or mouse lymphoma TK test is determined to be strongly positive, and the other is determined to be positive or strongly positive. [K]
- The PNEC derived according to II. (4-1) of the Determination Criteria is 3E-4 mg/L or lower in 3 types of chronic toxicity test results, 3E-5 mg/L or lower in 2 types of chronic test results and 1 type of acute toxicity test results, or 3E-5 mg/L or lower in 1 type of chronic test results and 2 types of acute toxicity test results. [K]
- Notwithstanding the above, determination of specified new chemical substances shall be made comprehensively with the assumption that toxicity could be posed by chronic toxicity tests and with the consideration of test data of general toxicity if the chemical substance has strong mutagenicity. [K]
- If [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] have given notice to the effect that the new chemical substance ... falls under any of items [above, except class I specified chemical substances and substances whether where it is unclear as to whether or not it falls under the previous items], they should give a public notice of the name of the relevant new chemical substance ...; provided, however, that this does not apply to a specified new chemical substance that has been designated [as priority assessment chemical substance]
- A person who has given a notification ... shall not manufacture or import the new chemical substance ... until after the receipt of notice ... relating to the relevant new chemical substance; provided, however, that this does not apply to either of the following cases
 - If the manufacture or import of the new chemical substance [that are exempted from notification]
 - In the case where the person has received confirmation ... where the quantity of manufacture or import of the relevant new chemical substance shall be not more than the quantity to which relevant confirmation pertains

Study of Hazardous Properties of Priority Assessment Chemical Substances (Art. 10 [A])

- If the report ... is made, [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] should judge whether or not the priority assessment chemical substance ... falls under [Class II specified chemical substance] and notify the person who made the report of the results

-
- falls within the category of a general chemical substance (excluding priority assessment chemical substances, monitoring chemical substances, class I specified chemical substances, and class II specified chemical substances)
 - that falls under any of the following items: (i) a chemical substance that poses a risk of seriously harming human health if taken in continuously, itself or one of its transformation products, (ii) a chemical substance that is likely to pose a risk of seriously interfering with the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna in the living environment, if the flora and fauna continuously take in or are exposed to the relevant chemical substance, itself or one of its transformation products [A]

¹¹⁶ <https://www.nite.go.jp/data/000128225.pdf>

Rescission of Designation as a Priority Assessment Chemical Substance (Art. 11 [A])

- *If a priority assessment chemical substance falls under any of the following items, [MHLW], [METI] and [MOE] should rescind the designation and make the rescission public without delay:*
 - *if the priority assessment chemical substance is designated as a class I specified chemical substance, a class II specified chemical substance (limited to cases when it falls under all of the items of paragraph (3) of Article 2) or a monitoring chemical substance;*
 - *if the priority assessment chemical substance falls under any of the following (a) through (d) based on the submission of materials ..., the report ..., or on knowledge that has been otherwise obtained and the status of its manufacture, import, use, etc.:*
 - *if the relevant priority assessment chemical substance is designated as a class II specified chemical substance falling under item (i) of paragraph (3) of Article 2, when it is found that the relevant priority assessment chemical substance is not likely to cause damage to the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna in the living environment by causing environmental pollution;*
 - *if the relevant priority assessment chemical substance is designated as a class II specified chemical substance falling under item (ii) of paragraph (3) of Article 2, when it is found that the relevant priority assessment chemical substance is not likely to cause damage to human health by causing environmental pollution*
 - *when the relevant priority assessment chemical substance is designated as a class II specified chemical substance falling under any of the items of paragraph (3) of Article 2, if it is found that the relevant priority assessment chemical substance falls under an item other than the relevant item*
 - *if it is found that the relevant priority assessment chemical substance is not likely to harm human health or damage to the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna in the living environment by causing environmental pollution*

Study on Hazardous Properties of Monitoring Chemical Substances (Art. 14 [A])

- *If [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] have received a report ..., they should make a determination as to whether or not the monitoring chemical substances ... falls under [class I specified chemical substance] and notify the result thereof to the person who has made the report.*

Rescinding the designation of monitoring chemical substance (Art. 15 [A])

- *When [MHLW], [METI], and [MOE] find that a monitoring chemical substance falls under either of the following items, they should rescind the designation and make it public to that effect without delay*
 - *If the relevant chemical substance is designated as a class I specified chemical substance*
 - *If the relevant chemical substance is found not to fall under [class I specified chemical substance]*

Permission to manufacture class I specified chemical substance (Article 17 [A])

- *[METI] shall not grant permission ..., unless the minister finds that the application for permission under the relevant paragraph conforms to the following items:*
 - *the granted permission does not result in the capacity to manufacture the relevant class I specified chemical substance in excess in light of the demand for the relevant class I specified chemical substance;*
 - *the manufacturing equipment shall conform to the technical standards specified by [MHLW], [METI] and [MOE];*
 - *the applicant shall have a sufficient fiscal basis and technical capacity to implement the business appropriately.*

Permission to import class I specified chemical substance

- Article 23 [A]: *When [METI] has received an application for permission ... the minister should not grant permission ... unless the minister finds that the import of the class I specified chemical substance to which the relevant application pertains is necessary for meeting the demand for the relevant class I specified chemical substance.*
- Article 24 [A]: *A person shall not import any product that is specified by Cabinet Order and in which a class I specified chemical substance is used¹¹⁷ ... The Cabinet Order ... should [be] established for each class I specified chemical substance by giving consideration to such matters as the circumstances of the use of the relevant class I specified chemical substance overseas.*

Restriction on use of class I specified chemical substance

- Article 25 [A]: *A person shall not use a class I specified chemical substance for any usages other than those specified by Cabinet Order for each class I specified chemical substance as being compliant with the following requirements; provided, however, that this does not apply to the case when a person uses a class I specified chemical substance for testing and research purposes*
 - *It is difficult to substitute the relevant chemical substance with any other substance with regard to the relevant usage*
 - *It shall not be likely to pose a risk of harming human health or damage to the inhibition and/or growth of flora and fauna in the living environment by causing environmental pollution attributable to the relevant class I specified chemical substance that is used for in the relevant usage.*

Order to take measures in connection with designation of class I specified chemical substances (Article 34 [A])

- *If any chemical substance has been designated as a class I specified chemical substance, if the competent ministers find it particularly necessary for preventing the spread of environmental pollution attributable to the relevant chemical substance, they may, to the extent necessary, order persons who were operating the business of manufacturing or importing the relevant chemical substance or a product in which the relevant chemical substance is used at the time of the relevant designation to make efforts to recall the relevant chemical substance or the relevant product and to take any other measures necessary for preventing the spread of environmental pollution attributable to the relevant chemical substance.*
- *If any product has been designated as a product using a class I specified chemical substance, if the competent ministers find it particularly necessary for preventing the spread of environmental pollution attributable to the class I specified chemical substance being used in the relevant product, they may, to the extent necessary, order persons who were operating the business of importing the relevant product at the time of the relevant designation to make efforts to recall the relevant product which they imported and to take any other measures necessary for preventing the spread of environmental pollution attributable to the class I specified chemical substance being used in the relevant product.*
- *In any of the cases listed in the following items, if the competent ministers find it particularly necessary for preventing the spread of environmental pollution attributable to the class I specified chemical substance, they may, to the extent necessary, order the persons respectively specified in those items to make efforts to recall the class I specified chemical substance which they manufactured, imported or used or the product using a class I specified chemical substance which they imported and to take any other measures necessary for preventing the spread of environmental pollution attributable to the relevant class I specified chemical substance:*

¹¹⁷ Detailed products for individual class I specified chemical substances are specified in [B].

- *if a class I specified chemical substance has been manufactured in violation of [permission to manufacture]: the person who has manufactured the ... chemical substance;*
- *if a class I specified chemical substance has been imported in violation of [permission to import]: the person who has imported the relevant class I specified chemical substance;*
- *if a product using a class I specified chemical substance has been imported in violation of [restriction on import of products]: the person who has imported the relevant product using a class I specified chemical substance;*
- *if a class I specified chemical substance has been used in violation of [restrictions on use]: the person who has used the relevant class I specified chemical substance.*

Notification of the Planned Quantity to Be Manufactured of class II specified chemicals (Art. 35 [A])

- *In the case of a situation when it is necessary to restrict the manufacture or import of a class II specified chemical substance or the import of a product using a class II specified chemical substance in order to prevent damage to human health or to the inhabitation and/or growth of flora and fauna in the human living environment through environmental pollution attributable to the relevant Class II Chemical Substance, in light of the state of the manufacture, import, use, etc. of the relevant class II specified chemical substance or product using a class II specified chemical substance as well as the effects, etc. of the implementation of measures under the provisions of the following Article and Article 37 taken in relation to the relevant class II specified chemical substance, [MHLW], [METI] and [MOE] are to make an acknowledgement to that effect ...*
- *When the acknowledgment ... has been made, [METI] may order the person who has given a notification ... to change the planned quantity to be manufactured or the planned quantity to be imported ...*

Publication of Technical Guidelines for class II specified chemical substances (Art. 36 [A])

- *For each class II specified chemical substance, the competent ministers should publish technical guidelines on the measures to be taken by persons who operate the business of manufacturing the relevant class II specified chemical substance, persons who use the relevant class II specified chemical substance or products that are specified by Cabinet Order in which the relevant class II specified chemical substance is used ... as their businesses, and any other persons who handle the relevant class II specified chemical substance, etc. as their businesses ... in order to prevent environmental pollution attributable to the class II specified chemical substance they handle.*
- *If the competent ministers have published technical guidelines ..., if they find it necessary, they may make necessary recommendations to a business operator handling a class II specified chemical substance, etc. ... with regard to the measures that should be taken for preventing environmental pollution attributable to the relevant class II specified chemical substance, by taking the relevant technical guidelines into consideration.*

Recommendations (Art. 38 [A])

- *When the competent ministers find a sufficient reason to suspect that a chemical substance other than a class I specified chemical substance falls under [class I specified chemical substance], they may, to the extent necessary for preventing the spread of environmental pollution attributable to the relevant chemical substance, make any necessary recommendation concerning a restriction on the manufacture, import, use, etc. of the relevant chemical substance to a person operating the business of manufacturing or importing the relevant chemical substance or to a person using the relevant chemical substance as their business.*
- *If the competent ministers find a sufficient reason to suspect that a chemical substance other than a class II specified chemical substance falls under [class II specified chemical substance], they may, to the extent*

necessary for preventing the spread of environmental pollution attributable to the relevant chemical substance, make necessary recommendation concerning a restriction on the manufacture or import of the relevant chemical substance or an improvement in the method of use of the relevant chemical substance to a person operating the business of manufacturing or importing the relevant chemical substance or to a person using the relevant chemical substance as their business.

Guidance and advice (Art. 39 [A])

- *When the competent ministers find it particularly necessary for preventing environmental pollution attributable to a priority assessment chemical substance, a monitoring chemical substance, a class II specified chemical substance, a specified general chemical substance or specified new chemical substance they may provide a business operator handling the priority assessment chemical substance pertaining to the priority assessment chemical substance, a business operator handling a monitoring chemical substance, etc. pertaining to the monitoring chemical substance, a business operator handling class II specified chemical substance, etc. pertaining to the class II specified chemical substance, a business operator handling a specified general chemical substance pertaining to the specified general chemical substance or a business operator handling a specified new chemical substance pertaining to the specified new chemical substance with the necessary guidance and advice concerning the method of handling the each respective chemical substance.*

8. Data submission format

Writing, electronic or optical disk, depending on the requirements [C, D]

9. Data confidentiality

Notification of quantity of manufacture [E]

- *If a notifier (manufacturers and importers in Japan) has extreme difficulties in identifying a certain chemical substance or its concentration rate in mixture (e.g. because an exporter claims the chemical identity as confidential), the notifier is currently allowed to notify the annual volume of General Chemical Substances jointly with a chemical supplier etc. (hereinafter “chemical supplier(s)”, for example, the foreign exporter or manufacturer of the chemical substances under the consent of METI. (This notification method is not acceptable for Specified Chemical Substances, Monitoring Chemical Substances, and Priority Assessment Chemical Substances.) This procedure does not intend to exempt the notifier from its legal obligations as a notifier. Therefore, this procedure may not be used without the consent of the notifier.*

10. Data that are published publicly

- CSCL Inventory: The name of the new chemical evaluated through Normal procedure will be published in five years and listed on the inventory; the name of the new chemical evaluated through Low Volume exemption, small volume exemption and polymers of low concern will not be published. [L]
 - Online (downloadable) - Name, CAS No., Registration Number, MITI No, molecular formula, categories, testing results (e.g. biodegradability), national and international regulatory status
- Article 9 [A]: [METI] *shall in every fiscal year, make public the sum of the manufacture quantity and import quantity [of priority assessment chemical substance]; provided, however, that this does not apply when the sum of the manufactured quantity and import quantity of a priority assessment chemical substance is less than [100 tonnes; D].*
- Article 13 [A]: [METI] *should make public, each fiscal year, the sum of the manufactured quantity and import quantity in the preceding fiscal year ... for each monitoring chemical substance; provided, however, that this does not apply when the sum of the manufactured quantity and import quantity for one monitoring chemical substance is less than [1 tonne; D].*

11. International information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.11 Industrial Safety and Health Act (ISHA) inventory, Japan

Last update: 11 August 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Industrial Safety and Health Act: (Last version, Amendment of Act No. 25 of 2006)
<http://www.japaneselawtranslation.go.jp/law/detail/?printID=&id=1926&re=&vm=02>
- B. Ordinance on Industrial Safety and Health (Last version, Amendment of Ordinance of the Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare No. 185 of 2006:
<http://www.japaneselawtranslation.go.jp/law/detail/?ft=2&re=2&dn=1&yo=industrial+safety+and+health&x=51&y=17&ia=03&ja=04&ph=&ky=&page=3>
- C. Order for Enforcement of Industrial Safety and Health Act (Last version, Amendment of Cabinet Order No. 13 of 2012):
<http://www.japaneselawtranslation.go.jp/law/detail/?ft=2&re=2&dn=1&yo=industrial+safety+and+health&x=0&y=0&ia=03&ja=04&ph=&ky=&page=2>
- D. Lists “under Industrial Safety and Health Act (ISHA)”:
https://www.nite.go.jp/en/chem/chrip/chrip_search/sltLst
- E. MHLW’s relevant page:
https://www.mhlw.go.jp/stf/seisakunitsuite/bunya/koyou_roudou/roudoukijun/enzen/anzeneisei06/index.html; https://anzeninfo.mhlw.go.jp/enzen_pg/KAG_FND.aspx (in Japanese)

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

- Art. 1: *The purpose of this Act is to secure, in conjunction with the Labor Standards Act (Act No. 49 of 1947), the safety and health of workers in workplaces, as well as to facilitate the establishment of comfortable working environment, by promoting comprehensive and systematic countermeasures concerning the prevention of industrial accidents, such as taking measures for the establishment of standards for hazard prevention, clarifying the safety and health management responsibility and the promotion of voluntary activities with a view to preventing industrial accidents.* [A]
- Distinction between new vs. existing¹¹⁸ chemicals: *The [MHLW] shall, when notification has been made for a new chemical substance ..., make public the name of the said new chemical substance, as provided for by the Ordinance of the [MHLW].* [A]
- The new substance will be added to the ISHA list within one year after the receipt of the notification or after the confirmation [of Exemption 2] (or in the case that the application pursuant to the provision of paragraph (1) of Article 36 of the Patent Act (Act No. 121 of 1959) in regard to the said new chemical substances has been submitted, soon after the publication of application pursuant to the provision of paragraph (1) of Article 64 of the same Act or soon after the publication of patent application pursuant to the provision of paragraph (3) of Article 66 of the same Act has been made). The publication of names

¹¹⁸ Art. 9-2 *The Minister of Labour shall, as provided for by the Ordinance of the Ministry of Labour, publish names, etcl., of chemical substances manufactured or imported by period February 28, 1979 (excluding those manufactured or imported for test and research purpose by the same date) by May 31, 1979; and those manufactured or imported during a period starting on March 1, 1979, and ending on June 29, 1979, (excluding those are identical to chemical substances manufactured or imported by February 28, 1979, for purposes other than test and research and those manufactured or imported during the period starting on March 1, 1979, and ending on June 29, 1979, for test and research purposes) by August 31, 1979. However, this shall not apply to the chemical substances listed in the following items: (i) chemical elements, (ii) naturally produced chemical substances, (iii) radioactive substances.* [C]

On the basis of the public notice of February 5, 1979, chemicals that have been published pursuant to the provisions of the CSCL by June 29, 1979, and the chemicals listed in Japanese Pharmacopoeia eighth amendment (1971), are also treated as existing chemical substances for ISHA.

of new chemical substances shall be made periodically once every period within three months by publishing in official gazette. [B]

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligations¹¹⁹

Permission for Manufacturing

- Art. 56: (1) A person who intends to manufacture dichlorobenzidine, preparations containing dichlorobenzidine or other substances which are likely to inflict serious health impairment upon works and are provided for by Cabinet Order¹²⁰ shall obtain advance permission from the Minister of Health, Labour and Welfare [MHLW] [A]

Investigation of Toxicity of Chemical Substances

- Art. 57-3: To prevent impairment of workers' health caused by chemical substances¹²¹, an employer who intends to manufacture or import a chemical substance (hereinafter in this Article referred to as "new chemical substance") other than the chemical substances defined by Cabinet Order as the existing chemical substances (including chemical substances whose names were made public under the provisions of paragraph (3)), shall, in advance, undertake an investigation of toxicity provided for by the Ordinance of the [MHLW] (meaning investigation of the influence of the said new chemical substance on the health of workers and hereinafter the same applying in this Article) and shall, as provided for by the Ordinance of the [MHLW], notify the [MHLW] of the name of the said new chemical substance and the result of the investigation of toxicity and other matters. [A]

3.2 Exemptions

Investigation of Toxicity of Chemical Substances (Art. 57-3) [A]

- When, as provided for by the Ordinance of the [MHLW], in respect of the said new chemical substance, an affirmation by the [MHLW] has been obtained stating that the method etc., of manufacturing or treating of the new chemicals substance has been reviewed, it is not likely for the workers to be exposed to the said new chemical substance.
- When, as provided for by the Ordinance of the [MHLW], in respect of the said new chemical substance, an affirmation by the [MHLW] has been obtained, stating that the said new chemical substance does not have the [carcinogenicity] according to the knowledge, etc., already gained.
- When the said new chemical substance is to be manufactured or imported for the sake of research or examination.

¹¹⁹ Other obligations under the Act include Art. 55 (prohibition of manufacturing, etc.), Art. 57(1) (labeling), Art. 57(2) (delivery of documents/SDS, etc.) [A]

¹²⁰ (1) Dichlorobenzidine and its salts, (2) alpha-naphthylamine and its salts, (3) chlorinated biphenyl (alias PCB), (4) o-tolidine and its salts, (5) dianisidine and its salts, (6) beryllium and its compounds, (7) benzotrichloride, (8) preparations and other substances containing the substances listed in (1) to (6) exceeding 1% of the weight of the said preparations and other substances, or the substances listed in (7) exceeding 0.5% of the weight of the said preparations and other substances (for alloy, limited to those containing beryllium exceeding 3% of their weight). [C]

¹²¹ Elements, chemical substances produced naturally, radioactive substances, chemical substances that the [MHLW] has made public pursuant to the provisions of Article 9-2 of the Supplementary Provisions. [C]

- *When, as provided for by the Ordinance of the [MHLW], the said new chemical substance is imported primarily for ordinary use of general consumers (including a product containing the said new chemical substance).¹²²*
- *Art 18-4 (low-volume exemptions): The case as provided for by the Cabinet Order set forth in the proviso of paragraph (1) of Article 57-3 of the Act shall, in the case that as provided for by the Ordinance of the [MHLW], the employer who intends to manufacture or import the new chemical substances prescribed in the same paragraph (hereinafter referred to as “new chemical substances” in this Article) has obtained the confirmation by the [MHLW] that the amount of manufacturing or importing per one year at one workplace (for the employer to intend to manufacture and import the said new chemical substance, the sum of these amounts) are 100 kg or less, be at the time when the said employer intends to manufacture or import them in compliance with the said confirmation. [C]*

4. Initial data requirements

Investigation of Toxicity of Chemical Substances

Generally speaking, there are two types of notification: Standard notification (Ames test is required) and confirmation (<=100kg/year, no test required).

- *Art. 34-3(1): The investigation of toxicity ... shall be carried out prescribed as follows: (i) of a mutagenicity test, a test from which information equivalent to better than that obtainable from a mutagenicity test or the carcinogenicity tests, to carry out any one of these tests; (ii) to carry out at the testing laboratory,¹²³ etc., to be deemed as having the technical basis to properly conduct toxicity investigation with respect to the organization, facilities, etc. [B]*
- *Art. 34-4: A person who intends to submit the notification ... shall submit the notification using Form No. 4-3 accompanied by the document showing the result of the toxicity test ... for the new chemical substances ..., the document certifying that the said test has been carried out at the testing laboratory, etc., which satisfies the standard provided by the [MHLW] ... and the document indicating designed methods of manufacturing and handling of the new chemical substance to the [MHLW]. [B]*
- *Art. 34-5 (Exemption 1): A person who intends to receive the confirmation ... shall submit an application using Form No. 4-4 to the [MHLW] by 30 days prior to the day when the new chemical substance is to be first manufactured or imported based on the said confirmation, accompanied by the documents indicating the designed method of manufacture or handling of the new chemical substance. [B]*
- *Art. 34-8 (Exemption 2): A person who intends to receive the confirmation ... shall submit an application using Form No. 4-4 to the [MHLW] by 30 days prior to the day when the new chemical substance is to be first manufactured or imported based on the said confirmation, accompanied by the document showing any knowledge, information, etc., of the effect that the new chemical substance concerned is free from [carcinogenicity]. [B]*
- *Art. 34-10 (low-volume confirmation): A person who intends to receive the confirmation set forth in Article 18-4¹²⁴ of the Order shall submit an application document using Form No. 4-4 to the [MHLW]*

¹²² *Those in which workers will not be exposed to new chemical substances such as those in which workers are not obliged to do the work of subdividing or repacking the said chemical substances domestically. [B]*

¹²³ Standard to be satisfied by test facilities etc. conducting toxicity investigation (Industrial Safety and Health Law GLP): <https://www.mhlw.go.jp/content/000563263.pdf>; Enforcement of public notice that revises part of the standards to be provided at the test facilities: <https://www.mhlw.go.jp/content/000563267.pdf> If the test have been conducted in overseas in conformity with OECD-GLP and implemented in accordance with OECD test guidelines, the result is also acceptable.

¹²⁴ *Art. 34-11: The confirmation set forth in Article 18-4 of the Order shall be valid for two years. [B]*

by 30 days prior to the day when the new chemical substance is to be first manufactured or imported based on the said confirmation.

5. Updates by companies

- Art. 57-3: *The employer who has carried out the investigation of toxicity shall soon take necessary measures, based on the result of the said investigation for preventing impairment of workers' health caused by the said new chemical substance.* [A]
- Art. 34-6 (Exemption 1): *The employer who has received the confirmation ... shall report to the [MHLW] in writing without delay when there should arise any change in the matters stated in the application form or documents set forth in the same Article.* [B]

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

Investigation of Toxicity of Chemical Substances

- Article 57-4(1): *When it is deemed necessary for preventing impairment of workers' health caused by a chemical substance likely to bring about cancer or other serious health impairment to workers the [MHLW] may, as provided for by the Ordinance of the [MHLW], instruct the employer who is manufacturing, importing or using the said chemical substance or other employers prescribed by the Ordinance of the [MHLW] to carry out an investigation of toxicity provided for by Cabinet Order (meaning investigation of the influence of the said chemical substance on the impairment of workers' health) and to report the result.* [A]
 - Art. 18-5: *The investigation of the toxicity as provided for by the Cabinet Order set forth in paragraph (1) of Article 57-4 of the Act shall be the carcinogenicity investigation carried out by such methods as inhaled or oral administration by use of experimental animals.*
 - *The instruction ... shall be given in conformity with the standards provided for by the [MHLW], after taking every factor into consideration such as technical level of the investigation of toxicity of the chemical substance, the preparedness of the institution carrying out the investigation, the ability of investigation of the said employer, etc.* [A]
 - *The [MHLW] shall, when the instruction is made to the said employer ..., hear the opinion of the person with relevant knowledge and experience¹²⁵ in advance, as provided for by the Ordinance of the [MHLW].* [A]
 - Art. 34-20: *The provisions set forth in Article 34-15 and 34-16 shall apply mutatis mutandis to the case in which opinions by persons of learning and experience are to be obtained. In this case, the clause reading “results of a mutagenicity test, etc.” in these provisions shall instead be read as “the instruct regarding a carcinogenicity test”.* [B]
 - Art. 34-18: *Instructions ... shall be given in writing, indicating the names of chemical substances which are subject to the investigation of toxicity ..., reasons for carrying out the said investigations, method of the said investigation and other necessary matters.* [B]
- Article 57-5: *In order to contribute to the adequate implementation of the investigation of toxicity under the provisions of the preceding two Articles, the State shall endeavor to prepare facilities carrying out*

¹²⁵ Art. 34-15: *The [MHLW] shall, when hearing opinions of persons learning and experience ..., nominate review members corresponding to the content of the subject to be reviewed, from among the candidate list of review members for the result of a mutagenicity test, etc., ... and shall hear the opinions of such members.* [B]

Art. 34-16: *The [MHLW] shall entrust candidates of review member for the results of a mutagenicity test, etc., from those who have highly expert knowledge as regards the investigation of toxicity of chemical substances, and prepare and make public their name list.* [B]

the investigation of the toxicity of chemical substances, and to ensure the provision of information and other necessary assistance, and endeavor to carry out investigation of toxicity for itself. [A]

Epidemiological Survey, etc.

- Art. 108-2(1): *The [MHLW], when he/she finds it necessary in order to find the association of chemical substances, etc., to which employees are exposed or the work and the diseases of these said workers, make an epidemiological survey and other investigations. [A]*

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

Permission for Manufacturing

- Article 56(2): *The [MHLW] shall, where an application for the permission ... was presented, examine the said application and shall not grant the permission ... unless the equipment for manufacturing, the method of work, etc., are found to comply with the standards by the [MHLW]. [A]*

Investigation of Toxicity of Chemical Substances

- Art. 57-3(4): *In case where notification has been made ..., the [MHLW] may, hearing the opinion of the person with relevant knowledge and experience on the result of the investigation of toxicity as provided for by the Ordinance of the [MHLW], recommend to the employer who made the notification to take due measures including establishment or improvement of facilities or equipment, provision of personal protective equipment or other actions, where it is deemed necessary for preventing workers' health impairment caused by the chemical substance of the said notification. [A]*
 - Art. 34-15 and Art. 34-16: see above.
 - Art. 34-17: *The [MHLW] shall, when having heard the opinion of persons of learning and experience on the results of investigation of the toxicity of new chemical substances ... report the content of such opinions to the Labour Policy Council within a year after the names of the new chemical substances concerned are officially published ...*
- Art. 34-7 (Exemption 1): *The [MHLW] shall, when it has been deemed, based on the report [of changes] or other reference, that workers are in danger of exposure to relevant new chemical substances after the confirmation ... has been granted, revoke the said confirmation and notify the employer concerned to that effect without delay. [B]*
- Art. 34-12: *The [MHLW] shall, when having receiving an application set forth in Article 34-5 [Exemption 1], Article 34-8 [Exemption 2] and Article 34-10 [low-volume exemption], examine it and notify the applicant of the results of the said examination without delay. [B]*
- Art. 34-21: *The [MHLW] shall, when having received from an employer a report regarding the results of investigations carried out on the toxicity of chemical substances based on the instructions given ..., report the content such a report to the Labour Policy Council within a year from the day such a report was received.*

8. Data submission format

Online platform

9. Data confidentiality

Investigation of Toxicity of Chemical Substances

- Art. 57-3(5), 57-4(5): *The person with relevant knowledge and experience who were asked their opinions ... shall not divulge any confidential information known to them in connection with the said result/instruction. However, this shall not apply where they are compelled to disclose this information for the purpose of preventing the impairment of workers' health. [A]*

10. Data that are published publicly

Registration Number, ISHA number, date of notification in the official gazette, chemical substance name, additional details to Existing Chemical Substances of Industrial Safety and Health Act (if any, in Japanese)

11. Information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.12 Korea Existing Chemicals Inventory (KECI)

Last update: 11 November 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Act on Registration, Evaluation, etc. of Chemicals (K-REACH, version: Oct. 2018):
https://elaw.klri.re.kr/eng_service/lawView.do?hseq=48870&lang=ENG (latest update: 14 Oct. 2021;
<https://www.law.go.kr/LSW/lsInfoP.do?lsiSeq=231425&ancYd=20210413&ancNo=18034&efYd=20211014&nwJoYnInfo=N&efGubun=Y&chrClsCd=010202&ancYnChk=0#0000>, in Korean)
- B. Enforcement Decree of the Act on Registration, Evaluation, etc. of Chemicals (version: December 2018): https://elaw.klri.re.kr/eng_service/lawView.do?hseq=49167&lang=ENG (latest update: 15 Oct. 2021; <https://www.chemnavi.or.kr/chemnavi/spkreach/archivesdetail.do?idx=56411&category=1>, in Korean)
- C. Enforcement Rule of the Rule on Registration, Evaluation, etc. of Chemicals (version: December 2018): https://elaw.klri.re.kr/eng_service/lawView.do?hseq=49170&lang=ENG, including detailed requirements on forms and procedures (latest update: 15 Oct. 2021; <https://www.chemnavi.or.kr/chemnavi/spkreach/archivesdetail.do?idx=56412&category=1>)
- D. Chemical Substances Control Act (CCA, version: May 2020):
https://elaw.klri.re.kr/eng_service/lawView.do?hseq=55950&lang=ENG
- E. Enforcement Decree of the Chemical Substances Control Act (version: November 2018):
https://elaw.klri.re.kr/eng_service/lawView.do?hseq=49093&lang=ENG
- F. Enforcement Rule of the Chemicals Substances Control Act (version: November 2018):
https://elaw.klri.re.kr/eng_service/lawView.do?hseq=52240&lang=ENG, including detailed requirements on forms and procedures
- G. National Chemicals Information System (NCIS): <https://ncis.nier.go.kr/en/mttrList.do>
- H. Helpdesk: <https://www.chemnavi.or.kr/main.do> (in Korean)
- I. Exemption from registration of chemical substances, including relative regulations, process of application for the exemption and receiving notification, applicant of exemption, subject to confirmation of exemption, flow chart for polymer:
https://www.keco.or.kr/en/core/hazardous_Exemption/contentsid/3099/index.do
- J. *The Act on Registration, Evaluation, etc. of Chemicals was amended on January 1, 2019*:
<https://www.nite.go.jp/data/000099560.pdf>
- K. *Introduction to revised K-REACH and sub-ordinance* by JunYong Yang:
<http://www.rsc.org/events/download/Document/fbf97663-03bd-4f2d-975c-215a435f1f31>

Note: the following text is retrieved from unofficial translation of the corresponding text by the Korea Law Translation Center of the Korea Legislation Research Institute (https://elaw.klri.re.kr/eng_service/lawTotalSearchPart.do?pCode=01).

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory and underlying framework

- The purpose of this Act is to protect public health and the environment by providing for matters regarding the registration and reporting of chemical substances, the review and assessment of hazards and risks of chemical substances, and the designation of hazardous chemical substances, and by producing and utilizing information on chemical substances. [A]
- The purpose of this Act is to prevent risks posed by chemical substances to people's health and the environment and protect the lives and property of the people or the environment from chemical substances by properly controlling chemical substances and promptly responding to accidents that occur due to chemical substances. [D]

- KECI contains more than 44,000 chemicals that were domestically circulated in South Korea prior to Feb 2, 1991 or those published by the Ministry of Environment after hazard evaluation under the previous TCCA after Feb 2, 1991. Those not listed in the KECI are regarded as new chemical substances subject to new chemical registration.

3. Scope of the inventory and underlying framework

3.1 Obligations

Registration of chemical substance + Reporting [A]

- Article 10: Any person who intends to manufacture or import at least 100 kilograms of a non-phase-in substance per year or at least 1 tonne of a phase-in substance¹²⁶ per year ... shall register the chemical substance with the Minister of Environment before it is manufactured or imported.
 - Article 10(2): ... any person who intends to manufacture or import a phase-in substance may manufacture or import such substance without registration thereof during a registration grace period ...
 - Where he or she intends to manufacture or import at least 1 tonne of a phase-in substance per year designated and publicly notified by the Minister of Environment following deliberation by the Evaluation Committee, which causes or is likely to cause cancer, mutation or reproductive disorders to humans or animals, or at least 1000 tonnes of a phase-in substance per year: By December 31, 2021
 - Where he or she intends to manufacture or import at least 100 tonnes and less than 1000 tonnes of a phase-in substance per year: By December 31, 2024
 - Where he or she intends to manufacture or import at least 10 tonnes and less than 100 tonnes of a phase-in substance per year: By December 31, 2027 [B]
 - Where he or she intends to manufacture or import at least 1 tonne and less than 10 tonnes of a phase-in substance per year: By December 31, 2030 [B]
 - Article 10(4): Any of the following persons shall report the Minister of Environment before he or she manufactures or imports the following relevant non-phase-in substances
 - A person who intends to manufacture or import less than 100 kilograms of a non-phase-in substance per year
 - A person who has obtained confirmation of exemption from hazard reviews of any of the following non-phase-in substances pursuant to Article 10(1)3 of the previous Toxic Chemical Substances Control Act ... and who, accordingly, intends to import the relevant non-phase-in substance
 - A non-phase-in substance manufactured or imported in quantities of not more than 100 kilograms per year
 - A non-phase-in substance designated and publicly notified by the Minister of Environment, which is a polymer¹²⁷ only composed of chemical substances other than non-phase-in substances

¹²⁶ Chemical substances publicly notified by the Minister of Environment in consultation with the Minister of Employment and Labor, which were domestically distributed for commercial purposes before February 2, 1991, and chemical substances publicly notified by the Minister of Environment and where the hazard reviews thereof have been conducted pursuant to the previous Toxic Chemical Substances control Act after February 2, 1991 [A]

¹²⁷ A chemical substance satisfying all the following requirements. In such cases, where a polymer consisting of monomers excluding monomers whose weight ratio does not exceed two percent falls under phase-in substances, such polymer shall be deemed a phase-in substances.

- It shall be composed of molecules in which at least one kind of monomer unit is continuously repeated

- Article 10(5): Any person who intends to manufacture or import a chemical substance which is designated and publicly notified by the Minister of Environment ... because the chemical substance is deemed highly likely to inflict serious damage on human health and the environment though not subject to registration under paragraph (1) or because the total quantity of such chemical substance domestically manufactured or imported per year exceeds [1 tonne for the total quantity of a non-phase-in substance domestically manufactured or imported in quantities of less than 100 kilograms per manufacturer or importer per year; 10 tonnes for the total quantity of a phase-in substance domestically manufactured or imported in quantities of less than 1 tonne per manufacturer or importer per year; B], shall register the relevant chemical substance with the Minister of Environment within a [3-year period from the date when the relevant chemical substance is designated and publicly notified, taking account of factors, including the hazards, risks and volume of domestic distribution of such chemical substance; B]

Notification of Substance Subject to Intensive Control Contained in Product [A]

- Article 32: Where a product containing a substance subject to intensive control fully meets the following requirements, a person who manufactures or imports such product shall notify the name, content, hazard information, exposure information and uses of the substance subject to intensive control contained in the relevant product to the Minister of Environment before the manufacture or import thereof:
 - The content of each individual substance subject to intensive control contained in one unit of the product shall exceed 0.1 weight percent
 - The total quantity of each individual substance subject to intensive control contained in the whole products shall exceed one tonne per year

Verification of Chemical substances [D]

- Article 9(1): Any person who intends to manufacture or import a chemical shall verify whether the relevant chemical or any ingredient thereof falls under any of the following, ..., and submit the details thereof to the Minister of Environment:
 - Existing chemicals under subparagraph 3 of Article 2 of the Act on Registration, Evaluation, etc. of Chemicals
 - New chemicals under subparagraph 4 of Article 2 of the Act on Registration, Evaluation, etc. of Chemicals
 - Toxic substances
 - Substances requiring permission
 - Restricted substances
 - Prohibited substances
 - Substances requiring preparation for accidents.
- Article 9(3): Where any person who intends to manufacture or import chemical substances ... deems it necessary to verify the chemical substances, he or she may request the Minister of Environment to certify whether the relevant chemical substances or any ingredient thereof falls under any of [above].

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- It shall represent the characteristic distribution of molecular weights in accordance with repetitive numbers of monomer units in each molecule
 - Its molecules that at least three monomer units form a covalent bond with at least one monomer unit or other reactants shall be at least 50 percent
 - Its molecules of the same molecular weight shall be not more than 50 percent of the weight ratio [B]

Permission to manufacture, import, or use substances subject to permission¹²⁸ [D]

- Article 19(1): Any person who intends to manufacture, import, or use substances subject to permission shall obtain a permission from the Minister of Environment in advance by submitting the following information: Provided, That the foregoing shall not apply within a permission grace period under Article 25 of the Act on Registration, Evaluation, etc. of Chemical Substances

Permit to import restricted substances and declaration for import of toxic substances [D]

- Article 20(1): Any person who intends to import restricted substances shall obtain a permission from the Minister of Environment, only when relevant restricted substances have a clear use and are under proper control ...

Approval for export of restricted substances or prohibited substances [D]

- Article 21(1): Any person who intends to export restricted substances (limited to uses for which handling is restricted) or prohibited substances shall prepare documents concerning information required to be included in a notification of export [, as provided for in Annex V to the Rotterdam Convention] and obtain approval from the Minister of Environment every year, ... The foregoing shall also apply to a change in any important matters prescribed [the kind or content of the substance, the export of which is approved; an estimated quantity of export approved (only where at least 50/100 of the quantity increases); the name and representative of the workplace, or the location of the office; F]

3.2 Exemptions

- Article 3 [A]: [K-REACH] shall not apply to any of the following chemical substances
 - Radioactive materials defined in subparagraph 5 of Article 2 of the Nuclear Safety Act
 - Drugs defined in subparagraph 4 of Article 2 of the Pharmaceutical Affairs Act and quasi-drugs defined in subparagraph 7 of the said Article
 - Narcotics defined in subparagraph 1 of Article 2 of the Narcotics Control Act
 - Cosmetics defined in subparagraph 1 of Article 2 of the Cosmetics Act and raw materials used for cosmetics
 - Pesticides defined in subparagraph 1 of Article 2 of the Pesticide Control Act and active ingredients defined in subparagraph 3 of the said Article
 - Fertilizers defined in subparagraph 1 of Article 2 of the Fertilizer Control Act
 - Foods defined in subparagraph 1 of Article 2 of the Food Sanitation Act, food additives defined in subparagraph 2 of the said Article, apparatus defined in subparagraph 4 of the said Article, containers and packages defined in subparagraph 5 of the said Article
 - Feed defined in subparagraph 1 of Article 2 of the Control of Livestock and Fish Feed Act
 - Explosives defined in Article 2 (3) of the Act on Control of Guns, Swords, and Explosives
 - Munitions defined in Article 2 of the Act on the Management of Military Supplies and subparagraph 2 of Article 3 of the Defense Acquisition Program Act (excluding ordinary commodities prescribed in Article 3 of the Act on the Management of Military Supplies)
 - Health functional foods defined in subparagraph 1 of Article 3 of the Health Functional Foods Act
 - Medical devices defined in Article 2 (1) of the Medical Devices Act
 - Hygiene products defined in subparagraph 1 of Article 2 of the Hygiene Products Control Act

¹²⁸ Chemical substances that are likely to pose a risk, as publicly notified by the Minister of Environment ... so that such chemical substances may be manufactured, imported, or used with permission from the Minister of Environment [D]

- Biocidal substances and biocidal products defined in subparagraphs 7 and 8 of Article 3 of the Act on Safety Control of Consumer Chemical Products and Biocides
- Article 3 [D]: [CCA] shall not apply to any of the following chemical substances
 - Radioactive materials ...
 - Medicines and non-pharmaceutical items ...
 - Narcotics ...
 - Cosmetics ...
 - Pesticides and technical ingredients ...
 - Fertilizers ...
 - Foods, food additives, appliances, containers, and packages ...
 - Feed ...
 - Explosives ...
 - Munitions (excluding ordinary commodities) ...
 - Health functional foods ...
 - Medical devices ...
 - Toxic gases under the High-Pressure Gas Safety Control Act

Exemption from registration of chemical substance

- Article 11: Any of the following persons may manufacture or import a chemical substance without registration ... or reporting ...:
 - A person who intends to manufacture or import any of the following chemical substances:
 - A chemical substance contained in a machine imported
 - A chemical substance imported along with a machine or device used for a test run
 - A chemical substance contained in a product performing a certain function in a specific solid form, which does not leak in the process of using the product
 - A person who intends to manufacture or import a chemical substance of very low risk designated and publicly notified by the Minister of Environment following deliberation by the Evaluation Committee;
 - A person who intends to manufacture or import [the following substances], in which case he or she has obtained confirmation of exemption from registration or notification ... from the Minister of Environment.
 - Any person who intends to obtain confirmation of exemption from registration, etc. shall file an application for confirmation of exemption from registration, etc. with the Minister of Environment. In such cases, the Minister of Environment shall confirm whether a chemical substance is eligible for exemption from registration or reporting ... and notify the applicant of the eligibility determination ...
 - A chemical substance manufactured or imported to export the whole amount thereof [B] – confirmation of exemption from registration, etc. on an annual basis [C]
 - A chemical substance manufactured or imported for manufacturing other chemical substances to export the whole amount of such other chemical substances [B] – confirmation of exemption from registration, etc. on an annual basis [C]
 - A chemical substance for scientific experiments, analysis or research, such as reagents [B] – confirmation of exemption from registration, etc. only once for the first confirmation [C]
 - A chemical substance for any of the following research and development purposes: [B] – confirmation of exemption from registration, etc. for each plan for research and development of chemical substances [C]
 - Developing chemical substances, products, etc.

- Improving or developing manufacturing processes
 - Testing application fields of chemical substances at the place of business
 - Pilot manufacturing of chemical substances or pilot production of products, etc.
- Any of the following polymers: [B] – confirmation of exemption from registration, etc. only once for the first confirmation [C]
 - A polymer whose number average molecular weight is at least 10,000, in which the content of molecules whose weight is less than 1,000 is less than 5 percent and the content of molecules whose weight is less than 500 is less than 2 percent;
 - A polymer whose number average molecular weight is at least 1,000 but less than 10,000, in which the content of molecules whose weight is less than 1,000 is less than 25 percent and the content of molecules whose weight is less than 500 is less than 10 percent;
 - Any of the following polymers is NOT included in those subject to confirmation of exemption from registration or reporting
 - A cationic polymer (excluding a polymer that is used only in solid state and not soluble or dissolved in water);
 - A polymer whose number average molecular weight is less than 10,000, in which an unreacted monomer, which is any of the following chemical substances, constitutes more than 0.1 percent by weight:
 - A hazardous chemical substance;
 - A substance subject to intensive control;
 - A non-phase-in substance (excluding any non-phase-in substance that is to be manufactured or imported in quantities of 1 ton or more per year and has undergone a hazard review under Article 18 of the Act).
- A chemical substance formed by reacting functional groups on the surface of a substance subject to surface treatment with another substance that treats the surface of the substance where both the substance subject to surface treatment and another substance that treats the surface of the substance fall under any of the following: [B] – confirmation of exemption from registration, etc. only once for the first confirmation [C]
 - A chemical substance registered pursuant to Article 10 (1) or (5) of the Act;
 - A chemical substance reported pursuant to Article 10 (3) of the Act, which is a phase-in substance and where the registration grace period of which has not expired under Article 10 (2) of the Act;
 - A chemical substance reported pursuant to Article 10 (4) of the Act;
 - A chemical substance not subject to registration pursuant to Article 10 (1) or (5) of the Act or not subject to reporting pursuant to Article 10 (4) of the Act;
 - A non-isolated intermediate [B] – confirmation of exemption from registration, etc. only once for the first confirmation [C]
 - An on-site isolated intermediate (which means a chemical substance that does not meet the criteria of a non-isolated intermediate and is created in the manufacturing process of another chemical substance and is used and completely consumed in the subsequent process on the same manufacturing site under controlled conditions complying with the procedure and manner prescribed by Ordinance of the Ministry of Environment;

hereinafter the same shall apply), the leakage or exposure of which is blocked by technical means. [B] – confirmation of exemption from registration, etc. only once for the first confirmation [C]

Exemption of reporting of substance subject to intensive control contained in product

- Article 32(2): Where a chemical substance falls under any of the following, a person may manufacture or import a product containing a substance subject to intensive control without making a report ...
 - A chemical substance to which humans or the environment is not exposed where a product is used in a usual way
 - A chemical substance already registered ... or reported ... for the use of the relevant product
 - A chemical substance that can be manufactured or imported without registration or notification pursuant to Article 11 (1)
 - Where the details of a report ... conform to this Act, the Minister shall accept such report.

Exemption of verification of Chemicals [D]

- Article 9(2): ... chemical substances that meet the standards prescribed and publicly notified by the Minister of Environment, such as cases where chemical substances contained in a product that performs a certain function in a solid state are not released during use of the product

Permission to manufacture, import, or use substances subject to permission [D]

- Article 19(2): ... shall not apply to any of the following chemical substances
 - Imported chemical substances contained in machinery
 - Chemical substances imported with machinery or equipment for a test run
 - Chemical substances contained in a product that performs certain functions in a specific solid form, which are not released during use of the product
 - Chemical substances manufactured or imported for survey or research purposes, or any other chemical substances prescribed [not more than 100 kilograms are manufactured, imported or used annually; E]

Permit to import restricted substances and declaration for import of toxic substances [D, E]

- Article 20(3): ... shall not apply to cases the following cases
 - Where he or she imports reagents for experimental, research, or testing purposes (including standard gas to be used for correction or measurement of measuring instruments; hereinafter the same shall apply) to use them for such purposes
 - Where he or she imports toxic substances not exceeding 100 kilograms per year.

Reporting on reagent sales business [D]

- Article 29-3(1): Notwithstanding Article 29, a person who intends to conduct a business of selling reagents for use in experiments, research, or testing that fall under toxic chemical substances for their intended purpose shall file a report thereon with the Minister of Environment

4. Initial data requirements

Registration of Chemical Substance [A]

- Article 14 (1) Any person who intends to register ... shall submit data on the following matters ... Provided, that in the case of a phase-in substance or non-phase-in substance prescribed by Presidential Decree,¹²⁹ he or she need not submit some of the relevant data ...:
 - The name, location, and representative of a person who intends to manufacture or import the chemical substance
 - Information on the identification of the chemical substance, such as the name, molecular formula, and structural formula of such chemical substance
 - Uses of the chemical substance
 - Classification and labelling of the chemical substance
 - Physical and chemical properties of the chemical substance¹³⁰

¹²⁹ With the exception of its subparagraphs, means any of the following substances: [B]

- A non-phase-in substance manufactured or imported, satisfying the standards provided in Table 3
- A chemical substance to be manufactured or imported by any of the following persons, which has been designated and publicly notified ... because the total quantity domestically manufactured or imported per year exceeds the level provided in Article 10(3)(1)
 - A person who intends to manufacture or import less than 10 kilograms of a non-phase-in substance per year
 - A person who intends to manufacture or import less than 100 kilograms of a phase-in substance per year
- A phase-in substance whose human health or environmental hazards, as contained in data submitted for the registration, etc. thereof, satisfy the level prescribed [in the Enforcement Rules; C] (excluding any phase-in substance to be manufactured or imported for use by consumers)
- An on-site isolated intermediate: provided, that any on-site isolated intermediate, the leakage or exposure of which is blocked by technical means, is excluded
- A transported isolated intermediate
- A chemical substance whose human health or environmental hazards may be determined based on the results obtained from internationally recognized qualitative or quantitative structure activity relationship models (QSAR models), the quantity of which to be manufactured or imported is less than 10 tonnes per year
- A chemical substance whose human health or environmental hazards may be determined based on the results obtained by internationally recognized in vitro testing methods
- A chemical substance whose human health or environmental hazards may be determined based on the results obtained from a chemical substance with similar structure or similar physical and chemical properties, such as metallic compounds containing same metals
- A chemical substance whose human health or environmental hazards may be determined based on the reliable results equivalent to those obtained by internationally recognized testing methods
- A chemical substances whose human health or environment hazards may be determined based on the results of the hazard assessment published by a foreign government or an international organization
- A chemical substance the test of which is technically impossible
- A chemical substance that may be determined based on data to apply for registration ... that such chemical substance will not be exposed to humans or the environment

Data that do not need to be submitted for the individual cases above are described in the Enforcement Rule [C].

¹³⁰ Article 14(2): [Among the physical and chemical properties and hazards], the data prescribed shall be submitted in documents stating the results of a test conducted by any of the following testing institutions:

- A Korean testing institution prescribed in Article 22(1)
- A confirmed foreign testing institution ... to comply with the Principles of Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) [A]

Article 16-2: Vertebrate animal testing for registration of chemical substances, hazard reviews and risk assessments thereof shall be minimized with alternatives to vertebrate animal testing or other means. Except for

- Hazards of the chemical substance
- Risks of the chemical substance, including an exposure scenario describing handling, exposure controls, and management measures during the life-cycle of the chemical substance (applicable only where the quantity of the chemical substance that the applicant intends to manufacture or import is at least ten tonnes per year)
- Guidance on safe use (personal protections, first-aid measures, etc. in case of explosion, fire or leakage)

the cases prescribed ..., such as where new findings suggest that the relevant chemical substance poses a risk on humans, animals, or the environment, no duplicate test shall be conducted on the same chemical substance. [A]

- Where existing data obtained by an alternative to vertebrate animal testing is insufficient to assess the hazards or risks of the relevant chemical substance because such chemical substance's hazards or risks to humans, animals or the environment have been newly identified or a new hazard or risk is likely to be identified by the internationally recognized test results or by other means [B]
- Where existing data recording the results of testing on vertebrate animals ... is not sufficiently reliable to assess the risks to humans, animals or the environment [B]
- Where it is impracticable to determine the hazards or risks of the relevant chemical substance based on existing data obtained by an alternative to vertebrate animal testing [B]
- Where generating and retaining new vertebrate animal test data is deemed appropriate for managing information on the hazards or risks of the relevant chemical substance, taking into account the cost and terms and conditions of purchasing existing vertebrate animal test data available locally or internationally [B]
- Where the Minister of Environment orders vertebrate animal test data to be submitted as he or she deems it necessary for a hazard review ... or a risk assessment [B]

Article 17(1): Any person who intends to register ... shall check if vertebrate animal test data already exist, to minimize vertebrate animal testing. [A]

- Where the check ... finds that vertebrate animal test data already exist, any person who intends to apply for registration shall use the relevant vertebrate animal test data for the purpose of his or her own application for registration with the consent to use of the relevant animal test data from the owner thereof: provided, that where at least 15 years have passed since vertebrate animal test data were registered as data to apply for registration, he or she may use such data without consent to use from the owner thereof
- where the owner of vertebrate animal test data does not consent to their use, a person who intends to apply for registration need not submit the relevant data to apply for registration with confirmation from the Minister of Environment: Provided, That where deemed necessary to submit vertebrate animal test data, such as where it is difficult to determine hazards, etc. of chemical substances without the relevant vertebrate animal test data, the Minister of Environment may order him or her to produce and submit the relevant data within a period prescribed by Ordinance of the Ministry of Environment
- Any person requested to consent to use of vertebrate animal test data ... shall comply with such request, unless there are good reasons prescribed
 - Where the price a person who has requested consent to use vertebrate animal test data intends to pay to the owner of the relevant data is not equivalent to the amount to be paid for the use of vertebrate animal test data [B]

Article 22: The Minister of Environment shall designate a testing institution that may perform testing on physical and chemical properties and hazards of chemical substances from among the research institutions prescribed ... In such cases, the Minister of Environment shall also designate a test field or test item in which the relevant test institution may perform tests.

- The research institutions include: national or public testing and research institutes or inspection agencies, schools, specific research institutes established, business-affiliated research institutes, government-funded research institutes, testing and research institutes designated or recognized by other statues [B]
- The Minister of Environment shall regularly evaluate whether a testing institution designated ... is properly operated as prescribed.

Detailed data requirements are described in the Enforcement Rules [C].

- Data concerning information on exposure from the uses of the relevant chemical substance prepared according to the methods for preparation under [Table 8 attached in the Enforcement Rules]: provided, that any person who has submitted data regarding risks of the chemical substance ... need not submit the data referred to in the main sentence [C].
- Article 14(3): Any person who intends to register ... may submit a plan that includes the details of and schedule for testing and other relevant matters ... in lieu of some of the data to apply for registration on the matters referred to [physical and chemical properties, and hazards of the chemical substance] ... In such cases, the Minister of Environment shall review the appropriateness, etc. of the details of and schedule for testing in such testing plan ... and shall inform a manufacturer or importer of the specific details of such testing, the deadline for such data submission, and other relevant matters.
 - A testing plan ... shall be formulated containing the following matters
 - The name of the test data [C]
 - Reasons for submitting the testing plan [C]
 - Detailed methods for the test [C]
 - Expected schedules for the test [C]
 - The data when the test data can be submitted [C]
- Article 16(1): Any person who intends to register ... may use the data to apply for registration prescribed ... among the existing such data submitted by another registrant ... for the purpose of applying for his or her own registration after obtaining consent to use from the owner thereof: provided, that in the case of data to apply for registration where 15 years have passed since the data was registered, he or she may use such data without obtaining consent to use from the owner thereof
- Article 16(2): Any person who intends to register ... may inquire of the Minister of Environment whether the same chemical substances has been registered and other relevant matters to use the existing data to apply for registration ... In such cases, the Minister of Environment shall inform him or her of the results thereof ...
- Article 30: Where any person who manufactures or imports a chemical substance or mixture requests any downstream user or seller of the chemical substance or mixture to provide information to file a registration or report ..., the downstream user or seller shall provide the manufacturer or importer with information on uses of the chemical substance he or she uses or sells, exposure information, the quantities used and sold, information on safe use, and other similar matters.

Reporting phase-in substances during registration grace period [A]

- Article 10(3): Any person who intends to manufacture or import a phase-in substance without registration thereof during the registration grace period ... shall report the following to the Minister of Environment before he or she manufactures or imports the phase-in substance ...
 - Name of the chemical substance
 - Annual quantity of manufacture or import
 - Classification and labelling of the chemical substance
 - Uses of the chemical substance
 - Other matters prescribed [in the Enforcement Rules; C] such as the trade name of the person who intends to manufacture or import the chemical substance [, and specific forms to be used].

Reporting non-phase-in substances (low-volume chemicals and polymers composed of phase-in substances)

- Article 14(6): Any person who intends to make a report ... shall submit the following data ...
 - The name, location, and representative of a person who intends to manufacture or import the chemical substance
 - Information on the identification of the chemical substance, such as the name, molecular formula, and structural formula of such chemical substance

- Uses of the chemical substance
- Classification and labelling of the chemical substance
- Hazards of the chemical substance [C]
- Risks of the chemical substance, including an exposure scenario describing handling, exposure controls, and management measures during the life-cycle of the chemical substance (applicable only where the quantity of the chemical substance that the applicant intends to manufacture or import is at least ten tons per year) [C]
- Guidance on safe use (personal protections, first-aid measures, etc. in case of explosion, fire or leakage) [C]
- Data concerning information on exposure from the uses of the relevant chemical substance prepared according to the methods for preparation under [Table 8 attached in the Enforcement Rules]: provided, that any person who has submitted data regarding risks of the chemical substance ... need not submit the data referred to in the main sentence [C].

Permission to manufacture, import, or use substances subject to permission [D]

- Name, location, and representative of a person who intends to manufacture, import or use the substances subject to permission;
- Information to identify the chemical substances, such as the name, molecular and structural formulas of the chemical substances;
- Purposes of the chemical substances;
- Risk of the chemical substances;
- Analysis of an alternative to the substances subject to permission and the feasibility thereof;
- Plan for replacement of the substances subject to permission.

Permit to import restricted substances and declaration for import of toxic substances [D]

- Article 20(2): Any person who intends to import toxic chemical substances shall report the types and purposes of the toxic chemical substances to the Minister of Environment ...

Verification of chemical substances

- The verification of chemical substances ... shall be conducted on the basis of any of the following documents [F]
 - A document stating the names, content, Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS) numbers, etc. of chemical substances (hereinafter referred to as “specification of ingredients”) which constitute a product intended to be manufactured or imported.
 - A document related to the verification of a chemical substance provided by a manufacturer, exporter or person delegated with the verification
 - A certificate of the verification (any person to whom a certificate has been issued ... shall be exempted from the submission of a detailed statement of verification ...)
- Any person who verifies a chemical substance ... shall submit a detailed statement of verification in attached Form 1 to the association related to the control of chemical substances established pursuant to 53(1) of the Act, together with the data used to verify the chemical substance among the documents specified [above]. In such cases, a detailed statement of verification regarding a chemical substance not directly related to market release, such as a reagent for experiments, research or testing or a chemical substance for trial production, may be submitted within 30 days after it is manufactured or imported.
- Any person who intends to apply for certification of the verification of a chemical substance ... shall submit an application for certification in attached Form to the Association together with a specification of ingredients.

- The head of the Association who has received an application for certification ... shall identify whether the relevant chemical substance or any ingredient thereof constitutes any chemical substance referred to ... and shall then deliver a certificate of identification ...

5. Information updates by companies

Reporting phase-in substances during registration grace period [A]

- Article 10(3): ... where the matters prescribed ... are changed among the matters reported, he or she shall report such change to the Minister of Environment ...
 - Where any of the following tonnage bands for annual quantities manufactured or imported is changed to another one: [B]
 - At least 1 tonne but less than 10 tonnes
 - At least 10 tonnes but less than 100 tonnes
 - At least 100 tonnes but less than 1,000 tonnes
 - At least 1,000 tonnes;
 - Where any change is made in the classification or labeling of the chemical substance [B]
 - Where any change is made in the use of the chemical substance according to the chemical substances classifications by uses provided ... (only applicable to a change resulting from a newly-identified consumer use) [B]
 - Where any change is made in the trade name, location or contact details of the reporter under Article 10 (3) of the Act [B]
 - Where any change is made in the composition of chemical substance importers (only applicable where such change is reported by a person appointed by an overseas manufacturer or producer under Article 38 of the Act) [B]
 - Where any change is made in the composition of persons who manufacture the chemical substance under entrustment (only applicable where such change is reported by a person who manufactures the chemical substance under entrustment) [B]

Confirmation of exemption from registration [A]

- Article 11: Any person who is informed of confirmation of exemption from registration, etc. from the Minister of Environment ... shall file an application for changes with the Minister of Environment, where any change is made to the [following] matters.
 - Where any change is made regarding a chemical substance for any research and development purpose ..., such as the period required for research and development, the estimated quantities of manufacture or import, or a research institute, among the matters exempted from registration, etc. [C]
 - Where a chemical substance ... which is a substance subject to surface treatment of another substance that treats the surface of the above-mentioned substance, is changed from a chemical substance under any item of Article 11(1)(6) of the Decree to one falling under a different item of the same subparagraph [C]
 - Where the composition of the importers of the relevant chemical substance is changed (limited to cases where an application for confirmation of exemption from registration, etc. is filed by a person appointed by an overseas manufacturer or producer ...) [C]
 - Where the composition of the manufacturers to whom the manufacture of the relevant chemical substance is outsourced is changed (limited to cases where an application for confirmation of exemption from registration, etc. is filed by the person who outsources the manufacture of the chemical substance. [C]

Registration and Reporting of Change [A]

- Article 12: Where any of the following changes occurs, a person who has registered ... shall register such change ...:
 - Where any change is made to an annual quantity of a registered chemical substance manufactured or imported beyond the range prescribed ...
 - Where any change is made to the matters prescribed ... concerning uses, hazards, and risks of registered chemical substances
- Where any of the following changes occurs, a person who has registered pursuant to ... shall report such change ...:
 - The trade name, name or location of a person who has registered
 - The representative (only applicable where a person who has registered is a corporation)
 - Other matters prescribed ... concerning reporting.
- Where any of the following changes occurs, a person who has made a report ... shall report such change to the Minister of Environment ...:
 - The trade name, name or location of a person who has made a report
 - The representative (only applicable where a person who has made a report is a corporation)
 - Matters prescribed ... concerning uses, hazards and risks of notified chemical substances

Recording and Retaining Document [A]

- Article 44: Any of the following persons shall record and retain documents on matters related to manufacture, import, sale, and use of relevant chemical substances ...
 - Any person who applies for a registration or makes a report of a chemical substance ... (including a person who registers any change, makes a report or reports any change ...)
 - Any Person who applies for confirmation or change of exemption from registration, etc. of a chemical substance ...
 - Any person who reports a substance subject to intensive control contained in a product ...
- Any person required to record and retain documents ... shall record and retain the following documents related to the manufacturing, import, sale and use of the relevant chemical substances for five years. [C]
 - Data related to registration and registration of changes and a report and a report on changes of a chemical substance ...
 - Management register of transported isolated intermediates ... related to the registration of transported isolated intermediates ...
 - Data related to confirmation of exemption from registration, etc. of a chemical substance ...
 - Data related to the report on substances subject to intensive control contained in products ...
 - Data concerning information provided under Articles 29, 30 and 35 of the Act
 - Data subject to data protection
 - Shall be recorded and retained for five years from the date the period for data protection ... expires
- Article 50 [D]: Any of the following persons shall record and preserve matters related to the handling of the relevant chemical substances for five years ...
 - A person who has verified chemical substances pursuant to Article 9(1)
 - A person who has obtained a permission to manufacture, import, or sell prohibited substances ...
 - A person who has obtained a permission to manufacture, import, or use substances subject to permission
 - A person who has obtained a permission to import restricted substances ... or a person who has made make an import declaration in respect of toxic substances ...
 - A person who has obtained approval to export restricted substances or prohibited substances ...
 - A person who has obtained a permission to conduct hazardous chemical substance business ...

- A person who sells reagents for use in experiments, research, or testing that fall under toxic chemical substances ...
- A person who handles substances requiring preparation for accidents ...
- Any person required to record and retain relevant documents ... shall record and retain the following documents for five years [F]
 - Specifications of ingredients and certificates of the verification of chemical substances, and documents related to the verification of chemical substances provided by manufacturers, exporters or import agencies
 - Import-related documents such as a certificate of a report on import (limited to imports)

Permission to manufacture, import, or use substances subject to permission [D]

- Article 19(6): Any person allowed to manufacture, import or use substances subject to permission for a limited period ... shall renew his or her permit within such period

Permit to import restricted substances and declaration for import of toxic substances [D]

- Article 20(4): Where a person makes any changes in matters for which he or she has obtained a permission ... or which he or she has reported ..., he or she shall obtain a permission for modification or report any changes made

Reporting on reagent sales business [D]

- Article 29-3: Where a person who has filed a report pursuant to paragraph (1) intends to modify any important matter prescribed ..., he or she shall file a report on the relevant modification.

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

Registration of chemical substances

- Article 14(4): The Minister of Environment may acquire the data to apply for registration concerning [physical and chemical properties, and hazards of the chemical substance] for some phase-in substances and may provide such data to a person who intends to register ... In such cases, the Minister of Environment may receive the expenses incurred in acquiring the data to apply for registration from a person who intends to register ... [A]
- Article 14(5): Where the Minister of Environment intends to acquire the data to apply for registration ..., he or she shall first acquire test data in which the results of test conducted by testing institutions prescribed [i.e. a Korean testing institution prescribed in Article 22(1), or a confirmed foreign testing institution ... to comply with the Principles of GLP of OECD] using vertebrate animals are recorded to minimize animal testing or data prepared in accordance with alternatives to animal testing.

Hazard Review [A]

- Article 18(2): Where necessary for hazard review, the Minister of Environment may order a registrant to submit data necessary for hazard review.
 - Data concerning the physical and chemical properties of the relevant chemical substance [C]
 - Data concerning the hazards of the relevant chemical substance [C]

Risk assessment [A]

- Article 24(2): Where necessary to conduct a risk assessment, the Minister of Environment may order a registrant to submit data necessary for the risk assessment ... [C]
 - Data concerning the uses of the relevant chemical substance ...
 - Data concerning the risks of the relevant chemical substance ...
 - Data concerning the instructions for safe use ...

- Data concerning information on exposure from the uses of the relevant chemical substance
- Data concerning downstream users of the relevant chemical substance

Reporting and Inspection [A]

- Article 43: The Minister of Environment may ... require the following persons to submit necessary reports or data, or related public officials to access their facilities or places of business to collect chemical substances or inspect related documents, facilities and equipment.
 - A person who manufactures, imports or sells a chemical substance
 - A person who makes a report pursuant to Article 10(3)
 - A person who produces or imports a product containing substances subject to intensive control ...
- Access and inspection ... shall be conducted where any of the following grounds exists
 - Where access and inspection are conducted according to a plan for regular guidance and inspection as provided by the head of a regional environmental agency to ensure the proper management of chemical substances and products containing chemical substances
 - Where the risks of chemical substances and products containing chemical substances have caused or are likely to cause harm to public health or the environment
 - Where any other agency requests access and inspection with legitimate authority or a civil petition therefor is filed
 - Where it is necessary to verify whether any duty under the Act has been fulfilled regarding chemical substances, such duties as applying for registration or registration of changes; filing a report or a report on changes; confirming exemption from registration, etc.; and reporting any substance subject to intensive control contained in products
 - Where it is necessary to verify whether any data to be protected under Article 45(1) of the Act is appropriately managed to a level that the protection thereof may be requested
- Article 49 [D]: The Minister of Environment may require any of the following persons to make a necessary report or submit data, or require relevant public officials to access the relevant workplace or facility to collect chemical substances or inspect relevant documents, facilities, equipment, etc. In such cases, he or she may require relevant public officials to collect the minimum quantity of chemical substances and samples necessary for testing without compensation
 - A person required to verify chemical substances pursuant to Article 9(1)
 - A person required to obtain permission to manufacture, import, or sell prohibited substances ...
 - A person required to obtain permission to manufacture, import, or use chemical substances requiring permission ...
 - A person required to obtain permission to import restricted substances ...
 - A person required to make an import declaration in respect of toxic chemical substances ...
 - A person required to obtain approval for export of restricted or prohibited substances ...
 - A person required to implement a plan for the prevent and management of chemical accidents ...
 - A person required to obtain permission to conduct hazardous chemical substance business ...
 - A person who sells reagents for use in experiments, research, or testing that fall under toxic chemical substances ...
 - A person required to report the succession to the rights and obligations of hazardous chemical substance business operator ...
 - A person required to observe standards for management of substances requiring preparation for accidents ...
 - A person required to report a chemical accident ...
 - A person entrusted with duties by the Minister of Environment ...
- Access and inspection ... shall be permitted where any of the following grounds exists [F]

- Where such access and inspection are required in accordance with such plan for regular or occasional guidance and inspection as determined by the Minister of Environment, the President of the National Institute of Chemical Safety or the head of a regional environmental agency for the proper control of chemical substances
 - Where a chemical accident has occurred or is likely to occur
 - Where a justifiable request for access and inspection has been made by another institution or a civil petition has been raised
 - Where such access and inspection are inevitable for properly conducting affairs regarding permission, a report, approval, etc. under the Act
 - Where such access and inspection are required to verify whether an off-site consequence analysis or a review on amending evaluation information on off-site consequence analysis under Article 29(2)5 is consistent with relevant facts and meets requirements
 - Where such access and inspection are required to verify whether a trial production plan under Article 29(2)4 is consistent with relevant facts and is complied with
 - Where such access and inspection are required to verify whether the human resources under Article 23-2(3) of the Act have been provided with educational programs
 - Where such access and inspection are required to verify whether the matters provided in the subparagraphs of Article 23-3 (1) of the Act are observed
 - Where such access and inspection are required to verify whether the criteria for the arrangement, installation and management of hazardous chemical substance handling facilities under Article 24 of the Act are observed
 - Where such access and inspection are required to verify whether an improvement order under Article 25 of the Act or an order to take measures under Article 46 of the Act is implemented
 - Where such access and inspection are required to verify whether any person is subject to revocation of permission to conduct hazardous chemical substance business for any ground under Article 35 of the Act
 - Where such access and inspection are required to verify whether the standards for control of substances requiring preparation for accidents under Article 40 of the Act are observed
 - Where such access and inspection are required to verify whether a risk management plan is consistent with relevant facts and is implemented
 - Where such access and inspection are required to verify whether a report on a chemical accident under Article 43 of the Act is proper
 - Where such access and inspection are required to respond to a chemical accident on-site pursuant to Article 44 of the Act
 - Where such access and inspection are required to conduct an investigation into the impact of a chemical accident under Article 45 of the Act
 - Other cases which the Minister of Environment deems necessary for the safe control of chemical substances, other than the matters provided [above].
- Where the Minister of Environment or the head of a regional environmental agency collects chemical substance ..., he or she may request the following institutions to test whether such chemical substances constitute toxic substances
 - The National Institute of Environmental Research; the National Institute of Chemical Safety; the relevant river basin environmental office or the relevant regional environmental office; the Korea Environment Corporation under the Korea Environment Corporation Act; public health and environmental research institutes established in the Special Metropolitan City, Metropolitan Cities, Dos and the Special Self-Governing Province pursuant to the Public Health and Environment Research Institute Act; the Korea Occupational Safety and Health Agency under the Korea Occupational Safety and Health Agency Act.

Statistical surveys on chemical substances [D]

- Article 10: The Minister of Environment shall conduct statistical surveys on the current status of handling relating to the handling of chemical substances, handling facilities, etc. ... every two years. In such cases, the relevant provisions of Statistics Act shall apply mutatis mutandis to collecting and preparing statistics
 - The Minister shall conduct offsite or onsite surveys, or establish and operate an information system for the efficient establishment and implementation of statistical surveys on chemical substances
 - Where necessary for statistical surveys on chemical substances and the establishment and operation of an information system ..., the Minister of Environment may request the heads of relevant central administrative agencies, local government, public institutions ..., relevant institutions, organizations, etc. to provide necessary data and information. In such cases, any person requested to provide data and information shall comply with the request unless there is a compelling reason not to do so
 - The Minister of Environment may require persons who handle chemical substances to submit data necessary for statistical surveys on chemical substances, or require relevant public officials to have access to the relevant place of business, etc. and inspect the current status related to chemical substances. In such cases, any public official who has access to the place of business, etc. and conducts inspection on the current status shall carry a certification indicating his or her authority and show it to interested persons
 - The subject matter of a statistical survey of chemical substances ... shall be as follows [F]
 - A workplace which has been granted permission for or reported on the establishment of a discharge facility pursuant to Article 23(1) of the Clean Air Conservation Act or Article 33(1) of the Water Environment Conservation Act
 - A workplace which manufactures, preserves, stores, uses, exports or imports chemical substances
 - Other subject matters publicly notified by the Minister of Environment as those deemed necessary for a statistical survey of chemical substances
 - The content a statistical survey of chemical substances shall be as follows [F]
 - General information on business entities, such as the types of business, the names of business entities, the locations of workplaces and inflow drainage systems
 - Kinds, uses, product names, and handling quantities of chemical substances which business entities manufacture, import, sell, use and otherwise handle
 - Quantities of distribution, such as quantities warehoused and released, quantities stored and preserved and quantities exported and imported of chemical substances
 - Information related to the kinds, locations and scales of chemical substance handling facilities
 - Other information publicly notified by the Minister of Environment as those deemed necessary for a statistical survey of chemical substances
 - The head of a river basin environmental office or the head of a regional environmental office ... may, if deemed necessary for statistical surveys, request the Association to provide support for the relevant affairs.

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)**Master Plan for Evaluation of Chemical Substance [A]**

- Article 6: The Minister of Environment shall formulate a master plan for registering, reporting and evaluating chemical substances, and reporting substances subject to intensive control contained in products, etc. ... every five years ... A master plan shall include the following:

- Methods and plans for registering and reporting chemical substances, hazard reviews and risk assessments, reporting substances subject to intensive control contained in products, etc.
- Matters concerning registering and reporting chemical substances, reporting substances subject to intensive control contained in products, developing technology necessary for hazard reviews and risk assessments, etc.
- Matters concerning surveys and research, safety management, and international cooperation related to hazards and risks of chemical substances
- Matters concerning industrial activities to prevent any harm caused by chemical substances to public health or the environment, safety support and education for workers and consumers
- Other matters necessary for registering and reporting chemical substances, hazard reviews, risk assessments, etc.

Registration [A]

- Article 10(7): The Minister of Environment shall decide whether to accept a registration or report, and shall notify an applicant of his or her decision within a period prescribed ... from the date of receipt of an application for such registration or report ...

Hazard Review [A]

- Article 18(1): The Minister of Environment shall conduct a hazard review of a chemical substance registered ... (including a chemical substance in which case any change in the registration thereof has been registered ...) ... and shall inform a registrant of the results thereof.
 - A non-phase-in substance: six months: provided, that where further review is required regarding the submitted data, the period may be extended two times by up to six months each time [C]
 - A phase-in substance: one year: provided, that where further review is required regarding the submitted data, the period may be extended two times by up to one year each time [C]
 - Where ... conducts a hazard review, priorities may be determined in consideration of the following matters [C]
 - The quantities of domestic manufacture or import
 - The hazards of the relevant chemical substance
 - Whether any damage has been caused to human health or the environment due to the relevant chemical substance
 - Methods for a hazard review shall be as listed in [the Enforcement Rule; C].
- Article 20: With regard to a chemical substance that is found hazardous based on the results of a hazard review, the Minister of Environment shall designate and publicly notify such chemical substance as a toxic substance.
 - The standard for identifying toxic substance is provided in the Enforcement Decree [B].
- Article 21: Where the Minister of Environment completes a hazard review, he or she shall publicly notify the name and hazards of the relevant chemical substance, whether the chemical substance falls under the category of toxic substances ..., and other matters prescribed.
 - Where the name of a chemical substance publicly notified ... is subject to data protection ..., the Minister of Environment shall publicly notify such chemical substance by its generic name until the period for data protection expires: provided, that where the chemical substance falls under the category of toxic substances ..., the Minister of Environment shall publicly notify its name.

Hazard Assessment [A]

- With regard to the [following] chemical substances prescribed ... as hazard assessment of which is deemed necessary ... the Minister of Environment shall conduct hazard assessment on such chemical substances ...

- A chemical substance that the Republic of Korea assesses by itself, among chemical substances that their hazard assessment is conducted by international organizations, such as the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) [B]
- A chemical substance for the implementation of international conventions [B]
- A chemical substance manufactured or imported to export the whole quantity thereof [B]
- A chemical substance whose human health or environmental hazards may be determined based on the results obtained from internationally recognized qualitative or quantitative structure activity relationship models (QSAR models), the quantity of which to be manufactured or imported is less than 10 tonnes per year [B]
- A chemical substance whose human health or environmental hazards may be determined based on the results obtained by internationally recognized in vitro testing methods [B]
- A chemical substance whose human health or environmental hazards may be determined based on the results obtained from a chemical substance with similar structure or similar physical and chemical properties, such as metallic compounds containing same metals [B]
- A chemical substance whose human health or environmental hazards may be determined based on the reliable results equivalent to those obtained by internationally recognized testing methods [B]
- A chemical substance whose human health or environmental hazards may be determined based on the results of the hazard assessment published by a foreign government or an international organization [B]
- A chemical substance to develop test methods concerning physical and chemical properties and hazards of chemical substances [B]
- A chemical substance that harms or is likely to harm human health or the environment [B]
- A chemical substance manufactured by small and medium enterprises defined in the subparagraphs of Article 2(1) of the Framework Act on Small and Medium Enterprises [B]
- Nanomaterials¹³¹ [B]
- Attached Table 9 shall apply mutatis mutandis to the method for hazard assessment [C]
- Any person who intends to use hazard data generated for hazard assessment ... for registration of a chemical substance or application for hazard review under domestic or foreign statutes and regulations, including provisions concerning registration under Article 10, shall obtain approval from the Minister of Environment.
 - The Minister of Environment may revoke approval where any person who has obtained approval for the use of hazard data ... falls under any of the following: provided, that in case falling under subparagraph 1, the Minister of Environment shall revoke such approval
 - Where he or she has obtained the approval by fraud or other improper means
 - Where he or she allows another person who has not obtained approval for the use of hazard data to use such data
 - Where he or she uses hazard data for any purpose other than that for which the approval was obtained.

Risk assessment [A]

¹³¹ Any of the following materials [B]

- A material containing particles where, for 50 percent or more of the particles in the number size distribution, one or more external dimensions is in the size range of 1 to 100 nanometers;
- A fullerene, graphene flake, and single-wall carbon nanotube with one or more external dimensions below 1 nanometer.

- Article 24: The Minister of Environment shall conduct a risk assessment of any of the following chemical substances from among chemical substances registered ..., based on the results of a hazard review, and shall inform a registrant of the results thereof, as prescribed ...
 - Where the quantity of a chemical substance manufactured or imported is at least ten tons per year
 - Where the risk assessment of a chemical substance is deemed necessary based on the results of a hazard review thereof
 - ... shall conduct risk assessments of chemical substances listed ..., after determining the priority thereof in consideration of the following [C]
 - The quantities of the relevant chemical substance domestically manufactured and imported
 - Hazards of the relevant chemical substance
 - Uses of and ways of using the relevant chemical substance
 - Likelihood to damage human health or the environment
 - Other available data concerning the risks of the relevant chemical substance
 - A risk assessment ... shall be conducted based on the following data [C]
 - Data submitted to apply for registration ... and registration of change ...
 - Other recognized domestic and international information concerning the relevant chemical substance
 - Where ... conducts a risk assessment ..., he or she shall prepare a report on risk assessment, including the following matters [C]
 - The name of the chemical substance subject to the risk assessment
 - The period of the risk assessment
 - Assessment of the physical and chemical properties of the relevant chemical substance with respect to human health
 - Hazard assessment of the relevant chemical substance with respect to human health and the environment
 - Dose-response assessment of the relevant chemical substance
 - Exposure assessment of the relevant chemical substance
 - Risk level of the relevant chemical substance
- The Minister of Environment may take necessary measures to minimize risks, based on the results of the risk assessment ...
 - Recommending related administrative agencies, public institutions, etc. to implement risk management measures, including measures that can prevent risks ... in the process of handling the relevant chemical substances
 - Recommending manufacturers, importers, and downstream users of chemical substances to implement risk management measures
 - Other measures deemed necessary by the Minister of Environment to minimize risks of chemical substances
 - ... [the Minister of Environment] shall formulate risk management measures in advance

Designation of substance subject to permission [A]

- Article 25: The Minister of Environment may designate and publicly notify substances subject to intensive control and other chemical substances likely to pose a risk based on a hazard review and a risk assessment as a substance subject to permission before they are manufactured, imported or used ... In such cases, the Minister of Environment may designate and publicly notify the uses of such chemical

substances or substances that can be manufactured, imported, or used without his or her permission because they are less likely to pose a risk¹³²

- The standard for identifying substances subject to intensive control is provided in the Enforcement Decree [B].
- The Minister of Environment may request the head of an association established pursuant to Article 53(1) of the Chemical Substances Control Act ... for controlling chemical substances to prepare and submit a review report on the uses and the permission grace period of the relevant chemical substance before designating the uses of such chemical substance that can be manufactured, imported, or used without permission ... or granting the permission grace period, where necessary. [B]
- Where the Minister of Environment designates and publicly notifies a substance subject to permission ..., he or she shall include the name of the substance subject to permission, and the period during which the substance may be manufactured, imported or used without obtaining permission.
 - The name and identification number of the relevant chemical substance [B]
 - Uses of the relevant chemical substance that can be manufactured, imported, or used without permission, such as a scientific experiment, analysis, or reagent for chemical research [B]
 - The permission grace period [B]
- Article 26: Where a substance subject to permission falls under any of the following, the Minister of Environment may terminate the designation as a substance subject to permission, or may fully or partially change the details publicly notified In such cases, the Minister of Environment shall publicly notify such termination or change:
 - Where the substance subject to permission no longer needs to be used, as a substance that can substitute the substance subject to permission is manufactured or new technology is developed
 - Where any use of the substance subject to permission no longer poses a risk due to the commercialization of new technology

¹³² Any of the following situations [B]

- Where the Minister of Environment designates a chemical substance as a substance subject to permission ..., he or she shall prepare a socio-economic analysis ... that has analyzed socio-economic impacts arising from the use of the chemical substance in advance and shall also conduct a risk assessment if no risk assessment of the chemical substance has been conducted: provided, that the Minister of Environment may elect to omit a socio-economic analysis or risk assessment if a chemical substance that he or she intends to designate as a substance subject to permission has been, or is determined to be, regulated by a foreign government, international organization, or similar agency; meets the criteria provided in attached Table 1-2; and there is sufficient information proving the risks of the chemical substance.
- Where the Minister of Environment designates the uses of a substance subject to permission that can be manufactured, imported, or used without his or her permission ... or determines the period during which the substance can be manufactured, imported or used without his or her permission ..., he or she shall take into account the following
 - Findings of a risk assessment of the relevant chemical substance (only applicable where such risk assessment has been conducted ...)
 - Results of a socio-economic analysis of the relevant chemical substance (only applicable where such socio-economic analysis has been prepared ...)
 - Risk management measures for the relevant chemical substance
 - Information on a substance or new technology that can replace the relevant chemical substance and on the time of introduction thereof

- Where new scientific evidence verifies that the substance subject to permission does not pose a risk.

Designation of Restricted Substance or Prohibited Substance [A]

- Article 27: Where a chemical substance falls under any of the following, the Minister of Environment shall designate and publicly notify the relevant chemical substance as a restricted substance or prohibited substance¹³³
 - Where the chemical substance is deemed to pose a risk based on the results of a hazard review and a risk assessment
 - Where a foreign government, international organization, etc. deems that the chemical substance poses a risk
 - Where manufacture, import or use of the chemical substance is prohibited or restricted in accordance with an international agreement, etc.;
 - Where the chemical substance falls under substances subject to permission that the designation of which has been terminated due to the ground that [the substance subject to permission no longer needs to be used, as a substance that can substitute the substance subject to permission is manufactured or new technology is developed]
- Where the Minister of Environment intends to designate a chemical substance as a restricted substance or prohibited substance, he or she shall notify beforehand the name of the chemical substance to be designated, the timing of designation, and other similar matters in the Official Gazette or on the website: Provided, That this shall not apply where urgent response is required because the relevant chemical substance poses or is likely to pose a critical risk to human health or the environment.
 - The name and identification number of the relevant chemical substance [B]
 - Uses for which the restriction or prohibition is required and the details thereof [B]

¹³³ Any of the following situations [B]

- Where the Minister of Environment intends to designate a chemical substance as a restricted substance or prohibited substance ..., he or she shall take into consideration the possibility of replacement, such as a substance or new technology that can replace the relevant chemical substance, and socio-economic impacts generated from the uses of the relevant chemical substance
- Where the Minister of Environment designates a chemical substance as a restricted substance or prohibited substance ..., he or she shall prepare a socio-economic analysis in advance and shall also conduct a risk assessment if no risk assessment of chemical substance has been conducted: provided, that the Minister of Environment may elect to omit a socio-economic analysis or risk assessment if a chemical substance that he or she intends to designate as a restricted substance or prohibited substance has been, or is determined to be, regulated by a foreign government, international organization, or similar agency and there is sufficient information proving the risks of the chemical substances

Prohibition on handling of prohibited substances and restriction on handling of restricted substances – Art. 18 [D]

- No person shall handle prohibited substances: provided, that the foregoing shall not apply where a person who intends to manufacture, import, or sell a reagent intended for use in experiments, research, or testing, which fall under prohibited substances, for their intended purposes obtains a permission thereof from the Minister of Environment
 - Where a person who has obtained a permission to handle prohibited substances ... intends to modify any of the matters prescribed ... among the permitted matters, he or she shall obtain a permission for modification or file a report on modification ...
 - Where the Minister of Environment grants a permission ..., he or she may attach thereto conditions necessary for the appropriate control of the relevant prohibited substances, such as submission of a plan for preventive measures against chemical accidents.
- No person shall handle restricted substances for any restricted purpose.

- Where the Minister of Environment designates and publicly notifies a chemical substance as a restricted substance or prohibited substance, he or she shall include the name of the restricted substance or prohibited substance, details of prohibition depending on its use, and similar matters.
- In any of the following cases, the Minister of Environment may terminate the designation of a chemical substance as a restricted substance or prohibited substance, or may fully or partially change the details publicly notified ... In such cases, the Minister of Environment shall publicly notify such termination or change:
 - Where the restricted substance or prohibited substance no longer poses a risk due to commercialization of new technology
 - Where new scientific evidence verifies that the restricted substance or prohibited substance does not pose a risk.

Suspension of manufacture and import of toxic chemical substances [D]

- Where the Minister of Environment deems that toxic chemical substances poses or is likely to pose a serious risk to human health or the environment, he or she may order the suspension of the manufacture, import, sale, keeping, storage, transport, or use of the toxic chemical substances.
 - Where the Minister of Environment deems that toxic chemical substances whose manufacture, import, etc. was suspended ... is unlikely to pose a risk to human health or the environment, he or she shall cancel all or part of the relevant suspension without delay.

Permission to manufacture, import, or use substances subject to permission [D]

- The Minister of Environment shall review information submitted ... within a period prescribed ... from the date of the receipt of the application ..., determine whether to grant a permission in accordance with the following requirements, and notify the applicant of his or her determination:
 - Where the risk to human health and the environment may be appropriately controlled
 - Where socioeconomic benefits obtained from the use of the substances subject to permission exceed the risk to human health and the environment
 - Where no appropriate chemical substances or technology that can substitute the substances subject to permission exists
- Where the Minister of Environment notifies permission ..., he or she shall impose conditions, such as the permission number, purposes of the substances subject to permission, and the limit on the period of manufacturing, importing, or using the substances subject to permission.

8. Data submission format

electronically

9. Data confidentiality

- Article 45 [A]: Where any person who has submitted data pursuant to Articles 11 (2) and (3) [i.e. a chemical substance of very low risk or chemicals exempted from registration, etc.], 12 (1) through (3) [i.e. registration and notification of change], 14 (1), (3) and (6) [i.e. data to be submitted by registration], 18 (2) [i.e. Hazard review], 24 (2) [i.e. Risk assessment] and 32 (1) [i.e. Notification of Substance Subject to Intensive Control Contained in Product] requests the Minister of Environment to protect data on components, etc. of a chemical substance to protect confidential information, the Minister of Environment shall not disclose such data during the period of data protection prescribed ...: Provided, That where the data requested to be protected is already disclosed or falls under the data prescribed ..., such data may be disclosed.
 - Where data requested to be protected ... is not eligible for protection ..., the Minister of Environment shall notify the person who has requested data protection of such fact

- Where any ground for data protection ceases to exist, a person who has requested data protection ... shall request the Minister of Environment to terminate data protection ...
- The Minister of Environment shall not disclose data submitted to him or her ... for five years: provided, that where a person who has submitted data applies for an extension of the period for data protection ..., the Minister of Environment may permit the extension thereof only twice by five years
- Any of the following data, which are not trade secrets
 - Data concerning the commercial names of chemical substances or the names, etc. of products, etc.
 - Data concerning the uses of chemical substances or products
 - Data concerning the safe use, such as matters requiring attention when handling chemical substances or products or methods of destruction
 - Data concerning methods of responding to accidents related to chemical substances
 - Data concerning physical and chemical properties of chemical substances
 - Summary data concerning hazards of chemical substances
 - Summary data concerning risks of chemical substances
 - Other data publicly notified by the Minister of Environment, as he or she deems that the disclosure of such data is necessary to protect human health and the environment
- Article 52 [D]: Where a person who submitted data pursuant to this Act requests the Minister of Environment to protect data on the ingredients of chemical substances, etc. for confidentiality, he or she shall not disclose such data during the data protection period [for five years, E]¹³⁴: provided, that the foregoing shall not apply where data falls under any of the following
 - Data for which the request for data protection is made has been disclosed in the Republic of Korea and abroad [E]
 - Data determined to be disclosed [of results of surveys of chemical substances and information] [E]
 - The commercial name of a chemical substance or data concerning the name of the product [E]
 - Data concerning the usages of a chemical substance [E]
 - Data concerning the safe use of chemical substances, such as handling precautions or disposal methods [E]
 - Data concerning methods for responding to the occurrence of a chemical accident [E]
 - Data concerning physical or chemical properties of a chemical substance [E]
 - Summary data concerning the hazards of a chemical substance [E]
 - Summary data concerning the risk of a chemical substance [E]
 - Data concerning the volume of chemical substance discharges into the environment [E]
 - Other data publicly notified by the Minister of Environment, as he or she deems that the disclosure of such data is necessary to protect human health and the environment [E]

10. Data that are published publicly

Registration, etc.

- Article 42: The Minister of Environment shall ... disclose information on the names, risks, etc. of chemical substances so that the general public may readily access and use the information on hazards and risks of chemical substances. [A]

¹³⁴ Provided, that where any person who has submitted data applies for extension of the period of data protection, ... the Minister of Environment may allow the extension of the period of data protection for each five years but not more than twice. [E]

- The name and identification number of the relevant chemical substance [C]
- Uses of the relevant chemical substance according to the use classification system of chemical substances [C]
- Classification and labelling of the relevant chemical substance [C]
- Whether the chemical substance constitutes a toxic substance, substance subject to permission, restricted substance or prohibited substance [C]
- Physical and chemical properties of the relevant chemical substance [C]
- Hazards and risks of the relevant chemical substance [C]
- Details of safe use of the relevant chemical substance, such as precautions in handling [C]
- KECI: information on CAS No, Chemical Name, KE No. is generally shown, and additional information such as molecular formula, molecular weight, other registration numbers, content (%), and classification and labelling may be shown). [G]

Disclosure of results of surveys of chemical substances and information

- Article 12 [D]: Where the Minister of Environment completes statistical surveys on chemical substances and surveys for the pollutant release and transfer registers, he or she shall disclose, without delay, the results thereof for each place of business: provided, that the foregoing shall not apply where the result thereof fall under any of the following
 - Where the disclosure of the results of such survey is deemed to cause serious interference with national security, maintenance of order, or public welfare
 - Where the results of such survey are deemed to cause confusion in the use thereof due to low reliability
 - Where it is deemed necessary not to disclose some of the results of such survey because it is related to trade secrets of business
 - Where a person subject to disclosure information ... wishes not to disclose the results of a survey ... or information about the handling of chemical substances ..., he or she may request that the Minister of Environment deliberate on whether the relevant information needs to disclose ... In such cases, it shall be deemed that a request for protection of data prescribed in the main sentence of Article 52(1) has been made.

Approval for export of restricted substances or prohibited substances [D]

- The Minister of Environment shall publicly notify the following matters in consultation with the Minister of Trade, Industry and Energy:
 - Names of chemical substances, the import of which is prohibited or restricted by the parties to the agreement pursuant to Article 5 of the Rotterdam Convention on the Prior Informed Consent Procedure for Certain Hazardous Chemicals and Pesticides in International Trade ... and the details of prohibitions or restrictions;
 - Matters to be observed by those who export chemical substances pursuant to Article 13 of the Rotterdam Convention;
 - Chemical substances listed in Annex III to the Rotterdam Convention;
 - Information that shall be included in a notification of export, as provided for in Annex V to the Rotterdam Convention.

11. International information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.13 Malaysian MyEHS System (Environmentally Hazardous Substances Information System; formerly Notification and Registration Scheme of Environmentally Hazardous Substances, EHSNR)

Last update: 29 June 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Main website: <https://myehs.doe.gov.my/portal/myehs/> (EHS References List: https://myehs.doe.gov.my/myehs/ehs_references_public/view)
- B. Guidance for the industry (2012): <https://studylib.net/doc/18461314/guidance-on-notification-and-registration-scheme-of-ehs> [note: No newer version was identified after an internet search; therefore, this document is still used in this study.]
- C. Online system user guidance (in Bahasa): <https://studylib.net/doc/18461314/guidance-on-notification-and-registration-scheme-of-ehs>

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

- **Objective:** [A]
 - to ensure importers and manufacturers to notify the manufacturing and importation of EHS¹³⁵
 - to provide the necessary information on EHS
 - to manage EHS in a safe and sound manner to protect the human health and the environment
- Based on the information submitted by industry, Department of Environment (DOE) will establish the **Malaysian EHS Reference List**. It will contain information about the identity of substances that have been notified to DOE, their uses in Malaysia, their hazard classification and the accumulated amounts placed on the market in Malaysia. The information in this system will be available to the public. [A]
- **As of 4 June 2021:** The EHSNR system is on a voluntary basis [and] will become mandatory as soon as the draft regulations on EHS is gazetted. The information will be published on the DOE website. [A]

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligations

- all substances that are not covered by other notification or registration system in Malaysia and fulfilling the criteria for classification according to [GHS]. [A]
- Other substances that are considered substances of concern due to properties not covered by the GHS classification scheme. [A]
- The scheme is aimed at manufacturers and importers of EHS and importers of chemical mixtures or finished products that contain EHS as their constituents. The scheme is also aimed at companies importing individual EHS and/or chemical mixtures or finished products containing EHS as constituents above certain cut-off limits. [B]
- The scheme will cover substances such as [B]
 - Petrochemicals including plastics and resins
 - Chemicals in fertilizers and pesticides (not active ingredients which are already regulated)
 - soap and detergents
 - cosmetics, toiletries and household products
 - organic chemicals

¹³⁵ For the purposes of notification and registration under the EQA, an EHS will be defined as follows: An EHS is a substance that is assigned a hazard category under the GHS classification scheme or is present on an existing internationally agreed list of proscribed substances. [B]

- *oleo-chemical products*
- *chemicals in pharmaceutical products (not active ingredients which are already regulated)*
- *industrial gases*
- *paints and paints products*
- *basic industrial chemicals*
- *rubber industry*
- likely accumulated tonnage of equal to or more than 1 metric ton [B]

3.2 Exemptions

- *The notification requirement does not apply to substances for which information is already submitted to a Government agency in Malaysia by means of other legislations such as: Poisons Act 1952; Pesticides Act 1974; Atomic Energy Licensing Act 1984; Chemical Weapons Convention Act 2005. [A]*
- *Chemical industries involved in the manufacturing of chemical mixtures or products using locally manufactured EHS or imported EHS sourced from local suppliers as raw materials are not subject to this scheme. Chemical companies involved in formulation, distribution, retailing and use of EHS or EHS containing mixtures/products from locally sourced EHS are not subject to this scheme. [B]*
- *Substances which are exempted [B]*
 - *naturally occurring materials*
 - *incidental/end-use reaction products*
 - *substances formed during the manufacture of an article*
 - *mixtures (but not mixture components)*
 - *impurities*
 - *by-products*
 - *non-isolated intermediates*
 - *contained site-limited intermediates*
 - *transported intermediates*
 - *substances manufactured solely for export*
 - *substances used in research and development*
 - *substances produced for test marketing*
 - *low volume substances (<1 tonne per annum)*
 - *polymers*

4. Initial data requirements

Pre-registration [B]

- *List out chemicals imported or manufactured into a table which contains: name of substances; CAS No/EC No/index No; tonnage imported/manufactured*
- *prepare any available material safety data sheet (MSDS) for each of the substances*

Registration [B]

- *Substances which are already listed in the EHS reference List or CMR Reference List are required to do Basic Notification only*
 - *Substance identification (CASRN, EC number or index number)*
 - *Annual tonnage in metric tons*
 - *Use of the substance*
 - *Concentration interval of substance in raw materials or finished products (maximum and minimum concentration)*
 - *Country of export (if imported)*

- *Substances which are NOT listed in the EHS reference List or CMR Reference List are required to go for further clarification.*
 - *the substance may be classified as NOT hazardous based on the GHS hazard classification. The manufacturer/importer (M/I) are required to go through the substance material safety data sheet and search for any clues or statements which can related the substance as hazardous or not hazardous*
 - *The substance is not yet classified and therefore is not yet listed in the list. In this case, M/I are required to submit additional information (Detailed Notification) together with the basic information. The information required are*
 - *Data on substance identification (e.g. structural formula, molecular weight, etc.)*
 - *Data on physical-chemical properties (e.g. melting point, auto-ignition temperature, etc.)*
 - *Data on physical hazards (e.g. flammability, corrosivity to metals, etc.)*
 - *Data on hazards to human health (e.g. acute toxicity, skin corrosion/irritation, etc.)*
 - *Data on hazards to aquatic environment (e.g. acute aquatic toxicity and properties like bioaccumulation, etc.)*
 - *overall GHS Classification*
- *For substances that are unable to be classified due to lack of data or data cannot be submitted due to no information available, the manufacture/importer can submit the notification with reasons on why those information cannot be submitted.*

5. Data updates by companies

- *[Basic] Notification [needs] to be done annually based on the previous year data. [B]*
- *If a substance had been previous notified in detail (e.g. in the previous year), a detailed notification of the said substance is not required anymore. However, a new detailed notification of the substance should be made if new data are available to the company. In this case, detailed data previously notified can be accessed and edited to reflect the changes. [B]*
 - *Once submitted the substance will be registered in the list and therefore the substance will fall under Basic Notification in the following year.*

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

- *In the case of DOE disputing the GHS classification assigned by the M/I, there will be discussion between DOE and the M/I to resolve any disagreement or misunderstanding. If agreement still cannot be reached, the Technical Committee on Classification will decide on the agreed GHS classification. [B]*

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

- *It takes five (5) working days to approve the company registration in the MyEHS system. [A]*
- *DOE will check the substance classification data supplied by the M/I for [B]*
 - *accuracy and self consistency*
 - *consistency of classification assigned with those by other M/I and/or Department of Occupational Safety and Health to that substance*
 - *correct assignment of GHS classification based on the substance data supplied and GHS classification rules*
- *Once the GHS classification has been accepted, DOE will enter the substance and the associated data into the Register of Notified Substances.*

8. Data submission format

via the online portal

9. Data confidentiality

- *External Notification is to allow the submission from the overseas suppliers (third party) due to the Confidential Business Information (CBI). Locally registered companies register their overseas suppliers in the system in case that the substances are classified as confidential by the overseas suppliers. This is only applicable to substances that require detailed notification. [A]*

10. Data that are published publicly

- EHS References List: CASRNs, EC Numbers and chemical names

11. International information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.14 Chemicals Information Management System (CIMS), Malaysia

Last update: 18 June 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Homepage: <http://cims.dosh.gov.my>
- B. Occupational Safety and Health Act (1994) Occupational Safety and Health (Classification, Labelling and Safety Data Sheet of Hazardous Chemicals) Regulations (2013):
https://www.ilo.org/dyn/natlex/natlex4.detail?p_lang=en&p_isn=109406&p_count=96167
- C. <https://www.dosh.gov.my/index.php/list-of-documents/osh-info/chemical-management-1/promotional-materials/2265-chemical-information-management-system-cims-rqtm>
- D. Summary report hazardous chemical inventory 2019 from Chemical Information Management System (CIMS): <https://www.dosh.gov.my/index.php/list-of-documents/osh-info/chemical-management-1/3734-summary-report-hazardous-chemical-inventory-2019-from-cims/file>

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory [C]

- *To facilitate compliance to CLASS Regulation 2013*
- *to monitor compliance status of the CLASS Regulation 2013*
- *to identify chemicals supplied to workplaces with its hazard classification and total quantity*
- *knowledge sharing of hazard information of hazardous chemicals*

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligation

- *An importer or a manufacturer, as the case may be, shall prepare an inventory of hazardous chemicals¹³⁶ consisting of information on each hazardous chemical imported or supplied in a quantity of one metric tonne and above per year for each calendar year. [B]*
- *These Regulations shall apply to chemicals supplied for use at a place of work. [B]*

3.2 Exemptions [B]

- *These Regulations shall not apply to:*
 - *A chemical which is*
 - *A radio-active material as defined under the Atomic Energy Licensing Act 1984 [Act 304]*
 - *Scheduled waste as defined under the Environmental Quality (Scheduled Wastes) Regulations 2005 [P.U. (A) 294/2005]; and*

¹³⁶ *Chemical means (a) a substance which is a chemical element and its compounds in the natural state or obtained by any manufacturing process, including any additive necessary to preserve its stability and any impurity deriving from the process used, but excluding any solvent which may be separated without affecting the stability of the element and its compounds, or changing its composition; and (b) a chemical mixture which is a mixture or solution composed of two or more substances which do not react, for use at a place of work, including an alloy. [B]*

Hazardous substances = classification in accordance with the list of classified chemicals specified in Part 1 of the Industry Code of Practice on Chemicals Classification and Hazard Communication; if the chemical to be classified is not listed as a classified chemical in Part 1 of the Industry Code of Practice, the classification of the chemical as a hazardous chemical shall be in accordance with the physical, health and environment hazard of the chemical as specified in Part 2 of the Industry Code of Practice. [B]

The Industry Code of Practice is aligned with GHS Rev. 3.

- *A cosmetic or product as defined under the Control of Drugs and Cosmetics Regulations 1984 [P.U. (A) 223/1984]*
 - *A chemical used for scientific research and development, or trial purposes which*
 - *Is not for sale in the market*
 - *Does not exceed five kilograms in capacity, and*
 - *Adequate information on the safe use of the chemical is made available by the supplier, and*
 - *A manufactured item, other than a fluid or particle, which*
 - *Forms to a specific shape or design during manufacture*
 - *Has end use function dependent in whole or in part upon its shape or design during end use, and*
 - *Under normal conditions of use, does not release significant quantity of chemical which poses physical hazard or risk to health.*
- *Parts II [classification], III [packaging], IV [labelling] and VI [inventory of hazardous chemicals] shall not apply to*
 - *A chemical which is a pesticide as defined under the Pesticides Act 1974 [Act 149], and*
 - *A chemical in transit prior to export which is stored at any storage area.*

4. Initial data requirements [B]

- *The inventory of hazardous chemicals shall contain the following information*
 - *The product identifier*
 - *The name of the hazardous chemical*
 - *The composition and ingredients of a hazardous chemical*
 - *The hazard classification; and*
 - *The total quantity of each hazardous chemical imported or supplied*
- *The name of the hazardous chemical, and composition of the ingredients shall include the CAS Registry Numbers, if applicable.*

5. Updates by companies &

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators [B]

- *A principal supplier shall record the classification of chemicals as hazardous chemicals ... in such form and manner specified in Part 2 of the Industry Code of Practice*
- *A principal supplier shall make the record of the classification of chemicals as hazardous chemicals ... available for inspection by an officer.*

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

- *If the Director General finds that there is inconsistency in the classification of the same chemical, the Director General may determine the classification based on the list of classified chemicals in Part 1 of the Industry Code of Practice and in accordance with the physical, health and environmental hazard of the chemical as specified in Part 2 of the Industry Code of Practice.*
- *Upon the determination on the classification of a chemical as a hazardous chemical by the Director General ... the principal supplier shall comply with such determination. [B]*

8. Data submission format

via the online portal [A]

9. Data confidentiality [B]

- *A supplier may omit the information required ... in a Safety Data Sheet or an inventory of hazardous chemicals, as the case may be, if the information on (a) the name of a hazardous chemical; or (b) the composition and ingredients of a hazardous chemical, constitutes confidential business information.*
- *If the information is omitted, such information shall be replaced with the generic name of the hazardous chemical or allowable concentration range of the ingredients of the hazardous chemical, as the case may be, as specified in Part 4 of the Industry Code of Practice.*
- *The Director General, an occupational health doctor, or a person who uses or handles a hazardous chemical may request in writing from a principal supplier for the disclosure of the confidential information.*
- *Upon receipt of the request, the principal supplier shall disclose the information to the Director General, occupational health doctor, or person who uses or handles the hazardous chemical, as the case may be.*
- *The information obtained shall only be used for the purpose of protection of the safety and health of employees.*

10. Data that are published publicly / in the inventory [C]

- *Product identifier*
- *Name, CASRN (if any)*
- *Composition & ingredients*
- *Hazard classification*
- *Total quantity of chemicals supplied*

11. International information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.15 Inventario Nacional de Sustancias Químicas (INSQ), Mexico

Last update: 7 June 2021

1. Links

- A. Actualización del Inventario Nacional de Sustancias Químicas 2010-2013 (2014; in Spanish): https://www.gob.mx/cms/uploads/attachment/file/191430/2014_Actualizaci_n_del_inventario.pdf;
- B. Mendoza Cantu A, Ize Lema IAR. 2017. Chemical substances in Mexico. Perspectives for proper management. *Rev Int Contam Ambient* 33(4). <https://doi.org/10.20937/rica.2017.33.04.15> (in Spanish; text below were extracted based on Google translate).
- C. Inventory: http://www2.inecc.gob.mx/sistemas/inventarioNSQ/buscar_cas.php

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory [B]

- In 2012, the National Institute of Ecology and Climate Change (INECC) published the INSQ base 2009, which was the result of the review of official data that accounted for the production and importation of chemicals, including the Annual Operation Certificate (COA)¹³⁷, customs databases and the environmental audits of the Federal Attorney for Environmental Protection (PROFEPA). The INSQ include the chemical identity of 5852 chemicals and their quantities reported.
- The INSQ was then updated using data from 2010 to 2013, based on sources such as the COA and the SAT import petition. The update represents an important advance in the identification of chemical substances in commerce in Mexico, with 9849 chemical substances traded in Mexico identified.

3. Scope of the inventory

- **INSQ:** Regulated chemicals; PRTR study; national chemical industry association annual report of operations (COA); customs office reports
- In Mexico, the regulation of the importation and production of chemical substances is limited to certain groups through permits or registrations. For substances subject to sanitary control, authorization must be obtained from the Federal Commission for the Protection against Sanitary Risks (COFEPRIS). These are drugs, narcotics, psychotropics, diagnostic agents, dental supplies and hygiene products, that is, substances of primary contact or direct exposure, as well as pesticides and plant nutrients. [B]

4. Initial data requirements (done by the National Institute of Ecology and Climate Change)

¹³⁷ The COA includes a section for raw materials and inputs and other sections that feed the database of the Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (PRTR). These reports provide a certain idea of the substances that are used and released from industrial establishments and service under federal jurisdiction. El Reglamento de la Ley General del Equilibrio Ecológico y Protección al Ambiente (LGEEPA) regarding the Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (PRTR) and NOM-165-SEMARNAT-2013 establish the list of substances subject to reporting. Other relevant regulations in Mexico include [B]: NOM-001-SEMARNAT-1996 (the maximum permissible limits of pollutants in wastewater discharges into national waters and goods; NOM-047-SSA1-2011 Environmental Health: biological exposure indices for personnel occupationally exposed to chemical substances; NOM-010-STPS-2014, chemical pollutants in the work environment: recognition, evaluation and control; NMX-R-019-SCFI-2011 voluntary standard on GHS (excluding drugs, food additives, cosmetics, pesticides and waste); and NOM-018-STPS-2015 The Harmonized identification and Hazard Communication and Risk System of Workplace Hazardous Chemicals (a mandatory standard based on the **5th Revision of GHS**; requires that chemical label must include physical and health hazards; for interpretation of this standard, the chemical industry may use the voluntary standard NMX-R-019-SCFI-2011, and that the environmental hazards are not mandatory in the label; <https://www.ul.com/news/mexicos-ghs-implementation-officially-comes-force>).

CASRN (preferred, alternate, deleted; substances whose assigned CASRN could be identified were included); CAS name and synonyms; formula and molecular structure; chemical class; quantities produced and imported (2009); ecotoxicological data; environmental persistence; bioaccumulation; toxicity in aquatic organisms (information on hazards and risks from cooperation with Canada and EU REACH)

5. Data updates by companies

N.A.

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

N.A.

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

N.A.

8. Data submission format

N.A.

9. Data confidentiality

N.A.

10. Data that are published publicly

CASRN, chemical name, synonyms, chemical formula, type of chemicals, information sources, whether it was listed on the TSCA, whether it was listed on PORFEPA (substances linked to chemical emergencies)

11. Information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.16 New Zealand Inventory of Chemicals (NZIoC)

Last update: 21 June 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Homepage: <https://www.epa.govt.nz/industry-areas/hazardous-substances/guidance-for-importers-and-manufacturers/hazardous-substances-databases/>
- B. Operational Policies and Procedures – New Zealand Inventory of Chemicals (NZIoC) (November 2011) <https://www.epa.govt.nz/assets/Uploads/Documents/Hazardous-Substances/Guidance/eabf91ae56/Operational-Policies-NZIoC.pdf>
- C. New Zealand Inventory of Chemicals (NZIoC) guide (2020): <https://www.epa.govt.nz/assets/Uploads/Documents/Hazardous-Substances/New-Zealand-Inventory-of-Chemicals-NZIoC-Guidance.pdf>
- D. Hazardous Substances and New Organisms Act 1996 (Reprint as at 1 April 2021): <https://www.legislation.govt.nz/act/public/1996/0030/latest/whole.html>

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

- Distinction of existing vs. new hazardous chemicals
- *The aim of the NZIoC is to provide a list of all the chemicals in New Zealand. It is not a list of approvals. The maintenance of an NZIoC is consistent with the approach taken in many other developed countries, including Australia, USA and Europe and forms an integral part of the risk management framework for Group Standards. [C]*
- *The majority of the listed CAS numbers were compiled using the lists of individual chemical substances that were transferred to HSNO under the transitional provisions of the Act. This includes the substances from the Hazardous Substances (Dangerous Goods and Scheduled Toxic Substances) Transfer Notice 2004, the Hazardous Substances (Chemicals) Transfer Notice 2006, all the components of [notified substances], whether they were single chemicals or formulated products where CAS numbers were provided, components of various applications that have been approved under HSNO and any notifications to the Inventory received since 1 July 2006.¹³⁸ [B]*
- *The transfer of over 100,000 notified substances (NOTS) from the transitional provisions to the main part of the HSNO Act was completed on 1 July 2006; this transfer was effected with the EPA issuing 200 Group Standards in the Hazardous Substances (Group Standards) Notice 2006. [B]*

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligations

- *Where a substance¹³⁹ is imported into, or manufactured in, New Zealand after 30 June 2006, if that substance contains a hazardous chemical¹⁴⁰ that is not listed on the NZIoC, then the importer or*

¹³⁸ The EPA were accepting notification for components of notified substances (NOTS) without hazard data till 1 July 2008. Only the following information needed to be supplied when notifying components of notified substances: NOTS number, substance/product name, new chemical component name, CAS number. [B]

¹³⁹ Substance means—(a) Any element, defined mixture of elements, compounds, or defined mixture of compounds, either naturally occurring or produced synthetically, or any mixtures thereof;

(b) Any isotope, allotrope, isomer, congener, radical, or ion of an element or compound which has been declared by the Authority, by notice in the Gazette, to be a different substance from that element or compound:

(c) Any mixtures or combinations of any of the above... [C]

¹⁴⁰ Hazardous chemical means any chemical, unless expressly provided otherwise by regulations, (a) with 1 or more of the following intrinsic properties: explosiveness; flammability; a capacity to oxidise; corrosiveness; toxicity; ecotoxicity, with or without bioaccumulation; or (b) which on contact with air or water (other than air

manufacturer of the substance must at the time they first import or manufacture the substance, notify the Authority. [C] A hazardous chemical which does not have an EPA approval cannot be imported or manufactured before an approval is obtained.

- Any hazardous component of a new formulated product using a Group Standard approval that is not on the NZIoC will need to be notified. [C]
 - Cut-off levels for notification will be based on the respective hazard cut-off concentrations. The simple rule will be that if a component contributes to the hazard of a product, then if the component is not on the NZIoC, it is required to be notified. Regulations require much of this information on the Safety Data Sheet (SDS) at the same concentration as the hazard cut-offs for class 6 classifications. [0.1% for 6.5A/B - sensitisation, 6.6A - mutagen, 6.7A/B - carcinogen, 6.8A/B – reproductive/developmental & 1% for 6.6B, 6.9A/B – target organ]
- Notification of a new chemical component in accordance with Schedule 1 of the Group Standards will be required at the time the substance containing the new chemical is first imported or manufactured in New Zealand.

3.2 Exemptions

- Impurities and by-products will not be included on NZIoC. [C]
- Manufactured articles that contain a hazardous substance (other than an explosive substance) are not considered hazardous substances under the HSNO Act and are, therefore, not required to be notified. [C]
- Exceptions to what needs to be notified include: [C]
 - concentration/s of component/s less than the mixture cut-off values unless there are hazardous property reasons to notify the component/s. For example, CAS 263403305, 1,2-Benzisothiazol-2(3H)-one (BIT), which is a sensitizer at concentrations as low as 0.05% compared to the standard cut-off of 0.1%.
 - new fragrance materials for inclusion under a Food Additives and Fragrance Materials Group Standard
 - components of cosmetic products covered under the Cosmetics Group Standard
 - chemicals held under exempt laboratory status. [application for approval is still necessary, see Article 30–33, D]
 - hazardous substance required for use in an emergency, including using agricultural compound or medicine in special emergency. [application for approval is still necessary, see Article 46–49, D]
- While notification of new chemicals which fall under these exceptions is not a requirement, any chemicals that are notified to the EPA will be added to the NZIoC.

or water where the temperature or pressure has been artificially increased or decreased) generates a substance with any 1 or more of the properties specific in paragraph (a) of this definition. [C] Hazardous substances include petrol, solvents, explosives, industrial chemicals, fireworks, agrichemicals, household cleaners and cosmetics.

New Zealand adopted GHS 7 on 30 April 2021 (<https://www.epa.govt.nz/industry-areas/hazardous-substances/new-zealands-new-hazard-classification-system/>), with the following obligations:

- Substances with an individual approval issued after 30 April 2021 must comply with these three notices immediately.
- Individual approvals issued before 30 April 2021 have a four-year transitional period, through to 30 April 2025, to comply with the updated labelling, safety data sheets and packaging notices.
- Substances managed under a group standard must also comply with the labelling, safety data sheet and packaging notices by 30 April 2025, regardless of when the substance was imported into or manufactured in New Zealand.

- Note that notification of single component chemical products is not allowed for most Group Standards under clause 4 (Scope of Group Standard). The definition of single component chemical product has the same meaning as the definition of chemical in the Group Standards.

4. Initial data requirements [C]

- the name of the substance
- the HSNO (Hazardous Substances and New Organisms Act) approval number and/or title of the Group Standard¹⁴¹ under which the substance has a deemed approval
- the name and CAS number of the chemical not listed on the NZIoC that is present in the substance
- the concentration of that chemical in the substance
- the hazardous properties of the chemical, including the provision of the relevant hazard data used to assign the substance to the Group Standard¹⁴²
- the proposed use of the substance

Note

- the notification process is not designed to provide enough information for a new chemical component to be fully assessed, classified and given an approval.
- If the notifier does not have any hazard data for the new chemical component, they will need to submit a Status of Substance request to the Agency for informal advice on the hazards of the substance. [B]
- Where the importer/manufacturer does not have access to the full compositional information for a product, provisions for third party notification can be provided. [B]
- Where the third party has all the relevant information, they can notify on behalf of a New Zealand supplier. [B]

5. Data updates by companies (and others)¹⁴³

- Anyone, including the EPA, can apply to have an approved hazardous substance reviewed for reassessment.
 - In a first step, an applicant may show that there are grounds because
 - There is significant new information about the effects of the chemical
 - There has been a significant change in the chemical's use and quantity
 - There is an alternative
 - Or as a consequence of changes to the Health and Safety at Work Act.
 - If grounds exist, an applicant may apply for reassessment, "modified" or "full". A modified reassessment can only assess a specific aspect of the approval.

¹⁴¹ Group standards are approvals for a group of hazardous substances of a similar nature, type or use. Most domestic and workplace chemicals (except for pesticides, timber treatment chemicals and vertebrate toxic agents) are approved under group standards. The substances within a Group Standard are covered by one set of conditions, which state how they can be used and how to manage the related risks. Different types of products with different uses can be approved together under a single group standard. For example, the aerosol Group Standards include aerosol paints and aerosol cleaners. Each Group Standard contains a condition that requires notification to the EPA of any new chemical present in products approved under that standard. [C]

¹⁴² Hazard information of the component is required for notification to show that the hazards associated with the new chemical component have been assessed by the notifier and have been taken into account when the product has been classified. **There are no criteria for acceptability of hazard data provided through the notification process.** [C]

¹⁴³ <https://www.epa.govt.nz/industry-areas/hazardous-substances/chemical-reassessment-programme/apply/>

- The reassessment considers issues such as manufacture and import volumes, use and application information, environmental exposure mitigation measures, scientific and technical information, cultural impacts, and the existence of alternatives.
- Anyone can also apply for amendments to correct a minor or technical error in the existing approval of a substance (if it would not result in a different decision about the substance or affect the way the risk assessment was approached), or involve minor changes to the approval (if it would not create any changes to the risk of using the chemical after applying the controls; this type of amendment would also not change the financial costs of complying with the approval), including
 - correcting typographical or drafting errors
 - adjusting existing controls to make them more practical, workable or enforceable
 - removing inconsistencies between the decision and the controls
 - correcting information that was inadvertently overlooked or misinterpreted at the time the decision was made - providing it does not lead to a change in the way the controls are applied
 - minor changes to controls that are considered reasonably insignificant or unnoticeable changes to controls in response to new technology or new information becoming available
 - changes to approvals to provide consistency with other approvals.
 - To apply for a more extensive change, then one must apply for grounds for reassessment.
- Anyone can apply to have an existing group standard amended to reflect industry changes or to incorporate additional products. Sometimes applications come from within the EPA.¹⁴⁴

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

- *Where the Authority considers that an applicant is able to provide further relevant information, the Authority may, by written notice given to the applicant not later than 10 working days after the receipt of the application, require the applicant to supply such further information relating to the application as is specified in the notice. [D]*
- *Where the applicant fails to comply with any request ... within 1 year after the date of the request, the application shall lapse. [D]*

reassessment¹⁴⁵

- The EPA may notify certain parties when they receive a reassessment application. These people will be given the opportunity to make a submission about the application. The general public will be notified when the EPA receive an application for a full reassessment. For modified reassessments (assessing only a specific aspect of the approval), the EPA will decide whether publication notification is needed, or not. If a modified reassessment is not publicly notified, the EPA will consult with people who may be affected by the reassessment.

Amendment of existing group standards¹⁴⁶

- Applications to amend group are publicly notified. This means that submissions from the public and interested parties are sought before a final decision is made by the EPA decision-making committee.

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)¹⁴⁷

¹⁴⁴ <https://www.epa.govt.nz/industry-areas/hazardous-substances/group-standards/applying-for-a-group-standard-amendment/>; the application is to be made in consultation with the EPA.

¹⁴⁵ <https://www.epa.govt.nz/industry-areas/hazardous-substances/chemical-reassessment-programme/apply/>

¹⁴⁶ <https://www.epa.govt.nz/industry-areas/hazardous-substances/group-standards/applying-for-a-group-standard-amendment/>

¹⁴⁷ Time limits can be found in Article 59 of [D].

After considering any application for approval [D]

- *The Authority may approve a hazardous substance [making a **rapid assessment**¹⁴⁸ of the adverse effects of importing or manufacturing the substance] if the Authority is satisfied that*
 - *A substance having a similar composition and similar hazardous properties has been approved, or*
 - *The substance has 1 or more hazardous properties and each hazardous property has the least degree of hazard for that property, or*
 - *The substance has been formulated so that 1 or more of its hazardous properties has a lesser degree of hazard than any substance that has been approved under this Act.*
- *Otherwise, the Authority may, in its discretion,*
 - *Approve/Decline the application if, after taking into account*
 - *Any controls which may be imposed on the substance, and*
 - *All effects of the substance during the life cycle of that substances, and*
 - *The likely effects of the substance being unavailable, the positive effects of the substance outweigh the adverse effects*
 - *Decline the application if insufficient information is available to enable the Authority to determine the adverse effects of the substance*

In practice

- *The EPA will review if the hazardous properties of the new chemical meet the conditions specified under the Group Standard selected ... [The EPA] aims to provide notification confirmation within 40 working days of the EPA formally receiving the notification. The new chemical is considered to be notified upon receipt of a confirmation letter from the EPA. [C]*
 - *If a new hazardous substance being considered for approval fits the conditions of an existing group standard, it is automatically deemed an approved substance.¹⁴⁹*
- *The new chemical information will be sent to CAS for verification of the CAS number. Subject to verification, it will be added to the NZIoC and made publicly accessible on the website (if non-confidential). If there are any issues with CAS verification, the notifier will be contacted. [C]*
- *Under either individual or Group Standard approvals, some chemicals have controls or conditions placing restrictions on their use. These restrictions will be noted on the NZIoC. Examples include (1) veterinary medicine may not be used for any purpose other than as a component in a formulated veterinary medicine; (2) POPs - Lindane may not be used for any purpose other than (a) for research and development; or (b) as an ingredient in the manufacture of a medicated product for use on humans. [C]*
- *Under a Group Standard approval, a new CMR can only be added to the NZIoC, if (a) the new CMR is used to completely replace an existing CMR in the substance, and (b) the new CMR has a lower hazard classification than the existing CMR. [C]*

Reassessment – It is a two-step process:¹⁵⁰

¹⁴⁸ Some substances can be processed under a "rapid assessment" route. If a substance only has minor risks (or similar substances meeting defined thresholds & rules) and requires minimal assessment. For others, it requires a standard assessment, including three sub-categories: A. controlled use (low hazard and/or risk); B. moderate hazard, general release; C. high hazard and/or widespread release

¹⁴⁹ <https://www.epa.govt.nz/industry-areas/hazardous-substances/group-standards/types-of-group-standards/>

¹⁵⁰ <https://www.epa.govt.nz/industry-areas/hazardous-substances/chemical-reassessment-programme/about/>

- In a first step, the application that the EPA receives, as well as EPA's own research and analysis, is used by a sub-group of HSNO Committee to decide if there are grounds for reassessment.¹⁵¹
- In a second step, the EPA will work with an applicant to ensure all required information is received before progressing with an application.
- The decision is made by a two- or three-person decision-making committee, a sub-group of the HSNO Committee, including (1) increase or change the controls, or rules, around the chemical's use; (2) ban the chemical; (3) make no change to the existing approval.
- The EPA use a screening tool, called FRCaST, that evaluates chemicals' potential risks to human health and the environment. The EPA have screened hundreds of chemicals using the tool. For the chemicals screened, the EPA decides which ones to add to the Priority Chemicals List that needs further review and scrutiny.¹⁵²

8. Data submission format

- *using the HSC14 Application Form for Notification of New Chemical Components Approved under Group Standards. Information on the hazardous properties of the "new chemical component" can be supplied in the form of a Safety Data Sheet. [C]*

9. Data confidentiality [C]

- *NZIoC consists solely of a list of chemicals and there is no linkage to commercial or proprietary products which contain these chemicals and components. The EPA acknowledges that, in some circumstances, notifiers may wish to keep some information confidential for reasons of commercial sensitivity. There can be a conflict between a notifier's need for confidentiality and the objective of providing for full and informed public participation in the operation of HSNO Act. However, to the extent that it is legally able to do so, the EPA will treat information provided by that notifier which is classified as commercially confidential. Where supporting data is provided, the EPA will recognise confidential listings on other international inventories. The EPA will, however, rely on the person providing proposed confidential information, to identify it as such and to justify this position.*
- *Confidential information for these purposes is primarily information which may be withheld under the Official Information Act, in particular, section 9(2)(b) which provides a good reason for withholding information where it is necessary to ""protection information where making available of the information (1) would disclose a trade secret; or (2) would be likely unreasonably to prejudice the commercial position of the person who supplied or who is the subject of the information.*
- *In addition to the Official Information Act, information may be protected by virtue of the interaction of HSNO with other Acts. For example, in applications for an innovative agricultural compound under Part 6 of the ACVM Act 1997 or for an innovative medicine under the Medicines Act 1981, the relevant confidentiality provisions of those Acts will apply to the EPA as provided for in section 55 of the HSNO Act.*
- *For confidentiality reasons, it is possible that a chemical may not have a CAS number. When notifying a chemical with no CAS number, one needs to provide a proper chemical name, and where this information is required to be kept confidential, one needs to demonstrate good grounds for this. These*

¹⁵¹ Hazardous Substance Risk Assessment Methodology guide:

<https://www.epa.govt.nz/assets/Uploads/Documents/Hazardous-Substances/Risk-Assessment-methodology/Risk-Assessment-Methodology-for-Hazardous-Substances-How-to-assess-the-risk-cost-and-benefit-of-new-hazardous-substances-for-use-in-New-Zealand-v2.docx>

¹⁵² <https://www.epa.govt.nz/industry-areas/hazardous-substances/chemical-reassessment-programme/priority-chemicals-list/>

chemicals will be verified as not currently having a CAS number before they are added to the confidential or non-confidential section of the NZIoC.

10. Data that are published publicly

- Online & offline versions of NZIoC
 - chemical name (CAS name)
 - CASRN
 - synonyms or associated names (including the gazetted name where relevant, any known common name and the name supplied by the notification process, if it is a legitimate name. Other registry numbers and names may be included where this is appropriate to the class of chemical. Trade names will not be included) [not on offline version]
 - approval status
 - restrictions/exclusions
 - date added to NZIoC [not on offline version]
- *All other information supplied on the notification form will be stored in a confidential file. In addition, a confidential section will be maintained on the NZIoC ... Requests for information under the Official Information Act may require the EPA to release information to other parties. [C]*

11. Information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.17 Philippine Inventory of Chemicals and Chemical Substances (PICCS)

Last update: 7 June 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. PICCS: https://chemical.emb.gov.ph/?page_id=138; https://chemical.emb.gov.ph/?page_id=121
(relevant laws and policies)
- B. Pre-manufacture and pre-importation notification (PMPIN): http://chemical.emb.gov.ph/?page_id=135
- C. Data Requirements For Pre-Manufacture and Pre-Importation Notification (PMPIN) Procedures (2020): <http://chemical.emb.gov.ph/?p=581>
- D. Polymers and polymer of low concern (PLC) exemption from the pre-manufacture and pre-importation notification (PMPIN) process (2019): <https://chemical.emb.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/DAO201918Polymer.pdf>
- E. Guidelines on small quantity importation under Republic act 6969 and its implementation rules and regulations (2003): <https://chemical.emb.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/EMB-MEMO-2003-SQI.pdf>
- F. Implementing rules and regulations of Republic Act 6969 (1992): <https://chemical.emb.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/DAO-1992-29-IRR-of-6969.pdf>

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory [A]

- **Distinction between new vs. existing chemicals:** PICCS is a list of all existing chemicals and chemical substances used, imported, distributed, processed, manufactured, stored, exported, treated or transported in the Philippines. The chemicals and chemical substances in the inventory were nominated by the industries themselves. Manufacturers and importers need not notify and secure clearance from DENR-EMB before they manufacture or import chemicals included in PICCS; provided that these chemicals are not in the Priority Chemicals List (PCL) and not are subject to the Revised Chemical Control Order (CCO). Chemicals and chemical substances not included in PICCS cannot be manufactured or imported unless the proponent follows the PMPIN notification assessment process as discussed in the subsequent sections of this manual.
 - * Fuel additives are required to be reviewed under Republic Act 8749, the Clean Air Act over if the chemical ingredients are already in PICCS.
- After receipt of the Notice of Commencement, the new chemical shall be listed in the public PICCS after a year, unless requested for Confidential Business Information. [C]
- The PICCS was published by DENR-EMB in 1995 and subsequently PICCS updates were published in 2000, 2002, 2005, 2008, 2011, 2013, 2015, 2017, 2020 and 2021. [A]

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligation to notify [F]

After 31 December 1993, a chemical substance which is not included in the PICCS shall be considered as new chemical substance. No person shall use, store, transport, import, sell, distribute, manufacture, or process a new chemical substance unless permitted by the Department. Permit shall be granted under the following conditions: a. the Department must be notified of the intention to do so at least one hundred and eighty (180) days before commencing such activity; and b. the Department shall be provided with [requested] information.

3.2 Exemptions

- **Exemption to PICCS:**
 - Non-chemical substances [A]
 - Naturally occurring substances [A]

- Mixtures (the individual components are the ones to be checked for inclusion in PICCS, not the mixture itself) [A]
- Radioactive substances, pesticides, drugs, foodstuffs, and consumer products that are regulated by other laws in the Philippines [A, F]
- By-products (Wastes) [A]
- Articles [C]
- Those that are reaction intermediates which do not leave the closed production system or undergo intermediate storage during the reaction process [F]
- Those to be produced or used in small quantities solely for experimental or research and development purposes [F]
- Certain polymers¹⁵³ and polymers of low concern¹⁵⁴ [D]

Criteria for polymer exemption from PMPIN process – meet any of the following criteria:

- (1) All of its monomers must be listed in the PICCS.
- (2) Polymers containing monomers and other reactants (including crosslinking, chain transfer agents, and post polymerization reactants) not in the PICCS added at quantities less than 2 percent (by weight).
- (3) A new polymer if two or more of the top (top by weight) monomers are included in the definition of another polymer already in PICCS.
- (4) The PLC shall fall into one of the conditions: (a) polymers that have number average molecular weight (NAMW)¹⁵⁵ equal to or greater than 10,000 Da, less than 5% of oligomers with MW lower than 1000 Da and less than 2% of oligomers with MW lower than 500 Da, and for cationic polymers, the FGEW¹⁵⁶ should be greater than 5,000 Da. (b) NAMW equal to or greater than 1000 Da and less than 10,000 Da, less than 25% of oligomers with MW lower than 1000 Da and less than 10% of oligomers with MW lower than 500 Da, and no reactive functional group (RFGs)¹⁵⁷ in excess of the levels of 2% by weight.

- **Exemption to the PICCS updating** [A]:

¹⁵³ **Polymer:** (1) the same as OECD definition of polymers; (2) is a substance composed of more than 50% of molecules containing a sequence of at least three monomer units covalently bound to at least one other monomer unit or other reactant; (3) has molecules distributed over a range of MW; and (4) has no single MW molecule reaching 50% (w/w) of total molecules. [D]

¹⁵⁴ **Polymer of Low Concern (PLC):** (a) must meet the definition of polymers; (b) must meet criteria [4 above]; and (c) must not be unstable, degradable, decompose, or depolymerize. [D]

¹⁵⁵ **NAMW:** as the arithmetic mean average of the molecular weight of all the molecules in a polymer, not taking into account unreacted monomers and other reactants but must include oligomers. [D]

¹⁵⁶ **FGEW:** functional group equivalent weight, as the ratio of the [NAMW] to the number of functional groups in the polymer. It is the weight of a polymer that contains one formula weight of the functional group. [D]

¹⁵⁷ **RFG:** an atom or associated group of atoms in a chemical substance that is intended or can be reasonably anticipated to undergo facile chemical reaction. RFG are categorized into low-concern (that may be used without limits; carboxylic acids, aliphatic hydroxyls, olefins – unconjugated or unactivated, blocked isocyanates including ketoximes, thiols, nitriles – unconjugated, halogens except active e.g. benzylic or allylic), medium concern (that has a combined (total) reactive group equivalent weight or FGEW greater than or equal to 1000 Da; acid halides, acid anhydrides, aldehydes, alkoxysilanes – alkyl >C2, allyl ethers, conjugated olefins, cyanates, epoxides, hemiacetals, hydroxymethylamides, imines, methylolamides, methylolamines, methylolureas, unsubstituted position ortho- or para- to phenolic hydroxyl) and high concern (that has a combined (total) reactive group equivalent weight or FGEW greater than or equal to 5000 Da; acrylates – pendant, alkoxysilanes – alkyl = C1 or C2, amines, aziridines, carbodiimides, halosilanes, hydrazines, isocyanates, isothiocyanates, α and β -Lactones, methacrylates – pendant, vinyl sulfones; if a RFG is not explicitly listed as low, medium or high concern, one must assume it is high concern with FGEW \geq 5000). [D]

- Small-quantity chemicals manufactured or distributed (not imported) for market test and research and development in quantities less than 1,000 kg per year (for SQI¹⁵⁸ Application)

4. Initial data requirements

Until 31 December 1993, a person shall submit a list of **existing chemical substances**, containing the minimum data (chemical names, trade name or names, chemical structure, CAS number, anticipated volume in cubic meters, or weight in tonnes per annum of chemicals being nominated, nominating person contact) or more. [F]

There are two kinds of PMPIN forms for notification [C]:

- **Abbreviated Form:** *for a new chemical already listed in either of the chemical inventories of US, EU, Australia, Japan, Canada and/or Korea.*
 - *a duly accomplished and notarized Abbreviated Form*
 - *a Material Safety Data Sheet (MSDS)/Safety Data Sheet (SDS) of the new chemical*
 - *scientific literatures, reports or tests for physico-chemical, toxicological, and environmental properties compliant with **Good Laboratory Practices (GLP)**.*
- **Detailed Form:** *those not applicable with Abbreviated Form.*
 - *a duly accomplished and notarized Detailed Form*
 - *a Material Safety Data Sheet (MSDS)/Safety Data Sheet (SDS) of the new chemical*
 - *tests for physico-chemical, toxicological, and environmental properties compliant with **Good Laboratory Practices (GLP)**.*

The following specific requirements for each application should be written on the notarized application forms.

- **Application details:**
 - *Name and address of the notifier;*
 - *Proper chemical name/CAS registered chemical name/IUPAC name*
 - *CAS RN (if available)*
 - *Chemical and molecular structure*
 - *Trade name*
 - *Anticipated weight in kilogram per annum of the chemical substance being imported or manufactured by the notifier*
 - *100% composition of product with complete CAS RN; wherein the new chemical is a component of the product being imported*
 - *Intended use of the chemical*
- **Physicochemical properties:**
 - *Appearance and color*
 - *Odor*
 - *Boiling point/Range*
 - *Melting point/Range*
 - *Specific gravity/Density*
 - *Vapor pressure*
 - *Water/octanol partition coefficient*
 - *Flammability*
 - *Solubility in water and other solvents*
 - *Known stability and incompatibilities.*

¹⁵⁸ SQI: *as the amount of “new chemical substance” as defined in RA 6969 which shall not exceed 1000 kg/yr. as: a) pure chemical substance or b) component, in percentage by weight, of a product, mixture, etc. [E]*

- **Toxicological and environmental/ecological properties:**
 - Acute oral and dermal toxicities in terms of Lethal Dose 50 (LD50)
 - Acute inhalation toxicity in terms of Lethal Concentration 50 (LC50)
 - Chronic toxicity
 - Irritation on skin and eyes
 - Respiratory/skin sensitization
 - Carcinogenic, teratogenic and mutagenic properties
 - Acute toxicities for either fish, invertebrates and/or algae in terms of LC50/EC/50
 - Degradability
 - Bioaccumulation and persistence.
- For Detailed application, the physicochemical, toxicological and environmental/ecological properties should be **accompanied with laboratory tests**.
- If the notifier is **unable to supply information** for application(s) due to physicochemical-based constraints of the chemical itself, the notifier shall submit a position paper on why the information on the chemical cannot possibly be supplied, with references to published and peer-reviewed articles, journals and books. This also applies to given information based on “similar substances”. The validity shall be evaluated by the Chemical Review Committee (CRC), if needed.

Requirements for application of polymer exemption from PMPIN process [D], including

- Duly notarized and accomplished Polymer Exemption Form.
- Polymer information like specific chemical name, chemical structure, CAS number (if available), use/s of the polymer.
- [SDS] for the polymer alone or the mixture/product where the polymer is part of the ingredients.
- 100% composition of the polymer including CAS numbers of monomers and other reactants.
- Data requirements that show proof that the polymer meets any of the conditions i.e., Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC) Data, IR Spectroscopy, etc.
- Request for Confidential Business Information through an official letter with justification.

Applicants for **SQI** of a new chemical substance shall be required to submit or undertake the following [E]:

- identify the new chemical substance by chemical name, CAS number and structure;
- indicate the percentage of the new substance in the product/mixture;
- list unit weight (in kg) in which the product/mixture shall be supplied;
- submit information on the annual amount (kg) of the product/mixture containing the new substance.

5. Data updates by companies

PMPIN:

- The company shall submit a **Notice of Commencement (NOC)** after the first **importation** of the new chemical. Submission shall include Filled-up NOC Form, Bill of Lading/Airway Bill/Seaway Bill, Import Entry Tax Declaration, signed PMPIN Certificate, and Proforma Invoice or Commercial Invoice. The product name or the new chemical must be reflected in the document of entry. Notifier will be invited every year for clarification and updates. [C]

In the case of **SQI** (general exemption from the PICCS updating, see above) [E],

- monitor and assure that import of the new chemical does not exceed the approved amount;
- keep document records of the importation within the approved period and submit the same within 60 days after arrival of shipment. An annual report shall be submitted to EMB Central Office not later than 15 days after the end of the Calendar year
- Submit PMPIN if amount exceeds SQI requirements.

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

Priority Chemical List [F] - the Department may

- *determine which chemical substance from the chemical inventory should be included, deleted, or excluded from the Priority Chemicals List.*
- *require information from any person for the purpose of assessing the public and environmental risk posed by the use, storage, manufacture, import, process or transport of the priority chemicals.*

Chemicals Subject to Testing [F]

- *Testing shall be required in all cases where:*
 - *There is a reason to believe that the chemical substances or mixture may present an unreasonable risk to health or the environment or there may be substantial human or environmental exposure thereto;*
 - *There are insufficient data and experience for determining or predicting the health and environmental effects of the chemical substance or mixture; and*
 - *The testing of the chemical substance or mixture is necessary to develop such data.*
- *The manufacturers, processors or importers shall shoulder the costs of testing the chemical substance or mixture that will be manufactured, processed, or imported.*

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

PMPIN

- *For applications for new chemicals under the **Detailed Form**, a Chemical Review Committee shall be invited to evaluate the new chemicals. This technical working group shall include but not limited to representatives of the **academe** and other regulatory agencies. [C, F]*
- *Assessment of the new chemical shall be 90 working days for Abbreviated Form and 120 working days for Detailed Form. After assessment of the new chemical, the Department shall issue a PMPIN Compliance Certificate, or a letter. A letter shall be issued on the basis of non-compliance of the notifier to the information required by the Department. After 3 months of non-compliance, reapplication will be needed. [C]*
- *Any falsification of information or violation of the requirements specified in this Order shall subject the person(s) liable thereof to the applicable administrative and criminal sanctions as provided for under Section 41 and 43 of DAO 92-29. [C]*

Polymer exemption [D]

- *The Bureau shall process the polymer exemption application within twenty (20) working days from receipt of the complete documentary requirements. The exempted polymer will not be listed in the PICCS.*
- *Any misrepresentation, misinformation, misstatement, fabrication and falsification of submitted information will automatically cause the issuance of the polymer exemption to be revoked and the applicant shall be subjected to the penalty provision.*

SQI [E] – The EMB Regional Office shall

- *Notify the applicant of its approval within twenty (20) working days from date of receipt of the application*
- *Provide the Bureau of Customs (BoC) a copy of the SQI*
- *Reserve the right to request of compliance during the approval period.*
- *Monitor that the amount of the new chemical does not exceed 1,000 kg/yr*
- *Submit a quarterly report to the EMB Central Office on issuance of [SQI] clearances.*

Chemical Control Orders¹⁵⁹ [F]

- *If the Department has determined that the use, storage, transport, process, manufacture, import or export of any new substance or a priority chemical poses an unreasonable risk or hazard to public health or the environment, the Department, may, by order published in the Official Gazette or any newspaper or general circulation:*
 - *a. prohibit the use, manufacture, import, export, transport, process, storage, possession or sale of the chemical substance;*
 - *b. limit the use, manufacture, import, export, transport, process, storage, possession or sale of the chemical substances; or*
 - *c. place such controls or conditions on the use, manufacture, import, export, transport, process, storage, possession or sale of the chemical substance to abate or minimize risks or hazards posed by the chemical substances on public health and environment.*

8. Data submission format

All PMPIN applications shall be applied to the Online Permitting and Monitoring System (OPMS) website. [C]

9. Data confidentiality

The confidentiality of information shall be consistent with Section 40 of DAO 92-99. The following are additional procedures/information required for notifications where certain information [is] requested to be considered confidential by the notifier or their supplier, due to confidential information regarding trade secrets. The PMPIN Certificate to be issued shall only indicated the name of the product they will be importing. [C]

- *In the case of importation of a new chemical in a mixture, the company shall submit an updated and adequate [MSDS/SDS] of the product where the new chemical is a component.*
- *The company shall submit 100% composition of the product to be imported, including all the CAS RN of the components of the product. The physicochemical, toxicological and environmental properties of the new chemical shall also be submitted. In case of confidentiality of the information, the supplier or manufacturer may submit a duly accomplished Confidential Business Information Form along with the data subject to requirements to the Bureau by mail or email at chemicals@emb.gov.ph and corresponding justification.*

DAO 1992-29, Section 40 Confidentiality of Information [A]

¹⁵⁹ Hazardous Substances are substances which present either:

- a) Short-term acute hazards such as acute toxicity by ingestion, inhalation or skin absorption, corrosivity, or other skin or eye contact hazard or the risk of fire or explosion;
- b) Long-term environmental hazards, including chronic toxicity upon repeated exposure, carcinogenicity (which may in some case result from acute exposure but with a long latent period, resistance to detoxification process such as biodegradation, the potential to pollute underground or surface waters, or aesthetically objectionable properties such as offensive odors.

Note: GHS has been adopted in the Philippines (version 4th; <https://chemical.emb.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/DAO-2015-011-GUIDANCE-MANUAL.pdf>) with the following implementation schedule (<https://chemical.emb.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/DAO-2015-09-Implementation-of-GHS.pdf>): 2016 - single substances and compounds covered under CCO and PCL chemicals initially listed; 2017 – high volume toxic chemicals (https://chemical.emb.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/MC-2017-010_GUIDELINES-IN-THE-IMPLEMENTATION-OF-GHS-CLASSIFICATION-AND-LABELLING-REQUIREMENTS-FOR-HVCs.pdf); 2018 – toxic chemicals under the IATA and IMDG list of dangerous goods; and 2019 – mixtures. Readers may check this website for possible updates: <https://chemical.emb.gov.ph/?p=196>.

- 40(2) *The Department of Environment and Natural Resources may consider a record, report of information or particular person thereof confidential and may not be made public when such would divulge trade secrets, or sales figures or methods production or processes unique to such manufacturer, processor or distributor or would otherwise tend to affect adversely the competitive position of such manufacturer, processor or distributor,*
- 40(3) *No disclosure of any information shall be done subject to Sections 40(1) and 40(2) except –*
 - *a. where there is written consent provided the person who requested confidentiality under Section 40(1);*
 - *b. under an agreement, convention or treaty between the government of the Philippines and other foreign nations provided that the foreign nation undertakes to keep the information confidential;*
 - *c. under an agreement between the Department and other statutory bodies and local authorities provided that the information is required to fulfill their obligations and provided that they agree to keep the information confidential;*
 - *d. under formal instruction of a competent court of law;*
 - *e. to a physician or prescribed medical professional who request the information for the purpose of making a medical diagnosis of, or rendering medical treatment to, a person in an emergency and who agrees, in writing to keep the information confidential; or*
 - *f. where the department certifies that the disclosure of the information is in the interest of public health and safety or protection of the environment.*
- *Where practical, the person who takes the request for confidentiality under Section 40(1) shall be notified in writing prior or as soon as possible to the intention of disclosure of information under Section 40(3)*

In the case of **SQI [E]** - *The EMB Regional Office shall*

- *Ensure that all information submitted on [SQI] of chemicals under RA 6969 are held confidential and shall be disclosed only upon approval by the EMB Director.*

10. Data that are published publicly [A]

CASRN¹⁶⁰ and chemical names (CAS Registry Index names or common name)

Section 12. of RA6969 Public Access to Records, Reports or Notification.

- *The public shall have access to records, reports, or information concerning chemical substances and mixtures including safety data submitted, data on emission or discharge into the environment, and such documents shall be available for inspection or reproduction during normal business hours except that the Department of Environment and Natural Resources may consider a record, report or information or particular portions thereof confidential and may not be made public when such would divulge trade secrets, production or sales figures or methods, production or processes unique to such manufacturer, processor or distributor, or would otherwise tend to affect adversely the competitive position of such manufacturer, processor or distributor. The Department of Environment and Natural Resources, however, may release information subject to claim of confidentiality to a medical research or scientific institution where the information is needed for the purpose of medical diagnosis or treatment of a person exposed to the chemical substance or mixture.*

11. International information exchange and sharing – N.A.

¹⁶⁰ *All these new chemicals are submitted for verification of their CAS Registry Name and CAS Registry No. with the Chemical Abstract Office in the USA. Any correction is consulted with the notifier of the chemical [A]*

S1.18 Russian Register of Potentially Hazardous Chemical and Biological Substances (RPOHV)

Last update: 18 June 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. homepage: <http://www.rpohv.ru/lang/en/> (English version)
- B. Reihlen et al. 2010. *The Russian system of chemicals management*. Published by Baltic Environmental Forum Group:
https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/capchemru_chemmgntru_final.pdf [Note: some information in this document may be outdated.]
- C. Krueger et al. 2018. *National chemicals registers and inventories: benefits and approaches to development*. Published by World Health Organization.
https://www.euro.who.int/_data/assets/pdf_file/0018/361701/9789289052948-eng.pdf

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

- *In accordance with the Russian Federation Law No 52-FZ of 30/03/1999 on “Sanitary and Epidemiological Well-being of the Population” (Art. 43 concerning state registration of substances and products) and with the RF Government’s Decree about “State Registration of Potentially Hazardous Chemical and Biological Substances” No 869 of 12/11/1002, in the Russian Federation a mandatory state registration of potentially hazardous chemical and biological substances has been implemented in order to prevent their adverse effect on human health and the environment. [A]*
- *It contains information about chemical compounds which passed state registration. [A]*
- *Production, import and use of unregistered substances is prohibited. [B]*
- *Since 1992 approximately 3,400 substances have been registered and are contained in a respective registration database. However, about 15,000 substances have been investigated prior to 1992, and those are considered as being registered as well. [B]*
- *Each substance needs to be registered only once and the registration costs have to be borne by the first registrant only. [B]*

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligation

- *All individual chemical and biological compounds produced and/or imported into Russia including those used as ingredients in the composition of end products. [A] In general, all substances are considered as “potentially hazardous substances”.*
- *Substances having in their composition by-products¹⁶¹ produced in the course of manufacturing or use are to be registered like individual substances. [A]*
- *All chemicals that are dangerous for human health during their production, use, transport and household use must be registered before they are placed on the Customs Union market. The same rules are applicable for chemical mixtures and products. New substances that are ingredients in mixtures are also subject to registration. [C]*

3.2 Exemptions

- *Pharmaceutical substances pesticides and other plant protection products, agricultural, and forestry growth regulators, there are, however, separate registration regimes (legislation) applying instead. [B]*

¹⁶¹ Legislation is not further specifying the meaning of this clause, i.e. does it requires registration of impurities or unintentionally produced substances. [B]

- *Substances used for the production of weapons or warfare agents are also exempted.* [B]

4. Initial data requirements

- *Companies having to register a substance have to provide information on its identity and other information for the preparation of documents.* [B]
 - *An organization which wants to market a chemical substance will contract an accredited organisation to carry out the assessment ... Once the assessment is done, the applicant presents the dossier to the [authority] to prepare the registration documentation.*
 - *The assessment and compilation of the respective documentation can be done by any accredited institution having access to accredited laboratories. The results of the assessment contain information on hazardous properties of a substance (test results from literature as well as newly performed studies, classification of substance into different hazard classes) and measures to ensure safe handling together with proposed environmental quality standards (MPCs)¹⁶². The data collection and assessment of a substance takes between 1 and 2 years.*
 - *This may include the conclusion that, based on the available information, no hygienic norm is necessary to ensure safe handling.*
 - *For a substance which shall also to be produced in Russia, the dossier must also include all technical documentation related to the production processes, e.g. standards, technical conditions ... technological instructions, product specifications, etc., and that all necessary approvals or permits are obtained.*
 - *For substances to be imported, the dossier must include copies of documents confirming their safety for human health, issued by authorities of the country of origin (MSDS). Moreover, the necessary label on the packaging (or confirmed design of it) must be presented in both cases.*

5. Data update by companies

- *The preparation of documents on the properties of substances under question and subject to state registration by the authority* [B]
- *The substance is registered for a certain term, usually for 3 years. Upon expiry of the certification term the registration procedure should be repeated. The renewal of the certification is justified based on scientific arguments, i.e. if new data is available, this should be taken into account in MPCs [maximum permissible concentrations] and they may need revision.* [B]

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators &

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

- *The procedure of the state registration includes* [B]
 - *The examination of documents submitted by applicants ... , including results of investigations, toxicological, hygienic and other assessments*
 - *The preparation of documents on the properties of substances under question and subject to state registration by the authority* [B]
 - *The issuing of state registration certificates*
- *After a substance assessment is completed, the dossier is given to competent authorities for evaluation and establishing MPCs.*

¹⁶² *The full procedure of assigning a MPC is not fully described in legislation: if the registrant proposes the MPCs in the documentation, should the MPC be assigned in the legislation by the competent authorities before or after the registration occurs. With hygienic norms it is not a major issue, as the authority confirming MPC and registration is the same.* [B]

- *The assessment of toxicological properties of substances for registration is done according to the provisions of the Hygienic Regulation GN 1.1701-98 "Hygienic criteria for rating the necessity for setting up MPCs and TSELs/ODU of harmful substances in the occupational air, the ambient air of residential areas and the water of water bodies hygienic norms", adopted in 1998 ... The scope of the assessment depends on the substance's physico-chemical properties, the level of toxicity to humans and other organisms, the production volume, the amount of people potentially being exposed, economic priority or importance [if there is economic pressure to use the substance, it is assessed if it is possible to assign MPC by express methods or to assign a temporary norm], presence/concentrations in different environmental compartments, stability and other parameters which may have relevance for defining impacts on human health.*
- *If data are already available (provided by registrant, available in literature or databases on substance properties, including foreign ones), they are used in the assessment. If information is missing, respective studies are conducted.*
- *The test methods of toxicological (for hygienic assessment of water bodies) and ecotoxicological parameters have repeatedly been stated to be similar with EU ones. Also laboratories performing testing have to be accredited (so far according to ISO 17025, GLP system is being still introduced in Russia). Still, the testing results might be difficult to compare (details given in Russian methodological guidelines were not compared with OECD testing guidelines).*
- *Endocrine disruption is not assessed according to the standard procedure. However, if there are indications of a hormone-like mode of action and or respective epidemiologic evidence, testing could be carried out.*
- *For extremely hazardous substances, belonging to hormones, cytostatic substances, allergens, and certain groups of antibiotics, which discharge to water bodies is prohibited, also no MPC is established. The issue could be considered as a basis to ban substances regarded as too dangerous for the Russian market. But this decision is not formalised and depends on the opinion of the assessor the substance.*
- *After having been successfully certified, the substance can be used in industrial production. Nevertheless, new substances¹⁶³ are subject to a clinical-hygienic probation period over one year. In the case that observations indicate damage to human health or the environment are caused by such substances, it is immediately reported and MPCs are amended correspondingly. [B]*
- *It is worthwhile to mention that if test results and product assessments indicate high risks, a temporary registration for two years is given and manufacturing or use of the substance is not prohibited (unless competent institutions have refused to assign MPCs due to extremely high risks). [B]*

8. Data submission format

On Paper [C]

9. Data confidentiality

- *Data on the amounts which are produced or imported are subject to confidentiality. [B]*
- *In accordance with the legislation, data on the effects of chemicals on human health and the environment are not considered confidential. Confidentiality issues are specified in contracts made between the registry and its customers. [C]*

¹⁶³ There is no legal definition of „new substance“, but according to the information received in expert workshops, substances placed on the market after 1992 should be considered as new ones. [B]

10. Data that are published publicly [A, B]

- Information on whether or not a substance is already registered can be obtained from the database or requested from the registering authority. On its homepage, the authority lists recently registered substances and substances of which the registration has expired.
- The database “Hazardous Substances” contains information about chemical compounds which have passed state registration.
 - Physical and chemical properties
 - Toxicity and hazards to humans and the environment
 - Hygienic and environmental standards
- *Information on registered chemicals is published in the Toxicological Bulletin issued by the registry. [C]*

11. International information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.19 EAEU Existing Chemical Substance Inventory

Last update: 11 August 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. TR EAEU 041/2017 Technical Regulations of the Eurasian Economic Union on the safety of chemical products: <http://docs.cntd.ru/document/456065181> ;https://docs.eaeunion.org/docs/en-us/01413938/cncd_18052017_19 (was due to enter into force on June 2, 2021, but will be postponed to at least November 30, 2022 as the secondary legislation is still under amendments¹⁶⁴ in accordance with the Letter No. 28726/13 dated 09.04.2021; in Russian);
Note that the text below is based on informal translation using DeepL.
- B. Consolidated list of chemical substances in Russia (public): <https://gisp.gov.ru/cheminv/pub/app/search/>;
- C. Global GHS Training Course – No.2 EAEU GHS features and EAEU-REACH by CIRS: http://www.cirs-reach.com/Uploads/file/20200713/1594624929_22306.pdf
- D. Druzhinina N. 2021. *Technical regulation of the Eurasian Economic Union <<on the Safety of Chemical Products>> (TR EAEU 041/2017)*: http://chemical-net.env.go.jp/pdf/20210204_Seminar1_Druzhinina_ENG.pdf
- E. *Updates on the Technical regulation of the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) “On the Safety of Chemical Products” – transmitted by the expert from the Russian Federation (UN/SCEGHS/37/INF.22)*: <https://unece.org/DAM/trans/doc/2019/dgac10c4/UN-SCEGHS-37-INF22e.pdf>
- F. Coordinating information center of CIS Member States on approximation of regulatory practices: https://www.ciscenter.org/en/Inventory_formation/faq/

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

- Will be valid for all EAEU member countries (Armenia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Russia). It will consist of national parts which are assigned to particular certification bodies in each country. [F]
- **New vs. existing:** Once the inventory is finalized, any new substances which are not listed on the inventory will require notification before they can be placed on the market of the Union. [D, E]
- *The Register is an informational resource containing data on the chemical substances and mixtures properties, including information on the prohibition, restriction, or permission to use it in the EAEU territory. It consists of the Inventory and Database.* [E]

3. Scope of the inventory

¹⁶⁴ Including (1) the procedure of formation and maintenance of the Union registry (with 8 Annexes): registry structure and stages of its formation, list of restricted substances (Annex 7) – agreement is not reached as of February 2021, the ability of use information from national and international databases, list of official information sources on chemicals (Annex 3), the ability to use alternative methods (read-across, grouping, QSAR) instead of testing, single window mode for submission of a set of documents, CBI protection, joint data submission for the permitting state registration; (2) the procedure for the notification of new substances (with 2 Annexes): the order of notification (required documents and timeframe), recommendations for completing a chemical safety report (Annex 2), the possibility of a phased submission of information regarding the new substance (part 1 of CSR + strategy for further testing), the ability to use information from databases (if available) and alternative methods [D]

3.1 Obligations

Scope of the TR: *All chemical products placed on the market of the Union customs territory as substance¹⁶⁵ and mixture¹⁶⁶. [D]*

- Identification of chemical products is carried out by the manufacturer or importer of these products. Identification includes: a) establishing the name of the chemical products; b) attributing chemical products to chemical substances or mixtures; c) establishment of an IUPAC name and a CAS number; d) determination of the chemical composition of the mixture with the identification of each identifiable component according to IUPAC name and CAS number (if available); e) determination of the presence of new chemicals in the composition of chemical products in concentrations greater than 0.1% (by weight); (f) classification of chemicals in chemical products;¹⁶⁷ (g) determination of the scope of application / use of the chemical products; (h) other necessary information [A]

Pre-registration/inventory phase (now)

- *All chemical substances as such or within the mixture that [a] company is releasing or just planning to release for Russian (or Union) market are subject of inventory. [F]*
 - *For chemical product released for Union's market as a chemical substance, [one needs] to do an inventory of the main component and all impurities and supplements presented in a concentration of more than 0.1% (by weight).*
 - *For mixtures, it is necessary to take into account all components presented in their composition in a concentration of more than 0.1% (by weight). In a case, if some substance is present in a concentration of less than 0.1%, but there is a probability of increasing of content, [such substance is recommended to be put into inventory, too].*

Notification of new substances

- *If a substance (individual or as a part of the mixture) is not included in the register of substances and mixtures of the Union, such substance is considered to be new to the EAEU market and shall undergo the notification procedure. [D]*

¹⁶⁵ *a chemical element and (or) its compounds in the natural state or obtained by any manufacturing process, including any additive necessary to preserve its stability and any impurity deriving from the process used, but excluding any solvent which may be separated without affecting the stability of the substance or changing its composition (chemical substance is the chemical product in which the percentage of the main component is equal to 80% or more by mass while the total content of impurities and/or additives is less than 20% by mass). [D]*

¹⁶⁶ *A mixture of solution of two or more substances in which they do not react with each other. [D]*

¹⁶⁷ *The chemical products exhibiting hazardous properties with regard to human and animal life and health include the following chemical products, which contain hazardous chemical substances and mixtures in amounts exceeding the concentration values specified in the standards included in the list of international and regional (interstate) standards, and in their absence – national (state) standards, as a result of which application on a voluntary basis compliance with the requirement of these technical regulations shall be observed: (a) acute toxicity, (b) causing corrosion and skin irritation, (c) causing serious damage (irritation) to the eyes, (d) having a sensitizing effect, (e) mutagens, (f) carcinogens, (g) affecting reproductive function, (h) possessing selective toxicity to individual organs (target organs) and/or systems of a living organism during a single and short-term exposure or during repeated and prolonged exposure, (i) posing a danger of aspiration, (j) PBT, (k) vPvB, (l) substance of equivalent concern to compounds such as endocrine disruptors. [A]*

Chemical products hazardous to the environment include which contain hazardous chemical substances and mixtures in amounts exceeding the concentration values specified in the standards included in the list of international and regional (interstate) standards, and in their absence – national (state) standards, as a result of which application on a voluntary basis compliance with the requirement of these technical regulations shall be observed: (a) destroying the ozone layer, (b) having acute and chronic toxicity to the aquatic environment, (c) bioaccumulation, (d) persistent, (e) having toxicity for soil. [A]

- It is the procedure for including information about new chemicals in the registry of chemical substances and mixtures of the Union. [A]

Conformity assessment / State registration¹⁶⁸ [A]

- 49. Chemical products shall be subject to conformity assessment prior to their release into circulation on the customs territory of the Union.
- 50. Assessment of compliance of chemical products with the requirements of this technical regulation shall be carried out in the forms: a) notifying state registration; b) permitting state registration.
- 53. Notifying state registration of chemical products shall be carried out if information on chemical products is included in the register of chemical substances and mixtures of the Union and one of the following requirements is met
 - Chemical products do not include banned or restricted chemical substances and mixtures included in the register of chemical substances and mixture of the Union
 - Chemical products contain restricted chemical substances and mixtures, information on which is included in the register of chemical substances and mixtures of the Union, in concentrations below the established limit content according to Annex 4¹⁶⁹
- Permitting state registration is carried out in respect of: (a) new chemical products; (b) chemical products, which contain restricted chemical substances and mixtures, information on which is included in the register of chemical substances and mixtures of the Union, in concentrations exceeding the limit content established in Annex 4 to this technical registration

3.2 Exemptions

List of exceptions provided in Annex 1 to TR [A; a list of chemical products on which the technical regulation does not apply] as follows [D]

- *Chemical products used in scientific research and development*
- *Minerals in their natural state of occurrence, as well as the following products, if it was not chemically modified: minerals, ores, ore concentrates, cement clinker, natural gas, liquefied natural gas, gas condensate, process gas and its components, oil dehydrated and desalted stable, associated gas, coal and coke*
- *Medical products and preparations for veterinary use*
- *Perfumes and cosmetics*
- *Chemical products serving as an ionizing radiation source*
- *Food products, dietary supplements and nutritional supplements, as well as ready-for-use feed for animals*
- *Products in articles which during circulation in the customs territory of the EAEU / Russian Federation do not change their chemical composition and which are not subject to decomposition or oxidation processes, and which do not form dusts, vapours and aerosols containing chemicals that are hazardous to the life and health of humans, animals or plants, the environment, or property*

¹⁶⁸ Deferred norm for state registration (draft decision, as of February 2021) [D]:

If an imported chemical product is a substance, start of state registration would be: >1000 t/yr (tonnage for one legal entity per year)—as soon as TR EAEU 041/2017 comes into force; 100–1000 t/yr—30 November 2024; 1–100 t/yr—30 November 2026; <1 t/yr—additional decision (must be resolved by 30 November 2028)

If an imported chemical product is a mixture, start of state registration would be: >1000 t/yr—30 November 2027; 100–1000 t/yr—30 November 2029; 10–100 t/yr—30 November 2031; <1 t/yr—additional decision (must be resolved by 30 November 2028)

¹⁶⁹ Carcinogen – class 1 and 2: 0.1 weight%; mutagens – class 1: 0.1 weight%, class 2: 1 weight%; reproductive toxicant – class 1 and 2: 0.1%; chronic aquatic toxicity – class 1: 1%. [A]

- *Wastes from the production and consumption of chemical products*
- *Chemical products that are subject to the procedure of **customs transit***

Additional exceptions [D]

- ***Preparative forms of pesticides** and associated processes of their manufacture, storage, transport, sale and disposal (see item 4 of Decision No. 19)*
- *Certain types of chemical products subject to **other (“vertical”) technical regulations** of the Union with respect to conformity assessment (note: hazard classification, SDS and labelling are still required) (see Article 1, item 3 of TR)*
 - e.g. TU CU 013/2011 on requirements for the motor gasoline and aviation motor gasoline, diesel and marine fuels, jet engine fuel and black oil fuel; TR CU 028/2012 on the safety of explosives on their basis; TR CU 030/2012 on requirements for lubricants, oils and special fluids; TR EAEU 036/2016 on requirements for liquefied petroleum gases for use as fuel; TR EAEU 039/2016 on the requirements for mineral fertilizers

4. Initial data requirements

Pre-registration/inventory stage (now) [E]

- *Provided information should contain above all identification numbers, synonyms¹⁷⁰ and GHS classification according to the Annex 1 to the order “On the procedure of formation and maintenance of the register”. [E]*
 - *All information about chemical substances is requested for the inventory without reference to the final product and the percentage in the composition, i.e. the supplier need to give a list of all the chemical substances in a single list. In addition, they do not need to duplicate the information, if several mixed products contain the same substance. [F]*
 - *For polymers, it is necessary to provide information on monomers, as well as on all additive components in accordance with the formulation (for example, plasticizers, polymerization activators, etc.) in an amount of more than 0.1%. Due to the high variety of polymers, notification of them is not applicable, and information about them is optional for the inventory. [F]*
 - *For UVCBs, one should determine them by the production technology, feedstock, typical content of components and definitive physicochemical parameters. [Companies] need to fill information on a substance of a complex and variable composition as a whole (without separation into components) with an indication of the CAS number assigned to it (if available). [F]*
 - *Application (scope of use) is providing on the substance in its pure form. [F]*
 - *For chemical substances in a composition of chemical products (components of a mixture) tonnage is not indicated (no need to recount it). [Companies] need to fill in the column with the phrase “as part of a mixture” (or “as part of a polymer” for monomers). For chemical substances provided to the Union market as a separate product, [companies] need to indicate the average production/import volume for the last three years. For those substances that [a] company plans to release in the future (to expand the product line), [companies] need to write the planned amount. This information is requested to assess the upcoming workload in the framework of state registration of chemical products under the TR EAEU 041/2017 and justify the need (or lack thereof) for the phased introduction of state registration depending on the tonnage. [F]*

¹⁷⁰ structural formula (preferably in the "InChI=" format) [C]

- The hazard classification is filling in for a chemical substance, and, in the case of mixtures, for each component of a mixture separately ... If there is no data on the results of the hazard classification of components, choose the “no data available” button. If [one wants] to provide a hazard classification of the components, [one needs] to collect all available data for each substance, including information from open sources. Hazard classification criteria are established by GOST 32419-2013¹⁷¹.
- Foreign companies exporting to Russia are asked to participate in Inventory development by the Only representative, authorized in the Russian Federation. [E]
 - There are no special requirements to the representative like sufficient knowledge in the practical handling of the substances as it is in REACH Regulation. [F]
- At the inventory stage ... the submission of information is free of charge and does not require the attaching of any documents confirming the fact of a substance circulation in the Russian Federation. [F]
- Those companies that for some reason has not been participated in the inventory and have realized that their substances are not in the Register after the entry force of the TR EAEU 041/2017, (and therefore they identified as new chemicals), can submit data in the Register within a deferred form: before June 2, 2023 companies have the right to submit information on a chemical substance for inclusion in the Register without a notification procedure, but with attaching of the documents that confirm the circulation of a chemical substance on the Union market before the effective data TR EAEU 041/2017. Confirming documents may include a supply agreement (an act of purchase and sale), consignment note, information on the presence of a chemical substance in the national list of chemicals of a Member state, etc. [F]

Notification of new substances

- 48. Information to be sent to the authorized body for the purpose of notification of new chemical substances shall include [A]:
 - a chemical safety report in accordance with the structure according to Annex 3
 - the name of the chemical according to the IUPAC nomenclature
 - the structural formula of the chemical
 - CASRN (if available)
 - data from instrumental analysis of the chemical
 - the degree of purity of the chemical
 - the intended use of the chemical
 - proposed methods of disposal (processing) of the chemical
 - the method of transportation of the chemical and measures to prevent and eliminate emergencies
 - analytical control methods
 - physical and chemical data of the chemical
 - data on the toxicity of the chemical
 - data on the ecotoxicity of the chemical
 - copies of the data (protocols) of studies (tests) of the chemical to determine its bioaccumulation, carcinogenicity, mutagenicity, toxicity, carried out in laboratories (centers) recognized as complying with the principles of good laboratory practice by the authorized body in accordance with the Federal Law “on accreditation in national accreditation system” and having the

¹⁷¹ As of August 2021, based on GHS rev. 4. Note that concentration limits not fully consistent with EU (e.g., 0.1% for both repro tox category 1 and 2 in Russia, while 0.3% and 3% are applied in EU). [A] At the moment all the national standards are undergoing a revision procedure in accordance with the 7th edition of the GHS recommendations. [E]

appropriate scope of accreditation for 2 years from the date of entry into force of this technical regulation.

Notifying state registration

- 54. For notifying state registration of chemical products with issuance of a certificate of notifying state registration of chemical products, the applicant shall submit the following documents to the authorized body [A]
 - Application for notification of state registration of chemical products according to the form in Annex 5
 - Safety data sheet, drawn up in accordance with paragraphs 36–43 of these technical regulations
 - Research (test) protocols conducted in testing (research) laboratories (centers), and (or) documents containing information obtained from official information sources. Research (test) protocols shall not be submitted for chemical products included in the register of chemical substances and mixtures of the Union, as well as for chemical products, which can be classified by calculation methods

Permitting state registration

- 60. The applicant shall send the following documents to the authorized body [A]
 - Application form in Annex 5 to this technical regulation
 - Safety data sheets, drawn up in accordance with paragraphs 36–43 of these technical regulations
 - Research (test) protocols conducted in testing (research) laboratories (centers), and (or) documents containing information obtained from official information sources. Research (test) protocols shall not be submitted for chemical products included in the register of chemical substances and mixtures of the Union, as well as for chemical products, which can be classified by calculation methods
 - The information specified in paragraph 48 of these technical regulations [see above]

5. Updates by companies

State registration

- 64. Chemical products with changes in their component composition shall be subject to re-notifying state registration or permitting state registration, if at such a change the concentration of hazardous chemical substances included in their composition in relation to their original concentration exceeded the allowable deviations specified in Annex 2 to this technical regulation. [A]

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

- Under development [D]

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

Notifying state registration [A]

- 57. The authorized body shall review the documents submitted by the applicant both electronically and in hard copy, make a decision on the notifying state registration of chemical products or refusal thereof, assign an individual registration number to chemical products, issue a certificate of notifying state registration of chemical products in the form according to Annex 6, as well as mark the registration in electronic form within 10 business days from the date of receipt of
- 58. The period of validity of the certificate of notifying state registration of chemical products and the mark of registration in electronic form is not limited.

Permitting state registration [A]

- 61. Consideration of the documents submitted by the applicant both in electronic form and on paper, making a decision on permitting state registration of chemical products or refusal thereof, assigning an individual registration number to chemical products, entering information on the name of chemical products, their chemical composition and properties in the register of chemicals and mixtures of the Union, issuing a permit for the use of chemical products in the form according to Annex 7 shall be made by the authorized body within 45 working days from the date of receipt of the documents.
- 62. The term of validity of a permit for the use of chemical products is 5 years from the date of its issuance. In the absence of comments from the authorized body on the non-compliance of chemical products with the requirements of these technical regulations within 5 years from the date of issuance of permission to use the chemical products, the authorized body automatically re-registers these products.

64. Notification and permitting state registration of chemical products may be refused if: a) submission by the applicant of incomplete or unreliable information specified in Para 54 and 60 of the regulation; 2) non-compliance of chemical products with the requirements of the technical regulation. [A]

66. The release into circulation of chemical products in the customs territory of the Union may be suspended by the authorized body in cases where a) chemical products in circulation on the customs territory of the Union do not meet the requirements of these technical regulations; (b) new safety requirements are established for chemical products. [A]

8. Data submission format

Pre-registration phase (now)

- To submit information on substances at the inventory stage, it is necessary to complete a template and submit it electronically to the Ministry of Industry & Trade. The submitter needs to send an information letter on official company letterhead, signed by the managing director, with contact details of the responsible person in the company for the submission procedure.
- In Russia, data can be submitted only by a Russian legal entity. A foreign company without a legal entity there can appoint a Russian representative for data submission. Unlike EU REACH, the representative is not required to have knowledge in the practical handling of the substances. The Russian importer or customer can act as a representative for inventory data submission.

Notification of new substances

- Under development

9. Data confidentiality

Pre-registration phase (now)

- Information on the volume of production / import of chemicals and the applicant will not be provided in the public domain. The list of chemicals in circulation on the territory of the Russian Federation, drawn up based on the results of the inventory, will be impersonal. [F]

Notification of new substances

- Under development [D]

10. Data that are published publicly

- Chemical name, synonyms, RTECS number, TN VED Eurasian Economic Union code, abbreviations, molecular formula, structural formula (SMILES, image), purpose and hazard classification, chemical industry

11. International information exchange and sharing – N.A.

S1.20 List of New Substances Notified or Registered in Switzerland (NSNRS)

Last update: 29 June 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Homepage: <https://www.anmeldestelle.admin.ch/chem/en/home/themen/pflicht-hersteller/stoffe/neuer-stoff.html>
- B. Ordinance on Protection against Dangerous Substances and Preparations (ChemO, 2020): <https://www.admin.ch/opc/en/classified-compilation/20141117/index.html>
- C. Guidelines for notification, reporting and declaration of new substances in accordance with the Swiss Chemicals Ordinance (04.03.2021): https://www.anmeldestelle.admin.ch/dam/chem/en/dokumente/wegleitung-anmeldungen-meldungen-mitteilungen-neuer-stoffe-chemv-schweiz.pdf.download.pdf/Wegleitung_NS_EN.pdf
- D. List of new substances notified or reported in Switzerland (09.12.2020): <https://www.anmeldestelle.admin.ch/chem/en/home/themen/pflicht-hersteller/stoffe/neuer-stoff/neue-stoffe-kurz-erklaert.html>
- E. Guidelines Reporting and Notifying new substances in Product Register for Chemicals (04.03.2021): <https://www.anmeldestelle.admin.ch/dam/chem/en/dokumente/leitfaden-an-meldungen-neue-stoffe-in-rpc.pdf.download.pdf/Guidelines%20Reporting%20and%20Notifying%20new%20substances%20in%20RPC.pdf>

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

- Distinction between existing and new substances.
- *New substances are those not listed in the European Inventory of Existing Commercial Substances (EINECS), i.e. those placed on the market for the first time after 18 September 1981. [A]*
- The list provides information about which new substance are notified or reported in Switzerland.

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligations

All new substances¹⁷² must be notified, reported and/or declared in Switzerland before they are placed on the market, even if they are already registered in the EU. When a preparation has been reported to the chemical products register, new substances must be notified or reported nonetheless (or declared, as regards substances placed on the market for product- and process-oriented research and development only). [C]

Notification

- *New substances that are placed on the market in Switzerland (including those imported for professional or commercial purposes) are subject to notification requirements under Chemicals Ordinance. [A, C]*
 - *A new substance must be notified not only as such or as a component of a preparation, but also if it forms part of an object [i.e. article] from which it can be released when used under normal or reasonably foreseeable conditions of use. The notification authority can require the notification of a substance contained in an object if it assumes that the substances can be released during the use of the object (article 24, paragraph 3, ChemO) [B].*
 - *The obligation to notify is generally applicable for quantities of more than 1 tonne per manufacturer or importer (Swiss quantity).*

¹⁷² A chemical element and its compounds in the natural state or obtained by any manufacturing process, including any additive necessary to preserve its stability and any impurity deriving from the process used, but excluding any solvent which may be separated without affecting the stability of the substance or changing its composition. [B]

- The notifier (manufacturer, importer or only representative) must have his habitual residence, registered office or subsidiary in Switzerland.
- New substances are also subject to self-regulation requirements under Article 5 of the ChemO.
- Substances, which must be notified, do not have to be additionally reported to the product register (PRC)

Reporting

- Manufacturers of new substances that are exempt from notification according to Article 26, ChemO, must report these within 3 months after first placing them on the market and independently of the obligation to establish a SDS (art. 48, art. 19 ChemO): [A]
 - dangerous substances¹⁷³
 - substances assessed as PBT or vPvB
 - substances in annex 3 ChemO (candidate list)
 - nanomaterials¹⁷⁴ purposefully containing fibres or tubes with a length of more than 5 µm. Materials with a water solubility of less than 100 mg per liter or with a half-life of 40 days or more in the lungs are considered being biopersistent.
 - Intermediates subject to the obligation to report: intermediates in the form of monomers which are new substances, intermediates which are given to third parties, leaving the manufacturing sites and placed on the market in quantities >100 kg/a [C]

Declaration

- The notification authority for chemicals must be informed of substances which do not have to be notified (art. 26 par. 1 let. e ChemO) and which are intended solely for product and process-orientated research and development (PPORD, art. 34 ChemO¹⁷⁵). [A, C]

3.2 Exemptions [A, B, C]

Substances and groups of substances which are regulated by special laws **are not subject to the provisions of the ChemO** (article 1 paragraph 5 and 6 ChemO). This applies: [C]

- to the transport of substances and preparations by road, rail, water, air or pipelines, art. 10 par. 1 let. b excepted;

¹⁷³ If they fulfil the criteria for classification of physical, health, environmental or other hazards specified in the technical provisions referred to in Annex 2 number 1 [Annexes I–VII to the CLP Regulation]. [B]

¹⁷⁴ A material containing particles in an unbound state or as an aggregate or as an agglomerate, where one or more external dimensions is in the size range 1–100 nm, or a material where the specific surface area by volume is greater than 60 m²/cm³. A material is only considered to be a nanomaterial if it is deliberately produced to utilise the properties arising from the defined external dimensions of the particles it contains, or from the defined surface area by volume of the material. Fullerenes, graphene flakes and single-wall carbon nanotubes with one or more external dimensions below 1 nm are considered to be nanomaterials. [B]

¹⁷⁵ A maximum period for exemption from full notification of five years from the date of application will generally be granted for product- and process-orientated research and development. This exemption from the duty of full notification can only be claimed if the substances placed on the market by the notifier meet the following conditions: exclusively for the purpose of product- and process-orientated research and development, in quantities no greater than those necessary for the stated purpose, and for a period not exceeding five years; in justified cases and after consultation with the evaluation units, the notification authority may extend this period by a further five or ten years.

Applications for exemption must be made to the notification authority for chemicals in good time, i.e. at least 30 days before the notifier intends to place the substance on the market for the first time.

After the five-year exemption period expires, these substances are subject to full notification if no prolongation demand is submitted [C]

- *to the transit of substances and preparations under customs supervision provided that they do not undergo any processing or transformation*
- *to substances and preparations in the form of finished products ready for supply to the end consumer that fall into the following categories:*
 - *foodstuffs as defined by article 4 of the Foodstuffs Act of 20 June 2014*
 - *medicines as defined by article 4 paragraph 1 letter a and medical devices as defined by article 4 paragraph 1 letter b of the Therapeutic Products Act of 15 December 2000*
 - *animal feedstuffs as defined by article 2 paragraph 1 of the Feedstuffs Ordinance of 26 May 1999*
- *to weapons as defined by article 4 paragraph 1 and ammunition as defined by article 4 paragraph 4 of the Weapons Act of 20 June 1997*
- *to substances, preparations and objects which are waste according to article 7 paragraph 6 of the EPA [Environmental Protection Act]*
- *Article 57 [storage], 62 (storage) and 67 (theft, loss, erroneous placing on the market) apply to imported substances and preparations that are simply relabelled and then exported without alteration. Dangerous substances and preparations that are exported are also governed by the PIC Ordinance of 10 November 2004.*
- *Crop protection products and biocidal products*
 - *new substances that are used exclusively as active ingredients and co-formulants in crop protection products and as active ingredients in biocidal products are not subject to the requirement for notification because they are required to undergo a regulatory approval procedure*
- *Cosmetic products*
 - *for cosmetic products within the meaning of art. 53 par. 1 of the Ordinance of 16 December 2016 on foodstuffs and commodities, in form of finished products which are destined for private or professional users (Art. 1 par. 4 ChemO), only Articles 5-7 (self-regulation, classification) and 81 (review of self-regulation) apply and only with regard to environmental protection and to classification or assessment in relation to risks to the environment.*
- ***Exemptions for new substances to which the ChemO applies:*** *Not all new substances to which the ChemO applies are subject to the notification requirement. The exceptions are listed in Article 26 ChemO. This article states that notification is not required for*
 - *polymers¹⁷⁶ as well as substances contained therein (monomers or substances chemically bound to the polymer) below 2% [by weight, monomers must be notified]*
 - *substances included in the No-Longer Polymers (NLP) list [EC numbers beginning with 5; classified NLP must be reported]*
 - *substances placed on the market (in Switzerland) in quantities of less than 1 tonne per year [this adaptation of the minimum quantity threshold for notification corresponds with that for registration according to the REACH Regulation. Here, the quantity actually placed on the market in Switzerland counts, notwithstanding the place where the substance is manufactured.]*
 - *substances placed on the market by a manufacturer:*
 - *purely for product and process-orientated research and development*
 - *limited to the quantities required for the said purposes, and*

¹⁷⁶ A substance consisting of molecules characterised by the sequence of one or more types of monomer units and comprising: 1. a simple weight majority of molecules containing at least three monomer units which are covalently bound to at least one other monomer unit or other reactant and 2. less than a simple weight majority of molecules of the same molecular weight; these molecules must be distributed over a range of molecular weights wherein differences in the molecular weight are primarily attributable to differences in the number of monomer units. [B]

- *for a period not exceeding five years; in justified cases and on request, the Notification Authority may, after consultation with the evaluation unit, may extend this period by a further five or ten years;*
 - *substances used exclusively as raw materials, active ingredients or additives in foodstuffs, therapeutic products and animal feed*
 - *substances acquired in Switzerland*
 - *intermediates, provided that they are not monomers [including three types of intermediates introduced in the EU with the REACH Regulation, i.e. non-isolated intermediates, on-site isolated intermediates, and transported isolated intermediates. Monomers may also represent intermediates. However, if a new substance is notified in accordance with Article 24 paragraph 2, monomers are not covered by the exemption for intermediates.]*
 - *substances listed in Annex V REACH [Exemptions from the obligations to register in accordance with Article 2(7)(b)]¹⁷⁷*

¹⁷⁷ (1) *Substances which result from a chemical reaction that occurs incidental to exposure of another substance or article to environmental factors such as air, moisture, microbial organisms or sunlight.*

(2) *Substances which result from a chemical reaction that occurs incidental to storage of another substance, mixture or article.*

(3) *Substances which result from a chemical reaction occurring upon end use of other substances, mixtures or articles and which are not themselves manufactured, imported or placed on the market.*

(4) *Substances which are not themselves manufactured, imported or placed on the market and which result from a chemical reaction that occurs when: (a) a stabiliser, colorant, flavouring agent, antioxidant, filler, solvent, carrier, surfactant, plasticiser, corrosion inhibitor, antifoamer or defoamer, dispersant, precipitation inhibitor, desiccant, binder, emulsifier, de-emulsifier, dewatering agent, agglomerating agent, adhesion promoter, flow modifier, pH neutraliser, sequesterant, coagulant, flocculant, fire retardant, lubricant, chelating agent, or quality control reagent functions as intended; or (b) a substance solely intended to provide a specific physicochemical characteristic functions as intended.*

(5) *By-products, unless they are imported or placed on the market themselves.*

(6) *Hydrates of a substance or hydrated ions, formed by association of a substance with water, provided that the substance has been registered by the manufacturer or importer using this exemption.*

(7) *The following substances which occur in nature, if they are not chemically modified: Minerals, ores, ore concentrates, raw and processed natural gas, crude oil, coal.*

(8) *Substances which occur in nature other than those listed under paragraph 7, if they are not chemically modified, unless they meet the criteria for classification as dangerous according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 or unless they are persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic or very persistent and very bioaccumulative in accordance with the criteria set out in Annex XIII or unless they were identified in accordance with Article 59(1) at least two years previously as substances giving rise to an equivalent level of concern as set out in Article 57(f).*

(9) *The following substances obtained from natural sources, if they are not chemically modified, unless they meet the criteria for classification as dangerous according to Directive 67/548/EEC with the exception of those only classified as flammable [R10], as a skin irritant [R38] or as an eye irritant [R36] or unless they are persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic or very persistent and very bioaccumulative in accordance with the criteria set out in Annex XIII or unless they were identified in accordance with Article 59(1) at least two years previously as substances giving rise to an equivalent level of concern as set out in Article 57(f): Vegetable fats, vegetable oils, vegetable waxes; animal fats, animal oils, animal waxes; fatty acids from C6 to C24 and their potassium, sodium, calcium and magnesium salts; glycerol.*

(10) *The following substances if they are not chemically modified: Liquefied petroleum gas, natural gas condensate, process gases and components thereof, coke, cement clinker, magnesia.*

(11) *The following substances unless they meet the criteria for classification as dangerous according to Directive 67/548/EEC and provided that they do not contain constituents meeting the criteria as dangerous in accordance with Directive 67/548/EEC present in concentrations above the lowest of the applicable concentration limits set out in Directive 1999/45/EC or concentration limits set out in Annex I to Directive 67/548/EEC, unless conclusive scientific experimental data show that these constituents are not available throughout the lifecycle of the substance and those data have been ascertained to be adequate and reliable: Glass, ceramic frits.*

- substances already notified and exported by the manufacturer, and re-imported by the same or another manufacturer in the same supply chain, if he can demonstrate that:
 - the substance is the same
 - he has been provided with a safety data sheet in accordance with Article 20 for the exported substance, if this is required under Article 19.
- Substances manufactured in Switzerland and exclusively exported [C]

Reporting

- Exemptions to the obligation to report are listed in Article 54 ChemO [A, B]
 - intermediates that: are not given to third parties, do not leave the manufacturing site, or are placed on the market in quantities less than 100kg per year
 - substances and preparations which are placed on the market solely for purposes of analysis, research or education, or which are subject to research and development
 - substances and preparations used exclusively for foodstuffs, therapeutic products or animal feeding stuffs
 - fertilisers which require authorisation from the Federal Office for Agriculture (FOAG) or have to be notified to the FOAG under the Fertiliser Ordinance of 10 January 2001
 - explosives and pyrotechnic devices which require authorisation under the Explosives Ordinance of 27 November 2000
 - substances obtained in Switzerland
 - preparations obtained in Switzerland and supplied in packaging other than that provided by the original manufacturer, provided that: the trade name, composition and intended use are unchanged, and the name of the original manufacturer is also indicated
 - gas mixtures consisting exclusively of reported gases
 - preparations not deemed to be dangerous under Article 3 which are in packages containing no more than 200 ml, if they are manufactured in Switzerland and supplied directly to professional or private users
 - preparations placed on the market in quantities of less than 100 kg per year and intended exclusively for professional users
 - substances notified by the manufacturer in accordance with Article 24.

4. Initial data requirements

Notification

- The data and documents that the technical dossier must contain are listed in Article 27 Chemo. They are the following [C]
 - the substance quantity placed on the market;
 - a technical dossier with the following details, listed in detail in Annex 4 [depending on the substance quantity placed on the market]
 - identity of the notifier
 - identity of the substance¹⁷⁸

(12) Compost and biogas.

(13) Hydrogen and oxygen. <https://reachonline.eu/reach/en/annex-v.html>

¹⁷⁸ Data specified in Section 2 of Annex VI to the REACH Regulation: If it is not technically possible or if it does not appear scientifically necessary to give information on one or more of the items below, the reasons shall be clearly stated. **Name or other identifier of each substance** [name(s) in the IUPAC nomenclature or other international chemical name(s); other names (usual name, trade name, abbreviation); EINECS or ELINCS number (if available and appropriate); CAS name and CAS number (if available); other identity code (if

- *information on manufacture and use*¹⁷⁹
- *classification and labelling*
- *guidance on safe use*
- *if applicable, an exposure assessment*¹⁸⁰
- *robust study summaries*¹⁸¹ *relating to the physical and chemical properties*
- *robust study summaries relating to harmful effects on people*
- *robust study summaries relating to harmful effects on the environment*
- *if the quantity placed on the market amounts to 10 tonnes per year or more: a chemical safety report in accordance with Article 28*¹⁸² [in accordance with Annex I to the REACH Regulation; this does not apply to new substances that are placed on the market in the form of preparations/mixtures if the concentration of the substance is lower than a) the cut-off values in accordance with Art. 11, Para 3 of the CLP regulation, or b) 0.1 per cent by weight for PBT or vPvB substances]
- *a proposed safety data sheet in the case of dangerous substances or PBT or vPvB substances*¹⁸³
- *all available documentation and information on the properties, exposure and harmful effects of the substance on people and the environment, unless these are already apparent from the technical dossier [as listed above]*

available)]; **Information related to molecular and structural formula of each substance** [molecular and structural formula (including SMILES notation, if available); information on optical activity and typical ratio of (stereo) isomers (if applicable and appropriate); molecular weight or molecular weight range]; **Composition of each substance** [degree of purity (%); nature of impurities, including isomers and by-products; percentage of (significant) main impurities; nature and order of magnitude (... ppm, ... %) of any additives (e.g. stabilising agents or inhibitors); spectral data (ultra-violet, infra-red, nuclear magnetic resonance or mass spectrum); high-pressure liquid chromatogram, gas chromatogram; description of the analytical methods or the appropriate bibliographical references for the identification of the substance and, where appropriate, for the identification of impurities and additives. This information shall be sufficient to allow the methods to be reproduced]. <https://reachonline.eu/reach/en/annex-vi-2.html>

¹⁷⁹ Including *information on waste quantities and composition of waste resulting from manufacture of the substance, the use in objects and identified uses; uses advised against.* [C]

¹⁸⁰ *If the substance quantity placed on the market is less than 10 tonnes per year, a simplified exposure assessment is sufficient. If this quantity is exceeded, a comprehensive exposure assessment must be carried out as part of the chemical safety assessment.* [C]

¹⁸¹ *A "robust study summary" according to article 2, paragraph 2, letter n, ChemO, is a detailed summary of the aims, methods, results and conclusions of a comprehensive test report, with information sufficient for an independent assessment of the test, such that, if possible, the comprehensive test report need not to be consulted. Robust study summaries replace the full study reports and facilitate the assessment, provided they are of good quality. If this is not the case, full studies should be submitted and the authorities can ask the notifier to submit a full study report.*

For substances registered in the EU after 1.6.2008, it is not mandatory to send in copies of the full test reports. A full completed summary in IUCLID, corresponding to the criteria of a robust study summary, is sufficient.

For notification of substances notified in the EU before 1.6.2008, it is necessary to include copies of all the testing reports available. [C]

¹⁸² *In addition, a chemical safety report is also required if it is available in the EEA, provided that it can be obtained by the manufacturer with reasonable effort. The chemical safety report contains the chemical safety assessment according to the provisions of Annex I REACH. The chemical safety assessment comprises the following steps (article 28, ChemO): a. human health hazard assessment; b. physicochemical hazard assessment; c. environmental hazard assessment; d. PBT and vPvB assessment; e. If the substance fulfils the criteria specified in Article 14 paragraph 4 REACH (an exposure assessment covering all identified uses, a description of the risks associated with all identified uses).* [C]

¹⁸³ *If the new substance is imported as such. If the substance is imported in a preparation or in an object, the submission by the notifier of the manufacturer's safety data sheet is recommended.* [C]

- Generally, and independently of the quantities placed on the market in Switzerland, all available information must be provided (such as the chemical safety report and the robust study summaries also submitted for registration in the EEA). In practice, this corresponds to information submitted to ECHA in the context of registration.
- For substances developed using genetic resources or with traditional knowledge related to them, the manufacturer must inform on his own initiative the Notification Authority and indicate the registration number pursuant to Art. 4 of the Nagoya Ordinance
- If the Notification Authority notices that a new substance has already been notified in Switzerland, it communicates the names and addresses of previous notifiers to the notifier. [C]
 - Pursuant to Art. 29 ChemO, the Notification Authority may refer to data from a previous notifier instead of data produced by the notifier if:
 - The new notifier proves with a letter of access from a previous notifier that the latter agrees to the Notification Authority consulting its data; or
 - The data protection period (5 years after submission of additional information; 10 years after notification in Switzerland) has expired.
 - The notifier must not refer to data from previous notifiers regarding
 - The identity and purity of the substance and the nature of any impurities;
 - Action to render the substance harmless
- Article 31 ChemO requires all further notifiers to establish whether the substance has already been notified before any studies involving vertebrates are carried out. In this procedure, the potential further notifier must demonstrate its justified interest to the notification authority for chemicals and enquire whether it is necessary to carry out animal studies, which must not be repeated ... for such a request, the substance quantity placed on the market must be submitted (art. 31 par. 2 ChemO), as well as substance identity information (described in Annex 4 ChemO, which corresponds to Chapter 2 of Annex VI REACH).
- The first and the further notifier shall make every effort to reach an agreement on data sharing and compensation. [C]

Reporting

- The reporting application must include the following data: [A, B, C]
 - the manufacturers' name and address
 - name of the person responsible for placing on the market in the EEA in accordance with Art. 7 para. 1 let. A CLP, if the manufacturer's identity is not mentioned on the label
 - In the case of substances
 - the chemical name according to Art. 18, para 2a-d of the CLP regulation
 - the [CASRN]
 - the EC number
 - the classification and labelling
 - uses
 - for substances dangerous to the environment: the annual quantity likely to be placed on the market
 - for nanomaterials:
 - the composition, particle shape and average particle size as well as, if available, the particle size distribution, specific surface to volume ratio, surface coating and surface functionalisation
 - the estimated quantity to be placed on the market [annually] in one of the following categories: <1 kg, 1–10 kg, 10–100 kg, 100–1000 kg, 1–10 tonnes, 10–100 tonnes, >100 tonnes;
 - if applicable, the identification as a PBT or vPvB substance

- *the chemical safety report available in the EEA, provided the manufacturer can reasonably be expected to be obtain it*
- *in the case of preparations:*
 - *the trade name*
 - *for preparations intended for private users and that are classified as dangerous because of the physical or health hazards they pose: the UFI*
 - *data relating to the constituents in accordance with the provisions concerning the safety data sheet*
 - *the classification and labelling*
 - *the intended uses*
 - *the physical state*
 - *in the case of preparations dangerous to the environment: the quantity likely to be placed on the market annually, according to one of the following categories: <1 tonne, 1–10 tonnes, 10–100 tonnes, >100 tonnes*
 - *in the case of preparations containing nanomaterials that must be specified in the safety data sheet: the composition of the nanomaterials, their particle form and mean particle size and, where available, the number size distribution, specific surface area by volume, crystal structure, aggregation status, surface coating and surface functionalisation.*
- *In the case of dangerous preparations sold to private users, the Notification Authority must be informed of the full composition. Constituents which are not deemed to be dangerous under Article 3 may be designated by a name that identifies the most important functional groups.*

Declaration

- *According to article 35, paragraph 2, ChemO, the declaration must include: [C]*
 - *Name and address of the manufacturer*
 - *If the manufacturer has imported the substance: name and address of the foreign manufacturer*
 - *The key information for identifying the substance*
 - *The uses*
 - *The expected quantity of the substance to be placed annually on the market in Switzerland*
 - *The intended classification and labelling*
 - *The research programme and a list of recipients of the substance*
 - *For dangerous substances or PBT or vPvB substances: a proposed safety data sheet*

Request to use an alternative chemical name

- *Art. 15 [B]: requests must contain*
 - *The manufacturer's name, address and telephone number*
 - *The following information relating to the substances whose identity is to remain confidential on the label: the chemical name, [CASRN], the EC number*
 - *The alternative name of the substance*
 - *The reasons for the request*
 - *The trade name or designation of the preparation*
 - *The information on the constituents in accordance with the provisions relating to the safety data sheet*
 - *The classification of the preparation*
 - *The labelling of the preparation*
 - *The intended use of the preparation*
 - *The physical state*

- *If applicable, the safety data sheet*

5. Data updates by companies

After placing on the market [C]

- Art. 44: *Manufacturers must reassess or further assess substances, preparations and objects containing dangerous constituents and, where necessary, reclassify, relabel and repackage them if: [B]*
 - *a). they are to be supplied for different purposes;*
 - *b). they are to be used in a different way; c). they are to be used in much larger quantities than before;*
 - *d). variations arise in the nature and quantity of impurities, which could have adverse effects on human health or the environment;*
 - *e). the assessment of the risks they pose to human health or the environment needs to be modified in the light of practical experience, new data or new information.*
- Art. 45: *They must retain or ensure the availability of the main documents used in the assessment and classification, together with the results of the assessment and classification, for at least ten years after the products are last placed on the market. They must retain **samples and specimens** for as long as their condition allows them to be analysed. [B]*
- Article 46 paragraph 1 letter b ChemO *requires the notifier to inform the notification authority for chemicals immediately and unbidden in writing if the substance quantity placed on the market is expected to reach one of the quantity thresholds according to Article 47, paragraph 1, ChemO (10 tonnes, 100 tonnes, 1000 tonnes or more per year, respectively). In this case the notifier must specify which tests it intends to carry out in order to produce the supplementary information (see table below). This corresponds to the provisions of the REACH Regulation and, particularly for tests on vertebrates, animal protection requirements. After receiving this information, the notification authority for chemicals shall inform the notifier about the relevant data already in its possession (article 32 and article 47, paragraph 2, ChemO). Once the tests have been specified, the authorities will draw up a timetable for the implementation of the additional tests after consulting the notifier and taking account of test programmes that are already under way in the EEA.*
- Article 46 paragraph 1 letters a and c to g ChemO *stipulates that the notifier must inform the notification authority for chemicals immediately in writing if:*
 - *The following details, listed in detail in Annex 4, ChemO, change: identity of the notifier, identity of the substance, information on manufacture and use, classification and labelling, guidelines on safe use, any implemented exposure assessment*
 - ***The substance quantity placed on the market has more than doubled or more than halved compared to the last notified quantity***
 - *The notifier has new information about the effect of the substance on humans or the environment*
 - *The notifier places the substance on the market for a new use, or is aware that the substance is being used for purposes that it has not disclosed to the notification authority*
 - *The notifier produces, or commissions, test reports for the substance that exceed the scope of the technical dossier specified in Article 27, paragraph 2, letter b*
 - *It can obtain further test reports that exceed the scope of the technical dossier specified in Article, paragraph 2, letter b*

Reporting [B]

- *Any modifications to the information specified in Articles 49 and 50 [on reporting] must be reported within 3 months.*

- *If the quantity of substances and preparations dangerous to the environment actually supplied in a year falls outside the reported category of quantities placed on the market, the quantity placed on the market in the previous year must be reported by 31 March of the following year.*

Declaration [C]

- *The notification authority must be informed immediately in writing in the event of any changes to the above-mentioned compulsory information for declarations (article 35, paragraph 2, ChemO).*

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

Notification

- *If there is reason to assume that a certain substance which, according to the above criteria, does not have to be notified could pose a risk to humans or the environment, the notification authority for chemicals will, at the request of an evaluation unit, require the manufacturer to submit certain test reports. The requirements for these test reports should not exceed the scope of the technical dossier according to Annex 4 (Article 26, Paragraph 2 ChemO). [C] [also true for reporting, declaration]*
- *The notification authority can request the full study reports and, if available and procurable by the notifier with reasonable effort: robust study summaries or test reports exceeding the scope of the technical dossier and which are relevant to the assessment and to classification (article 27, paragraph 5, ChemO). [C]*
- *If the dossier is incomplete or flawed, the notification authority for chemicals will request the notifier to remedy this situation (article 38 ChemO). [C]*

Notification updates [B, C]

- *If the risks associated with a substance cannot be adequately evaluated, the notification authority will, if so requested by an evaluation unit, require the notifier to submit additional information or tests relating to the substances or its transformation products (Article 47, paragraph 3, ChemO).*
- *Supplementary to the above data and test reports, the notification authority for chemicals may request the notifier to provide individual or all test reports which exceed the scope of the technical dossier and which have been prepared or commissioned by the notifier or can be obtained with a reasonable effort.*
- *If the notifier fails to submit the additional test reports by the specified deadline, the Notification Authority may arrange for the required tests to be carried out at the notifier's expense and, if necessary, prohibit the notifier from continuing to place the substance on the market.*

Review of existing substances [B]

- *The assessment authorities may review any existing substances which*
 - *May represent a particular risk to human life or health or to the environment, owing to the quantities manufactured or placed on the market or owing to their dangerous nature or the dangerous nature of their secondary products or wastes; or*
 - *Are included in an international existing substances programme*
- *If an existing substance is to be reviewed, the Notification Authority, at the request of an assessment authority, shall require all the manufacturers concerned to provide the following information*
 - *The name and address of the manufacturer, and the name and address of the foreign manufacturer if the manufacturer imports the substance*
 - *All documents used in assessing and establishing the hazardous properties of the substance*
 - *The known uses;*
 - *Information on the quantities placed on the market by the manufacturers*
 - *The registration dossier submitted to the [ECHA], provided it is available and can be obtained by the notifier with reasonable effort*

- *If requested by an assessment authority, the Notification Authority shall request one of the manufacturers to carry out investigations or studies. The costs incurred by the manufacturer shall be borne jointly by all the manufacturers concerned.*

Review of self-regulation and monitoring [B]

- *If there is reason to suppose that assessment of classification has not been carried out or has not been carried out correctly, the Notification Authority, at the request of an assessment authority, shall require the manufacturer concerned to provide*
 - *All the documents used in establishing the hazardous properties or in the assessment*
 - *The safety data sheet, if appropriate*
- *At the request of an assessment authority, the Notification Authority shall require the manufacturer to perform tests or additional assessments if there are indications that*
 - *Substances or preparations and their secondary products or wastes may endanger human health or the environment*
 - *Objects, their secondary products or their wastes may endanger the environment*
- *If a manufacturer does not comply with an official order, the Notification Authority shall, if so requested by an assessment authority, prohibit it from continuing to supply the substances, preparations or objects concerned.*
- *By means of random sampling, the cantonal enforcement authorities shall inspect substances, preparations and objects placed on the market, including*
 - *That the notification, declaration and reporting requirements (Articles 24, 34, 48, 52, 53) and the provisions governing updated information (Art. 46) have been respected*

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

Notification [C]

- *The notification authority for chemicals will examine the dossier for formal completeness. This includes, for example, checking whether the test reports for non-clinical tests assessing properties dangerous for health or the environment that have been submitted have been produced in compliance with the principles of Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) as specified in the Good Laboratory Practice Ordinance.¹⁸⁴*
 - *The evaluation units will examine the aspects of the dossier for which they are responsible to see whether the data are complete and plausible in scientific terms and whether the test reports are based on tests as required by art. 43 ChemO.*
 - *If a test is neither recognised by the European Commission nor specified in the OECD testing guidelines, or the notifier can plausibly explain why a specified method is not suitable for determining a physical or chemical property of the substance, other test methods may be used. In this case, however, the notifier must be able to demonstrate that the tests produce valid results*

¹⁸⁴ *The following may be used to demonstrate compliance:*

- *A document showing that the tests were carried out by a testing body which at the time of testing was listed in the Swiss directory of testing bodies which comply with the principles of GLP;*
- *A signed test report (draft not acceptable) in which the study director confirms in an official language or in English that the test was carried out in compliance with the principles of GLP.*

If the test has been carried out in another country, the test report must be accompanied by a directory or certificate from the competent authority showing that the testing body was participating in the official monitoring programme at the time of testing. The notification authority for chemicals may request different documentation from countries which are not members of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) if this documentation is necessary to evaluate compliance with the principles of GLP. [C]

and that animal welfare has been taken adequately into consideration if animal studies are carried out (article 43, paragraph 3, ChemO).

- *Art. 16 ChemA stipulates that new substances subject to notification must undergo a targeted risk assessment, without indicating when this has to happen. Art. 37 par. 2 ChemO states more precisely that in specific cases a targeted risk assessment can be conducted during evaluation of notification data ... If the authorities do have access to information that is not contained in the notification data, they may use them for risk assessment.*
 - *For the authorities as well as for the notifier, it is more efficient if the result of this targeted risk assessment is communicated in one single step, i.e. with the notification's acceptance (see art. 39 par. 2 ChemO). As stipulated in art. 16 ChemA, the notifier is informed about the proposed risk management measures and consulted, before a decision is taken. No further tests are requested (art. 16 par. 1 ChemA) at this stage of risk assessment so that the notification process be met, unless the notification dossier must be completed pursuant to art. 38 par. 2 ChemO.*
- *If examination of the dossier shows that it is complete and adequate for assessing the dangers and risks associated with the substance, the notification authority for chemicals will decide to accept it in agreement with the evaluation units (article 39 ChemO).*
 - *If a targeted risk assessment was performed in parallel with evaluation of the notification dossier and if risk management measures have to be taken, they are indicated in the decision accepting the notification.*
 - *The authorities have a period of 60 days in which to examine a notification (article 40 ChemO). The period begins on the day after the complete technical dossier is received by the notification authority for chemicals. It ends at the end of the last day of the period.*
 - *If the notification authority for chemicals does not decide to accept the notification or does not comment materially on the notification within the period of time mentioned before, the substance may be placed on the market once this period expires (article 40 letter b ChemO). If the authorities request supplementary data or documents, the period starts again.*

Reporting

- *If the automatic validation has not found any error then the entered dataset is shown as qualified and the reporting is thus terminated.*
- *Although the authorities do not issue any order, they can evaluate the submitted data.*

Declaration

- *According to Article 41, ChemO, the authorities have a period of 30 days in which to examine the application ... If the notification authority for chemicals does not decide to accept the notification or does not comment materially on the declaration within 30 days, the substance may be placed on the market once this period expires.*

Review of self-regulation and monitoring

- *The assessment authorities shall review, in their area of competence, for substances, preparations and objects*
 - *The assessment and classification*
 - *The information that appears in the safety data sheet*
- *They may instruct the Notification Authority*
 - *To verify the composition and the physicochemical properties of substances, preparations and objects*
 - *To ask cantonal enforcement authorities to take samples.*

8. Data submission format

- IUCLID substance export file
- Reporting is to be submitted to the notification authority for chemicals using the E-application for chemicals (RPC): <https://www.rpc.admin.ch/rpc/private> [A]

9. Data confidentiality

Art. 14 [B]: *Manufacturers of preparations may use an alternative chemical name for a substance if:*

- *They demonstrate that disclosing the name of the substance on the label or in the safety data sheet would put the confidential nature of their business, in particular their intellectual property rights, at risk; and*
- *The substance meets the criteria specified in Section 1.4 of Annex I to the CLP Regulation, in the applicable version referred to in Annex 2 number 1*
- *The alternative chemical name shall be a name that identifies the most important functional groups or serves as an alternative designation.*
- *Manufacturers wishing to use an alternative chemical name must make a request in writing.*
- *The use of an alternative chemical name may be request for a preparation*
 - *In a specific composition*
 - *With a specific trade name or a specific designation; and*
 - *Reserved for certain uses.*
- *Authorisation to sue an alternative chemical name is granted to the manufacturer and is non-transferable.*
- *During the first six years after the reporting, declaration or notification of a new substance, an alternative chemical name request is not necessary. After that, the chemical name pursuant to Art. 18(2) CLP¹⁸⁵ must be used, or a request for using an alternative chemical name must be submitted (art. 14 and 15 ChemO). [C]*

Art. 73: Confidential data [B]

- *The enforcement authorities shall treat data as confidential when an interest in its confidentiality is worthy of protection, unless there is an overriding public interest in its disclosure.*
- *The Notification Authority shall designate the confidential data in consultation with the assessment authorities. It shall do so before passing it on to the competent cantonal or federal authorities specified in Article 75 paragraph 2.*
- *In particular, shall be deemed worthy of protection the interest in maintaining commercial/manufacturing secrecy, including:*

¹⁸⁵ *The product identifier for a substance shall consist of at least the following:*

- if the substance is included in Part 3 of Annex VI, a name and an identification number as given therein;*
- if the substance is not included in Part 3 of Annex VI, but appears in the classification and labelling inventory, a name and an identification number as given therein;*
- if the substance is not included in Part 3 of Annex VI nor in the classification and labelling inventory, the number provided by the CAS (hereinafter referred to as 'the CAS number'), together with the name set out in the nomenclature provided by the IUPAC (hereinafter referred to as 'the IUPAC Nomenclature'), or the CAS number together with another international chemical name(s); or*
- if the CAS number is not available, the name set out in the IUPAC Nomenclature or another international chemical name(s).*

Where the name in the IUPAC nomenclature exceeds 100 characters, one of the other names (usual name, trade name, abbreviation) referred to in section 2.1.2 of Annex VI to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 may be used provided that the notification in accordance with Article 40 includes both the name set out in the IUPAC Nomenclature and the other name used.

<https://reachonline.eu/clp/en/title-iii-chapter-1-article-18.html>

- *information on the identity of intermediates*
- *the complete composition of a preparation*
- *the quantities of a substance of a preparation placed on the market*
- *the information on nanomaterials referred to in Article 49 (obligation to report, see above).*
- *If the Notification Authority discovers that data deemed to be confidential has subsequently been lawfully disclosed, this data shall no longer be treated as confidential.*
- *The following are not deemed confidential under any circumstances:*
 - *the trade name*
 - *the name and address of the person subject to notification, declaration or reporting requirements*
 - *the physicochemical properties*
 - *procedures for proper disposal, for possible recycling or reuse, and for other ways of rendering materials harmless*
 - *the summary of results of toxicological and ecotoxicological tests*
 - *the degree of purity of a substance and the identity of the impurities and additives that are relevant for classification*
 - *recommendations regarding precautions during use and emergency measures in the event of an accident*
 - *information that appears in the safety data sheet, with the exception of the identity of intermediates*
 - *suitable analytical methods for determining the exposure of human beings and presence in the environment.*
- *The Notification Authority and assessment authorities may publish data in the register of products which is not deemed confidential under any circumstances.*

10. Data that are published publicly

- public name of the substance (including ambiguous ones such as “AIC-6”, “AIC-9”, “AIM-5”, “AIY-8”), EC-number / list number (not for all) [D]

Art. 72 Register of products [B]

- *The Notification Authority shall maintain a register of substances and preparations that fall within the scope of the following Ordinances: [B], the ORRChem, the Biocidal Products Ordinance, the Plant Protection Products Ordinance*
- *The register shall be compiled on the basis of data*
 - *That has been collected or produced by a Swiss authority under one of the ordinances*
 - *That is made available by foreign authorities or by international organisations*

11. International information exchange and sharing – Art. 76 [B]

- *The Notification Authority and assessment authorities may pass on data that is not confidential to foreign authorities and institutions, and to international organisations.*
- *They may pass on confidential data if*
 - *this is required by international agreements or decisions of international organisations; or*
 - *it is necessary to prevent an imminent danger to human life or health or to the environment.*

S1.21 Thailand Existing Chemicals Inventory #1 (TECI-1)

Last update: 14 June 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Background and lists from the years 2012 and 2016: <http://thaiipcs.fda.moph.go.th> (in Thai)
- B. Master Plan on Chemical Management (2019–2037): <https://online.fliphtml5.com/bcbgj/cklz/#p=6>

Note: The texts below referring to the Source “A” are based on informal translation using Google Translate.

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory [A]

- TECI-1 is the results of the 4th *National Strategic Plan on Chemical Management (2012–2021)* and was developed for the purpose of enabling the general public and related sectors to use it for searching and auditing for surveillance and research studies.
- TECI-1 will be taken into account in the development of future TECI under the new Chemical Act (for details, see the next Section).

3. Scope of the inventory

There are two lists available, compiled by the Food and Drug Administration. The data are collected and sorted from customs data (imported goods) and chemical factories’ production data [A & personal communication].

- The 2012 list compiles a list of single substances that were imported or produced in Thailand during the one-year period of 2012 (in total 7211 substances, 7180 imported and 239 produced domestically)
- The 2016 list compiles a list of single substances and mixtures (that have the assigned CASRN available) that were imported or produced in Thailand during the one-year period of 2016 (in total 9494 substances).

4. Data confidentiality

N.A.

5. Data updates by companies

N.A.

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

N.A.

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

N.A.

8. Initial data requirements

N.A.

9. Data submission format

N.A.

10. Data that are published publicly

TECI number; CASRN; English common name; Thai name; IUPAC name; customs tariff code; control law; import quantity (kg); domestic product

11. International information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.22 Thailand Existing Chemicals Inventory #2 (TECI-2)

Last update: 16 June 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Inventory: <http://inventory.diw.go.th/hazardous61/>
- B. Hazardous Substances¹⁸⁶ Act B.E. 2535 (2019):
http://www.ratchakitcha.soc.go.th/DATA/PDF/2562/A/056/T_0231.PDF (in Thai);
https://www.jetro.go.jp/thailand/e_survey/hazardousact.html (informal translation; overall page)
- 2008 version: https://www.jetro.go.jp/ext_images/thailand/e_activity/pdf/hazsubact2535.pdf
 - 2019 amendments:
https://www.jetro.go.jp/ext_images/thailand/pdf/HazSubAct_20190201NLAapproved.pdf
 - Notification of the production and import of hazardous chemicals in Thailand (2015):
https://www.chemsafetypro.com/Topics/Thailand/Thailand_Chemical_Inventory_Notification.html;
https://www.chemsafetypro.com/Topics/Thailand/Thailand_chemical_inventory_notification.pdf (informal translation)
 - Notification of Ministry of Industry, Re: Registration of hazardous substances. B.E. 2543 (2000): https://www.jetro.go.jp/ext_images/thailand/e_activity/pdf/hmoinoti2.pdf (informal translation)
 - Ministerial Regulation, B.E. 2537 (1994) Issued pursuant to the Hazardous Substance Act B.E. 2535 (1992): https://www.jetro.go.jp/ext_images/thailand/e_activity/pdf/hminreg1.pdf (informal translation)
 - Notification of Ministry of Industry, subject: Hazard classification and communication system of hazardous substances¹⁸⁷, B.E. 2555 (2012):
https://www.jetro.go.jp/ext_images/thailand/e_activity/pdf/moinoti2555.pdf (informal translation)
- C. **Draft** Chemical Act (version 4, 07 January 2021; the final version will replace [B]):
[http://thaiipcs.fda.moph.go.th/\(ร่าง\)พ.ร.บ.สารเคมี%20พ.ศ.%2007012021.pdf](http://thaiipcs.fda.moph.go.th/(ร่าง)พ.ร.บ.สารเคมี%20พ.ศ.%2007012021.pdf) (in Thai)
- D. *Thailand Hazardous Substance Control Act (HSCA)* by Matt Lyu, Chemlinked (December 18, 2020):
<https://chemical.chemlinked.com/chempedia/thailand-hazardous-substance-control-act-hsca>, including visual illustration of obligations with regard to different types of substances and actors

Note: The texts below are based on informal translation provided by JETRO or using Google Translate.

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

Currently [B]

- a list of chemicals that have been declared as hazardous substances and other chemicals that have been notified to DIW (non-hazardous substances are NOT included)

¹⁸⁶ In this Act, "hazardous substance" means the following substances: (1) an explosive; (2) an inflammable substance; (3) an oxidizing agent and a peroxide substance; (4) a toxic substance; (5) an infectious substance; (6) a radioactive substance; (7) a mutagen; (8) a corrosive substance; (9) an irritating substance; (10) other substances, whether chemical or else, which may be harmful to person, animal, plant, property or environment. [B.1]

¹⁸⁷ "Hazardous substance" means hazardous substance under responsibility of Department of Industrial Works, excluding chemical wastes and used electrical and electronic equipment as mentioned in the Notification of Ministry of Industry regarding List of Hazardous Substance, which is issued under the second paragraph of the Article 18 of the Hazardous Substance Act B.E. 2535. [B.6]

Future [C]

- distinction between existing and new chemicals: Details of the preparation, updates and information disclosure are to be defined, including exemptions.
 - Existing substances will be classified into three categories: Category 1 = all activities must comply with the rules and conditions stipulated by the authorities; Category 2 = all activities must be permitted; and Category 3 = all activities are prohibited. The authority will have the power to modify the classification. The basis will be all existing lists in Thailand.
 - All other chemicals are regarded as new chemicals. A business operator who wants to import, produce or transit must apply for (including the Only Representative system)
 - In assessing the chemicals, the authority may allow to import or manufacture such new chemicals in the necessary quantities as samples for an experimental analysis of its efficiency, evaluation of its benefits, and assessment of the hazards and risks.
 - In order for the assessment of chemicals to be accurate, appropriate and expeditious to the board, **the authority have the power to assign experts, expert organizations, or agencies in the country and abroad who have knowledge and expertise to support the assessment.**
 - **Other important points include:** the validity period of licenses is specified and shall not exceed 6 years. The insurance and compensation for the damages arising from chemicals are regulated, and the penalty scheme will be stricter. Measures to promote and support chemical management, including tax assistance, investment promotion, etc.

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligation to register

- Section 20/2: A person making a transit of 1st or 2nd Category of hazardous substance shall notify the competent official before each transit and after receiving the notification, the competent official shall issue a transit license as an evidence of notification ... A transit operator of 3rd Category of hazardous substance shall get permission from the competent official prior to each transit and after granting permission, the competent official shall issue a transit license as an evidence of permission. [B.2]
- Section 36: The production or import of any Category 2 or 3 of hazardous substances¹⁸⁸ other than those specified in the list [of hazardous substances]¹⁸⁹ shall be **registered** with the competent official prior to production or import. Upon receiving certificate of registration, it may be produced or imported under Section 22 or the production or import license thereof may be granted under Section 23 ... The certificate of registration of hazardous substance shall be valid for not more than six years as from the date of issuance of the certificate of registration. [B.1]

¹⁸⁸ Hazardous substances which its production, import or export or to have it in possession shall be in accordance with the determined rules and procedures (Category 1) / notified in advance to the competent official and shall be in accordance with the determined rules and procedure (Category 2) / licensed (Category 3). [B.1] Hazardous substances which its production, import or export or to have it in possession is prohibited (Category 4). [B.2]

¹⁸⁹ Notification of Ministry of Industry, Subject: List of hazardous substances. B.E. 2556 (2013): https://www.jetro.go.jp/thailand/pdf/hazardlist13_eng.pdf (informal translation). Amendment to the list of hazardous substances B.E. 2558 (2015): https://www.chemsafetypro.com/Topics/Thailand/BE_2558.pdf (in Thai). List 1 = responsible by Department of Agriculture (686 substances and 12 substance groups); List 2 = responsible by Department of Fisheries (17 substances and 2 substance groups); List 3 = responsible by Department of Livestock Development (23 substances and 13 substance groups); List 4 = responsible by Food and Drug Administration (224 substances, 28 substance groups and 6 product groups); List 5 = responsible by Department of Industrial Works (486 substances, 6 types of chemical wastes, used electrical and electronic appliance, 8 groups of other substances, chemical weapons); List 6 = responsible by Department of Energy Business (natural gas and liquefied petroleum gas).

- BE 2543: Any person who **produces or imports type 2 or type 3** hazardous substances [that are under the authorization of Department of Industrial Works] shall submit an application for **registration** of such hazardous substance to Department of Industrial Works, Ministry of Industry, or to other agencies designated by the Ministry of Industry. [B.4]
- BE 2537: Any person who intends to apply for **permission to produce, import, export or have in possession a type 3** hazardous substance shall submit two copies of the application and documentation as specified in the application form annexed to this Ministerial Regulation. [B.5]
- BE 2558: The **manufacturer or importer** of hazardous substances **>1t/year** (including both substances and mixtures) listed in the Annex 5.6 of Thailand Hazardous Substance List¹⁹⁰, which is a generic entry covering **industrial** chemicals meeting the definition of hazardous substances (this would mean that almost all substances or mixtures meeting GHS classification criteria (GHS Rev. 3) will fall within the notification scope). [B.3] The **notification** shall be submitted within 60 days from the date of manufacture or importation (only once).
- Section 43: No person shall produce, import or have in possession of the 4th Category of hazardous substance, except for use as standard substance in laboratory and written permission has been granted by the responsible agency. The application for, and the granting of, permission shall be in accordance with the rules, procedure and conditions as specified by the Responsible Minister ... and published in the Government Gazette. [B.1]

3.2 Exemptions

- Section 36: Where there is a Notification of the Responsible Minister exempting the registration on the ground that that hazardous substances has been registered by another person or on any other reasonable grounds. [B.1]
- Section 44: The Responsible Minister shall ... have the power to issue the notifications the exemption of the following hazardous substances from being compiled with this Act, wholly or partly, according to the prescribed rules, procedures and conditions [B.2]: hazardous substance that its nature or quantity may cause modest harm or the enforcement of various measures under this Act to such hazardous substance may cause undue burden; hazardous substance that its purpose of use is for study, testing, analysis, research and development; hazardous substance belonged to ministries, sub-ministries, departments, local administrations, state enterprises, state organisations, The Thai Red Cross Society or other agencies to be determined as appropriate.
 - BE 2543: Where a hazardous substance has already been registered or permitted to be produced or imported under other laws, or there is distinct and reliable information about the hazardous substance in question, the competent official may allow the exemption from compliance with any article in this Ministerial Notification. [B.4]
 - BE 2537: The person who has already been granted a permit for production, import or export of hazardous substance (category 3) shall be exempt from obtaining a permit for the possession of the particular hazardous substance. [B.5]
- BE 2558: Chemicals that are already included in the other annexes of Thailand Hazardous Substances List and already subject to the control or supervision of production and import are excluded from this notification requirement, including pesticide active ingredients and formulations listed in Annex 1 and veterinary drugs in Annex 3. [B.3]

¹⁹⁰ Annex 5.6 - Hazardous substances include (1) explosives; (2) inflammable substances; (3) oxidizing agents and peroxide substances; (4) toxic substances; (5) mutagenic substances; (6) corrosive substances; (7) irritative substances; (8) Carcinogen; (9) toxic substance to reproductive organ (10) environmentally hazardous substance – All category 1

4. Initial data requirements

- BE 2543: application form + one copy of following documentation [B.4]:
 - 1. Material Safety Data Sheet (MSDS), in accordance with the form WoAo./AoKo.3 annexed to this Ministerial Notification or with that of ISO 11014-1
 - 2. specification of the hazardous substance
 - 3. document or photograph evidencing characteristic of container or tanks
 - 4. document or photograph evidencing methods used to secure the containers (if any)
 - 5. a specimen of the hazardous substance for analysis of its specification, or the analysis result issued by an analytical laboratory approved by DIW, or a document proving specification.
 - A sample may be submitted as a substitute for the documents in (3) and (4), nonetheless the specimen, the analysis result or the document in (5) shall be as prescribed by the competent official.
- BE 2558: Form for the notification of production or import [B.3]
 - legal entity info
 - type of activity: production or import;
 - type of chemical products: substance or mixture;
 - trade names
 - HS code, UN number, class;
 - Composition (chemical name, chemical formula, CASRN, percentage by weight), state (solid/liquid/gas/other), characteristics of the chemical product
 - packaging details;
 - manufacturer name and country of origin;
 - GHS classification: physico-chemical properties; toxicological info; eco-toxicological info; disposal considerations; a copy of GHS SDS prepared in Thai or English needs to be provided when submitted the notification.
- BE 2537: Form + the following documents [B.5]
 - Copy of identification card or copy of alien identification card
 - Copy of certificate of juristic person registration
 - Copy of certificate of registration of hazardous substance (in case where the applicant for production of hazardous substance has already registered the hazardous substance)
 - Sketch map of production facility and surrounding area [in the case of production only] / Copy of the analysis result of hazardous substance [in the case of export only] / Evidence of possession of hazardous substance, list of hazardous substances in possession, in case of more than one substance [in the case of possession only]
 - Sketch map of storage facility and surrounding area
 - Floor plan of the building used for production [in the case of production only] and storage of hazardous substance, both as raw materials and products
 - Production process diagram [in the case of production only]
 - Document evidencing the knowledge and expertise of experts and specialized personnel in charge of production.
 - Document describing the characteristics of containers, tanks and method used to secure the containers.
 - Material Safety Data Sheet
- For non-hazardous chemical products imported into Thailand, a statement from supplier is sufficient. There is no need to disclose full composition.
- *DIW [Department of Industrial Works] would require 100% composition disclosure for evaluation. Companies may choose to keep some composition information to themselves due to CBI [confidential]*

business information] concern. Under such circumstances, the company has to take its own risk since the DIW could only evaluate the chemicals are hazardous or not based on the information provided. This undoubtedly could give rise to potential risks of non-compliance. The recommended strategy would be to compare the chemicals of your concern against the hazardous control list.

For importers, it should also be specially noted that Thailand Customs would also inspect the 100% concentration disclosure declaration, to make sure the information provided are consistent with those on the SDS. [D]

5. Data updates by companies

- BE 2543: A recipient of a certificate of registration of hazardous substance, who needs to correct or alter any information on the certificate, shall submit a written request to the competent official. The competent official may ask the recipient in written to conduct an additional analysis or any other matter, where sees appropriate. After reviewing the application and considering it legitimate, the competent official shall approve of correction or alteration on the certificate and shall notify the recipient of such approval. [B.4]
- BE 2537: Correction, Alteration, and Renewal of Permit [B.5]
 - A recipient of a permit for production, import or export of hazardous substance who needs to correct or alter the trade name of the hazardous substance, its country of origin or the expert or specialized personnel in charge of production or storage shall submit a written request together with the original permit granted and all necessary documentation to the agency responsible for the control of such hazardous substance.
 - A recipient of a permit for possession of hazardous substance who needs to change the expert or specialized personnel in charge of storage, the name of the hazardous substance in possession, the quantity, or the area of possession of the hazardous substance shall submit a written request together with the original permit granted and all necessary documentation to the agency responsible for the control of such hazardous substance.

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

- BE 2543: In the process of examining the application, the competent official may direct the applicant to submit additional information related to such hazardous substance or to conduct an additional analysis. [B.4]

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

- Section 38. No competent official shall accept the registration of hazardous substance if the Committee is of the opinion that: (1) The hazardous substance seeking registration is not reliably beneficial as applied for registration, or its usage may be harmful to people, animals, plants, property or environment without ordinarily reasonable prevention; (2) the hazardous substance seeking registration is named in boastful, impolite, or misleading manner, or (3) the hazardous substance seeking registration is a forged hazardous substance or a hazardous substance the registration of which has been revoked. The registration refusal order by the competent official shall be final. [B.1]
- Section 39. For the purpose of providing protection to people, animals, plants, property, or environment, the competent official ... shall have the power to order the rectification of the hazardous substance registration particulars as necessary. [B.1]
- Section 40. If it appears later on that a registered hazardous substance is not as useful as described in the register or its usage may be harmful to people, animals, plants, property or environment without ordinary reasonable prevention, the competent official ... shall have the power to revoke the registration of such hazardous substance. [B.1]
- BE2543: After examining the application and all documentation, the competent official, where sees legitimate, shall grant a certificate of registration of hazardous substance. [B.4]

- BE2537: Upon receiving an application with the documents and evidence, the competent official shall proceed with its examination and issue a permit in accordance with the stages and durations as follows [B.5]:
 - Application for permission to produce a hazardous substance
 - (a) Upon receiving an application, the competent official shall **inspect** the site of the production facility, storage facility, machinery and the accuracy of documents, and prepare an inspection report within 30 days.
 - (b) Upon the completion of (a), consideration of the application shall be completed within 20 days.
 - (c) The applicant shall be notified of the application result within 10 days. In the case where permission is denied, the applicant shall also be notified of the rejection order as well as the reasons for rejection.
 - Application for permission to import, export or have in possession a hazardous substance
 - (a) Upon receiving an application, the competent official shall inspect the site of the storage facility and the accuracy of documents, and prepare an inspection report within 10 days.
 - (b) Upon the completion of (a), consideration of the application shall be completed within 10 days.
 - (c) The applicant shall be notified of the application results within 10 days. In the case where permission is denied, the applicant shall also be notified of the rejection order as well as the reasons for rejection.
 - [The time periods above] shall not include the period during which the agency considering the application has directed the applicant to satisfy all requirements or the period for obtaining the approval, permission or authorization from other agencies as prescribed by law or rules of practice.

8. Data submission format

- BE 2558: ... via a computer network of the Department of Industrial Works (DIW) or other system as prescribed by the Ministry of Industry [B.3]

9. Data confidentiality

- BE 2558: For imported products, foreign suppliers may consider using a local third-party agent to submit all info on behalf of importers to protect confidential business info.

10. Data that are published publicly

- TECI-2: CASRNs, chemical names, molecular formula, chemical group, type of hazardous substance, and chemical code (applies to substances notified between 2017 and 2020) for 11476 substances (as of July 2020) [A]
- Section 18: For the purpose of prevention and extinguishing of any harm which may happen to people, animals, plants, property or environment, the Minister of Industry... shall have the power to publish in the Government Gazette the name, or properties and category of hazardous substance, enforcement period and responsible agency for the control of such hazardous substance. [B.1]
- Section 36: The Minister of Industry ... shall publish in the Government Gazette the list of hazardous substances which are generally and clearly known that their production and nature may cause harm. [B.1]

11. International information exchange and sharing -- N.A.

S1.23 TK-REACH / KKDİK

Last update: 26 November 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. KİMYASALLARIN KAYDI, DEĞERLENDİRİLMESİ, İZİNİ VE KISITLANMASI HAKKINDA YÖNETMELİK (KKDİK, aka By-Law on Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals – Turkey REACH Regulation, June 2017): English version –
https://kimyasallar.csb.gov.tr/uploads/file/KKDİK%20ingilizce_29112019.doc (main text);
https://kimyasallar.csb.gov.tr/uploads/file/KKDİK_EKLER_İNG_29112019.DOCX (Annexes)
- B. MADDELERİN VE KARIŞIMLARIN SINIFLANDIRILMASI, ETİKETLENMESİ VE AMBALAJLANMASI HAKKINDA YÖNETMELİK (By-Law on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures, December 2013): English version –
<https://kimyasallar.csb.gov.tr/uploads/file/By-Law%20on%20CLP.docx> (main text);
https://kimyasallar.csb.gov.tr/uploads/file/CLP_By_law_Annexes%20all.docx (Annexes)
- C. MADDELERİN VE KARIŞIMLARIN FİZİKO-KİMYASAL, TOKSİKOLOJİK VE EKOTOKSİKOLOJİK ÖZELLİKLERİNİN BELİRLENMESİNDE UYGULANACAK TEST YÖNTEMLERİ HAKKINDA YÖNETMELİK (Regulation on the Test Methods to be Applied in Determining the Physico-Chemical, Toxicological and Ecotoxicological Properties of Substances and Mixtures, December 2013):
https://kimyasallar.csb.gov.tr/uploads/file/TestYontemleri_2020Aralik11.docx (main text; in Turkish)
- D. *Turkish Chemical Substance Inventory* by TURKREACH: <https://www.turkreach.com.tr/kkdik-turkreach-inventory>; https://0bd52e6b-f128-472f-8402-b4689cb3e3cd.filesusr.com/ugd/3cefc8_fa2d06217f1441beae0d236e6c2a0317.pdf; https://0bd52e6b-f128-472f-8402-b4689cb3e3cd.filesusr.com/ugd/3cefc8_9d6bd728c111447d998b786480e30542.pdf; https://0bd52e6b-f128-472f-8402-b4689cb3e3cd.filesusr.com/ugd/3cefc8_17328ffe4fb44f199fb598749de3acc6.pdf

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

- *Former Turkish chemical substance inventory is a list of chemical substances submitted by chemical manufacturers and importers under the Regulation on Inventory and Control of Chemicals (CICR). Since the CICR has been replaced by KKDİK regulation in 2017, this inventory is no longer meaningful and valid. [D]*
- Article 1 [A]: *The purpose of this Bylaw is to ensure a high level of protection of human health and the environment, including the promotion of alternative methods for assessment of hazards of substances while enhancing competitiveness and innovation.*
- According to KKDİK, the pre-registration phase ends on December 31, 2020. All substances that are placed on the market in volumes of 1 metric ton per year have to be pre-registered at the authority. As under EU REACH, the substance information exchange forums (SIEFs) are formed to enable the study data to be shared. Registration dossiers must be submitted by December 31, 2023. However, essential parts of the dossier have to be prepared by a certified chemical assessment expert.

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligations

Registration

- Article 6 [A]: *Subject to Articles 7 [general obligation to register substances on their own or in mixtures], 8 [registration and notification of substances in articles] and 21 [manufacturing and import of substances],*

substances on their own, in mixtures or in articles shall not be manufactured or placed on the market unless they have been registered in accordance with the relevant provisions of this Part

- Article 7(1) [A]: *Save where this Regulation provides otherwise, any manufacturer or importer of a substance, either on its own or in one or more mixture (s), in quantities of one ton[ne] or more per year shall submit a registration to the Ministry through Chemicals Registration System in the website of Ministry.*
- Article 7(3) [A]: *Any manufacturer or importer of a polymer shall submit a registration to the Ministry for the monomer substance(s) or any other substance(s), that have not already been registered by an actor up the supply chain, if both the following conditions are met:*
 - *The polymer consists of 2 % weight by weight (w/w) or more of such monomer substance(s) or other substance(s) in the form of monomeric units and chemically bound substance(s);*
 - *the total quantity of such monomer substance(s) or other substance(s) makes up one ton[ne] or more per year.*

Registration of on-site isolated intermediates

- Article 17(1) [A]: *Any manufacturer of an on-site isolated intermediate in quantities of one ton[ne] or more per year shall submit a registration to the Ministry through Chemicals Registration System in the website of Ministry for the on-site isolated intermediate.*

Registration of transported isolated intermediates

- Article 18(1) [A]: *Any manufacturer or importer of a transported isolated intermediate in quantities of one ton or more per year shall submit a registration to the Ministry through Chemicals Registration System in the website of Ministry for the transported isolated intermediate.*

Registration and notification of substances in Articles

- Article 8(1) [A]: *Any producer or importer of articles shall submit a registration ... for any substance contained in those articles, if both the following conditions are met:*
 - *the substance is present in those articles in quantities totaling over one ton[ne] per producer or importer per year*
 - *the substance is intended to be released under normal or reasonably foreseeable conditions of use.*
- Article 8(2) [A]: *Any producer or importer of Articles shall notify the Ministry ... if a substance meets the criteria in Article 47 [substances to be included in Annex XIV authorisation] and defined in the Article 49 [defining the substances in Article 47] if both the following conditions are met*
 - *the substance is present in those Articles in quantities totaling over one ton[ne] per producer or importer per year*
 - *the substance is present in those Articles above a concentration of 0.1 % weight by weight (w/w)*
 - *... shall apply six months after a substance is identified in accordance with Article 49(1)*
- Article 8(5) [A]: *The Ministry may take decisions requiring producers or importers of articles to submit a registration, for any substance in those articles, if all the following conditions are met:*
 - *The substance is present in those articles in quantities totalling over one ton[ne] per producer or importer per year*
 - *The Ministry has grounds for suspecting that*
 - *the substance is released from the articles, and*
 - *the release of the substance from the articles presents a risk to human health or the environment*
 - *the substance is not subject to paragraph 1*

Manufacturing and import of substances

- Article 21(1) [A]: *A registrant may start or continue the manufacture or import of a substance or production or import of an article, if there is no indication to the contrary from the Ministry in accordance with Article 20(2) [completeness check] within the three weeks after the submission date, without prejudice to Article 24(8).*
 - *In the case of an update of a registration according to Article 22, a registrant may continue the manufacture or import of the substance, or the production or import of the article, if there is no indication to the contrary from the Ministry in accordance with Article 20(2) within the three weeks after the update date, without prejudice to Article 24(8).*
 - *If the Ministry has informed the registrant that he is to submit further information the registrant may start the manufacture or import of a substance or production or import of an article if there is no indication to the contrary from the Ministry within the three weeks after receipt by the Ministry of the further information necessary to complete his registration, without prejudice to Article 24 (8).*

Obligation for downstream users to report information

- Article 34 [A]: *Before commencing or continuing with a particular use of a substance that has been registered by an actor up the supply chain in accordance with Articles 7 [general obligation to register substances on their own or in mixtures] or 18 [registration of transported isolated intermediates], the downstream user shall report to the Ministry the information specified in paragraph 2 of this Article, in [either of] the following cases*
 - *The downstream user has to prepare a chemical safety report in accordance with Article 33(4)¹⁹¹;*
 - *The downstream user is relying on the exemptions in Article 33(4)(c) or (e).*

Authorization and substitution

- Article 45 [A]: *All manufacturers, importers and downstream users applying for authorizations shall analyse the availability of alternatives and consider their risks, and the technical and economic feasibility of substitution.*
- Article 46(1) [A]: *A manufacturer, importer or downstream user shall not place a substance on the market for a use or use it himself if that substance is included in Annex XIV, unless [one of the followings]:*
 - *The use(s) of that substance on its own or in a mixture or the incorporation of the substance into an article for which the substance is placed on the market or for which he uses the substance himself has been authorized in accordance with Articles 50, 51, 52, 53, 54*

¹⁹¹ Article 33(4): *A downstream user of a substance on its own or in a mixture shall prepare a chemical safety report in accordance with Annex XII for any use outside the conditions described in an exposure scenario or if appropriate a use and exposure category communicated to him in a safety data sheet or for any use his supplier advises against. A downstream user need not prepare such a chemical safety report in any of the following cases:*

- *A safety data sheet is not required to be communicated with the substance or mixture in accordance with Article 27 [requirements for safety data sheets]*
- *A chemical safety report is not required to be completed by his supplier in accordance with Article 15 [chemical safety report and duty to apply and recommend risk reduction measures]*
- *The downstream user uses the substance or mixture in a total quantity of less than one ton[ne] per year*
- *The downstream user implements or recommends an exposure scenario which includes as a minimum the conditions described in the exposure scenario communicated to him in the safety data sheet*
- *The substance is present in a mixture in a concentration lower than any of the concentrations set out in Article 15(2) [see below]*
- *The downstream user is using the substance for the purposes of product and process oriented research and development, provided that the risks to human health and the environment are adequately controlled in accordance with the requirements of legislation for the protection of workers and the environment.*

- *The use(s) of that substance on its own or in a mixture or the incorporation of the substance into an article for which the substance is placed on the market or for which he uses the substance himself has been exempted from the authorization requirement in Annex 14 itself in accordance with Article 48(2)*
- *The date referred to in Article 48(1)(c)(1) has not been reached*
- *The date referred to in Article 48(1)(c)(1) has been reached and he made an application 18 months before that date but a decision on the application for authorization has not yet been taken*
- *In cases where the substance is placed on the market, authorization for that use has been granted to his immediate downstream user.*
- Article 46(2) [A]: *A downstream user may use a substance meeting the criteria set out in paragraph 1 provided that the use is in accordance with the conditions of an authorization granted to an actor up his supply chain for that use.*
 - Article 56 [A]: *Downstream users using a substance in accordance with Article 46(2) shall notify the Ministry within 90 days of the first supply of the substance. The Ministry shall establish and keep up to date a register of downstream users who have made a notification in accordance with paragraph 1.*

Restriction

- Article 57 [A]: *A substance on its own, in a mixture or in an article, for which Annex 17 contains a restriction shall not be manufactured, placed on the market or used unless it complies with the conditions of that restriction.*

3.2 Exemptions

Article 2(2) [A]: [KKDIK] *shall not apply to the substances and mixtures below*

- *Radioactive substances and mixtures within the scope of Bylaw on the Safe Transportation of Radioactive Substances published in the Official Gazette dated 08/07/2005 and numbered 25869*
- *Substances, on their own, in a mixture or in an Article, which are subject to customs supervision, provided that they do not undergo any treatment or processing, and which are in temporary storage, or in a free zone or free warehouse with a view to re-exportation, or in transit*
- *Non-isolated intermediates*
- *The carriage of hazardous substances and hazardous mixtures by rail, road, inland waterway, sea or air*
- *Wastes in the scope of the Bylaw on Waste Management published in the Official Gazette dated 02/04/2015 and numbered 29314 and Bylaw on Radioactive Waste Management published in the Official Gazette dated 09/03/2013 and numbered 28882.*
- *Substances and mixtures which are manufactured or imported for the purpose of defense*

Article 2(3) [A]: *The provisions of Second Part [Registration], Fifth Part [Downstream Users], Sixth [Evaluation] and Seventh Part [Authorization] shall not apply to the substances manufactured or imported in order to use in the products below:*

- *Medicinal products for human or veterinary use within the scope of Bylaw on the Licencing of Medicinal Products for Human Use published in the Official Gazette dated 19/01/2005 and numbered 25705, Bylaw on the Packaging and Labelling of Medicinal Products for Human Use published in the Official Gazette dated 12/08/2005 and numbered 25904 and Bylaw on Veterinary Medicinal Products published in the Official Gazette dated 24/12/2012 and dated and numbered 28152*
- *Food within the scope of the Bylaw on Turkish Food Codex published in the Official Gazette dated 29/12/2011 and numbered 28157*

- *Feeding stuffs within the scope of the Bylaw on Placing on the Market and Use of Feeding Stuffs published in the Official Gazette dated 27/12/2011 and numbered 28155*

Article 2(4) [A]: *The provisions of Fourth Part [Information in the supply chain] shall not apply to the extent the following mixtures in the finished state, intended for the final user:*

- *Medicinal products for human or veterinary use within the scope of Bylaw on the Licencing of Medicinal Products for Human Use published in the Official Gazette dated 19/01/2005 and numbered 25705, Bylaw on the Packaging and Labelling of Medicinal Products for Human Use and published in the Official Gazette dated 12/08/2005 and numbered 25904 and Bylaw on Veterinary Medicinal Products published in the Official Gazette dated 24/12/2012 and numbered 28152*
- *Cosmetic products within the scope of Bylaw on Cosmetics published in the Official Gazette dated 23/05/2005 and numbered 25823*
- *Invasive medical devices or medical devices which can be used in direct physical contact with the human body*
- *Feeding stuffs within the scope of the Bylaw on Placing on the Market and Use of Feeding Stuffs published in the Official Gazette dated 27/12/2011 and numbered 28155*
- *Food within the scope of the Bylaw on Turkish Food Codex published in the Official Gazette dated 29/12/2011 and numbered 28157*

Article 2(5) [A]: *The following shall be exempted from the provisions of Second Part [Registration], Fifth Part [Downstream Users] and Sixth Part [Evaluation]:*

- *Substances included in Annex IV¹⁹²*
- *Substances included in Annex V¹⁹³*

¹⁹² *D-glucitol; ascorbic acid; glucose; fructose; L-lysine; sucrose; α -tocopheryl acetate; galactose; DL-methionine; lactose; D-mannitol; L-sorbose; glycerol stearate; carbon dioxide; calcium pantothenate; DL-phenylalanine; sodium gluconate; sorbitan oleate; krypton; neon; argon; helium; xenon; nitrogen; water; lecithins; syrups, hydrolyzed starch; tallow, hydrogenated; dextrin; starch; maltodextrin; sodium D-gluconate; D-glucitol monostearate; fatty acids, coco, Me esters; cellulose pulp; glycerides, C₁₆₋₁₈ and C₁₈-unsaturated; syrups, corn, dehydrated; glycerides, tallow mono-, di- and tri-, hydrogenated; glycerides, C₁₆₋₁₈ and C₁₈-unsaturated, mono- and di-; glycerides, C₁₀₋₁₈ [A]*

¹⁹³ Annex V [A]

- *Substances which result from a chemical reaction that occurs incidental to exposure of another substance or article to environmental factors such as air, moisture, microbial organisms or sunlight*
- *Substances which result from a chemical reaction that occurs incidental to storage of another substance, mixture or article*
- *Substances which result from a chemical reaction occurring upon end use of other substances, mixtures or articles and which are not themselves manufactured, imported or placed on the market*
- *Substances which are not themselves manufactured, imported or placed on the market and which result from a chemical reaction that occurs when:*
 - *a stabiliser, colorant, flavouring agent, antioxidant, filler, solvent, carrier, surfactant, plasticiser, corrosion inhibitor, antifoamer or defoamer, dispersant, precipitation inhibitor, desiccant, binder, emulsifier, de-emulsifier, dewatering agent, agglomerating agent, adhesion promoter, flow modifier, pH neutraliser, sequesterant, coagulant, flocculant, fire retardant, lubricant, chelating agent, or quality control reagent functions as intended; or*
 - *a substance solely intended to provide a specific physicochemical characteristic functions as intended.*
- *By-products, unless they are imported or placed on the market themselves*
- *Hydrates of a substance or hydrated ions, formed by association of a substance with water, provided that the substance has been registered by the manufacturer or importer using this exemption*

- *Substances on their own or in mixtures, registered in accordance with Second Part, exported from Turkey by an actor in the supply chain and re-imported into Turkey by the same or another actor in the same supply chain who proves that*
 - *The substance being re-imported is the same as the exported substance*
 - *He has been provided with the information in accordance with Articles 27 [requirements for safety data sheets] or 28 [duty to communicate information down the supply chain for substances on their own or in mixtures for which a safety data sheet is not required] relating to the exported substance.*
- *Substances, on their own, in mixtures or in articles, which have been registered in accordance with Second Part [registration] and which are recovered in Turkey if:*
 - *The substance that results from the recovery process is the same as the substance that has been registered in accordance with Second Part; and*
 - *The information required by Articles 27 or 28 relating to the substance that has been registered in accordance with Second Part is available to the establishment undertaking the recovery.*

Article 2(6) [A]: *Section I of Second Part [Information Requirements and General Obligation to Register], with the exception of Articles 9 [only representative] and 10 [exemption from the general obligation to register for product and process orientated research and development (PPORD)]¹⁹⁴; and Seventh Part [Authorization] shall not be applied to the on-site isolated intermediates and transported isolated intermediates.*

-
- *The following substances which occur in nature, if they are not chemically modified: Minerals, ores, ore concentrates, raw and processed natural gas, crude oil, coal.*
 - *Substances which occur in nature other than those listed under paragraph 7, if they are not chemically modified, unless they meet the criteria for classification as dangerous according to By-law on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures or unless they are persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic or very persistent and very bioaccumulative in accordance with the criteria set out in Annex XIII or unless they were identified in accordance with Article 49(1) at least two years previously as substances giving rise to an equivalent level of concern as set out in Article 47(1)(f).*
 - *The following substances obtained from natural sources, if they are not chemically modified, unless they meet the criteria for classification as dangerous according to By-law Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures with the exception of those classified as flammable liquid and vapour (H224, H225, H226), skin irritant (H315) or eye irritant (H319) or unless they are persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic or very persistent and very bioaccumulative in accordance with the criteria set out in Annex XIII or unless they were identified in accordance with Article 49(1) at least two years previously as substances giving rise to an equivalent level of concern as set out in Article 47(1)(e): Vegetable fats, vegetable oils, vegetable waxes; animal fats, animal oils, animal waxes; fatty acids from C₆ to C₂₄ and their potassium, sodium, calcium and magnesium salts; glycerol.*
 - *The following substances if they are not chemically modified: Liquefied petroleum gas, natural gas condensate, process gases and components thereof, coke, cement clinker, magnesia.*
 - *The following substances unless they meet the criteria for classification as hazardous according to By-law on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures and provided that they do not contain constituents meeting the criteria as hazardous in accordance with By-law on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures present in concentrations above the lowest of the applicable concentration limits or concentration limits set out in Annex 2 to same By-law, unless conclusive scientific experimental data show that these constituents are not available throughout the lifecycle of the substance and those data have been ascertained to be adequate and reliable: Glass, ceramic frits.*
 - *Compost and biogas.*
 - *Hydrogen and oxygen.*

¹⁹⁴ Any scientific development related to product development or the further development of a substance, on its own, in mixtures or in articles in the course of which pilot plant or production trials are used to develop the production process and/or to test the fields of application of the substance [A]

Article 2(7) [A]: *The provisions of the Second [Registration], and Sixth Part [Evaluation] shall not apply to the polymers¹⁹⁵.*

Registration

- Article 7(2) [A]: *For monomers that are used as on-site isolated intermediates or transported isolated intermediates, Articles 17 [Registration of on-site isolated intermediates] and 18 [Registration of transported isolated intermediates] shall not apply.*

Substances regarded as being registered (Article 16 [A])

- *Active substances and co-formulants manufactured or imported for use in plant protection products only and included in the Bylaw on Licensing of Plant Protection Products published in the Official Gazette dated 25/03/2011 numbered 27885 and Bylaw on the Classification, Packaging and Labelling of Plant Protection Products published in the Official Gazette dated 23/03/2010 and numbered 27530 shall be regarded as being registered and the registration as completed for manufacture or import for the use as a plant protection product and therefore as fulfilling the requirements of Section 1 of Part 2.*
- *Active substances manufactured or imported for use in biocidal products only and included in Bylaw on Biocidal Products published in the Official Gazette dated 31/12/2009 numbered 27449 (4th bis) on the placing of biocidal products on the market, shall be regarded as being registered and the registration as completed for manufacture or import for the use in a biocidal product and therefore as fulfilling the requirements of Section 1 of this Part.*

Registration and notification of substances in Articles

- Article 8(3) [A]: *Paragraph 2 shall NOT apply where the producer or importer can exclude exposure to humans or the environment during normal or reasonably foreseeable conditions of use including disposal. In such cases, the producer or importer shall supply appropriate instructions to the recipient of the article.*
- Article 8(6) [A]: *Paragraphs 1 to 5 shall not apply to substances that have already been registered for that use.*

Exemption from the general obligation to register for product and process orientated research and development (PPORD)

- Article 10(1) [A]: *Articles 6 [placing of the substances on the market], 7 [general obligations to register substances on their own or in mixtures], 8 [registration and notification of substances in articles], 17 [registration of on-site isolated intermediates], 18 [registration of transported isolated intermediates] and 21 [manufacturing and import of substances] shall not apply for a period of five years to a substance manufactured in the Turkey or imported for the purposes of product and process orientated research and development by a manufacturer or importer or producer of articles, by himself or in cooperation with listed customers and in a quantity which is limited to the purpose of product and process orientated research and development.*

¹⁹⁵ A substance consisting of molecules characterised by the sequence of one or more types of monomer units, distributed over a range of molecular weights wherein differences in the molecular weight are primarily attributable to differences in the number of monomer units and comprises the following

- *A simple weight majority of molecules containing at least three monomer units which are covalently bound to at least one other monomer unit or other reactant; and*
- *Less than a simple weight majority of molecules of the same molecular weight [A]*

- Article 10(5) [A]: *In the absence of any indication to the contrary, the manufacturer or importer of the substance or the producer or importer of articles may manufacture or import the substance or produce or import the articles not earlier than two weeks after the notification.*
- Article 10(6) [A]: *The Ministry may decide to extend the five-year exemption period by a further maximum of five years or, in the case of substances to be used exclusively in the development of medicinal products for human or veterinary use, or for substances that are not placed on the market, for a further maximum of ten years, upon request if the manufacturer or importer or producer of articles can demonstrate that such an extension is justified by the research and development program.*

Authorization and substitution (Article 46 [A])

- *... shall not apply to the use of substances in scientific research and development. Annex IV shall specify if [authorization requirements] apply to product and process orientated research and development as well as the maximum quantity exempted.*
- *... shall not apply to the following uses of substances:*
 - *Uses in plant protection products within the scope of Bylaw on the Classification, Packaging and Labelling of Plant Protection Products*
 - *Uses in biocidal products within the scope of Bylaw on Biocidal Products*
 - *Use as motor fuels covered by Bylaw on Environmental Effects of Motor Fuels and Diesel Fuels Types; published in the Official Gazette dated 01/04/2017 and numbered 30025*
 - *Uses as fuel in mobile or fixed combustion plants of mineral oil products and use as fuels in closed systems*
- *In the case of substances that are subject to authorization only because they meet the criteria in Article 47 (1) (a) [C], (b) [M] or (c) [R] or because they are identified in accordance with Article 47 (1) (e) [substance of equivalent concern] only because of hazards to human health, [authorization requirements] shall not apply to the following uses:*
 - *Uses in cosmetic products within the scope of Bylaw on Cosmetics*
- *Uses in food contact materials within the scope of Bylaw on the Turkish Food Codex Substances and Materials in Contact with Food Paragraphs 1 and 2 shall not apply to the use of substances when they are present in mixtures:*
 - *For substances referred to in Article 47 (1) (ç), (d) and (e), below a concentration limit of 0,1 % weight by weight (w/w)*
 - *For all other substances, below the lowest of the concentration limits specified in Annex 6, Section 3 of Bylaw on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures which result in the classification of the mixture as hazardous.*

Restriction (Article 57 [A])

- *This shall not apply to the manufacture, placing on the market or use of a substance in scientific research and development. Annex 17 shall specify if the restriction shall not apply to product and process orientated research and development, as well as the maximum quantity exempted.*
- *Paragraph 1 shall not apply to the use of substances in cosmetic products, as defined by Bylaw on Cosmetics with regard to restrictions addressing the risks to human health within the scope of that Bylaw.*

Introducing new and amending current restrictions (Article 58 [A])

- *The first subparagraph shall not apply to the use of a substance as an on-site isolated intermediate.*

4. Initial data requirements

General registration (Article 11(1)) [A]

- *A technical dossier*¹⁹⁶ including:
 - *The identity of the manufacturer(s) or importer(s) as specified in section 1 of Annex VI*
 - *The identity of the substance as specified in section 2 of Annex VI*
 - *Name of other identifier of each substance*
 - *name(s) in the IUPAC nomenclature or other international chemical name(s)*
 - *other names (usual name, trade name, abbreviation)*
 - *EINECS or ELINCS number (if available and appropriate)*
 - *CAS name and CASRN (if available)*
 - *other identity code (if available)*
 - *Information related to molecular and structural formula of each substance*
 - *Molecular and structural formula (including SMILES notation, if available)*
 - *Information on optical activity and typical ratio of (stereo) isomers (if applicable and appropriate)*
 - *Molecular weight or molecular weight range*
 - *Composition of each substance*
 - *Degree of purity (%)*
 - *Nature of impurities, including isomers and by-products*
 - *Percentage of (significant) main impurities*
 - *Nature and order of magnitude (... ppm, ... %) of any additives (e.g. stabilising agents or inhibitors)*
 - *Spectral data (ultra-violet, infra-red, nuclear magnetic resonance or mass spectrum)*
 - *High-pressure liquid chromatogram, gas chromatogram*

¹⁹⁶ *The technical dossier ... shall include under points (6) [study summaries] and (7) [robust study summaries] of that provision all physicochemical, toxicological and ecotoxicological information that is relevant and available to the registrant and as a minimum the following: [A]*

- For substances meeting at least one of the criteria specified in Annex III, manufactured or imported in quantities of one tonne or more per year per manufacturer or importer: *The information specified in Annex VII*
 - *substances for which it is predicted (i.e. by the application of (Q)SARs or other evidence) that they are likely to meet the criteria for category 1A or 1B classification in the hazard classes carcinogenicity, germ cell mutagenicity or reproductive toxicity or the criteria in Annex XIII;*
 - *substances:*
 - *with dispersive or diffuse use(s) particularly where such substances are used in consumer 3 mixtures or incorporated into consumer articles; and*
 - *for which it is predicted (i.e. by application of (Q)SARs or other evidence) that they are likely to meet the classification criteria for any health or environmental hazard classes or differentiations under [B]*
- For substances manufactured or imported in quantities of one ton[ne] or more per year per manufacturer or importer which do not meet either of the criteria specified in Annex 3: *The information on physicochemical properties specified in Annex VII, section 7*
- For substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 10 tonnes or more per year per manufacturer or importer: *The information specified in Annexes VII and VIII*
- For substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 100 tonnes or more per year per manufacturer or importer: *The information specified in Annexes VII and VIII and testing proposals for the provision of the information specified in Annex IX*
- For substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 1000 tonnes or more per year per manufacturer or importer: *Testing proposals for the provision of the information specified in Annexes VII and VIII and testing proposals for the provision of the information specified in Annexes IX and X*
- *This Article shall apply to producers of articles adapted as necessary.*

- *Description of the analytical methods or the appropriate bibliographical references for the identification of the substance and, where appropriate, for the identification of impurities and additives. This information shall be sufficient to allow the methods to be reproduced.*
- *Information on the manufacture and use(s) of the substance as specified in section 3 of Annex VI; this information shall represent all the registrant's identified use(s). This information may include, if the registrant deems appropriate, the relevant use and exposure categories*
 - *Overall manufacture, quantities used for production of an article that is subject to registration, and/or imports in tonnes per registrant per year in: the calendar year of the registration (estimated quantity)*
 - *In the case of a manufacturer or producer of articles: brief description of the technological process used in manufacture or production of articles. Precise details of the process, particularly those of a commercially sensitive nature, are not required.*
 - *An indication of the tonnage used for his own use(s)*
 - *Form (substance, mixture or article) and/or physical state under which the substance is made available to downstream users. Concentration or concentration range of the substance in mixtures made available to downstream users and quantities of the substance in articles made available to downstream users.*
 - *Brief general description of the identified use(s)*
 - *Information on waste quantities and composition of waste resulting from manufacture of the substance, the use in articles and identified uses*
 - *Uses advised against (see Section 1.2 of the safety data sheet) Where applicable, an indication of the uses which the registrant advises against and why (i.e. non-statutory recommendations by supplier). This need not be an exhaustive list.*
- *The classification and labelling of the substance as specified in section 4 of Annex VI [B]*
- *Guidance on safe use of the substance as specified in Section 5 of Annex VI*
- *Study summaries¹⁹⁷ of the information derived from the application of Annexes VII to XI*
 - *Annex VII Standard information requirements for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of one tonne or more*
 - *Annex VIII Standard information requirements for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 10 tonnes or more*
 - *Annex IX Standard information requirements for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 1000 tonne or more*
 - *Annex X Standard information requirements for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of one tonne or more*
 - *Annex XI General rules for adaptation of the standard testing regime set out in Annexes VII to X, including testing does not appear scientifically necessary (use of existing data, weight of evidence, qualitative or quantitative structure-activity relationship ((Q)SAR), in vitro methods, grouping of substances and read-across approach), testing is technically not possible, substance-tailor exposure-driven testing,*

¹⁹⁷ A summary of the objectives, methods, results and conclusions of a full study report providing sufficient information to make an assessment of the relevance of the study [A]

- Robust study summaries¹⁹⁸ of the information derived from the application of Annexes VII to XI¹⁹⁹

¹⁹⁸ A detailed summary of the objectives, methods, results and conclusions of a full study report providing sufficient information to make an independent assessment of the study minimising the need to consult the full study report [A]

¹⁹⁹ Article 13(1) [A]: The technical dossier ... shall include under [study summaries] and [robust study summaries] all physicochemical, toxicological and ecotoxicological information that is relevant and available to the registrant and as a minimum the following:

- The information specified in Annex VII for substances meeting at least one of the criteria specified in Annex 3, manufactured or imported in quantities of one ton[ne] or more per year per manufacturer or importer
 - substances for which it is predicted (i.e. by the application of (Q)SARs or other evidence) that they are likely to meet the criteria for category IA or IB classification in the hazard classes carcinogenicity, germ cell mutagenicity or reproductive toxicity or the criteria in Annex XIII;
 - substances: with dispersive or diffuse use(s) particularly where such substances are used in consumer 3 mixtures or incorporated into consumer articles; and for which it is predicted (i.e. by application of (Q)SARs or other evidence) that they are likely to meet the classification criteria for any health or environmental hazard classes or differentiations under By-law on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures.
- The information on physicochemical properties specified in Annex VII, section 7 for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of one ton[ne] or more per year per manufacturer or importer which do not meet either of the criteria specified in Annex 3
- The information specified in Annex VII and VIII for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 10 ton[ne]s or more per year per manufacturer or importer
- The information specified in Annexes VII and VIII and testing proposals for the provision of the information specified in Annex IX for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 100 ton[ne]s or more per year per manufacturer or importer
- Testing proposals for the provision of the information specified in Annexes VII and VIII and testing proposals for the provision of the information specified in Annexes IX and X for substances manufactured or imported in quantities of 1 000 ton[ne]s or more per year per manufacturer or importer.

Article 14 [A]: Information on intrinsic properties of substances may be generated by means other than tests, provided that the conditions set out in Annex XI are met. In particular for human toxicity, information shall be generated whenever possible by means other than vertebrate animal tests, through the use of alternative methods, for example, in vitro methods or qualitative or quantitative structure-activity relationship models or from information from structurally related substances (grouping or read-across). Testing in accordance with Annex VIII, Sections 8.6 and 8.7, Annex IX and Annex X may be omitted where justified by information on exposure and implemented risk management measures as specified in Annex XI.

- Annex XI includes: testing does not appear scientifically necessary (use of existing data, weight of evidence, qualitative or quantitative structure-activity relationship ((Q)SAR), in vitro methods, grouping of substances and read-across approach), testing is technically not possible, substance-tailored exposure-driven testing
- These methods shall be regularly reviewed and improved with a view to reducing testing on vertebrate animals and the number of animals involved
- Where tests on substances are required to generate information on intrinsic properties of substances, they shall be conducted in accordance with the Bylaw on the Test Methods to Apply on Specifying the Physico-Chemical, Toxicological, and Eco-Toxicological Properties of the Substances and the Mixtures published in the Official Gazette dated 11/12/2013 and numbered 28848 (bis) [C]. The information on the intrinsic properties of chemical substances can be provided by the other test methods provided that the conditions are met under Annex XI.
- Ecotoxicological and toxicological tests shall be carried out in compliance with Bylaw on the Principles of Good Laboratory Practice, Harmonization of Test Units, Inspection of Good Laboratory Practice and Work published in the Official Gazette dated 9/3/2010 and numbered 27516.
- If a substance has already been registered, a new registrant shall be entitled to refer to the study summaries or robust study summaries, for the same substance submitted earlier, provided that he can

- *an indication as to which of the information submitted under (3), (4), (6), (7) or subparagraph (b) has been reviewed by an chemical assessment expert chosen by the manufacturer or importer and certified according to Annex 18 of this Bylaw*
 - *Annex 18 conditions for receiving certificate of competency of chemical assessment expert*
- *Proposals for testing where listed in Annexes IX and X*
- *For substances in quantities of 1 to 10 ton[nes], exposure information as specified in section 6 of Annex VI*
 - *Main use category*
 - *Industrial uses; and/or professional use; and/or*
 - *Used in closed system; and/or*
 - *Used resulting in inclusion into or onto matrix; and/or*
 - *Non-dispersive use; and/or*
 - *Dispersive use*
 - *Consumer use*
 - *Significant route(s) of exposure*
 - *Human exposure: oral; dermal; and/or inhalatory*
 - *Environmental exposure: water; air; solid waste; and/or soil*
 - *Pattern of exposure: accidental/infrequent; occasional; and/or continuous/frequent*
- *a request as to which of the information in Article 61(2) [public access] the manufacturer or importer considers should not be made available on the Internet including a justification as to why publication could be harmful for his or any other concerned party's commercial interests.*

show that the substance that he is now registering is the same as the one previously registered, including the degree of purity and the nature of impurities, and that the previous registrant(s) have given permission to refer to the full study reports for the purpose of registration. A new registrant shall not refer to such studies in order to provide the information required in Section 2 of Annex 6.

Article 23: In order to avoid animal testing, testing on vertebrate animals for the purposes of this Bylaw shall be undertaken only as a last resort. It is also necessary to take measures limiting duplication of other tests.

- *The sharing and joint submission of information in accordance with this Bylaw shall concern technical data and in particular information related to the intrinsic properties of substances. Registrants shall refrain from exchanging information concerning their market behaviour, in particular as regards production capacities, production or sales volumes, import volumes or market shares.*
- *Any study summaries or robust study summaries of studies submitted in the framework of a registration at least 12 years previously can be used for the purposes of registration by another manufacturer or importer.*

Article 24: Every potential registrant of a substance shall inquire from the Ministry through Chemicals Registration System in the website of Ministry from 31/12/2023 whether a registration has already been submitted for the same substance...

- *Where a substance has previously been registered less than 12 years earlier, potential registrant shall require necessary information with respect to the Article 11 (a) (6) and (7) from the previous registrant(s) in order to register*
 - *Shall, in the case of information involving tests on vertebrate animals; and*
 - *May, in the case of information not involving tests on vertebrate animals.*
- *When a request for information has been made according to paragraph 1, the potential and the previous registrant(s) as referred to in paragraph 1 shall make every effort to reach an agreement on the sharing of the information requested by the potential registrant(s) with respect to Article 11 (a) (6) and (7).*

Article 25 on Substance Information Exchange Forums (SIEF); Article 26: Sharing of data involving tests within SIEF

- *A chemical safety report when required under Article 15 [For substances in quantities of 10 tonnes or more per year per registrant], in the format specified in Annex I. The relevant sections of this report may include, if the registrant considers appropriate, the relevant use and exposure categories.*
 - *Annex I General provisions for assessing substances and preparing chemical safety reports*
 - *Article 15(2): A chemical safety assessment ... need not be performed for a substance which is present in a mixture if the concentration of the substance in the mixture is less than the lowest of any of the following*
 - *The concentration threshold values that have been set Article 13 of Bylaw on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures published in the Official Gazette dated 11/12/2013 and numbered 28848.*
 - *0,1 % weight by weight (w/w), if the substance meets the criteria in Annex 13 of this Bylaw.*
 - *A chemical safety assessment of a substance shall include the following steps*
 - *Human health hazard assessment*
 - *Physicochemical hazard assessment*
 - *Environmental hazard assessment*
 - *PBT and vPvB assessment*
 - *If ... the registrant concludes that the substance fulfils the criteria of PBT or vPvB or any of the following hazard classes or categories set out in Annex 1 to the Bylaw on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures, the substance includes chemical safety assessment exposure scenarios or exposure scenario assessment including specifying the exposure scenario categories and exposure scenario assumptions and the risk characterization. The exposure scenarios (where appropriate the use and exposure categories), exposure assessment and risk characterisation shall address all identified uses of the registrant.*
 - *Hazard classes 2.1 to 2.4, 2.6 and 2.7, 2.8 types A and B, 2.9, 2.10, 2.12, 2.13 categories 1 and 2, 2.14 categories 1 and 2, 2.15 types A to F*
 - *Hazard classes 3.1 to 3.6, 3.7 adverse effects on sexual function and fertility or on development, 3.8 effects other than narcotic effects, 3.9 and 3.10*
 - *Hazard class 4.1*
 - *Hazard class 5.1*
 - *The chemical safety report need not include consideration of the risks to human health from the following end uses*
 - *In food contact materials within the scope Bylaw on the Turkish Food Codex Substances and Materials in Contact with Food published in the Official Gazette dated 29/12/2011 and numbered 28157*
 - *In cosmetic products within the scope of Bylaw on Cosmetics*
 - *Any registrant shall identify and apply the appropriate measures to adequately control the risks identified in the chemical safety assessment, and where suitable, recommend them in the Safety Data Sheets which he supplies in accordance with Article 27.*
 - *Any registrant required to conduct a chemical safety assessment shall keep his chemical safety report available and up to date.*
- *Save the cases in the scope of Article 23(3), Article 24(7) or Article 26(3), the registrant shall have the legal ownership or the right to refer to the summarised full study report intended for registration according to paragraphs (1)(a)(6) and (1)(a)(7).*

Registration of on-site isolated intermediates²⁰⁰

- Article 17(2) [A]: A registration for an on-site isolated intermediate shall include all the following information, to the extent that the manufacturer is able to submit it without any additional testing:
 - The identity of the manufacturer as specified in Section 1 of Annex VI
 - The identity of the intermediate as specified in Sections 2.1 to 2.3.4 of Annex VI
 - The classification of the intermediate as specified in Section 4 of Annex VI
 - Any available existing information on physicochemical, human health or environmental properties of the intermediate. Where a full study report is available, a study summary shall be submitted
 - Registrant shall have permission to the ownership or the right to refer to the full study report for purpose of registration
 - A brief general description of the use, as specified in Section 3.5 of Annex IV
 - Details of the risk management measures applied.

Registration of transported isolated intermediates²⁰¹

- Article 18(2) [A]: A registration for a transported isolated intermediate shall include all the following information
 - The identity of the manufacturer or importer as specified in Section 1 of Annex VI
 - The identity of the intermediate as specified in Sections 2.1 to 2.3.4 of Annex VI
 - The classification of the intermediate as specified in Section 4 of Annex VI
 - Any available existing information on physicochemical, human health or environmental properties of the intermediate. Where a full study report is available, a study summary shall be submitted
 - A brief general description of the use, as specified in Section 3.5 of Annex VI
 - Information on risk management measures applied and recommended to the user in accordance with paragraph 4
- Article 18(3) [A]: A registration for a transported isolated intermediate in quantities of more than 1000 ton[nes] per year per manufacturer or importer shall include the information specified in Annex VII in

²⁰⁰ Article 17(3) [A]: ... shall apply only to on-site isolated intermediates if the manufacturer confirms that the substance is only manufactured and used under strictly controlled conditions in that it is rigorously contained by technical means during its whole lifecycle. Control and procedural technologies shall be used to minimise emission and any resulting exposure. If these conditions are not fulfilled, the registration shall include the information specified in Article 11 [general registration].

²⁰¹ Article 18(4) [A]: ... shall apply only to transported isolated intermediates if the manufacturer or importer confirms himself or states that he has received confirmation from the user that the synthesis of (an)other substance(s) from that intermediate takes place on other sites under the following strictly controlled conditions:

- The substance is rigorously contained by technical means during its whole lifecycle including manufacture, purification, cleaning and maintenance of equipment, sampling, analysis, loading and unloading of equipment or vessels, waste disposal or purification and storage. If these conditions are not fulfilled, the registration shall include the information specified under Article 11
- Procedural and control technologies shall be used that minimize emission and any resulting exposure
- Only properly trained and authorized personnel handle the substance
- In the case of cleaning and maintenance works, special procedures such as purging and washing are applied before the system is opened and entered
- In cases of accident and where waste is generated, procedural and/or control technologies are used to minimize emissions and the resulting exposure during purification or cleaning and maintenance procedures
- Substance-handling procedures are well documented and strictly supervised by the site operator.

addition to the information required under paragraph 2. For the generation of this information, Article 14 [general requirements for generation of information on intrinsic properties of substances] shall apply.

Registration and notification of substances in Articles

- Article 8(4) [A]: *The information to be notified shall include the following*
 - *The identity and contact details of the producer or importer as specified in section 1 of Annex 6, with the exception of their own use sites*
 - *The registration number(s) referred to in Article 20(1), if available*
 - *The identity of the substance as specified in sections 2.1 to 2.3.4 of Annex 6*
 - *Classification of the substance(s) as specified in sections 4.1 and 4.2 of Annex 6*
 - *A brief description of the use(s) of the substance(s) in the article as specified in section 3.5 of Annex 6 and of the uses of the article(s)*
 - *The tonnage range of the substance(s) (1-10 tonnes; 10-100 tonnes; 100-1000 tonnes, and more than 1000 tonnes)*

Exemption from the general obligation to register for product and process orientated research and development (PPORD)

- Article 10(2) [A]: *... the manufacturer or importer or producer of articles shall notify the Ministry of the following information:*
 - *The identity of the manufacturer or importer or producer of articles as specified in section 1 of Annex 6*
 - *The identity of the substance, as specified in section 2 of Annex 6*
 - *The classification of the substance as specified in section 4 of Annex 6, if any*
 - *The estimated quantity as specified in section 3.1 of Annex 6*
 - *The list of customers referred to in paragraph 1, including their names and addresses*

Obligation for downstream users to report information

- Article 34(2) [A]: *The information reported by the downstream user shall include the following:*
 - *His identity and contact details as specified in Section 1.1 of Annex VI*
 - *The registration number(s) referred to in Article 20(3), if available*
 - *The identity of the substance(s) as specified in Section 2.1 to 2.3.4 of Annex VI*
 - *The identity of the manufacturer(s) or the importer(s) or other supplier as specified in Section 1.1 of Annex VI*
 - *A brief general description of the use(s), as specified in Section 3.5 of Annex VI, and of the conditions of use(s);*
 - *Except where the downstream user is relying on the exemption in Article 33(4)(c) [low volume], a proposal for additional testing on vertebrate animals, where this is considered necessary by the downstream user to complete his chemical safety assessment.*

Applications for authorizations

- Article 52 [A]: *An application for an authorization shall be made to the Ministry through Chemicals Registration System in the website of Ministry.*
 - *Applications for authorization may be made by the manufacturer(s), importer(s) and/or downstream user(s) of the substance. Applications may be made by one or several persons.*
 - *Applications may be made for one or several substances that meet the definition of a group of substances in Section 1.5 of Annex XI, and for one or several uses. Applications may be made for the applicant's own use(s) and/or for uses for which he intends to place the substance on the market.*
- *An application for authorization shall include the following information*

- *The identity of the substance(s), as referred to in Section 2 of Annex IV*
- *The name and contact details of the person or persons making the application*
- *A request for authorization, specifying for which use(s) the authorization is sought*
- *Unless already submitted as part of the registration, a chemical safety report in accordance with Annex 1 covering the risks to human health and/or the environment from the use of the substance(s) arising from the intrinsic properties specified in Annex XIV*
- *An analysis of the alternatives considering their risks and the technical and economic feasibility of substitution and including, if appropriate information about any relevant research and development activities by the applicant*
- *Where the analysis referred to in paragraph (d) shows that suitable alternatives are available, taking into account the elements in Article 50(5), a substitution plan including a timetable for proposed actions by the applicant.*
- *The application may include:*
 - *A socio-economic analysis conducted in accordance with Annex XVI;*
 - *A justification for not considering risks to human health and the environment arising either from*
 - *Emissions of a substance from an installation for which a permit was granted; or*
 - *Discharges of a substance from a point source governed by the requirement for prior regulation.*
- *The application shall not include the risks to human health arising from the use of a substance in a medical device in the scope of Bylaw on Medical Devices published in the Official Gazette dated 07/06/2011 and numbered 27957, Bylaw on Invasive Active Medical Devices published in the Official Gazette dated 07/06/2011 and numbered 27957 and Bylaw on Medical Diagnosis Devices Which Are Used Outside The Body (In vitro) published in the Official Gazette dated 09/01/2007 and numbered 26398.*

5. Information updates by companies

Registration

- *Article 13(2) [A]: As soon as the quantity of a substance per manufacturer or importer that has already been registered reaches the next tonnage threshold, the manufacturer or importer shall inform the Ministry in twenty working days of the additional information he would require under paragraph 1.*

New information / Update

- *Article 22(1) [A]: Following registration, a registrant shall be responsible on his own initiative for updating his registration without undue delay with relevant new information and submitting it to the Ministry in the following cases:*
 - *Any change in his status, such as being a manufacturer, an importer or a producer of Articles, or in his identity, such as his name or address*
 - *Any change in the composition of the substance as given in Section 2 of Annex VI;*
 - *Changes in the annual or total quantities manufactured or imported by him or in the quantities of substances present in Articles produced or imported by him if these result in a change of tonnage band, including cessation of manufacture or import*
 - *New identified uses and new uses advised against as in Section 3.7 of Annex VI for which the substance is manufactured or imported*
 - *New knowledge of the risks of the substance to human health and/or the environment of which he may reasonably be expected to have become aware which leads to changes in the safety data sheet or the chemical safety report*
 - *Any change in the classification and labelling of the substance*

- *Any update or amendment of the chemical safety report or Section 5 of Annex VI*
- *The registrant identifies the need to perform a test listed in Annex IX or Annex X, in which cases a testing proposal shall be developed*
- *Any change in the access granted to information in the registration*
- *Article 22(2) [A]: A registrant shall submit to the Ministry an update of the registration containing the information required by the decision made in accordance with Articles 36 [examination of testing proposals], 37 [compliance check of registrations], 41 [requests for further information and check of information submitted] or 50 [granting of authorizations] within the deadline specified in that decision.*
- *Article 43(2) [A]: If a registrant has ceased the manufacture or import of the substance, or the production or import of an article, or the downstream user the use, he shall inform the Ministry of this fact with the consequence that the registered volume in his registration, if appropriate, shall be put to zero and no further information may be requested with respect to that substance, unless the registrant notifies the restart of the manufacture or import of the substance or the production or import of the article, or the downstream user notifies the restart of the use.*
- *Article 43(3) [A]: The registrant may cease the manufacture or import of the substance or the production or import of the article, or the downstream user the use, upon receipt of the decision. In such cases, the registrant, or downstream user, shall inform the Ministry of this fact with the consequence that his registration, or report, shall no longer be valid, and no further information may be requested with respect to that substance, unless he submits a new registration or report.*

Duty to communicate information on substances and mixtures up the supply chain

- *Article 30 [A]: Any actor in the supply chain of a substance or a mixture shall communicate the following information to the next actor or distributor up the supply chain*
 - *New information on hazardous properties, regardless of the uses concerned*
 - *Any other information that might call into question the appropriateness of the risk management measures identified in a safety data sheet supplied to him, which shall be communicated only for identified uses*
- *Article 33 [A]: A downstream user or distributor may provide information to assist in the preparation of a registration.*
 - *Any downstream user shall have the right to make a use, as a minimum the brief general description of use, known in writing (on paper or electronically) to the manufacturer, importer, downstream user or distributor who supplies him with a substance on its own or in a mixture with the aim of making this an identified use.*
 - *In making a use known, he shall provide sufficient information to allow the manufacturer, importer or downstream user who has supplied the substance, to prepare an exposure scenario, or if appropriate a use and exposure category, for his use in the manufacturer, importer or downstream user's chemical safety assessment.*
 - *Distributors shall pass on such information to the next actor or distributor up the supply chain. Downstream users in receipt of such information may prepare an exposure scenario for the identified use(s), or pass the information to the next actor up the supply chain.*
 - *For registered substances, the manufacturer, importer or downstream user may request the manufacturer, importer or downstream user, to add the substance on identified use in accordance with paragraph 2. Provided that the request was made at least one month before the supply, either before he next supplies or within one month after the request, whichever is the later, shall apply the duties of Article 15 [chemical safety report and duty to apply and recommend risk reduction measures].*

Obligation to keep information

- Article 32 [A]: *Each manufacturer, importer, downstream user and distributor shall assemble and keep available all the information he requires to carry out his duties under this Bylaw for a period of at least 10 years after he last manufactured, imported, supplied or used the substance or mixture. That manufacturer, importer, downstream user or distributor shall submit this information or make it available without delay upon request to the Ministry without prejudice to Parts 2 [registration] and 6 [evaluation].*
 - *In the event of a registrant, downstream user or distributor ceasing activity, or transferring part or all of his operations to a third party, the party responsible for liquidating the registrant, downstream user or distributor's undertaking or assuming responsibility for the placing on the market of the substance or mixture concerned shall be bound by the obligation in paragraph 1 in place of the registrant, downstream user or distributor.*

Obligation for downstream users to report information

- Article 34(3) [A]: *The downstream user shall update this information without delay in the event of a change in the information reported in accordance with paragraph 1.*
- Article 34(4) [A]: *A downstream user shall report to the Ministry if his classification of a substance is different to that of his supplier.*

Review of authorizations (Article 51 [A])

- *Authorizations granted in accordance with Article 50 shall be regarded as valid until the Ministry decides to amend or withdraw the authorization in the context of a review, provided that the holder of the authorization submits a review report at least 18 months before the expiry of the time-limited review period. Rather than re-submitting all elements of the original application for the current authorization, the holder of an authorization may submit only the number of the current authorization, subject to the second, third and fourth subparagraphs.*
- *A holder of an authorization granted in accordance with Article 50 shall submit an update of the analysis of alternatives referred to in Article 52(4)(d), including information about any relevant research and development activities by the applicant, if appropriate, and any substitution plan submitted under Article 52(4)(e). If the update of the analysis of alternatives shows that there is a suitable alternative available taking into account the elements in Article 50(5), he shall submit a substitution plan, including a timetable for proposed actions by the applicant. If the holder cannot demonstrate that the risk is adequately controlled, he shall also submit an update of the socio- economic analysis contained in the original application.*
- *If he can now demonstrate that the risk is adequately controlled, he shall submit an update of the chemical safety report.*
- *If any other elements of the original application have changed, he shall also submit updates of these element(s).*

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

Completeness check of each registration

- Article 20(2) [A]: *In respect to registration dossier*
 - *The Ministry shall undertake a completeness check of each registration in order to ascertain that all the elements required under Articles 11 and 13 or under Articles 17 or 18 ... have been provided. The completeness check shall not include an assessment of the quality or the adequacy of any data or justifications submitted.*
 - *The Ministry shall undertake the completeness check within three weeks of the submission date. If a registration is incomplete, the Ministry shall inform the registrant, before expiry of the*

three-week period, as to what further information is required in order for the registration to be complete, while setting a deadline for this.

- *The registrant shall complete his registration and submit it to the Ministry within the deadline set. The Ministry shall confirm the submission date of the further information to the registrant. The Ministry shall perform a further completeness check, considering the further information submitted.*
- *The Ministry shall reject the registration if the registrant fails to complete his registration within the deadline set. The registration fee shall not be reimbursed in such cases.*
- *Article 22(3) [A]: The Ministry shall undertake a completeness check of each updated registration according to Article 20(2) (a) and 20 (2) (b). In cases where the update is in accordance with Article 13(2) and with paragraph 1(c) of this Article, then the Ministry shall check the completeness of the information supplied by the registrant and Article 20(2) shall apply adapted as necessary.*

Examination of testing proposals

- *Article 36(2) [A]: It shall invite third parties to submit, using the format provided by the Ministry, scientifically valid information and studies that address the relevant substance and hazard end-point, addressed by the testing proposal, within 45 days of the date of publication. All such scientifically valid information and studies received shall be taken into account by the Ministry in preparing its decision in accordance with paragraph 3.*
- *Article 36(3) [A]: On the basis of the examination under paragraph 1, the Ministry shall draft one of the following decisions and that decision shall be taken in accordance with the procedure laid down in Articles 43:*
 - *A decision requiring the registrant(s) or downstream user(s) concerned to carry out the proposed test and setting a deadline for submission of the study summary, or the robust study summary if required by Annex 1*
 - *A decision in accordance with subparagraph (a), but modifying the conditions under which the test is to be carried out*
 - *A decision in accordance with subparagraphs (a), (b) or (d) but requiring registrant(s) or downstream user(s) to carry out one or more additional tests in cases of non-compliance of the testing proposal with Annexes IX, X and XI*
 - *A decision rejecting the testing proposal*
 - *A decision in accordance with subparagraphs (a), (b) or (c), if several registrants or downstream users of the same substance have submitted proposals for the same test, giving them the opportunity to reach an agreement on who will perform the test on behalf of all of them and to inform the Ministry accordingly within 90 days. If the Ministry is not informed of such agreement within 90 days, it shall designate one of the registrants or downstream users, as appropriate, to perform the test on behalf of all of them.*
- *The registrant or downstream user shall submit the information required to the Ministry by the deadline set.*
- *Article 39 [A]: The Ministry shall prepare the draft decisions in accordance with the Article 36 (3) in order to fulfil the information requirements in Annexes 9 and 10 by 31/12/2025 for the proposals received by 31/12/2023 including the testing proposals.*

Compliance check of registrations

- *Article 37(1) [A]: The Ministry may examine any registration in order to verify any of the following:*
 - *That the information in the technical dossier(s) submitted pursuant to Article 11 complies with the requirements of Articles 11, 13 and 14 and with Annex III, Annex VI, Annex VII, Annex VIII, Annex IX and Annex X*

- *That the adaptations of the standard information requirements and the related justifications submitted in the technical dossier(s) comply with the rules governing such adaptations set out in Annexes 7 to 10 and with the general rules set out in Annex XI*
- *That any required chemical safety assessment and chemical safety report comply with the requirements of Annex 1 and that the proposed risk management measures are adequate*
- *That any explanation(s) submitted in accordance with Article 12(3) or Article 19(2) has an objective basis.*
- *To ensure that registration dossiers comply with this Bylaw, the Ministry shall select a percentage of those dossiers, no lower than 5 % of the total received by the Ministry for each tonnage band, for compliance checking. The Ministry shall give priority, but not exclusively, to dossiers meeting at least one of the following criteria:*
 - *The dossier contains information in Article 11(1)(a), (4) [classification and labelling], (6) [study summaries] and/or (7) [robust study summaries] submitted separately as per Article 12(3); or*
 - *The dossier is for a substance manufactured or imported in quantities of one tonne or more per year and does not meet the requirements of Annex VII applying under either Article 13(1)(a) or (b), as the case may be.*
- *Article 37(2) [A]: On the basis of an examination made pursuant to paragraph 1, the Ministry may, within 12 months of the start of the compliance check, prepare a draft decision requiring the registrant(s) to submit any information needed to bring the registration(s) into compliance with the relevant information requirements and specifying adequate time limits for the submission of further information. Such a decision shall be taken in accordance with the procedure laid down in Article 43.*
 - *The registrant shall submit the information required to the Ministry by the deadline set.*

Procedure for authorization

- *Article 54 [A]: The Ministry shall make available on its website broad information on uses, taking into account Articles 60 and 61 on access to information, for which applications have been received and for reviews of authorizations, with a deadline by which information on alternative substances or technologies may be submitted by interested third parties.*
- *During the process for adoption of authorization decisions in paragraph 1, the Ministry shall first check that the application includes all the information specified in Article 52 that is relevant to its remit. If necessary, the Ministry shall, request to the applicant for additional information to bring the application into conformity with the requirements of Article 52. The Ministry may, if it deems it necessary, require the applicant or request third parties to submit, within a specified time period, additional information on possible alternative substances or technologies. The Ministry shall also take into account any information submitted by third parties.*

Requests for further information and check of information submitted (Substance evaluation)

- *Article 41(1) [A]: Ministry may require further information from the registrants defined in Annex VII, Annex VIII, Annex IX and Annex X including the ones not defined there.*
 - *The registrant shall submit the information required to the Ministry by the deadline set.*
- *Article 43(4) [A]: The Ministry may request further information for the following(s) in the context of Article 41:*
 - *If a dossier has been prepared under Annex 15 and it was decided to be harmful to the human or environmental health and so a further information is needed*
 - *If the risk of exposure to the substance manufactured or imported by the registrant or manufactured or imported in an article or used by the downstream user is significantly increasing.*

Inspection (Article 62)

- *Inspections regarding Article 46 [authorization] and 57 [restrictions] shall be conducted according to the Law numbered 4703, Law on Occupational Health and Safety published in the Official Gazette dated 13/07/2012 and numbered 6331, Law on Provincial Administration published in the Official Gazette dated 10/06/1949 and numbered 5442 and Law numbered 5996 by Relevant Institutions.*
- *Inspections regarding the other provisions shall be conducted according to Law numbered 2872 and Law numbered 4703 by the Ministry.*

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)**Exemption from the general obligation to register for product and process orientated research and development (PPORD)**

- Article 10(4) [A]: *The Ministry may decide to impose conditions with the aim of ensuring that the substance or the mixture or article in which the substance is incorporated will be handled only by staff of listed customers as referred to ... in reasonably controlled conditions, in accordance with the requirements of legislation for the protection of workers and the environment, and will not be made available to the general public at any time either on its own or in a mixture or article and may ask the notifier to provide additional necessary information. Also, The Ministry may re-collect remaining quantities following the exemption period.*

Examination of testing proposals

- Article 36(1) [A]: *The Ministry shall examine any testing proposal set out in a registration or a downstream user report for provision of the information specified in Annexes IX and X for a substance. Priority shall be given to registrations of substances which have or may have PBT, vPvB, sensitising and/or carcinogenic, mutagenic or toxic for reproduction (CMR) properties, or substances above 100 tons per year with uses resulting in widespread and diffuse exposure, provided they fulfil the criteria for any of the following hazard classes or categories set out in Annex 1 of Bylaw on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures.*
 - *Hazard classes 2.1 to 2.4, 2.6 and 2.7, 2.8 types A and B, 2.9, 2.10, 2.12, 2.13 categories 1 and 2, 2.14 categories 1 and 2, 2.15 types A to F*
 - *Hazard classes 3.1 to 3.6, 3.7 adverse effects on sexual function and fertility or on development, 3.8 effects other than narcotic effects, 3.9 and 3.10*
 - *Hazard class 4.1*
 - *Hazard class 5.1*

Check of information submitted and follow-up to dossier evaluation

- Article 38 [A]: *The Ministry shall examine any information submitted in consequence of a decision taken under Articles 36 [examination of testing proposals] or 37 [compliance check of registration], and draft any appropriate decisions in accordance with these Articles, if necessary.*
 - *The Ministry shall use the information obtained from this evaluation for the purposes of Article 40 [criteria for substance evaluation].*

Substance evaluation

- Article 40 [A]: *Prioritization shall be made by the Ministry on a risk-based approach:*
 - *Hazard information, for instance structural similarity of the substance with known substances of concern or with substances which are persistent and liable to bio-accumulate, suggesting that the substance or one or more of its transformation products has properties of concern or is persistent and liable to bio-accumulate*
 - *Exposure information*

- Tonnage, including aggregated tonnage from the registrations submitted by several registrants
- Article 41(3) [A]: *The Ministry shall examine any information submitted, and shall draft any appropriate decisions in accordance with this Article, if necessary, within 12 months of the information being submitted.*
- Article 41(4) [A]: *The Ministry shall finish its evaluation activities within 12 months of the start of the evaluation of the substance or within 12 months of the information being submitted under paragraph 2.*
- Article 42 [A]: *For on-site isolated intermediates that are used in strictly controlled conditions, neither dossier nor substance evaluation shall apply. However, the Ministry considers that a risk to human health or the environment, equivalent to the level of concern arising from the use of substances meeting the criteria in Article 47, arises from the use of an on-site isolated intermediate and that risk is not properly controlled, it may:*
 - *Require the registrant to submit a written justification on further information directly related to the risk identified,*
 - *Examine any information submitted and, if necessary, recommend any appropriate risk reduction measures to address the risks identified in relation to the site in question.*

Authorization – Substances to be included in Annex XIV

- Article 47 [A]: *The following substances defined as the substances of high concern may be included in Annex XIV in accordance with the procedure laid down in Article 48:*
 - *Substances meeting the criteria for classification in the hazard class carcinogenicity category 1A or 1B in accordance with title 3.6 of Annex 1 of Bylaw on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures*
 - *Substances meeting the criteria for classification in the hazard class germ cell mutagenicity category 1A or 1B in accordance with title 3.5 of Annex 1 of the Bylaw on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures*
 - *Substances meeting the criteria for classification in the hazard class reproductive toxicity category 1A or 1B in accordance with title 3.7 of Annex 1 to Bylaw on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures*
 - *Substances which are persistent, bio-accumulative and toxic in accordance with the criteria set out in Annex XIII of this Bylaw*
 - *Substances which are very persistent and very bio accumulative in accordance with the criteria set out in Annex XIII of this Bylaw*
 - *Substances — such as those having endocrine disrupting properties or those having persistent, bio accumulative and toxic properties or very persistent and very bio accumulative properties, which do not fulfill the criteria of [PBT or vPvB] — for which there is scientific evidence of probable serious effects to human health or the environment which give rise to an equivalent level of concern to those of other substances listed in this paragraph and which are identified on a case-by-case basis in accordance with the procedure set out in Article 49.*

Authorization – Inclusion of substances in Annex XIV

- Article 48(1) [A]: *Whenever a decision is taken by the Ministry to include the substances referred to in Article 47 in Annex XIV, such a decision shall specify for each substance:*
 - *The identity of the substance as specified in Section 2 of Annex VI*
 - *The intrinsic property (properties) of the substance referred to in Article 47*
 - *Transitional arrangements:*
 - *The date(s) from which the placing on the market and the use of the substance shall be prohibited unless an authorization is granted, the sunset date, which should take into account, where appropriate, the production cycle specified for that use*

- *A date or dates at least 18 months before the sunset date(s) by which applications must be received if the applicant wishes to continue to use the substance or place it on the market for certain uses after the sunset date(s); these continued uses shall be allowed after the sunset date until a decision on the application for authorization is taken*
 - *Review periods for certain uses, if appropriate*
 - *Uses or categories of uses exempted from the authorization requirement, if any, and conditions for such exemptions, if any*
 - *Uses or categories of uses may be exempted from the authorization requirement provided that, on the basis of the existing specific related legislation imposing minimum requirements relating to the protection of human health or the environment for the use of the substance, the risk is properly controlled. In the establishment of such exemptions, account shall be taken, in particular, of the proportionality of risk to human health and the environment related to the nature of the substance, such as where the risk is modified by the physical form.*
- *Article 48(3) [A]: Prior to a decision to include substances in Annex 14, the Ministry shall, determine priority substances to be included specifying for each substance the items set out in paragraph 1. Priority shall normally be given to substances with [one of the followings]:*
 - *PBT or vPvB properties; or*
 - *Wide dispersive use; or*
 - *High volumes.*
- *The number of substances included in Annex XIV and the dates specified under paragraph 1 shall also take account of the Ministry's capacity to handle applications in the time provided for.*
 - *Subject to paragraph 6, after inclusion of a substance in Annex XIV, this substance shall not be subjected to new restrictions under the procedure outlined in Part 8 covering the risks to human health or the environment from the use of the substance on its own, in a mixture or incorporation of a substance in an article arising from the intrinsic properties specified in Annex XIV.*
 - *A substance listed in Annex XIV may be subjected to new restrictions under the procedure outlined in Part 8 covering the risks to human health or the environment from the presence of the substance in (an) article(s).*
 - *Substances for which all uses have been prohibited under Part 8 or by other relevant legislation shall not be included in Annex XIV or shall be removed from it.*
 - *Substances which as a result of new information no longer meet the criteria of Article 47 shall be removed from Annex XIV by the Ministry.*

Authorization – Defining the substances in Article 47

- *Article 49(1) [A]: The procedure mentioned in this article is applied in order to define the substances compliant with the criteria mentioned in Article 47 and the substances to be included in Annex XIV.*

Granting of authorizations (Article 50 [A])

- *The Ministry shall be responsible for taking decisions on applications for authorizations in accordance with this Section.*
 - *Without prejudice to paragraph 3 provisions of this Article, an authorization shall be granted if the risk to human health or the environment from the use of a substance arising from the intrinsic properties specified in Annex XIV is adequately controlled in accordance with Section 6.4 of Annex 1 and as documented in the applicant's chemical safety report. When granting the authorization, and in any conditions imposed therein, the Ministry shall take into account all discharges, emissions and losses, including risks arising from diffuse or dispersive uses, known at the time of the decision.*

- Paragraph [right above] shall not apply to:
 - Substances meeting the criteria in Article 47 (1) (a), (b), (c) or (e) for which it is not possible to determine a threshold in accordance with Section 6.4 of Annex I
 - Substances meeting the criteria in Article 47 (1) (ç) [PBT] or (d) [vPvB];
 - Substances identified under Article 47 (1) (e) having persistent, bio accumulative and toxic properties or very persistent and very bio accumulative properties.
- If an authorisation cannot be granted under paragraph 2 or for substances listed in paragraph 3, an authorisation may only be granted if it is shown that socio-economic benefits outweigh the risk to human health or the environment arising from the use of the substance and if there are no suitable alternative substances or technologies. This decision shall be taken after consideration of all of the following elements and taking into account the opinions of the Risk Assessment and the Socio-economic Analysis referred to in Article 54(4)(a) and (b):
 - The risk posed by the uses of the substance, including the appropriateness and effectiveness of the risk management measures proposed
 - The socio-economic benefits arising from its use and the socio-economic implications of a refusal to authorize as demonstrated by the applicant or other interested parties
 - the analysis of the alternatives submitted by the applicant under Article 52(4)(d) or any substitution plan submitted by the applicant under Article 52(4)(e), and any third party contributions submitted under Article 54(2)
 - Available information on the risks to human health or the environment of any alternative substances or technologies.
- When assessing whether suitable alternative substances or technologies are available, all relevant aspects shall be taken into account by the Ministry including:
 - Whether the transfer to alternatives would result in reduced overall risks to human health and the environment, taking into account the appropriateness and effectiveness of risk management measures
 - The technical and economic feasibility of alternatives for the applicant
- A use shall not be authorized if this would constitute a relaxation of a restriction set out in Annex XVII.
- The authorization shall specify:
 - The person(s) to whom the authorization is granted
 - The identity of the substance(s)
 - The use(s) for which the authorization is granted
 - Any conditions under which the authorization is granted
 - The time-limited review period
 - Any monitoring arrangement
- Notwithstanding any conditions of an authorization, the holder shall ensure that the exposure is reduced to as low a level as is technically and practically possible

Review of authorizations

- Article 51(2) [A]: The Ministry shall set a reasonable deadline by which the holder(s) of the authorization may submit further information necessary for the review and indicate by when it will take a decision in accordance with Article 54. Authorizations may be reviewed at any time if:
 - The circumstances of the original authorization have changed so as to affect the risk to human health or the environment, or the socio-economic impact; or
 - New information on possible substitutes becomes available.
- Article 51(4) [A]: If an environmental quality standard referred to in relevant legislation on IPPC is not met, the authorizations granted for the use of the substance concerned may be reviewed.

- Article 51(5) [A]: *If the environmental objectives as referred to in Article 4 of Bylaw on Water Pollution Control published in Official Gazette dated 31/12/2004 and numbered 25687 are not met, the authorizations granted for the use of the substance concerned in the relevant river basin may be reviewed.*
- Article 51(3) [A]: *In its review decision the Ministry may, if circumstances have changed and taking into account the principle of proportionality, amend or withdraw the authorization, if under the changed circumstances it would not have been granted or if suitable alternatives in accordance with Article 50(5) become available. In the latter case the Ministry shall require the holder of the authorization to present a substitution plan if he has not already done so as part of his application or update.*
 - *In cases where there is a serious and immediate risk for human health or the environment, the Ministry may suspend the authorization pending the review, taking into account the principle of proportionality.*
- *If a use of a substance is subsequently prohibited or otherwise restricted in regulations on persistent organic pollutants, the Ministry shall withdraw the authorization for that use.*

Procedure for authorization

- Article 54 [A]: *The Ministry shall acknowledge the date of receipt of the application. Following the receipt of application, the Ministry shall conduct the Risk Assessment and Socio-economic Analysis referred to in this Article and shall give its draft opinions within ten months of the date of receipt of the application.*
 - *Risk Assessment: an assessment of the risk to human health and/or the environment arising from the use(s) of the substance, including the appropriateness and effectiveness of the risk management measures as described in the application and, if relevant, an assessment of the risks arising from possible alternatives*
 - *Socio-economic Analysis: an assessment of the socio-economic factors and the availability, suitability and technical feasibility of alternatives associated with the use(s) of the substance as described in the application, when an application is made in accordance with Article 52 and of any third party contributions submitted under paragraph 2 of this Article*
 - *The Ministry shall send these draft opinions to the applicant by the end of the deadline set out in paragraph 1. Within 60 days of receipt of the draft opinion, the applicant may provide written notice that he wishes to comment.*
 - *If the applicant does not send comment to the Ministry in 60 days, the draft opinion will be finalized. After the Ministry takes the written opinion in 60 days, it will finalize its draft opinion in 60 days.*
 - *The Ministry shall prepare a draft authorization decision within 90 days of the issuance of its opinions. A final decision granting or refusing the authorization shall be taken.*

Introducing new and amending current restrictions (Article 58 [A])

- *When there is an unacceptable risk to human health or the environment, arising from the manufacture, use or placing on the market of substances, Annex XVII shall be amended by the Ministry by adopting new restrictions, or amending current restrictions in Annex XVII, for the manufacture, use or placing on the market of substances on their own, in mixtures or in articles. Any amendment shall take into account the socio- economic impact of the restriction, including the availability of alternatives.*
- *Ministry shall conduct risk assessment and socio-economic analysis to evaluate the risk to human health or the environment and the socio-economic impact of restriction during the restriction process. Ministry may use the services of third parties or compose committees consisting of experts in order to conduct or help to conduct such Risk Assessments and socio-economic analysis.*
- *Any relevant entity may prepare a restriction proposal dossier under Annex XV and can submit this to the Ministry.*

8. Data submission format

Chemicals Registration System in the website of Ministry.

9. Data confidentiality

- Article 60(1) [A]: *Disclosure of the following information shall normally be deemed to undermine the protection of the commercial interests of the concerned person:*
 - *details of the full composition of a mixture*
 - *without prejudice to Article 8(6) and Article 54(2), the precise use, function or application of a substance or mixture, including information about its precise use as an intermediate*
 - *the precise tonnage of the substance or mixture manufactured or placed on the market*
 - *links between a manufacturer or importer and his distributors or downstream users*
- *Where urgent action is essential to protect human health, safety or the environment, such as emergency situations, the Ministry may disclose the information referred to in this paragraph.*

General registration

- Article 11(1)(a)(11): *a request as to which of the information in Article 61(2) the manufacturer or importer considers should not be made available on the Internet including a justification as to why publication could be harmful for his or any other concerned party's commercial interests*

10. Data that are published publicly

Examination of testing proposals

- Article 36(2) [A]: *Information relating to testing proposals involving tests on vertebrate animals shall be published on the Ministry website. The Ministry shall publish on its website the name of the substance, the hazard end-point for which vertebrate testing is proposed, and the date by which any third party information is required*

Authorisation

- Article 54(9) [A]: *Summaries of the Ministry decisions, including the authorization number and the reasons for the decision, in particular where suitable alternatives exist, shall be published in the website of the Ministry.*

Public access (Article 60 [A])

- *The following information held by the Ministry on substances whether on their own, in mixtures or in Articles, shall be made publicly available, free of charge, over the Internet:*
 - *Without prejudice to paragraph 2(e) of this Article, the name in the IUPAC nomenclature for substances fulfilling the criteria for any of the following hazard classes or categories set out in Annex 1 to Bylaw on the Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures*
 - *Hazard classes 2.1 to 2.4, 2.6 and 2.7, 2.8 types A and B, 2.9, 2.10, 2.12, 2.13 categories 1 and 2, 2.14 categories 1 and 2, 2.15 types A to F*
 - *Hazard classes 3.1 to 3.6, 3.7 adverse effects on sexual function and fertility or on development, 3.8 effects other than narcotic effects, 3.9 and 3.10*
 - *Hazard class 4.1*
 - *Hazard class 5.1*
 - *If applicable, the name of the substance as given in EINECS*
 - *The classification and labelling of the substance*
 - *Physicochemical data concerning the substance and on pathways and environmental fate*
 - *toxicological and eco toxicological information*
 - *Any derived no-effect level (DNEL) or predicted no-effect concentration (PNEC)*

- *The guidance on safe use provided in accordance with Sections 4 and 5 of Annex 6*
- *Analytical methods if requested in accordance with Annexes 9 or 10 which make it possible to detect a dangerous substance when discharged into the environment as well as to determine the direct exposure of humans.*
- *The following information on substances whether on their own, in mixtures or in Articles, shall be made publicly available, free of charge, over the Internet except where a party submitting the information submits a justification in accordance with Article 11(a)(11), accepted as valid by the Ministry, as to why such publication is potentially harmful for the commercial interests of the registrant or any other party concerned:*
 - *If essential to classification and labelling, the degree of purity of the substance and the identity of impurities and/or additives which are known to be hazardous*
 - *The total tonnage band(i.e. 1 to 10 ton[ne]s, 10 to 100 ton[ne]s, 100 to 1 000 ton[ne]s or over 1 000 ton[ne]s) within which a particular substance has been registered*
 - *The study summaries or robust study summaries of the information referred to in paragraph 1(ç) and (d)*
 - *Information, other than that listed in paragraph 1, contained in the safety data sheet*
 - *The trade name(s) of the substance*
 - *Subject to Article 26 of Bylaw on the Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Substances and Mixtures, the name in the IUPAC nomenclature for substances that are only used as one or more of the following:*
 - *As an intermediate*
 - *In scientific research and development*
 - *In product and process orientated research and development.*

11. International information exchange and sharing

N.A.

S1.24 Toxic Substances Control Act (TSCA) Chemical Substance Inventory, US

Last update: 30 November 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. US EPA Homepage on TSCA inventory: <https://www.epa.gov/tsca-inventory>
- B. TSCA (15 USC Ch.53: Toxic Substances Control):
<https://uscode.house.gov/view.xhtml?path=/prelim@title15/chapter53&edition=prelim;>
<https://www.law.cornell.edu/uscode/text/15/chapter-53/subchapter-I>
- C. 40 CFR 720—premanufacture notification (15 U.S.C. 2604, 2607 and 2613): https://www.ecfr.gov/cgi-bin/text-idx?node=pt40.33.720&rgn=div5#se40.33.720_130
- D. 40 CFR 723—premanufacture notification exemptions (15 U.S.C. 2604): <https://www.ecfr.gov/cgi-bin/text-idx?node=pt40.34.723&rgn=div5#sp40.34.723.b>
- E. 40 CFR 702—general practices and procedures (15 U.S.C. 2605 and 2619):
<https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-702>
- F. 40 CFR 704—reporting and recordkeeping requirements (15 U.S.C. 2607(a)):
<https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-704>
- G. 40 CFR 710—compilation of the TSCA chemical substance inventory (15 U.S.C. 2607(a) and (b)):
<https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-710>
- H. 40 CFR 711—TSCA chemical data reporting requirements (15 U.S.C. 2607(a)):
<https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-711>
- I. 40 CFR 712—chemical information rules (15 U.S.C. 2607(a)):
<https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-712>
- J. 40 CFR 716—health and safety data reporting (15 U.S.C. 2607(d)):
<https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-716>
- K. 40 CFR 717—records and reports of allegations that chemical substances cause significant adverse reactions to health or the environment (15 U.S.C. 2607(c)):
<https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-717>
- L. 40 CFR 721—significant new uses of chemical substances (15 U.S.C. 2604, 2607 and 2625(c)):
<https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-721>
- M. 40 CFR 790—procedures governing testing consent agreements and test rules (15 U.S.C. 2603):
<https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-790>
- N. 40 CFR 792—good laboratory practice standards (15 U.S.C. 2603): <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-792>
- O. 40 CFR 795—provisional test guidelines (15 U.S.C. 2603): <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-795>
- P. 40 CFR 796—chemical fate test guidelines (15 U.S.C. 2603): <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-796>
- Q. 40 CFR 797—environmental effects test guidelines (15 U.S.C. 2603):
<https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-797>
- R. 40 CFR 798—health effects test guidelines (15 U.S.C. 2603): <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-798>
- S. 40 CFR 799—identification of specific chemical substance and mixture testing requirements (15 U.S.C. 2603, 2611, 2625): <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-799>
- T. New Chemical Working Approach (12-20-2019): <https://www.regulations.gov/document/EPA-HQ-OPPT-2019-0684-0002>
- U. Title I of the Toxic Substances Control Act (TSCA): A summary of the Statute (Updated July 20, 2021): <https://fas.org/sgp/crs/misc/R45149.pdf>

V. Overview: Office of Pollution Prevention and Toxics Programs (December 24, 2003):

<http://chemicalspolicy.org/downloads/TSCA10112-24-03.pdf>

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

TSCA Section 8(b) (§2607) – inventory [B]

- [EPA] shall compile, keep current, and publish a list of each chemical substance which is manufactured or processed in the United States. Such list shall at least include each chemical substance which any person reports, under section 2604 of this title or subsection (a) of this section, is manufactured or processed in the United States. Such list may not include any chemical substance which was not manufactured or processed in the United States within three years before the effective date of the rules promulgated pursuant to the last sentence of subsection (a)(1). In the case of a chemical substance for which a notice is submitted in accordance with section 2604 of this title, such chemical substance shall be included in such list as of the earliest date (as determined by the Administrator) on which such substance was manufactured or processed in the United States. The Administrator shall first publish such a list not later than 315 days after January 1, 1977. The Administrator shall not include in such list any chemical substance which is manufactured or processed only in small quantities (as defined by the Administrator by rule) solely for purposes of scientific experimentation or analysis or chemical research on, or analysis of, such substance or another substance, including such research or analysis for the development of a product.
 - If a manufacturer or processor demonstrates to the Administrator that a chemical substance appears multiple times on the list published under paragraph (1) under different CAS numbers, the Administrator may recognize the multiple listings as a single chemical substance.
 - The initial reporting period by manufacturers, processors and importers was January to May of 1978 for chemical substances that had been in commerce since January of 1975. The inventory was initially published in 1979, and a second version, containing about 62,000 chemical substances, was published in 1982.
 - §710.4 [G]: Only chemical substances which are manufactured, imported, or processed “for a commercial purpose,” as defined in § 710.3(d), are subject to these regulations.

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligations

TSCA Section 5 (§2604) – manufacturing and processing notice²⁰² [B]

- A person may manufacture a new chemical substance, or manufacture or process any chemical substance for a use which EPA has determined is a significant new use²⁰³ if
 - Such person submits to [EPA], at least 90 days before such manufacture or processing, a notice ... of such person’s intention to manufacture or process such substance and such person complies with any applicable requirement of, or imposed pursuant to, subsection (b), (e), or (f); and

²⁰² Note: TSCA sets the legal ground for the regulations, and information that is detailed in the regulations is not repeated here, including how EPA reviews and makes determination, how any person submits information, how EPA extends review period, content of notice, how EPA publishes in the Federal Register.

²⁰³ A determination shall be made by a rule promulgated after a consideration of all relevant factors, including the projected volume of manufacturing and processing of a chemical substance, the extent to which a use changes the type or form of exposure of human beings or the environment to a chemical substance, the extent to which a use increases the magnitude and duration of exposure of human beings or the environment to a chemical substance, and the reasonably anticipated manner and methods of manufacturing, processing, distribution in commerce, and disposal of a chemical substance. [B]

- [EPA] conducts a review of the notice; and makes a determination ... and takes the actions required in association with that determination ... within the applicable review period.
- [EPA] may require notification under this section for the import or processing of a chemical substance as part of an article or category of articles ... if [EPA] makes an affirmative finding in a rule ... that the reasonable potential for exposure to the chemical substance through the article or category of articles subject to the rule justifies notification.
- [EPA] may, by rule, compile and keep current a list of chemical substances with respect to which [EPA] finds that the manufacture, processing, distribution in commerce, use, or disposal, or any combination of such activities, presents or may present an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment, without consideration of costs or other nonrisk factors.
 - [EPA] shall consider all relevant factors, including the effects of the chemical substance on health and the magnitude of human exposure to such substance; and the effects of the chemical substance on the environment and the magnitude of environmental exposure to such substance.
 - [EPA] shall ... identify those uses, if any, which [EPA] determines, by rule ... would constitute a significant new use of such substance.

Premanufacture notice [C]

- § 720.22: Any person who intends to manufacture/import a new chemical substance (any chemical substance which is not included on the TSCA inventory) in the United States for commercial purposes must submit a premanufacture notice unless the substance is excluded under § 720.30 (see below).

Significant new uses (§ 721.5) [L]

- The following persons must submit a significant new use notice as specified under the provisions of section 5(a)(1)(B) of the Act, part 720 of this chapter, and § 721.25
 - A person who intends to manufacture, import, or process for commercial purposes a chemical substance identified in a specific section in subpart E of this part, and intends to engage in a significant new use of the substance identified in that section.
 - A person who intends to manufacture, import, or process for commercial purposes a chemical substance identified in a specific section in subpart E of this part, and intends to distribute the substance in commerce. A person described in this paragraph is not required to submit a significant new use notice if that person can document one or more of the following as to each recipient of the substance from that person: (i) That the person has notified the recipient, in writing, of the specific section in subpart E of this part which identifies the substance and its designated significant new uses. (ii) That the recipient has knowledge of the specific section in subpart E of this part which identifies the substance and its designated significant new uses. (iii) That the recipient cannot undertake any significant new use described in the specific section in subpart E of this part.
 - A person ... must submit a significant new use notice if that person has knowledge at the time of commercial distribution of the substance identified in the specific section in subpart E of this part that a recipient intends to engage in a designated significant new use of that substance without submitting a notice under this part.
 - If at any time after commencing distribution in commerce of a chemical substance identified in a specific section in subpart E of this part a person described in paragraph (a)(2) of this section has knowledge that a recipient of the substance is engaging in a significant new use of that substance designated in that section without submitting a notice under this part, the person is required to cease supplying the chemical substance to that recipient and to submit a significant new use notice for that chemical substance and significant new use, unless the person is able to document each of the following:
 - (i) That the person has notified the recipient and EPA enforcement authorities (at the address in paragraph (d)(1)(iii) of this section), in writing within 15 working

days of the time the person develops knowledge that the recipient is engaging in a significant new use, that the recipient is engaging in a significant new use without submitting a significant new use notice.

- *(ii) That, within 15 working days of notifying the recipient as described in paragraph (d)(1)(i) of this section, the person received from the recipient, in writing, a statement of assurance that the recipient is aware of the terms of the applicable section in subpart E of this part and will not engage in the significant new use.*
 - *If EPA notifies the manufacturer, importer, or processor that the recipient is engaging in a significant new use after providing the statement of assurance described in paragraph (d)(1)(ii) of this section and without submitting a notice under this part, the manufacturer, importer, or processor shall immediately cease distribution to that recipient until the manufacturer, importer, or processor or the recipient has submitted a significant new use notice under this part and the notice review period has ended.*
 - *If, after receiving a statement of assurance from a recipient under paragraph (d)(1)(ii) of this section, a manufacturer, importer, or processor has knowledge that the recipient is engaging in a significant new use without submitting a notice under this part, the manufacturer, importer, or processor must immediately cease distributing the substance to that recipient and notify EPA enforcement authorities at the address identified in paragraph (d)(1)(iii) of this section. The manufacturer, importer, or processor may not resume distribution to that recipient until any one of the following has occurred: (i) The manufacturer, importer, or processor has submitted a significant new use notice under this part and the notice review period has ended. (ii) The recipient has submitted a significant new use notice under this part and the notice review period has ended. (iii) The manufacturer, importer, or processor has received notice from EPA enforcement authorities that it may resume distribution to that recipient.*
- *(iii) That the person has promptly provided EPA enforcement authorities with a copy of the recipient's statement of assurance described in paragraph (d)(1)(ii) of this section. The copy must be sent to the Office of Enforcement and Compliance Assurance, Office of Compliance (2224A), U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Ariel Rios, 1200 Pennsylvania Ave., N.W., Washington, DC, 20044.*
- *A person who processes a chemical substance identified in a specific section in subpart E of this part for a significant new use of that substance is not required to submit a significant new use notice if that person can document each of the following: (1) That the person does not know the specific chemical identity of the chemical substance being processed. (2) That the person is processing the chemical substance without knowledge that the substance is identified in subpart E of this part.*
- *Any significant new use notice relating to import of a substance must be submitted by the principal importer.*
- *A person who intends to manufacture (including import) or process a chemical substance which is described by a generic chemical name in subpart E of this part may ask EPA whether the substance is subject to the requirements of this part. EPA will answer such an inquiry only if EPA determine that the person has a bona fide intent to manufacture (including import) of process the chemical substance for commercial purposes.*
- *Persons who intend to export a chemical substance identified in subpart E of this part, or in any proposed which would amend subpart E of this part, are subject to the export notification provisions of section 12(b)*

of the Act. The regulations that interpret section 12(b) appear at 40 CFR part 707. Persons who import a substance identified in a specific section in subpart E of this part are subject to the import certification requirements under section 13 of the Act, which are codified at 19 CFR 12.118 through 12.127 and 127.28. The EPA policy in support of the import certification requirements appears at 40 CFR part 707.

Chemical data reporting [H]

- § 711.8: Except as provided in §§ 711.9 [a small manufacturer] and 711.10²⁰⁴, the following persons are subject to the requirements of this part. Persons must determine whether they must report under this section for each chemical substance that they manufacture (including import) at an individual site.
 - Persons subject to recurring reporting. Any person who manufactured (including imported) for commercial purposes 25,000 lb (11,340 kg) or more of a chemical substance described in § 711.5 at any single site owned or controlled by that person during any calendar year since the last principal reporting year.
 - **Exceptions.** Any person who manufactured (including imported) for commercial purposes any chemical substance that is the subject of a rule proposed or promulgated under TSCA section 5(a)(2), 5(b)(4), or 6, or is the subject of an order in effect under TSCA section 4, 5(e) or 5(f), or is the subject of relief that has been granted under a civil action under TSCA sections 5 or 7 is subject to reporting as described in § 711.8(a), except that the applicable production volume threshold is 2,500 lb (1,134 kg).

Reporting and recordkeeping [F]

- § 704.20: Chemical substances manufactured or processed at the nanoscale
 - Persons who can reasonably ascertain that they are manufacturers and processors of a discrete form of a reportable chemical substance during the three years prior to the final effective date of the rule must report except [see below]
 - Persons who can reasonably ascertain that they propose to manufacture or process a discrete form of a reportable chemical substance after the final effective date of the rule which was not reported under paragraph (b)(1) of this section must report except [see below]

²⁰⁴ <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-711/section-711.10>

- The person manufactured or imported the chemical substance solely in small quantities for research and development.
- The person imported the chemical substance as part of an article.
- The person manufactured the chemical substance in a manner described in 40 CFR 720.30(g) or (h).
- The person manufactured the chemical substance in any of the following manners:
 - Byproduct substances listed in paragraph (i) of this section for the following manufacturing processes, when recycled or otherwise used within a site-limited, physically enclosed system that is part of the same overall manufacturing process from which the byproduct substance was generated, and when the site is reporting the byproduct or a different chemical substance that was manufactured from the recycled byproduct or manufactured in the same overall manufacturing process:
 - (i) List of processes and certain related byproduct substances: (A) Portland Cement Manufacturing (i.e., CASRN 68475-76-3, Flue dust, portland cement). (B) Kraft Pulping Process (i.e., CASRN 66071-92-9, Sulfite liquors and Cooking liquors, spent; CASRN 68514-09-0, Sulfite liquors and Cooking liquors, spent, oxidized; and CASRN 471-34-1, Carbonic acid calcium salt (1:1)).
 - A quantity of the byproduct that is manufactured solely in the following equipment when it is not integral to the chemical manufacturing processes of the site: (i) Pollution control equipment. (ii) Boilers used to generate heat or electricity for that site.

[beginning on June 21, 2006 and ending on June 21, 2016, as defined in Aug. 11, 2017], *except as provided in § 710.27, must submit a Notice of Activity Form A as specified under §§ 710.29 and 710.30(a), unless such person has evidence in the form of a CDX receipt, documenting EPA's receipt of a Notice of Activity Form A from another person, for the same chemical substance, or unless the prior manufacturing of such a substance is not known to or reasonably ascertainable by the person. Evidence in the form of a CDX receipt for a Notice of Activity Form A is not a basis for exemption from the requirements of § 710.25(c) if the chemical substance is ultimately designated as inactive due to withdrawal of the Notice of Activity Form A.*

- **Who else may submit the Notice of Activity Form A?** *Any person not required to submit a Notice of Activity Form A under § 710.25(a), who manufactured (including imported) or processed a reportable chemical substance, at any time during the lookback period, may submit a Notice of Activity Form A as specified under §§ 710.29 and 710.30(a).*
- **Who must submit the Notice of Activity Form B?** *Any person who intends to manufacture (including import) or process an inactive substance, except as provided in § 710.27, after the effective date of the Administrator's designation of such chemical substance as an inactive substance, must submit a Notice of Activity Form B as specified under §§ 710.29 and 710.30(b), unless the presence of the inactive substance on the confidential portion of the Inventory is not known to or reasonably ascertainable by the person.*

3.2 Exemptions

- §2602.2(B) [B]: The term “chemical substance” under the TSCA *does not include*
 - Any mixture
 - Any pesticide (as defined in the Federal Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Act [7 U.S.C. 136 et seq.]) when manufactured, processed, or distributed in commerce for use as a pesticide
 - Tobacco or any tobacco product
 - Any source material, special nuclear material, or byproduct material (as such terms are defined in the Atomic Energy Act of 1954 [42 U.S.C. 2011 et seq.] and regulations issued under such Act)
 - Any article the sale of which is subject to the tax imposed by section 4181 of the Internal Revenue Code of 1986 [26 U.S.C. 4181] (determined without regard to any exemptions from such tax provided by section 4182 or 4221 or any other provision of such Code)²⁰⁷ and any component of such as article (limited to shot shells, cartridges, and components of shot shells and cartridges), and
 - Any food, food additive, drug, cosmetic, or device (as such terms defined in section 201 of the Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act [21 U.S.C. 321]) when manufactured, processed, or distributed in commerce for use as a food, food additive, drug, cosmetic, or device.

Premanufacture Notification Exemptions²⁰⁸

- § 720.30: *The following substances are not subject to the notification requirements of this part [C]:*
 - Any substance which is **not a “chemical substance”** [see above]
 - Any **mixture**²⁰⁹ *(a new chemical substance that is manufactured or imported as part of a mixture is subject to the requirements of this part. This exclusion applies only to a mixture as a whole and not to any chemical substances which are part of the mixture.)*

²⁰⁷ Pistols, revolvers, firearms (other than pistols and revolvers), shells and cartridges [<https://www.law.cornell.edu/uscode/text/26/4181>]

²⁰⁸ according to EPA, the agency has received over 14,000 exemption application since 1976

²⁰⁹ Mixtures = *any combination of two or more chemical substances if the combination does not occur in nature and is not, in whole or in part, the result of a chemical reaction; except “mixture” does include (1) any combination which occurs, in whole or in part, as a result of a chemical reaction if the combination could have been manufactured for commercial purposes without a chemical reaction at the time the chemical substances comprising the combination were combined, and if all of the chemical substances comprising the combination*

- Any new chemical substance which will be manufactured or imported in small quantities solely for **research and development** under §720.36
- Any new chemical substance which will be manufactured or imported solely for **test-marketing** purposes under an exemption granted under §720.38.
- Any new chemical substance manufactured **solely for export** if, when the substance is distributed in commerce: (1) The substance is labeled in accordance with section 12(a)(1)(B) of the Act. (2) The manufacturer knows that the person to whom the substance is being distributed intends to export it or process it solely for export as defined in §721.3 of this chapter.
- Any new chemical substance which is manufactured or imported under the terms of a rule promulgated under section 5(h)(4) of TSCA.
- Any **byproduct** if its only commercial purpose is for use by public or private organizations that (1) burn it as a fuel, (2) dispose of it as a waste, including in a landfill or for enriching soil, or (3) extract component chemical substances from it for commercial purposes. (This exclusion only applies to the byproduct; it does not apply to the component substances extracted from the byproduct.)
- The chemical substances described below: (Although they are manufactured for commercial purposes under TSCA, they are not manufactured for distribution in commerce as chemical substances per se and have no commercial purpose separate from the substance, mixture, or article of which they are a part.)
 - Any impurity.
 - Any byproduct which is not used for commercial purposes.
 - Any chemical substance which results from a chemical reaction that occurs incidental to exposure of another chemical substance, mixture, or article to environmental factors such as air, moisture, microbial organisms, or sunlight.
 - Any chemical substance which results from a chemical reaction that occurs incidental to storage or disposal of another chemical substance, mixture, or article.
 - Any chemical substance which results from a chemical reaction that occurs upon end use of another chemical substance, mixture, or article such as an adhesive, paint, miscellaneous cleanser or other housekeeping product, fuel additive, water softening and treatment agent, photographic film, battery, match, or safety flare, and which is not itself manufactured or imported for distribution in commerce or for use as an intermediate.
 - Any chemical substance which results from a chemical reaction that occurs upon use of curable plastic or rubber molding compounds, inks, drying oils, metal finishing compounds, adhesives, or paints, or any other chemical substance formed during the manufacture of an article destined for the marketplace without further chemical change of the chemical substance except for those chemical changes that occur as described elsewhere in this paragraph.
 - Any chemical substance which results from a chemical reaction that occurs when (i) a stabilizer, colorant, odorant, antioxidant, filler, solvent, carrier, surfactant, plasticizer, corrosion inhibitor, antifoamer or defoamer, dispersant, precipitation inhibitor, binder, emulsifier, deemulsifier, dewatering agent, agglomerating agent, adhesion promoter, flow modifier, pH neutralizer, sequesterant, coagulant, flocculant, fire retardant, lubricant, chelating agent, or quality control reagent functions as intended, or (ii) a chemical

are not new chemical substances, and (2) hydrates of a chemical substance or hydrated ions formed by association of a chemical substance with water, so long as the nonhydrated form is itself not a new chemical substance. [C]

substance, which is intended solely to impart a specific physiochemical characteristic, functions as intended.

- *Any nonisolated intermediate.*
 - *Any chemical substance which is manufactured solely for non-commercial research and development purposes. Non-commercial research and development purposes include scientific experimentation, research, or analysis conducted by academic, government, or independent not-for-profit research organizations (e.g., universities, colleges, teaching hospitals, and research institutes), unless the activity is for eventual commercial purposes.*
- § 720.36: Exemption for research and development [C]
 - *This part does not apply to a chemical substance if the following conditions are met:*
 - *The chemical substance is manufactured or imported only in small quantities solely for research and development.*
 - *The manufacturer or importer notifies all persons in its employ or to whom it directly distributes the chemical substance, who are engaged in experimentation, research, or analysis on the chemical substance, including the manufacture, processing, use, transport, storage, and disposal of the substance associated with research and development activities, of any risk to health, ..., which may be associated with the substance ...*
 - *The chemical substance is used by, or directly under the supervision of, a technically qualified individual.*
 - *A chemical substance is not exempt from reporting under this part if any amount of the substance, including as part of a mixture, is processed, distributed in commerce, or used, for any commercial purpose other than research and development, except where the chemical substance is processed, distributed in commerce, or used only as an impurity or as part of an article.*
 - *A person who manufactures or imports a chemical substance in small quantities solely for research and development is not required to comply with the requirements of this section if the person's exclusive intention is to perform research and development activities solely for the purpose of determining whether the substance can be used as a pesticide.*
 - *Quantities of the chemical substance, or of mixtures or articles containing the chemical substance, remaining after completion of research and development activities may be: (1) disposed of as a waste in accordance with applicable Federal, state, and local regulations, or (2) used for the following commercial purposes: (i) burning it as a fuel, (ii) reacting or otherwise processing it to form other chemical substances for commercial purposes, including extracting component chemical substances.*
- § 720.38: Exemptions for test marketing [C]
 - *Any person may apply for an exemption to manufacture or import a new chemical substance for test marketing. EPA may grant the exemption if the person demonstrates that the chemical substance will not present an unreasonable risk to injury to health or the environment as a result of the test marketing.*
- § 720.50: Chemical substances manufactured in quantities of 10,000 kilograms or less per year, and chemical substances with low environmental releases and human exposures [D]
 - *To manufacture a new chemical substance under the terms of this exemption a manufacturer must: (i) submit a notice of intent to manufacture 30 days before manufacture begins, as required under paragraph (e) of this section; (ii) comply with all other provisions of this section.*
 - *Any manufacturer of a new chemical substance satisfying all of the following low environmental release and low human exposure eligibility criteria*
 - *For exposure of consumers and the general population to the new chemical substance during all manufacturing, processing, distribution in commerce, use, and disposal of the substance:*

- *no dermal exposure.*
- *no inhalation exposure (except as described in paragraph (c)(2)(iv) of this section).*
- *exposure in drinking water no greater than a 1 milligram per year (estimated average dosage resulting from drinking water exposure in streams from the maximum allowable concentration level from ambient surface water releases established or a higher concentration authorized by EPA, see below).*
- *For exposure of workers to the new chemical substance during all manufacturing, processing, distribution in commerce, use and disposal of the substance:*
 - *no dermal exposure (this criterion is met if adequate dermal exposure controls are used in accordance with applicable EPA guidance).*
 - *No inhalation exposure (this criterion is considered to be met if adequate inhalation exposure controls are used in accordance with applicable EPA guidance).*
- *For ambient surface water releases, no releases resulting in surface water concentrations above 1 part per billion, calculated using the methods prescribed in §§721.90 and 721.91, unless EPA has approved a higher surface water concentration supported by relevant and scientifically valid data submitted to EPA in a notice ... on the substance or a close structural analogue of the substance which demonstrates that the new substance will not present an unreasonable risk of injury to aquatic species or human health at the higher concentration*
- *For ambient air releases from incineration, no releases of the new chemical substance above 1 microgram per cubic meter maximum annual average concentration, calculated using the formula: (kg/day of release after treatment) multiplied by (number of release days per year) multiplied by (9.68 × 10⁻⁶) micrograms per cubic meter.*
- *For releases to land or groundwater, no releases to groundwater, to land, or to a landfill unless the manufacturer has demonstrated to EPA's satisfaction in a notice under paragraph (e) of this section that the new substance has negligible groundwater migration potential*
- *A new chemical substance **cannot** be manufactured under this section ... if EPA determines ... that the substance, any reasonably anticipated metabolites, environmental transformation products, or byproducts of the substance, or any reasonably anticipated impurities in the substance may cause, under anticipated conditions of manufacture, processing, distribution in commerce, use, or disposal of the new chemical substance: (1) serious acute (lethal or sublethal) effects. (2) serious chronic (including carcinogenic and teratogenic) effects. (3) significant environmental effects.*
- §723.175: Chemical substances used in or for the manufacture or processing of instant photographic and peel-apart film articles [D]
 - *This exemption applies only to manufacturers of instant photographic or peel-apart film articles who: (1) Manufacture the new chemical substances used in or for the manufacture or processing of the instant photographic or peel-apart film articles. (2) Limit manufacture and processing of a new chemical substance to the site(s) listed in the exemption notice for that new chemical substance ... (3) Comply with the requirements ... (4) Do not distribute in commerce or use a peel-apart film article containing a new chemical substance until submission of a premanufacture notice under section 5(a)(1)(A) of the Act (15 U.S.C. 2604) and until the review period for the notice has ended without EPA action to prevent distribution or use.*
 - *All manufacturing, processing, and use operations involving the new chemical substance must be performed in a special production area under the conditions set forth in this paragraph until the*

new chemical substance has been incorporated into a wet mixture, photographic article, or instant photographic or peel-apart film article.

- *Exposure limits*
 - *Respiratory protection*
 - *Monitoring*
 - *Engineering controls and exposure safeguards*
 - *Training, hygiene, and work practices*
 - *Personal protection devices*
 - *Caution signs*
 - *Removal for storage or transportation*
 - *Labeling*
 - *Areas immediately adjacent to the special production area*
- *Conditions of processing outside the special production area. A wet mixture may be incorporated into a photographic article or an instant photographic or peel-apart film article outside the special production area under the conditions listed in this paragraph:*
 - *Engineering controls and exposure safeguards*
 - *Training, hygiene, and work practices*
 - *Personal protection devices*
- *Environmental release and waste treatment*
- §723.250: Polymers²¹⁰ [D]
 - *Polymers that cannot be manufactured under this section*
 - *Cationic polymers (a polymer that contains a net positively charged atom(s) or associated groups of atoms covalently linked to its polymer molecule): A polymer cannot be manufactured under this section if the polymer is a cationic polymer ... or if the polymer is reasonably anticipated to become a cationic polymer in a natural aquatic environment (e.g., rivers, lakes) unless: (i) The polymer is a solid material that is not soluble or dispersible in water and will be used only in the solid phase (e.g., polymers that will be used as ion exchange beads), or (ii) The combined (total) functional group equivalent weight of cationic groups in the polymer is equal to or greater than 5,000.*
 - *Elemental limitations:*
 - *A polymer manufactured under this section must contain as an integral part of its composition at least two of the atomic elements carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, oxygen, silicon, and sulfur.*
 - *A polymer cannot be manufactured under this section if it contains as an integral part of its composition, except as impurities, any elements other than the following:*
 - *carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, oxygen, silicon, and sulfur*
 - *Sodium, magnesium, aluminum, potassium, calcium, chlorine, bromine, and iodine as the monatomic counterions Na = , Mg = 2, Al = 3, K = , Ca = 2, Cl⁻, Br⁻, or I⁻.*
 - *Fluorine, chlorine, bromine, and iodine covalently bound to carbon.*

²¹⁰ Polymers = a chemical substance consisting of molecules characterized by the sequence of one or more types of monomer units and comprising a simple weight majority of molecules containing at least 3 monomer units which are covalently bound to at least one other monomer unit or other reactant and which consists of less than a simple weight majority of molecules of the same molecular weight. Such molecules must be distributed over a range of molecular weights wherein differences in the molecular weight are primarily attributable to differences in the number of monomer units. In the context of this definition, sequence means that the monomer units under consideration are covalently bound to one another and form a continuous string within the molecule, uninterrupted by units other than monomer units. [D]

- *Less than 0.20 weight percent of any combination of the atomic elements lithium, boron, phosphorus, titanium, manganese, iron, nickel, copper, zinc, tin, and zirconium.*
- *Polymers which degrade, decompose, or depolymerize. A polymer cannot be manufactured under this section if the polymer is designed or is reasonably anticipated to substantially degrade, decompose, or depolymerize, including those polymers that could substantially decompose after manufacture and use, even though they are not actually intended to do so. For the purposes of this section, degradation, decomposition, or depolymerization mean those types of chemical change that convert a polymeric substance into simpler, smaller substances, through processes including but not limited to oxidation, hydrolysis, attack by solvents, heat, light, or microbial action.*
- *Polymers manufactured or imported from monomers and reactants not on the TSCA Chemical Substance Inventory. A polymer cannot be manufactured under this section if the polymer being manufactured or imported is prepared from monomers and/or other reactants (that are either charged to the reaction vessel or incorporated in the polymer at levels of greater than 2 weight percent) that are not already included on the TSCA Chemical Substance Inventory or manufactured under an applicable TSCA section 5 exemption.*
- *Water absorbing polymers with number average molecular weight (MW) 10,000 and greater. A polymer cannot be manufactured under this section if the polymer being manufactured or imported is a water absorbing polymer and has a number average MW greater than or equal to 10,000 daltons. For purposes of this section, a water-absorbing polymer is a polymeric substance that is capable of absorbing its weight of water.*
- *Polymers which contain certain perfluoroalkyl moieties consisting of a CF₃- or longer chain length. ... after February 26, 2010, a polymer cannot be manufactured under this section if the polymer contains as an integral part of its composition, except as impurities, one or more of the following perfluoroalkyl moieties consisting of a CF₃- or longer chain length: Perfluoroalkyl sulfonates (PFAS), perfluoroalkyl carboxylates (PFAC), fluorotelomers, or perfluoroalkyl moieties that are covalently bound to either a carbon or sulfur atom where the carbon or sulfur atom is an integral part of the polymer molecule.*
- *Exempted: Polymers with number average MW greater than or equal to 1,000 and less than 10,000 daltons (and oligomer content less than 10 percent below MW 500 and less than 25 percent below MW 1,000).*
 - *The polymer cannot contain reactive functional groups unless it meets one of the following criteria:*
 - *(A) The polymer contains only the following reactive functional groups: carboxylic acid groups, aliphatic hydroxyl groups, unconjugated olefinic groups that are considered "ordinary," (i.e., not specially activated either by being part of a larger functional group, such as a vinyl ether, or by other activating influences, e.g., strongly electron-withdrawing sulfone group with which the olefinic groups interact), butenedioic acid groups, those conjugated olefinic groups contained in naturally-occurring fats, oils, and carboxylic acids, blocked isocyanates (including ketoxime-blocked isocyanates), thiols, unconjugated nitrile groups, and halogens (except that reactive halogen-containing groups such as benzylic or allylhalides cannot be included).*
 - *(B) The polymer has a combined (total) reactive group equivalent weight greater than or equal to 1,000 for the following reactive functional groups: acidhalides; acid anhydrides; aldehydes, hemiacetals; methylolamides,- amines or,- ureas; alkoxy silanes with alkoxy greater than C₂-alkoxy silanes; allyl ethers; conjugated olefins; cyanates; epoxides; imines; or unsubstituted positions ortho or para to phenolic hydroxyl; or*

- *If any reactive functional groups not included in paragraph (A) and (B) [above] present, the combined (total) reactive group equivalent weight, including any groups listed in paragraph (B) [above], is greater than or equal to 5,000.*
- *Exempted: Polymers with number average MW greater than or equal to 10,000 (and oligomer content less than 2 percent below MW 500 and less than 5 percent below MW 1,000)*
- *Exempted: Polyester polymers (a chemical substance that meets the definition of polymer and whose polymer molecules contain at least two carboxylic acid ester linkages, at least one of which links internal monomer units together) and is manufactured solely from one or more of the reactants in the following:*
 - Benzoic acid; canola oil; coconut oil; corn oil; cottonseed oil; dodecanoic acid; fats and glyceridic oils, anchovy/herring/menhaden/sardine/oiticica; fatty acids, C16-18 and C18-unsatd./castor-oil/coco/dehydrated castor-oil/linseed oil/safflower oil/soya/sunflower oil/sunflower-oil, conjugated/tall-oil/tall-oil, conjugated/vegetable oil; glycerides, C16-18 and C18-unsatd.; heptanoic acid; hexanoic acid; hexanoic acid, 3,3,5-trimethyl-; linseed oil; linseed oil, oxidized; nonanoic acid; oils cannabis/palm kernel/perilla/walnut; safflower oil; soybean oil; sunflower oil; tungo oil
 - 1,2/1,3/1,4-Benzenedicarboxylic acid (and some esters); 1,2,4-Benzenetricarboxylic acid; butanedioic acid (and dimethyl and diethyl esters); 2-butenedioic acid (E)-; decanedioic acid (and dimethyl and diethyl esters); dodecanedioic acid; fatty acids, C18-unsatd., dimers; heptanedioic acid (and dimethyl ester); hexanedioic acid (and dimethyl and diethyl esters); nonanedioic acid (and dimethyl and diethyl esters); octanedioic acid (and dimethyl ester); pentanedioic acid (and dimethyl and diethyl esters); undecanedioic acid;
 - 1,3-butanediol; 1,4-butanediol; 1,4-cyclohexanedimethanol; 1,2-ethanediol; ethanol, 2,2'-oxybis-; 1,6-hexanediol; 1,3-pentanediol, 2,2,4-trimethyl-; 1,2-propanediol; 1,3-propanediol, 2,2-bis(hydroxymethyl)-/2,2-dimethyl-/2-ethyl-2-(hydroxymethyl)-/2-(hydroxymethyl)-2-methyl/2-methyl; 1,2,3-propanetriol; 1,2,3-propanetriol, homopolymer; 2-propen-1-ol, polymer with ethenylbenzene;
 - Acetic acid, 2,2'-oxybis; 1-butanol; cyclohexanol; cyclohexanol, 4,4'-(1-methylethylidene)bis-; ethanol, 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)-; 1-hexanol; Methanol, hydrolysis products with trichlorohexylsilane and trichlorophenylsilane; 1-Phenanthrenemethanol, tetradecahydro-1,4a-dimethyl-7-(1-methylethyl)-; Phenol, 4,4'-(1-methylethylidene)bis-, polymer with 2,2'- [(1-methylethylidene)bis(4,1-phenyleneoxymethylene)] bis[oxirane]; Siloxanes and Silicones, di-Me, di-Ph, polymers with Ph silsesquioxanes, methoxy-terminated; Siloxanes and Silicones, di-Me, methoxy Ph, polymers with Ph silsesquioxanes, methoxy-terminated; Siloxanes and Silicones, Me Ph, methoxy Ph, polymers with Ph silsesquioxanes, methoxy- and Ph-terminated; Silsesquioxanes, Ph Pr

Significant new uses [L]: (a) for test marketing; (b) in small quantities solely for research and development (which needs to meet §721.47); (c) applied for and been granted an exemption under section 5(h)(5) of the Act; (d) as an impurity; (e) as a byproduct which is used only by public or private organizations that burn it as a fuel, dispose of it as a waste, including in a landfill or for enriching soil, or extract component chemical substances from it for commercial purposes; (f) as part of an article; (g) solely for export; (h) prior to the effective date of such section; under the terms of a consent order issued under section 5(e) of the Act applicable to that person.

Chemical data reporting [H]

- *The following groups or categories of chemical substances are exempted from some or all of the reporting requirements of this part, with the following exception: [polymers], [microorganisms], [water and certain forms of natural gas], or [partial exemptions] is not exempted from any of the reporting requirements of this part if that chemical substance is the subject of a rule proposed or promulgated under TSCA sections 4,*

5(a)(2), 5(b)(4), or 6, or is the subject of an enforceable consent agreement (ECA) developed under the procedures of 40 CFR part 790, or is the subject of an order issued under TSCA sections 4, 5(e), or 5(f), or is the subject of relief that has been granted under a civil action under TSCA sections 5 or 7.

- **Full exemptions.** The following categories of chemical substances are exempted from the reporting requirements of this part.
 - **Polymers:** (i) any chemical substance described with the word fragments “*polym,” “*alkyd,” or “*oxylated” in the Chemical Abstracts (CA) Index Name in the Master Inventory File, where the asterisk (*) in the listed word fragments indicates that any sets of characters may precede, or follow, the character string defined. (ii) Any chemical substance that is identified in the Master Inventory File as an enzyme, lignin, a polysaccharide (cellulose, gum, starch), a protein (albumin, casein, gelatin, gluten, hemoglobin), rubber, siloxane and silicone, or silsesquioxane. (iii) This exclusion does not apply to a polymeric substance that has been depolymerized, hydrolyzed, or otherwise chemically modified, except in cases where the intended product of this reaction is totally polymeric in structure.
 - **Microorganisms.** Any combination of chemical substances that is a living organism, and that meets the definition of microorganism at 40 CFR 725.3. Any chemical substance produced from a living microorganism is reportable under this part unless otherwise excluded.
 - **Naturally occurring chemical substances.** Any naturally occurring chemical substance, as described in 40 CFR 710.4(b). The applicability of this exclusion is determined in each case by the specific activities of the person who manufactures the chemical substance in question. Some chemical substances can be manufactured both as described in 40 CFR 710.4(b) and by means other than those described in 40 CFR 710.4(b). If a person described in § 711.8 manufactures a chemical substance by means other than those described in 40 CFR 710.4(b), the person must report regardless of whether the chemical substance also could have been produced as described in 40 CFR 710.4(b). Any chemical substance that is produced from such a naturally occurring chemical substance described in 40 CFR 710.4(b) is reportable unless otherwise excluded.
 - **Water and certain forms of natural gas.** Chemical substances with the following Chemical Abstracts Service Registry Number (CASRN): CASRN 7732-18-5, water; CASRN 8006-14-2, natural gas; CASRN 8006-61-9, gasoline, natural; CASRN 64741-48-6, natural gas (petroleum), raw liq. mix; CASRN 68410-63-9, natural gas, dried; CASRN 68425-31-0, gasoline (natural gas), natural; and CASRN 68919-39-1, natural gas condensates.
- **Partial exemptions.** The following groups of chemical substances are partially exempted from the reporting requirements of this part (i.e., the information described in § 711.15(b)(4) need not be reported for these chemical substances). Such chemical substances are not excluded from the other reporting requirements under this part.
 - **Petroleum process streams.** EPA has designated the chemical substances listed in Table 1 of this paragraph by CASRN,²¹¹ as partially exempt from reporting under the CDR.

²¹¹ <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-711>

- **Specific exempted chemical substances.** EPA has determined that, at this time, the information in §711.15(b)(4) associated with the chemical substances listed in paragraph (b)(2)(iv) of this section is of low current interest.²¹²

Reporting and recordkeeping

- 40 CFR §704.5 [F]: A person who is subject to reporting requirements for a substance identified in this part is exempt from those requirements to the extent that the person and that person's use of the substance is described in this section. This section is superseded by any TSCA section 8(a) rule that adds to, removes, or revises the exemptions described in this section.
 - **Articles.** A person who imports, processes, or proposes to import or process a substance identified in this part solely as part of an article is exempt from the reporting requirements of this part with regard to that substance.
 - **Byproducts.** A person who manufactures, imports, or proposes to manufacture or import a substance identified in this part solely as a byproduct is exempt from the reporting requirements of this part.
 - **Impurities.** A person who manufactures, imports, processes, or proposes to manufacture, import, or process a substance identified in this part solely as an impurity is exempt from the reporting requirements of this part.

²¹² **Considerations [H].** In making its determination of whether this partial exemption should apply to a particular chemical substance, EPA will consider the totality of information available for the chemical substance in question, including but not limited to, one or more of the following considerations:

- Whether the chemical substance qualifies or has qualified in past IUR or CDR collections for the reporting of the information described in § 711.15(b)(4).
- The chemical substance's chemical and physical properties or potential for persistence, bioaccumulation, health effects, or environmental effects (considered independently or together).
- The information needs of EPA, other Federal agencies, Tribes, States, and local governments, as well as members of the public.
- The availability of other complementary risk screening information.
- The availability of comparable processing and use information.
- Whether the potential risks of the chemical substance are adequately managed.

Amendments. EPA may amend the chemical substance list in paragraph (b)(2)(iv) of this section on its own initiative or in response to a request from the public based on EPA's determination of whether the information in § 711.15(b)(4) is of low interest.

- Any person may request that EPA amend the chemical substance list in Table 2 in paragraph (b)(2)(iv) of this section. Your request must be in writing and must be submitted to the address provided in 40 CFR 700.17(a). Please label your request as follows: Attention: TSCA Chemical Data Reporting - Partial Exemption Request. Requests must identify the chemical substance in question, as well as its CASRN or other chemical identification number as identified in § 711.15(b)(3)(i), and must contain a written rationale for the request that provides sufficient specific information, addressing the considerations listed in § 711.6(b)(2)(ii), including cites and relevant documents, to demonstrate to EPA that the collection of the information in § 711.15(b)(4) for the chemical substance in question either is or is not of low current interest. If a request related to a particular chemical substance is resubmitted, any subsequent request must clearly identify new information contained in the request. EPA may request other information that it believes necessary to evaluate the request. EPA will issue a written response to each request within 120 days of receipt of the request, and will maintain copies of these responses in a docket that will be established for each reporting cycle.
- As needed, the Agency will initiate rulemaking to make revisions to Table 2
- ..., requests must be submitted to EPA no later than 12 months prior to the start of the next principal reporting year.

- **Non-isolated intermediate.** A person who manufactures or proposes to manufacture a substance identified in this part solely as a non-isolated intermediate is exempt from the reporting requirements of this part.
- **Research and development.** A person who manufactures, imports, processes, or proposes to manufacture, import, or process a substance identified in this part only in small quantities solely for research and development is exempt from the reporting requirements of this part.
- **Small manufacturers and importers.** Small manufacturers and importers are exempt from the reporting requirements of this part.
- § 704.20 [F]: Chemical substances manufactured or processed at the nanoscale
 - Except: (i) chemical substances formed at the nanoscale as part of a film on a surface. (ii) DNA. (iii) RNA. (iv) proteins. (v) enzymes. (vi) lipids. (vii) carbohydrates. (viii) peptides. (ix) liposomes. (x) antibodies. (xi) viruses. (xii) microorganisms. (xiii) chemical substances which dissociate completely in water to form ions that are smaller than 1 nanometer. (xiv) chemical substances that are not on the TSCA Chemical Substance Inventory at the time reporting would otherwise be required under this section.
 - Persons who submitted a notice under 40 CFR parts 720 [premanufacture notification], 721 [significant new uses of chemical substances], or 723 [premanufacture notification exemptions] for a reportable chemical substance on or after January 1, 2005 are not required to submit a report for the reportable chemical substance submitted except where the person manufactures or processes a discrete form of the reportable chemical substance.
 - Section 704.5(a) through (e) apply to reporting under this section. Small manufacturers and processors as defined in paragraph (a) of this section are exempt from reporting under this section.
 - Persons who submitted some or all of the required information for a reportable chemical substance as part of the Nanoscale Materials Stewardship Program are not required to report the information previously submitted except where the person manufactures or processes a discrete form of the reportable chemical substance.
- § 712.20 [I]: Manufacturers Reporting – Preliminary Assessment Information
 - Solely for purposes of scientific experimentation, analysis, or research, including research or analysis for product development
 - Manufactured or imported fewer than 500 kilograms (1100 pounds) of the chemical substance at a single plant site
 - Small manufacturers (including importers) – with exemptions
 - As a byproduct that was not used or sold or that was accidentally formed
 - As a non-isolated intermediate
 - As an impurity

Commercial activity notification [G]

- *In general. The following activities do not trigger notification requirements under this subpart:*
 - *The manufacturing or processing of a chemical substance in small quantities solely for research and development.*
 - *The import or processing of a chemical substance as part of an article.*
 - *The manufacturing or processing of a chemical substance as described in § 720.30(g) or (h).*
 - *The manufacturing or processing of a chemical substance solely for export from the United States as described in § 720.30(e) or § 721.3, except where the Administrator has made a finding described in TSCA section 12(a)(2).*
 - *The manufacturing or processing of a chemical substance solely for test marketing purposes.*
- *Manufacturing or processing naturally occurring chemical substances. The following activities do not trigger notification requirements under this subpart:*

- *The manufacture of a naturally occurring chemical substance, as described in § 710.4(b). Some chemical substances can be manufactured both as described in § 710.4(b) and by means other than those described in § 710.4(b). If a person manufactures a chemical substance by means other than those described in § 710.4(b), this exemption is inapplicable, regardless of whether the chemical substance also could have been produced as described in § 710.4(b). This exemption does not cover the manufacture of a chemical substance from a naturally occurring chemical substance.*
- *The processing of a naturally occurring chemical substance only by manual, mechanical, or gravitational means; by dissolution in water; by flotation; or by heating solely to remove water.*

4. Initial data requirements

Premanufacture notification

- 40 CFR §720.45 [C]: *Each person who submits a notice must include the information specified in the notice form to the extent it is known to or reasonably ascertainable by the submitter. However, no person is required to include information which relates solely to exposure of human or ecological populations outside of the United States. The notice form requires the following information ...*
 - *The specific chemical identity of the substance²¹³*
 - *the currently correct [CAS name] for the substance, based on the Ninth Collective Index (9CI) of CA nomenclature rules and conventions, and consistent with listing for similar substances in the Inventory²¹⁴*
 - *the currently correct CASRN for the substance if a CASRN already exists for the substance*
 - *for a Class 1 substance and for any Class 2 substance for which a definite molecular formula is known or reasonably ascertainable, the correct molecular formula*
 - *for a Class 1 substance, a complete, correct chemical structure diagram, for a Class 2 substance or polymer, a correct representative or partial chemical structure diagram, as complete as can be known, if one can be reasonably ascertained.*
 - *For a polymer:*
 - *the specific chemical name and CASRN, if the number is available, of each monomer and other reactant used, at any weight percent, to manufacture the polymer. Tradenames or generic names of chemical reactants or monomers are not acceptable as substitutes from specific chemical names.*
 - *the typical percent by weight of each monomer and other reactant in the polymer (weight of the monomer or other reactant expressed as a percentage of the weight of the polymeric chemical substance manufactured), and the maximum residual amount of each monomer present in the polymer.*
 - *for monomers and other reactants used at 2 weight percent or less (based on the dry weight of the polymer manufactured), indicate on the PMN form any such monomers and other reactants that should be included as part of the polymer*

²¹³ *If an importer submitting the notice cannot provide all the information ... because it is claimed as confidential by the foreign supplier of the substance, the importer must have the foreign supplier ... provide the correct chemical identity information ... directly to EPA ... [C]*

²¹⁴ *For each substance having a chemical composition that can be represented by a specific, complete chemical structural diagram (a Class 1 substance), a CA Index Name must be provided. For each chemical substance that cannot be fully represented by a complete, specific chemical structure diagram (a Class 2 substance), or if the substance is a polymer, a CA Index Name or CA Preferred Name must be provided (whichever is appropriate based on CA 9CI nomenclature rules and conventions). In addition, for a Class 2 substance, the notice must identify the immediate chemical precursors and reactants by specific chemical name and [CASRN], if the number is available. Tradenames or generic names of chemical precursors or reactants are not acceptable as substitutes for specific chemical names. [C]*

description on the Inventory, where the weight percent is based on either (A) the weight of monomer or other reactant actually charged to the reaction vessel, or (B) the minimum weight of monomer or other reactant required in theory to account for the actual weight of monomer or other reactant molecules or fragments chemically incorporated (chemically combined) in the polymeric substance manufactured.

- *for a determination that 2 weight percent or less of a monomer or other reactant is incorporated (chemically combined) in a polymeric substance manufactured, as specific specified in [paragraphs (B)], analytical data or appropriate theoretical calculations (if it can be documented that analytical measurement is not feasible or not necessary) to support this determination must be maintained at the site of manufacture or import of the polymer.*
- *measured or estimated values of the minimum number-average molecular weight of the polymer and the amount of low molecular weight species below 500 and below 1,000 molecular weight, with a description of how the measured or estimated values were obtained.*
- *The impurities anticipated to be present in the substance by name, [CASRN], and weight percent of the total substance*
- *Known synonyms or trade names of the new chemical substance*
- *A description of the byproducts resulting from the manufacture, processing, use, and disposal of the new chemical substance*
- *The estimated maximum amount to be manufactured or imported during the first year of production and the estimated maximum amount to be manufactured or imported during any 12-month period during the first three years of production*
- *A description of intended categories of use by function and application, the estimated percent of production volume devoted to each category of use, and the percent of the new substance in the formulation for each commercial or consumer use*
- *For sites controlled by the submitter*
 - *The identity of sites where the new substance will be manufactured, processed, or used*
 - *A process description of each manufacture, processing, and use operation which includes a diagram of the major unit operations and chemical conversions, the identity and entry point of all feedstocks, and the points of release of the new chemical substance*
 - *Worker exposure information, including worker activities, physical form of the new substance to which workers may be exposed, the number of workers, and the duration of activities*
 - *Information on release of the new substance to the environment, including the quantity and media of release and type of control technology used*
 - *For sites not controlled by the submitter, a description of each type of processing and use operation involving the new chemical substance, including identification of the estimated number of processing or use sites, situations in which worker exposure to and/or environmental release of the new chemical substance will occur, the number of workers exposed and the duration of exposure, and controls which limit worker exposure and environmental release*
- *Each notice must contain all test data in the submitter's possession or control which are related to the effects on health or the environment of any manufacture, processing, distribution in commerce, use, or disposal of the new chemical substance or any mixture or article containing the new chemical substance, or any combination of such activities. This includes test data concerning the new chemical substance in a pure, technical grade, or formulated form.*

- *A full report or standard literature citation²¹⁵ must be submitted for the following types of test data: health effects data, ecological effects data, physical and chemical properties data, environmental fate characteristics, monitoring data and other test data related to human exposure to or environmental release of the chemical substance.*
- *Other data concerning the health and environmental effects of the new chemical substance that are known to or reasonably ascertainable by the submitter*
- *Data that need not be submitted: data previously submitted to EPA, (product) efficacy data, non-U.S. exposure data*
- *If a person (i) intends to manufacture or import a new chemical substance which is subject to the [premanufacture notification] and which is subject to a rule issued under section 5(b)(4) [concern list]; and (ii) is not required by a rule issued under section 4 of the Act [testing] to submit test data for the substance before the submission of a notice, the person submit to EPA data [which the person submitting the notice believes show that the manufacture, processing, distribution in commerce, use and disposal of the substance, or any combination of such activities, will not present an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment]. [C]*

§ 720.38: Exemptions for test marketing [C]

- *All existing data regarding health and environmental effects of the chemical substance, including physical/chemical properties or, in the absence of such data, a discussion of toxicity based on structure-activity relationships (SAR) and relevant data on chemical analogues.*
- *The maximum quantity of the chemical substance which the applicant will manufacture or import for test marketing.*
- *The maximum number of persons who may be provided the chemical substance during test marketing.*
- *The maximum number of persons who may be exposed to the chemical substance as a result of test marketing, including information regarding duration and route of such exposures.*
- *A description of the test-marketing activity, including its length and how it can be distinguished from full-scale commercial production and research and development.*

§ 720.50: low production-volume/exposure exemptions [D]

A manufacturer applying for an exemption ... must submit an exemption notice to EPA at least 30 days before manufacture of the new chemical substance begins...

- *Manufacturer identity*
- *Chemical identity*
- *Impurities*
- *Known synonyms or trade names*
- *Byproducts*

²¹⁵ *If the data do not appear in the open scientific literature, the submitter must provide a full report. A full report includes the experimental methods and materials, results, discussion and data analysis, conclusions, references, and the name and address of the laboratory that developed the data.*

If a test of experiment is completed before the notice review period ends, the person must submit the study, report, or test to the address listed on the notice form ... within ten days of receiving it, but no later than five days before the end of the review period. If the test or experiment is completed during the last five days of the review period, the submitter must immediately information its EPA contract for that notice by telephone.

For test data in the submitter's possession or control which are not listed ... a person is not required to submit a complete report. The person must submit a summary of the data. If EPA so requests, the person must submit a full report within ten days of the request, but not later than five days before the end of the review period.

All test data are subject to these requirements, regardless of their age, quality or results. [C]

- *Production volume*²¹⁶
- *Description of intended categories of use*
- *For manufacturer-controlled sites, the manufacturer shall supply identity of manufacturing sites, process descriptions, and worker exposure and environmental release information; for sites not controlled by the manufacturer, processing and use operation descriptions, estimated number of processing and use sites, and worker exposure/environmental release information*²¹⁷
- *Type and category of notice ...*
- *Test data*
- *Certification*²¹⁸
- *Sanitized copy of notice*

§723.175: Chemical substances used in or for the manufacture or processing of instant photographic and peel-apart film articles [D]

- *An exemption notices must be submitted to EPA when manufacture of the substance begins*
 - *manufacturer and sites*
 - *chemical identification*
 - Class 1 substances (whose composition can be represented by a definite structural diagram): chemical name (preferably CAS or IUPAC nomenclature), the molecular formula, CASRN (if available), known synonyms (including trade names), and a structural diagram
 - Class 2 substances (that cannot be fully represented by a structural diagram): chemical name, the molecular formula, CASRN (if available), and known synonyms (including trade names), the immediate precursors and reactants (by name and CASRN, if available), a partial or incomplete structural diagram, if available

²¹⁶ A. *Manufacturers submitting a [low production volume] exemption application ... will be assumed to be manufacturing at an annual volumes of less than 10,000 kilograms. Manufacturers who intend to manufacture an exempted substance at annual volumes of less than 10,000 kilograms and wish EPA to conduct its risk assessment based upon such lesser annual production level rather than a 10,000-kilograms level, may so specify by writing the lesser annual production volume in the appropriate box on the PMN form and marking the adjacent binding option box. Manufacturers who opt to specify annual production levels below 10,000 kilograms and who mark the production volume binding option box shall not manufacture more than the specific annual amount of the exempted substance unless a new exemption notice for a higher (up to 10,000 kgs) manufacturing volume is submitted and approved pursuant to this section.*

B. Manufacturers submitting a [low environmental release and low human exposure] exemption ... shall list the estimated maximum amount to be manufactured during the first year of production and the estimated maximum amount to be manufactured during any 12-month period during the first 3 years of production. [D]

²¹⁷ *A manufacturer applying for an [low production volume] exemption ... need not provide information on worker exposure and environmental release ... if such information is not known or not readily available to the manufacturer. To assist in reporting this information, manufacturers may obtain a copy of EPA' Guidance for Reporting Occupational Exposure and Environmental Release Information under 40 CFR 723.50 ... Where worker exposure and environmental release information is not supplied by the manufacturer, EPA will generally apply "bounding estimates" (i.e. exposure estimates higher than those incurred by persons in the population with the highest exposure) to account for uncertainties in actual exposure and release scenarios. [D]*

²¹⁸ *(A) the manufacturer intends to manufacture or import the new chemical substance for commercial purposes, other than in small quantities solely for research and development. (B) the manufacturer is familiar with the terms of this section. The manufacturer is familiar with the terms of this section and will comply with those terms. (C) The new chemical substance for which the notice is submitted meets all applicable exemption conditions. (D) For substances manufactured under an [low production volume] exemption, the manufacturer intends to commence manufacture of the exempted substance for commercial purposes within 1 year of the date of the expiration of the 30-day review period. [D]*

- Polymers: monomers and other reactants (by chemical name and CASRN), the amount of each monomer used (by weight percent of total monomer), the maximum residual of each monomer present in the polymer, a partial or incomplete structural diagram (if available), the number average molecular weight, the anticipated low molecular weight species. The notice must include this information for each typical average molecular weight composition of the polymer to be manufactured.
- Impurities (that can be reasonably anticipated to be present) by name and CASRN, by class of substances, or by process or source), estimated maximum percent (by weight) of each impurity, and the percent of unknown impurities
- Physical-chemical properties (where specific data are not available, reasonable estimates and the techniques used to develop these estimates must be provided)
- Byproducts: the name, CASRN (if available), the volume of each byproduct
- Production volume: anticipated maximum annual production volume
- Test data: on the health and environmental effects that are known to or reasonably ascertainable by the manufacturer
- Identity of the article (instant photographic film article(s) or peel-apart film article(s))
- Release to water: a description of the methods used to control and treat wastewater or discharge released to a POTW or other receiving body of water
- Certification (that the manufacturer is familiar with the terms of the exemption and compliance commitments)

§723.250: Polymers [D]

- *A report of manufacture or import must be submitted (postmarked) by January 31 of the year subsequent to initial manufacture*
 - *Manufacturer's name*
 - *Number of substances manufactured*

Significant new uses [L]

- § 721.25: *Each person who is required to submit a significant new use notice under this part must submit the notice at least 90 calendar days before commencing manufacture, import, or processing of a chemical substance identified in subpart E of this part for a significant new use. The submitter must comply with any applicable requirement of section 5(b) of the Act, and **the notice must include the information and test data specified in section 5(d)(1) of the Act.** The notice must be submitted on EPA Form 7710-25, and must comply with the requirements of part 720 of this chapter, except to the extent that they are inconsistent with this part 721.*
- § 721.30: *In certain sections of subpart E of this part, significant new uses for the identified substances are described as the failure to establish and implement programs providing for the use of either: specific measures to control worker exposure to or release of substances which are identified in such sections, or alternative measures to control worker exposure or environmental release which EPA has determined provide substantially the same degree of protection as the specified control measures. Persons who manufacture, import, or process a chemical substance identified in such sections and who intend to employ alternative measures to control worker exposure or environmental release must submit a request to EPA for a determination of equivalency before commencing manufacture, import, or processing involving the alternative control measures. ... A request for a determination of equivalency must contain:*
 - *The name of the submitter.*
 - *The specific chemical identity of the substance.*
 - *The citation for the specific section in subpart E of this part which pertains to the substance for which the request is being submitted.*

- *A detailed description of the activities involved.*
- *The specifications of the alternative worker exposure control measures or environmental release control measures.*
- *An analysis justifying why such alternative control measures provide substantially the same degree of protection as the specific control measures identified in the specific section in subpart E of this part which pertains to the substance for which the request is being submitted.*
- *The data and information described in § 720.50 (a) and (b) of this chapter unless such data and information have already been submitted to the Office of Pollution Prevention and Toxics, EPA.*

5. Information updates by companies

PMN notification

- *During the notice review period, if the submitter possesses, controls, or knows of new information that materially adds to, changes, or otherwise makes significantly more complete information included in the notice, the submitter must that information to the address listed on the notice form within ten days of receiving the new information, but no later than five days before the end of the notice review period. ... If the new information becomes available during the last five days of the notice review period, the submitter must immediately inform its EPA contract for that notice by telephone. [C]*

PMN notification – Recordkeeping [C]

- *Any person who submits a notice ... must retain documentation of information in the notice, including (1) other data, as defined in § 720.50(b), in the submitter's possession or control; and (2) records of production volume for the first three years of production or import, the date of commencement of manufacture or import, and documentation of this information. This information must be retained for five years from the date of commencement of manufacture of import.*

PMN notification – commencement of manufacture or import

- *Any person who commences the manufacture or import of a new chemical substance for a nonexempt commercial purpose for which that person previously submitted a section 5(a) notice under this part must submit a notice of commencement of manufacture or import.*
- *The submitter must submit the notice to EPA on, or no later than 30 calendar days, after the first day of such manufacture or import.*
- *The notice must contain the following information: (i) The specific chemical identity of the PMN substance. (ii) A generic chemical name (if the chemical identity is claimed as confidential by the submitter). (iii) The premanufacture notice (PMN) number assigned by EPA. (iv) The date of commencement for the submitter's manufacture or import for a non-exempt commercial purpose (indicating whether the substance was initially manufactured in the United States or imported). The date of commencement is the date of completion of non-exempt manufacture of the first amount (batch, drum, etc.) of new chemical substance identified in the submitter's PMN. For importers, the date of commencement is the date the new chemical substance clears United States customs. (v) The name and address of the submitter. (vi) The name of the authorized official. (vii) The name and telephone number of a technical contact in the United States. (viii) The address of the site where commencement of manufacture occurred. (ix) Clear indications of whether the chemical identity, submitter identity, and/or other information are claimed as confidential by the submitter.*
- *If the submitter claims the chemical identity confidential, and wants the identity to be listed on the confidential portion of the Inventory, the claim must be reasserted and substantiated in accordance with § 720.85(b). Otherwise, EPA will list the specific chemical identity on the public Inventory. Submitters who did not claim the chemical identity, submitter identity, or other information to be confidential in the PMN cannot claim this information as confidential in the notice of commencement.*

§ 720.36: Exemption for research and development [C] - Recordkeeping

- *Persons who manufacture or import a chemical substance under § 720.36 must retain the following records: (i) Copies of, or citations to, information reviewed and evaluated under § 720.36(b)(1) to determine the need to make any notification of risk. (ii) Documentation of the nature and method of notification under § 720.36(c)(1) including copies of any labels or written notices used. (iii) Documentation of prudent laboratory practices used instead of notification and evaluation under § 720.36(b)(2). (iv) The names and addresses of any persons other than the manufacturer or importer to whom the substance is distributed, the identity of the substance to the extent known, the amount distributed, and copies of the notifications required under § 720.36(c)(2). These records are not required when substances are distributed as impurities or incorporated into an article, in accordance with paragraph (d) of this section.*
- *A person who manufactures or imports a chemical substance under § 720.36 and who manufactures or imports the substance in quantities greater than 100 kilograms per year must retain records of the identity of the substance to the extent known, the production volume of the substance, and the person's disposition of the substance. The person is not required to maintain records of the disposition of products containing the substance as an impurity or of articles incorporating the substances.*
- *Records under this paragraph must be retained for 5 years after they are developed.*

§ 720.38: Exemptions for test marketing [C] - Recordkeeping

- *Any person who obtains a test-marketing exemption under this part must retain documentation of information in the application and documentation of compliance with any restrictions imposed by EPA when it granted the application. This information must be retained for five years from the final date of manufacture or import under the exemption.*

§ 720.50: low production-volume/exposure exemptions [D]

- *If the manufacturer of a new chemical substance under the terms of this exemption obtains test data or other information indicating that the new chemical substance may not qualify under terms of this section, the manufacturer must submit these data or information to EPA within 15 working days of receipt of the information. If, during the notice review period ..., the submitter obtains possession, control, or knowledge of new information that materially adds to, changes, or otherwise makes significantly more complete the information included in the notice, the submitter must send that information ... within 10 days of receiving the new information, but no later than 5 days before the end of the notice review period. The new submission must clearly identify the submitter and the exemption notice to which the new information is related. If the new information becomes available during the last 5 days of the notice review period, the submitter must immediately inform its EPA contact for that notice by telephone.*

§ 720.50 Exemption Notice - Changes

- *Any person who manufactures a new chemical substance ... must comply with the provisions of this section, including submission of a new notice ..., before [manufacturing]*
 - *... at a site that was not approved in a previous exemption notice for the substance ...*
 - *... for a use that was not approved in a previous exemption notice for the substance.*
 - *... without employing the human exposure and environmental release controls approved in a previous exemption notice for the substance.*
 - *... in a physical form different than that physical form approved in a previous exemption notice for the substance and which form may increase the human exposure to, or environmental release of, the new chemical substance over those exposures or releases resulting from the physical form approved in the previous notice.*
 - *... in annual production volumes above any volume designated by the manufacturer as binding ... in a previous exemption notice for the substance.*

- *In an exemption notice informing EPA of a change in site, use, or worker protection, or environmental release controls, the manufacturer is not required to provide all of the same information submitted to EPA in a previous exemption notice for that chemical substance. The new exemption notice, however, must indicate the identity of the new chemical substance; the manufacturer's name; the name and telephone number of a technical contact; and location of the new site, new worker protection or environmental release controls, and new use information.*
- *A manufacturer may, without submitting a new notice, manufacture the new chemical substance at a site not listed in its exemption application under the following conditions:*
 - *the magnitude, frequency, and duration of exposure of individual workers to the new chemical substance at the new manufacturing site is equal to, or less than, the magnitude, frequency, and duration of exposure of the individual workers to the new chemical substance at the manufacturing site for which the EPA performed its original risk-assessment pursuant to the original exemption notice; and*
 - *Either (1) at the new manufacturing site, the manufacturer does not release to surface waters any of the new chemical substance, or any waste streams containing the new chemical substance; or (2) at the new manufacturing site, the manufacturer maintains surface water concentrations of the chemical substance, resulting from direct or indirect discharges from the manufacturing site, at or below 1 part per billion, or at or below an alternative concentration level approved by the Agency in writing or under the procedures described ...*
 - *The manufacturer shall notify EPA of any new manufacturing site no later than 30 days after the commencement of manufacture of the new chemical substance under the exemption at the new manufacturing site ... The notification must contain the EPA-designated exemption number to which the notification applies, manufacturer identity, the street address of the new manufacturing site, the date on which manufacture commenced at the new site, the name and telephone number of a technical contact at the new site, any claim of confidentiality, and a statement that the notification is an amendment to the original exemption application under the terms of this section.*

§ 720.50 Exemption Notice - **Customer notification**

- *If the manufacturer learns that a direct or indirect customer is processing or using the new substance in violation of use restrictions or without imposing prescribed worker protection or environmental release controls, the manufacturer must cease distribution of the substance to the customer or the customer's supplier immediately unless the manufacturer is able to document each of the following:*
 - *That the manufacturer has, within 5 working days, notified the customer in writing that the customer has failed to comply with the conditions specified in this section and the exemption notice under paragraph (e) of this section.*
 - *That, within 15 working days of notifying the customer of the noncompliance, the manufacturer received from the customer, in writing, a statement of assurance that the customer is aware of the terms of this section and the exemption notice and will comply with those terms.*
- *If, after receiving a statement of assurance from a customer ... the manufacturer obtains knowledge that the customer has again failed to comply with any of the conditions specified in this section or the exemption notice, the manufacturer shall cease supplying the new chemical substance to that customer and shall report the failure to comply to EPA within 15 days of obtaining this knowledge. Within 30 days of its receipt of the report, EPA will notify the manufacturer whether, and under what conditions, distribution of the chemical substance to the customer may resume.*

§ 720.50 Exemption Notice - **Record keeping**

- *A manufacturer of a new chemical substance ... must maintain the records described in this paragraph at the manufacturing site or site of importation for a period of 5 years after their preparation.*

- *The records must include the following to demonstrate compliance with this section:*
 - *Records of annual production volume and import volume.*
 - *Records documenting compliance with the applicable requirements and restrictions ...*
- *Any person who manufactures a new chemical substance under the terms of this section must, upon request of a duly designated representative of EPA, permit such person at all reasonable times to have access to and to copy records kept under paragraph (n)(2) of this section.*
- *The manufacturer must submit the records listed in paragraph (n)(2) of this section to EPA upon request. Manufacturers must provide these records within 15 working days of receipt of such request.*

§723.175: Chemical substances used in or for the manufacture or processing of instant photographic and peel-apart film articles [D]

- *Manufacturers of a new chemical substance under this exemption must keep the following records for 30 years from the final date of manufacture*
 - *Production records*
 - *Exposure monitoring records: at a minimum – the chemical identity, date of the monitoring, the actual monitoring data for each monitoring location and sampling, and a reference to or description of the collection and analytic techniques, a record of the reasons for not monitoring and the methods used to determine compliance with the exposure limits (if no monitoring)*
 - *Training and exposure records: including the regular use of personal exposure safeguards (including the results of any personal exposure monitoring, the results of the quantitative fit test for the worker’s personal respirator)*
 - *Treatment records (of wastewater or discharge)*
- *The manufacturer must make the records listed in paragraph (j)(1) of this section available to EPA upon written request ... The manufacturer must provide these records within 15 working days of receipt of this request.*

§723.250: Polymers [D]

- *the manufacturer must to the extent known to or reasonably ascertainable by the manufacturer identify the following and maintain the records:*
 - *A specific chemical name and CAS Registry Number (or EPA assigned Accession Number) for each “reactant,” ..., used at any weight in the manufacture of the polymer. For purposes of determining chemical identity, the manufacturer may determine whether a reactant is used at greater than two weight percent according to either the weight of the reactant charged to the reaction vessel or the weight of the chemically combined (incorporated) reactant in the polymer. Manufacturers who choose the “incorporated” method must have analytical data, or theoretical calculations (if it can be documented that an analytical determination cannot be made or is not necessary), to demonstrate compliance with this paragraph. Reactants that introduce into the polymer elements, properties, or functional groups that would render the polymer ineligible for the exemption are not allowed at any level.*
 - *A representative structural diagram, if possible.*
- *a manufacturer must as of the date of first manufacture, make the following certification statements and maintain them:*
 - *The substance is manufactured or imported for a commercial purpose other than for research and development.*
 - *All information in the certification is truthful.*
 - *The new chemical substance meets the definition of a polymer, is not specifically excluded from the exemption ... of this section, and meets the conditions of the exemption ...*

- *A manufacturer ..., must retain the records described in this paragraph at the manufacturing site for a period of 5 years from the date of commencement of manufacture or import.*
 - *Chemical identity information ...*
 - *Information to demonstrate that the new polymer is not specifically excluded from the exemption.*
 - *Records of production volume for the first 3 years of manufacture and the date of commencement of manufacture.*
 - *Information to demonstrate that the new polymer meets the exemption criteria ...*
 - *Analytical data, or theoretical calculations (if it can be documented that an analytical determination cannot be made or is not necessary), to demonstrate that the polymer meets the number-average MW exemption criteria The analytical tests may include gel permeation chromatography (GPC).vapor pressure osmometry (VPO), or other such tests which will demonstrate that the polymer meets the number-average MW criterion.*
 - *Analytical data, or theoretical calculations (if it can be documented that an analytical determination cannot be made or is not necessary), to demonstrate that the polymer meets the criteria ..., meets the low MW content criteria*
 - *If applicable, analytical data, or theoretical calculations (if it can be documented that an analytical determination cannot be made or is not necessary) ... for determining monomers or reactants charged to the reaction vessel at greater than 2 weight percent but incorporated at 2 weight percent or less in the manufactured polymer.*
 - *The certification statements*
- *The manufacturer must submit the records ... to EPA upon written request by EPA. The manufacturer must provide these records within 15 working days of receipt of this request. In addition, any person who manufactures a new chemical substance under the terms of this section, upon request of EPA, must permit such person at all reasonable times to have access to and to copy these records.*

TSCA Section 8(c) (15 U.S.C. 2607) – records [B]

- *Any person who manufactures, processes, or distributes in commerce any chemical substance or mixture shall maintain records of significant adverse reactions to health or the environment, as determined by the Administrator by rule, alleged to have been caused by the substance or mixture. Records of such adverse reactions to the health of employees shall be retained for a period of 30 years from the date such reactions were first reported to or known by the person maintaining such records. Any other record of such adverse reactions shall be retained for a period of five years from the date the information contained in the record was first reported to or known by the person maintaining the record. Records required to be maintained under this subsection shall include records of consumer allegations of personal injury or harm to health, reports of occupational disease or injury, and reports or complaints of injury to the environment submitted to the manufacturer, processor, or distributor in commerce from any source. Upon request of any duly designated representative of the Administrator, each person who is required to maintain records under this subsection shall permit the inspection of such records and shall submit copies of such records.*

TSCA Section 8(e) (15 U.S.C. 2607) – notice to administrator of substantial risks [B]

- *Any person who manufactures, processes, or distributes in commerce a chemical substance or mixture and who obtains information which reasonably supports the conclusion that such substance or mixture presents a substantial risk of injury to health or the environment shall immediately inform [EPA] of such information unless such person has actual knowledge that the Administrator has been adequately informed of such information.*

Chemical data reporting [H]

- *The information described ... must be reported for each chemical substance manufactured (including imported) in an amount of 25,000 lb (11,340 kg) or more (or in an amount of 2,500 lb (1,134 kg) or more for*

chemical substances subject to the rules, orders, or actions described in § 711.8(b)) at any one site during any calendar year since the last principal reporting year. The requirement to report information described in paragraph (b)(4) of this section is subject to exemption as described in § 711.6.

- *A certification statement signed and dated by an authorized official of the submitter company*
- *Company and site information*
- **Chemical-specific information**
 - *The specific, currently correct CA Index name as used to list the chemical substance on the TSCA Inventory and the correct corresponding CASRN for each reportable chemical substance at each site. Submitters who wish to report chemical substances listed on the confidential portion of the TSCA Inventory will need to report the chemical substance using the corresponding TSCA Accession Number that is listed on the public portion of the Inventory. In addition to reporting the chemical identifying number itself, submitters must specify the type of number they are reporting by selecting from among the codes in Table 1 to paragraph (b)(3)(i).*
 - *For the principal reporting year only, a statement indicating, for each reportable chemical substance at each site, whether the chemical substance is manufactured in the United States, imported into the United States, or both manufactured in the United States and imported into the United States.*
 - *For the principal reporting year only, the total annual volume (in pounds) of each reportable chemical substance domestically manufactured or imported at each site. The total annual domestically manufactured volume (not including imported volume) and the total annual imported volume must be separately reported. These amounts must be reported to two significant figures of accuracy. In addition, the total annual volume (domestically manufactured plus imported volumes in pounds) of each reportable chemical substance at each site for each complete calendar year since the last principal reporting year.*
 - *For the principal reporting year only, the volume used on site and the volume directly exported of each reportable chemical substance domestically manufactured or imported at each site. These amounts must be reported to two significant figures of accuracy.*
 - *For the principal reporting year only, a designation indicating, for each imported reportable chemical substance at each site, whether the imported chemical substance is physically present at the reporting site.*
 - *For the principal reporting year only, a designation indicating, for each reportable chemical substance at each site, whether the chemical substance is being recycled or otherwise used for a commercial purpose instead of being disposed of as a waste or included in a waste stream.*
 - *For the principal reporting year only, the total number of workers reasonably likely to be exposed to each reportable chemical substance at each site.*
 - *For the principal reporting year only, the maximum concentration, measured by percentage of weight, of each reportable chemical substance at the time it is sent off-site from each site. If the chemical substance is site-limited, you must report the maximum concentration, measured by percentage of weight of the reportable chemical substance at the time it is reacted on-site to produce a different chemical substance. This information must be reported regardless of the physical form(s) in which the chemical substance is sent off-site/reacted on-site.*
 - *For the principal reporting year only, the physical form(s) of the reportable chemical substance as it is sent off-site from each site. If the chemical substance is site-limited, you must report the physical form(s) of the reportable chemical substance at the time it is reacted on-site to produce a different chemical substance. For each chemical substance at*

each site, the submitter must report as many physical forms as applicable from among the physical forms listed in this Unit: (A) Dry powder. (B) Pellets or large crystals. (C) Water- or solvent-wet solid. (D) Other solid. (E) Gas or vapor. (F) Liquid.

- For the principal reporting year only, submitters must report the percentage, rounded off to the closest 10 percent, of total production volume of the reportable chemical substance, reported in response to paragraph (b)(3)(iii) of this section, that is associated with each physical form reported under paragraph (b)(3)(ix) of this section.
- **Chemical-specific information related to processing and use.** ... Information required to be reported under this paragraph is limited to domestic (i.e., within the customs territory of the United States) processing and use activities. If information responsive to a given data requirement under this paragraph, including information in the form of an estimate, is not known or reasonably ascertainable, the submitter is not required to respond to the requirement.
 - **Industrial processing and use information.** (A) A designation indicating the type of industrial processing or use operation(s) at each site that receives a reportable chemical substance from the submitter site directly or indirectly (whether the recipient site(s) are controlled by the submitter site or not). (B) A code indicating the sector(s) that best describe the industrial activities associated with each industrial processing or use operation reported under paragraph (b)(4)(i)(A) of this section. (C) For each sector reported under paragraph (b)(4)(i)(B) of this section, the applicable code(s) from Table 6 to paragraph (b)(4)(i)(C) must be selected to designate the function category(ies) that best represents the specific manner in which the chemical substance is used. (D) The estimated percentage, rounded off to the closest 10 percent, of total production volume of the reportable chemical substance associated with each combination of industrial processing or use operation, sector, and function category. Where a particular combination of industrial processing or use operation, sector, and function category accounts for less than 5 percent of the submitter's site's total production volume of a reportable chemical substance, the percentage must not be rounded off to 0 percent if the production volume attributable to that industrial processing or use operation, sector, and function category combination is 25,000 lb (11,340 kg) or more during the reporting year. Instead, in such a case, submitters must report the percentage, rounded off to the closest 1 percent, of the submitter's site's total production volume of the reportable chemical substance associated with the particular combination of industrial processing or use operation, sector, and function category. (E) For each combination of industrial processing or use operation, sector, and function category, the submitter must estimate the number of sites at which each reportable chemical substance is processed or used. (F) For each combination of industrial processing or use operation, sector, and function category, the submitter must estimate the number of workers reasonably likely to be exposed to each reportable chemical substance.
 - **Consumer and commercial use information.** (A) Using the applicable codes listed in Table 9 to paragraph (b)(4)(ii)(A), submitters must designate the consumer and commercial product category(ies) that best describe the consumer and commercial products in which each reportable chemical substance is used (whether the recipient site(s) are controlled by the submitter site or not). (B) An indication, within each consumer and commercial product category reported under paragraph (b)(4)(ii)(A) of this section, whether the use is a consumer or a commercial use. (C) Submitters must determine, within each consumer and commercial product category reported under paragraph (b)(4)(ii)(A) of this section, whether any amount of each reportable chemical substance manufactured (including imported) by the submitter is present in (for example, a plasticizer chemical substance used to make pacifiers) or on (for example, as a component in the paint on a toy)

any consumer products intended for use by children age 14 or younger, regardless of the concentration of the chemical substance remaining in or on the product. (D) The estimated percentage, rounded off to the closest 10 percent, of the submitter's site's total production volume of the reportable chemical substance associated with each consumer and commercial product category. Where a particular consumer and commercial product category accounts for less than 5 percent of the total production volume of a reportable chemical substance, the percentage must not be rounded off to 0 percent if the production volume attributable to that commercial and consumer product category is 25,000 lb (11,340 kg) or more during the reporting year. Instead, in such a case, submitters must report the percentage, rounded off to the closest 1 percent, of the submitter's site's total production volume of the reportable chemical substance associated with the particular consumer and commercial product category. (E) Where the reportable chemical substance is used in consumer or commercial products, the estimated typical maximum concentration, measured by weight, of the chemical substance in each consumer and commercial product category reported under paragraph (b)(4)(ii)(A) of this section. (F) Where the reportable chemical substance is used in a commercial product, the submitter must estimate the number of commercial workers reasonably likely to be exposed to each reportable chemical substance.

Chemical data reporting [H] – Recordkeeping

- Each person who is subject to the reporting requirements of this part must retain records that document any information reported to EPA. Records relevant to reporting during a submission period must be retained for a period of 5 years beginning on the last day of the submission period. Submitters are encouraged to retain their records longer than 5 years to ensure that past records are available as a reference when new submissions are being generated.

Reporting and Recordkeeping

§723.250: Chemical substances manufactured or processed at the nanoscale [F]

- The following information must be reported for each discrete form of a reportable chemical substance to the extent that it is known to or reasonably ascertainable by the person reporting:
 - The common or trade name, the specific chemical identity including the correct Chemical Abstracts (CA) Index Name and available Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS) Registry Number, and the molecular structure of each chemical substance or mixture. Information must be reported as specified in § 720.45²¹⁹.
 - Material characteristics including particle size, morphology, and surface modifications.
 - Physical/chemical properties.
 - The maximum weight percentage of impurities and byproducts resulting from the manufacture, processing, use, or disposal of each chemical substance.
 - (i) Persons described in paragraph (b)(1) of this section must report the annual production volume for the previous three years before the effective date of the final rule and an estimate of the maximum production volume for any consecutive 12-month period during the next two years of production after the final effective date of this rule. (ii) Persons described in paragraph (b)(2) of this section must report the estimated maximum 12 month production volume and the estimated maximum production volume for any consecutive 12 month period during the first three years of production.

²¹⁹ <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-720/subpart-C/section-720.45>

- (iii) *Estimates for paragraphs (d)(5)(i) and (ii) of this section must be on 100% chemical basis of the discrete form of the solid nanoscale material.*
- *Use information describing the category of each use by function and application, estimates of the amount manufactured or processed for each category of use, and estimates of the percentage in the formulation for each use.*
 - *Detailed information on methods of manufacturing or processing.*
 - *Exposure information with estimates of the number of individuals exposed in their places of employment, descriptions and duration of the occupational tasks that cause such exposure, descriptions and estimates of any general population or consumer exposures.*
 - *Release information with estimates of the amounts released, descriptions and duration of the activities that cause such releases, and whether releases are directly to the environment or to control technology.*
 - *Risk management practices describing protective equipment for individuals, engineering controls, control technologies used, any hazard warning statement, label, safety data sheet, customer training, or other information which is provided to any person who is reasonably likely to be exposed to this substance regarding protective equipment or practices for the safe handling, transport, use, or disposal of the substance.*
 - *Existing information concerning the environmental and health effects.*

Commercial activity notification [G]

- *The system described under § 710.29(a) will provide a list of reportable chemical substances from which a person can select his or her chemical. The list will include the correct CASRN and CA Index name used to list a non-confidential chemical substance on the Inventory. For confidential substances on the Inventory, the list will include the TSCA Accession Number and generic name.*
 - *If an importer submitting a notice cannot provide the information specified in § 710.29(d)(4) because it is unknown to the importer and claimed as confidential by the supplier of the chemical substance or mixture, the importer must ask the supplier to provide the specific chemical identity information directly to EPA in a joint submission Contact information for the supplier, a trade name or other name for the chemical substance or mixture, and a copy of the request to the supplier must be included with the importer's submission.*
 - *If a manufacturer or processor submitting a notice cannot provide the information specified in § 710.29(d)(4) because the reportable chemical substance is manufactured or processed using a reactant having a specific chemical identity that is unknown to the manufacturer or processor and claimed as confidential by its supplier, the manufacturer or processor must ask the supplier of the confidential reactant to provide the specific chemical identity of the confidential reactant directly to EPA in a joint submission ... Contact information for the supplier, a trade name or other name for the chemical substance, and a copy of the request to the supplier must be included with the manufacturer's or processor's submission with respect to the chemical substance.*

Commercial activity notification [G] – Recordkeeping

- *Each person who is subject to the notification requirements of this part must retain records that document any information reported to EPA. Records relevant to a Notice of Activity under §§ 710.25(a) and 710.25(b) must be retained for a period of 5 years beginning on the last day of the submission period. Records relevant to a Notice of Activity under § 710.25(c) must be retained for a period of 5 years beginning on the day that the notice was submitted.*

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

TSCA Section 5(e) (15 U.S.C. 2604) – regulation pending development of information [B]

- [EPA] shall issue an order, to take effect on the expiration of the applicable review period, to prohibit or limit the manufacture, processing, distribution in commerce, use, or disposal of such substance or to prohibit or limit any combination of such activities to the extent necessary to protect against an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment, without consideration of costs or other nonrisk factors, including an unreasonable risk to a potentially exposed or susceptible subpopulation identified as relevant by [EPA] under the conditions of use, and the submitter of the notice may commence manufacture of the chemical substance, or manufacture or processing of the chemical substance for a significant new use including while any required information is being developed, only in compliance with the order.
 - The information available to [EPA] is insufficient to permit a reasoned evaluation of the health and environmental effects of a chemical substance with respect to which notice is required ..., or
 - In the absence of sufficient information to permit [EPA] to make such an evaluation, the manufacture, processing, distribution in commerce, use, or disposal of such substance, or any combination of such activities, may present an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment, without consideration of costs or other nonrisk factors, including an unreasonable risk to a potentially exposed subpopulation identified as relevant by [EPA] under the conditions of use, or
 - Such substance is or will be produced in substantial quantities, and such substance either enters or may reasonably be anticipated to enter the environment in substantial quantities or there is or may be significant or substantial human exposure to the substance.
 - An order may not be issued ... later than 45 days before the expiration of the applicable review period, and unless [EPA] has, on or before the issuance of the order, notified, in writing, each manufacturer or processor, as the case may be, of such substance of the determination which underlies such order.

Premanufacture notice [C]

- *Errors in the notice.*

Within 30 days of receipt of the notice, EPA may request that the submitter remedy errors in the notice. The following are examples of such errors: (i) Failure to date the notice form. (ii) Typographical errors that cause data to be misleading or answers to any questions to be unclear. (iii) Contradictory information. (iv) Ambiguous statements or information. In the request to correct the notice, EPA will explain the action which the submitter must take to correct the notice. If the submitter fails to correct the notice within 15 days of receipt of the request, EPA may extend the notice period under section (5)(c) of the Act, in accordance with § 720.75(c).
- *Incomplete submissions.*²²⁰
 - If EPA receives an incomplete submission, [EPA] will notify the submitter within 30 days of receipt that the submission is incomplete and that the notice review period will not begin until EPA receives a complete notice.

²²⁰ A submission is not complete, and the notification period does not begin, if: (i) The wrong person submits the notice form. (ii) The submitter does not sign the notice form. (iii) Some or all of the information in the notice or the attachments are not in English, except for published scientific literature. (iv) The submitter does not submit the notice in the manner set forth in § 720.40(a)(2). (v) The submitter does not provide information that is required by section 5(d)(1) (B) and (C) of the Act and § 720.50. (vi) The submitter does not provide information required on the notice form and by § 720.45 or indicate that it is not known to or reasonably ascertainable by the submitter. (vii) The submitter does not submit a second copy of the submission with all confidential information deleted for the public file, as required by § 720.80(b)(2). (viii) The submitter does not include any information required by section 5(b)(1) of the Act and pursuant to a rule promulgated under section 4 of the Act, as required by § 720.40(g). (ix) The submitter does not submit data which the submitter believes show that the chemical substance will not present an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment, if EPA has listed the chemical substance under section 5(b)(4) of the Act, as required in § 720.40(h). (x) The submitter does not include an identifying number and a payment identity number as required by 40 CFR 700.45(e)(3).

- *If EPA obtains additional information during the notice review period that indicates the original submission was incomplete, [EPA] may declare the submission incomplete within 30 days after EPA obtains the additional information and so notify the submitter.*
- *The notification that a submission is incomplete under paragraph (c)(2) (i) or (ii) of this section will include: (i) A statement of the basis of EPA's determination that the submission is incomplete. (ii) The requirements for correcting the incomplete submission. (iii) Information on procedures under paragraph (c)(4) of this section for filing objections to the determination or requesting modification of the requirements for completing the submission.*
- *Within ten days after receipt of notification by EPA that a submission is incomplete, the submitter may file written objections requesting that EPA accept the submission as a complete notice or modify the requirements necessary to complete the submission.*
 - *EPA will consider the objections filed by the submitter. [EPA] will determine whether the submission was complete or incomplete, or whether to modify the requirements for completing the submission. EPA will notify the submitter in writing of EPA's response within ten days of receiving the objections.*
 - *If [EPA] determines, in response to the objection, that the submission was complete, the notice review period will be deemed suspended on the date EPA declared the notice incomplete, and will resume on the date that the notice is declared complete. The submitter need not correct the notice as EPA originally requested. If EPA can complete its review within 90 days from the date of the original submission [EPA] may inform the submitter that the running of the review period will resume on the date EPA originally declared it incomplete.*
 - *If [EPA] modifies the requirements for completing the submission or concurs with EPA's original determination, the notice review period will begin when EPA receives a complete notice.*
- *Materially false or misleading statements.*
If EPA discovers at any time that person submitted materially false or misleading statements in the notice, EPA may find that the notice was incomplete from the date it was submitted, and take any other appropriate action.
- *Inspections.*
EPA will conduct inspections under section 11 of the Act to assure compliance with section 5 and this section, to verify that information submitted to EPA under this section is true and correct, and to audit data submitted to EPA under this section.

TSCA Section 4 / 15 U.S. Code § 2603 – Testing of chemical substances and mixtures [B]

- *[EPA] shall by rule, [(or order, or consent agreement, in the case of existing chemicals or mixtures)], require that testing be conducted on such substance or mixture to develop information with respect to the health and environmental effects for which there is an insufficiency of information and experience and which is relevant to a determination that the manufacture, distribution in commerce, processing, use, or disposal of such substance or mixture, or that any combination of such activities, does or does not present an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment, [If EPA finds that]*
 - *the manufacture, the distribution in commerce, processing, use, or disposal of a chemical substance or a mixture, or that any combination of such activities, may present an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment / a chemical substance or mixture is or will be produced in substantial quantities, and it enters or may reasonably be anticipated to enter the environment in substantial quantities or there is or may be significant or substantial human exposure to such substance or mixture*

- *there is insufficient information and experience upon which the effects of such manufacture, distribution in commerce, processing, use, or disposal of such substance or mixture or of any combination of such activities on health or the environment can reasonably be determined or predicted,*
- *testing of such substance or mixture with respect to such effects is necessary to develop such information, and*
- *in the case of a mixture, the effects which the mixture's manufacture, distribution in commerce, processing, use, or disposal or any combination of such activities may have on health or the environment may not be reasonably and more efficiently determined or predicted by testing the chemical substances which comprise the mixture*
- [EPA] *may, by rule, order, or consent agreement*
 - *require the development of new information relating to a chemical substance or mixture if [EPA] determines that the information is necessary to review a notice under Section 2604 ... or to perform a risk evaluation under section 2605(b) ...; to implement a requirement imposed in a rule, order, or consent agreement under [section 2604(e) or (f)] or in a rule promulgated under section 2605(a) ...; at the request of a Federal implementing authority under another Federal law, to meet the regulatory testing needs of that authority with regard to toxicity and exposure; or pursuant to section 2611(a)(2) ...*
 - *require the development of new information for the purposes of prioritizing a chemical substance under section 2605(b) ... only if [EPA] determines that such information is necessary to establish the priority of the substance, subject to the limitations that*
 - *not later than 90 days after the date of receipt of information regarding a chemical substance complying with a rule, order, or consent agreement ..., [EPA] shall designate the chemical substance as a high-priority substance or a low-priority substance, and*
 - *information required by [EPA] ... shall not be required for the purposes of establishing or implementing a minimum information requirement of broader applicability.*
 - *... [EPA] shall identify the need for the new information, describe how information reasonably available to [EPA] was used to inform the decision to require new information, explain the basis for any decision that requires the use of vertebrate animals, and, as applicable, explain why issuance of an order is warranted instead of promulgating a rule or entering into a consent agreement.*
 - *... [EPA] shall employ a tiered screening and testing process, under which the results of screening-level tests or assessments of available information inform the decision as to whether 1 or more additional tests are necessary, unless information available to the Administrator justifies more advanced testing of potential health or environmental effects or potential exposure without first conducting screening-level testing.*
- *A rule, order, or consent agreement ... shall include*
 - *identification of the chemical substance or mixture*
 - *protocols and methodologies for the development of information²²¹ for such substance or mixture, and*

²²¹ *A prescription of the health and environmental effects and information relating to toxicity, persistence, and other characteristics which affect health and the environment for which information for a chemical substance or mixture are to be developed and any analysis that is to be performed on such information, and to the extent necessary to assure that information respecting such effects and characteristics are reliable and adequate the manner in which such information are to be developed, (ii) the specification of any test protocol or methodology to be employed in the development of such information, and such other requirements as are necessary to provide such assurance. [B]*

- *with respect to chemical substances which are not new chemical substances and to mixtures, a specification of the period (which period may not be of unreasonable duration) within which the persons required to conduct the testing shall submit to [EPA] information ...*
- *in determining the protocols and methodologies and period to be included ... [EPA's] considerations shall include the relative costs of the various test protocols and methodologies which may be required under the rule, order, or consent agreement and the reasonably foreseeable availability of the facilities and personnel needed to perform the testing required under the rule, order, or consent agreement. Any such rule, order, or consent agreement may require the submission to [EPA] of preliminary information during the period prescribed ...*
- *Any rule, order, or consent agreement under subsection (a) requiring the testing of and submission of information for a particular chemical substance or mixture shall expire at the end of the reimbursement period²²² which is applicable to information for such substance or mixture unless [EPA] repeals the rule or order or modifies the consent agreement to terminate the requirement before such date; and a rule, order, or consent agreement ... requiring the testing of and submission of information for a category of chemical substances²²³ or mixtures shall expire with respect to a chemical substance or mixture included in the category at the end of the reimbursement period ... which is applicable to information for such substance or mixture unless [EPA] before such date repeals or modifies the application of the rule, order, or consent agreement to such substance or mixture or repeals the rule or order or modifies the consent agreement to terminate the requirement.*
- *Any person required by a rule or order ... to conduct tests and submit information on a chemical substance or mixture may apply to [EPA] ... for an exemption from such requirement. EPA shall exempt the applicant from conducting tests and submitting information on such substance or mixture under the rule or order with respect to which such application was submitted, on the basis of*
 - *the existence of previously submitted information*
 - *the fact that information is being developed by one or more persons pursuant to a rule, order, or consent*
- *Priority list – In making a recommendation respecting which chemical substances and mixtures to give priority consideration for the development of information, the committee shall consider all relevant factors, including*
 - *the quantities in which the substance or mixture is or will be manufactured,*
 - *the quantities in which the substance or mixture enters or will enter the environment,*
 - *the number of individuals who are or will be exposed to the substance or mixture in their places of employment and the duration of such exposure,*
 - *the extent to which human beings are or will be exposed to the substance or mixture,*
 - *the extent to which the substance or mixture is closely related to a chemical substance or mixture which is known to present an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment,*
 - *the existence of information concerning the effects of the substance or mixture on health or the environment,*

²²² The reimbursement period for any information for a chemical substance or mixture is a period beginning on the date such information is submitted in accordance with a rule, order, or consent agreement ... and ending—five years after the beginning date or at the expiration of a period which begins on the beginning date and which is equal to the period which EPA determines was necessary to develop such information, whichever is later. [B]

²²³ category of chemical substances/mixtures = a group of [chemical substances/mixtures] the members of which are similar in molecular structure, in physical, chemical, or biological properties, in use, or in mode of entrance into the human body or into the environment, or the members of which are in some other way suitable for classification as such for purposes of this chapter, except that such term does not mean a group of chemical substances which are grouped together solely on the basis of their being new chemical substances. [B]

- *the extent to which testing of the substance or mixture may result in the development of information upon which the effects of the substance or mixture on health or the environment can reasonably be determined or predicted, and*
 - *the reasonably foreseeable availability of facilities and personnel for performing testing on the substance or mixture.*
- *Priority list – The recommendations of the committee shall be in the form of a list of chemical substances and mixtures which shall be set forth, either by individual substance or mixture or by groups of substances or mixtures, in the order in which the committee determines [EPA] should take action [on testing] ... with respect to the substances and mixtures. In establishing such list, the committee shall give priority attention to those chemical substances and mixtures which are known to cause or contribute to or which are suspected of causing or contributing to cancer, gene mutations, or birth defects. The committee shall designate chemical substances and mixtures on the list with respect to which the committee determines [EPA] should, within 12 months of the date on which such substances and mixtures are first designated, initiate a proceeding [on testing]. The total number of chemical substances and mixtures on the list which are designated under the preceding sentence may not, at any time, exceed 50.*
 - *... the committee shall publish in the Federal Register and transmit to [EPA] the list and designations ... together with the reasons for the committee's inclusion of each chemical substance or mixture on the list. At least every six months after the date of the transmission to [EPA] of the list pursuant to the preceding sentence, the committee shall make such revisions in the list as it determines to be necessary and shall transmit them to [EPA] together with the committee's reasons for the revisions.*
 - *Upon receipt of any such revision, [EPA] shall publish in the Federal Register the list with such revision, the reasons for such revision, and the designations ... [EPA] shall provide reasonable opportunity to any interested person to file with [EPA] written comments on the committee's list, any revision of such list by the committee, and designations made by the committee, and shall make such comments available to the public.*
 - *Within the 12-month period beginning on the date of the first inclusion on the list of a chemical substance or mixture designated by the committee ... [EPA] shall with respect to such chemical substance or mixture issue an order, enter into a consent agreement, or initiate a rulemaking proceeding ..., or, if such an order or consent agreement is not issued or such a proceeding is not initiated within such period, publish in the Federal Register the Administrator's reason for not issuing such an order, entering into such a consent agreement, or initiating such a proceeding.*
- *Reduction of testing on vertebrates*
 - *Prior to making a request or adopting a requirement for testing using vertebrate animals ... taking into consideration, as appropriate and to the extent practicable and scientifically justified, reasonably available existing information, including toxicity information, computational toxicology and bioinformatics, and high-throughput screening methods and the prediction models of those methods*
 - *Encouraging and facilitating the use of scientifically valid test methods and strategies that reduce or replace the use of vertebrate animals while providing information of equivalent or better scientific quality and relevant that will support regulatory decisions under this subchapter; the grouping of 2 or more chemical substances into scientifically appropriate categories in cases in which testing of a chemical substance would provide scientifically valid and useful information on other chemical substances in the category; and the formation of industry consortia to jointly conduct testing to avoid unnecessary duplication of tests, provided that such consortia make all information from such testing available to [EPA].*
 - *Any person developing information for submission under this subchapter on a voluntary basis and not pursuant to any request or requirement by [EPA] shall first attempt to develop the information*

by means of an alternative test method or strategy identified by [EPA] ... before conducting new vertebrate animal testing.

- ... [EPA] shall ... develop a strategic plan to promote the development and implementation of alternative test methods and strategies to reduce, refine, or replace vertebrate animal testing and provide information of equivalent or better scientific quality and relevance for assessing risks of injury to health or the environment of chemical substances or mixtures through, for example computational toxicology and bioinformatics, high-throughput screening methods, testing of categories of chemical substances, tiered testing methods, in vitro studies, systems biology, new or revised methods identified by validation bodies such as the Interagency Coordinating Committee on the Validation of Alternative Methods or the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, or industry consortia that develop information submitted under this subchapter.

TSCA Section 8b (§2607) – reporting and retention of information [B]

- Not later than 1 year after June 22, 2016, [EPA], by rule, shall require manufacturers, and may require processors, subject to the limitations under subsection (a)(5)(A), to notify the Administrator, by not later than 180 days after the date on which the final rule is published in the Federal Register, of each chemical substance on the list published under paragraph (1) that the manufacturer or processor, as applicable, has manufactured or processed for a nonexempt commercial purpose during the 10-year period ending on the day before June 22, 2016.
 - No chemical substance on the list published under paragraph (1) shall be removed from such list by reason of the implementation of this subparagraph, or be subject to section 2604(a)(1)(A)(i) of this title by reason of a change to active status under paragraph (5)(B).

TSCA Section 8(d) (15 U.S.C. 2607) – health and safety studies [B]

- [EPA] shall promulgate rules under which [EPA] shall require any person who manufactures, processes, or distributes in commerce or who proposes to manufacture, process, or distribute in commerce any chemical substance or mixture (or with respect to paragraph (2), any person who has possession of a study) to submit to [EPA]—
 - lists of health and safety studies (A) conducted or initiated by or for such person with respect to such substance or mixture at any time, (B) known to such person, or (C) reasonably ascertainable by such person, except that [EPA] may exclude certain types or categories of studies from the requirements of this subsection if [EPA] finds that submission of lists of such studies are unnecessary to carry out the purposes of this chapter; and
 - copies of any study contained on a list submitted pursuant to paragraph (1) or otherwise known by such person.

TSCA Section 11 (15 U.S.C. 2610) – inspections [B]

- For purposes of administering this chapter, [EPA], and any duly designated representative of [EPA], may inspect any establishment, facility, or other premises in which chemical substances, mixtures, or products subject to subchapter IV are manufactured, processed, stored, or held before or after their distribution in commerce and any conveyance being used to transport chemical substances, mixtures, such products, or such articles in connection with distribution in commerce.
 - Each such inspection shall be commenced and completed with reasonable promptness and shall be conducted at reasonable times, within reasonable limits, and in a reasonable manner.
 - an inspection conducted under subsection (a) shall extend to all things within the premises or conveyance inspected (including records, files, papers, processes, controls, and facilities) bearing on whether the requirements of this chapter applicable to the chemical substances, mixtures, or products subject to subchapter IV within such premises or conveyance have been complied with.

- *No inspection under subsection (a) shall extend to (A) financial information, (B) sales information (other than shipment information), (C) pricing information, (D) personnel information, or (E) research information (other than information required by this chapter or under a rule promulgated, order issued, or consent agreement entered into thereunder), unless the nature and extent of such information are described with reasonable specificity in the written notice required by subsection (a) for such inspection.*

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

TSCA Section 5 / 15 U.S. Code § 2604(f) – protection against unreasonable risks [B]

- *If [EPA] determines that a chemical substance or significant new use with respect to which notice is required ... present an unreasonable risk of injury to health or environment, without consideration of costs or other nonrisk factors, including an unreasonable risk to a potentially exposed subpopulation identified as relevant by [EPA] under the conditions of use, [EPA] shall, before the expiration of the applicable review period, take the action authorized to the extent necessary to protect against such risk.*
 - *[EPA] may issue a proposed rule ... including a requirement limiting the amount of such substance which may be manufactured, processed, or distributed in commerce, a requirement described in paragraph (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), and/or (7) of section 2605(a)*
 - *[EPA] may issue an order to prohibit or limit the manufacture, processing, or distribution in commerce of [the] substance.*
 - *Not later than 90 days after taking an action (above) or issuing an order under subsection (e) relating to [the] substance ... [EPA] shall consider whether to promulgate a rule ... that identifies as a significant new use any manufacturing, processing, use, distribution in commerce, or disposal of the chemical substance that does not conform to the restrictions imposed by the action or order, and as applicable, initiate such a rulemaking or publish a statement describing the reasons of [EPA] for not initiating such a rulemaking.*
 - *If [EPA] finds ... that a chemical substance or significant new use is not likely to present an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment, then notwithstanding any remaining portion of the applicable review period, the submitter of the notice may commence manufacture of the chemical substance or manufacture or processing for the significant new use, and [EPA] shall make public a statement of [EPA]'s finding. Such a statement shall be submitted for publication in the Federal Register as soon as is practicable before the expiration of such period. Publication of such statement in accordance with the preceding sentence is not a prerequisite to the manufacturing or processing of the substance with respect to which the statement is to be published.*

Premanufacture notice [C]

- *When EPA receives a notice, EPA will review it to determine whether the chemical substance is subject to the requirements of this part. If EPA determines that the chemical substance is not subject to these requirements, EPA will notify the submitter that section 5 of the Act does not prevent the manufacture or import of the substance and that the submission is not a notice under this part.*
- *Notification to the submitter.*
EPA will acknowledge receipt of each notice ... to the submitter that identifies the premanufacture notice number assigned to the new chemical substance and date on which the review period begins. The review period will begin on the date the notice is received by the Office of Pollution Prevention and Toxics Document Control Officer. The acknowledgment does not constitute a finding by EPA that the notice, as submitted, is in compliance with this part.
- *Notice review*
The notice review period specified in section 5(a) of the Act runs for 90 days from the date [EPA] receives a complete notice, or the date EPA determines the notice is complete ..., unless the Agency extends the period ...

- *A submitter may voluntarily suspend the running of the notice review period if [EPA] agrees. If [EPA] does not agree, the review period will continue to run, and EPA will notify the submitter. A submitter may request a suspension at any time during the notice review period. The suspension must be for a specified period of time.*
- *At any time during the notice review period, EPA may determine that good cause²²⁴ exists to extend the notice review period specified in paragraph (a) of this section.*
 - *If EPA makes such a determination, EPA will: Notify the submitter that EPA is extending the notice review period for a specified length of time, and state the reasons for the extension. Issue a notice for publication in the Federal Register which states that EPA is extending the notice review period and gives the reasons for the extension.*
 - *The initial extension may be for a period of up to 90 days. If the initial extension is for less than 90 days, EPA may make additional extensions. However, the total period of extensions may not exceed 90 days for any notice.*
- *Notice of expiration of notice review period.*
EPA will notify the submitter that the notice review period has expired or that EPA has completed its review of the notice. Expiration of the review period does not constitute EPA approval or certification of the new chemical substance, and does not mean that EPA may not take regulatory action against the substance in the future. After expiration of the statutory notice review period, in the absence of regulatory action by EPA under section 5(e), 5(f), or 6(a) of the Act, the submitter may manufacture or import the chemical substance even if the submitter has not received notice of expiration.

§ 720.38: Exemptions for test marketing [C]

- *No later than 45 days after EPA receives an application, the Agency will either approve or deny the application. Thereafter, EPA will publish a notice in the Federal Register explaining the reasons for approval or denial.*
- *In approving an application for exemption, EPA may impose any restrictions necessary to ensure that the substance will not present an unreasonable risk of injury to health and the environment as a result of test marketing.*

§ 720.50: low production-volume/exposure exemptions [D]

- *EPA will review the notice submitted ... to determine whether manufacture of the new chemical substance is eligible for the exemption. The review period will end 30 days after receipt of the notice ... To provide additional time to address any unresolved issues concerning an exemption application, the exemption applicant may, at any time during the review period, request a suspension of the review period ...*
 - *Upon expiration of the 30-day review period, if EPA has taken no action, the manufacturer may consider its exemption approved and begin to manufacture the new chemical substance ...*
 - *If the EPA determines during the review period that manufacture of the new chemical substance does not meet the terms of this section or that there are issues concerning toxicity or exposure that require further review which cannot be accomplished within the 30-day review period, EPA will notify the manufacture ... that the substance is not eligible ... The manufacturer may not begin manufacture of the new chemical substances without complying with section 5(a)(1) of the Act or submitting a new notice ... that satisfies EPA's concerns.*

²²⁴ (4) *Examples: (i) EPA has reviewed the notice and determined that there is a significant possibility that the chemical substance will be regulated under section 5(e) or section 5(f) of the Act, but EPA is unable to initiate regulatory action within the initial 90-day period. (ii) EPA has reviewed the submission and is seeking additional information. (iii) EPA has received significant additional information during the notice review period. (iv) The submitter has failed to correct a notice after receiving EPA's request under § 720.65(b).*

- *If at any time after the review period ... [EPA]²²⁵ makes a preliminary determination that manufacture of the new chemical substance does not meet the terms ... [EPA] will notify the manufacturer ...*
 - *The manufacturer may continue to manufacture, process, distribute in commerce, and use the substance after receiving the notice ... if the manufacturer was manufacturing, processing, distributing in commerce, or using the substance at the time of the notification and if the manufacturer submits objection or an explanation ... Manufacturers not manufacturing, processing, distributing in commerce, or using the substance at the time of the notification may not begin manufacture until EPA makes its final determination ...*
 - *... [EPA] will notify the manufacturer of the final determination ... within 15 days of receipt of the objections or explanation ...*
 - *If [EPA] determines the manufacture of the new chemical substances does not meet the terms of this section and that the manufacturer did not act with due diligence and in good faith to meet the terms of this section, the manufacturer must cease any continuing manufacture, processing, distribution in commerce, and use of the new chemical substance within 7 days of the written notification ... The manufacturer may not resume manufacture, processing, distribution in commerce, and use of the new chemical substance until it submits a [premanufacture] notice ... and the notice review period has ended.*
 - *If [EPA] determines the manufacture of the new chemical substances does not meet the terms of this section and that the manufacturer acted with due diligence and in good faith to meet the terms of this section, the manufacturer may continue manufacture, processing, distribution in commerce, and use of the new chemical substance if*
 - *it was actually manufacturing, processing, distributing in commerce, or using the chemical substance at the time it received the notification ...*
 - *it submits a [premanufacture] notice on the new chemical substance ... within 15 days of receipt of the written notification ... Such manufacture, processing, distribution in commerce, and use may continue unless EPA takes action under section 5(e) or 5(f) of the Act.*

§723.175: Chemical substances used in or for the manufacture or processing of instant photographic and peel-apart film articles [\[D\]](#)

- *EPA may amend or repeal any term of this exemption if it determines that the manufacture, processing, distribution, use, and disposal of new chemical substances under the terms of the exemption may present an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment. EPA also may amend this exemption to enlarge the exemption category or to reduce the restrictions or conditions of the exemption.*
- *[EPA] may prohibit the manufacture, processing, distribution, use, or disposal of any new chemical substance under the terms of this exemption if he or she determines that the manufacture, processing, distribution in commerce, use, or disposal of the new chemical substance may present an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment.*

Significant new use [\[L\]](#)

TSCA Section 4 / 15 U.S. Code § 2603 – Testing of chemical substances and mixtures [\[B\]](#)

- *Upon the receipt of any information required to be submitted ..., or any other information available to [EPA],*

²²⁵ In the original article, this is the role of the Assistant Administrator for the Office of Chemical Safety and Pollution Prevention. To simplified the read, the text here and below is replaced with [EPA].

which indicates to [EPA] that there may be a reasonable basis to conclude that a chemical substance or mixture presents a significant risk of serious or widespread harm to human beings, [EPA] shall, within the 180-day period beginning on the date of the receipt of such information, initiate applicable action under section 2604, 2605, or 2606 ... to prevent or reduce to a sufficient extent such risk or publish in the Federal Register a finding, **made without consideration of costs or other nonrisk factors**, that such risk is not unreasonable. For good cause shown [EPA] may extend such period for an additional period of not more than 90 days. [EPA] shall publish in the Federal Register notice of any such extension and the reasons therefor. A finding by [EPA] that a risk is not unreasonable shall be considered agency action ...

TSCA Section 6 / 15 U.S. Code § 2605 – prioritization, risk evaluation and regulation of chemical substances and mixtures [B]

- *If [EPA] determines ... that the manufacture, processing, distribution in commerce, use, or disposal of a chemical substance or mixture, or that any combination of such activities, presents an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment, [EPA] shall by rule ... apply one or more of the following requirements to such substance or mixture to the extent necessary so that the chemical substance or mixture no longer presents such risk*
 - *A requirement prohibiting or otherwise restricting the manufacturing, processing, or distribution in commerce of such substance or mixture, or limiting the amount of such substance or mixture which may be manufactured, processed, or distributed in commerce.*
 - *A requirement prohibiting or otherwise restricting the manufacture, processing, or distribution in commerce of such substance or mixture for a particular use or a particular use in a concentration in excess of a level specified by [EPA] in the rule imposing the requirement, or limiting the amount of such substance or mixture which may be manufactured, processed, or distributed in commerce for a particular use or a particular use in a concentration in excess of a level specified by [EPA] in the rule imposing the requirement.*
 - *A requirement that such substance or mixture or any article containing such substance or mixture be marked with or accompanied by clear and adequate minimum warnings and instructions with respect to its use, distribution in commerce, or disposal or with respect to any combination of such activities. The form and content of such minimum warnings and instructions shall be prescribed by [EPA].*
 - *A requirement that manufacturers and processors of such substance or mixture make and retain records of the processes used to manufacture or process such substance or mixture or monitor or conduct tests which are reasonable and necessary to assure compliance.*
 - *A requirement prohibiting or otherwise regulating any manner or method of commercial use of such substance or mixture.*
 - *A requirement prohibiting or otherwise regulating any manner or method of disposal of such substance or mixture, or of any article containing such substance or mixture, by its manufacturer or processor or by any other person who uses, or disposes of, it for commercial purposes.*
 - *[EPA] may not require any person to take any action which would be in violation of any law or requirement of, or in effect for, a State or political subdivision, and shall require each person subject to it to notify each State and political subdivision in which a required disposal may occur of such disposal.*
 - *A requirement directing manufacturers or processors of such substance or mixture to give notice of such determination to distributors in commerce of such substance or mixture and, to the extent reasonably ascertainable, to other persons in possession of such substance or mixture or exposed to such substance or mixture, to give public notice of such determination, and to replace or repurchase such substance or mixture as elected by the person to which the requirement is directed.*

- Any requirement (or combination of requirements) imposed ... may be limited in application to specified geographic areas.
- [EPA] shall designate as a high-priority substance a chemical substance that [EPA] concludes, without consideration of costs or other nonrisk factors, may present an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment because of a potential hazard and a potential route of exposure under the conditions of use, including an unreasonable risk to a potentially exposed or susceptible subpopulation identified as relevant by [EPA].
- [EPA] shall designate a chemical substance as a low-priority substance if the Administrator concludes, based on information sufficient to establish, without consideration of costs or other nonrisk factors, that such substance does not meet the standard ... for designating a chemical substance a high-priority substance.
- Not later than three and one half years after June 22, 2016, [EPA] shall ensure that risk evaluations are being conducted on at least 20 high-priority substances and that at least 20 chemical substances have been designated as low-priority substances, subject to the limitation that at least 50 percent of all chemical substances on which risk evaluations are being conducted by [EPA] are drawn from the 2014 update of the TSCA Work Plan for Chemical Assessments.²²⁶
- Upon designating a chemical substance as a high-priority substance, [EPA] shall initiate a risk evaluation on the substance. [EPA] may revise the designation of a low-priority substance based on information made available to [EPA]. [EPA] shall designate at least one high-priority substance upon the completion of each risk evaluation.
- [EPA] shall conduct and publish risk evaluations... for a chemical substance—
 - that has been identified under paragraph (2)(A) [initial risk evaluation] or designated under paragraph (1)(B)(i) [high-priority substance]; and
 - that a manufacturer of the chemical substance has requested ... be subjected to a risk evaluation.
 - [EPA] shall ensure that manufacturer-designated risk evaluation is not less than 25 percent (if sufficient requests are made) and not more than 50 percent of the EPA-designated risk evaluation
- In conducting a risk evaluation, [EPA] shall
 - Integrate and assess available information on hazards and exposures for the conditions of use the chemical substance, including information that is relevant to specific risks of injury to health or the environment and information on potentially exposed or susceptible subpopulations identified as relevant by [EPA]
 - Describe whether aggregate or sentinel exposures to a chemical substance under the conditions of use were considered, and the basis for that consideration
 - Not consider costs or other nonrisk factors
 - Take into account, where relevant, the likely duration, intensity, frequency, and number of exposures under the conditions of use of the chemical substance
 - Describe the weight of the scientific evidence for the identified hazard and exposure
- [EPA] shall complete a risk evaluation for a chemical substance as soon as practicable, but not later than 3 years after the date on which [EPA] initiates the risk evaluation ... and may extend the deadline for a risk evaluation for not more than 6 months. [EPA] shall provide no less than 30 days public notice and an opportunity for comment on a draft risk evaluation prior to publishing a final risk evaluation.
- If EPA determines that a chemical substance presents an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment, EPA shall propose and promulgate a rule according to defined deadlines and other requirements.

²²⁶ In identifying priorities for risk evaluation and conducting risk evaluations of metals and metal compounds, the Administrator shall use the Framework for Metals Risk Assessment of the Office of the Science Advisor, Risk Assessment Forum, and dated March 2007, or a successor document that addresses metals risk assessment and is peer reviewed by the Science Advisory Board. [B]

- [EPA] shall exempt replacement parts for complex durable goods²²⁷ and complex consumer goods²²⁸ that are designed prior to the date of publication ... of the rule ..., unless [EPA] finds that such replacement parts contribute significantly to the risk, identified in a risk evaluation ..., to the general population or to an identified potentially exposed or susceptible subpopulation.
- In selecting among prohibitions and other restrictions, [EPA] shall apply such prohibitions or other restrictions to an article or category of articles containing the chemical substance or mixture only to the extent necessary to address the identified risks from exposure to the chemical substance or mixture from the article or category of articles so that the substance or mixture does not present an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment identified in the risk evaluation ...
- [EPA] may, as part of a rule ..., or in a separate rule, grant an exemption from a requirement ... for a specific condition of use of a chemical substance or mixture, if [EPA] finds
 - The specific condition of use is a critical or essential use for which no technically and economically feasible safer alternative is available, taking into consideration hazard and exposure
 - Compliance with the requirement, as applied with respect to the specific condition of use, would significantly disrupt the national economy, national security, or critical infrastructure, or
 - The specific condition of use of the chemical substance or mixture, as compared to reasonably available alternatives, provides a substantial benefit to health, the environment, or public safety.
 - In proposing an exemption ..., [EPA] shall analyze the need for the exemption, and shall make public the analysis and a statement describing how the analysis was taken into account.
 - [EPA] shall establish, as part of a rule, a time limit on any exemption for a time to be determined by [EPA] as reasonable on a case-by-case, and, by rule, may extend, modify, or eliminate an exemption if [EPA] determines, on the basis of reasonably available information and after adequate public justification, the exemption warrants extension or modification or is no longer necessary.
 - As part of a rule ..., [EPA] shall include conditions, including reasonable recordkeeping, monitoring, and reporting requirements, to the extent that [EPA] determines the conditions are necessary to protect health and the environment while achieving the purposes of the exemption.
- [EPA] shall not be required to conduct risk evaluations on chemical substances that are persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic, and exposure to which under the conditions of use is likely to the general population or to a potentially exposed or susceptible subpopulation identified by [EPA], or the environment, on the basis of an exposure and use assessment conducted by [EPA].
 - In selecting among prohibitions and other restriction promulgated in a rule ..., [EPA] shall address the risks of injury to health or the environment that [EPA] determines are presented by the chemical substance and shall reduce exposure to the substance to the extent practicable.

TSCA Section 7 / 15 U.S. Code § 2606 – imminent hazards [B]

- [EPA] may commence a civil action in an appropriate district court of the United States—
 - for seizure of an imminently hazardous chemical substance or mixture²²⁹ or any article containing such a substance or mixture,

²²⁷ manufactured goods composed of 100 or more manufactured components, with an intended useful life of 5 or more years, where the product is typically not consumed, destroyed, or discarded after a single use. [B]

²²⁸ electronic or mechanical devices composed of multiple manufactured components, with an intended useful life of 3 or more years, where the product is typically not consumed, destroyed, or discarded after a single use, and the components of which would be impracticable to redesign or replace. [B]

²²⁹ a chemical substance or mixture which presents an imminent and unreasonable risk of serious or widespread injury to health or the environment, without consideration of costs or other nonrisk factors. Such a risk to health or the environment shall be considered imminent if it is shown that the manufacture, processing, distribution in commerce, use, or disposal of the chemical substance or mixture, or that any combination of such activities, is

- *for relief (as authorized by subsection (b)) against any person who manufactures, processes, distributes in commerce, or uses, or disposes of, an imminently hazardous chemical substance or mixture or any article containing such a substance or mixture, or*
- *for both such seizure and relief.*
- *A civil action may be commenced under this paragraph notwithstanding the existence of a determination under section 2604 or 2605 of this title, a rule under section 2603, 2604, or 2605 of this title or subchapter IV, an order under section 2603, 2604, or 2605 of this title or subchapter IV, or a consent agreement under section 2603 of this title, and notwithstanding the pendency of any administrative or judicial proceeding under any provision of this chapter.*

8. Data submission format

Form and attachments via EPA's electronic Chemical Data Exchange using e-PMN software [\[D\]](#)

9. Data confidentiality

TSCA Section 14(b) (15 U.S.C. 2613) – information not protected from disclosure [\[B\]](#)

- *Information that is protected from disclosure under this section, and which is mixed with information that is not protected from disclosure under this section, does not lose its protection from disclosure notwithstanding that it is mixed with information that is not protected from disclosure.*
- *Subsection (a) does not prohibit the disclosure of—*
 - *any health and safety study which is submitted under this chapter with respect to (i) any chemical substance or mixture which, on the date on which such study is to be disclosed has been offered for commercial distribution; or (ii) any chemical substance or mixture for which testing is required under section 2603 of this title or for which notification is required under section 2604 of this title; and*
 - *any information reported to, or otherwise obtained by, the Administrator from a health and safety study which relates to a chemical substance or mixture described in clause (i) or (ii) of subparagraph (A).*
 - *This paragraph does not authorize the disclosure of any information, including formulas (including molecular structures) of a chemical substance or mixture, that discloses processes used in the manufacturing or processing of a chemical substance or mixture or, in the case of a mixture, the portion of the mixture comprised by any of the chemical substances in the mixture.*
- *Subsection (a) does not prohibit the disclosure of—*
 - *any general information describing the manufacturing volumes, expressed as specific aggregated volumes or, if the Administrator determines that disclosure of specific aggregated volumes would reveal confidential information, expressed in ranges; or*
 - *a general description of a process used in the manufacture or processing and industrial, commercial, or consumer functions and uses of a chemical substance, mixture, or article containing a chemical substance or mixture, including information specific to an industry or industry sector that customarily would be shared with the general public or within an industry or industry sector.*

TSCA Section 14(c) (15 U.S.C. 2613) – requirements for confidentiality claims [\[B\]](#)

- *A person seeking to protect from disclosure any information that person submits under this chapter (including information described in paragraph (2)) shall assert to [EPA] a claim for protection from disclosure*

likely to result in such injury to health or the environment before a final rule under section 2605 of this title can protect against such risk. [\[B\]](#)

concurrent with submission of the information, in accordance with such rules regarding a claim for protection from disclosure as [EPA] has promulgated or may promulgate pursuant to this subchapter.

- *An assertion of a claim under subparagraph (A) shall include a statement that the person has—*
 - *taken reasonable measures to protect the confidentiality of the information;*
 - *determined that the information is not required to be disclosed or otherwise made available to the public under any other Federal law;*
 - *a reasonable basis to conclude that disclosure of the information is likely to cause substantial harm to the competitive position of the person; and*
 - *a reasonable basis to believe that the information is not readily discoverable through reverse engineering.*
- *In the case of a claim under subparagraph (A) for protection from disclosure of a specific chemical identity, the claim shall include a structurally descriptive generic name for the chemical substance that [EPA] may disclose to the public, subject to the condition that such generic name shall—*
 - *be consistent with guidance developed by [EPA] under paragraph (4)(A); and*
 - *describe the chemical structure of the chemical substance as specifically as practicable while protecting those features of the chemical structure— (I) that are claimed as confidential; and (II) the disclosure of which would be likely to cause substantial harm to the competitive position of the person.*
- *Subject to subsection (f), the following information shall not be subject to substantiation requirements under paragraph (3):*
 - *Specific information describing the processes used in manufacture or processing of a chemical substance, mixture, or article.*
 - *Marketing and sales information.*
 - *Information identifying a supplier or customer.*
 - *In the case of a mixture, details of the full composition of the mixture and the respective percentages of constituents.*
 - *Specific information regarding the use, function, or application of a chemical substance or mixture in a process, mixture, or article.*
 - *Specific production or import volumes of the manufacturer or processor.*
 - *Prior to the date on which a chemical substance is first offered for commercial distribution, the specific chemical identity of the chemical substance, including the chemical name, molecular formula, Chemical Abstracts Service number, and other information that would identify the specific chemical substance, if the specific chemical identity was claimed as confidential at the time it was submitted in a notice under section 2604 of this title.*
- *Information described in subsection (a)—*
 - *shall be disclosed to an officer or employee of the United States—in connection with the official duties of that person under any Federal law for the protection of health or the environment; or for a specific Federal law enforcement purpose;*
 - *shall be disclosed to a contractor of the United States and employees of that contractor—if, in the opinion of the Administrator, the disclosure is necessary for the satisfactory performance by the contractor of a contract with the United States for the performance of work in connection with this chapter; and subject to such conditions as the Administrator may specify;*
 - *shall be disclosed if [EPA] determines that disclosure is necessary to protect health or the environment against an unreasonable risk of injury to health or the environment, without consideration of costs or other nonrisk factors, including an unreasonable risk to a potentially exposed or susceptible subpopulation identified as relevant by the Administrator under the conditions of use;*

- shall be disclosed to a State, political subdivision of a State, or tribal government, on written request, for the purpose of administration or enforcement of a law, if such entity has 1 or more applicable agreements with the Administrator that are consistent with the guidance developed under subsection (c)(4)(B) and ensure that the entity will take appropriate measures, and has adequate authority, to maintain the confidentiality of the information in accordance with procedures comparable to the procedures used by the Administrator to safeguard the information;
- shall be disclosed to a health or environmental professional employed by a Federal or State agency or tribal government or a treating physician or nurse in a nonemergency situation if such person provides a written statement of need and agrees to sign a written confidentiality agreement with the Administrator, subject to the conditions that—
 - the statement of need and confidentiality agreement are consistent with the guidance developed under subsection (c)(4)(B);
 - the statement of need shall be a statement that the person has a reasonable basis to suspect that—(i) the information is necessary for, or will assist in—(I) the diagnosis or treatment of 1 or more individuals; or (II) responding to an environmental release or exposure; and (ii) 1 or more individuals being diagnosed or treated have been exposed to the chemical substance or mixture concerned, or an environmental release of or exposure to the chemical substance or mixture concerned has occurred; and
 - the person will not use the information for any purpose other than the health or environmental needs asserted in the statement of need, except as otherwise may be authorized by the terms of the agreement or by the person who has a claim under this section with respect to the information;
- shall be disclosed in the event of an emergency to a treating or responding physician, nurse, agent of a poison control center, public health or environmental official of a State, political subdivision of a State, or tribal government, or first responder (including any individual duly authorized by a Federal agency, State, political subdivision of a State, or tribal government who is trained in urgent medical care or other emergency procedures, including a police officer, firefighter, or emergency medical technician) if such person requests the information, subject to the conditions that such person shall—
 - have a reasonable basis to suspect that—(i) a medical, public health, or environmental emergency exists; (ii) the information is necessary for, or will assist in, emergency or first-aid diagnosis or treatment; or (iii) 1 or more individuals being diagnosed or treated have likely been exposed to the chemical substance or mixture concerned, or a serious environmental release of or exposure to the chemical substance or mixture concerned has occurred; and
 - if requested by a person who has a claim with respect to the information under this section—provide a written statement of need and agree to sign a confidentiality agreement, as described in paragraph (5); and submit to the Administrator such statement of need and confidentiality agreement as soon as practicable, but not necessarily before the information is disclosed;
- may be disclosed if the Administrator determines that disclosure is relevant in a proceeding under this chapter, subject to the condition that the disclosure is made in such a manner as to preserve confidentiality to the extent practicable without impairing the proceeding;
- shall be disclosed if the information is required to be made public under any other provision of Federal law; and
- shall be disclosed as required pursuant to discovery, subpoena, other court order, or any other judicial process otherwise allowed under applicable Federal or State law.

- *in the case of information described in subsection (c)(2) [information generally not subject to substantiation requirements], until such time as—(i) the person that asserted the claim notifies the Administrator that the person is withdrawing the claim, in which case the information shall not be protected from disclosure under this section; or (ii) the Administrator becomes aware that the information does not qualify for protection from disclosure under this section, in which case the Administrator shall take any actions required under subsections (f) and (g); and*
- *in the case of information other than information described in subsection (c)(2)—(i) for a period of 10 years from the date on which the person asserts the claim with respect to the information submitted to the Administrator; or (ii) if applicable before the expiration of such 10-year period, until such time as—(I) the person that asserted the claim notifies the Administrator that the person is withdrawing the claim, in which case the information shall not be protected from disclosure under this section; or (II) the Administrator becomes aware that the information does not qualify for protection from disclosure under this section, in which case the Administrator shall take any actions required under subsections (f) and (g).*
 - *In the case of information other than information described in subsection (c)(2), not later than the date that is 60 days before the expiration of the period described in paragraph (1)(B)(i), [EPA] shall provide to the person that asserted the claim a notice of the impending expiration of the period.*
 - *Not later than the date that is 30 days before the expiration of the period described in paragraph (1)(B)(i), a person reasserting the relevant claim shall submit to [EPA] a request for extension substantiating, in accordance with subsection (c)(3), the need to extend the period.*

Premanufacture notification [C]

A person may assert a claim of confidentiality for any information which he or she submits to EPA under this part.

- *Any claim of confidentiality must accompany the information when it is submitted to EPA.*
- *EPA will disclose information that is subject to a claim of confidentiality asserted under this section only to the extent permitted by the Act, this subpart, and part 2 of this title²³⁰.*
- *Chemical identity*
 - *Claims applicable to the period prior to commencement of manufacture or import*
 - *A submitter may assert this claim only if the submitter believes that public disclosure prior to commencement of manufacture or import of the fact that anyone intends to manufacture or import the specific chemical substance for commercial purposes would reveal confidential business information.*
 - *If the notice includes a health and safety study concerning the new chemical substance and if the claim for confidentiality with respect to the chemical identity is denied in accordance with § 720.90(c), EPA will deny a claim asserted under this paragraph.*
 - *Any person who intends to assert a claim of confidentiality for the chemical identity of a new chemical substance may seek a determination by EPA of an appropriate generic name for the substance before submitting a notice.*
 - *Any person who asserts a claim of confidentiality for chemical identity ... must provide one of the following items at the time the notice is submitted: the generic name which was accepted by EPA in the prenotice consultation; one generic name that is only as generic as necessary to protect the confidential chemical identity of the particular chemical substance. The name should reveal the specific chemical identity to the maximum extent possible. The generic name will be subject to EPA review and approval at the time a notice of commencement is submitted.*

²³⁰ <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-A/part-2>

- *If a submitter claims chemical identity to be confidential under this paragraph, and if the submitter complies with paragraph (a)(2) of this section, EPA will issue for publication in the Federal Register notice described in § 720.70 the generic name proposed by the submitter or one agreed upon by EPA and the submitter.*
 - *Claims applicable to the period after commencement of manufacture or import.*
 - *To maintain the confidential status of the chemical identity when the substance is added to the Inventory, a submitter must reassert the confidentiality claim and substantiate the claim in the notice of commencement of manufacture required under § 720.102. A submitter may not claim the chemical identity confidential for the period after commencement of manufacture or import unless the submitter claimed the chemical identity confidential for the period prior to commencement of manufacture or import.*
 - *A person who believes that public disclosure of the fact that anyone manufactures or imports the new chemical substance for commercial purposes would reveal confidential business information may assert a claim of confidentiality under this paragraph.*
 - *If the notice includes a health and safety study concerning the new chemical substance, and if the claim for confidentiality with respect to the chemical identity is denied in accordance with § 720.90(c), EPA will deny a claim asserted under this paragraph.*
 - *Any person who asserts a confidentiality claim for chemical identity must:*
 - *Comply with the submission of a generic name.*
 - *Agree that EPA may disclose to a person with a bona fide intent to manufacture or import the chemical substance the fact that the particular chemical substance is included on the confidential Inventory for purposes of notification under section 5(a)(1)(A) of the Act.*
 - *Have available for the particular chemical substance, and agree to furnish to EPA upon request: (A) An elemental analysis. (B) Either an X-ray diffraction pattern (for inorganic substances), a mass spectrum (for most other substances), or an infrared spectrum of the particular chemical substance, or if such data do not resolve uncertainties with respect to the identity of the chemical substance, additional or alternative spectra or other data to identify the chemical substance.*
 - *Provide a detailed written substantiation of the claim²³¹*

²³¹ (A) *What harmful effects to your competitive position, if any, do you think would result if EPA publishes on the Inventory the identity of the chemical substance? How could a competitor use such information given the fact that the identity of the substance otherwise would appear on the Inventory of chemical substances with no link between the substance and your company or industry? How substantial would the harmful effects of disclosure be? What is the casual relationship between the disclosure and the harmful effects?*

(B) *For what period of time should confidential treatment be given? Until a specific date, the occurrence of a specific event, or permanently? Why?*

(C) *Has the chemical substance been patented? If so, have you granted licenses to others with respect to the patent as it applies to the chemical substance? If the chemical substance has been patented and therefore disclosed through the patent, why should it be treated as confidential for purposes of the Inventory?*

(D) *Has the identity of the chemical substance been kept confidential to the extent that your competitors do not know it is being manufactured or imported for a commercial purpose by anyone?*

(E) *Is the fact that someone is manufacturing or importing this chemical substance for commercial purposes available to the public, e.g., in technical journals or other publications; in libraries; or in State, local, or Federal agency public files?*

(F) *What measures have you taken to prevent undesired disclosure of the fact that you are manufacturing or importing this substance for a commercial purpose?*

- *If the submitter does not meet the requirements of this paragraph, EPA will deny the claim of confidentiality.*
- *EPA will publish a generic name on the public Inventory if: (A) The submitter asserts a claim of confidentiality in accordance with this paragraph. (B) No claim for confidentiality of the specific chemical identity as part of a health and safety study has been denied in accordance with part 2 of this title or § 720.90.*
- *Publication of a generic name on the public Inventory does not create a category for purposes of the Inventory. Any person who has a bona fide intent to manufacture or import a chemical substance which is described by a generic name on the public Inventory may submit an inquiry to EPA under § 720.25(b) to determine whether the particular chemical substance is included on the confidential Inventory.*
- *Upon receipt of a request described in § 720.25(b), EPA may require the submitter which originally asserted confidentiality for a chemical substance to submit to EPA the information listed [above].*
- *Failure to submit any of the information required under paragraph (b)(3)(iii) of this section within ten days of a request by EPA under this paragraph is a waiver of the original submitter's confidentiality claim. In this event, EPA may place the specific chemical identity on the public Inventory without further notice to the original submitter.*
- *Categories or proposed categories of uses of a new chemical substance*
 - *A submitter that asserts such a claim must: (1) Report the categories or proposed categories of use of the chemical substance. (2) Provide, in nonconfidential form, a description of the uses that is only as generic as necessary to protect the confidential business information. The generic use description will be included in the Federal Register notice described in § 720.70. ...*
- *Data from health and safety studies*
 - *EPA will deny any claim of confidentiality with respect to information included in a health and safety study, unless the information would disclose confidential business information concerning: (1) Processes used in the manufacture or processing of a chemical substance or mixture. (2) In the case of a mixture, the portion of the mixture comprised by any of the chemical substances in the mixture. (3) Information which is not in any way related to the effects of a substance on human health or the environment, such as the name of the submitting company, cost or other financial data, product development or marketing plans, and advertising plans, for which the person submits a claim of confidentiality in accordance with § 720.80 [for information other than specific chemical identity] / the specific chemical identity is not necessary to interpret a health and safety data [for information on specific chemical identity]*

(G) To what extent has the fact that you are manufacturing or importing this chemical substance for a commercial purpose been disclosed to others? What precautions have you taken in regard to these disclosures? Has this information been disclosed to the public or to competitors?

(H) In what form does this particular chemical substance leave the site of manufacture, e.g., as part of a product; in an effluent or emission stream? If so, what measures have you taken to guard against discovery of its identity?

(I) If the chemical substance leaves the site of manufacture in a product that is available to either the public or your competitors, can they identify the substance by analyzing the product?

(J) For what purpose do you manufacture or import the substance?

(K) Has EPA, another Federal agency, or any Federal court made any pertinent confidentiality determinations regarding this chemical substance? If so, copies of such determinations must be included in the substantiation.

(L) If the notice includes a health and safety study concerning the new chemical substance, the submitter must also answer the questions in § 720.90(b)(2). [C]

- *When EPA discloses a health and safety study containing a specific chemical identity, which the submitter has claimed confidential, and if the Agency has not denied the claim ..., EPA will identify the chemical substance by the generic name ...*

§ 720.50: low production-volume/exposure exemptions [D]

- *If the manufacturer submits information to EPA under this section which the manufacturer claims to be confidential business information, the manufacturer must clearly identify the information at the time of submission to EPA by bracketing, circling, or underlining it and stamping it with “CONFIDENTIAL” or some other appropriate designation. Any information so identified will be treated in accordance with the procedures in part 2 of this chapter. Any information not claimed confidential at the time of submission may be made available to the public without further notice.*
 - *Any person who asserts a claim of confidentiality for chemical identity ... must provide a generic chemical name that is only as generic as necessary to protect the confidential chemical identity of the particular chemical substance. The name should reveal the specific chemical identity to the maximum extent possible.*
 - *The generic name provided by the manufacturer will be subject to EPA review and approval in accordance with the procedures specified in § 720.85(b)(6) of this chapter. The generic name provided by the submitter or an alternative selected by EPA under these procedures will be placed on a public list of substances exempt under this section.*
 - *If any information is claimed confidential, the manufacturer must submit a second copy of the notice with all information claimed as confidential deleted. EPA will place the second copy in the public file.*

§723.175: Chemical substances used in or for the manufacture or processing of instant photographic and peel-apart film articles [D]

- *If the manufacturer submits information ... which it claims to be confidential business information, the manufacturer must clearly identify the information at the time of submission to the Agency by bracketing, circling, or underlining it and stamping it with “CONFIDENTIAL” or some other appropriate designation. Any information so identified will be treated in accordance with the procedures in part 2 of this chapter²³². Any information not claimed confidential at the time of submission will be made available to the public without further notice to the submitter.*

§723.250: Polymers [D]

- *If a manufacturer submits information to EPA under this section which the manufacturer claims to be confidential business information, the manufacturer must clearly identify the information at the time of submission to EPA by bracketing, circling, or underlining it and stamping it with “CONFIDENTIAL” or some other appropriate designation. Any information so identified will be treated in accordance with the procedures in 40 CFR part 2. Any information not claimed confidential at the time of submission may be made available to the public without further notice.*

Chemical data reporting [H]

- **Generally.** *Any person submitting information under this part may assert a confidentiality claim for that information at the time it is submitted, except for information described in paragraph (a)(2). Any such confidentiality claims must be asserted at the time the information is submitted. These claims will apply only to the information submitted with the claim. Instructions for asserting confidentiality claims are provided in*

²³² <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-A/part-2>

the document identified in § 711.35. Information claimed as confidential in accordance with this section will be treated and disclosed in accordance with the procedures in 40 CFR part 2 and section 14 of TSCA.

- **Exceptions:** Confidentiality claims cannot be asserted: (i) For chemical identities listed on the public portion of the TSCA Inventory; (ii) For processing and use data elements required by § 711.15(b)(4)(i)(A), (B), and (C) and § 711.15(b)(4)(ii)(A), (B), (C), and (D); or (iii) When a response is left blank or designated as “not known or reasonably ascertainable.”
- **Substantiations:** All confidentiality claims must be substantiated at time of submission, in accordance with the requirements in paragraphs (b), (c), and (d)(1) of this section,²³³ and must be signed and dated by an authorized official. Confidentiality claims for the following data elements are exempt from this substantiation requirement: (i) Production volume information required pursuant to § 711.15(b)(3)(iii). (ii) Joint submission information from the primary submitter, consisting of trade name and supplier identification required pursuant to § 711.15(b)(3)(i)(A) and (B). (iii) Joint submission information from the secondary submitter, consisting of the percentage of formulation required pursuant to § 711.15(b)(3)(i)(A) and (B). (iv) Information that is supplied in a petition submitted under § 711.6(b)(2)(iii) or § 711.10(d)(1)(ii) and that is described in section 14(c)(2) of TSCA.
 - If any of the information contained in the answers to the questions listed in paragraphs (b) and (c) of this section is asserted to contain information that itself is considered to be confidential, you must clearly identify the information that is claimed confidential.
- **Processing and use information.** A submitter may assert a claim of confidentiality for each data element required by § 711.15(b)(4)(i)(D), (E) and (F) and § 711.15(b)(4)(ii)(E), (F), and (G) to protect the link between that information and the reported chemical substance. Such claim may be asserted only when the linkage of that information to a reportable chemical substance is confidential and not publicly available.

Reporting and Recordkeeping - §704.7 [F]

- Any person submitting a notice under this rule may assert a business confidentiality claim covering all or any part of the notice. Any information covered by a claim will be disclosed by EPA only to the extent and by means of the procedures set forth in part 2 of this title.²³⁴
- In submitting a claim of confidentiality, a person attests to the truth of the following four statements concerning all information which is claimed confidential:
 - My company has taken measures to protect the confidentiality of the information, and it intends to continue to take such measures.
 - The information is not, and has not been, reasonably obtainable without our consent by other persons (other than government bodies) by use of legitimate means (other than discovery based on a showing of special need in a judicial or quasi-judicial proceeding).
 - The information is not publicly available elsewhere.
 - Disclosure of the information would cause substantial harm to our competitive position.

Commercial activity notification [G]

- If an importer submitting a notice cannot provide the information specified in § 710.29(d)(4) because it is unknown to the importer and claimed as confidential by the supplier of the chemical substance or mixture, the importer must ask the supplier to provide the specific chemical identity information directly to EPA in a joint submission Contact information for the supplier, a trade name or other name for the chemical

²³³ <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-711>

²³⁴ <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/part-2>

substance or mixture, and a copy of the request to the supplier must be included with the importer's submission.

- If a manufacturer or processor submitting a notice cannot provide the information specified in § 710.29(d)(4) because the reportable chemical substance is manufactured or processed using a reactant having a specific chemical identity that is unknown to the manufacturer or processor and claimed as confidential by its supplier, the manufacturer or processor must ask the supplier of the confidential reactant to provide the specific chemical identity of the confidential reactant directly to EPA in a joint submission ... Contact information for the supplier, a trade name or other name for the chemical substance, and a copy of the request to the supplier must be included with the manufacturer's or processor's submission with respect to the chemical substance.
- **Chemical identity.** A person submitting information under this part may request to maintain an existing claim of confidentiality for the specific chemical identity of a reportable chemical substance, but may do so only if the identity of the chemical substance is listed on the confidential portion of the Inventory as of the time the notice is submitted for that chemical substance under this part. A request to maintain an existing claim of confidentiality must be made at the time the information is submitted. If no person submitting the information specified in § 710.29(d)(4) for a particular chemical substance requests that the claim be maintained, EPA will treat the specific chemical identity of that chemical substance as not subject to a confidentiality claim and will move the chemical substance to the public portion of the Inventory. Except as set forth in this subsection, information claimed as confidential in accordance with this section will be treated and disclosed in accordance with the procedures in 40 CFR part 2, subpart B.
 - **Substantiation** for confidentiality claims for specific chemical identity.
 - Is the confidential chemical substance publicly known to have ever been offered for commercial distribution in the United States? If you answered yes, explain why the information should be treated as confidential.
 - Does this particular chemical substance leave the site of manufacture (including import) or processing in any form, e.g., as a product, effluent, or emission? If yes, please explain what measures have been taken, if any, to guard against the discovery of its identity.
 - If the chemical substance leaves the site in a form that is available to the public or your competitors, can the chemical identity be readily discovered by analysis of the substance (e.g., product, effluent, or emission), in light of existing technologies and any costs, difficulties, or limitations associated with such technologies? Please explain why or why not.
- **Information other than specific chemical identity.** A person submitting information under this part may assert a claim of confidentiality for information other than specific chemical identity. Any such confidentiality claim must be made at the time the information is submitted. Except as set forth in this section, information claimed as confidential in accordance with this subsection will be treated and disclosed in accordance with 40 CFR part 2, subpart B. A person asserting a claim of confidentiality under this subsection must submit with the notice answers to the questions in paragraph (c)(1) of this section, signed and dated by an authorized official. If no claim is asserted at the time the information is submitted, or if the answers to the questions in paragraph (c)(1) of this section are not provided, EPA will consider the information as not subject to a confidentiality claim and may make the information public without further notice.
 - Pre-defined **substantiation** questions²³⁵
- **Confidentiality of substantiation.** If any of the information contained in the answers to the questions listed in paragraph (c)(1) or (c)(2) of this section is claimed as confidential business information, the submitter

²³⁵ <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-R/part-710>

must clearly indicate such by marking the substantiation as confidential business information as provided in a Notice of Activity Form A or Form B.

- **Review criteria and procedures.** Except as set forth in this subpart, confidentiality claims for specific chemical identities asserted in Notices of Activity Form A will be reviewed and approved or denied in accordance with the criteria and procedures in TSCA section 14 and 40 CFR part 2, subpart B.
- **Duration of protection from disclosure.** Except as provided in 40 CFR part 2, subpart B, and section 14 of TSCA, a specific chemical identity that is the subject of an approved confidentiality claim under this subpart will be protected from disclosure for a period of 10 years from the date on which the confidentiality claim was first asserted by any submitter after June 22, 2016, unless, prior to the expiration of the period, the claimant notifies EPA that the person is withdrawing the confidentiality claim, in which case EPA will not protect the information from disclosure; or EPA otherwise becomes aware that the information does not qualify for protection from disclosure, in which case EPA will take the actions described in TSCA section 14(g)(2) to notify the claimant of EPA's intent to disclose the information.
- **Updating the TSCA Inventory.** EPA will periodically update the TSCA Inventory based on the results of the reviews of the confidentiality claims asserted in Notices of Activity Form A.
- **Posting of annual goals and numbers of reviews completed.** At the beginning of each calendar year until all reviews are completed, EPA will publish an annual goal for reviews and the number of reviews completed in the prior year on the Agency website. Determination of annual review goals will take into consideration the number of claims needing review, available resources, and a target completion date for all reviews under this subpart not later than February 19, 2024.
- **Extension.** If EPA determines that the target completion date in paragraph (d) of this section cannot be met based on the number of claims needing review and the available resources, then EPA will publish a document in the Federal Register announcing the extension of the deadline to complete its review of all confidentiality claims under this subpart for not more than two additional years, together with an explanation of the reasons for the extension.

10. Data that are published publicly

TSCA Inventory

- Non-confidential chemical substance listings on the TSCA Inventory, as identified by Chemical Abstract Service (CAS) Registry Number and Chemical Abstracts (CA) Index Name
- Non-confidential data for the confidential chemical substance listings, as identified by EPA accession number and generic chemical name

Premanufacture notice [C]

- In accordance with section 5(d)(2) of the Act, after EPA receives a notice, EPA will file with the Office of the Federal Register a notice
 - In the public interest, the specific chemical identity listed in the notice will be published ... unless the submitter has claimed chemical identity confidential. If the submitter claims confidentiality, a generic name will be published ...
 - The categories of use of the new chemical substance will be published as reported in the notice unless this information is claimed confidential. If confidentiality is claimed, the generic information ... will be published.
 - A list of data submitted in accordance with § 720.50(a) will be published. In addition, for test data submitted in accordance with § 720.40(g), a summary of the data will be published.
 - The submitter's identity will be published, unless the submitter has claimed it confidential.

§ 720.38: Exemptions for test marketing [C]

- *In accordance with section 5(h)(6) of the Act, after EPA receives an application for exemption under this section, the Agency will file with the Office of the Federal Register a notice containing a summary of the information provided in the application, to the extent it has not been claimed confidential.*

TSCA Section 4 / 15 U.S. Code § 2603 – Testing of chemical substances and mixtures [B]

- *Upon the receipt of any information pursuant to a rule, order, or consent agreement ..., [EPA] shall publish a notice of the receipt of such information in the Federal Register within 15 days of its receipt. Subject to section 2613 ..., each such notice shall (1) identify the chemical substance or mixture for which information has been received; (2) list the uses or intended uses of such substance or mixture and the information required by the applicable protocols and methodologies for the development of information; and (3) describe the nature of the information developed. Except as otherwise provided in section 2613 [confidential information] ..., such information shall be made available by [EPA] for examination by any person.*

11. Information exchange and sharing

"EPA and Environment and Climate Change Canada/Health Canada (ECCC/HC) have been working together under the Regulatory Cooperation Council (RCC) to conduct a comparison of the new chemicals review programs in both nations, specifically EPA's SNUR and Canada's Significant New Activity (SNAc) programs that require notice to the governments before chemical substances and mixtures are used in new ways that might create environmental or health concerns.

EPA must develop information systems for the collection, dissemination, and use of information submitted to the agency under TSCA and for federal, state, and local entities to exchange relevant research and development information."

S1.25 Vietnam National Chemical Inventory (NCI)

Last update: 19 July 2021

1. Sources and links

- A. Law on Chemicals (No. 06/2007/QH12)
<https://www.ilo.org/dyn/natlex/docs/ELECTRONIC/80836/119230/F747782294/VBN80836%20Eng.pdf>
- B. Decree No. 113/2017/ND-CP dated October 09, 2017 of the Government on specifying and providing guidelines for implementation of certain articles of the Law on Chemicals: http://asemconnectvietnam.gov.vn/law.aspx?ZID1=10&ID1=2&MaVB_id=2618 (informal translation; note that in July 2021, the Vietnam Chemical Agency issued a notice to collect opinions on the amendment and supplement of articles of the Decree: http://www.cuchoachat.gov.vn/default.aspx?page=news&do=detail&category_id=43&id=4448)²³⁶
- C. Homepage: <http://chemicaldata.gov.vn/cms.xc> (in Vietnamese)
- D. Vietnam National Chemical Inventory. Presentation by Le Viet Thang, Deputy Head of Conventions and International Cooperation Division, Vietnam Chemicals Agency, Ministry of Industry and Trade, at the Global Forum on Environment: https://www.slideshare.net/OECD_ENV/global-forum-on-environment-dedicated-to-chemicals-management-le-viet-thang-deputy-head-of-conventions-and-international-cooperation-division-vietnam-chemicals-agency-ministry-of-industry-and-trade
- E. Project for Strengthening Chemicals Management in Vietnam. Final Report. 2019.
<https://openjicareport.jica.go.jp/pdf/12333951.pdf>
- F. *Vietnam: Latest Report on the Supplementation of NCI and the Draft of New Substance Act* published by Chemlinked. 2021. <https://chemical.chemlinked.com/expert-article/vietnam-latest-report-on-the-supplementation-of-nci-and-draft-of-new-substance-act>
- G. Circular No. 32/2017/TT-BCT dated December 28, 2017 of the Ministry and Trade specifying and providing guidelines for implementation of certain articles of the law on chemicals and the Government's Decree No. 113/2017/ND-CP dated October 09, 2017 specifying and providing

²³⁶ Decree No. 113/2017/ND-CP has designated 5 lists of chemicals subject to regulatory control and specified detailed conditions for manufacture or trade: the list of chemicals subject to conditional production or import (annex I, 819 chemicals, Certification for manufacturing and trading), the list of chemicals restricted from production or trade (annex II, 217 chemicals, license for production and trading), the list of banned chemicals (annex III, 18 chemicals, permission for production, import and use by the LoC), the list of hazardous chemicals for which chemical incident prevention and response plans are required (annex IV, 271 chemicals, approval of plan on incidents by evaluation council), and the list of chemicals subject to compulsory declarations (annex V, 1156 chemicals).

Conditional industrial chemicals include: 1. Chemicals on the list of conditional industrial chemicals stated in Appendix I attached hereto; 2. Mixtures of chemicals specified in Appendix I and Appendix II not subject to restricted industrial chemicals mentioned in Article 14 herein that are classified according to Article 23 herein subject to at least one of the following groups: a) category 1/category 2/category 3 of type A/B/C/D hazardous material; b) category 2 and category 3 acute toxicity (through variable exposures); c) category 1/category 2/category 2A serious eye damage/eye irritation; d) category 1 and category 2 skin corrosion/irritation; dd) category 2 carcinogenicity, germ cell mutagenicity or reproductive toxicity; e) category 1 environment hazard.

Restricted industrial chemicals include: 1. Chemicals on the list of restricted industrial chemicals stated in Appendix II attached hereto; 2. Mixtures of chemicals specified in Appendix II attached hereto classified according to Article 23 herein and subject to at least one of the following groups: a) category 1 acute toxicity (through variable exposures), b) category 1A and category 1B carcinogenicity, c) category 1A and category 1B reproductive toxicity, d) category 1A and category 1B germ cell mutagenicity [B, E]

guidelines for implementation of certain articles of the law on chemicals:

<https://handbook.ehs.vn/circular-32-2017-tt-bct> (informal translation)

2. Purpose(s) of the inventory

- Art. 30 [B]: *for the management of chemical safety and provide information for responding systems and hazardous chemicals in case of an emergency*
- Distinction between existing vs. new chemicals²³⁷ [*a chemical not yet listed in the national chemical inventory or foreign chemical inventories recognized by Vietnamese competent state agencies, i.e. Japan's Inventory of Existing and New Chemical Substances (ENCS), the US TSCA inventory, the European Inventory of Existing Commercial Chemical Substances (EINECS)*]. [A]
 - The inventory was initiated in December 2015 [A]. As of 24th February 2021, *the draft inventory contains 48857 chemical substances, while only 9618 substances have been approved, 9578 substances are now under examination, and the rest 29661 substances are lack of evidence.* [F]
 - For registration, industry is to provide: name of the substance, CASRN, safety data sheet, and documents proving that chemicals have been used/marketed in Vietnam (such as purchase contracts or invoices)
 - *The draft of the new substance act has completed, it is expected to be published in the second quarter of 2021 and finally enter into effect by this year.* [F]

3. Scope of the inventory

3.1 Obligations

Registration of new chemicals

- Art. 44 [A]: *New chemicals may be used or marketed only after they are registered with competent state agencies.*

Declaration of chemicals

- Art. 43 [A]: *Chemical-importing organizations and individuals shall declare chemicals²³⁸ to the Ministry of Industry and Trade; Chemical-producing organizations and individuals shall declare chemicals to professional agencies managing chemical-related activities under provincial-level Peoples Committees*
 - *In the 2017 Decree, there is a list of 1156 chemicals to be declared + mixtures containing substances on this list.* [B]
 - *producers shall declare chemicals produced every year through the annual reports*
 - *importers (declarants) shall declare imported chemicals before customs clearance through the national single-window website.*

3.2 Exemptions

- Art. 3 [A]: *Activities related to radioactive substances and radioactive wastes comply with the laws on radiation safety and atomic energy*
- Declaration of chemicals [B]
 - *chemicals produced or imported for the purposes of national security and response to natural disasters and epidemics*
 - *chemicals that are precursor chemicals of narcotics, precursor chemicals of explosives, industrial explosives and chemicals on the chemical table licensed to produce or import.*

²³⁷ *Chemical means an element, a compound or a mixture which is exploited or created by humans from nature or artificial raw materials.* [A]

²³⁸ *Classified according to Article 23 stated herein as hazardous chemicals [GHS, rev. 2 (2007)]* [B]

- *The amount of chemicals is under 10 kg/shipment. Exemption mentioned in this point shall not apply to restricted industrial chemicals.*
- *chemicals that are raw materials for medicine production issues with certificates of registration for sale of medicines in Vietnam, raw materials for the medicine production that are pharmaceutical substances for production under medicine registration applications which have been granted certificates of registration for sale of medicines in Vietnam.*
- *Chemicals that are raw materials for pesticide production with certificates of pesticide registration in Vietnam.*

4. Initial data requirements

Declaration of chemicals

- *A chemical declaration contains: a) name and address of the chemical-producing or -importing organization or individual; b) name, quantity and origin of the chemical [A]*
 - *Information about the declaration of the imported chemicals [B]*
 - *Information ... about the declarant and imported chemicals*
 - *sale and purchase invoices of chemicals*
 - *safety data sheets in Vietnamese*
 - *for non-commercial goods without chemical purchase or sale invoices, the declarant may use port return papers instead of commercial invoices.*

Registration of new chemicals other than for scientific research or protection of security and social order and safety

- *A dossier of registration of a new chemical ... comprises [A]*
 - *An application for registration of a new chemical*
 - *The name ... under the guidance of [IUPAC] and the chemical formula*
 - *Information on physical and chemical properties and hazardous properties of the chemical, certified by a new chemical-assessing organization²³⁹ prescribed in Article 45 of this law*

Registration of new chemicals for scientific research or protection of security and social order and safety

- *A dossier registration ... comprises [A]*
 - *An application for registration*
 - *the chemical name under the guidance of IUPAC and the chemical formula*
 - *information on the use purpose and duration of the chemical*

5. Information updates by companies

Registration of New chemicals

- *Art. 46: During five years from the date new chemicals are registered, annually, before January 31 of the subsequent year, organizations and individuals engaged in activities related to new chemicals shall send reports to line ministries and the Ministry of Industry and Trade. [A]*
- *Art. 48: Upon detection of signs of new hazardous properties of chemicals, organizations and individuals engaged in chemical-related activities shall promptly report these properties to the Ministry of Industry and Trade and notify these properties to organizations or individuals that have produced or imported these chemicals. [A]*

²³⁹ *Organizations capable of assessing new chemicals and designated by competent state agencies or foreign standard conformity testing organizations accredited by the [OECD] regarding chemical assessment. [A]*

- Art. 48: *Organizations and individuals producing or importing chemicals which show signs of new hazardous properties shall report to the Ministry of Industry and Trade for consideration and collection of additional scientific grounds on these new hazardous properties. [A]*

Labelling

- Art. 48: *after obtaining official conclusions of competent state agencies on new hazardous properties of chemicals, organizations and individuals that have produced or imported these chemicals shall modify and supplement chemical labels and chemical safety data sheets to suit new hazardous properties. [A]*

Reports on production, import and use of banned chemicals²⁴⁰

- Art. 52 [A]: *Annual, before January 31, organizations and individuals producing, importing or using chemicals on the list of banned chemicals shall send reports on the production, import or use of these chemicals to line ministries and the Ministry of Industry and Trade*
 - *name, use purposes and quantities of produced, imported or used chemicals;*
 - *quantities of warehoused, ex-warehoused and in-stock chemicals and the storage locations;*
 - *chemical safety measures already taken*
 - *other information, if requested.*

Preservation of information on hazardous chemicals

- Art. 53 [A]: *Organizations and individuals engaged in chemical-related activities shall formulate, regularly update and preserve information on hazardous chemicals in their chemical-related activities for at least three years from the date of ending activities involving these chemicals.*
 - *Information to be preserved covers scientific names and trade names of chemicals; quantities of chemicals produced, imported, used or discarded; use purposes and classification of hazard categories according to the [GHS]; and information relating to chemical incidents and chemical safety in the facilities. If a chemical facility has several branches, hazardous chemical data must cover all information relating to the facility and its branches.*

Reporting made by entities having chemical-related activities [B, G]

- *Before January 15 every year, entities having industrial chemical-related activities shall make reports on their chemical-related activities in the previous year according to the specimen No. 5a provided in Appendix No.5 attached hereto and send them to the Department of Industry and Trade of the province where such activities are carried out and to the Vietnam Chemicals Agency*
- *Entities having industrial chemical-related activities shall make reports on their chemical-related activities on an ad hoc basis and send them to the Department of Industry and Trade of the province where they are carrying out such activities when there is any chemical emergency arising or such activities are ceased or at the request of a competent authority*
- *A general report on annual chemical-related activities made by an entity shall specify*
 - *General information about the entity*
 - *Declaration of produced chemicals including the list of chemicals that must be declared for each factory*
 - *Production or trade in conditional chemicals, restricted chemicals, compulsorily declared chemicals and other chemicals*
 - *Provision of training courses in chemical safety*

²⁴⁰ Art. 18 [B]: *In case of special cases for the purposes of scientific research, national security and epidemic prevention and fighting, banned chemicals shall be produced and traded according to the provision of Article 19 of the Law on Chemicals and the Government's regulations.*

- *Plans and measures for prevention of and response to chemical emergencies and chemical safety and results thereof*

6. Data follow-up processes by regulators

- *Art. 49 [A]: Organizations and individuals engaged in chemical-related activities are obliged to supply sufficient accurate and timely information at the request of competent agencies*
 - *Upon occurrence of chemical incidents in chemical facilities*
 - *For the prevention of natural disasters which may cause chemical incidents in chemical facilities*
 - *For the investigation and survey in service of the elaboration of strategies, plannings and plans on regional or chemical industry development*
 - *For the examination and inspection of chemical-related activities*

7. Use of the data in risk assessment and management (including processes and by whom)

- *Art. 47 [A]: When requested, line ministries supply information on toxic chemicals and hazardous chemicals under their management for curing and treatment of humans, animals and plants affected by chemical incidents.*
- *Art. 48 [A]: The Ministry of Industry and Trade shall compile dossiers of chemicals which show signs of new hazardous properties in order to take measures to collect more scientific grounds and conduct additional testing to affirm new hazardous properties of chemicals.
After obtaining adequate proofs for determination of new hazardous properties of chemicals, the Ministry of Industry and Trade shall decide to apply appropriate measures to manage these chemicals.*
- *Art. 54 [A]: Agencies or organizations receiving reports on chemicals (new or banned) shall preserve them for at least 10 years.*

8. Data submission format

via National Chemical Database System website [C]

9. Data confidentiality

- *Art. 50 [A]: Agencies and persons that receive declaration and registration papers and reports on chemicals shall keep information confidential at the request of the declarants, registrants and reporters, except [supply at the request of competent state agencies]*
 - *Confidential information of declarants, registrants and reporters include: (1) name and quantities of chemicals to be produced, imported or traded; (2) information relating to technological know-how and trade secrets.*
 - *Art. 51: Agencies and persons receiving declaration and registration papers and reports on chemicals shall supply confidential information specified in Article 50 of this Law at the request of competent state agencies.*
 - *Agencies and persons receiving declaration and registration papers and reports on chemicals shall preserve confidential information in accordance with law.*
- *Art. 29 [B]: Important information for the protection of public health and the environment shall NOT be considered as confidential information, including*
 - *trade names of chemicals*
 - *names of chemical producers, importers or reporters of chemical-related activities*
 - *information stated in safety data sheets, except for confidential information stated above*
 - *information serving the prevention of and response to chemical emergencies; prevent and limit adverse effects of chemical toxicity; warnings on use, exposure to chemicals and precautions in the event of a chemical emergency*

- *analytical methods to determine the probability of exposure to humans and the environment; brief testing results of chemical toxicity*
- *the purity of mixtures and hazards of additives and impurities*

10. Data that are published publicly

In a searchable database, which includes the substance name (local and English) and other relevant information such as substance code; CASRN; and laws, regulations and chemical lists in which the substances are regulated, per Annex 1-5 of Decree 113/2017, as well as information regarding the GHS classification for each substance (if any).

11. International information exchange and sharing

N.A.

1 **S2. Supporting Details for Estimating Chemicals in Individual Inventories with Safety Data or Risk Assessments** (Last update: 3 May 2022)

2 **Table. Overview of chemicals in individual inventories. Inventory name in green = identities of chemicals with safety data/risk assessment fully available; in purple = identities of**
 3 **chemicals with safety data/risk assessment partially available (due to e.g., CBI, a lack of public data accessibility to the original file, or errors); in orange = identities of chemicals with**
 4 **safety data/risk assessment NOT available; in black = simplified registration at the moment; numbers that are used to make the figure in the main text are highlighted in bold.**

Inventory	Total number of substances	Number of substances that have been assessed / have safety data ⁹	Notes
AIIC/AICS ²⁴¹	As of 30.06.2020 ²⁴² 40769 (public) + 126 (confidential) As of 30.06.2021 ²⁴³ 39299 (public) + 94 (confidential) As of 10.02.2022, 39364 (public) + 96 (confidential)	As of 30.06.2020, 15,972 assessed under the Inventory Multi-Tiered Assessment and Prioritisation (IMAP) framework + 102 assessed under the priority existing chemical (PEC) program + new chemicals = ca. 47.6% of chemicals on the inventory have been assessed = ca. 19460 chemicals (ca. 3386 new) + 120 new and 813 existing assessed in 2020–2021 (note that the identities of assessed existing chemicals are not available in an easily accessible format, and thus not included in the compilation).	(1) Based on NICNAS (2018), 7.8% of the then 40571 AICS chemicals were new chemicals → existing chemicals = $40571 \times (1-7.8\%) = \text{ca. } \mathbf{37406}$ (2) those added after 16 July 1990 = new chemicals with safety assessment (3) chemicals for which an assessment certificate has been in force for 5 years are generally listed (applications can be made for early listing and industrial chemicals can be listed in certain other circumstances) → more substances introduced, but not added on the inventory (4) In the latest version, the sequence of CR numbers between 380 (Formaldehyde) and 37341 (CASRN 135800-40-7) roughly aligns with the listing order of existing chemicals (personal communication). → The number of new chemicals is 4355 , ca. 850 higher than the previous year's reported number (this could be the number of newly added chemicals since 30.06.2021, which is to be verified once the new DoH Annual Report for 2021–22 is out.

²⁴¹ Previous annual reports can be found at: <https://nla.gov.au/nla.obj-742488067>; official Chemical Gazettes: <http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-title1353>; the latest version of the inventory (from 10.02.2022) can be downloaded at: <https://www.industrialchemicals.gov.au/search-inventory>

²⁴² Here it refers to the number of chemicals in the previous AICS inventory, retrieved from the Department of Health Annual Report, 2019–20 (<https://www.health.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/2020/11/departement-of-health-annual-report-2019-20.pdf>). In 2019–20, 166 chemicals were added to the non-confidential section of the inventory and one chemical was deleted. In addition, NICNAS sought information, including CAS name and CASRN for industrial use, from businesses on a list of chemicals on the old Inventory believed to not have an industrial use. Following a review of the responses, 1,624 chemicals were found not to be industrial chemicals; that is they never had, and do not have, an industrial use in Australia. As the IC Act mandates the new Inventory contain only industrial chemicals, the 1,624 chemicals identified as not having an industrial use have not been listed on the new Inventory.

²⁴³ Here it refers to the number of chemicals in the new AIIC inventory, retrieved from the Department of Health Annual Report, 2020–21 (<https://www.health.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/2021/10/departement-of-health-annual-report-2020-21.pdf>): (1) 100 chemicals were added to the Inventory 5 years after the issue of an assessment certificate, and a further 20 added following an application for early listing; (2) 34 applications for protection of CBI were received, of which 20 were approved; (3) Inventory listings were varied for 38 chemicals following revocation of CBI approval at their 5 yearly review; (4) 627 reviews of registration level were undertaken, resulting in 594 registrants adjusting their registration level; 782 PIRs [for reported introductions] were submitted, with 100% of these reports subject to high throughput screening to select reports for further analysis. A total of 17% of submitted PIRs were further screened for potential miscategorisation, based on the information provided in the reports such as chemical identity and exposure/hazard information. Additional information to support categorisation was requested for 5% of submitted RIPS ... In addition, in 10% of submitted PIRs, introducers were contacted with specific guidance on their compliance obligations or advised of changes required; (5) Evaluations for human health and the environment were conducted in 2020–21 for 813 chemicals [via 18 evaluations].

DSL	28221 (as of 11.12.2020) 28392 (as of 6.12.2021), including 131 culture, enzymes and P RTP 28503 (as of 14.06.2022)	28392 (see Notes) An additional list of “existing substances” that have been assessed in detail as of 7 January 2021 was provided by Health Canada, containing 4734 chemicals + 5403 new chemicals (1757 non-polymer & non-CBI; 1194 non-polymer & CBI; 1035 polymer & non-CBI; 1385 polymer & CBI)	(1) those added after 1994 = new chemicals with safety assessments and approved by the competent authorities – 5403 chemicals (2) 22989 are grandfathered chemicals. Using information from Canadian industry, academic research and other countries, they were categorized according to P, B, inherent T, greatest potential for exposure (completed in September 2006); it is being used to focus attention on those chemicals of highest priority for assessment or further research, and those in need of controls to protect human health and the environment. ²⁴⁴ (3) There were chemicals taken out of DSL over time.
EU-Reg	23118 (as of 11.12.2020) 23445 (as of 13.10.2021)	7939 substances performed chemical safety assessment (after removing duplicated CASRNs, 6466 with CASRNs, 1473 without CASRNs)	(1) As of 11.12.2020: 7997 entries performed chemical safety assessment, 64 entries claimed CBI for chemical safety assessment, with duplications (2) As of 13.10.2021: 8104 entries performed chemical safety assessment 59 entries claimed CBI for chemical safety assessment, with duplications (3) Based on the registration from 08.2019, ECHA identified 1544 substances with high priority for data generation, 327 with high priority for risk management under consideration, 700 with currently no further actions proposed, 385 with risk management ongoing, and 18767 uncertain. (4) Based on the registration as of 12.2020, ECHA identified 1863 substances with high priority for data generation, 1409 substances with high priority for risk management under consideration, 892 with currently no further actions proposed, 630 with risk management ongoing, and 18478 not yet assigned ²⁴⁵

²⁴⁴ <https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/canadian-environmental-protection-act-registry/substances-list/domestic/categorization-existing.html>

²⁴⁵ <https://echa.europa.eu/de/universe-of-registered-substances>

IECSC	46817	<p>1205 new substances (941 with CASRNs, 90 without CASRNs, 174 CBIs)</p>	<p>(1) 2013: 37107 with CASRNs, 5235 without CASRNs, 3270 CBIs = 45612 existing sub.</p> <p>(2) those added after 15 October 2013 = new chemicals with safety assessment and approved by the competent authorities</p> <p>2016: 16 w/ CASRNs, 3 w/out CASRNs, 12 CBIs</p> <p>2018: 32 w/ CASRNs, 7 w/out CASRNs, 6 CBIs</p> <p>2019: 13 w/ CASRNs, 5 w/out CASRNs, 10 CBIs</p> <p>2020(1): 19 w/ CASRNs, 4 w/out CASRNs, 25 CBIs</p> <p>2020(2): 153 w/ CASRNs, 3 w/out CASRNs</p> <p>2020(3): 12 w/ CASRNs, 16 CBIs</p> <p>2020(4): 229 w/ CASRNs, 9 w/out CASRNs</p> <p>2021(1): 202 w/ CASRNs, 2 w/out CASRNs</p> <p>2021(2): 18 w/ CASRNs, 2 w/out CASRNs, 95 CBIs</p> <p>2021(3): 201 w/ CASRNs, 54 w/out CASRNs</p> <p>2021(4): 8 w/ CASRNs</p> <p>2021(5): 23 w/ CASRNs</p> <p>2021(6): 5 w/ CASRNs, 10 CBIs</p> <p>2021(7): 11 w/ CASRNs</p>
TCSI	96659	<p>106 existing ones with standard registration requirement²⁴⁶</p> <p>+ up to 3310 new substances (after removing duplicating CASRNs, small quantity registration – 432 with CASRNs, 2573 without CASRNs or CBIs; simplified registration – 57 with CASRNs, 142</p>	<p>(1) 72922 (public) + 20427 (confidential) = 93349 existing</p> <p>(2) 2512 entries of new, as of 01 December 2020</p> <p>(3) 3326 entries of new, as of 03 January 2022 (3032 small quantity registration + 205 simplified registration + 89 standard registrations)</p>

²⁴⁶ 既有化學物質標準登錄資料撰寫指引

<https://tcscachemreg.epa.gov.tw/Epareg/content/login/DownloadList.aspx?enc=0D613A16EE291362D69B33A3024B1FB701A5534B74980F4D>

		without CASRNs or CBIs; standard registration – 26 with CASRNs, 60 without CASRNs or CBIs)	
ICHCI	179	179 (161 with CASRNs, 18 without CASRNs)	(1) These are chemicals specified in the underlying framework. In addition, flammable substances and ammonium nitrate are subject to reporting under the framework.
CSCL	58314 (as of the version from 12 July, 2018) 59082 (as of the version from 9 January, 2022)	12565 (as of May 3, 2022: 3685 existing or unclear substances that are included in the various categories in the Notes – 3438 with unique CASRNs; 8945 new substances – 4211 with unique CASRNs)	<p>(1) 50137 existing substances + 1141 newly announced chemicals notified on and after April 1, 2011 + 7804 newly announced chemicals notified by March 31, 2011</p> <p>(2) 535 chemicals on the Class I Specified Chemical Substance that are persistent, highly bioaccumulative and pose a risk of long-term toxicity to humans or predator animals at a higher trophic level</p> <p>(3) 28 chemicals on the Class II Specified Chemical Substance that may pose a risk of long-term toxicity to humans or to flora and fauna in the human living environment, and that have been, or in the near future are reasonably likely to be, found in considerable amounts over a substantially extensive area of the environment</p> <p>(4) 135 chemicals on the Monitoring Chemical Substance List (substances that are persistent and highly bioaccumulative and whose long-term toxicity to humans or predator animals at higher trophic level is unclear)</p> <p>(5) 1501 chemicals on the Priority Assessment Chemical Substances List (substances whose long-term toxicity whose long-term toxicity to humans or to flora and fauna in the human living environment is unclear, and that have been found, or are expected to be found, in considerable amounts over a substantially extensive area of the environment)</p> <p>(6) 1288 chemicals on the Type II Monitoring Chemical Substances List (that are suspected to have a long-term toxicity to humans and that were published before April 1, 2011)</p> <p>(7) 453 chemicals on the Type III Monitoring Chemical Substances List (that may interfere with the survival and/or growth of flora and fauna, and that were published before April 1, 2011).</p> <p>(8) 3552 chemicals on the Chemical Substances exempted from notification of manufacturing/import amount List (substances that were publicized in the Official Gazette as a chemical substance for which it is not found necessary to conduct an assessment)</p> <p>(9) 8749 chemicals on the Biodegradation and Bioconcentration Results; 444 on the Toxicity Test Results (as part of the safety inspection of existing chemicals); 666 on the Eco-toxicity Test Results → cannot be downloaded and thus are not included in the analysis</p>

			(10) as of 2015, 11904 screened and 163 chemicals subject to detailed risk assessment ²⁴⁷
ISHA	48232 (as of the version from 12 July, 2018) 50582 (as of the version from 9 January, 2022)	30876 substances (147 Existing + 30729 New; from which, 14341 with CASRNs)	(1) 20519 Existing Chemical Substances (2) 30729 newly announced chemical substances registered after June 30, 1979, as of 9 January 2022. Note that there are two types of notification: standard notification (Ames test is required) and confirmation (≤ 100 kg/year, no test required) (3) 3502 chemicals requiring labelling and delivery of documents, etc. (substances that are deemed to have the possibility of inflicting serious damage on the health of workers at the time of their transfer or provision; 241 dangerous substances – explosive, combustible, oxidizing, inflammable substances, or flammable gases; 1603 chemicals on the Specified Chemical Substances List; with duplicates → Including 147 existing chemicals
KECI	44476, as of 08.05.2019 44517, as of 11.12.2020 46101 , as of 24.12.2021 (note that several entries have more than one CAS Nos.)	As of 24.12.2021, 7492 new substances (5557 with unique CASRNs and 1840 without CASRNs) + 1710 Existing substances assessed (1709 with unique CASRNs, 1 without CASRNs) + 1576 additional substances (1514 with unique CASRNs, 62 without CASRNs, see notes)	(1) those registered after Feb 2, 1991 = substances with hazard evaluation by the authority → 37106 circulated before Feb 2, 1991 and 7493 examined for hazard under the previous “Toxic Chemicals Control Act” (last revised August 12 2021) ²⁴⁸ (2) 2145 designated as hazardous chemical substances; 652 as substances subject to intensive control; 364 as CMR substances; 99 as substances requiring preparation for accidents (with duplicates in each category), as of 27.12.2021 ²⁴⁹ (3) Additional substances without KE_No: 1158 are on the list of OECD HPV and additional 416 substances have some sort of regulatory control measures
MyEHS	596 (according to the latest website as of 21 June 2022) ²⁵⁰	596 (company self-classified)	(1) 2'001 EHS entries officially notified to DOE (basic notification), 3'240 EHS officially notified to DOE, 1'228 EHS not in EHS reference list (detailed notification required), 343 EHS officially notified in detail by industry to DOE, 0 EHS reviewed and profiled in details

²⁴⁷ https://www.ajcsd.org/chrip_search/dt/pdf/hazard_Help/NITE-Japan%20Risk%20Assessment_2016%20.pdf

²⁴⁸ http://reach.ktr.or.kr/gnu/bbs/board.php?bo_table=law&wr_id=598; note that the file names indicated 37104 and 7383 substances as existing and new substances, respectively.

²⁴⁹ <https://ncis.nier.go.kr/en/mttrList.do>

²⁵⁰ <https://myehs.doe.gov.my/portal/myehs/>

			by DOE, 19 EHS register of overseas suppliers (as of 24 August 2017) – the list of chemicals cannot be downloaded
			(2) The EHS reference list contains 4582 chemicals – the list of chemicals cannot be downloaded
CIMS	1363 (as reported in 2015, 2016 and 2017)	1362 (the sum of the 2015, 2016 and 2017 reporting)	(1) The 2019 summary shows 3399 inventories were submitted (about 400 more than in 2017); however, there are likely duplications, as shown in the 2017 reporting
INSQ	9489 (as of the 2014 update version)	1039 with hazard classification information (data from DSL and REACH)	- Not included in the further analysis
NZIoC	28799, as of 9 December, 2020 28940 , as of 27 December 2021	CCID – 5430 (4879 with 4750 unique CASRNs (some CASRNs represent multiple dilutes), 551 w/out CASRNs)	(1) those added after 1 December 2006 = new substances with safety data – identifiable in the online database version, but not the excel spreadsheets ²⁵¹ (2) Chemical Classification and Information Database (CCID) holds detailed hazard information for 5430 single chemicals (as of 27 December 2021) ²⁵² (3) <i>Hazardous Substances (Dangerous Goods and Scheduled Toxic Substances) Transfer Notice</i> 2004, 2005 and 2006 ²⁵³ - mostly without CASRNs

²⁵¹ Personal communication: The reference to 100,000 previously notified substances encompasses both individual chemicals and formulated mixtures. This is the approximate number that were notified when the Hazardous Substances legislation came into force and existing substances were transferred into the new regime. About 27,000 of the 100,000 substances were individual chemicals that were set up as the original New Zealand Inventory of Chemicals (NZIoC). The remaining ~73,000 mixtures were either allocated individual approvals (mainly for pesticides, veterinary medicines, VTAs etc), or allocated to a Group Standard (eg cleaning products, cosmetics, surface coatings etc). Each year a further 100-200 chemicals are added to the NZIoC. Chemicals that are placed on the NZIoC are simply notified and there is no assessment as such. Approximately **1500** chemicals have been notified to the NZIoC since it was first set up.

²⁵² Available in a searchable online database format, but not downloadable: <https://www.epa.govt.nz/database-search/chemical-classification-and-information-database-ccid/DatabseSearchForm/?SiteDatabaseSearchFilters=35&Keyword=&DatabaseType=CCID>; from personal communication: Chemicals that have been fully assessed by the EPA have a specific approval number. Detailed hazard information for these chemicals can be found on the Chemical Classification and Information Database (CCID) – and they are listed on the NZIoC too. There are about 5500 such chemicals (I think you have a precise number in your document). These chemicals include active ingredients, commonly used components, or fuels.

²⁵³ Available in a pdf file, including tables of hazardous chemicals (chemical name, CASRN, UN number) and their hazard classification <https://www.epa.govt.nz/assets/Uploads/Documents/Hazardous-Substances/Policies/4c1a400f45/Hazardous-substances-Dangerous-goods-and-scheduled-toxic-substances-transfer-notice-no-35-2004.pdf>

			(4) FRCaST screening tool list includes 1246 chemicals (as of October 2020 version) ²⁵⁴ – not included in the further analysis
PICCS	22009 (as of the 2012 version) 22273 (as of the 2021 version)	460 new chemicals since the 2007 version	(1) The first PICCS was published by DENR-EMB in 1995 and subsequently PICCS updates were published in 2000, 2002, 2005, 2008, ²⁵⁵ 2011, 2013, 2015, 2017, 2020 and 2021. ²⁵⁶
RPOHV	11479 (contained in the online searchable database, as of 13.11.2020) 12074 (contained in the online searchable database, as of 01.05.2022)	As of 01.05.2022, In RPOHV, 11665 substances (after removing duplicates, 11200 with 11197 unique CASRNs and 465 without CASRNs)	- It is reported that about 18,400 (3,400 chemicals had been registered in Russia by the end of 2009; about 15,000 chemicals had been evaluated under Soviet regulations up to 1992) ²⁵⁷
NSNRS	1646 (as of June 2020) 2215 (as of 16.12.2021)	2215 (1382 for which the assigned CASRNs were identified – 1023 unique CASRNs and 833 without CASRNs)	(1) latest version of 16.12.2021 ²⁵⁸
TECI 1	7212 chemicals (2012)	-	- Not included in the further analysis

²⁵⁴ <https://www.epa.govt.nz/industry-areas/hazardous-substances/chemical-reassessment-programme/priority-chemicals-list>; personal communication: We have completed 51 reassessments to date, of which 25 are EPA-initiated reassessments, 18 are from individual chemical industry manufacturers, and 8 are from other organisations, including other government agencies, district councils and industry representative groups. It is important to note that reassessments vary in size and complexity, some including just a single formulated substance (quite common for the ones filed by chemical manufacturers), and others including multiple grouped substances (more common for the EPA-initiated reassessments, eg organophosphates, anti-fouling paints etc).

²⁵⁵ https://www.chemsafetypro.com/Topics/Philippine/PICCS_Philippine_Inventory_of_Chemicals_and_Chemical_Substances.html

²⁵⁶ 2017, 2020 and 2021 versions: https://chemical.emb.gov.ph/?page_id=138

²⁵⁷ https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/capchemru_chemmgmtru_final.pdf

²⁵⁸ <https://www.anmeldestelle.admin.ch/chem/en/home/themen/pflicht-hersteller/stoffe/neuer-stoff/neue-stoffe-kurz-erklaert.html>

	Up to 6600 chemicals (2016)		
TECI 2	11478 entries all with hazard classifications	11478 (11279 with CASRNs, 199 with wrong CASRNs due to Excel auto-conversion)	1 duplicate
TK-REACH (formerly TCSI)	2880 ²⁵⁹	618 (see Notes; 617 with CASRNs, 1 without CASRN)	(1) This number refers to chemicals in the previous List of High Production Volume Chemicals (which requires submission of physicochemical properties and hazard information) and List of Priority substances of groups of substances (Which requires risk assessments), after removing the duplicates (2) The previous List of chemicals produced between 1 and 1000 tonnes/year requires submission of volumes, classification and uses, but no requirement on physicochemical properties and hazard information
TSCA	As of June 2020 68091 (public), 18314 (confidential) As of August 2021 68191 (public), 18416 (confidential)	Ca. 28000 (see Notes) Ca. 20 existing substances assessed	(1) The initial existing chemical substances ²⁶⁰ (about 58000 chemicals, including ca. 1800 CBI) was based on information reported to EPA by manufacturers (including importers) and processors from 1975–1978, since the original enactment of TSCA, more than 24,000 chemicals have been added to TSCA as new chemical substances (2) Environment Canada chose the USA 1985 Toxic Substances Control Act Inventory as a basis for the Non-domestic Substances List (NDSL). The initial list appeared, along with the DSL, in the <i>Canada Gazette</i> Part I on January 26, 1991. Environment Canada updated the NDSL from the Toxic Substances Control Act Inventory additions of 1985 to 1990. This revision was published in the <i>Canada Gazette</i> Part I on January 6, 1996. The revision added 1,723 substances to the non-confidential portion as well as an additional 65 substances to the confidential portion, bringing the number of substances on the NDSL to over 42,000. ²⁶¹ In 1998, the non-confidential portion of the List was republished in a format consistent with the Domestic Substances List. The initial List of January 26, 1991 and all subsequent revisions appeared in the <i>Canada Gazette</i> Part I on January 31, 1998. There are now 43,797

²⁵⁹ The pre-registration of the new TK-REACH, i.e., KKDIK, ends on December 31, 2020. The number here refers to the former Turkish Chemical Substance Inventory (TCSI) that was published in December 2011.

²⁶⁰ <https://nepis.epa.gov/Exe/ZyPURL.cgi?Dockey=9101UJOA.TXT>

²⁶¹ https://www.ec.gc.ca/LCPE-CEPA/default.asp?lang=En&n=9AE4E9BB-1&offset=3&toc=show#A1_2

substances recognized as non-domestic. A revision to the confidential portion of the List was also published in the *Canada Gazette* Part I on March 28, 1998. This revision added a further 107 substances which received confidential identifiers in accordance with the Masked Name Regulations.²⁶²

→ TSCA new substances w/ CASRN ≈ TSCA 2021 – initial DSL – (NDSL published in 1998 – addition of NDSL in 1996) ≈ 8912 with CASRN (missing new substances added by 1985 (unknown amount) and those added in NDSL between 1996 and 1998 (ca. 1800))

→ TSCA new substances CBIs = 18416 – 1800 = ca. 16600

3) TSCA requires that EPA designate at least 20 chemical substances as a high priority for risk evaluation, and at least 20 chemical substances as low priority. On December 20, 2019, EPA finalized the designation of 20 chemical substances as a high priority for upcoming risk evaluations. On February 20, 2020, EPA finalized the designation of 20 chemical substances as a low priority.²⁶³

NCI	As of February 24, 2021, 48857	9618 substances have been approved, 9578 substances are now under examination, and the rest 29661 substances are lack of evidence ²⁶⁴
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No official assessment by the authority in Viet Nam has been conducted (reported as one of the challenges that they are facing²⁶⁵).

²⁶² https://www.ec.gc.ca/lcpe-cepa/default.asp?lang=En&n=9B7AFE30-1&offset=3#A1_1_2

²⁶³ <https://www.epa.gov/assessing-and-managing-chemicals-under-tsca/prioritizing-existing-chemicals-risk-evaluation>

²⁶⁴ <https://chemical.chemlinked.com/expert-article/vietnam-latest-report-on-the-supplementation-of-nci-and-draft-of-new-substance-act>

²⁶⁵ https://www.slideshare.net/OECD_ENV/global-forum-on-environment-dedicated-to-chemicals-management-le-viet-thang-deputy-head-of-conventions-and-international-cooperation-division-vietnam-chemicals-agency-ministry-of-industry-and-trade

S3. Supporting Details on the Countries that are in the Process of Establishing Its Own Regulatory Frameworks on Industrial Chemicals

S3.1 Argentina

Draft version of the National Law for the Risk Assessment of Chemical Substances published in June 2019, which was to be submitted to the Argentinian legislature, with no more current information available. <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/lf-2019-54718677-apn-dsypqsgp.pdf>

S3.2 Brazil

A bill was presented in the Chamber of Deputies in November 2019 that would require manufacturers, exporters, and importers of chemicals to report the amount of chemical substances annually produced and imported and the contents of material safety data sheets (MSDS) in accordance with GHS, including recommended uses, hazard classifications, and chemical risk assessment analysis studies for recommended uses.

<https://www.camara.leg.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao?idProposicao=2230281>

S3.3 Columbia

Columbia published a draft Decree for the establishment of a hazardous chemicals inventory for industrial operations. In addition to the identification of substances, the inventory would include data on the intended uses, volume, and hazard classification according to GHS revision 6 which will have to be reported by industries producing or importing hazardous chemical substances in Colombia above 100 kg/year. The Decree would enter into force following its publication in the Official Gazette.

http://www.andi.com.co/Uploads/2020_07_13_Proyecto%20Sustancias%20Qu%C3%ADmicas%20Consulta%20Nacional%202020.pdf

S3.4 Saudi Arabia

Saudi Arabia is drafting a national chemical safety programme, with no more current information available, to our best knowledge. <https://chemicalwatch.com/86858/saudi-arabia-expected-to-publish-national-chemical-safety-programme-in-2020>